

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable D1.8.

AWP Y3 including PARC Project Portfolio

WP1 – T1.1

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¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

¹ On date 05/03/2024, the Project Officer has requested that the deliverable D1.8 with title "AWPY3 including rolling SRIA " was renamed "AWP Y3 including PARC Project Portfolio", according to the ongoing amendment. D1.8 was resubmitted on 28 March 2024 with the new title, once the amendment was officially adopted on 26 March 2024.

Document history

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1	17/10/2023	WP co-leaders and Task co-leaders in close collaboration with the Project managers and partners involved in their WPs and Tasks	First draft with modifications in track changes
2	31/10/2023	WP co-leaders and PARC CT only	Review of the first draft
3	18/12/2023	WP co-leaders and Task co-leaders in close collaboration with the Project managers and partners involved in their WPs and Tasks	Second draft with modifications in track changes
4	05/01/2024	WP co-leaders and PARC CT only	Review of the second draft
5	16/02/2024	Project managers, tasks co-leaders and WP co-leaders	Update of the project description based on HaDEA's recommendations
6	29/02/2024	PARC CT	Review of the final draft and submission to HaDEA
7	27/03/2024	PARC CT	As requested by the Project Officer, the title of D1.8 was modified in "AWPY3 including PARC Project Portfolio" D1.8 was resubmitted once the amendment was officially approved in March 2024
8	10/07/2024	PARC CT, Project managers, tasks co-leaders and WP co-leaders	- Updated version of the AWPY3 submitted to answer HaDEA's comments - Table 2.2.a updated with the correct number of PMs per partner for each WP for Y3

			<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Table 2.2.b updated with the correct total number of PMs per WP- Table 2.3.a updated with the total effort per partner per WP for Y3- Table 2.3.b updated with the correct cost items for Y3 for some partners- Table 2.3.c updated with the correct overview of planned budget for project and per WP
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Abstract

This Annual Work Plan (AWP) describes the activities to be implemented during the 'PARC year', including the updated Project Portfolio. The AWP covers the period from May 2024 to April 2025 (M25-M36) which are referred to as 'PARC years'.

Key Words

Work Plan, Project Portfolio Period M25-M36

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List of abbreviations

AA: Anti-Androgenicity	MIEs: Molecular Initiating Events
ADME: Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion	MoA: Mode of Action
AE: Affiliated Entity	MS: Member States
AO/ AON/ AOP: Adverse Outcome/ AO Network/ Pathway	MTA: Material Transfer Agreement
API: Application Programming Interfaces	MRA: Mixture Risk Assessment
ASR/ AWP: Annual Summary Report/Work Plans	NAMs: New Approach Methodologies
BBB: Blood Brain Barrier	NGRA: Next Generation Risk Assessment
BCSFB: Blood-cerebrospinal Fluid Barrier	NGTxC: Non-Genotoxic Carcinogens
BMD: Benchmark dose	NHs: National Hubs
BPR: Biocides Products	NHCs: National Hub Coordinators
CA: Consortium Agreement	NHCPs: National Hub Contact Points
CEC: Chemicals of Emerging Concern	NTS: Non-Targeted Screening
CG: Core Group	OECD: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
CL/ ML: Chemical Leader/ Methodology Leader	OO: Operational Objectives
CLP: Classification, Labelling and Packaging	OSOA: One Substance One Assessment
CMS: Content Management System	PDB: Protein Data bank
COPCSD: Common Open Platform on Chemical Safety Data	PFAS: per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances
CPDC: Common Platform for Data on Chemicals	PFDP: PARC FAIR Data Policy
CPR: Cosmetic Products	PBK: Physiologically Based Kinetic
CSS: Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability	PBMC: Peripheral Blood Mononuclear Cells
CT: ANSES PARC Coordination Team	PBPK: Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic
DILI: Drug-Induced Liver Injury	PBTK: Physiologically Based Toxicokinetic
DEPB: Data and Ethics Protection Board	PM: Project Manager
DMP: Data Management Plan	PMT: Persistent Mobile and Toxic
DNT/ANT: Developmental and Acute Neurotoxicity	PoC: Prof of Concept
DoA: Description of Action	POD: Point of Departure
EATS: Estrogen, Androgen, Steroidogenesis, and Thyroid	POP: Persistent Organic Pollutant
EBD: Environmental Burden of Disease	PPPR: Plant Protection Products
EC: European Commission	PT: Proficiency Testing
ECHA: European Chemicals Agency	QA/QC: Quality Assurance / Quality Control
ED/ EDCs: Endocrine Disrupters / endocrine disrupting compounds	QAWG: Quality Assurance Working Group

EDA: Effect-Directed Analysis	QIVIVE: Quantitative in vitro / in vivo Extrapolation
EFSA: European Food Safety Authority	QSAR: Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship
EOSC: European Open Science Cloud	RA/RM: Risk Assessment / Risk Management
ERA: Environmental Risk Assessment	R&I: Research and Innovation
EWS: Early Warning System	RRM: Rapid Response Mechanism
FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable	SCCS: Scientific Committee on Consumer Safety
FIP: FAIR Implementation Profiles	SDGs: Sustainable Development Goals
FIT: FAIR Implementation Taskgroup	S2PD: Science-to-Policy Dialogue
GA: Grant Agreement	SAICM: Strategic Approach to International Chemicals Management
GB: Governing Board	SF: Stakeholder Forum
GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation	SG: Specialty Group
GFF: Go Fair Foundation	SO: Specific Objectives
GIVIMP: Good In Vitro Methods Practices	SPM: Suspended Particulate Matter
GS: Grant Signatory	SRIA: Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
GSB: Grant Signatory Board	SS: suspect screening
HA: Hazard Assessment	SSbD: Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design
HBM: Human BioMonitoring	SSO: Single-Sign-On
HBM GV: Health-based Guidance Values	SOP: Standard Operating Procedures
HRMS: High Resolution Mass Spectrometry	SVM: Support Vector Machine
IATA: Integrative Approaches for testing and Assessment	T/TL: Task/Task co-leaders
IB: International Board	TTC: Toxicological Threshold of Concern
IPR: Intellectual Property Rights	THSD: Thyroid Hormone System Disruptors
IVIVE: <i>in vitro</i> - <i>in vivo</i> extrapolation	TKTD: Toxicokinetic-toxicodynamic modelling
JRC: Joint Research Centre	UCWG: Use Case Working Group(s)
KIC: Knowledge and Innovation Communities	UNEP: United Nations Environment Programme
KEs: Key Events	US-EPA: US Environmental Protection Agency
KERs: Key Event Relationships	US-NTP: US National Toxicology Program
LCA: Life-cycle assessment	WHO: World Health Organization
MAF: Mixture Assessment Factor	WoE: Weight-of-Evidence
MB: Management Board	WP/ WPL: Work Package / WP co-leaders
MCRA: Monte Carlo Risk Assessment	WWTP: Wastewater treatment plants

Structure of the Annual Work Programme

1. Coherence with part B of the proposal

1.1 Annual Work Plan (AWP) objectives

The objectives of this third year are aligned with the specific objectives of PARC.

SO1 - To achieve a high scientific policy and societal impact, EU and national risk assessors and regulatory entities come together with the scientific community in a cross-disciplinary network to set priorities for research and innovation in chemical risk assessment

OO1-Maintaining a high management level through meeting of Boards. For the year 3 a consortium meeting will be organised on 13-16 May 2024, to review our progress, support discussion on new priorities established during the 2nd Semester of Y2 based on the mapping of needs.

OO2-National hubs will continue their activities to gather national needs, encourage cooperation and identify potential synergies.

OO3-Based on the work done during Y2 on the prioritisation process and review of needs, the review of new projects and monitoring on on-going ones will be performed.

OO4-Using PARCopedia, launched Y2, the chemical risk assessment community will find, co-create and discuss knowledge on all matters related to chemical risk assessment and Next Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA). The roadmap towards the uptake of NGRA into European chemicals legislation will be finalised with a broad range of relevant parties. Chemical and Method leaders will follow and report on the work developed within PARC.

OO5-Cooperation with other programmes and initiatives will be encouraged. The first SYNnet Forum will be organized back-to-back with a relevant scientific event.

OO6- Communication and dissemination of knowledge produced by PARC will be performed via the website, the open access to scientific publications.

SO2 - European and national risk assessment entities and their scientific networks carry out a joint research and innovation programme to respond to the agreed priorities in chemicals risk assessment.

OO7-Work programme. The programme will be monitored and six new projects started in Y3. Several on-going projects will continue to perform their testing and modelling activities to generate data.

OO8-Innovative concepts, models and tools. Some reports will be delivered end of Y3 on the work done on new approach methodologies, integrative approaches for testing and assessment (IATA) and physiologically based models (PBK) Reports on aggregate exposure for general

population and workers and source to dose modelling, real-life mixtures will be provided. Activities performed on the concept of health impact assessment will be reported.

A new version of the PARC Toolbox is planned end of Y3. A review of state-of-art models applicable for exposure, hazard and risk assessment will be performed. Integration of some of them in the PARC_Toolbox will be done in the new version. Establishment of the knowledge sharing platform on Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) will be done with the completion of the version 1 of the SSbD platform.

The design of an applicability and performance testing schemer of the Early Warning toolbox will be done.

To promote acceptability and uptake of the new approaches, several on-going case studies will report their results.

OO9-Monitoring capacity development. The human biomonitoring sampling phase will continue. The selection of the best, state-of-the-art exposure biomarkers and analytical methods will be performed according to the identified needs for implementation from Y4. The chemical analysis plan will be approved and implemented. A PARC-GEQUAS QA/QC programme will begin in the last quarter of Y3. A first list of qualified laboratories will be established.

For occupational studies (health sector, e-waste), candidate laboratories for the analysis of samples for the exposure and effect biomarkers will assess their internal performance and a proficiency test will be organised by PARC in case of lack of proficiency test providers for biomarkers selected. Analysis of some samples is expected to start.

For the environmental projects, the monitoring activities developed, the chemical analyses will be completed and reported according to the formats and procedures developed. The collection of existing per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) data for the “baseline part” will be completed.

OO10-To implement Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) data practices, the training and support of partners in the process of FAIRfication will continue. A durable list of data and project standard will be compiled in appropriate repositories. Guidance and background information to set-up training and supporting project will be provided. A 1st report on Data infrastructures, tools and services for FAIRification and reuse of data.

SO3 - European risk assessors, their scientific network and the wider stakeholder community have access to the research and innovation capacities required to implement innovative chemical risk assessment

OO11-Use of PARC results. PARCopedia and PARC Toolbox, trainings, webinars, scientific publications and sharing of guidances support the achievement of this objective as well as the international collaboration.

OO12-Networks of laboratories and research centres. During Y3, the dashboard will be implemented on the PARC webpage and will start running with the on-going collection of data. Catalogues of laboratory will be reported. The laboratories involved in the monitoring activities will be involved in proficiency tests organised PARC Quality Assurance / Quality Control (QAQC) scheme or external ones.

OO13-Capacity building. Three in-person training courses will be carried out, under the scientific coordination of PARC partners and aimed at both PARC partners and stakeholders. Information on external training (outside PARC) on relevant topics will be continuously updated on PARC website.

1.2 Expected impacts

Table 1.1: Links between projects/activities and objectives

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES (SO)	OPERATIONAL OBJECTIVES (OO)	PROJECTS/TRANSVERSAL ACTIVITIES CONTRIBUTING
SO1 - cross-disciplinary network to set priorities for R&I in chemical RA	OO1: Set-up and operate a high-level group to strategically steer PARC	WP1 - T1.1; T1.4; WP2 - T2.1; T2.2; WP3 – T3.1; T3.3; WP4 - P4.3.4.a;
	OO2: Expand long-term sustainable network of National Hubs (NH)	WP2 – T2.3; WP4 - P4.3.2.b; P4.3.4.a;
	OO3: Define common R&I strategies with transparent criteria and a prioritisation strategy	WP2 – T2.1; T2.2; WP4 – P4.1.c*; P4.2.a; P4.2.b; P4.3.1.a; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.2.a; P4.3.2.b; P4.3.3.b; P4.3.4.a; WP5 - P5.1.1.a; P5.1.1.b; P5.1.2.a; P5.1.2.b; P5.2.1.a; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e; P5.3.1.a; P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a; WP6 - P6.1.1.b; P6.1.1.c; P6.1.1.d; P6.2.4.b; P6.2.4.c; P6.2.4.d; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.4.a; WP7 – T7.1; WP8 – T8.1;

	<p>OO4: Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge</p>	<p>WP2 – T2.2; T2.3;</p> <p>WP3 – T3.1; T3.2; T3.3;</p> <p>WP4 – P4.1.c*; P4.1.1.4.d; P4.1.3.1.a; P4.1.4.2.a; P4.2.a P4.2.b P4.3.4.a;</p> <p>WP5 - P5.1.1.a; P5.1.1.b; P5.1.1.c*; P5.1.2.a; P5.1.2.b; P5.2.1.a; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e; P5.3.1.a; P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a;</p> <p>WP6 - P6.1.1.a; P6.1.1.b; P6.1.1.c; P6.1.1.d; P6.2.1.b; P6.2.3.a; P6.2.4.b; P6.2.4.c; P6.2.4.d; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.1.a; P6.4.1.b; P6.4.2.a; P6.4.2.b; P6.4.3.a; P6.4.3.b*; P6.4.4.a; P6.4.4.d; P6.4.4.e;</p> <p>WP7 – T7.2;</p> <p>WP8 – T8.3;</p>
	<p>OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives</p>	<p>WP2 – T2.2;</p> <p>WP3 – T3.3;</p> <p>WP4 – P4.1.c*; P4.1.3.1.a; P4.1.4.2.a; P4.2.a; P4.2.b P4.2.c*, P4.3.1.b; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.1.d; P4.3.2.a; P4.3.2.b; P4.3.3.a; P4.3.3.b;</p> <p>WP5 - P5.1.1.a; P5.1.1.b; P5.1.2.a; P5.1.2.b; P5.2.1.a; P5.2.1.b; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e; P5.3.1.a; P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a;</p> <p>WP6 - P6.1.1.a; P6.1.1.b; P6.1.1.c; P6.1.1.d; P6.2.1.a; P6.2.2.a; P6.2.4.a; P6.2.4.b; P6.2.4.d; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.1.a; P6.4.1.b; P6.4.2.a; P6.4.2.b;</p>

		<p>P6.4.3.a; P6.4.3.b*; P6.4.4.a; P6.4.4.d; P6.4.4.e;</p> <p>WP8 – T8.1;</p> <p>WP9 – T9.1; T9.2; T9.3; T9.4;</p>
	<p>OO6: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen's understanding/awareness of chemical RA</p>	<p>WP2 – T2.2; T2.3;</p> <p>WP3 – T3.2;</p> <p>WP4 – P4.1.c*; P4.1.1.4.c; P4.1.3.1.a; P4.1.4.2.a; P4.2.a; P4.3.1.a; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.2.a; P4.3.2.b; P4.3.4.a;</p> <p>WP5 - P5.1.1.a; P5.1.1.b; P5.1.2.a; P5.1.2.b; P5.2.1.a; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e; P5.3.1.a; P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a;</p> <p>WP6 - P6.2.1.b; P6.2.3.a; P6.2.4.c; P6.2.4.d; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.3.a; P6.4.3.b*;</p> <p>WP7 – T7.1; T7.2; T7.3</p>
<p>SO2 - carry out a joint R&I programme to respond to the agreed priorities in chemical RA</p>	<p>OO7: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA</p>	<p>WP1 – T1.1;</p> <p>WP2 – T2.1;</p> <p>WP4 - P4.1.1.2.a; P4.1.1.4.c; P4.1.1.4.d; P4.1.3.1.a; P4.1.3.3.a; P4.2.a; P4.2.b; P4.2.c*; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.1.d; P4.3.2.a; P4.3.2.b; P4.3.3.b;</p> <p>WP5 - P5.1.1.a; P5.1.1.b; P5.1.1.c; P5.1.2.a; P5.1.2.b; P5.2.1.a; P5.2.1.b; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e; P5.3.1.a; P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a</p>

		<p>WP6 - P6.1.1.a; P6.1.1.b; P6.1.1.c; P6.1.1.d; P6.2.1.a; P6.2.2.a; P6.2.4.a; P6.2.4.b; P6.2.4.c; P6.2.4.d; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.2.c; P6.4.3.a; P6.4.3.b; P6.4.4.c; P6.4.4.c; P6.4.4.e;</p> <p>WP8 – T8.2;</p>
	<p>OO8: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes</p>	<p>WP4 - P4.1.1.2.a; P4.1.1.4.c; P4.1.1.4.d; P4.1.3.1.a; P4.1.3.3.a; P4.1.4.2.a; P4.1.5.a; P4.2.a; P4.2.c*; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.1.d; P4.3.2.a; P4.3.2c*; P4.3.2.b; P4.3.3.a; P4.3.3.b; P4.3.4.a;</p> <p>WP6 - P6.2.1.a; P6.4.4.a; P6.4.4.c; P6.4.4.c;</p> <p>WP9 – T9.1; T9.2; T9.3;</p>
	<p>OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA</p>	<p>WP4 – P4.1.c*; P4.1.1.2.a; P4.1.3.1.a; P4.1.3.3.a; P4.1.4.2.a; P4.2.a; P4.2.b; P4.2.c*; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.1.d; P4.3.3.a; P4.3.4.a;</p> <p>WP5 - P5.1.1.a; P5.1.1.b; P5.1.2.a; P5.1.2.b; P5.2.1.a; P5.2.1.b; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e; P5.3.1.a; P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a;</p> <p>WP6 - P6.1.1.a; P6.1.1.b; P6.1.1.c; P6.1.1.d; P6.2.1.a; P6.2.2.a; P6.2.4.a; P6.2.4.b; P6.2.4.c; P6.2.4.d; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.1.a; P6.4.1.b; P6.4.3.a; P6.4.3.b*; P6.4.4.a; P6.4.4.c; P6.4.4.c; P6.4.4.d;</p> <p>WP7 - P7.2.2.a; P7.2.2.b; P7.3.3</p>

	<p>OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake</p>	<p>WP4 – P4.1.c*; P4.1.1.4.c; P4.1.3.1.a; P4.1.3.3.a; P4.2.b; P4.2.c*; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.1.d; P4.3.2.a; P4.3.3.a; P4.3.3.b;</p> <p>WP5 P5.1.1.c*; P5.1.2.b; P5.2.1.a; P5.2.1.b; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e; P5.3.1.a; P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a;</p> <p>WP6 - P6.1.1.a; P6.1.1.b; P6.1.1.c; P6.1.1.d; P6.2.1.a; P6.2.1.b; P6.2.2.a; P6.2.3.a; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.1.a; P6.4.1.b; P6.4.2.b; P6.4.3.a; P6.4.3.b*; P6.4.4.a; P6.4.4.c; P6.4.4.c; P6.4.4.d; P6.4.4.e;</p> <p>WP7 – T7.3</p> <p>WP8 – T8.1; T8.3;</p>
<p>SO3 - access to R&I capacities required to implement innovative chemical RA</p>	<p>OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC's results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA.</p>	<p>WP4 – P4.1.c*; P4.1.1.4.d; P4.1.3.1.a; P4.1.3.3.a; P4.2.b; P4.3.1.b; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.2.c*; P4.3.3.a;</p> <p>WP5 – P5.1.1.c*; P5.1.2.a; P5.1.2.b; P5.2.1.a; P5.2.1.b; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e, P5.3.1.a; P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a</p> <p>WP6 - P6.1.1.a; P6.1.1.b; P6.1.1.c; P6.1.1.d; P6.2.1.b; P6.2.2.a; P6.2.3.a; P6.2.4.b; P6.2.4.d; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.1.a; P6.4.2.a; P6.4.2.b; P6.4.2.c; P6.4.3.a; P6.4.3.b*; P6.4.4.c; P6.4.4.d; P6.4.4.e;</p>
	<p>OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres</p>	<p>WP4 – P4.1.c*; P4.1.1.4.d; P4.1.4.2.a; P4.2.a; P4.2.c*; P4.3.1.b; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.1.d; P4.3.2.a; P4.3.2.c*; P4.3.2.b; P4.3.3.a; P4.3.4.a;</p> <p>WP5 - P5.1.1.a; P5.1.1.b; P5.1.2.a; P5.1.2.b; P5.2.1.a; P5.2.1.b; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e; P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a;</p> <p>WP6 - P6.1.1.a; P6.1.1.b; P6.1.1.c; P6.1.1.d</p> <p>WP9 – T9.1; T9.2; T9.3;</p>

	OO13: Build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical RA	<p>WP4 - P4.1.1.4.d; P4.1.4.2.a; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.2.b; P4.3.4.a;</p> <p>WP5 - P5.2.1.b;</p> <p>WP6 - P6.2.1.a; P6.2.1.b; P6.2.3.a; P6.2.4.b; P6.2.4.d; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.2.b; P6.4.4.d;</p> <p>WP7 - P7.2.2.b;</p> <p>WP9 – T9.1; T9.4;</p>
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* = Projects starting Y3.

1.3 Correspondence with part B of the proposal

For this third AWP, the actions initiated in the form of projects, case studies and those activities corresponding to recurrent tasks are presented by WP and tasks using the structure described in Part B. AWPY3 has been designed to be intrinsically linked and complementary to the seven-year activity plan (Description of Action or DoA). It will provide the necessary basis on which to continue building the Partnership in the following years. This is true for the specific challenges, the scope of PARC as well as for the activities that will be initiated during the third year of PARC.

1.4 Update of the PARC Project Portfolio

The PARC Project Portfolio constitutes an overview of the PARC Projects, providing detailed information on timelines, outputs, etc. The PARC Project Portfolio is administered by the Coordinator and updated each year to integrate new Projects and follow those that have been implemented. It serves as a basis for the preparation of the AWP. The Project Portfolio annexed to this 3rd AWP is a compilation of all projects' summaries concerned that are already implemented and those additional ones that have been proposed and reviewed under task 2.1 and validated to start during the 3rd year of PARC.

Table 1.2: New projects Year 3

Project ID	Schedule
P4.2.c_Y3_Human exposure_INERIS_AU	M25-M72
P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03-Complementarydevelopments_JSI	M25-M72
P5.1.1.c_Y3_TG+ EnnB1_ANSES	M25-M60
P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_CS20_Y3_PESTNAM_ISS	M25-M48
P6.4.1.c_Y3_Skinsenmix_RegionH	M25-M72
P6.4.3.b_Y3_ENFORCE_KemI	M25-M72

Table 1.3: Projects and case studies planned to end Year 3

In bold, projects initially planned to end M36 that have been extended

Project ID	Schedule	Comments	Rationale for projects that have been extended
P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasability_TTL	M1-M29*	*The project has been extended from M18 to M29	The coding of occupations (according to ISCO codes) and transfer of coded information to PEH platform (allowing the transfer of data for statistical analysis) is taking more time than anticipated and is planned to occur only now in November-December 2023. Therefore, an extension of the deadline was applied. Impact on AD4.8 (postponed from M18 to M29)
P4.1.1.4.b_Y1_SentinelSystem_KULeuven	M1-M36*	*This project up to M81 has been broken down at M36 to assess what has been achieved.	
P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_DerivationofHBM-GVs_UBA	M1-M36*	*This project up to M81 has been broken down at M36 to assess what has been achieved.	
P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO	M1-M36	Discussions on the need for an extension are ongoing	
P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU	M1-M36		
P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02-QAQC_WR	M1-M60*	*The project has been extended from M36 to M60	The project has experienced a significant delay regarding the start of actual activities. Moreover, During the T4.3 meeting in Paris 9.10.2023, additional topics were identified to be included in P4.3.1.b_T02 (development of common mixture(s) of QAQC markers for harmonized method performance assessment, and development of strategies for improving the semi-quantitative performances obtained with screening approaches). Therefore, an extension was applied to allow to finetune generic guidance documents to be drafted in P4.3.1.b_T02 based on experiences and lessons learned from a pilot project that is starting in T4.2
P4.3.3.a_Y1_E01-Wastewater based epidemiology_UFZ-UBATH	M1-M48*	*The project has been extended from M36 to M48	The results of this project will serve as a proof-of-concept, illustrating the effectiveness of innovative sampling tools and the integration of suspect and non-target screening. The ambition of this study requires new, cutting-edge tools as well as coordinated actions focused on sampling / analysis / data mining. To enable these, and to maintain an inclusive nature of the project (an extended number of laboratories to take part) and to maintain

			quality of outputs, the project needs strong coordination, planning as well as a robust interlaboratory study. Also, an in-depth evaluation of the obtained large data sets using state-of-the-art statistical methods and a thorough interpretation should be achieved within the project time. Therefore, one year extension will provide opportunity to deliver this ambitious project with maximum output and impact with an extra assurance of the highest possible quality. Impact on D4.2 (postponed from M36 to M48)
P5.1.1.a_Y1_Toxins_BfR_UNIVIE	M1-M48*	*The project has been extended from M36 to M48	There was some delay on substance procurement (natural toxins) and on hiring personal. Therefore, an extension of one year was applied. Impact on D5.11 (shifted from M60 to M54)
P5.1.1.b_Y1_BPA_HumTox_BfR	M1-M54*	*The project has been extended from M36 to M54	There was some delay on substance centralize order (BPA alternative) and on hiring personal. Therefore, an extension of one year was applied. Impact on D5.11 (shifted from M60 to M54)
P5.1.2.a_Y1_NaturalToxinsAqua_UGent	M1-M36		
P5.2.1.b_Y1_MD-EDC_INRAE	M1-M48*	*The project has been extended from M36 to M48	There was some delay on substance centralize order and on hiring personal. Therefore, an extension of one year was applied. Impact on D5.5 (shifted from M36 to M48)
P5.2.1.d_Y1_Immunotox_Inserm	M1-M48*	*The project has been extended from M36 to M48	COVID-19 vaccination study was planned but did not get the money until 2023. In Y2 they got budget for this study. Moreover, there was some delay due to recruitment difficulties. Therefore, an extension of one year was applied. Impact on D5.5 (shifted from M36 to M48)
P5.2.1.e_Y1_DNT-ANT_UFZ_IUF_UU	M1-M48*	*The project has been extended from M36 to M48	There was some delay on Neg/Pos controls centralized and on hiring personal. Therefore, an extension of one year was applied. Impact on D5.5 (shifted from M36 to M48)
P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR	M1-M48*	*The project has been extended from M36 to M48	The start of case studies was delayed and there were some recruitment difficulties. Therefore, an extension of one year was applied. Impact on D5.7 (new title to englobe P5.3.1.a and P5.3.2.a).
P5.3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_Inserm	M1-M48*	*The project has been extended from M36 to M48	There was some delay due to the organization of the workshop that has been postponed until June 23 for practical reasons. Moreover, most of the T5.2 projects will be delayed, and as P5.3.2.a relies on them for data, an extension of one year was applied. Impact on D5.7 (new title to englobe P5.3.1.a and P5.3.2.a).
P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Kinetics_Fraunhofer	M1-M48*	*The project has been extended from M36 to M48	There was some delay due to the organization of the workshop that has been postponed until June 23 for practical reasons. Moreover, most of the T5.1 and T5.2 projects will be delayed, and as P5.3.4.a relies on them for data, an extension of one year was applied. Impact on D5.2 (postponed from M24 to M36)

P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM	M1-M36	Discussions on the need for an extension are ongoing	
P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA-ED_UAntwerpen	M1-M36	Discussions on the need for an extension are ongoing	
P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano	M1-M36	Discussions on the need for an extension are ongoing	
P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR	M1-M36	Discussions on the need for an extension are ongoing	
P6.2.1.a_Y1_SourcetoDose_VITO	M1-M36	Discussions on the need for an extension are ongoing	
P6.4.1.a_Y1_OPREMIXCS1_BRUNEL_UGot	M1-M40*	*The project has been extended from M36 to M40	The projects started with an extensive delay, since it took longer as expected to get organised. The administrative effort and requirements of the projects were underestimated. Therefore, the extension would provide more time to scientifically conclude on the outcome of the case studies and provide a more overarching picture of the projects. Impact on AD6.17 and AD6.18 (postponed from M36 to M40)
P6.4.1.b_Y1_MONAMMIXCS2_UFZ	M1-M40*	*The project has been extended from M36 to M40	
P6.4.2.a_Y1_LandscapingSurv_UNIBAS	M1-M36		
P6.4.2.b_Y1_NGRApractice_VKM_NIPH	M1-M36*	*This project up to M81 has been broken down at M36 to assess what has been achieved.	
P6.4.2.c_Y1_NAMAM_UT	M1-M36		
P6.4.3.a_Y1_SuProM_MU	M1-M36		
P6.4.4.b_Y1_PPPEXPCS2_SLU	M1-M36*	*This project up to M81 has been broken up into 2 phases. The first phase was planned to end M24 but will be extended until M36	There was a delay due to a change of project manager. First results will be available in 2024 and presented to regulatory stakeholders with the intention to continue the research addressing relevant questions from stakeholders. Therefore, an extension of one year was applied for the first phase.
P6.4.4.c_Y1_PPPEFFCS3_UFZ	M1-M36*	*This project up to M81 has been broken down at M36 to assess what has been achieved.	
P7.2.2.a_Y1_chemicals-in-environment_MU_VITO	M1-M36		

In bold, case studies initially planned to end M36 that have been extended

Project ID	Case Study ID	Case Study Schedule	Comments	Rationale for case studies that have been extended
P6.3.1.a_Y1_SubstanceRA_SU (M1-M48)	CS12_MethodOSOA_SU	M1-M42*	*The case study has been extended from M36 to M42	Extended due to a delay related to to recruitment process of the PhD-student
	CS13_Plasticizers RA_UCL	M1-M36*	*The case study has been extended from M24 to M36	Extended due to a delay related to obtaining data
P6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI (M1-M48)	CS10_ED-cosmetics_VUB	M8-M32		
	CS15_DNT_SU	M1-M36		
	CS17_ED-in vitro_BPI	M1-M48*	*The case study has been extended from M36 to M48	Extended due to a delay related to handling overwhelming amounts of literature data
	CS18_ED-classes_BPI	M1-M48*	*The case study has been extended from M36 to year 4 (end M48)	Extended due to a delay related to handling overwhelming amounts of literature data
P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU (M1-M48)	CS1_CARB_SYKE	M1-M36		
	CS2_RiskReduction_SU	M1-M36*	*The case study has been extended from M24 to M36	Extended due to a delay related to handling overwhelming amounts of literature and obtaining data
	CS3_WorkplaceRA_TTL	M1-M36		
	CS7_REGPREP_EAWAG	M1-M36*	*First phase M1-M36	
	CS8_OccupReproDev_KI	M1-M36		
	CS16_UncertaintyRA_ULUND	M1-M36		
	CS19_DataGapFilling_KEMI-DTU	M13-M30*	*The case study has been extended from M24 to M30	Extended due to a delay related to recruiting students

2. Annual Work Programme Activities

2.1 Annual Work Programme

2.1.1 Structure of the Annual Work Programme

The structure of the AWPY is based on the work packages (WP) description of transversal activities as well as more specific activities that are related to projects.

2.1.2 Timing of the different programmed activities and their components

The third AWP will cover a duration of 12 months (M25-M36) from 1 May 2024 to 30 April 2025. All WPs will be active in Y3.

2.2 Detailed work description

For all the WPs, the full description of work by projects is available in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex II.

The WP co-leaders have coordinated the writing for their WP with the Task co-leaders.

Table 2.2.a: Annual Work Programme Activities for each set of activities

WP N°	WP1	Lead Beneficiary	ANSES
WP title	Coordination and Management		
Partner N°	1	1.1	1.2
Partner short name	ANSES	INSERM	INRAE
PM/partner2	124.5	0.8	0.8
Start	M25	End	M36
	1.13	1.4	1.5
	EHESP	SpF	EAA
	2	3	3.1
	3	3.1	4
	4	4.2	5
	5	5.52	6
	6	AGES	7
	7	VITO	8
	8	3.3	9
	9	DOMG	10
	10	SCIENSANO	11
	11	CIPH	12
	12	1.1	13
	13	MOH-CY/SGL	14
	14	MU	15
	15	4.9	16
	16	DEPA	17
	17	AU	18
	18	HB	19
	19	3	20
	20	EEA	21
	21	0.1	22
	22	THL	23
	23	1.2	24
	24	TTL	25
	25	5.4	26
	26	UBA	27
	27	7.7	28
	28	BfR	29
	29	2.6	30
	30	NCPHP	31
	31	1.5	32
	32	UI	33
	33	1.7	34
	34	ISS	35
	35	20	36
	36	20.4	37
	37	IUSS	38
	38	20.6	39
	39	UNINA	40
	40	21	41
	41	RSU	42
	42	22	43
	43	NPHSL	44
	44	24	45
	45	LNS	46
	46	2.5	47
	47	5.2	48
	48	RIVM	49
	49	1.2	50
	50	NIPH	51
	51	26.4	52
	52	NIVA	53
	53	0.2	54
	54	NVI	55
	55	26.6	56
	56	27	57
	57	NIOM	58
	58	2.2	59
	59	6	60
	60	INSA	61
	61	1	62
	62	APA	63
	63	29.1	64
	64	3.1	65
	65	SZU-SK	66
	66	30	67
	67	0.5	68
	68	JSI	69
	69	31	70
	70	32	71
	71	NIJZ	72
	72	33	73
	73	CSIC	74
	74	34	75
	75	ISCI	76
	76	34.5	77
	77	IISPV	78
	78	35	79
	79	SEPA	80
	80	1.2	81
	81	3.4	82
	82	KEMI	83
	83	35.7	84
	84	35.8	85
	85	IVL	86
	86	0.2	87
	87	1	88
	88	SLV	89
	89	36	90
	90	AUTH	91
	91	5.6	92
	92	3	93
	93	GCSL	94
	94	36.2	95
	95	2	96
	96	UKHSA	97
	97	50	98
	98	3	99
	99	UOB	100
	100	1.2	
		EPA	

2 PMs have been allocated to the Grant Signatories for the management of their affiliated entities and their role of NHCP. In some cases, the Grant Signatories do not have any PM as they do not manage any AEs and are not NHCP in PARC.

Objectives

The main goal of WP1 is to ensure the coordination, the strategic scientific and administrative management of PARC, including impact evaluation and the ethical issues management, in cooperation with the different governance bodies of the Partnership. The specific objectives of WP1 for year 3 are:

- Task 1.1: Maintain an effective management and governance framework for the PARC consortium in compliance with the legal, ethical, financial and administrative rules and regulations and in compliance with the agreed timelines ensuring the highest quality standards;
- Task 1.2: Manage the tools to ensure the Partnership's progress and guide the PARC consortium and its activities in maintaining the course set out in the Grant Agreement, to achieve milestones and produce the agreed deliverables, within the defined budget and abiding by the highest quality standards;
- Task 1.3: Maintain and update the monitoring framework for the Partnership;
- Task 1.4: Ensure communication and collaboration between the Data and Ethics Protection Board (DEPB), notably composed of Ethics and Data contacts points from WP4, 5 and 7 and the PARC Consortium, and ensure that the PARC Participants follow the Ethics Charter in order to reduce and/or address ethical issues that may arise during the Partnership implementation.

Description of work

Task 1.1: Overall executive management and support of the Partnership

Leader: ANSES (FR)

Partners: All GSB members and WP co-leaders (as stated above)

The activities of this task will be managed by the PARC Coordination Team (CT) composed of the PARC Coordinator, the Deputy-Coordinator and the ANSES Project managers. The PARC CT will ensure an efficient management of the PARC activities and associated administrative and budgetary issues.

Management of the consortium and organisation of the Governance Bodies meetings:

- Ensuring the respect and proper implementation of the "Terms of reference and rules of procedure" by the PARC Governing Board (GB) and of the Consortium Agreement (CA) by the PARC Grant Signatory Board (GSB) in compliance with the agreed timelines.
- Setting the dates and organising the Partnership Consortium and Governance Bodies meetings (Management Board (MB), GB and GSB) to take place during the 3rd year of PARC:

Consortium meetings:

- A consortium meeting will be organised during the 3rd year of PARC on 13-16 May 2024 at the University for Health Sciences, Medical Informatics and Technology (UMIT) in Austria, according to the PARC Governance process timeline (D1.2). This meeting will offer the opportunity to share among the PARC participants what has been achieved, what are the difficulties encountered and how to solve them, what still needs to be done to progress towards achievement of the PARC objectives and what are the new topics PARC should address.

For the GSB:

- A virtual meeting of the GSB will be organised beginning of summer 2024 in order to prepare the AWP of the year 4 and update the portfolio of projects and the PARC SRIA.
- A virtual meeting of the GSB will be organised in December 2024 to discuss progress and approve the AWP for the year 4 and associated budget and annual summary report of the Y3 before submission to HaDEA.
- Additional virtual GSB meeting(s) and/or written consultation(s) (through forms, poll, and emails) may be organised, if needed.

For the GB:

- A physical meeting of the GB will be organised back-to-back to the Consortium meeting in May 2024 to validate the strategy and get inputs from the GB for the preparation of the AWPY4.
- A virtual meeting of the GB will be organised in November 2024. The objective will be to provide input and opinions on the PARC progression (AWPY4, SRIA) before submission to the HaDEA in December and discuss progress, indicators, sustainability, as well as the strategy for the AWPY5 that will be worked on by the MB and GSB over the spring/summer.
- Additional virtual GB meeting(s) and/or written consultation(s) (through forms, poll, and emails) may be organised on other specific topics if needed.
- Ahead of each GB meeting, the coordination team will prepare working documents with the GB co-chairs for each topic planned to be addressed during the meeting. These documents are tailored to fit with the GB level of understanding needed.

For the MB:

- Monthly MB meetings will be organised throughout the year, with two physical meetings, including one meeting in May 2024 back-to back to the Consortium meeting at the University for Health Sciences, Medical Informatics and Technology (UMIT) in Austria. The other MB meetings will take place online.

Follow-up of the Partnership's activities and budget:

- Managing the information system (EMDESK) for the monitoring of the budget and help the financial administrators of the PARC institutions to ensure a proper and efficient use of the system.
- Granting access rights to the PARC Consortium SharePoint to new individuals involved in PARC when requested in order to ensure that all individuals involved in PARC have access to internal working documents and calendar of meetings and actions to be done for the year 3 of PARC.
- Assisting participants on specific administrative and financial issues.
- Updating on request the Partnership handbook describing the internal requirements and specifying the common rules to be followed by all PARC Participants.

Contractual documents generated by PARC activities:

- Pursuing the preparation of contractual documents generated by PARC activities, when relevant: Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), Material Transfer Agreement and Data

Transfer Agreement; preparing, signing, and managing, when relevant, other PARC related agreements (e.g., confidentiality and collaboration agreements) that will arise during the 3rd year.

- Establishing PARC collaboration agreements with external initiatives or organisations to support synergies
- Ensuring the follow-up of the collaboration agreements signed with external initiatives or organisations, especially with JRC, through dedicated meetings.

Communication:

- Updating the internal and external communication rules of the Partnership handbook, in collaboration with WP3, when relevant.
- Providing articles and news items to feed the PARC website in close collaboration with the WP3.
- Providing rules and repositories to the PARC Participants for internal and external communication.

Task 1.2: Scientific steering and implementation of Annual Work Plans

Leader: ANSES (FR)

Partners: All WP co-leaders, NHCPs, NHCs,

The activities of this task will be managed by the PARC CT in close collaboration with the MB, GB, GSB, National Hub Coordinators (NHCs) and the Chemical Leaders and Methodology Leaders (CL/MLs). The MB will specifically play an active role to ensure the efficient setting up of the monitoring of the scientific progress and of the overall strategy of the Partnership, making sure that the PARC activities, resources and AWP are aligned. It will also ensure the relevance of the PARC work plan with regard to external events with WP3 (projects, initiatives, EU policies linked to the PARC objectives).

Scientific steering :

- Moderating the MB meetings and ensuring the cross-cutting scientific links between WPs
- Assisting the PARC NHCs in coordinating the National Hub (NH) contributions and activities in PARC
- Proposing amendments of the GA or solutions / redress actions to resolve any issues, and escalating unresolvable risks or issues to the relevant boards.
- Aligning work programmes to policy needs as defined by EU Agencies and partner countries.

Synergies:

- Ensuring the follow-up of opportunities for synergies (with WP3) (projects, initiatives, EU policies linked to the PARC objectives, National, EU and international initiatives ...)

Preparation and submission of AWPY4 with the Project Portfolio in Annex and ASRY3:

- Coordinating the preparation, collection and submission to HaDEA of:

- The 4th AWP and updated PARC Project Portfolio in Annex, in December 2024. This will be done in close collaboration with the MB members, the Task co-leaders, the PARC Participants, the Task 2.1 partners, and in consultation with the relevant PARC governance bodies (see task 1.1 for the organisation of the Governance Bodies meetings).
- The ASRY3 in December 2024.

Preparation and submission of an updated PARC SRIA :

- Coordinating the preparation and submission to HaDEA of an updated PARC SRIA validated by the GB at M33

Follow-up of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones:

- Ensuring respect of the different deadlines, and achievement of milestones, deliverables and additional deliverables according to the established review process.

Task 1.3: Impact evaluation and Monitoring of the performance indicators of the Partnership

Co-Leaders: DOMG (BE), INSA (PT)

Partners: All WP co-leaders

The monitoring frame and set of indicators will be further refined to ensure the key useful and impact-generating results and relevant target groups are clearly identified in order to maximise PARC's impact and exploitation. The output indicators were presented at the GB of November 2023.

Activities to be performed in the 3rd year include:

- Presenting the first numbers on output indicators in the first PARC periodic report and feed these into the Biennial Monitoring Report.
- Identifying potential barriers that could undermine the achievement of desired outcomes and impacts, and monitoring and discussing mitigation strategies.
- Pursuing interaction with WP2 – task 2.3 on sustainability – for the development of surveys for sustainability indicators.
- Developing further the outcome and impact indicators in collaboration with MB, GSB and GB, NHs and stakeholders.
- In close collaboration with WP3, task 3.2, preparing easily interpretable indicator leaflets and communication elements on outcome and impact indicators that provide and communicate the link between the objectives, key results and (expected) impacts of PARC.
- Presenting results of performance of output indicators to the MB/GB and disseminating these among WPs for awareness.
- Continuing the discussions with the European Environment Agency to ensure input from PARC in, and synergies with, the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability (CSS) indicator framework being developed by the EC.

Task 1.4: Ethics framework

Co-Leaders: NIJZ (SI), EHESP (FR)

Partners: All WP co-leaders

This task aims at maintaining an ethical perspective throughout all the Partnership’s activities and set up collaborative and constructive processes to ensure ethical considerations are properly taken into account.

Activities to be performed in the 3rd year include to:

- Organising consultations and dialogue between the DEPB and the MB through the WPs’ Ethics contacts points who have been nominated in order to develop and facilitate the uptake of proper ethics and data protection processes.
- Ensuring that the PARC Participants are aware of and acknowledge the Data and Ethics Protection Policy developed by the PARC CT and the Task 1.4 co-leaders in collaboration with the DEPB during year 1, in order to reduce and/or address ethical issues that may arise during the Partnership implementation. A training workshop on ethics intended for PARC participants may be organised in the second half of Y3.
- Organising at least two DEPB meetings (likely one physical and one online) with the option to schedule extraordinary online meetings if it proves necessary. DEPB members may also be invited to speak during other Governance Bodies meetings (MB, GSB, GB) on ethics and/or data relevant topics.

Deliverables:

D1.10 AWPY4 including PARC Project Portfolio – Leader: ANSES (M32)

D1.9 ASRY3 – Leader: ANSES (M32)

D1.21 PARC SRIA Y3 (M33)

D10.5 OEI - Requirement No. 7 – Leader: ANSES (M32)

Additional Deliverables:

NA

WP N°	WP2										Lead Beneficiary										EAA/EEA																			
WP title	A common science-policy agenda																																							
Partner N°	1	1.1	2	3	3.6	4.2	4.3	5.2	6	7	8	10	11	12	14	15	16	17	18	20	21	22	25	26	26.2	26.4	27	29	29.2	29.3	30	31	32	34	36	36.2	48	49	52	59
Partner short name	ANSES	INSERM	SpF	EAA	UG-AT	DOMG	OVAM	EV-ILVO	CIPH	MOH-	MU	DEPA	HB	EEA	TTL	UBA	BfR	NCPHP	UI	ISS	RSU	NPHSL	RIVM	NIPH	STAMI	NIVA	NIOM	INSA	DGS	ENSP	SZU-SK	JSI	NIJZ	ISCIII	AUTH	GCSL	ECHA	EFSA	Cefas-Defra	UOB
PM/partner	12	4.5	3	3.5	1	1.2	0.1	1	0.5	0.5	3	0.5	0.5	15	0.5	3.7	18.3	5.5	0.7	2	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.1	2.2	14	1	4	0.5	0.7	2	0.5	29	5	24	5	1	9	

Start	M25	End	M36
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Objectives

The main goal of WP2 is to establish a dialogue and priority-setting process bringing together regulatory entities and Risk Assessment (RA) agencies in Europe (European and national entities and agencies) to develop a strategic R&I agenda for chemicals RA in collaboration with the scientific and regulatory community, to promote the uptake of innovative NGRA methodology into policy and regulatory practice and to ensure the sustainability of the partnership.

The specific objectives of WP2 for year 3 are:

- Task 2.1:
 - o Implementing and refining a well-structured and transparent prioritisation strategy through a fluid dialogue between WP2 and other WPs, as well as with the GB and NHs, considering feedback from the first prioritisation round and making a proposal for a systematic, criteria-based prioritisation for projects and substances.
 - o Following the implementation of the project review process and providing input for the on-going and new projects in terms of chemical RA and regulatory and policy needs.
 - o Preparing the background documents in collaboration with Task 2.2
 - o Applying the Rapid Response Mechanism (RRM)
- Task 2.2:
 - o To establish PARCopedia, PARC's knowledge management and community platform, launched in November 2023, as a primary web resource for the chemical RA community for finding, co-creating and discussing knowledge on all matters related to chemical RA and its innovation as a means to actively promote the transition to NGRA.
 - o To finalise NGRARoute, the proposal for a roadmap towards the regulatory uptake of NGRA into European chemicals legislation, in cooperation with the European Commission's "Roadmap for phasing out animal testing in chemical safety assessments", engaging a broad range of relevant stakeholders/ institutions from different sectors, in- and outside of PARC.
 - o To follow, support, and report on the work being developed within PARC for the priority chemicals and methodologies for the nominated CLs and MLs.
- Task 2.3:
 - o Maintaining the continuous dialogue with the National Hub Contact Points (NHCPs) and translating their needs into actions,
 - o Elaborating sustainable frameworks and further developing and refining the monitoring framework with T1.3.

Description of Programmed Activities

A Work Package 2 (Task Lead) meeting will take place in Vienna in autumn 2024. The topic and the final decision on the organisation of the meeting have not yet been selected. The meeting will also promote dialogue between the Task Leaders and foster a common understanding of the common science policy agenda.

Task 2.1: Priority setting

Co-leaders: ANSES (FR), ECHA (EU), EFSA (EU)

Key Partners: EAA (AT), EEA (EU), UBA (DE), BfR (DE), ISS (IT), GCSL (EL), DGS (PT)

Task 2.1 will ensure the link between the high-level priorities and the activities that will be implemented in PARC through projects providing input in terms of RA and regulatory and policy needs. In fact, the needs expressed by the GB Principal Representatives (GB PRs), will be refined and discussed with the NHs to ensure synergy with their national needs as well as the Stakeholder Forum (SF). Priorities of PARC for years 4 to 7 will be set considering the feedback received from the WPLs on the first prioritisation round. The substances or endpoints selected will reflect the synergy between the WPs, while avoiding duplication of work and ensuring that every project meets a policy need. This will be aligned with the project review process and will be done in close collaboration with the PARC CT, the NHs for their national needs, the MB for the research work and task 2.2 to warrant the adequate identification of regulatory demands under a science to policy dialogue.

Task 2.1 will continue to follow the on-going projects and their outcomes and will apply to new submitted projects the revised review process including more criteria on the regulatory relevance of the projects. This will ensure that the work currently developed through the projects described in the Project Portfolio will improve the process for the development of future strategies in terms of policy implementation in Risk Management (RM) and governance of chemicals legislation in Europe and at National level.

Task 2.1 will develop tools to make interlinks with projects within PARC and interactions with projects outside PARC.

The mapping of needs and prioritisation for year 4 to 7 (D2.4. 1st Mapping of Needs report, M18) will take into account the needs from GB and EU agencies. T2.1 Partners, including ECHA, EFSA and EEA, will ensure that the work of the science-policy interface is well perceived.

T2.1 will prepare, with the appointed CLs, background documents that will formulate the regulatory problems and introduce how the PARC projects contribute to addressing them. These contributions will then be updated on a yearly basis in the scoping documents (T2.2). For methods/tools, policy and regulatory needs will be documented with the support of MLs.

Task 2.1 will apply the D2.5. Rapid Response Report, M18. The aim of the mechanism is to allow GB members and SF co-chairs to submit project requests for specific information to the PARC Consortium thus ensuring that the PARC responds to new and urgent needs for information on chemicals in the EU policy community and at national level, outside of the formal timeframes for substance nomination. Task 2.1 will coordinate the eligibility checking of the requests.

A new project will also be created in response to a new request submitted in February 2024 under the rapid response mechanism developed by Task 2.1. The request mainly concerns mono-n-hexyl phthalate (MnHexP), for which urinary concentrations have risen sharply in kindergarten children in Germany, but also in adults, notably in Denmark. The aim of the request is to evaluate the extent of exposure on the European level and to understand the potential sources of this phthalate metabolite, whose occurrence in human urine is undesirable. This need could be addressed within PARC with the help of numerous tasks, including T4.1, T4.2, T6.2, activity 6.4.3 and potentially the SF.

Task 2.2: Knowledge management and uptake into policy

Co-leaders: BfR (DE), INSA (PT)

Key Partners: AUTH (EL), UOB (UK), ANSES (FR), DEFRA (UK), EAA (AT), EEA (EU), ENSP (PT), GCSL (EL), EV-ILVO (BE), ISS (IT), JSI (SI), MU (CZ), NILU (NO), SOM (EE), STAMI (NO), UBA (DE), UKON (DE)

A2.2.1 PARCopedia

After the launch of PARCopedia (Nov 2023), the three components of the online platform will be optimised: 1) the knowledge base will be continuously populated with content and regularly updated; 2) a second focus will be on increasing the level of engagement in the social media part of PARCopedia and on stimulating public discussion of matters related to PARC's goals; 3) innovative solutions to improve PARCopedia's dashboard and search engine will be investigated and implemented whenever appropriate. Relevant communication activities aimed at incentivising the (optimal) use of PARCopedia (video tutorials and/or webinars) are also planned; 4) inclusion of resources/tools developed in other PARC WPs will be investigated.

A2.2.2 PARCroute

Guiding principles and work streams for NGRAroute (the first roadmap delivered under PARCroute activity) as elaborated on in a first high-level draft of roadmap document (AD2.1, April 2024) will be complemented with all appropriate information on the existing context of research activities, ongoing projects, legislation landscape. Furthermore, open research questions identified in that draft will be systematically addressed. The draft will also be shared with actors inside and outside of PARC: meetings will be organised as relevant, and critical feedback will be implemented to a final version of the roadmap by the end of April 2025. To ensure maximum acceptance at the policy level, the close co-operation between T2.2 and the EU Commission's DGs ENV, GROW and JRC, established in autumn 2023 under the Commission's "roadmap for phasing out animal testing in chemical safety assessments", will be continued.

A2.2.3 CLs/MLs

CLs and MLs will continue to follow their work and, when necessary, support the work involving the chemical or methodology across the several PARC WPs. Meetings with the CLs and MLs will be organised to keep track of the work being developed by the CLs/MLs. A report on the work done will be prepared at the end of Y3 (D2.13, January 2025). Assessment of further needs concerning CLs and MLs will be conducted and, if deemed necessary, nomination of CLs and/or MLs for additional chemicals and/or methodologies will be performed.

Task 2.3: Sustainability

Co-leaders: INSERM (FR), NCPHP (HU)

Partners: ANSES (FR), SpF (FR), EAA (AT), DOMG (BE), MU (CZ), EEA (EU), UBA (DE), BfR (DE), NIOM (PL), FMUL (PT), INSA (PT), JSI (SI), NIJZ (SI)

A2.3.1 National hubs needs & peer-to-peer learning

The mapping of needs of NHs is a living process. A new survey based on criteria-driven scoping documents will be created and launched in the third year of the Partnership to identify the new needs and expectations of the NHs based on the inputs of the NHCPs. The responses will be used to reflect on possible improvements to the progress of the development of the NHs, the way we ask questions or collect input from the NHCPs and the NHs and also to the implementation of activities such as capacity building or sharing good practices that would support the NHs and their structuring at the national level.

The peer-to-peer learning process established in the first year of the Partnership will continue to support the sustainable development of the NHs. This activity will be performed in close collaboration with WP9 'Building infrastructural and human capacities'. The process will be coordinated and the development of the NHs will be monitored by the NHCs. Besides the annual survey, the needs of the NHs will be collected and discussed during the annual meeting.

A2.3.2 Exit strategy

Following the first NH survey on the exit strategy that was carried out during the first 18 months of PARC, a careful analysis was undertaken to identify 1) the activities that are sustainable in some way at the national level and 2) the proposals of the NH and different partners concerning which activities should be sustainable at the EU level and through which operational framework. A deliverable is expected by April 2024. One clear conclusion is that different PARC activities may require different systems for their sustainability.

Year 3 will be devoted to:

- Task 2.3 partners will identify the major PARC activities that need to be sustainable and start elaborating on different scenarios for e.g. Human biomonitoring, Toxicology/NAMs, environmental monitoring, safe and sustainable by design.
- The work on HBM sustainability will be carried out in close collaboration with project P4.1.5 of task 4.1 as well as DGENV and EEA following the workshop and meeting on HBM sustainability of Y2. The aim is to identify the operational framework and the legal basis for such an objective.
- Concerning Toxicology, different scenarios will be elaborated. Following the first exit strategy survey, different proposals were made concerning the activities to be included in such a sustainable programme. The build-up of a European Toxicology Programme inspired by the US NTP will be examined and a proposal will be made.
- Concerning environmental monitoring, the primary objective is to clearly identify the activities that need to be sustainable in the context of current activities in this field and which are not covered by other legislations at the European level. Discussions with 4.2 Task leaders as well as EEA and JRC will lead to a common understanding on the need of further activities, including data collection and identifying data gaps.
- Concerning SSbD and emerging threats, we will first identify current activities at then EU level and identify what may be missing, together with WP8 leaders and the EU–Commission. The proposal shall be in line with the different frameworks: SSBD on one hand hand and the risk assessment framework under REACH as well as the “One substance, one assessment” (OSOA) perspective.

For each activity and its level of structuring in Europe, different targeted steps will be identified to analyse the relevant regulatory framework, the relevant (existing or not) networks and infrastructures and requirements needed for the future.

All these objectives will be discussed with the different PARC boards, notably the coordinator, the MB and individually with WP and task leaders, the GB whose active involvement will be sought on these subjects. These discussions will contribute to the identification of additional interactions and outreach actions, which will take place specifically with EU agencies and directions, some national ministries and agencies and major EU infrastructures (e.g., EIRENE) and project clusters (EHEN, EURION, ASPIS, etc.). These interactions will not cover only research options but also policy options and opportunities linked to the implementation of the

CSS. Open discussions will be encouraged to feed into the sustainability discussions at EU level and contribute to the development of different options for frameworks will be developed for long-term sustainability of the activities identified.

At least ten meetings will be held and will involve different actors (eg. leaders of relevant WPs, MB, GB, representatives of European Agencies,) Concerning the different activities of PARC (human and environmental biomonitoring, toxicology, safe and sustainable by design and early warning systems), Discussions will be based on the Deliverable 2.9 and recent policy developments.

Deliverables:

D2.10 2nd Annual CL/ML reports' coordination and submission – Leader: INSA (M33)

D2.11 PARCroute roadmap2 – Leader: BfR (M36)

Additional Deliverables:

AD2.1 Status report on NGRARoute – Leader: BfR (M29)

WP N°	WP3										Lead Beneficiary				INSA/GCSL									
WP title	Synergies, collaborations and awareness																							
Partner N°	1	2	3	3.1	3.8	4	4.2	6	7	8	10	11	12	14	15	16	17	18	20	20.4	20.6	21	22	24
Partner short name	ANSES	SpF	EAA	AGES	UMIT	VITO	DOMG	CIPH	MOH-CY/SGL	MU	DEPA	HB	EEA	TTL	UBA	BfR	NCPHP	UI	ISS	IUSS	UNINA	RSU	NPHSL	LNS
PM/partner	1	0.5	4	2	2	1	1.5	0.5	0.5	2	0.5	0.5	13	0.5	2.8	0.9	14	1	0.5	2	0.1	0.5	0.5	1.5

Partner N°	25	26	26.2	27	28	29	29.1	29.3	29.5	30	31	31.2	31.2	32	34	35.7	35.9	36	36.1	36.2	36.3	36.4	37	38	50	59
Partner short name	RIVM	NIPH	STAMI	NIOM	FMUL	INSA	APA	ENSP	UAVR	SZU-SK	JSI	NIB	NIC	NIJZ	ISCIH	KEMI	SLV	AUTH	EFET	GCSL	NKUA	UOC	BPI	FOPH	UKHSA	UOB
PM/partner	2	0.5	4.3	1.9	4.6	35.2	3	3	2.4	0.5	1.5	3	1.5	5.5	2	1	0.5	10	5.5	19	11.2	3.9	2.5	0.5	2	1
Start	M25										End					M36										

Objectives

The main goal of WP3 is to boost the impact of PARC outcomes through the diffusion of the knowledge produced within the Partnership while fostering synergies and collaborations with other projects/programmes at national, EU and international levels.

The specific objectives of WP3 for year 3 are:

- Task 3.1: Running the International Board (IB) and Stakeholder Forum (SF), and ensure their effective interaction with PARC's projects,
- Task 3.2: Continue the implementation of the communication strategy for PARC and promote its continuous improvement based on specific requirements from WPs,
- Task 3.3: Continue establishing collaborations and synergies with identified relevant scientific/regulatory/policy initiatives at national, EU and international levels.

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 3.1: Building effective interactions

Co-Leaders: EAA (AT): Stakeholder Forum; AUTH (EL): International Board

Partners: ANSES (FR), EEA (EU), UBA (DE), IUSS (IT), LNS (LU), STAMI (NO), FMUL (PT), INSA (PT), APA (PT), NIB (SI), NKUA (EL), UOC (EL), GCSL (EL)

Activity 3.1.1. Running of Stakeholder Forum (SF)

In year 3 of PARC, the SF (established in year 1) will be continuing the work with the members of the SF. Together with two nominated SF chairs the strategy on information flow and inclusion of SF members' perceptions according to the respective SF groups (NGOs, industry associations and other interest associations) will be discussed and further refined. Based on the discussions and outputs of the first two SF meetings and in close collaboration with SF co-chairs and WP co-leaders, TLs and Project Managers (PMs) topics of interest for the SF will be selected and prepared for presentation at the next SF meetings. A physical SF meeting early in Y3 will be held in Hall in Tyrol (AT) (organized back to back with the Consortium Meeting). Another online meeting will be organized in the second semester of Y3 to further present the work progress and to address the interests and needs of the SF members, raised in the latest meeting (all partners). Minutes of meetings will be taken to document progress and extracts will be published on the website. SF members will be encouraged to participate in existing PARC channels and communication tools (PARCopedia, SYNnet...), to offer them the possibility to articulate their needs and interact with the PARC consortium and other stakeholders. Partners involved: EAA, INSA, GCSL, UBA, STAMI, FMUL, APA, NIB, NKUA and UOC.

Interactions with industry, in particular on the subjects of New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) and of SSbD under WP5 and WP8 respectively, will be promoted through the SF, which has representatives of industry associations and also with other relevant stakeholders through specific consultations and participation in dedicated meetings (AUTH, ANSES).

Stakeholder interests brought to the attention of Task 3.1 will be taken up and forwarded to Tasks 3.3 and 2.2 or other WPs of specific interest.

Activity 3.1.2. Running of the International Board (IB)

TLs and partners will work in close collaboration to promote the interaction between the IB members and PARC WPs. Feedback on scientific steering needs will be collected from the WPLs

into a dedicated form that will be distributed in advance (two months prior the next IB meeting). The collected needs will be discussed and prioritized by the Activity 3.1.2 consortium, who will decide after consultation of the MB on the topics of the forthcoming IB meeting. Two meetings (one physical organized back to back with the Consortium Meeting in May 2024 and another online) will be organized to present the work progress and the main outcomes and to get feedback from the IB on the performance of Projects within PARC. Those meetings will also stimulate the interactions between PARC and external bodies (all partners).

Partners involved: AUTH, UBA, IUSS, LNS, STAMI, FMUL, INSA, NKUA, UOC, GCSL.

Task 3.2: Communication, dissemination, and awareness

Co-Leaders: EEA (EU), NCPHP (HU)

Partners: ANSES (FR), SpF (FR), EAA (AT), AGES (AT), UMIT (AT), VITO (BE), DOMG (BE), CIPH (CR), MOH-CY/SGL (CY), MU (CZ), HB (EE), TTL (FI), UBA (DE), BfR (DE), UI (IS), MOH-IL (IL), ISS (IT), UNINA (IT), RSU (LV), NPHSL (LT), LNS (LU), RIVM (NL), NIPH (NO), STAMI (NO), NIOM (PL), FMUL (PT), INSA (PT), APA (PT), ENSP (PT), UAVR (PT), SZU (SK), JSI (SI), NIB (SI), NIC (SI), NIJZ (SI), ISCIII (ES), KEMI (SE), SLV (SE), FOPH (CH), UKHSA (UK), UOB (UK), AUTH (EL), EFET (EL), NKUA (EL), UOC (EL), BPI (EL), GCSL (EL)

A3.2.1 Website and social media channels

The PARC website and the social media channels (LinkedIn, Twitter/X, Facebook and Instagram accounts) will be maintained and updated regularly with new content including up to date information about upcoming events, progress updates, interviews and results by EEA, NCPHP, INSA, EFET, NKUA, NIJZ, BPI, and GCSL.

A3.2.2 Development and implementation of the communication and dissemination strategy

Following the developed communication and dissemination strategy, a continuous dialogue will be maintained with all WP co-leaders, WP3 contact points and National Hub contact points to translate the latest PARC results and the PARC agenda into communication and dissemination outputs, ensuring a coherent approach. The roadmap for the development of communication materials will be updated. New communication materials and activities, such as a PARC video and infographics on the projects' outputs, will be created to increase PARC's visibility, build and grow the PARC brand and engage stakeholders. The monthly Science Digest listing the latest peer-reviewed scientific PARC articles will continue to be produced, while the PARC Sampler bringing together all the latest news, interviews, science impact and much more will continue to be published twice a year. All public project deliverables produced under the project will be made available via the PARC website. Webinars, meetings and training activities for transfer of good practices, experience and knowledge will be organized in collaboration with WP9 partners. Partners involved: UMIT, EEA, NCPHP, LNS, STAMI, FMUL, INSA, APA, ENSP, UAVR, JSI, NIB, NIJZ, EFET, NKUA, UOC and GCSL.

A3.2.3 Surveys and other tools to assess stakeholders' perception and concerns

Outreach activities will be carried out to raise awareness of specific target groups. New focus groups will be organized to collect more in-depth information about citizens' perceptions and

concerns about PARC-related subjects. The countries hosting focus group discussions will be selected in an internal call. The results of the first citizens' survey will be analysed. All information gathered from the citizens' survey and the focus groups will be fed into a deliverable on citizens' perceptions and concerns. Stakeholder surveys will be carried out targeting the key stakeholder groups. Communication with the scientific community and with all stakeholders, including the general public, regulators and policy makers will be done in dialogue through the different communication channels (website, social media, newsletters, PARCopedia, workshops and other events) and with the involvement of the NHs. Partners involved: EEA, ENSP, FMUL, GCSL, INSA, NCPHP, NIB.

A3.2.4 Risk communication

A survey for mapping the risk perception of the different stakeholders on risk communication will be conducted in Greece and Slovenia by EFET and NIJZ for validation purposes. The results of the survey will be analysed and a report on the risk communication activities will be produced (as additional deliverable AD3.1).

A.3.2.5 Monitoring of indicators

Monitoring of indicators defined for the communication and dissemination activities will continue to feed into task 1.3 by DOMG, EEA, GCSL, INSA and NCPHP.

Task 3.3: Networking and Synergies

Co-Leaders: INSA (PT), NKUA (EL)

Partners: ANSES (FR), MU (CZ), UBA (DE), FMUL (PT), APA (PT), ENSP (PT), UAVR (PT), JSI (SI), NIB (SI), NIC (SI), NIJZ (SI), EFET (EL), UOC (EL), BPI (EL), GCSL (EL)

A3.3.1 Inventory of scientific activities relevant to PARC

Update of the established database of partnerships, projects, networks and activities including platforms relevant to PARC within the frame of an efficient and dynamic collaboration strategy by filling up the online form created specifically for this purpose (all partners).

A3.3.2 SYNnet and roadmap for promotion of synergies

Continue updating SYNnet with the information gathered in the form created to register the established synergies and work on expanding the network to include new partnerships, projects, etc. and respond to PARC demands for synergies (ANSES, MU, UBA, FMUL, APA, ENSP, UAVR, JSI, NIB, NIC, NIJZ, EFET, UOC, BPI, GCSL).

A3.3.3 Development of internal and external interaction strategies

Revise and update the interaction strategy between SYNnet and WPs in order to identify and address internal needs and gaps (BPI, ENSP, NKUA, GCSL, INSA, UBA).

Coordinate with WP/Task/Project leaders to create adequate incentives for external scientific activities that are relevant to PARC.

SYNnet activities will be announced and published at the PARC website increasing the visibility of joint activities and of the external projects themselves. The first SYNnet Forum foreseen to

take place in Y2 will be organized in the beginning of Y3, back-to-back with a relevant scientific event, to promote dialogue and knowledge sharing among scientists (ENSP, FMUL, NIB, NIC, NIJZ, NKUA, UAVR, UOC, BPI).

Deliverables:

D3.5 1st Report on citizen's perception and concern: results of the surveys and focus groups – Leader: EEA (initial due date M28 postponed to M32)

Additional Deliverables:

AD3.1. Report on risk communication activities, Leader: *EFET* (M36)

WP N°	WP4	Lead Beneficiary	UBA/SpF
WP title	Monitoring and exposure		
Part ner N°	1		
Part ner short name	ANSES		
PM/partner	54.9		
	7.1	INSERM	
	85.3	INRAE	
	11.9	CEA	
	12.8	INERIS	
	2.8	CNRS	
	14.8	INRS	
	17.6	ONIRIS	
	1.0	OFB	
	15.3	BRGM	
	0.3	LNE	
	11.2	CSTB	
	16.4	EHESP	
	80.4	SpF	
	6.5	EAA	
	31.2	MUI	
	4.0	UG-AT	
	4.7	UNIVE	
	57.2	VITO	
	11.9	KU Leuven	
	1.0	UH	
	6.0	PIH	
	14.0	OVAM	
	31.5	ISSeP	
	19.4	UAntwerpen	
	18.4	SCIENSANO	
	0.9	EV-ILVO	
	1.0	CIPH	
	15.5	MOH-CY/SGL	
	38.6	MU	
	13.5	SZU-CZ	
	7.1	VSCHT	
	1.2	JU	
	40.5	AU	
			10.1

Partn er N°	10.3		
Partn er short name	REGIONH-RH		
PM/partner	10.0		
	12.3	UCPH	
	12.0	UT	
	6.1	SYKE	
	27.0	TTL	
	4.5	FFA	
	1.5	UOULU	
	70.7	UBA	
	13.5	BfG	
	57.6	UFZ	
	7.3	KUM	
	12.7	Fraunhofer-IRAMT/IME	
	9.0	UI	
	4.5	MOH	
	13.3	ISS	
	13.6	CNR-IRSA	
	7.0	UMIL	
	1.8	UNINA	
	2.0	UNIPD	
	31.3	RSU	
	4.7	UL	
	0.3	NHPSL	
	6.7	LSMU	
	65.8	LNS	
	21.0	UnILU	
	3.2	KWR	
	0.5	TNO	
	2.6	UU-IRAS	
	13.5	VUA	
			25.6

Partner N°	25.7
Partner short name	WR
PM/partner	14.0
Partner N°	25.9
Partner short name	SRU
PM/partner	9.5
Partner N°	26
Partner short name	NIPH
PM/partner	34.9
Partner N°	26.2
Partner short name	STAMI
PM/partner	9.5
Partner N°	26.3
Partner short name	NILU
PM/partner	5.5
Partner N°	26.5
Partner short name	NMBU
PM/partner	0.5
Partner N°	26.7
Partner short name	UNN
PM/partner	0.3
Partner N°	27
Partner short name	NIOM
PM/partner	35.3
Partner N°	27.2
Partner short name	UG-PL
PM/partner	5.6
Partner N°	27.3
Partner short name	WULS-SGGW
PM/partner	14.2
Partner N°	29
Partner short name	INSA
PM/partner	33.2
Partner N°	29.3
Partner short name	ENSP
PM/partner	2.2
Partner N°	30
Partner short name	SZU-SK
PM/partner	9.00
Partner N°	31
Partner short name	JSI
PM/partner	48.6
Partner N°	31.4
Partner short name	ULFFA
PM/partner	6.8
Partner N°	32
Partner short name	NIJZ
PM/partner	10.2
Partner N°	32.2
Partner short name	NLZOH
PM/partner	0.2
Partner N°	32.3
Partner short name	ARSO
PM/partner	2.1
Partner N°	33
Partner short name	CSIC
PM/partner	32.7
Partner N°	33.4
Partner short name	ULPGC
PM/partner	0.4
Partner N°	33.3
Partner short name	UGR
PM/partner	24.8
Partner N°	34
Partner short name	ISCI
PM/partner	38.0
Partner N°	34.1
Partner short name	EASP
PM/partner	6.5
Partner N°	34.2
Partner short name	FISABIO
PM/partner	1.0
Partner N°	34.5
Partner short name	IISPV
PM/partner	2.5
Partner N°	34.6
Partner short name	INNST
PM/partner	4.0
Partner N°	34.7
Partner short name	UCLM
PM/partner	6.5
Partner N°	34.8
Partner short name	UPV-EHU
PM/partner	8.5
Partner N°	35.3
Partner short name	ULLUND
PM/partner	4.4

Partner N°	35.4		
Partner short name	ORU		
PM/partner	11.9		
Partner N°	35.6		
Partner short name	SU		
PM/partner	8.5		
Partner N°	35.8		
Partner short name	IVL		
PM/partner	11.4		
Partner N°	35.10		
Partner short name	SLU		
PM/partner	17.0		
Partner N°	36		
Partner short name	AUTH		
PM/partner	16.0		
Partner N°	36.1		
Partner short name	EFET		
PM/partner	1.9		
Partner N°	36.2		
Partner short name	GCSL		
PM/partner	1.0		
Partner N°	36.3		
Partner short name	NKUA		
PM/partner	35.5		
Partner N°	37		
Partner short name	BPI		
PM/partner	15.0		
Partner N°	38		
Partner short name	FOPH		
PM/partner	1.0		
Partner N°	40		
Partner short name	UNISANTE		
PM/partner	6.3		
Partner N°	41		
Partner short name	EAWAG		
PM/partner	26.5		
Partner N°	45		
Partner short name	USI		
PM/partner	6.2		
Partner N°	47		
Partner short name	SECO		
PM/partner	0.4		
Partner N°	50		
Partner short name	UKHSA		
PM/partner	3.5		
Partner N°	53		
Partner short name	UKCEH		
PM/partner	5.0		
Partner N°	54		
Partner short name	EA		
PM/partner	1.5		
Partner N°	55		
Partner short name	HSE		
PM/partner	5.0		
Partner N°	56		
Partner short name	IOM		
PM/partner	1.1		
Partner N°	57		
Partner short name	UBAH		
PM/partner	3.0		
Partner N°	58		
Partner short name	UINABDN		
PM/partner	0.5		
Start	M25	End	M36

Objectives

The main goal of WP4 is to monitor chemicals guided by clearly defined regulatory and policy challenges both in humans and in the environment, observing different sources, chemical fates and exposure pathways, international activities, and coordinate with the WHO EHP on Human Biomonitoring (HBM) launched in Budapest in July 2023. The specific objectives of WP4 for year 3 are:

- Task 4.1: Continuation of an EU-wide general population HBM survey, continuing occupational surveys in health care sector and waste sector, developing targeted surveys (design and supporting materials), preparing and implementation of following aspects in above mentioned surveys: effect biomarkers, innovative (sampling) techniques for HBM in a tiered approach starting with state of the art analyses, update and integration of QA/QC aspects and analyses plan in the HBM surveys, evaluation of new chemical analysis methods needs, derivation of HBM guidance values (HBM-GV).
- Task 4.2: Complete the development of a mechanism to define priority chemicals/matrices/endpoints for environmental monitoring studies. Complete a first monitoring study on PFAS and endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs) and evaluate the process with regard to future monitoring studies. Initiate a study on human exposure to organic chemicals from environmental non-food sources.
- Task 4.3: Novel methodologies will be developed in a tiered approach for improvement and renewal of current monitoring approaches, with a focus on early life stages and on early warning systems for the timely observation of the occurrence of chemicals of emerging concern in the environment-food-human continuum. The work will be covered in 4 ongoing projects (started in year 1) and 3 projects started in year 2 and 1 project starting in year 3

From year 3 a specific attention will be given to transversal activities inside WP4 to ensure that the different tasks align their activities in the perspective of a better integration of human and environmental monitoring networks. Specifically, the project 4.2.c will be a collaboration between T4.1 and T4.2, with strong links to T4.3. In particular, a list of priority substances will be defined early in Y3 that link human and environmental monitoring. Case studies for joint data evaluation will be defined to evaluate the benefits and limitations of an integrative assessment of human and environmental exposure to chemicals.

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 4.1: Human Biomonitoring

Co-Leaders: VITO (BE), ISCIII (ES)

Partners: ANSES (FR), AU (DK), AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), CEA (FR), CSIC (ES), EAA (AT), EHESP (FR), FFA (FI), TTL (FI), FISABIO (ES), FOPH (CH), HSE (UK), KI (SE), IMROH (HR), INRAE (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), INSERM (FR), INSST (ES), IOM (UK), KUM (DE), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), IVL (SE), JSI (SI), KU Leuven (BE), LNS (LU), LSMU (LT), MOH-CY/SGL (CY), MOH (IL), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), MUW (AT), NIJZ (SI), NIOM (PL), NIPH (NO), NLZOH (SI), NPHSL (LT), ONIRIS (FR), UKHSA (UK), PIH (BE), REGIONH-RH (DK), RSU (LV), SRU (NL), SCIENSANO (BE), SLU (SE), SpF (FR), STAMI (NO), SZU-CZ (CZ), SZU-SK (SK), THL (FI), UAntwerpen (BE), UBA (DE), UGent (BE), UGR (ES), UH (BE), ULFFA (SI), ULPGC (ES), ULUND (SE), UMU (SE), UMIL (IT), UNINA (IT), UNIPD (IT), UNISANTE (CH), UNIVIE (AT), UNN (NO), UOULU (FI), UOC (EL), UPV/EHU (ES), USI (CH), UU-IRAS (NL), WULS-SGGW (PL), CIPH (HR), SHSO (CY), SDU (DK), Fraunhofer-IBMT (DE), UFZ (DE), NCPHP (HU), UI (IS), VSCHT (CZ), EASP (ES), SECO (CH)

A4.1.1 Design, alignment and fieldwork of HBM studies

The implementation of a general population HBM survey is ongoing and will be further supported (linked to P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO). Proposals for add-ons to be implemented, as small-scale research components, in the general survey will be finalized. The add-on topics are: i) implementation of effect biomarkers (linked to P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO), ii) identify the contribution of specific environmental compartments, products to internal exposure levels (in collaboration with T4.2 - in project P4.2.c_Y3_HumanExposure_INERIS_AU), and (iii) apply innovative screening methods (Suspect screening (SS), Non targeted screening (NTS)) (in collaboration with T4.3 - in project P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03 Complementary developments_JSI/UAntwerpen).

Project proposals for targeted surveys will be developed and submitted in Y3 to be initiated in Y4 (ISCIII, LNS, SpF, UBA, VITO). Preliminary priorities for targeted studies include: dietary exposure to e.g., food related exposures in young children, prenatal and newborn exposure to e.g., endocrine disruptors and Persistent Organic pollutants (POPs), health effects and risk factors related to (accumulated) exposure in the middle-aged population (40-69y) and elderly (70-85y), time trends in repeatedly sampled cohorts/regions and/or biobanked samples from longer time periods, PFAS hotspots. During the first year, two occupational surveys focusing on the waste management sector (linked to P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL) (phthalates, metals, flame retardants, bisphenols) and the health care sector (linked to

P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_Occuphealthcare_TTL_SRU) (HMPs and disinfectants) (HSE, INRS, INSST, IOM, MU, RSU, SRU, TTL, UGR) have been designed. Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) are performed for harmonised sampling procedures in accordance with the procedures for the PARC Aligned Studies and ethical permissions are applied in each participating countries in the end of Y1 and Y2. Sampling related to these studies will continue in Y3 for the waste management sector (AU, INSA, ENSP, ISS, KUL, LNS, MOH-CY/SGL, NIOM, STAMI, UMIL, UNIPD, UNINA, UNISANTE, WULS-SGGW, ULUND, IPA) and the health care sector (HSE, INRS, INSST, IOM, MU, RSU, SRU, TTL, UGR, LNS). Samplings will include also samples collected according to harmonised and quality assured SOPs for effect marker analyses (which have been planned in collaboration with P4.1.3.3a) and applying new innovative methods (T4.3: linked to P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02).

The project P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasability_TTL will be extended into Y3 to prepare a final report and scientific publication.

S4.1.1.1-supporting materials for a harmonized HBM conduct: the Y3 work plan will focus on the update of the material transfer agreement developed under HBM4EU and the elaboration of effective communication materials for reporting the research results to participants (CIPH, CSIC, EAA, EASP, FOPH, Fraunhofer-IBMT, IMROH, INSA, ISCIII, ISS, ISSeP, JSI, LNS, LSMU, MOH-IL, MUW, NIJZ, NIOM, PIH, RSU, SpF, STAMI, THL, UBA, UGR, ULUND, UMU, UOULU, UPV).

Details per project:

- P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO: Partners that will contribute to the PARC Aligned Studies in children (6-11 years) are UKHSA, RegionH-RH, RSU, UT, HB, WULS-SGGW, SZU-CZ, NCPHP, ISCIII, INSA, AUTH, JSI, MOH-CY/SGL, UBA, SPF, EAA, LNS. Partners that will contribute in teenagers (12-17 years) are UKHSA, RegionH-RH, NIPH, ULUND, RSU, NIOM, JSI, AUTH, INSA, UBA, SPF, VITO/PIH, and partners that will contribute in adults (18-39 years) are UKHSA, LSMU, RSU, UT, HB, UI, NIPH, SZU-CZ, NIOM, NCPHP, EASP, UPV, AUTH, INSA, MOH-CY/SGL, ISS, UBA, SPF, ISSeP, LNS, MOH-IL, RIVM. Discussions on potential contribution from Ireland and Slovakia are ongoing. Substance groups prioritized for analysis are in children: Phthalates and substitute DINCH, Bisphenols, Pesticides, metals in urine, Mercury (hair), in teenagers: PFAS, Phthalates and substitute DINCH, Bisphenols, arsenic species, pesticides, in adults: PFAS, metals in urine/blood, pesticides, bisphenols. In all age groups cotinine, creatinine and specific gravity will be assessed. Sample collection activities (up to 3650 children, 2750 adolescents and 4900 adults) continue throughout Y3, overall coordination will be taken up by VITO supported by ISCIII, UBA, SPF, LNS, INSA, RegionH-RH. A subset of the PARC Aligned Studies will contribute to the add-on “effect biomarker implementation”.

Following partners with HBM studies **in children** will implement effect biomarkers: WULS, AUTH, ISCIII, LNS, JSI, NPHC, RSU, MOH-CY/SGL.

Following partners with HBM studies **in teenagers** will implement effect biomarkers: AUTH, JSI, RSU, NIPH, VITO/PIH, SPF, NIOM.

Following partners with HBM studies **in adults** will implement effect biomarkers: AUTH, LNS, NPHC, RSU, MOH-CY/SGL, NIPH, SPF, NIOM, EASP, ISSeP.

- P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasability_TTL: learnings from this project can potentially be considered in sentinel surveillance study (P4.1.1.4.b_Y1_SentinelSystem_KULeuven) conducted as part of PARC. Due to delay in data exchange the project will be extended into Y3 to prepare the final report and scientific publication. Scientific publication is drafted (TTL (FI) SpF (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), LSMU (LT)).

- P4.1.1.4.b_Y1_SentinelSystem_KULeuven: The sentinel project has been reoriented to focus on occupational population rather than general population. The focus of the project is on the Assessment of exposure to substances of high concern in the working population through a sentinel surveillance system, to establish a robust sentinel surveillance system in occupational settings.

Phase 1 in Year 3: An Updated Mapping Exercise (Go/No-Go Decision): This phase incorporates a detailed mapping exercise in collaboration with partner countries, intending to implement the sentinel surveillance system at the national level. The exercise involves considerations for occupational sectors to be included and substances and compounds to be analyzed for assessing exposure to substances of high concern in each partner country. The mapping exercise encompasses key scientific components:

Capacity Assessment:

- Identification of occupational sectors and socio-economic status.
- Identification of prevalent occupational diseases, emerging health risks, and patterns of morbidity and mortality in the working population.
- Evaluation of existing infrastructure, resources, and technical capabilities within each partner country for implementing a sentinel surveillance system.
- Engagement assessment of physicians/nurses, employers, and workers, including the determination of the number of occupational physicians that can be recruited.
- Assessment of the availability of trained personnel, laboratory facilities, and information systems for data collection and analysis.
- Identification of the most relevant compounds and substances (along with relevant biomarkers) in the targeted and selected occupational sector, with partner countries making choices.
- Determination of laboratories available for each type of exposure biomarker to measure each selected substance of high concern.

Legal and Ethical Considerations:

- Review and analysis of legal and ethical frameworks governing data collection, storage, biobank procedures, ethical committee application processes and durations, and dissemination in occupational health surveillance.
- Development of protocols to ensure compliance with international standards and guidelines.

Pilot Implementation Plan:

- Development of a pilot implementation plan based on the findings of the mapping exercise.
- Design of protocols for testing the efficacy and scalability of the sentinel surveillance system in a targeted working population.

Upon completion of Phase 1 in Year 3, the project anticipates achieving a comprehensive understanding of the readiness and capacity of partner countries for implementing a sentinel surveillance system in occupational settings. These outcomes will inform the development of

tailored interventions and protocols for the subsequent project phase, thereby contributing to the global enhancement of occupational health monitoring

- P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthCareSurvey_TTL_SRU: In the end of year 2 and beginning of year 3, hospitals and volunteering participants will be recruited. Field workers have been trained to collect environmental and biological samples and contextual data according to harmonised methods and quality assured SOPs during year 2. Next, the sampling campaign will be launched, which will start early 2024 and continue in Y3. Collected samples will be shipped to laboratories for analysis. Aim is to include 20 hospitals and up to 650 workers. Analysis of samples is planned to begin in Y3. Chemical substance groups prioritized for analysis are cytotoxics, anesthetic substances and disinfectants. Effect Biomarkers prioritized for analysis are markers for genotoxicity, oxidative stress and inflammation. Samples are collected from hospital settings in 10 countries by the following partners: TTL (FI), SRU (NL), MU (CZ), UGR (ES), INRS (FR), ISS (IT), UMIL (IT), UNINA (IT), UNIPD (IT), RSU (LV), LNS (LU), ENSP (PT), HSE (UK), IOM (UK), INSST (ES). This activity is led by SRU and TTL and made in collaboration with task 4.1.2. The project specific data management plan is finalised by SRU and TTL by the beginning of Y3 with the support from the other partners (see the list above) and T7.1.

- P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL: Year 2 has been devoted to the preparation of SOPs for harmonised samplings, information materials and submission of the study protocol to the Ethical Committees. Data Management Plan (DMP) has been prepared in collaboration with WP7, as well as the online training on the implementation of the study protocols and procedures (collaboration with WP9). Sampling campaigns will begin by the end of Y2 and continue in Y3 of PARC. Aim is to cover 40-50 companies and up to 700 workers. Analysis of samples is planned to begin in Y3. Chemical substance groups prioritized for analysis are metals, Flame retardants, Phthalates, Bisphenols, PFAS, plasticizers. Effect Biomarkers prioritized for analysis are markers for genotoxicity, oxidative stress and inflammatory markers. Samples are collected in 13 countries by: ENSP-UNL (PT), AU (DK), ISS(IT), UNIPD (IT), UMIL (IT), UNINA (IT), WULS (PL), ULUND (SE), STAMI (NO), AUTH (GR), INSA (PT), TTL (FI), LNS (LU), MOH-CY (CY), NIOM (PL), IOM (UK), HSE (UK) and UGR (ES).

A4.1.2 Laboratory analysis and quality assurance

No project for this activity since it is a transversal activity.

During Y3, the selection of the best, state-of-the-art exposure biomarkers and analytical methods will be done (AU, AUTH, BPI, CEA, EHESP, FFA, FISABIO, IMROH, INSA, ISCI, ISS, JSI, KU Leuven, KUM, LNS, LSMU, NIOM, NIPH, NPHSL, UKHSA, RSU, SRU, SpF, STAMI, SZU-SK, THL, UAntwerpen, UGR, ULFFA, ULPGC, ULUND, UMIL, UNN, UOC, UOULU, USI, VSCHT) according to the needs identified in the proposals that will be developed during Y3 for the targeted studies to be implemented from Y4.

For occupational studies, selection of exposure and effect biomarkers have been made already during Y2 of PARC. Substance groups prioritized for analysis in P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_Occuphealthcare_TTL_SRU include hazardous medicinal products including cytotoxic drugs and anaesthetic gases, alcohols used in disinfection and cleaning products. Effect markers prioritized include genotoxicity, inflammatory and oxidative stress markers. Substance groups prioritized for analysis in P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL: Metals,

Flame retardants, Phthalates, Bisphenols, PFAS, plasticizers. Effect markers prioritized include genotoxicity, inflammatory and oxidative stress markers. Candidate laboratories (13 for waste management and 15 for health care study) for the analysis of different exposure and effect markers have been also selected. During Y2 and beginning of Y3, these candidate laboratories are expected to ensure their quality. For those biomarkers for which no proficiency test is provided by PARC-QEQUAS, an internal small-scale QA system/inter-laboratory comparison will be organised. Analysis of some samples is expected to start Y3. This applies especially to some effect biomarkers (like PBL MN) which require processing soon after the collection of samples.

The Quality Assurance Working Group (QAWG) (AU, ISCIII, NIPH, UAntwerpen, and WR) and collaborating partners (LNS) will still work in close collaboration with T9.1 and T9.3 to ensure the quality and comparability of the HBM data generated under T4.1. It is expected that the PARC-GEQUAS QA/QC program will begin in the spring of 2024 (Year 3 of PARC). In parallel, the proficiency test for total mercury in hair will be also implemented in Y3. This program is organised, implemented and coordinated by ISCIII with input from T9.3. Based on the timeline for the HBM surveys currently planned, the QA/QC program is expected to run for at least two more years (2025-2026 and 2026-2027) to cover the needs of all the studies. In Y3 we expect to have the first list of qualified laboratories that can analyse HBM samples in PARC. In addition, QA/QC aspects related to the innovative sampling techniques will be evaluated and included in the design of the add ons for the HBM surveys (ISCIII, LNS, MU, ONIRIS, UAntwerpen, UGR, UNIVIE, and UOC). The working group on reference analytical methods (ISCIII, ISS, IVL, LNS, MUI, NIPH, SCIENSANO, UAntwerpen, ULUND, UNIVIE, and UOC) will continue working in the inventory concept to identify strong/weak points related to the analytical methods for the selected substances. This information will allow to identify knowledge gaps and the concrete needs for analytical methods development. In addition, the need to harmonise important preanalytical issues will be also covered in this inventory. This activity will lead to the preparation of a project proposal on method development (or improvement). In Y3 the chemical analysis plan (adapted templates, monitoring tool on the sharepoint...) will be approved and implemented (LNS, MU, NIOM, RSU, SRU, SCIENSANO, SpF, THL, TTL, UAntwerpen, UBA, UGR, and ULUND). The harmonisation, quality assurance and implementation of effect biomarkers will take place under P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO, and details are provided below.

A4.1.3 Link exposure and health related information

No transversal activities under A4.1.3, all captured in projects.

Details per project:

- P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_Derivation of HBM-GVs_UBA: Year 3: Health-Based HBM Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) will be derived for a third set of prioritised substances (ANSES, AUTH, MOH-IL, NIJZ, NIPH-FHI, TTL, UBA, Unisante, SECO, LNS). HBM-GVs for selected substances or their specific exposure biomarkers will be derived according to the strategy agreed under HBM4EU and described by Apel et al. (2020; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2020.113622>). In principle, all lead experts conduct a literature search on the substance under consideration to determine the current state of toxicological/epidemiological knowledge. Depending on the data basis, the experts decide whether epidemiological data, or else a recognized external toxicity reference value respectively occupational exposure limit, or a point of departure from an experimental study

together with toxicokinetic information is used to derive the HBM-GV. Thus, HBM data are only included in the derivation if studies are available that show a relationship between human internal exposure and health effects. If additional data is needed WP 5 will be involved to fill the data gaps.

The substance dossiers including the derived values will afterwards be reviewed by project partners and other experts involved via the NHs.

NIPH-FHI and TTL will work on mercury. It is to be examined whether and, if so, which significant published toxicological findings need to be added to the dossier in the HBM4EU Deliverable D5.12 (Deliverables – HBM4EU – science and policy for a healthy future). The findings on the toxicology of mercury presented in the HBM4EU Deliverable D13.7 (Deliverables – HBM4EU – science and policy for a healthy future) should also be taken into account. Based on this, it should be clarified whether the provisional HBM-GVs for the general population (7 µg Hg/l urine, 3.5 µg Hg/l blood) which were derived within HBM4EU can be adopted. AUTH offered support regarding modelling work.

ANSES will check whether the derivation of HBM-GV for arsenic is possible and will work on HBM-GV for cis-/trans-DCCA as metabolites of various pyrethroids. A working group led by MOH-IL and involving NIPH, possibly LNS and WP 6 partners (6.2.3., case study on mixture risk assessment) will evaluate whether/which further work is needed to re-assess PFAS HBM guidance values as part of PARC. With the aim of deriving HBM-GV, UBA will work on Acetamidrid/ N-desmethyl acetamidrid and the phthalate substitute DEHA (di(2-ethylhexyl)adipate). It is planned that dossiers and reports for the abovementioned substances are included in AD4.3.

- P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO: This project will be continued. In Y3, a new approach for linking exposures and health effects will be explored. This approach will consist of a feasibility study that will explore the use of archived (stored in biobanks) samples previously collected in cohorts or biobanks to quantify past exposures and link them to effect biomarkers and health outcomes (BPI, EEA, EHESP, Fraunhofer-IBMT, INSST, JSI, KU Leuven, LNS, NIJZ, UKHSA, RSU, SpF, TTL, UBA). To perform this feasibility study, we will work on (i) The definition of the study criteria for measurements of exposures and effect biomarkers with the aim to link past exposures to current health effects and (ii) the development of a data analysis approach in collaboration with A4.1.4-Data management and analysis to link past exposures and health outcomes.

Year 3 will be devoted to continuing the feasibility study:

- Selection of effect biomarkers and related analytical methods, matrices, and health outcomes (VITO (Lead), AU, AUTH, EAA, CSIC, TTL, INRS, INSA, INSERM, ISCIII, JSI, KU Leuven, LNS, NIJZ, NLZOH, SECO, Sciansano, SpF, UGR, UKHSA, ULPGC, UNINA, UNIPD, USI)
- Development of a data analysis approach (SpF (Lead), AU, AUTH, CEA, EAA, EHESP, Fraunhofer, CSIC, INRS, INSA, INSST, ISCIII, JSI, KU Leuven, LNS, MU, NIJZ, NIOM, NLZOH, SRU, RSU, Sciansano, SECO, STAMI, TTL, UKHSA, UBA, UGR, UNINA, UNIPD, USI UPV/EHU)

In year 3, VITO will continue to lead the implementation of effect biomarkers in PARC surveys. The effect biomarkers have been identified and selected for the general survey and occupational studies in Y2. UGR will lead the selection of labs, together with T4.1.2 (ISCIII) and supported by

VITO. The QA/QC aspects for effect biomarker measurements and derivation of respective SOPs will be organized by UGR with support of ISCIII and T9.3.

A4.1.4 Data management and analysis

Details for transversal activities:

- Data management: the T4.1 data management team (VITO, MU, SPF, UBA, TTL, PIH) will further support all HBM related data management activities in T4.1. That is the development of the codebooks, the validation of the biomarker list, feedback and testing of the tools on data validation, calculation of derived variables and calculation of summary statistics (<https://hbm.vito.be/tools>), feedback on the integration of aggregated data into the European HBM dashboard and IPCHEM, definition of metadata for HBM studies, helpdesk for data management activities.

- Statistical working group: the statistical working group (VITO, UU-IRAS, MU, JSI, AU, SPF, UBA, NIPH, INSA, TTL, UH) will further elaborate the statistical analysis plan for the ongoing 4.1 projects. The statistical working group (WG) gives support and advice to research leads in performing the statistical analyses.

Details per project:

- P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO: Year 3 is the final year of the project and will be devoted to finalizing the statistical analyses of the data and the interpretation and discussion of the results. Scientific peer-reviewed publications will be elaborated and submitted. Results will be reported and communicated to the PARC community (AD4.11). Partners involved: AU, AUTH, BPI, EASP, INRAE, INRS, INSA, ISCIII, ISSeP, JSI, LNS, LSMU, MU, NIJZ, NIPH, Sciensano, SPF, SZU-SK, TTL, UBA, UGR, UU-IRAS, VITO.

A4.1.5 Preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe

No transversal activities under A4.1.5, all captured in projects.

Details per project:

- P4.1.5.a_Y1_SustainHBMSystem_VITO will be continued in Y3. The project's goal is the preparation of a sustainable human biomonitoring and surveillance system for Europe.

Following actions are planned for Y3:

Make an assessment of existing monitoring systems in human biomonitoring (e.g. WHO mother milk survey) or other domains such as food/feed, etc.. Assess existing international HBM programs and European HBM programs/studies. Foster interaction with international key players in HBM to exchange experiences and improve international collaboration and comparison of HBM data. Engagement with the PARC GB to develop a roadmap for sustainable HBM after PARC. The project is co-lead by VITO and SpF. Other partners involved in the actions are FOPH, INSA, ISCIII, LNS, LSMU, MOH-CY/SGL, NIPH, UBA. This project will be run in close collaboration with WP2 and the PARC Exit Strategy.

Task 4.2: Environmental and multisource monitoring

Co-leaders: INERIS (FR), AU (DK)

Partners: ANSES (FR), BfG (DE), BRGM (FR), CNRS (FR), CNR-IRSA (IT), CSIC (ES), CSTB (FR), EA (UK), EAWAG (CH), EFET (EL), Fraunhofer-IME (DE), FISABIO (ES), INRAE (FR), INSERM (FR), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), IVL (SE), JSI (SI), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), NKUA (EL), OFB (FR), ONIRIS (FR), OVAM (BE), SCIENSANO (BE), SLU (SE), SYKE (FI), UAntwerpen (BE), UBA (DE), UCLM (PT), UFZ (DE), UL (LV), ULFFA (SI), UniLU (LU), VITO (BE), VSCHT (CZ), ISCIII (ES), VUA (NL), NILU (NO), UKCEH (UK), BPI (EL), NMBU (NO), SpF (FR)

The work in T4.2 will proceed in the following three projects:

- P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU: this project focuses PFAS and EDCs with the purpose to establish and validate environmental monitoring structures for the long-term work in T4.2. Year 3 will be the last year of this project and include activities in the last three steps of the project cycle, i.e. the monitoring activities (analysis and QA/QC), data analysis and transfer and a feedback mechanism. Based on the monitoring plan (AD4.5) developed in Year 2 and the initial appointment of laboratories for the chemical analysis, the chemical analyses will be completed and reported according to the formats and procedures developed in Years 1 and 2. QA/QC-related work will involve WP9, to ensure inputs as well as harmonization across PARC. The chemical analyses will include, but not be limited to, the following compounds that are also prioritized in T4.1 and by regulatory agencies: 15 phthalates and substitutes, five bisphenols, pesticides (chlorpyrifos, six pyrethroids), and the group of PFAS. In addition, the collection of existing PFAS data for the “baseline part” of the study will be completed. Partners involved: SLU; BfG; NKUA; UFZ; MU; SCIENSANO; AU; INERIS; IVL; EAWAG; INRAE; SYKE; CSIC; CNR-IRSA; ONIRIS; OVAM; UAntwerp; VSCHT; INSERM; BRGM; FISABIO; UBA. The data analysis and transfer will be a continuation of work in Year 2, now with a stronger focus on coherent and harmonized data interpretation involving the Statistical Analysis Group that was set up in Year 2. Furthermore, continued attention will be paid to the long-term data storage under FAIR principles, in collaboration with WP7. Partners involved: UFZ; SLU; NKUA; MU; UBA; CSIC; AU; INERIS (The list of partners involved in this activity may change depending on the development of the work). Finally, lessons learnt will be addressed in the feedback mechanism including all steps of the process. Different perspectives will be included, i.e. from T4.2 partners, project leaders, task co-leads, WP co-leads and collaboration partners outside of WP4, as well as different topics, such as (but not limited to), i) internal organization, ii) timelines, iii) collaboration outside of T4.2, iv) technical challenges, v) expected and real outputs, vi) level of scientific progress, vii) impacts and products. Partners involved: AU; INERIS; CSIC; IVL; NKUA, UBA (The list of partners involved in this activity may change depending on the development of the work). The project will be concluded with a project report (R1; D4.4; M36).

- P4.2.b_Y2_Monitoringframe_AU_INERIS: The project will continue and finalize activities of Year 2 with the aim to establish an impartial, transparent and reproducible framework to select chemicals/matrices/endpoints for monitoring projects as described in D4.1. The aim of the final prioritisation tool is to allow users to select relevant criteria and associated indicators, depending on the specific research or regulatory question that needs to be addressed by monitoring studies. This selection will help prioritise chemicals, endpoints, or environmental matrices for monitoring. Year 3 will focus on finalizing steps in the working groups that have been established for data

sources and evaluation, IT and infrastructure. The prototype will be tested and subsequently refined through small-scale case studies using existing data. These case studies intend to address specific research or regulatory questions as identified in a workshop in the project (15 June 2023) and the overall priority setting process in PARC. Examples could include a watch list of insufficiently monitored chemicals in soil or of insufficiently monitored Persistent Mobile and Toxic (PMT) substances and their relevant environmental matrices. The case studies were defined in Year 2, also considering the collaborative use of prioritization tools with T8.2 and external key players, such as NORMAN. Work in Year 3 will also include potential updates on regulatory needs, as mapped and communicated by T2.1 and contributions to a workshop planned in T8.2 on prioritization activities in PARC and outside of PARC. Following the test of the prototype in case studies, the prioritization scheme will be finalized and implemented as an online tool. The project will be concluded with a final project report (R1; AD4.9; M34). Partners involved: NKUA; UBA; AU; INERIS; UFZ; OVAM; UKCEH; NILU; CSIC; EAWAG; UAntwerp; LNS. (The list of partners involved in this activity may change depending on the development of the work).

- P4.2.c_Y3_HumanExposure_INERIS_AU: This new project will support the T4.1 project (P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO) with personal exposure data to chemicals from environmental samples (e.g. dust, soil). This includes activities with regard to study definition, review of existing knowledge and infrastructure and the design of the monitoring campaign in Year 3. The study definition will include a workshop within WP4 including WPLs and TLs and other interested PARC partners (e.g. from WP7 and WP9) to define the cross-section with T4.1 as well as a standalone T4.2 part of the project, to minimize risks in case of non-matching timelines with the T4.1 General Human Biomonitoring Survey and to ensure a comprehensive environmental monitoring project focusing on relevant non-food media for human exposure. The workshop will also include initial discussions of data use and treatment, to be addressed in depth later in the project, and technical aspects about sampling and analysis. Its outcome will be presented to WP4 leaders in order to discuss potential adjustments and future directions. The scientific literature will be reviewed for the selected compounds and exposure media, also including technical aspects. Catalogues will be established of existing samples for the relevant exposure media, and possibilities of complementary sampling as part of the study will be explored. The design of the monitoring campaign will follow the process developed in the project P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU, with appropriate project-specific adjustments, developing the monitoring strategy, the QA/QC concept (with WP9), procedures for the selection of laboratories and the data flow, including a dedicated workshop. The design phase will be concluded with a detailed monitoring plan. Based on this plan, the project budget for other direct costs (related to the chemical analyses) will be finalized. Besides the close collaboration with T4.1, links with T4.3 will be explored and implemented where relevant. Partners involved: AU; INERIS; LNS; CSTB; VITO; ISCIII; UBA; UAntwerp; MU; JSI; SpF; NILU; BRGM; SLU; CSIC; ISSeP; IVL; NKUA; OVAM; UL; UniLU; UFZ; VSCHT (The list of partners involved in this activity may change depending on the development of the work).

T4.2 will also contribute to relevant horizontal activities in PARC, for example the group on environmental questions (replacing the previously mentioned Ecotoxicology Working Group), the PARC QA/QC core group (initiated by WP9) and potential substance-specific working groups. T4.2 will collaborate with WP7 and WP9 on all activities regarding inventorying and automated retrieval of data from external data sources, as well as storage of monitoring data generated by

T4.2 projects. Furthermore, T4.2 will continue to actively build links to T4.1 and T4.3, facilitated by WP4 co-leaders, for optimized collaboration and long-term integration of human biomonitoring, environmental monitoring and innovative methods.

Task 4.3: Innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys

Co-Leaders: INRAE (FR), VUA (NL)

Partners: ANSES (FR), AU (DK), BfG (DE), BRGM (FR), CEA (FR), CNRS (FR), EAWAG (CH), EHESP (FR), INERIS (FR), INRS (FR), IRFM (IT), JSI (SI), KWR (NL), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), ONIRIS (FR), ORU (SE), SLU (SE), SpF (FR), UAntwerpen (BE), UBA (DE), UBAH (UK), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), UGR (ES), UniLU (LU), UNIVIE (AT), VITO (BE), WR (NL), AUTH (EL), BPI (GR), CNR-IRSA (IT), CSIC (ES), EA (UK), EV-ILVO (NL), FMUL (PT), GCSL (GR), GeoZS (SI), CSIC (ES), IISPV (ES), ISCIII (ES), ISS (IT), IVL (SE), JU (CZ), KUM (DE), LNE (FR), NIB (SI), NIJZ (SI), NILU (NO), NIOM (PL), OFB (FR), STAMI (NO), SU (SE), SYKE (FI), THL (FI), TNO (NL), TTL (FI), UEF (FI), UG-AT (AT), UG-PL (PL), UKCEH (UK), UL (LV), ULFFA (SI), UNIABDN (UK), VSCHT (CZ), WULS-SGGW (PL)

A4.3.1 Transversal actions

Details per project :

- P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02-QA/QC Issues_WR. This project will define minimum quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC) requirements to be used specifically for chemical screening methods based on chromatography coupled to High Resolution Mass Spectrometry (HRMS) and biological effect-directed analysis (EDA) and will be closely linked to the activities in T9.3 (Joint activities – harmonisation, and its project: towards harmonised QA/QC in laboratory testing). In this, existing international standards (e.g. ISO/IEC 17025, OECD GLP) are taken into account and serve as a basis for more detailed and dedicated protocols/procedures (and where appropriate criteria). In addition, there are also links with projects in T4.2. In year 3 a prioritized focus will be operated to work more specifically on (1) the proposal of one (or more) common mixture(s) of QA/QC markers to be used for harmonized method performance assessment purpose and reporting across laboratories with the perspective of a medium term and sustainable objective, and (2) the proposal of operational strategies for improving the semi-quantitative performances typically obtained with these screening approaches with the perspective of increasing the resulting data interpretability and usefulness under a support to policy context [Partners involved: Lead: WR (NL). Partners: INRAE (FR), ANSES (FR), AU (DK), BfG (DE), BRGM (FR), EAWAG (CH), EHESP (FR), INRS (FR), JSI (SI), KWR (NL), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), MUI (AU), ONIRIS (FR), ORU-MTM (SE), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (UA), UBA (DE), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), AUTH (GR), EV-ILVO (BE), CSIC (ES), LNE (FR), WULS (PL)].

- P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03-Early Warning System_SLU. This project will support the development of an early warning system (EWS) in T8.2 by ensuring that data generated by innovative (self) sampling methods in combination with suspect-screening (SS)/non-target screening (NTS) /Effect-direct-analysis (EDA) approaches can be used to identify and to prioritize hazardous substances. In year 3, a reinforced focus will be operated to formulate a set of operational criteria for the categorization of annotated data to be integrated in the EWS format, as a basis to further elaborate a global decision tree aiming at guiding the way from the lab data to the

useful support to policy with regard to these new innovative methodological approaches [Lead: SLU (SE), Participants: INRAE (FR), VUA (NL), ANSES (FR), BRGM (FR), EAWAG (CH), JSI (SI), MUI (AT), ORU-MTM (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), UBA (DE), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), UniLU (LU), AUTH (GR), ISS (IT), NILU (NO)].

- P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04-Data Processing Workflow_EHESP. This project consists in developing a comprehensive, user-friendly and semi-automated pipeline for SS/NTS/EDA related data processing, to be used as a harmonized provision across laboratories contributing to a more rapid and efficient interpretability of the generated data for research and support to policy purposes. In Y3, one main achievement will be the evaluation of several data processing strategies and parametrization of the envisaged pipeline, using 3 real data sets now identified (and made available) as fit for purpose for this objective (covering both the environmental, food and human monitoring fields and their relative specificities, and sufficiently consolidated regarding the QAQC issues). This work will embed more specifically 3 among the established working groups (namely WG1 QAQC, WG2 preprocessing and WG3 annotation tools and databases). In parallel, the elaboration of the envisaged user-friendly viewer expected to finally integrate all the underlying bioinformatics functionalities of the built workflow will be pursued. [Lead: EHESP, Participants: INRAE (FR), MUI (AT), UFZ (DE), ANSES (FR), UniLU (LU), WR (NL), VUA (NL), INRS (FR), ONIRIS (FR), MU (CZ), UCPH (DK), JSI (SI), KWR (DE), UBA(DE)].

A4.3.2 Human samples based proof-of-concepts

Details per project:

- P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE. The objective of this project is to develop a proof-of-concept permitting to assess the performances of selected innovative sampling (silicone wristbands, dried blood spots) and chemical profiling methods (HRMS based SS/NTS and EDA) and elucidating biasing factors in comparison with those of conventional and targeted approaches with a specific focus on perinatal exposure. During Year 3, the results generated by partners involved during the first round of urine, blood and milk analyses (partner self-capacities, second half of Y2 work), as well as the results obtained from the first interlab assay (also performed during the second half of Y2 period) will be examined and digested, as a first cooperative real case study possibly valorisable as such, and as a lesson learned basis for further harmonization through the proposal of updated/refined SOPs. The finalization of the methodological testing phase performed for Silicone WristBands (evaluation of different pre-treatments/clean up procedures), as well as the conception and realization of a similar testing phase for dried blood spots, will be also important components of this Y3 workplan. [Lead: INRAE (FR), Participants: EHESP (FR), CEA (FR), VUA (NL), KUM (DE), UNIVIE (AT), UFZ (DE), WR (NL), JSI (SI), MUI (AT), UAntwerpen (BE), UGR (ES), AU (DK), UniLU (LU), LNS (LU), UNIADBN (UK), MU (CZ), ISPV (ES), VSCHT (CZ), BPI (GR), VITO (BE), CSIC (ES), ISCIII (ES), ISS (ES), SU (SE), AUTH (GR)].

- P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02-Occupational exposure_INRS. The objective of this project is to develop in a tiered approach starting with state of knowledge analyses a proof-of-concept of innovative sampling and HRMS based screening methods for exploring occupational exposure in workplaces to chemicals of emerging concern, as an add-on aligned with the conventional approaches based occupational studies developed under T4.1. One expected output is to assess

the performances of selected innovative sampling (silicone wristbands, dried blood spots) and exposure measurement (HRMS based SS/NTS) related methods, in comparison with those of conventional and targeted approaches. Another goal is to evidence new exposure markers associated to the considered occupational exposures. During Y3, sample collection will be completed and a first round of sample analyses will be performed, based on the SOPs elaborated on Y2. In close connexion with the previous project 4.3.2.a, an interlab assay will be designed and realized as a major piece of method performance assessment and harmonization. This workplan will involve the whole set of partners embedded in the project based on complementary capacities (then contributions) that have been identified on Y2 in term of targeted versus SS measurements and type of samples analyzed.[Lead: INRS (FR), LNS (LU), participants: WULSSGGW (PL), INRAE (FR), MUI (AT), UGR (ES), STAMI (NO), TNO (NL), UAntwerpen (BE), TTL (CZ), MU (CZ), JSI (SI), WR (NL), BPI (GR), AUTH (GR), AEF (FI)].

- P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03-Complementary developments_JSI/UAntwerpen. This new project will elaborate and conduct a set of actions complementary to those already running in the previous project H01 and H02 that cannot address all necessary aspects of innovative method assessment and improvement with regard to their application to human samples. One primary project objective is to evaluate the effectiveness of complementary methodological strategies including orthogonal liquid chromatography separation systems (e.g. HILIC adapted to highly polar compounds/metabolites), alternative sample preparation protocols directly impacting the analytical results (e.g. deconjugation, phospholipid removal), and the use of alternative non-invasive matrices (e.g. hair or saliva), finally leading to potential additional SOPs of interest. A second objective is to start capitalizing on main results and lessons learnt originated from our transversal projects related in particular to QA/QC and data processing issues, as a means to apply those gained outputs to new batches of real samples as an extended illustration of their usefulness. To that end, a direct link will be established to PARC task 4.1 aligned studies to source a set of supporting samples already planned to be analysed through conventional targeted methods for complementing these analyses with innovative screening results. During Y3, the defined workplan includes more specifically the following actions: consolidation of the refined global roadmap and its mutual understanding by all partners, comprehensive synthesis of existing knowledge regarding innovative methodological approaches, encompassing sampling (hair and saliva), sample preparation (deconjugation, phospholipid removal), and instrumental analysis (HILIC chromatography), summarizing known advantages and limitations of those innovative approaches in the specific light of policy priorities within the overarching objectives of PARC's science-to-policy goals. [Lead: JSI (SI), UAntwerpen (BE), Participants: AUTH (GR), BPI (GR), CEA (FR), IISPV (ES), ISCI (ES), ISS (IT), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), SU (SE), UFZ (DE), VITO (BE), VSCHT (CZ), VUA (NL), WR (NL), WULS (PL), INRAE (FR), CNRS (FR), CSIC (ES), INRS (FR), AU (DK)].

A4.3.3 Environment samples based proof-of-concepts

Details per project:

- P4.3.3.a_Y1_E01_Wastewater based epidemiology_UFZ-UBATH. This project addresses both human and environmental exposure, focusing on fingerprinting of wastewater treatment plant influents as a proxy for community wide human exposure assessment and on screening of wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) effluents to assess the release of Chemicals of Emerging

Concern (CECs) into the water cycle. In year 3, we will focus on the delivery of a pan-European study to capture both human and environmental exposures to hazardous chemicals. This will include further development targeted and screening methods including validation for the assessment of human exposure will be continued Partners involved: UFZ (DE), UBATH (UK), MUI (AT), UCPH (DK), EAWAG (CH), KWR (NL), UniLU (LU), INERIS (FR), BfG (DE), BRGM (FR), IRFM (IT), ORU-MTM (SE), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), JSI (SI), WULS-SGGW (PL), JU (CZ), UG-PL (PL).

For the environmental exposure assessment, the prioritization of features and patterns from screening data and the method development for new enrichment tools will be finalised [Partners involved: UFZ (DE), UBATH (UK), MUI (AT), UCPH (DK), EAWAG (CH), ORU-MTM (SE), SLU (SE), JSI (SI), KWR (NL), UniLU (LU), VUA (NL), INERIS (FR), BfG (DE), VITO (BE), BRGM (FR), WULS-SGGW (PL), JU (CZ), MU (CZ), INRAE (FR), OFB (FR), UL (LV), UG-PL (PL).]. The Method for high-throughput EDA [Partners involved: UFZ (DE), UCPH (DK), EAWAG (CH), ORU-MTM (SE), SLU (SE), KWR (NL), VUA (NL), ISS (IT), INERIS (FR), BfG (DE), VITO (BE), UL-FFA (SI), JU (CZ), INRAE (FR), UG-PL (PL)] and the data mining methods and proof of concept on existing datasets [Partners involved: UFZ (DE), UBATH (UK), MUI (AT), UCPH (DK), EAWAG (CH), KWR (NL), UniLU (LU), INERIS (FR), BfG (DE), BRGM (FR)] will be developed. WBE-based human exposure to chemicals will be assessed across Europe via the development of Wastewater Based Epidemiology (WBE) workflows and their application in samples collected across European towns and cities.

- P4.3.3.b_Y2_E02-Sentinel animals_ONIRIS. This project will elaborate and conduct a proof-of-concept demonstrating the potential use of sentinel animal species for capturing human exposure to emerging chemicals along the food chain. During Y3, the selection of relevant marine and terrestrial animal species such as mussels, earthworm or bird eggs to be considered in the project will be fixed based on concerted discussions performed on Y2. The envisaged operational workplan as refined on Y2 will be conducted associating the complementarities of the different partners involved. The identification of a first set of relevant and accessible archived samples and data to be used in the project will be completed, as well as the necessary Material Transfer Agreement (MTA) elaboration, sample shipment, and data sharing from sample owners to receivers. The perspective of developing this project in a support to policy context (e.g., contribution to early warning system through the capture of chemical hazards of concern for ecosystem and human health will be pursued. [Lead : ONIRIS (FR), Participants : ANSES (FR), AU (DK), BfR (DE), Eawag (CH), CSIC (ES), INRAE (FR), JSI (SI), JU (CZ), OFB (FR), ORU-MTM (SE), SU (SE), UFZ (DE), UG-AT (AT), VUA (NL).].

A4.3.4 Food samples based proof-of-concepts

- P4.3.4.a_Y2_F02- Food items exposure_ANSES. This project will elaborate and conduct a set of complementary studies to illustrate the facility of innovative screening approaches (SS/NTS/EDA) to investigate real life complex co-exposures and emerging chemicals from food items. During Y3, the selection of relevant food items to be considered in the project will be fixed based on concerted discussions performed on Y2. The envisaged operational workplan as refined on Y2 will be conducted associating the complementarities of the different partners involved. The identification of a first set of relevant and accessible archived samples and data to

be used in the project will be completed, as well as the necessary MTA elaboration, sample shipment, and data sharing from sample owners to receivers. The perspective of developing this project in a support to policy context (e.g. contribution to early warning system through the capture of chemical hazards of concern associated to food exposure) will be pursued. [Lead: ANSES (FR). Participants: INRAE (FR), VUA (NL), BfG (DE), CEA (FR), CNRS (FR), EAWAG (CH), CSIC (SP), ISS (IT), JSI (SI), MUI (AT), Oniris (FR), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), UL-FFA (SL), VSCHT (CZ), WR (NL), WULS (PL), EV-ILVO (BEL), GCSSL (GR).]

Deliverables:

D4.2. 1st Proof-of-concept assessing the usefulness of innovative (self-) sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches (P4.3.3.a_Y1_EO1-Wastewater based epidemiology_UFZ-UBATH, delayed from M36 to M48), Leader: VUA (M35). New delivery date M48

D4.3 1st Progress report on the general survey (P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO, M52 and P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO, M81) – Leader: VITO (M36)

D4.4 Progress report on ongoing monitoring projects (P4.2.a_Y1_ENVEnvironmentalPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU, M36) – Leader: AU (M36)

Additional Deliverables

AD4.2 Periodic report on analytical methods and measurements for exposure and effect biomarkers (P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO, M52) – Leader ISCIII (new delivery date M36)

AD4.3 Derivation of HBM-GVs – first set (P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_DerivationofHBM-GVs_UBA, M36) – Leader UBA (new delivery date M36)

AD4.8. Report on the occupational exposure in general population surveys: analysis of existing data and recommendations for future general population studies (P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasability_TTL, M29) – Leader TTL (new delivery date M29)

AD4.9 Final report on the prioritization project (P4.2.b_Y2_MonitoringFrame_AU_INERIS, M30) – Leader: AU/INERIS (M34)

AD4.10 Description of the study concept (P4.2.c_Y3_HumanExposure_INERIS_AU, M72) – Leader: INERIS/AU (M36)

AD4.11 Progress report statistical analyses (P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO, M36) - Leader: VITO (M36)

WP N°	WP5	Lead Beneficiary	ANSES/BfR
WP title	Hazard Assessment		
Partner N°	1	1.1	1.2
	1.4	1.5	1.6
	1.8	3.2	3.4
	3.7	3.9	4.1
	4.7	5	5.1
	5.3	8	10.1
	10.2	10.5	14
	15.1	15.2	16
	16.1	16.2	16.3
	16.4	16.6	16.7
	16.8	16.9	16.10
	17	20	20.3
	20.5	24.1	24.2
	25	25.4	25.5
	25.6		

Partner short name	ANSES
PM / partner	75.2
Partner short name	INSERM
PM / partner	197.4
Partner short name	INRAE
PM / partner	70.4
Partner short name	INERIS
PM / partner	8.4
Partner short name	CNRS
PM / partner	23
Partner short name	INRS
PM / partner	12.6
Partner short name	IRSN
PM / partner	2
Partner short name	AIT
PM / partner	12
Partner short name	MUI
PM / partner	21.6
Partner short name	UIBK
PM / partner	14.9
Partner short name	UNIVE
PM / partner	39.3
Partner short name	KU Leuven
PM / partner	10
Partner short name	UAntwerpen
PM / partner	32.2
Partner short name	SCIENSANO
PM / partner	33.3
Partner short name	UGent
PM / partner	14.2
Partner short name	VUB
PM / partner	22
Partner short name	MU
PM / partner	11.5
Partner short name	AU
PM / partner	11
Partner short name	DTU
PM / partner	44.5
Partner short name	SDU
PM / partner	34.4
Partner short name	TTL
PM / partner	1.9
Partner short name	BfG
PM / partner	9.5
Partner short name	UFZ
PM / partner	59.1
Partner short name	BfR
PM / partner	122.9
Partner short name	Fraunhofer
PM / partner	13.9
Partner short name	KIT
PM / partner	11.6
Partner short name	IUF
PM / partner	48
Partner short name	IfADO
PM / partner	12
Partner short name	RPTU
PM / partner	12
Partner short name	TUB
PM / partner	0.6
Partner short name	UKON
PM / partner	7
Partner short name	TiHo
PM / partner	6.8
Partner short name	UHC
PM / partner	9.8
Partner short name	NCPHP
PM / partner	27.7
Partner short name	ISS
PM / partner	26
Partner short name	IRFM
PM / partner	10.3
Partner short name	UMIL
PM / partner	9
Partner short name	LIH
PM / partner	27.6
Partner short name	LIST
PM / partner	4
Partner short name	RIVM
PM / partner	16.4
Partner short name	UL-LACDR
PM / partner	46.7
Partner short name	UU-IRAS
PM / partner	24
Partner short name	VUA
PM / partner	8

Partner number	25.7
Partner short name	WR
PM/partner	9.6
Start	M25
Partner number	25.8
Partner short name	WU-TOX
PM/partner	5.2
Start	End
Partner number	26
Partner short name	NIPH
PM/partner	56.5
Start	M36
Partner number	26.1
Partner short name	IMR
PM/partner	7.5
Partner number	26.2
Partner short name	STAMI
PM/partner	15
Partner number	26.3
Partner short name	NILU
PM/partner	6.5
Partner number	26.4
Partner short name	NIVA
PM/partner	14.2
Partner number	26.5
Partner short name	NMBU
PM/partner	13
Partner number	26.6
Partner short name	NVI
PM/partner	12
Partner number	27.1
Partner short name	IEP-NRI
PM/partner	10.7
Partner number	27.2
Partner short name	UG-PL
PM/partner	18.6
Partner number	29
Partner short name	INSA
PM/partner	40.2
Partner number	29.5
Partner short name	UAVR
PM/partner	6.5
Partner number	31
Partner short name	JSI
PM/partner	7
Partner number	31.2
Partner short name	NIB
PM/partner	33.5
Partner number	31.3
Partner short name	NIC
PM/partner	37.5
Partner number	31.4
Partner short name	ULFFA
PM/partner	12
Partner number	31.5
Partner short name	MFUM
PM/partner	0.3
Partner number	33
Partner short name	CSIC
PM/partner	77
Partner number	33.2
Partner short name	UNAV
PM/partner	28.5
Partner number	33.4
Partner short name	UPO
PM/partner	12
Partner number	34
Partner short name	ISCIll
PM/partner	44.5
Partner number	34.5
Partner short name	IISPV
PM/partner	43
Partner number	35.2
Partner short name	KI
PM/partner	1
Partner number	35.6
Partner short name	SU
PM/partner	6.5
Partner number	35.10
Partner short name	SLU
PM/partner	34
Partner number	35.12
Partner short name	UU
PM/partner	16
Partner number	36
Partner short name	AUTH
PM/partner	21
Partner number	37
Partner short name	BPI
PM/partner	46.1
Partner number	41
Partner short name	EAWAG
PM/partner	23
Partner number	54
Partner short name	EA
PM/partner	0.5
Partner number	58
Partner short name	UINABDN
PM/partner	0.2
Partner number	59
Partner short name	UOB
PM/partner	18

Objectives

The main goal of WP5 is to focus on Hazard Assessment (HA) for human and environmental health on three different directions: fill data gaps (task 5.1), develop and/or improve methodologies for HA to progress towards NGRA (task 5.2) and to work on Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs), quantitative systems toxicology and physiologically based toxicokinetic (PBTK) modelling (task 5.3). The specific objectives of WP5 for year 3 are:

- Task 5.1: Collection of data is the core aspect of the work in Y3, for human health (prioritised compounds are Bisphenol A (BPA) alternatives/analogues and alternaria toxins and enniatins) and the environmental health (prioritised compounds are BPA alternatives, including mixtures, cyanotoxins and mycotoxins).
- Task 5.2: The focus of our work will be on advancing and refining innovative methodologies for hazard identification. In human health, we will continue focusing on five different endpoints and effects: immunotoxicity, non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, (developmental) neurotoxicity, endocrine disruption (with a focus on thyroid) and metabolic disruption. In environment, we will be creating New approach methodologies (NAMs) in four primary areas employing i) *in silico* and modelling tools, ii) invertebrate animal models, iii) vertebrate models, and newly iv) complex microbial community.
- Task 5.3: The objectives for Y3 are to keep fostering the different core or extended groups

established in Y1 and Y2 that are relevant for the activity of this task: omics, AOPs, bioinformatics, effect markers, PBTK, and *in vivo/in vitro* mode of action. We will use and update when needed our inventory and mapping established in Y1 and Y2 of available knowledge, reference *in vivo*/human datasets, activities and models in systems biology, PBTK and AOP frameworks and prioritising additional studies. We will also continue the studies initiated in Y1 and Y2 to characterise coregulated gene networks, for already published AOPs (to make them quantitative) and linking chemicals to available AOPs, linking omics data to human physiopathology, generating high quality data.

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 5.1: Toxicity testing addressing data gaps of concern

Co-leaders A5.1.1: NIPH (NO), INSA (PT), Co-leader A5.1.2: BPI (EL)

Participants:

Activity 5.1.1: ANSES (FR), BfR (DE), BPI (EL), CNRS (FR), Fraunhofer-IBMT (DE), IMR (NO), INRAE (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), INSERM (FR), ISCIII (ES), ISS (IT), LIH (LU), MUI (AT), NIB (SI), NILU (NO), NIPH (NO), NVI (NO), Sciensano (BE), SDU (DK), STAMI (NO), TTL (FI), TUB (DE), ULFFA (SI), UMIL (IT), UNAV (ES), UNIVIE (AT), WU-TOX (NL)

Activity 5.1.2: BPI (EL), EAWAG (CH), IEP-NRI (PL), IISPV (ES), INERIS (FR), INRAE (FR), NIB (SI) NIVA (NO), SDU (DK), SLU (SE), SU (SE), UAVR (PT), UFZ (DE), UG-PL (PL), UGent (BE), UU (SE), Cefas-Defra (UK), UOB (UK).

A5.1.1 Closing data gaps of concern for human health.

We look forward to continuing the lab-based activities in year 3 and to having time to discuss and interpret the results and disseminate our findings to regulatory EU and national agencies (e.g EFSA, ECHA, EMA) to ensure regulatory uptake of the results. Results will also be shared with some institutions which showed interests in these activities (Health Canada, Ontario University and RIVM).

For year 3 is planned the publication of the results in peer-reviewed journals, presentation of data in conferences, meetings (e.g. SETAC, WP5 annual on site meeting), and the preparation of new projects.

In Year 3 the project P5.1.1.c_Y3_TG+EnnB1_ANSES “TG+ enniatin B1” will start.

Details per project:

- Project P5.1.1.a_Y1_Toxins_BfR_UNIVIE: The enniatins A, A1, B and B1 as well as Beauvericin have testing priority. Alternariol, Alternariol monomethylether, Alvertoxin I, Altenuene, Tentoxin and Tenuazonic acid are among the prioritized compounds for the *Alternaria* study program.

The *in vitro* studies agreed upon natural toxins (enniatis and *Alternaria* toxins) to close data gaps will include genotoxic, endocrine and immunotoxic effects, as well as other potential endpoints/target organs. Overall, the studies will provide needed *in vitro* data and identify critical toxicological effects of enniatis and *Alternaria* toxins. Experimental work will start for some test substances in late Y2, and for some substances in early Y3 due to the sourcing process including

the procurement process that was very time consuming. Due to the delays in obtaining the test substances a 1-year extension of the project length has been required in Y2, therefore, the planned ending date for this project is now M48.

We are in contact with the scientific officer from the feed and contaminants unit from EFSA regarding the availability of data on enniatins and beauvericin program since EFSA is searching for new data to possibly update its current opinion. We are in contact with the OECD AOP project to exchange information.

[Participants: BfR, UNIVIE, NIB, SCIENSANO, INSA, UNAV, ISS, BPI, INRS, NVI, STAMI, NIPH, IMR, ANSES, WU-TOX, Fraunhofer-IBMT, TUB]

- P5.1.1.b_Y1_BPA_HumTox_BfR: The test substances for the set of *in vitro* studies are: BPZ, BPE, BPP, BPAP, BPPH, and BPS-MAE. The WP5 experts also agreed on using BPA as a reference substance and for metabolism halogenated analogues as TBBPA and Pergafast 201).

We have a delay, due to the time taken in hiring the personnel and acquiring the BPA alternatives in a centralized manner and are currently requesting an extension of 18 months for this project.

Results will be shared with Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic (PBPK) modelers in 5.3. We are in contact with both ECHA, RIVM and Health Canada/Ontario University to avoid duplication of efforts. Contact has been made with the EURION cluster regarding endocrine disruption studies.

Y3 experimental work for each of the five endpoints:

1. Endocrine effects: *In vitro* Human H295R Steroidogenesis Assay (OECD TG 456) (ISS), effect of BPA and alternatives in thyroid hormone synthesis key events using *in vitro* test (under consideration by EURL ECVAM (ISCIII), and analysis of the data by assay (i.e., calculation EC50 and benchmark dose (BMD) values, fold changes) (ISS, INRAE, ISCIII).

2. Developmental Neurotoxicity: *In vitro* screening of cellular effects of BPA and BPA alternatives (CNRS, INRAE), molecular analyses for the identification of relevant biomarkers (CNRS, INRAE, LIH), epigenetic analyses for the identification of relevant biomarkers (LIH), and data analyses, identification of biomarkers, proposition of new AOPs / implementing existing AOPs (CNRS, INRAE, LIH).

3. Immunotoxicity: Identification of immune cell targets and effects of bisphenols on immune functions (UMIL), investigation of the relationship between bisphenols immunotoxicity and their effect on the inflammation-induced tryptophan breakdown and related immunobiochemical pathways (MUI), to investigate the relationship between bisphenols immunotoxicity and their effect on the glucocorticoid system (ULFFA), and to provide new mechanistic data for AOP development, by evaluating the effects of BPA analogues on the intracellular calcium homeostasis of both resting and stimulated immune cells (ISS).

4. Carcinogenicity: *In vitro* test as foreseen in the battery of genotoxicity testing (INSA, ISS), *in vitro* genotoxicity of BPA and BPA alternatives and relevant metabolites will be assessed on hepatic 2D and/or 3D (spheroids) cell models developed from HepG2 using micronucleus, comet and transcriptomic assays (collaboration with T5.2a) (INSA, IBMT, NILU), non-genotoxic carcinogenicity of BPA and BPA alternatives will be assessed by Bhas 42 cell transformation

assay (following OECD guidance document) (INRS, INSA, ISCI, TTL, NILU).

5. Metabolism bioactivation routes and kinetics: *In vitro* study of the metabolic fate and bioactivation pathways of key BPA alternatives (INRAE) and absorption studies with intestinal models as input of PBK modelling (ISS).

[Participants: ISS, UMIL, INRAE, TTL, ULFFA, MUI, ISCI, INRS, Fraunhofer-IBMT, CNRS, LIH, SDU, NILU, INSA]

For both projects 5.1.1a and 5.1.1b, we are in close contact with partners within PARC, especially 5.2, 5.3 and WP6 to exchange data.

- P5.1.1.c_Y3_TG+ EnnB1_ANSES: The purpose of this project will be to fill an *in vivo* data gap on Enniatin B1 identified by EFSA by conducting a TG408 study. The tissues originating from this study will also be used for further analyses. In parallel, the work on Enniatin performed on NAMs will increase regulatory confidence in the corresponding approach. A 5-d study may also be conducted using enniatin B1, as proof of concept of using transcriptomic data to estimate health-based guidance values.

[Participants: ANSES, BfR, NIPH, INSA, INSERM, TUB, UNAV]

A5.1.2 Toxicity assessment addressing data gaps of concern (Environment)

Details per project:

- P5.1.2.a_Y1_NaturalToxinsAqua_Ugent: Mixtures of natural toxins, including both cyanotoxins and mycotoxins, will be tested during Y3. Selection of mixtures will be based on results of the toxicity testing with single compounds carried out in Y1 and Y2. Specifically, the following OECD tests will be carried out with mixtures of natural toxins:

- (1) OECD 243: *Lymnaea stagnalis* Reproduction Test (SLU)
- (2) OECD 211: *Daphnia magna* reproduction test (UGent)
- (3) In close collaboration with (2), acute exposure experiment on the same mixtures with *Daphnia* will be conducted to assess behaviour and transcriptomics. (UoB)
- (4) OECD 201: Freshwater Alga and Cyanobacteria, Growth Inhibition Test (*Chlorella vulgaris*) (UAVR)
- (5) OECD: harpacticoid copepod development and reproduction test with *Nitocra Spinipes* (UGent).

Exposure scenarios for invertebrates will be conducted through water exposures to pure toxins or dietary exposure of mixture of toxin-producing strains ordered from certified culture collections (e.g., same strains as used for individual testing).

[Participants: SLU, UGent, UAVR, UOB]

- P5.1.2.b_Y1_BPAalternatives_BPI_MU: Toxicity testing of bisphenol alternatives selected during Y1 on certain organisms has been started and will continue during Y3. It is noted that the experimental work started with a delay mainly due to time-consuming procedures followed for chemicals order (centralized order for all PARC partners) and difficulties faced by several partners in hiring personnel. Therefore 6 more months of the project's duration is requested. A

list of 26 assays (OECD TG, ASTM and ISO) will be conducted by the involved partners covering a wide range of organisms (e.g., fish, aquatic invertebrates, alga, marine bacteria, earthworms, soil microorganisms, xenopus, C. elegans) and effects (e.g., acute effects, effects on reproduction and on endocrine system). In Y3 we will mainly focus on experiments with mixtures. The mixtures to be tested will be selected based on the results of tests with individual substances (carried out during Y1 & Y2). In addition, the mixtures will be selected considering also the occurrence of bisphenols in different environmental compartments (i.e., surface water, soil, sediment) as revealed by reviewing the available literature data (review article will be published in Y2) and the results from monitoring activities that will be carried out in the frame of PARC WP4.

[Participants: BPI, SLU, IISPV, SDU, INERIS, NIB, IEP-NRI, UU, UG-PL, UAVR, EAWAG, NIVA, UFZ, SU, Cefas-Defra]

Task 5.2: Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling

Co-leaders A5.2.1: DTU (DK), VUB (BE), Co-leader A5.2.2: MU (CZ)

Participants:

Activity 5.2.1: AIT (AT), ANSES (FR), BfR (DE), DTU (DK), IfADo (DE), INRAE (FR), INSA (PT), INSERM (FR), IRFM (IT), ISCIII (ES), IUF (DE), LIH (LU), LIST (LU), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), NIB (SI), NILU (NO), NIPH (NO), NMBU (NO), NCPHP (HU), RIVM (NL), SDU (DK), TiHo (DE), UAntwerpen (BE), UFZ (DE), UG-PL (PL), UIBK (AT), RPTU (DE), UKON (DE), UL-LACDR (NL), ULFFA (SI), UNAV (ES), UOB (UK), UU (SE), UU-IRAS (NL), VUA (NL), VUB (BE), WR (NL)

Activity 5.2.2: BfG (DE), BPI (EL), EAWAG (CH), IISPV (ES), INERIS (FR), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), NIB (SI), NIC (SI), NIVA (NO), SDU (DK), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), UFZ (DE), UG-PL (PL), UPO (ES), CSIC (ES), INRAE (FR)

A5.2.1 Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling

In the preceding year, after having installed the project and recruited skilled personnel, emphasis was primarily on chemical selection and initiating lab work. Looking forward to the upcoming year, priorities will pivot towards the substantive development of wet lab operations and the associated generation and dissemination of results.

Details per project:

- P5.2.1.a_Y1_NGTXCs_INRAE: The development of tests that can identify tissue and substance specific effects related to distinct aspects of non-genotoxic carcinogenesis will be continued in Y3. In general, given the distinct throughput possibilities of the various test systems, at least two and up to 10 substances will be tested for the 5 different MoA selected (proliferation, cytotoxicity inducing regenerative proliferation, nuclear receptor activation, inflammation and changes in cellular morphology indicative for cell migration). The data will be compiled and analysed to identify specific Mode of toxic Action (MoA) than can be detected by different assays, including a comparison of the minimal concentration needed to detect a significant effect. The

compilation and analysis of the data will reveal the need for optimization of assays and facilitate the development of an efficient testing battery. The set-up of novel NAMs for identified gaps in the assessment of non-genotoxic carcinogens (NGTXC) will be initiated.

[Participants: INRAE, BfR, ANSES, INSERM, NIB, UL-LACDR, UNAV, IRFM, RIVM, RPTU, NILU, MU]

- P5.2.1.b_Y1_MD-EDC_BfR: An extended spectrum of substances from the priority families has been assessed in Y2 and will continue in Y3, including major metabolites and breakdown molecules, allowing further MoA exploration, as well as AOP and read-across development synergies. Exploration of nuclear receptor (NR)-driven effects will continue focusing on the characterization of prioritized BPA alternatives (BPZ, BPE, BPP, BPAP, BPPH, and BPS-MAE). The WP5 experts also agreed on using BPA as a reference substance and for metabolism halogenated analogues as TBBPA and Pergafast interaction with the nuclear receptors PPAR γ , PXR, CAR, and RXR α using stable reporter cell lines and biophysical approaches (crystallization, 3D structure determination). Similar to Y2, in Y3 several articles characterizing the interaction of bisphenols and their halogenated analogues with different nuclear receptors will be written. Developments in the human mesenchymal stem cells models (2D/3D), as well as with BPA alternatives effects on adipocyte (human, murine) and in zebrafish models will continue in Y3. The effects of selected substances on triglyceride accumulation in liver cells will be analysed and work on an *in vitro* phospholipidosis assay using human liver cells will be continued. Moreover, involvement of mTOR signaling in metabolic disruption will be further explored, as well as the potential of mTOR-related assays to detect MDC.

Due to some delays in the overall project progress in the initial phase of the project as e.g. resulting from difficulties in recruiting personnel, a 1-year extension of the project is necessary to complete the envisaged tasks.

Actions /Experiments:

1. Structural and functional study - Extended assessment of Nuclear Receptor (NR) activities testing (PPAR γ , PXR, CAR and RXR α) using transfected cell lines, and application of this testing strategy to major BPA alternatives, metabolites and other compounds (INSERM).
2. *In vitro* assays for screening MBD using different cell types established and tools for MTOR signaling characterisation (BfR, UIBK, UU-IRAS, UFZ, UU, IfaDo).
3. Whole organism - Development of early life stage zebrafish metabolic disruption test (UAntwerpen).

[Participants: INRAE, BfR, INSERM, IfaDo, UU-IRAS, UAntwerpen, UU, UIBK, UFZ]

- P5.2.1.c_Y1_EDThDisruption_DTU: Characterization of the molecular mechanisms and assays that can be exploited for NAM -Thyroid Hormone System Disruptors (THSD)- testing will be continued in Y3. Already initiated *in vitro* and *in silico* assay developments will continue. An OATP3A1 overexpressing cell line will be tested for its capacity to assess compounds interfering with TH transport across the blood-cerebrospinal fluid barrier (BCSFB). In addition, the currently established *in vitro* choroid plexus organoid model will be further characterized and used to test suspect EDCs for their capacity to interfere with TH transport across the BCSFB. Quantitative

Structure Activity Relationship (QSAR) development of the models for inhibition of MCT8, DEHAL1, TTR and TRHR will be finalized and applied to screen a large inventory of chemical substances, including 13,406 REACH-registered substances. Data analysis of data from the *in vivo* multi-organ transcriptomics will be performed. A toxicogenomic comparison between *in vivo* effects in the developing rat liver and in the human stem cell-based hepatocyte *in vitro* assay will be performed to assess cross-species and assay translatability. The evolutionary conservation of the Thyroid Hormone System (THS) axis will be further characterized to make better use of non-human NAMs to inform on human health risks. The literature review to extrapolate THSD from fish/amphibians to mammals/humans is ongoing. The feasibility and appropriateness for developing a bisphenols case study will be assessed based on literature data availability.

[Participants: DTU, VUB, BfR, SDU, UAntwerpen, VUA, ISCIII, INSERM]

- P5.2.1.d_Y1_Immunotox_Inserm: In year 3, based on the first results from the set-up of *in vitro* systems and the *in vivo* experiments, work on developing specific NAMs will continue. In Y3, work will focus on pre-selected most relevant methods, compared to Y2 where the pre-screening was performed.

In the different *in vitro* systems relevant for respiratory immunotoxicity, NAM concept will be finalized and characterized for their usefulness and limitations to come to a testing strategy (MUI, NCPHP, RIVM, LIST). To determine common markers of immunosuppression and response to vaccination, studies in human, animal and in different primary cells and cell lines will be further combined to identify the most relevant *in vitro* or *ex vivo* system for human health (INSERM, NIPH, INSA, LIH).

Studies on NAMs and assays for immunotoxic events by (mixtures of) model or priority compounds including mycotoxins and bisphenols (table below) will be continued to support the build-up of AOPs and IATAs (UL-FFA, UFZ, WR).

Biocides	chloramine-T, piperazine
BPA alternatives	BPA, BPS-MAE, BPZ, BPB, TCBPA, BPAP, Bis-Z, BPPH, BPG, BPS-MPE, PF201, BTUM, BPE, BPP
Mycotoxins	Deoxynivalenol, fumonisin B1, aflatoxin B1, enniatin A, A1, B, B1, ochratoxin A, zearalenone, alternariol, tenuazonic acid, tentoxin
Therapeutic substances	dexamethasone, chloroquine, sirulimus (rapamycin), cyclosporine A, tacrolimus (FK506), doramapimod, Hydrocortisone, dapsone
Perfluorinated substances	PFAS, PFOA, PFOS
Other	BP3, MIKB, B[a]P

The report released by ECHA (Key areas of Regulatory Challenge) in June 2023 mentions DIT (Developmental Immunotoxicity) as a priority for the development of related NAM to assess the potential hazard of substances. Some discussions have been engaged (intra and inter projects through PARC) and will continue to include DIT in the frame of this project. A meeting is planned in spring 2024 with interested partners as well as ECHA and CAAT. This project will be delayed by 12 months due to recruitment difficulties. The new end date of this project is M48.

[Participants: INSERM, NIPH, MUI, NCPHP, RIVM, UU-IRAS, ULFFA, INSA, UFZ, WR, LIH, LIST]

- P5.2.1.e_Y1_DNT-ANT_UFZ_IUF_NIPH: The 96 chemicals selected together with EC_JRC test set (positive/negative controls) will be sourced, purchased, and distributed by the JRC to all participants (for these reasons, 12-month extension has been requested). The chemical test set is challenging and of extreme importance as highlighted by ECHA (Key areas of Regulatory Challenge, June 2023).

In year 3, partners with developed DNT (Developmental Neurotoxicity) or ANT (Adult Neurotoxicity) NAMs will start testing chemicals. Partners with less well developed NAMs will continue to optimize them, using positive control chemicals and a subset of reference compounds. In addition, a large group of partners are evaluating NAMs to identify the applicability domain from a mode-of-action perspective. Year 3 will center on data generation using references chemicals from the EC-JRC using partner -specific NAMs (see Project Description in the Annex). If the extension is granted, following data generation, a comparative study on performance, sensitivity, specificity, and redundancy will be performed. Improved characterization of the models for the presence and function of transporters/receptors is planned. Two new partners joined: BfR (DE) and UOB (UK). BfR will develop a complex, *ex vivo* cultured zebrafish model as an intermediate model between the human in vitro NAMs and zebrafish embryo functional assays that evaluate behavior, startle responses, learning, and memory.

[Participants: INSERM, UU, NIPH, IUF, UKON, RIVM, UFZ, ISCIII, TiHo, AIT, NMBU, UG-PL, UOB, TiHO, BfR].

In Y3, a transversal project focusing on regulatory readiness of NAMs will be initiated. This project aims to facilitate the uptake of the NAMs being generated in WP5 by assessing their readiness, supporting NAMs developers with, for instance, SOPs development (GIVIMP workshops), and working on the alignment with AOPs / IATAs being developed in PARC. The objectives of this project can be broken down as follows:

1. Expand ReadEDtest to analyse methods for other endpoints
2. Independent peer-review of readiness of NAM developed in WP5 (SOPs, results of ReadEDtest...)
3. Support validation activities for willing partners
4. Writing a manuscript based on the position paper, further guidance and respective deliverables.

This project will be coordinated by ANSES and main contributors will be BfR, and INSERM (more partners will be involved as the project moves forward).

A5.2.2 Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling for Environmental Toxicology / Ecotoxicology

The collection of state-of-the-art information helped us to identify gaps in toxicity testing (i.e. BPA alternatives that are overlooked in toxicity testing, and gaps in toxicity testing) and finally to define a strategy for the development and optimization of NAMs and the selection of suitable BPA

alternative candidates, which will be continued in Year 3. It is anticipated that completed assays will be delivered and shared through publications.

In addition, a new partner INRAE (FR) will join the project from Y3-Y4 with a proposal of new research area: methods focused on complex microbial community (development of high throughput metabolomics in aquatic periphyton).

Further, the partner CSIC (ES) will join the project (Y3-Y4) focusing on the development of new *Daphnia magna* methodologies to determine cardiotoxicity, neurotoxicity and metabolic disruptive potency, enhancing zebrafish liver (ZFL) spheroids for toxicity testing and, adapting the methodology for assessing gait impairment in zebrafish.

The activity A5.2.2 in Y3 will be closely aligned with other PARC tasks, specifically with T5.3 (data derived in A5.2.2 will be offered for AOP development / modeling), T6.1 and T6.2 (building NAMs confidence for regulatory purposes), WP7 (data management) and WP9 to identify synergies.

[Participants: BfG, BPI, EAWAG, IISPV, INERIS, MU, MUI, NIB, NIC, NIVA, SDU, SLU, UAntwerpen, UFZ, UG-PL, UPO, CSIC, INRAE, CNRS]

Task 5.3: Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs

Co-leaders: UL-LACDR (NL), SCIENSANO (BE), INSERM (FR), Fraunhofer-ITEM (DE)

Participants:

Activity 5.3.1 and 5.3.3: AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), IISPV (ES), INSERM (FR), IRFM (IT), ISCIII (ES), ISS (IT), KIT (DE), MUI (AT), NIPH (NO), NCPHP (HU), Sciensano (BE), UFZ (DE), UGent (BE), UG-PL (PL), UIBK (AT), UL-LACDR (NL), UMIL (IT), UNIABDN (UK), UOB (UK), WR (NL)

Activity 5.3.2: ACES/SU(SE), AU (DK), AUTH (EL), BfG (DE), BPI (EL), Cefas-Defra (UK), DTU (DK), IISPV (ES), INSERM (FR), IRSN (FR), ISS (IT), KI (SE), KIT (DE), KU-Leuven (BE), LIST (LU), MUI (AT), NILU (NO), NIPH (NO), NCPHP (HU), Sciensano (BE), SDU (DK), UAntwerpen (BE), UGent (BE), UG-PL (PL), UHC (DE), UIBK (AT), UL-LACDR (NL), UMIL (IT), UNIVIE (AT), WR (NL)

Activity 5.3.4: ANSES (FR), AUTH (EL), Cefas-Defra (UK), EA (UK), ETHZ (CH), Fraunhofer-ITEM (DE), IISPV (ES), INERIS (FR), INSERM (FR), ISCIII (ES), ISS (IT), NIPH (NO), NVI (NO), UFZ (DE), UHC (DE), UNIVIE (AT), WR (NL), WU-TOX (NL), UNISANTE (CH), STAMI (NO)

A5.3.1 Prioritized NAM-based mechanistic hazard characterisation & A5.3.3 Translation to human pathophysiology

A5.3.1 and A5.3.3 (Systems toxicology approaches for mechanism-based chemical safety assessment) were combined in a single project for coherence purposes.

Details per project:

- P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR: In Y3, partners will continue working on the 3 identified case-studies (how systems toxicology can contribute to CS1 – Read-across, CS2 – ab initio studies, CS3 – temporal responses). In particular CS1 is on one hand investigating the use of omics to support chemical grouping together with structural and molecular features, and on the other hand developing tools to support the partitioning of chemicals into tissues. CS1 is focusing on PFAS and BPA alternative datasets. CS2 is carrying out a comparison on how different systems toxicology approaches identify and assess hazard, developing methods to connect systems toxicology to the AOP framework and providing tools to connect to human pathophysiology. CS2 is focusing on renal toxicity induced by cisplatin. CS3 aims to define best practices for time course experiments in systems toxicology, in particular how different methods compare, which time points are particularly relevant and how those map to AOP in terms of early and late KEs. In Y3 we will gather data from other projects to apply the methods developed and compare in each CS to additional endpoints and area of interests. Additionally, all case studies will be discussed with regulatory agencies and relevant stakeholders to present the progress and obtain feedback. This project will be delayed by 12 months due to recruitment difficulties and delays with the start of the case studies. The new end date of this project is M48.

[Participants: UGent, MUI, ISCIII, INSERM, ISS, UL-LACDR, BPI, KIT, NCPHP, WR, Sciensano, NIPH, UNIABDN, UFZ, UG-PL, IRFM, UIBK, UMIL, AUTH, UOB and IISPV]

A5.3.2 AOP development based on integration of in vivo and in vitro data sets

Details per project:

- P5.3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_Inserm: In year 3, the core group of this project (CG) will continue to develop new tools supporting AOP development, in particular artificial intelligence (AI) and text mining tools. The CG will support the work of the Specialty groups (SGs) and help them in the building of new AOPs or further developing incomplete AOPs. Following the workshop organized by the CG in Y2, closer interactions are foreseen with European and international organizations involved in AOP development such as OECD, JRC, US-EPA and European agencies. The deliverable D5.3 will continue the inventory of available AOPs to be (further) developed (based on AD5.5): SG1 will focus on AOPs in the fields of respiratory sensitization, immunosuppression and non-genotoxic carcinogenesis and will collaborate with P5.2.1.d and P5.2.1.a. SG2 will focus on AOPs in the fields of endocrine disruption and metabolism and will collaborate with P5.2.1b and P5.2.1c. SG3 will focus on AOPs in the field of Neurotoxicity and will collaborate with P5.2.1e. The SG1 (Immunotoxicity), SG2 (Endocrine and metabolic disruption), SG3 (Neurotoxicity) and the Effect Marker Group (EMG) are structured into subgroups corresponding to the themes of SG1, SG2 and SG3 as well as a subgroup on epigenetics. Each group meets every 6 weeks on average to monitor the progress of the work. New AOPs or improved AOPs are submitted to AOPwiki. A close collaboration with AOPwiki is foreseen. It has to be noted that all CG partners are also involved in the SGs so that their technical support is made easier. Most of the T.5.2 projects will be delayed, and as 5.3.2.a relies on them for data, it will be delayed as well. As such, its new end date is M48.

[Participants: ACES or SU, AU, AUTH, BfG, BPI, DTU, IISPV, Inserm, IRSN, ISS, KI, KIT, KU-Leuven, LIST, MUI, NILU, NIPH, NCPHP, UG-PL, SDU, Sciensano, UAntwerpen, UGent, UHC, UIBK, UL-LACDR, UMIL, UNIVIE, WR and Cefas-Defra].

A5.3.4 PBK models and quantitative systems toxicology

Details per project:

- P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Kinetics_Fraunhofer: Seven case studies are ongoing in year 3 of the project, namely 01- Xenobiotic metabolism in human_microbiome; 02- bioavailability of PFAS; 03_Isoform-specific metabolism in liver; 04- tiered testing strategy for inhalable compounds; 05-PBK modeling of the blood brain barrier; 06- bioavailability of Alternaria toxins and 07-bioavailability of Enniatins. The zebrafish case study (01b) will be discontinued because UFZ had to reallocate budgets in PARC. In general, this will not significantly affect the core objectives of Activity 5.3.4. Furthermore, ETHZ will test some zebrafish microbiome samples provided by UFZ and compare them with the human microbiome samples under the umbrella of CS 01a. In the second half of this project, a new case (08) study will be started to develop *in vitro* ADME models to predict the placental uptake of compounds. In addition, case study 09 will integrate new mechanisms of metabolic disruption from P5.2.1.b_MD-ED and link them to PBK modelling.

It is planned that most of the *in vitro* testing of compound specific ADME data will be completed early in year 3, although some case studies, particularly those on natural toxins, are experiencing delays due to problems in the procurement of substances and recruitment of staff. In year 3, the case studies without delays will spend most of the time on the integration of this *in vitro* ADME data into the PBK models, the *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation and the uncertainty and sensitivity analysis of the PBK models. A 12-month extension of the project duration is required to complete the actions planned by those partners who are behind in generating data required for the PBK modelling.

[Participants: UNISANTE, ANSES, ETHZ, IISPV, INERIS, Inserm, ISCIII, ISS, Fraunhofer-ITEM, NVI, UKK/UoC, WR, WU-TOX, EA, AUTH, Cefas-Defra and NIPH, STAMI, UNIVIE, UIBK]

Deliverables:

D5.2 New PBK Models report (P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Kinetics_Fraunhofer, delayed from M36 to M48) – Leader: Fraunhofer-ITEM (M24) (New delivery date M36)

D5.4 1st closing data gaps report – Leader: ANSES (M36)

(P5.1.1.a_Y1_Toxins_BfR_UNIVIE, delayed from M36 to M48; 5.1.1.b_Y1_BPA_HumTox_BfR, delayed from M36 to M54; P5.1.1.c_Y3_TG+ EnnB1_ANSES, M60;

P5.1.2.a_Y1_NaturalToxinsAqua_UGent, M36; P5.1.2.b_Y1_BPAalternatives_BPI_MU, delayed from M42 to M48)

D5.5 2nd New approach methodologies report – Leader: BfR (M36). New delivery date M48

(P5.1.1.c_Y3_TG+ EnnB1_ANSES, M60; P5.1.2.b_Y1_BPAalternatives_BPI_MU, delayed from M42 to M48; P5.2.1.a_Y1_NGTXCs_INRAE, M60; P5.2.1.b_Y1_MD-EDC_INRAE, delayed from M36 to M48; P5.2.1.c_Y1_EDThDisruption_DTU M48;

P5.2.1.d_Y1_Immunotox_Inserm delayed from M36 to M48, P5.2.1.e_Y1_DNT-ANT_UFZ_IUF_UU delayed from M36 to M48)

Additional Deliverables

No additional deliverables are foreseen for year 3.

WP N°	WP6	Lead Beneficiary	RIVM/KEMI
WP title	Innovation in regulatory risk assessment		
Partner N°	1		
Partner short name	ANSES		
PM/partner	78		
	13.2	INSERM	
	33.9	INRAE	
	2	INERIS	
	3	INRS	
	10.3	ONIRIS	
	5.5	IRSN	
	14.5	OFB	
	0.5	EHESP	
	3	EAA	
	17.3	AGES	
	3	MUI	
	1.5	UNIVIE	
	35.7	VITO	
	0.9	OVAM	
	15	ISSEP	
	17.5	UAntwerpen	
	63.6	SCIENSANO	
	15	UGent	
	13.5	VUB	
	1	MOH-CY/SGL	
	61.4	MU	
	10.6	AU	
	24.5	DTU	
	22	REGIONH-GE	
	7	UCPH	
	4	SDU	
	18	UT	
	3	SYKE	
	9.2	TTL	
	3	Tukes	
	30.4	UBA	
	31.3	UFZ	
	8.5	UOS	

Partner N°	16.1		
Partner short name	Fraunhofer-IBMT/IME		
PM/partner	7.5		
	12	IfAdo	
	31	RPTU	
	2.3	UI	
	30	ISS	
	7.8	ICPS	
	2.7	IRFM	
	6.5	IUSS	
	3	UMIL	
	1	UNIPD	
	2	RSU	
	3.5	LSMU	
	6.5	LNS	
	9	LIST	
	52.8	RIVM	
	3.7	KWR	
	8.1	TNO	
	23.3	UL-LACDR	
	26.2	UU-IRAS	
	9.5	VUA	
	6.5	WR	
	24	WU-TOX	
	7	SRU	
	23.6	NIPH	
	27.5	STAMI	
	2.5	NILU	
	11.4	NIVA	
	20.4	NIOM	
	9.8	IEP-NRI	
	16.5	UG-PL	
	5	FMUL	
	13.3	INSA	
	4.1	ENSP	
	36	UC	
	11.2	UAVR	
	5.4	JSI	
	7.8	GeZS	

Partner N°	32	
Partner short name	NIJZ	
	32.1	OI
	32.2	NLZOH
	33	CSIC
	33.3	UGR
	34	ISCIH
	34.1	EASP
	34.3	FINBA
	34.5	IIPV
	34.7	UCLM
	35.1	UGOT
	35.2	KI
	35.3	ULUND
	35.4	ORU
	35.5	RISE
	35.6	SU
	35.7	KEMI
	35.8	IVL
	35.10	SLU
	36	AUTH
	37	BPI
	38	FOPH
	40	UNISANTE
	41	EAWAG
	44	FOEN
	45	USI
	46	UNIBAS
	49	EFSA
	53	UKCEH
	54	EA
	59	UOB
	60	UCL

PM/partner	18.5	5.5	0.1	54	5.5	22	0.5	25.3	34.5	36	25.2	8.8	2	3	16.6	46	17.3	9.20	22.1	43	40.5	1	14	10.8	5	2	23	4.1	10.1	0.4	26.5	2
Start	M25								End								M36															

Objectives

The main goal of WP6 is to drive innovation in regulatory RA by strengthening its scientific basis, with implementation of NGRA as ultimate goal. The specific objectives of WP6 for year 3 are:

1. Task 6.1: To further develop and refine (quantitative) networks of AOPs for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption (thyroid dysfunction and anti-androgenic effects) and liver toxicity (liver fibrosis) and to identify associated NAMs. To re-design, based on this work, regulatory relevant IATAs for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and liver toxicity in close collaboration with relevant stakeholders and (re-)evaluate the applicability of developed IATAs by means of dedicated case studies in an iterative way. To further refine a draft workflow for the assessment of human relevance of toxicological pathways and associated NAMs. To perform regulatory relevant case studies aimed at the evaluation of new versions of the workflow.
2. Task 6.2: To further develop and apply innovative methods, tools and concepts to perform integrative risk and health impact assessments based on internal and external human exposures to single chemicals and mixtures in integrating multiple sources and routes from general and occupational environments.
3. Task 6.3: To continue implementation and further refinement of case studies reviewing selected methodologies and approaches for regulatory RA.
4. Task 6.4: To develop an efficient and protective regulatory workable RA methods through in-depth analysis of collected data for mixtures, articles, NAMs and biodiversity.

Description of Programmed Activities

WP6 annual workshop

The joint annual WP6 workshop with WP and task leaders, partners, and relevant stakeholders (e.g. EU and national authorities) will be organized to discuss activities, focusing on ongoing work and proposals for developments and new case studies to ensure the regulatory relevance. In preparation for the annual WP6 workshop, webinars will be organised where research results from all tasks in WP6 will be presented. The relevant regulatory stakeholders (ECHA, EFSA, EEA, JRC, DGs) will also be approached to provide feedback, to present priorities and regulatory needs as well as recent and upcoming developments regarding chemical risk assessments. This feedback and input will be used to provide support for discussions on how WP6 can further contribute to addressing these needs and meet the regulatory challenges. Collaborations with other WPs, in particular WP2, will be continued to optimize the output (KEMI, RIVM, all WP6 partners).

Task 6.1: Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment of Chemicals

Co-Leaders: SCIENSANO (BE), UL-LACDR (NL)

Partners: AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), CEFAS-DEFRA (UK), DTU (DK), ENSP (PT), Fraunhofer-ITEM (DE), IISPV (ES), INRAE (FR), INSERM (FR), IRFM (IT), IRSN (FR), ISS (IT), KI (SE), KWR (NL), LIST (LU), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), NILU (NO), NIPH (NO), RIVM (NL), SDU (DK), STAMI (NO),

UAntwerpen (BE), UGent (BE), UG-PL (PL), UKHSA (UK), UKCEH (UK), VUB (BE), WR (NL), WU-TOX (NL)

A6.1.1: Development of IATAs for regulatory purposes

In Y3, we will continue the development of IATAs for the 'low-hanging fruit' endpoints, *i.e.* genotoxicity, endocrine disruption (with a focus on (1) thyroid hormone system disruption and (2) antiandrogen activity) and liver toxicity (with a focus on liver fibrosis) for selected regulatory framework(s) and specific population groups. Based on the outcome of the mapping exercise on the availability and maturity (*i.e.* the level of completeness) of existing AOPs and existing NAMs, and the extent to which these NAMs have already been mapped to AOPs for these endpoints, AOP networks (AON) have been created; these will be refined in Y3. Where sufficient information is available, AON are being (partially) quantitated; this work is also continued in Y3. The IATAs will be based on human relevant AOPs/AONs. Additionally, the work on a workflow for human relevance assessment will be continued in Y3. Both the work on this workflow and the IATA development for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and liver toxicity will be an iterative process consisting of various cycles of optimization, thereby taking into account the feedback from different stakeholders (A6.1.3). For the IATAs, the progress made, issues encountered and the draft IATAs will be reported in AD6.9 (UL-LACDR, M30). This additional deliverable is delayed from M24 to M30, to allow for inclusion of the draft IATAs.

Details per project:

- P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM: This project is focused on a pragmatic workflow for the assessment of human relevance of AOPs and the relevance of NAMs related to the key events (KEs) or key event relationships (KERs) of the pathway under study. In Y3, the project will continue the work on the case studies initiated in Y2 to further improve the workflow. The case studies initiated comprise AOP#54 (Inhibition of NIS leading to learning and memory impairment) and AOP #162 (Enhanced hepatic clearance of thyroid hormones leading to thyroid tumors). Improvements will be achieved by making use of relevant existing approaches for weight of evidence assessment and uncertainty analysis. This will be done in close collaboration with WP7. The improved version of the workflow and the case studies performed will be described in a scientific manuscript. Additional case studies related to the IATAs for endocrine disruption will be performed, to provide insights on the human relevance and to identify possible aspects that need further improvement. To allow for dedicated discussions on the workflow and the case studies performed a face-to-face stakeholder workshop will be organized in Autumn 2024 (see A6.1.3). [Partners: AUTH (EL); RIVM (NL); ENSP (PT); BPI (EL); WU-TOX (NL); NIPH (NO); STAMI (NO); IRSN (FR); ISS (IT); IISPV (ES); LIST (LU)]

- P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA-ED_UAntwerpen: IATA development for endocrine disruption. In Y3, this project will continue to integrate information on readiness of methods from external activities such as OECD TDM EG and perform additional readiness assessments if required. An inventory of AOP networks for thyroid (THSD) and anti-androgenicity (AA) has been completed. Based on these networks we are refining the draft IATAs for THSD and AA. A workshop will be held in early Summer 2024, in collaboration with the regulatory stakeholders (primarily ECHA and EFSA), to discuss the available options including individual test method decision criteria for developing

Defined Approaches, based on current regulatory priorities and future needs. The development of quantitative KERs, if required, will be focused on critical linkages in the AOP networks / conceptual IATA models. Finally, case studies to evaluate the draft IATAs and to initiate discussion around development of Defined Approaches will be designed and initiated in Y3. [Partners: UAntwerpen (BE); UKHSA (UK); MU (CZ); AUTH (EL); UGent (BE); INSERM (FR); UL-LACDR (NL); RIVM (NL); ISS (IT); DTU (DK); SDU (DK); LIST (LU); BPI (EL); UG-PL (PL); IISPV (ES); STAMI (NO); KI (SE); IRFM (IT); ENSP (PT); Sciensano (BE); CEFAS-DEFRA (UK)]

- P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano: IATA development for genotoxicity. In Y3, this project will continue to characterize KERs within the AOP network for genotoxicity based on evidence collected via systematic reviews. We will develop, to the extent possible, a qAOP for DNA alkylation leading to increases in mutations and structural and numerical chromosome aberrations and characterize the uncertainties related to genotoxicity methods. Also, we will identify the main drivers of variability. Based on all these activities, the project will design an IATA for genotoxicity. This project will also design and execute an initial case study for genotoxicity, including existing as well as newly generated data. [Partners: Sciensano (BE), INRAE (FR), VUB (BE), UL-LACDR (NL), WU-TOX (NL), ISS (IT), IBMT (DE), UG-PL (PL), STAMI (NO), LIST (LU), BPI (EL), IRSN (FR), RIVM (NL), KWR (NL), NILU (NO), IRFM (IT), NIPH (NO), WR (NL), MUI (AT)].

- P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR: IATA development for liver toxicity. In Y3, building on the inventory of existing (draft) AOPs and AOP networks and associated NAMs relevant for liver fibrosis, this project will design a draft IATA for liver fibrosis. In order to evaluate the draft IATA, dedicated case studies for liver fibrosis will be designed and initiated. These case studies include collection of existing data as well as generation of new data using relevant NAMs. This will be done in close collaboration with WP5 and related research initiatives. For the draft IATA and initial case studies, we will benefit from the initial quantification of AOPs related to fibrosis. In collaboration with RISK-HUNT3R, qAOP development for liver fibrosis on the basis of existing *in vivo* data will be finalized in Y3, while quantification of AOPs related to fibrosis based on data generated in the project initial case study and literature data will be continued in Y3. [Partners: UL-LACDR (NL), WU-TOX (L), INSERM (FR), Ugent (BE), AUTH (EL), MU (CZ), IISPV (ES), STAMI (NO), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), WR (NL)]

A6.1.2: Evaluation of IATAs through case studies

The draft versions of the IATAs for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and liver toxicity as well as the draft workflow for human relevance assessment developed in A6.1.1 will be evaluated through (additional) case studies. Under the coordination of the case study leaders, case study teams will investigate the case study regulatory hypotheses that were defined in Y1 and Y2 with the selected relevant case study compounds. Regarding uncertainty analysis and weight of evidence assessment, we will closely collaborate with WP7. This will be achieved through joint case studies/use cases, where both WPs bring in their own expertise. First candidates have been identified in the project on human relevance (P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM). For ultimate integration of the data into QIVIVE, we will further strengthen the link with the experts

and tools established in T5.3. For the latter, dedicated discussions in Spring/Summer 2024 will be organized between T6.1 and T5.3, with the aim to determine how to best organize this collaboration. Reports on the case study modeling and experimental activities will be submitted for review via the project management system under T2.1 (M36). In the IATA case studies, the lessons learned by different stakeholders from previous case studies mapped in T6.3 will also be implemented as soon as this information becomes available. [*Partners: AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), CEFAS-DEFRA (UK), DTU (DK), ENSP (PT), Fraunhofer (DE), IISPV (ES), INRAE (FR), ISS (IT), KI (SE), KWR (NL), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), RIVM (NL), SCIENSANO (BE), SDU (DK), UAntwerpen (BE), UG-PL, UKHSA (UK), UL-LACDR (NL), VUB (BE), WR (NL), WU-TOX (NL)*]

A6.1.3: Stakeholder engagement

For each of the health effects addressed we will continue the interactions with relevant related (research) initiatives, such as EURION, EU-ToxRISK, RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX, PrecisionTOX and HESI GTTC, established in Y1 and Y2. For a wider stakeholder involvement, the progress made on AOP/AON and IATA development for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and liver toxicity as well as on the workflow for human relevance will be discussed with a diverse group of stakeholders in the annual two-day WP6 workshop. For the design of the case studies related to the IATAs as well as the workflow for human relevance, we will again actively seek input from ECHA, EFSA, JRC and OECD, to maximize regulatory impact. This will be achieved through online meetings. Additionally, ECHA, EFSA, JRC and OECD will be consulted regarding the additional IATAs for complex endpoints (described in AD6.1 (M24)), in terms of considerations to be taken into account when designing projects for Y4 and beyond. Additionally, we will organize a physical meeting with regulatory stakeholders in Autumn 2024, with the aim to explicitly collect their feedback on the work done, issues encountered and possible next steps. [*Partners: RIVM (NL), Sciensano (BE), UL-LACDR (NL), STAMI (NO), ISS (IT), UG-PL (PL), BPI (EL)*]

Task 6.2: Integrative exposure and risk assessment

Co-Leaders: ANSES (FR), VITO (BE)

Partners: AU (DK), ARSO (SI), AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), CSTB (FR), DTU (DK), EFSA (IT), EHESP (FR), ENSP (PT), FINBA (ES), TTL (FI), FMUL (PT), FOPH (CH), Fraunhofer (DE), GGeoSZ (SI), ICPS (IT), CSIC (ES), IISPV (ES), KI (SE), INERIS (FR), INRAE (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), IRFM (IT), ISCIII (ES), ISSeP (BE), IUSS (IT), IVL (SE), KWR (NL), LNS (LU), MOH-CY/SGL (CY), MU (CZ), NIJZ (SI), NIOM (PL), NIPH (NO), NLZOH (SI), OI (SI), ONIRIS (FR), OVAM (BE), RIVM (NL), SRU (NL), SCIENSANO (BE), SECO (CH), SLU (SE), STAMI (NO), TNO (NL), UAVR (PT), UBA (DE), UGR (ES), UG-PL (PL), UNIPD (IT), UNISANTE (CH), USI (CH), UoB (UK), UU-IRAS (NL), WR (NL)

Synergies between T6.2 projects case studies (PFAS, pyrethroids and metals) will be deployed during year 3 to propose an integrative and dynamical way to model mixture exposure and perform health impact assessment. For example, developments and implementation in Parc ToolBox of PBPK models from P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPK_INERIS will serve into P6.2.1.a_Y1_SourcetoDose_VITO, P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM and P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES to convert doses and enable model verification. Also,

aggregate exposures from P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES will be used to identify the main sources that contribute to the risk related to mixtures in P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM.

In addition, during year 3, the project leaders and the case study leaders will start discussing the impact of the case studies with regulators from DG SANTE, DG ENVI, DG EMPL. The case study results should not might be sensitive for regulators and may raise concern in society. Regulators may then timely provide answers on possible risk mitigation measures. Furthermore, regulators should be informed timely and before publications are out in the public. Task 6.2 leaders will discuss synergies with EFSA's Chief Scientific Officers and leader and experts of EFSA knowledge and innovation communities (KIC). The expected synergies are related to risk interpretation of mixture risk assessment using HBM data and aggregated exposure. EFSA is working on the ExpoAdvance strategic roadmap. Depending on the outcome of this Roadmap report, task 6.2 leaders will discuss potential work for EFSA and for PARC related to aggregated exposure and sources of exposure.

Four deliverables will be delivered by month 36.

- D6.1 Report on aggregate exposure for general population and workers, and source to dose models applied to case studies (P6.2.1)
- D6.2 Report on innovative methods based on PBK models (P6.2.2)
- D6.3 Report on innovative approaches for real-life mixture RA (P6.2.3)
- D6.4 Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications (P6.2.4)

A6.2.1 Aggregated exposure assessment from multiple sources and routes for general population and workers

Details per project:

- P6.2.1.a_Y1_SourcetoDose_VITO: from the inventory of source-to-dose models for the general population, the existing model parameters and the gap analysis (models and data for model parameters), the development of realistic models (for identified gaps) will continue. This involves the translation of the mechanistic understanding of source-to-dose exposure into conceptual models, for two aspects (i) exposure to chemicals released from consumer products and materials to the indoor environment (general population), and (ii) direct and indirect exposure via release and transfer from the outdoor environment. Case studies have been started in Y2. In Y3, we will continue elaboration of the case studies. The case studies are organized by chemicals and by type of environment (indoor and outdoor). Case studies for the outdoor environment (PFAS and metals) involve 1) case studies in hotspots in participating countries (hotspots, being complementary to general population background exposure for metals and PFAS covered in P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES), and 2) transfer-specific aspects for general population exposure (e.g. transfer from soil to crops and subsequent dietary exposure). Case studies for the indoor environment focus on model parameterization and validation for phthalates and other plasticizers. Other possible case studies will be presented and selected in Y3 (in view of gaps, PARC chemical priorities and policy needs). Case studies include several aspects: set up of scenarios, model parameterization, model runs and interpretations, verification of model outcomes, and policy implications (e.g. innovative methods for setting health-based soil standards built on epidemiological data). Deliverable D6.1 (developed together with 6.2.1b) is foreseen for M36, and scientific publications on case studies will be written in Y3. [Lead: VITO

(BE); LNS (LU); Contributors: RIVM (NL); ANSES (FR); IVV (DE); CSTB (FR); KWR (NL); IVL (SW); NIJZ (SI); FOPH (CH); GeoZS (SI); FMUL (PT), IISPV (ES), OVAM (BE); ISSeP (BE), ARSO (SI)].

- P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES: the strategy to assess aggregate exposure through different sources from general and occupational environments and different routes of entry (inhalation, dermal, ingestion) will continue to be developed and implemented in case studies (All partners). In collaboration with T8.3, selected exposure models from the scoring process that has followed the inventory of the associated models and tools will be connected in the ParcToolBox. This is the part of the ParToolBox on integrative models such as MCRA and kinetic models for reverse dosimetry to link HBM data (internal exposure) to external exposure). A training on aggregated exposure will be organized by WR-BIOM with the help of at least ANSES, UNISANTE, RIVM, FOPH, TNO, TTL. The development of case studies will continue with the analysis of the data collected, and the combination of the heterogenous datasets to sustain aggregated cases studies for the two selected metals (Cd and CrVI), selected pesticides (e.g. the pyrethroids), the PFAS and the phthalates. Aggregate exposures and associated risk will be produced for several European populations. The innovative approach developed to aggregate exposures and its application to several case studies will be part of a second deliverable at the end of year 3 and several scientific publications will start. Several meetings by project subworking groups (method/functional design/model inventory/different case studies) are planned at least every two months and at least one preferably physical meeting for the whole project. [Lead: ANSES (FR) Unisanté (CH). Case study/method lead : ANSES (FR), UNISANTE (CH), WUR-BIOM (NL), TNO (NL), TTL (FI), IVL (SE), ISCIII (ES), FOPH(CH) Contributors: CSTB (FR), INRS (FR), CSIC (ES), IISPV (ES), INSA (PT), ENSP-UNL (PT), FMUL (PT), VITO (BE), ISSeP (BE), OVAM (BE), LNS (LU), SRU (NL), WR-BIOM (NL), KWR (NL), IVV (DE), MU/RECETOX (CZ), NIOM (PL), NIJZ (SI), GeoZS (SI), ARSO (SI), BPI (EL), AUTH (EL), UOB (UK), NIPH (NO), STAMI (NO), AU (DK), EFSA (EU), UoB (UK)].

A6.2.2 Modelling exposure through life

Details per project:

- P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPk_INERIS: In the first two years, an inventory of PBPk models and their gaps, as well as refinement in PBPk models to account for lifetime exposure in terms of physiology and exposure routes were made for pesticides (pyrethroids and organophosphates), metals (Cd, As, Pb, Hg), bisphenols and PFAS. In year 3, the aim is to extend the parameterisation of PBPk models for these compounds to address identified gaps and needs for human lifetime exposure, including sensitive populations: (i) description of *in utero* exposure and the placental transfer process based on the physicochemical properties of the different compounds (INERIS, AUTH, IISPV, ANSES, RIVM, SLU), (ii) description of physiological changes at different stages of development and pregnancy (INERIS, AUTH, IISPV, ANSES, RIVM, SLU, TNO), (iii) including maturity of detoxification or transport processes (INERIS, AUTH, IISPV, ANSES, RIVM, SLU, TNO), (iv) integration of gender-specific differences for both physiological and Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion (ADME) processes (INERIS, AUTH, IISPV, ANSES, RIVM, SLU), (v) transfer across the blood-brain barrier (AUTH, IISPV, ANSES, RIVM, SLU), (vi) inclusion of new compartments in PBPk models to account for new biomarkers predicting specific

exposure, such as the concentration of chemicals in hair (e.g., MeHg) (AUTH, IISPV, ANSES, RIVM, SLU, INERIS) and (vii) implementation of models in the integrative ParcToolBox (MCRA/Integra) in collaboration with T8.3 (WR-BIOM). Extensive parameterisation of newly generated data in PARC (e.g., in WP5) will continue. To facilitate the use of PBPK models in other T6.2 projects, training sessions will be organised in year 3. One whole meeting is expected to be organised every 3 months, and one meeting per thematic working group every 2 months. [Lead: INERIS (FR), AUTH (EL); working group lead: IISPV (ES), ANSES (FR), ONIRIS (FR), TNO (NL). PFAS case study: IISPV (ES), WR (NL), SLU (SE), NIPH (NO), INERIS (FR), VITO (BE), RIVM (NL), TNO (NL). Metals case study: ANSES (FR), AUTH (EL), ONIRIS (FR). Bisphenols case study: AUTH (EL). Parameterisation working group: ANSES (FR), ONIRIS (FR), AUTH (EL), SLU (SE), INERIS (FR), IISPV (ES), IRFM (IT), RIVM (NL). Exposure routes working group: TNO (NL), IISPV (ES), VITO (BE), INERIS (FR), SLU (SE), RIVM (NL). Implementation of models: WR-BIOM (NL), ANSES (FR), ONIRIS (FR), RIVM (NL). Other contributors: IVL (SE)]

A6.2.3 Mixture exposure and risk assessment

Details per project:

- P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM: the year 3 will be consecrated to the application of the developed strategy in each case study (e.g., pesticides and neurotoxic effects, PFAS and immune effect, metals and kidney effects, metals and developmental effects) to perform mixture risk assessment (MRA) using several HBM dataset from different European general and occupational populations. The case studies will be extended to cover mixtures of substances from different chemical families regarding real-life exposure and common health effects. For that, a set of real-life of mixtures crossing regulatory silos will be produced from combined exposures by applying statistical methods on selected HBM studies. Additional hazard and kinetic data will be collected to group the new selected chemicals in assessment groups. The started work on comparing statistical methods to study the link between mixtures biomarkers of exposure and health effects will continue. The integration in the PARCToolBox (MCRA) of the input data (HBM, hazard, kinetic parameters), the statistical and kinetic models as well as the updated risk metrics needed for each case studied will be improved and tested during the application phase. The MCRA Integrated Risk Assessment Dashboard as part of the PARC Toolbox will be extended with occupational data and risk interpretation. Partners with HBM data will be trained to be able to perform MRA on their own dataset. Training will be also given to stakeholders and synergy will be discussed in particular with EFSA and ECHA.

The proposed strategy to perform MRA and its application to case studies will be part of a second deliverable at the end of year 3 and several associated publications will start during year 3. The project will offer tools, concepts and realistic examples/case studies on how the risk assessment can be innovated. Case studies will show impact for selected regulatory silos (prioritized chemical families). In year 4 this might be extended with chemicals overarching regulatory silos.

Work will be performed in close cooperation with WP7 (linked to the project and via data champions), T4.1 for data generation and analysis, WP5 for newly hazard data and T8.3 for the development of the model network. Case study leaders will contribute to PARCopedia. Three project meeting comprising physical meeting are planned and one meeting for each case study will be yield every 6 weeks. Regular meetings between case studies leaders will be also conducted.

[Lead: ANSES (FR), RIVM (NL). Case study and method WG lead: ANSES (FR), RIVM (NL), BPI (GR), UGR (ES), VITO (BE) Contributors: AU (DK), AUTH (EL), CSIC (ES), IISPV (ES), DTU

(DK), EASP (ES), EFSA (EU), EHESP (FR), FINBA (ES), ICPS (IT), JSI (SI), INERIS (FR), INSERM (FR), ISCIH (ES), IVL (SE), LNS (LU), MOHCY/SGL (CY), MU (CZ), NIJZ (SI), NIPH (NO), SRU (NL), SLU (SE), STAMI (NO), TTL (FI), UBA (DE), UG-PL (PL), UNIPD (IT), UU-IRAS (NL), VITO (BE), WR (NL), INRAE (FR), KWR (NL), FMUL (PT), GeoZS (SI), UNIVIE (AT), IRFM (IT) INRAE (FR), Oniris/INRAE (FR)].

A6.2.4 Human health impact assessment and risk indicators

In this task on environmental burden of disease (EBD) and health impact assessment (HIA) the project on case studies (P6.2.4.c_Y1_HIACaseStudies_UU-IRAS) functions currently as a central hub to which other projects (P6.2.4.a_Y1_HIADDataAvailability_VITO; P6.2.4.b_Y1_HIAMethod_UU-IRAS; P6.2.4.d_Y1_HIAIndicators_VITO) are linked. Starting from the case studies, data are gathered to perform environmental burden of disease (EBD) calculations, hurdles in the methodology are described and indicators are developed when finalizing the case studies. Deliverable D6.4 is foreseen for M36, consisting of all performed work regarding methodological improvements, data availability, case studies, and indicators on health impact assessment and burden of disease. Overarching project meetings will be organized with all partners every 2 months, and each case study will have roughly meeting every 4/6 weeks.

Details per project:

- P6.2.4.a_Y1_HIADDataAvailability_VITO: in Y3, the project will continue the exploration of possibilities to gather data and fill data gaps for data-poor chemicals identified and prioritized in year 1. In Y3, focus will be on exposure data (external & internal), health data, exposure-response data and data on socio-economic status. The availability of data will be linked to the case studies where starting from the individual case studies, data and data gaps will be identified. A quick scan of newly available health impact assessments and environmental burden of disease calculations, exposure data, and exposure-effect functions necessary for the case studies will be performed in Y3. Additional data gaps to be addressed in the course of PARC will be identified and prioritized. [Project lead: VITO (BE) UU-IRAS (NL). Contributors: ANSES (FR), AUTH (EL), DTU (DK), ENSP (PT), FMUL (PT), IISPV (ES), INSA (PT), ISSeP (BE), IVL (SE), KI (SE), MU (CZ), NIJZ (SI), NIPH (NO), NLZOH (SI), OI (SI), SRU (NL), Sciensano (BE), STAMI (NO), USI (CH)]

- P6.2.4.b_Y1_HIAMethod_UU-IRAS: the project will continue the activities related to exposure-effect relationships initiated and elaborated in year 1 and 2 : inventory of existing exposure-biomarker of effect-health outcome relationships, analyse possibilities for incorporation of effect biomarker measurements as surrogate markers for toxicity associated with chemical exposure which would allow health impact assessment for (pre)clinical outcomes, development of an integrative approach to take different lines of evidence (in vitro, in vivo, and human data, mode of action, biomarkers of effect) into account to establish human relevant exposure-effect relationships, addressing all associated uncertainties, and development of a Weight-of-evidence (WoE) approach for selection of exposure-effect functions including information from epidemiological, toxicological and mechanistic studies. A manuscript on the methodological challenges for calculating the EBD related to chemical exposure has been initiated in Y2 and will be finalized in Y3. Case studies in Y2 focusing on the burden of disease will be analysed for hurdles towards methodological aspects. In Y3, extension of the case studies towards calculations of costs for society will be included, depending on the specific case studies. Other methodological improvements identified and prioritized in year 1 and 2 may be initiated as well

in Y3; feasibility of addressing those during the course of PARC will be assessed and activities will be planned accordingly. [Project lead: UU-IRAS/UBA Contributors: ANSES (FR), AUTH (EL), DTU (DK), ENSP (PT), FMUL (PT), IISPV (ES), INSA (PT), IVL (SE), KI (SE), MU (CZ), NIPH (NO), OI (SI), RIVM (NL), Sciensano (BE), UBA (DE), USI (CH), UU-IRAS (NL), VITO (BE), WR (NL)].

- P6.2.4.c_Y1_HIACaseStudies_ UU-IRAS: the first case studies to calculate health impact, burden of disease, risk/benefit and/or cost/benefit focusing on chemicals, exposure-(biomarker of) effect relationships, exposure scenarios, and methodological improvements and innovations prioritized in year 1, were running during year 2 and most will be finalized during year 3. Case studies already running in year 2 are:

- Pyrethroid exposure and association with ADHD (leading partner VITO)
- Environmental burden of a mixture of heavy metals on cancer and cardiovascular related mortality in adults living close to waste incinerators (leading partner FMUL)
- EBD of arsenic exposure and cancers (lung, bladder & skin) (leading partner Sciensano)
- HIA of lead exposure and cardiovascular diseases and chronic kidney disease (leading partner DTU)
- Influence of waste co-incineration in a cement plant on cancer burden (leading partner OI)
- Lead (Pb) and methylmercury (meHg) and IQ loss in Children in Europe for single substance and for mixtures (Leading partner ANSES)

Case studies already discussed in Y2 and starting in Y3 are exposure to PFAS and related immune effects (leading partner VITO), cadmium and chronic kidney disease (leading partner Sciensano, RIVM) and possibly exposure to dioxins and reduced fertility (leading partner DTU).

Other possible case studies starting in Y3 will be presented and selected through a multi-criteria decisions analysis tool developed during Y1.

[Project lead: ANSES (FR), VITO (BE) Contributors: AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), DTU (DK), ENSP (PT), FMUL (PT), IISPV (ES), INSA (PT), KI (SE), NIPH (NO), OI (SI), SRU (NL), Sciensano (BE), SPF (FR), STAMI (NO), UU-IRAS (NL)].

- P6.2.4.d_Y1_HIAIndicators_VITO: in year 3, the project will focus on the development and implementation of indicators (proposed in year 1 and 2) to assess the human health risk and/or impact of selected exposure scenarios to inform policy makers. In Y2, input was given to EEA for the development of risk indicators for BPA and for pesticides, In Y3, we will continue developing indicators (for other substances, cfr. case studies), which will aid the translation of science to policy and answer policy-related questions (e.g.; in collaboration with EEA). Main focus will be on indicators coming from the case studies.

[Project lead: VITO (BE) UU-IRAS (NL) Contributors: ANSES (FR), FMUL (PT), Sciensano (BE), DTU (DK), OI (SI), VITO (BE) Contributors: , AUTH (EL), ENSP (PT), INSA (PT), IVL (SE), MU (CZ), NIJZ (SI), , UU-IRAS (NL), WR (NL)].

Task 6.3: Review of risk assessment methodology

Co-Leaders: SU (SE), BPI (EL)

Partners: UCL (UK), INSA (PT), EAA (AT), EAWAG (CH), TTL (FI), FOEN (CH), INERIS (FR), INSERM (FR), INRAE (FR), IRFM (IT), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), JSI (SI), KI (SE), LSMU (LT), DTU (DK), REGIONH (DK), UCPH (DK), RSU (LV), SCIENSANO (BE), STAMI (NO), NILU (NO), SYKE (FI), UBA (DE), ULUND (SE), VUB (BE), UNIBAS (CH), KEMI (SE), SU (SE), BPI (EL), UMIL (IT), UNIPD (IT), EFSA (EU), UT (EE)

The initiated projects will continue during M25-M36, with further refinement of reviews and analysis through case studies as well as further exploration of stakeholder interactions. The interactions with ECHA, EFSA, SCCS, JRC and OECD on their involvement in the task, either to follow or actively take part in specific case studies, will continue, focusing both on input to ongoing and planned work as well as to disseminate results and increase regulatory uptake. Possibilities to disseminate results to national authorities will be explored. The need to describe regulatory relevance of the projects and case studies will continuously be highlighted. Case studies will be ongoing for two to five years. Due to delays related to e.g., recruiting PhD students, obtaining data, and handling overwhelming amounts of literature data, three case studies (CS2, CS13, and CS19) planned to end in M24 will continue also in Y3 and three case studies (CS12, CS17, and CS18) planned to end M36 will continue in Y4. One additional case study (CS20) will be initiated M25.

One to two project meetings to present and discuss the progress of the case studies will be organized during Y3 [Partners involved: SU (SE), BPI (EL), KEMI (SE), All partners].

Case study-specific meetings for planning and progress updates will be organized by the case study leaders as needed.

A6.3.1 Substance and effect specific reviews

- P6.3.1.a_Y1_SubstanceRA_SU; Case studies reviewing substance-specific RA depending on intended use. The reviews of substance-specific assessments depending on intended use will continue through two case studies. The case studies are described below and will evaluate differences and similarities, and subsequent implications, across legislations. The outcomes of this project may serve as a ground for adjustments of the relevant regulations. The identification of dissimilarities in testing requirements and hazard assessments of substances depending on specific uses will offer valuable information for the implementation and potential impacts of the "One Substance One Assessment" approach on regulations targeting specific uses of chemicals. Further, the potential barriers and opportunities, and available methods, for harmonisation in a systematic way will be presented. [Partners involved: SU (SE), UCL (UK), SCIENSANO (BE), IRFM (IT), KI (SE)].

- CS12_MethodOSOA_SU: In this case study, we will perform an analysis of risk assessment processes, including significant differences between processes, strengths of the current system(s), and potential gaps, overlaps, or inefficiencies. We have performed a mapping of substances regulated in more than one regulation and we will from that select a number of substances to investigate further how lack of harmonization across

regulations impact the risk assessment and subsequent risk management. (SU (SE), KI (SE))

- CS13_PlasticizersRA_UCL: During Y3, we will assess the implications of similarities and differences in approaches to hazard, exposure, and risk assessments in 37 pieces of legislation listing at least one of 417 plastic additives (according to EUCLEF). Justifications for differences in overall approach (not in assessments of individual substances), e.g., in relation the balance of risks and benefits for a specific intended use and/or availability of alternatives, will be reviewed, as will potential and available solutions for harmonization. This aims to highlight barriers and opportunities for the implementation of the OSOA ambition of the CSS, using plastic additives as a case for which there will be a multiplicity of intended uses and correspondingly relevant chemical regulations. Due to a delay in obtaining data the end date has been extended from M24 to M36. (UCL (UK), SCIENSANO (BE), IRFM (IT)).
- CS14_BiocidesRA_SU: M1-M24 (finalised). (SU (SE), KI (SE)).

- P6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI; Case studies reviewing effect-specific RA: The reviews of effect-specific assessments will continue through six case studies. The case studies are described below and will include aspects such as sensitization and developmental neurotoxicity as well as use of non-animal methods for identification of endocrine disruption, genotoxicity, and carcinogenicity. The project will evaluate and suggest opportunities for improving and harmonising aspects of risk assessment methodology, including *in vitro* short-term tests and structure-activity based methodologies. The project will analyse and discuss relevant gaps and research needs and, when relevant, propose improvements and harmonization of the testing requirements, criteria, recommendations, and best practices across EU regulations. The results will be made available to and discussed with regulatory agencies. These case studies reviewing risk assessment methodology concerning specific priority endpoints will contribute to conclusions on the need for innovation in regulatory risk assessment to rapidly and effectively identify chemicals with hazardous properties for human health and the environment through a more effective, accurate and harmonised across silos OSOA approach. [Partners involved: REGIONH (DK), STAMI (NO), SU (SE), IRFM (IT), UNIBAS (CH), VUB (BE), ISS (IT), NILU (NO), INSA (PT), BPI (EL), KI (SE), INSERM (FR), INERIS (FR), EAA (AT), UBA (DE), INRAE (FR), UT (EE)].

- CS9_SKINSENSIRISK_REGIONH: Year 3 will be devoted to finalising the systematic review of components in risk assessment methods, including the IATAs described by OECD (Guideline 497) and QRA2 adopted by Scientific Committee on Consumer Safety (SCCS), mixtures and gaps of knowledge. Further the specific case study on successes and failures in risk assessment of skin sensitizers will be initiated. Results will be used for suggesting improvements in regulatory practices across areas and highlight gaps of knowledge. (REGIONH (DK), STAMI (NO), SU (SE), IRFM (IT), UNIBAS (CH)).
- CS10_ED-cosmetics_VUB: The critical analysis of risk assessments will continue during the third year using (a) selected candidate(s) of the SCCS priority endocrine disruptors list (ED) list. The results obtained in this case study will be discussed with the SCCS and a reporting of the safety evaluation *modus operandi* of the selected substances will be done. During a final meeting with the relevant stakeholders, recommendations and best practices will be formulated with respect to the inclusion of NAMs and new technology to cover the biological complexity and as such enable the prediction of human health effects for substances with potential ED activity (VUB (BE), INRAE (FR)).
- CS11_GenotoxCarc_ISS: Year 3 will be devoted to finalizing the revision and comparison

of regulatory practices for genotoxicity and carcinogenicity classification and risk assessment. In particular, the analysis will be extended to also include pharmaceuticals and nanomaterials. The most relevant gaps and research needs will be analysed and discussed with the aim of proposing improvements and harmonization of the testing requirements across EU regulations. Concerning regulatory acceptability of QSAR approaches for genotoxicity and carcinogenicity, the use of the recently published OECD QSAR Assessment Framework for evaluating the models and their predictions (<https://www.oecd.org/chemicalsafety/risk-assessment/qsar-assessment-framework.pdf>) will be explored. Starting from year 3, an inventory of NAMs for genotoxicity and carcinogenicity assessment will be compiled and constantly updated, including NAMs under development within PARC. NAMs will be evaluated in terms of their suitability to fill existing gaps and for their regulatory readiness. Moreover, a scoping study on substances known as human carcinogens (i.e., GHS class 1 A) and on the *in silico* models available for predicting carcinogenesis will be carried out. (ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), NILU (NO), INSA (PT)).

- CS15_DNT_SU: Year 3 will be devoted to assessing if a uniform graphical and statistical analysis of behavioural outcome data, developed for high statistical power, can identify previously unreported effects. Code for graphical and statistical analyses will be made available to regulatory agencies and the public. Analyses indicating previously unrecognised effects will be made available to regulatory agencies, where relevant. We increase the number of compounds to be included from 5-7 to approximately 40, due to a new PhD student to be involved in the project. (SU (SE)).
- CS17_ED-in vitro_BPI: Year 3 will be devoted to the implementation of reliability and relevance criteria developed for the evaluation of prioritised *in vitro* methods on estrogen, androgen, steroidogenesis, and thyroid (EATS) modalities on selected studies from the open literature. The developed reliability and relevance criteria will be refined based on experience gained from implementation on specific studies. (BPI (EL), KI (SE), INSERM (FR), INERIS (FR), UBA (DE)).
- CS18_ED-classes_BPI: Year 3 will be devoted to exploring how available *in vitro*, *in silico* and read-across approaches can be used for classification (or not) of a substance under the new classification, labelling and packaging (CL) criteria for ED, through implementation of specific examples of regulated chemicals. The outcomes of this CS will contribute to the harmonized implementation of the new CLP criteria on hazard classes for ED taking into consideration all available methods and tools. (BPI (EL), INSERM (FR), EAA (AT), IRFM (IT), VUB (BE), UT (EE)).

A6.3.2 Use of tools, criteria, and methods reviews

- P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU; Case studies reviewing tools, criteria, and methods used in regulatory RA

The reviews on the use of tools, criteria, and methods in regulatory RA will continue through nine case studies, with one case study initiated in Y3. The case studies are described below and include general aspects such as application of risk-based benchmarks, uncertainty analysis, and handling data gaps as well as aspects related to occupational RA and Environment Risk Assessment (ERA). The project will guide the future design of legislation on chemical risk assessment, focusing on sustainable management of chemical risks, as well as the implementation of the OSOA approach. The project will provide regulators, legislators, and other stakeholders an in-depth understanding of the commonly used decision benchmarks and the significance of their appropriate foundation and application. The project will provide new

knowledge about the practical challenges in using quantitative expressions of uncertainty in assessment, as well as pedagogical examples on how to implement quantitative expressions of uncertainty and the benefit of these in assessment and communication. The project will provide recommendations for harmonizing data gap-filling approaches in relevant EU legislations, which will have an impact on the practices of filling data gaps during compliance reporting, monitoring and assessment by companies, scientists, and policymakers alike. [Partners involved: SYKE (FI), ISSeP (BE), SU (SE), STAMI (NO), UBA (DE), JSI (SI), UCL (UK), TTL (FI), KI (SE), RSU (LV), INERIS (FR), KEMI (SE), ULUND (SE), BPI (EL), LSMU (LT), EAWAG (CH), FOEN (CH), DTU (DK), UCPH (DK), UMIL (IT), UNIPD (IT), EFSA (EU)].

- CS1_CARB_SYKE: The comparative analysis of selected risk-based decision benchmarks under different EU regulatory frameworks will continue alongside stakeholder engagement. A final report and a policy paper on the analysis will be produced. Our results will provide the regulators, legislators and other stakeholders with information and recommendations on how the studied regulatory frameworks and their implicit decision benchmarks, or their application, could be improved. Our results will also stimulate the necessary dialogue on the regulation of environmental chemicals and support the development of more coherent risk-based approaches between the relevant EU agencies (SYKE (FI), ISSeP (BE)).
- CS2_RiskReduction_SU: During Y3, the literature review on methods for evaluating the effectiveness of risk assessment for reducing risk will continue, as well as the semi-structured interviews with relevant stakeholders on the effectiveness of current risk assessment methodologies in reducing risk. Assessment and comparison between methods for evaluating the effectiveness of risk assessment for reducing risk will be performed. Due to a delay in obtaining data the end date has been extended from M24 to M36. (SU (SE), UBA (DE), STAMI (NO), UCL (UK), JSI (SI)).
- CS16_UncertaintyRA_ULUND: Collection of information on practical challenges through a questionnaire with follow up interviews will continue. We will make a policy brief including justifications for expressing uncertainty quantitatively by % probability (or bounded probabilities) and how to manage uncertainty captured in scenarios or assumptions, as well as unknown unknowns. A list of examples of applications of uncertainty analysis has been created and will be expanded based on support from the community of experts. As an outreach activity and to support implementations of uncertainty analysis, sources introducing uncertainty will be collected on a public webpage with explanatory text and videos. Here we will ask for examples where uncertainty analysis done with quantitative expressions have been beneficial to an assessment. (ULUND (SE), KI (SE), BPI (EL), UBA (DE)).
- CS19_DataGapFilling_KEMI-DTU: In Y3, the inventory of EU regulations and policies relevant for chemical data gap filling as well as approaches used will be analysed. Semi-structured interviews with relevant stakeholders on practices related to data gap filling will be performed. A report will be produced that provides a systematic overview of how chemical data gaps are addressed across EU regulations and policies, including an assessment of similarities, differences, and possibilities for cross-policy harmonization of data gap filling approaches. Due to a delay in recruitment, the end date has been extended from M24 to M30. (DTU (DK), UCPH (DK), KEMI (SE), SU (SE)).
- CS7_REGPREP_EAWAG: Mapping of topics and identification of substances with several different effect values as case studies, identification of similarities and differences, and areas requiring further analysis will continue. A review regarding aquatic and sediment RA will be done and work will be started for soil RA. Case studies on comparative assessment of pro- and retrospective effects values will be underway. (EAWAG (CH), FOEN (CH)),

INERIS (FR), UBA (DE)).

- CS20_PESTNAM_ISS: During Y3, which is the first year of the study, interactions within and outside PARC will be established as well as refining of work plan and methodology. Critical review of the actual implementation of NAMs within the EFSA evaluation of the approval of active substances in plant protection products in the area of hazard characterization in both human and environmental health in the last 10 years will be performed and data gaps will be identified. (ISS (IT), UMIL (IT), UNIPD (IT), BPI (EL), EFSA (EU)).
- CS4_SecPoisoning_INERIS: Following the analysis of the main legislations considered, i.e. chemical regulations which already have a clear framework for secondary poisoning assessment and the Water Framework Directive which also gives provisions for secondary poisoning, the main area where harmonization is needed will be treated sequentially using examples and identifying the consequences of the lack of harmonization. Borderline cases (which do not meet persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic (PBT) or POP criteria) but that may still cause a risk because highly exceeding one of the P or B criteria will be identified and will also help to select substances for testing. For areas where differences have been identified, e.g., selection of the initial accumulation metrics, the definition of the trophic network and levels and the exposure duration, selection of the metric use for bioaccumulation will be compared among regulations for selected chemicals, and if achievable, tested through the recent IATA on bioaccumulations examined within the OECD IATA CSP. The second topic treated in Y3 will be the use of TK modelling for both prioritization of borderline PBT/POP chemicals, and how these models can be used to improve the definition of the trophic network, including apex species. The workplan and intermediate results will be sent out to targeted regulators to obtain feedback on the strategy proposed and on possible way to suggest implementation of our findings. (INERIS (FR)).
- CS8_OccupReproDev_KI: Y3 will focus on comparing and contrasting findings of the in-depth reviews of the safety margin to reproductive and developmental toxicity for selected case-study substances. Analysis and discussion of threshold vs non-threshold reproductive effects and regulatory status of studied substances. Finalising report of results and recommendations. (KI (SE), TTL (FI), LSMU (LT), STAMI (NO), RSU (LV)).
- CS3_WorkplaceRA_TTL: In Y3, the results of the questionnaire study for workplaces (OSH managers) and labour inspectors (execution 2023 Q4/2024 Q1), as well as the related theme interviews for relevant stakeholders (e.g., industrial/employee organisations, authorities) (execution 2024 Q1/Q2) will be analysed and reported. The questionnaire study and interviews are expected to reveal how limit values and related information produced under different regulatory processes are interpreted and used in workplace chemical risk assessment and risk mitigation in practice. This information may be used to support regulatory decision making as well as providing guidance for workplaces. (TTL (FI), KI (SE), JSI (SI), STAMI (NO), RSU (LV)).

Task 6.4: Transposing results to regulatory risk assessment methodologies

Co-leaders: AGES (AT), UNIBAS (CH)

Partners: ANSES (FR), INERIS (FR), OFB (FR), EAA (AT), AGES (AT), MU (CZ), AU (DK), REGIONH-GR (DK), UT (EE), EFSA (EU), SYKE (FI), Tukes (FI), UBA (DE), UFZ (DE), UKOLD (DE), USO (DE), Fraunhofer (DE), UCPH (DK) UI (IS), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), LSMU (LT), VUA (NL), NIPH (NO), STAMI (NO), NIVA (NO), NIOM (PL), IEP-NRI (PL), UG-PL (PL), INSA (PT), ENSP (PT), UC (PT), UAVR (PT), ISCIII (ES), UCLM (SI), UGOT (SE), ULUND (SE), RISE (SE),

KEMI (SE), SLU (SE), NLZOH (SI) AGROSCOPE (CH), EAWAG (CH), FOEN (CH), UNIBAS (CH), BUL (UK), UKCEH (UK), UOB (UK), EA (UK), UBATH (UK) BPI (EL)

A6.4.1. Develop regulatory relevant approaches and methods for chemical mixtures

Details per project:

- P6.4.1.a_Y1_OPREMIXCS1_BRUNEL_UGot: In the third year of this project, the focus will be on the ongoing case studies for generating new information for sizing the Mixture Assessment Factor (MAF) and for identifying where and how the MAF approach can be productively applied in a regulatory context. This will be based on the recently published paper by Backhaus (2023), which provides an overview of the different MAF algorithms and their relevant properties. The following case studies will be implemented: “Benchmarking of different approaches to calculate MAF values for use in prospective environmental risk assessment (UBA, EAWAG)”; “Data-driven sizing of a MAF- a male reproductive health case study” (BUL, BPI); “Evaluation of the applicability of MAF for human health risk assessment regarding contaminants in food” (AGES); “Identification of potential mixtures of Food Additives and Food flavourings and the estimation of a potential health risk by using two tools- the mRPI and the MAF” (AGES). Besides the MAF, two case studies will focus on the EU Water Framework Directive and will establish assessment groups (UBA, EAWAG) and set Mixture EQS for certain substance groups (UGoT). Since Y3 is the last year of this project, a description of the case studies, the outcome of the questionnaire on the current practice of mixture toxicity evaluation in the competent authorities of the EU member states and the general project conclusion will be published as an additional deliverable (AD.6.17 Optimizing regulatory risk assessment and management of chemical mixtures in Europe), which is part of the D6.18: Final report on risk assessment and management methods for chemical mixtures across legislations (M81). Project meetings (online) to present and discuss the progress of the case studies will be organized during Y3. Case study-specific meetings (online) for planning and progress updates will be organized by the case study leaders as needed. It is foreseen to share the results within regulatory agencies on a national and European level via meeting/webinars and a policy brief on the main findings of the activity. Additionally, a meeting with stakeholders is planned, where relevant outcomes from OPREMIX and MONAMMIX Projects will be shared. The organisation of this meeting starts in Y3, but since no date is yet set, the meeting can also take place early in Y4.

(Lead partner: UGOT, BUL, Participants: AGES, BPI, EAWAG, UBA, UI, NIVA, EA, ENSP, LSMU, NIOM, UAVR, KEMI, UKCEH, NLZOH).

- P6.4.1.b_Y1_MONAMMIXCS2_UFZ: In Y3, the work on the ongoing case studies will be continued. The case studies will deal with a) identification of an European waste water treatment plant (WWTP) effluent reference mixture (UFZ), b) investigation of mixture risk heterogeneity in European freshwater bodies (UFZ), c) to curate a mode of action database of chemicals that are relevant for the aquatic environment (UFZ), d) a review of pollution of river Krupa with PCBs and their mixtures (NLZOH), e) using groundwater and drinking water monitoring data to identify potential new mixtures in drinking water (AGES), f) BioAI- to understand the long-term impact of chemical mixtures on biodiversity and ecosystem functions by leveraging lake sedimentary archives, paleoecotoxicology and AI-based forecasting (, g) Investigation on New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) application in European freshwaters monitoring based on monitoring and

effect data. Since it is planned to submit the literature review on use of NAMs and monitoring data for describing mixture exposure relevant for regulation to a peer review journal in Y2, a final revision in Y3 is possible. Anyhow, the outcome of the case studies and the literature review will be summarized in the AD 6.18 “Dealing with mixtures in regulatory risk assessment through the use of monitoring data and NAMs”, which is part of the D6.18: Final report on risk assessment and management methods for chemical mixtures across legislations (M81). Project meetings (online) to present and discuss the progress of the case studies will be organized during Y3. Case study-specific meetings (online) for planning and progress updates will be organized by the case study leaders as needed. (Lead partner: UFZ, UBA Participants: AGES, BPI, UI, NLZOH, UKCEH, ENSP, UOB, NIVA, EA, EAWAG, UBATH).

- P6.4.1.c_Y3_Skinsenmix_RegionH will start in Y3 and will develop new tools for risk assessment and management of mixtures of skin sensitizers/irritants. In the first year of this project an overview of current knowledge gaps and practices concerning mixtures will be conducted. The skin sensitizers, which will be studied as a mixture will be selected based on the reference Chemical potency list. Mixtures will be composed based on predicted potency and function (biocide, fragrance, dye), which are found as mixtures in consumer products. In the first year the focus will be on identifying mixtures and planning and start to perform in vitro studies on single ingredients and mixtures of priority skin sensitizers and on combinations of skin sensitizers with irritants (the ingredients for the mixture, amount of tests, etc, will be discussed in the first project year and stays in the range of the submitted budget). The data management plan will be established within the first year with the dedicated Data Liaison from WP7. A project kick-off meeting (physical or online, tbd) will take place. (Lead partner: RegionH-DK, STAMI, participants: UCPH, AGES)

A6.4.2. Facilitate the regulatory acceptance and practical use of new methods

Details per project:

- P6.4.2.a_Y1_LandscapingSurvey_UNIBAS: Building on the expert consultation (structured interviews, online survey with EU chemical risk assessors) and qualitative research to develop vignettes, the focus in Y3 will be put on further analyzing gaps, barriers and drivers to the regulatory acceptance of NAMs in the hazard/risk assessment workflow (i.e., at technological, organizational, structural, cultural, and individual level). The vignettes developed in Y2 will inform the identification of regulatory-relevant, real-life scenario-based case studies (e.g., focusing on the application of NAMs to specific decision-making contexts) to be further prioritized in PARC. A workshop will be organized in Y3 to facilitate this process and the drafting of an action plan. The work will (i) combine generic, sector-agnostic as well as sector-specific approaches to understand the commonalities and differences in the current use of NAMs for risk assessment within and across the various chemical sectors; (ii) explore cross-sectorial fertilization of knowledge and practice for the use of NAMs in chemical risk assessment; and (iii) continue actively to reflect on the successful conditions for developing criteria for regulatory acceptance of NAMs to pave the way forward for NGRA. (Lead partner: UNIBAS, Participants: BPI, EAA, ENSP, INERIS, ISS, NIPH; UAVR, UoB, UBA, UKCEH, UT). Planned year 3 of PARC:

Short description of next planned key project action 4: Expand the work done in Y1-Y2 to include an environmental focus, with similar aims and objectives. (Lead partner: UKCEH. Partners involved: UAVR, UB, UKCEH, UNIBAS).

Short description of next planned key project action 5: continues previous key project action 2, i.e. conduct a more in-depth analysis to identify the key factors and drivers for a successful implementation of NAMs in the regulatory risk assessment practice. (Lead partner: UNIBAS. Partners involved: BPI, EAA, ENSP, INERIS, ISS, UAVR, UoB, UBA, UKCEH, UNIBAS, UT).

Short description of next planned key project action 6: continues previous key project action 3, i.e., identification and prioritization of real-life, context-specific, and scenario-based case studies. (Lead partner: UNIBAS. Partners involved: BPI, EAA, ENSP, INERIS, ISS, UAVR, UoB, UBA, UKCEH, UNIBAS, UT).

- P6.4.2.b_Y1_NGRApractice_VKM_NIPH aims to develop evidence-based tools and guidance for hazard/risk assessment of NAMs, which will be integrated in an overall evidence-based NGRA framework across chemical sectors. The lead partner is NIPH (represented by VKM). The other partners involved in the work Y3 are BPI, ISS, and UNIBAS. The project has a scientific advisory group including 14 participants from the following institutions/organisations/projects: Karolinska Institutet, ECHA, OECD, U.S. EPA, CAAT, EBTC, Radboud University, EFSA, JRC, University of California San Francisco, University of New South Wales, NIEHS, the ASPIS cluster, as well as observers from WP2 (BfR) and WP3 (AUTH).

The internal validity project: Two protocols describing the creation and user testing of a tool for evaluation of internal validity of in vitro studies have been prepared. The first study in the creation of the tool has been performed. In Y3, the remaining studies for the creation of the tool will be performed, as well as the user testing of the tool, and the release version of the tool will be created.

The external validity project: A protocol for the identification of external validity items will be prepared, and this study will be started.

The terminology project: The protocol will be submitted in November, and the study will be started as soon as the protocol is approved.

- P6.4.2.c_Y1_NAMAM_UT will address the existing landscape and potential acceptance of AI (artificial intelligence) & ML (machine learning) driven QSAR models to important properties in chemical risk identification with an emphasis on the regulatory use. The aim is to conduct a review and analysis of the AI & ML QSAR models and to identify best practices and further actions to ensure a transparent regulatory use, uncertainty estimation and its communication towards end-users, independent verification and understanding of the outcome of such models. Focus is on reporting standards and decision-making criteria for ML and AI predictive models in the context of NAMs and NGRA. The best examples will be identified and made available as FAIR data through the repository solutions (like QsarDB.org). Project builds on the outcome of the literature review and of the prioritization process that identified potential regulatory-relevant case studies. A more in-depth analysis of the existing knowledge of data-driven ML & AI QSARs will be conducted. Activities will include the preliminary description of a framework for more transparent reporting of predictions obtained using ML and AI models for regulatory purposes, and the

prioritization of case studies. (Lead partner: UT. Participants: INERIS, IRFM, ISS, NIPH, NIVA, UG-PL, UKCEH, UNIBAS, EA, KEMI).

Project action 1, Y3 short description: Research priorities and requirements will be finalized and the survey is in progress (the round of responses ended by the start of Y3) and results are under analysis; one to two publications is foreseen. (partners involved: UT, UG-PL, IRFM, UNIBAS, NIPH, ISS, INERIS, KEMI)

Project action 2, Y3 short description: A more in-depth analysis of the existing knowledge of data-driven ML or AI QSARs is conducted, and corresponding publications are in the writing phase, two publications are in preparation. (partners involved: UT, UG-PL, IRFM, ISS, INERIS, KEMI).

Project action 3, Y3 short description: As part of previous activity description of a framework for more transparent reporting of predictions obtained using ML & AI models for regulatory purposes will continue in Y3. (partners involved: UT, UG-PL, IRFM, UNIBAS, NIPH, ISS, INERIS, UKCEH, NIVA, EA, KEMI)

Project action 4, Y3 short description: Work for the selection of case studies will start in Y3 (partners involved: UT, INERIS, IRFM, ISS, NIPH (VKM), NIVA, UG-PL, UKCEH, UNIBAS, EA, KEMI).

A6.4.3. Developing information transfer structures and enforcement methodology for chemicals in articles to support the transition to a circular economy

Biweekly meetings with all partners will be held to monitor and discuss the progress of individual actions steering towards the overarching aim of A6.4.3. Focused working meetings will be held in between the biweekly meetings when needed. A connection with ECHA forum for enforcement has been established to continuously receive feed-back on the methods being developed under 6.4.3b and dissemination of the results. Dissemination will also occur via the agencies directly involved in the project (KEMI and TUKES).

Details per project:

- P6.4.3.a_Y1_SuProM_MU will be continued, with the completion of two ADs and one report outlining the current screening and enforcement structures for chemicals in articles and how chemical hazards are incorporated in LCA (AD6.14: Report on current screening and enforcement structures – Leader: TUKES (M28); AD6.15: Report on existing database structures with recommended structures (M36) Report on LCA incorporation of chemical hazards - Leader: MU (M36). A prolongation has been agreed with the CT for the report and AD originally planned for M24. Results from mapping activities regarding existing data structures relevant to substances in products and materials will be synthesized and summarized in a research article. Case studies testing the information structures for retrieving information for enforcement and supporting chemical hazard assessment in LCA models will be completed. (Lead partner: MU: Participants: KEMI, Rise, TUKES, VUA, VITO, TNO).

Planned year 3 of PARC:

Short description of next planned key project action 1: Synthesizing and summarizing results from the evaluation of data sources for enforcement and testing methods. Results from surveys and interviews performed during Y2 will be interpreted and gaps and needs related to analysis of chemicals in product and overall enforcement structures will be identified. Recommendations

for optimized structure of enforcement activities and project ideas will be summarized in a report AD6.14. Partners involved: MU, RISE, KEMI, TUKES, VUA.

Short description of next planned key project action 2: Testing the existing information structures and tracking how data produced in response to regulatory structures and enforcement is stored in the systems. Based on the review of databases performed during Y2 the ability to generate comprehensive occurrence data will be tested for 1) chemical class and (2) product class. The results will be summarized together with the review in AD6:15 (M36). Partners involved: MU, RISE, KEMI.

Short description of next planned key project action 3: Case study on how current information structures on chemicals in materials and articles can be used as input to Life cycle assessment (LCA) models for evaluation of chemical hazards. Information on chemicals in Life cycle inventories will be reviewed to assess the completeness of existing databases compared to other sources reviewed in Y2. The impact of data quality on LCA toxicity assessment will be evaluated and areas for improvement will be identified. The results on LCA assessment of chemical footprints and data needs will be summarized in a report (M36); Partners involved: MU, RISE, KEMI.

- P6.4.3.b_Y3_ENFORCE_KEMI will be initiated during Y3. The project will evaluate the applicability of methods of chemical identification for use in the enforcement of chemical safety legislation, to fulfil crucial needs raised in project 6.4.3a. For effective enforcement rapid screening methods that cover a wide range of restricted/SVHC substances that can be applied to a variety of sample matrices are typically needed. In evaluating methods, this project will further test to what extent databases reviewed in P6.4.3a capture the chemical composition of articles. By developing and applying rapid analytical techniques for screening and validation the project will provide a proof-of-concept methodology that could be used in enforcement of chemicals legislation. The project will have a specific focus on additives in high volume plastics and per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances in articles identified as major use categories.

Lead partner: KEMI, Participants include MU Kemi, RISE, TUKES, VUA, New partners in A6.4.3 SU and ORU

Planned Y3 of PARC.

Short description of next planned key project action 1. Testing of recently developed methods and interlaboratory comparison of selected products for PFAS analysis will be conducted for different product matrices. Product categories to be tested for PFAS will be selected based on their relative importance for environmental emissions and near-field exposure for consumers. Analysis will be performed by using available in-house methods for the same samples to evaluate the agreement of PFAS measurements between laboratories. Lead partner KEMI, Participants include MU, RISE, TUKES, VUA, SU and ORU

Short description of next planned key project action 2. Analytical methods for rapid screening of plastics will be developed based on the needs identified under P6.4.3a. Plastic product categories to be tested will be selected based on annual production numbers and quality of databases describing presence of chemical additives (e.g., construction plastics or vehicle plastics). A methodology based on data base searches by product category and polymer type

together with suspect screening using mass-spectrometry will be developed and tested. Lead partner MU, Participants include RISE, TUKES, VUA, ORU

A6.4.4. Risk assessment to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity

Details per project:

- P6.4.4.a_Y3_CRNCS1_KEMI : Science-policy scoping workshops with stakeholders will be used to continue to develop the Technical report outlining the regulatory needs for ERA development areas (Report title: Clarifying regulatory needs for advancing the environmental risk assessment of pesticides). Activity 6.4.4 follows an iterative, collaborative knowledge-building process coordinated through the CRN project. Stakeholder views will be gathered through online surveys and workshops at European, national, and regional levels. This feedback will be used to update the first existing report by refining the problem formulation, assess the current ERA framework for pesticides, and shape the continued research in PARC 6.4.4 projects. Coordination and alignment with regulatory needs will continue to be strengthened with WP 2, in particular Task 2.2 projects PARCopedia and NGRAroute, and with WP3 on communication and dissemination to stakeholders, including EU and national authorities. In this context, also the mapping of projects of relevance within PARC and external projects will thus be pursued during year 3 in order to establish new and deepen existing collaborations.

Currently a survey is being conducted to capture views on the current ERA framework among regulatory environmental risk assessors working with plant protection products under Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009. The survey is sent to more than 300 recipients in national authorities and EFSA. The survey results will be presented and discussed in follow-up workshops with regulatory risk assessors in September 2024. A key WS objective is to engage regulatory risk assessors in the collaborative knowledge-building process and ensure regulatory relevance of the research in PARC 6.4.4. The ongoing survey is conducted in collaboration with Horizon Europe projects Syberac and PollinERA, with the aim to synergize stakeholder engagement strategies as well as concrete activities.

The project will also continue to coordinate the four other projects in PARC A6.4.4 with regular coordination meetings with project leaders, Forum for Exchange meetings and an Activity 6.4.4 Workshop.

AD6.7: Technical report outlining the regulatory needs for ERA development areas. (M36 delay from originally planned M24. The rationale for the proposed delay is that project P6.4.4.a made agreement with EFSA to align and coordinate stakeholder commitment and input (survey and workshops). This to avoid duplication of work from both PARC, EFSA and stakeholders to be invited. To align with EFSA's timeplan the first workshop needs to be delayed till after month 24.) (Lead partner: KEMI Participants: UBA, FOEN, EFSA, ANSES, UOS, ULUND, NIVA)

- P6.4.4.b_Y3_PPPEXPCS2_UFZ Extension of existing project from M24 to M36. Findings reported in the technical reports produced during year 2 will be used to identify the most relevant factors for predicting PPP concentrations in surface waters within agricultural catchments as well as potential impact on predictive power of regional differences in key environmental properties. During year 3 we will close remaining knowledge gaps and ensure regulatory feasibility. We will include additional data from supporting databases in the data analysis (e.g. geo-referenced soil properties), further improve the curation of exposure monitoring data sets to eliminate

confounding factors and study artefacts and the inclusion of additional substances covering a wider range of physico-chemical properties. In the beginning of year 3 feedback from regulatory experts will also be gathered (in collaboration with project 6.4.4.a) on opportunities for improved reality-benchmarking and potential to reduced complexity in regulatory surface water exposure models. The feedback from regulators will be included in the further scoping of research questions to be explored during year 3. Moreover, the Exposure project will strengthen a cross disciplinary link between exposure modelling and effects monitoring by performing a dedicated study on benchmarking predictions based on Toxicokinetic-toxicodynamic (TKTD)-modelling and alternative approaches to aquatic effects monitoring with the SPEAR-index. This study will provide further information on an appropriate level of detail in predictive modelling for aquatic exposure. The technical reports from year 2 will during year 3 be developed into Additional deliverable AD6.20 (Technical report on factors and processes needed to be included in robust aquatic exposure predictions for regulatory use, including an assessment of geographic representativeness), based on the above mentioned results and with expert feedback from stakeholder workshops. Lead partner: UFZ (DE) Participants: SLU (SE), Fraunhofer IME (DE), UOS (DE), EAWAG (CH), NIVA (NO), ULUND (SE), IEP-NRI (PL), UoB (UK). Regulatory core group: KEMI (SE), UBA (DE), FOEN (CH), ANSES (FR), EFSA (EU).

- P6.4.4.c_Y3_PPPEFFCS3_UFZ will continue to expand the meta-database with information and data that are species related (e.g. ecological, traits), site related and methods related (e.g. omics data, Pict and Spear concepts) from national and EU-level sources. Network within PARC WPs and externally through partners will continue to be used to identify monitoring and active substance effects data sources. Using this data the project will inform on factors and processes needed to be included in the ERA to obtain an improved balance between reduced complexity and increased ecological realism. Moreover, the project will continue to test exposure models against monitoring data to support the interpretation of effects assessments in the field. In the beginning of year 3 feedback from regulatory experts will be gathered on implications of possibilities and solutions for improved reality-benchmarking and potential reduced complexity of exposure models This will be done in workshops coordinated with P6.4.4.a. The feedback from regulators will be used to define new research questions to close knowledge gaps and ensure regulatory feasibility. The project will be reported in AD 6.8 Report informing on factors and processes needed to be included in the ERA to obtain an improved balance between reduced complexity and increased ecological realism. (Lead partner: UFZ Participants: UC (PT), EAWAG (CH), SLU (SE); UKOLD (DE); ULUND (SE), NIVA (NO), UCLM (ES), UOS (DE), ISCIII (ES), Regulatory core team: KEMI (SE), UBA (DE), FOEN (CH), EFSA (EU), ANSES (FR), UKCEH (UK)).

- P6.4.4.d_Y3_PPPBENCHCS4_RPTU will continue to build a database for comparable risk quotients of authorised and non-authorised PPPs. Collected substance toxicity and physicochemical data from the current ERA regulatory process have been compiled, and use data for exposure calculations have been retrieved from national pesticide registries in different member states. Based on these data alternative ways to conduct comparable ERAs will be tested and benchmarked to monitoring and field data in collaboration with project 6.4.4.c and 6.4.4.e. Prototype comparative databases will be used as templates for further development. (Lead partner: RPTU Participants: UFZ, ISCIII, NIVA, EAWAG and ULUND). Regulatory core team: KEMI (SE), UBA (DE), FOEN (CH), ANSES (FR), EFSA (EU)

- P6.4.4.e_Y3_PPPOSCS5_ISCIII Case studies in ES, FR, PL, and NO reflecting different agricultural landscape conditions and climates will be conducted during year 3. The case studies will generate field-based data designed to test a generic conceptual model for landscape environmental risk assessment for pesticides and other stressors. Alongside with this generic model other prospective ERA methods and models, such as exposure and effect predictor models will be tested in the case studies. (Lead partner: ISCIII Participants: UFZ (DE), RPTU (DE), NIVA (NO), IEP-NRI (PL), OFB (FR), UCLM (ES), ULUND (SE), Uni Osnabrück UOS (DE), UOB (UK), UKCEH (UK), EA (UK), UAVR (PT), SYKE (FI), INERIS (FR), UC (PT), EAWAG (CH), Regulatory core team: KEMI (SE), UBA (DE), FOEN (CH), ANSES (FR), EFSA (EU))

Deliverables:

D6.1 1st Report on aggregate exposure for general population and workers, and source to dose models applied to case studies (P6.2.1.a_Y1_SourcetoDose_VITO, M36 and P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_Anse, M48) – Leader: ANSES (M36)

D6.2 1st Report on innovative methods based on PBK models (P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPk_INERIS_AUTH, M48) – Leader: AUTH (M36)

D6.3 1st Report on innovative approaches for real-life mixture RA (P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM, M48) – Leader: RIVM (M36)

D6.4 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications (P6.2.4.a_Y1_HIADDataAvailability_VITO, M66; P6.2.4.b_Y1_HIAMethod_UU-IRAS, M66; P6.2.4.c_Y1_HIACaseStudies_UU-IRAS, M42; P6.2.4.d_Y1_HIAIndicators_VITO, M42) – Leader: VITO (M36)

Additional Deliverables³

AD6.7 Technical report outlining the regulatory needs for ERA development areas (P6.4.4.a_Y1_CRNCS1_KEMI, M42) – Leader: KEMI (New delivery date M36)

AD6.9: Report on draft IATAs and associated case studies (P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM, M36; P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA_ED_UAntwerpen, M36; P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano, M36; P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR, M36) – Leader: UL-LACDR (New delivery date M30)

AD6.14: Report on current screening and enforcement structures (P6.4.3.a_Y1_SuProM_MU, M36) –Leader: TUKES (New delivery date M28)

AD6.15: Report on existing database structures with recommended structures (P6.4.3.a_Y1_SuProM_MU, M36) - Leader: MU (M36)

AD6.16: Status of integration and use of NAMs in the EU chemical regulatory risk assessment landscape – a mapping exercise and gaps & needs analysis (P6.4.2.a_Y1_LandscapingSurv_UNIBA, M36; P6.4.2.b_Y1_NGRApractice_VKM_NIPH, M36; P6.4.2.c_Y1_NAMAM_UT, M36) - Leader: UNIBAs (New delivery date M36)

³ AD6.17 (Optimizing regulatory risk assessment and management of chemical mixtures in Europe) and AD6.18 (Dealing with mixtures in regulatory risk assessment through the use of monitoring data and NAMs) will be postponed from M36 to M40 due to the delay of the projects P6.4.1.a_Y1_OPREMIXCS1_BRUNEL_UGot and P6.4.1.b_Y1_MONAMMIXCS2_UFZ, delayed from M36 to M40.

AD6.19 Technical report informing on factors and processes needed to be included in the ERA to obtain an improved balance between reduced complexity and increased ecological realism. (P6.4.4.c_Y1_PPPEFF CS3_UFZ, M36) – Leader: UFZ (M36)

AD6.20 Technical report on factors and processes needed to be included in robust aquatic exposure predictions for regulatory use, including an assessment of geographic representativeness. (P6.4.4.b_Y3_PPPEXPCS2_UFZ, M36) – Leader: UFZ (M36)

WP N°	WP7										Lead Beneficiary					VITO/UOB											
WP title	FAIR Data																										
Partner N°	1	1.1	1.6	1.10	4	6.1	8	9	15	15.2	20	24.3	25.1	25.2	25.4	25.7	26	26.4	27.2	31	32	34.5	35.2	35.12	36	49	59
Partner short name	ANSES	INSERM	INRS	BRGM	VITO	IMROH	MU	UZIS	UBA	UFZ	ISS	UnILU	KWR	TNO	UL-LACDR	WR	NIPH	NIVA	UG-PL	JSI	NIJZ	IISPV	KI	UU	AUTH	EFSA	UOB
PM/partner	24.7	3.1	1.5	7.5	32	2	80	0.6	5.5	5	4	8	1.1	4.1	2.4	1.3	2	4	4.1	29.7	6	30	0.50	5	7	2	5
Start	M25										End					M36											

Objectives

The main goal of WP7 is to support innovation and transparency in chemical Risk Assessment (RA) through improved exchange and re-use of data between different RA actors and disciplines, and through innovative data analytical approaches. The specific objectives of WP7 for year 3 are:

- Task 7.1:
 - o Updating the DMP with clusters of project-level DMPs, using the online DMP tool;
 - o Finalisation of a scientific paper on the PARC Fair Data Policy (PFDP)
 - o Finalisation of white paper on PARC FAIR ambitions and implementation roadmap;
 - o Continuous “training through doing” for Data Champions, Liaisons and FAIR Implementation Taskgroup (FIT) on use of online DMP tooling to ensure proper collection of project specific DMPs, to build the PARC domain-specific and cross-domain tools to enable FAIR metadata and data
- Task 7.2:
 - o Consolidation of the FAIR PARC data hub and expanding it with new functionalities;
 - o Implementation of identified data management use cases and ongoing identification of new use cases
 - o Enrichment of the set of controlled vocabularies at PARC level, as well as domain-specific standards
 - o First steps towards implementation of cross-domain interoperability framework for CRA
 - o Consolidation and reporting on the approaches, tools and instruments developed in the first three years
- Task 7.3:

- Selection and initial implementation of identified uncertainty and data analysis use cases and ongoing identification of new use cases.
- Development of user guidelines for different statistical analytical (meta-, pooled etc.) techniques and demonstration of the utility and feasibility of different approaches via the selected use cases.
- Gap analysis of uncertainty assessment methodologies and demonstration of the process with domain specific uses cases.
- Development of a harmonised FAIR evidence representation framework for computed entity associations
- Building a consistent data exchange schema according to the FAIR principles to integrate and assemble information from wider sources.
- Harmonising use of existing and new ontologies in text mining for AOP development. Scoping, gap analysis and initial benchmarking of data / knowledge mining and AI/ML tools.
- Enriching existing background knowledge resources for chemical risk assessment through multi-modal data analysis.

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 7.1: FAIR Data policy and implementation

Co-leaders: TNO (NL), UOB (UK)

Partners: ANSES (FR), BRGM (FR), VITO (BE), MU(CZ), UZIS (CZ), UBA (DE), ISS (IT), KWR (NL), UL-LACDR (NL), NIVA (N), UG-PL (PL), JSI (SI), KI (SE), AUTH (EL), ISSEP (BE)

Sub-contractors: GFF (BE)

No project submitted for this task

A7.1.1 PARC Data Policy and Data Management Plan

The first version of the PARC FAIR data policy was finalized (M18), although some key issues need further elaboration, including the detailed analysis of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) FAIR data levels, and how achievable these are for the different sub-domains of PARC, which will be addressed in Y3. The initial PFDP will be reformatted into a scientific paper. For this, the content will be augmented with [1] possible unidentified additional topics (using an AI model on internet resources) and [2] a semi-quantitative analysis of the relevance of different PFDP topics for different stakeholders, using text mining approaches. [Partners involved: KI, UBA, KWR, UoB, VITO, TNO, JSI, ISS and EFSA; support of GFF].

In collaboration with WP2 (PARCopedia) the PARC WP7 Glossary of key terms will be maintained and continuously updated as the various WP7 use cases produce formalised vocabularies. This, to ensure that the various A-Zs presented in PARCopedia are fully consistent and aligned with these community developed standards that are agreed with the domain experts from across PARC WPs 4-8 and formalised via the controlled vocabularies. [Partners involved: UoB, KWR, MU].

An ongoing activity throughout Y3 will be implementation of the project-level DMPs. The initial data management sections of the PARC project proposals and implementation plans (developed

in Y2) will be further elaborated, documented via the selected online DMP tool (Data Stewardship Wizard), into the final project DMPs, summarising how data have been managed, stored, archived and made FAIR. The WP7 data liaisons (see also T7.2) will support the responsible partners in the projects from the R&I WPs (e.g., represented by the Data Champion) to fill in the project specific DMPs (after training) [Partners involved: VITO, UOB, MU, UG-PL, UL-LACDR, IISPV, AUTH, TNO, ISSEP, UFZ, KI, UBA, JSI]. This work will directly feed into starting with updating and reviewing the overarching DMP (1st review of the Data Management Plan, due M42) [Partners involved: TNO, ANSES, VITO, UBA, UL-LACDR, MU, ISS].

The process for monitoring of the KPI on the number of datasets FAIRified will be extended as outlined in D1.3.

A7.1.2 Communication and Training: organisation and delivery across PARC⁴

The dedicated training programme has been completed in Y2, led by Go Fair Foundation (GFF), resulting in a set of Data Liaisons and FAIR implementation Task group will be delivered, leading to sets of facilitators and trainers able to deliver additional training in FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIP), and Metadata 4 Machines (M4M). As part of this training, the participants will develop the domain-specific FIPs for PARC, as well as develop tools and solutions to support the implementation of FAIR in PARC. [Partners involved: ISSeP, UL-LACDR, MU].

Ongoing communication and dissemination (including hands-on training) of WP7 activities – at WP, Task and Project levels, and support of data management across-WPs is needed on a continuous basis. Building on the extensive feedback during Y2, we have undergone a re-organisation of the approaches to engaging and communicating with WPs and project clusters. The training approach will be less theoretical and more hands-on and focussed on the specific datasets and experimental approaches utilised by the various projects and their partners in Y3. [Partners involved: ISS, UL-LACDR].

The FAIR Implementation Team (see also T7.2) has implemented a process for finalising documentation and deployment (roll-out) of the tools and approaches to increase data management efficiency and facilitate data use and re-use within PARC and beyond. As tools / approaches are finalised and documented, including with WP-specific training materials, these will be rolled out to WPs / project clusters via hands-on training sessions tailored to the needs of the individual WPs / project clusters, on a rolling basis. Deployed and documented tools will also be discussed with WP2 for integration into PARCopedia, with WP8 for integration into the SSbD Toolbox, with WP9 for integration into the PARC-wide training activities and inventories, and WP3 for communication and dissemination beyond PARC. [Partners involved, PL-UG, ISS, MU].

A7.1.3 FAIR Data Use Case Coordination

For increased consistency and follow up this activity has been integrated into activity 7.2.3.

Task 7.2: Data libraries

⁴ The name of the activity was modified compared to AWPY2. The previous name in AWPY2 was: Training and organisation

Co-Leaders: MU (CZ), VITO (BE)

Partners: ANSES (FR), AUTH (EL), BRGM (FR), EFSA (EU), EV-ILVO (BE), IISPV (ES), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), JSI (SI), KI (SE), MU (CZ), NIVA (NO), UFZ (DE), UG-PL (PL), UBA (DE), UL-LACDR (NL), UNILU (LU), UOB (UK), UU (SE), UZIS (CZ), KWR (NL), WR (NL)

Sub-contractors: GFF (NL)

For Task 7.2 two projects were submitted in Y1. These projects encompass a broad and integrated approach towards two specific *a priori* identified domains and cut across the different activities defined under 7.2. Additional to these projects, use cases, where possible clustered for specific domains, are identified through the established horizontal links between WP7 and R&I WPs and projects, and are added on a rolling basis. Therefore, no additional projects have been defined. Actions related to these additional use cases and clusters identified in Y2 are added under the respective activities A7.2.1 to A7.2.4 as transversal activities.

- P7.2.2.a_Y1_chemicals-in-environment_MU_VITO [Participants: MU, VITO, UFZ, BRGM, UniLU, ISSEP, JSI, ANSES, NIVA, UBA, KWR, AUTH]. The project is linked to activities under 4.2 (multiple exposure monitoring, PFAS baseline use case and ECDs) and specific activities under 6.4 such as the collection of existing exposure monitoring data on pesticides and chemicals in the articles and to some extent with A7.2.1 (the environmental component of the CRA landscaping).

Within the project, existing synergies between major data platforms/networks will be further supported (IPCHEM, NORMAN, GENASIS). The collaboration with NORMAN established in Y2, and will continue in Y3, as NORMAN has been identified as one of priority platforms for environmental data reuse and storage. New synergies will be established and supported to harmonize the (meta)data exchange templates, workflows, metadata standards, vocabularies, with the aim to increase the community data FAIRness. Pipelines will be set up to share datasets generated or compiled in PARC with IPCHEM.

The (meta)data structure analysis will also feed the PARC FAIR Data Hub environmental component.

Further on, broadening the landscaping to other matrices/other priority chemicals will take place once the whole process is completed for the first set of priority substances (PFAS, EDs, pesticides)/matrices (e.g., water) and it will allow the WP7 team to test the approach, further improve the landscaping exercise and assess the expected efforts needed when broadening to other matrices and substances and consequently also improve the design of future use cases.

A communication with other WPs will continue to identify potential use cases. The use cases will further be analyzed by the use case management group, prioritized, and implemented according to their priority.

In Y3, the project will also focus on linking the environmental data with the HBM data in close collaboration with the 7.2.2.b project, and on building and promoting FAIR enabling and FAIR supporting resources for environmental data. The as-is FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) will be consecutively assessed for major resources according to their priority, and they will serve as a basis to build a community reference FIP.

- P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO [Participants: VITO, MU, UU, UBA, ISSeP, JSI, WR].
The WP7 HBM data project will build on the Y1 and Y2 selection of relevant HBM datasets and linked communities, and the roadmap for FAIRification that has been developed (see table 1.4). Projects that will use these datasets include different 4.1.1 activities (HBM survey, monitoring and occupational hazards), Activity 4.1.3 (Guidance Values) and Activity 4.1.4 (HBM Data Analysis) in WP4, several WP6 projects (A6.2.3 -real life mixtures- and A6.4.1 -regulatory risk assessment-) and the T8.2 (Early Warning Systems) and T8.3 (risk modelling network) Tasks in WP8.

Parts (Schedule)	Actions	Participant Institution(s) (Country)
1. Transfer HBM4EU to PARC (M1 to M36)	Operation of PEH platform	VITO
2. Use case management (M1 to M42)	Use case working group	VITO, MU, UBA, ISSEP, JSI, WR
	Collaboration/exchange with IPCHEM	VITO
	Collaboration with other related data initiatives	VITO, MU
5. Implementation and testing (M18 to M42)	Implement use of data model, metadata schema and ontology	VITO, MU, ISSEP, JSI, WR, UU
	Set up HBM data platform and services, integrating tools and pipelines for harmonization, processing and quality control of existing and newly generated datasets; integration with models (WP8); pipeline for sharing of data with IPCHEM (and, in future, the EEA); connection to geospatial data; connection to environmental data; HBM dashboard	
	Depending on the outcome of the “Assessment of federated systems for privacy-preserving analysis” set up a pilot case with HBM data	

Table 1.4: Planned actions for P7.7.2.b in Y3

As mentioned, *domain-specific clusters* have been identified in Y2, among which data management activities on toxicology data. Activities on toxicology data will be coordinated by

UoB, with support from BfR (WP5) and UL-LACDR. Work plans drafted and embarked upon in Y2, will flow further into year 3.

A7.2.1 Mapping the PARC Data Landscape

[Lead: MU, Partners involved: UOB, KWR, ISS, ISSEP, UL-LACDR, UNILU, ANSES, VITO, NIVA]

A7.2.1 identifies existing databases or repositories that may be appropriate to store newly generated data for the different CRA domains. This activity is in close collaboration with WP9, where WP7 is focused mainly on the assessment of FAIRness and sustainability, and support in FAIR management of inventories (see A7.2.2) carried out by WP9 with support of WP7, or other R&I WPs in collaboration with WP9.

The landscape made available to the PARC project partners in Y2, will be enriched further with newly identified resources resulting from specific clusters and use cases. In Y3, a major focus will include detailed assessment of the PARC data landscape for Regulatory Toxicology, Omics (sequencing data, MS NTS data, phenomics), New Approach Methodologies (NAMs), Mixture Toxicology and RA Modelling. [Partners involved: UoB, KWR, ISS, UL-LACDR, ANSES, MU, VITO, NIVA]

The FAIRness of the prioritised databases/repositories' systems, standards, and methods of operations will be assessed following application of the 'as is' FAIR implementation profiles (FIPs) developed by the FAIR Implementation Team (who were trained in Activity 7.1.2). [Partners involved: UOB, ISSeP, UniLU, UL-LACDR, ANSES, MU]. Their sustainability will be assessed as well.

In parallel, the activities at the EC level related to the Common Platform for Data on Chemicals (CPDC) roadmap and implementation, will be further followed up and the proposed approaches followed to ensure the coherence of actions in the common European open data space. [Partners involved: MU, VITO, UFZ, UoB, UniLU, ANSES].

A7.2.2 PARC FAIR data hub

[Lead: MU/VITO, Partners involved: UOB, BRGM, UFZ, WR, ISS, JSI, ISSEP, NIVA]

The Proof of Concept (PoC) of the data hub will be extended with further functionalities, to support projects P7.2.2.a_Y1_chemicals-in-environment_MU_VITO, and P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO, and to cover also the data management needs of toxicology activities and use cases selected in Y1 and Y2.

A FAIRification toolbox component will be developed to provide the necessary tools for data providers to increase the FAIRness of their data (see 7.2.3). A tool/module to visualise FAIRness of datasets or underlying resources will be further developed. Conversion tools for interfacing towards established regulatory platforms (i.e., the CPDC, including ECHA, EFSA, EEA databases and IPCHEM) and other established domain-specific and national/local data platforms will be integrated. [Partners involved: VITO, MU, UoB, BRGM, ISSEP, NIVA].

The data hub will further develop the following features: [Partners involved: VITO, MU, UFZ, UoB, WR, ISS, JSI]

- publish metadata on different resource types, relevant to the chemical risk assessment community (datasets, FAIR Supporting Resources, etc). The resource types prioritised for implementation will come from use case specification and requirements identified in Y2.
- progressively include the inventories on existing datasets and databases taking place in R&I WPs and in WP9.
- develop the dashboard component (browser) to display and increase the findability of the datasets included in inventories and surveys carried out in other PARC WPs, and to track different (meta)data sets in their natural environment, in the first place for HBM and chemicals in the outdoor environment metadata, as identified by use case analysis and implementation within 7.2.2b and 7.2.2a projects.
- accommodating (meta)data structures and contents from newly identified domains and for the domains already taken up in Y1 and Y2.
- support/enable the data and/or information exchange with the other WPs (most notably WP2, WP8 and WP9). Based on inputs provided by WP9, the PARC FAIR Data Hub will also host metadata for inventories of laboratories made up in WP9.
- possibly include a provenance-based methodology for tracking the actual reuse of data (if in Y2 this is identified as a valuable contribution to the community)

Feedback will be collected from the various types of data hub stakeholders to ensure a positive evolution in terms of meeting users' requirements, alignment with the wider landscape and useability. [Partners involved: MU, UoB].

The status of the PARC FAIR data hub development at the end of Y3 will be reported in *D7.3 1st report on Data infrastructure, tools and services for FAIRification and reuse of chemical RA data*.

A7.2.3 Solutions for FAIR data: development and implementation

(for increased consistency in resource allocation and follow up, Task 7.1.3 has been integrated here from Y3 onwards)

[Lead: VITO, Partners involved: MU, AUTH, GU-PL, IISPV, ISS, ISSeP, JSI, TNO, UBA, UL-LACDR, UOB, WR, NIVA, EV-ILVO, UG-PL, UFZ]

Use case and cluster identification [Partners involved: VITO, MU, AUTH, GU-PL, IISPV, ISSeP, JSI, TNO, UBA, UL-LACDR, UOB, WR, NIVA, EV-ILVO] Priority data domains (clusters) and use cases for Y3 and Y4 will be identified and described in interaction with the non-WP7 projects, Tasks and WPs, based on their relevance to PARC projects and to regulatory stakeholders. New use cases will be described, and where possible clustered for specific domains, on a rolling basis. Dedicated working groups, consisting of domain experts and technical experts will be set up on use case or on cluster basis (formerly called Use Case Working Group(s) (UCWGs)).

Development and implementation of solutions Solving the needs for specified clusters starts from evaluation of the actual landscape (i.e., FAIR enabling resources available in the involved community, A7.2.1.). Bottlenecks for data reuse and synergies with existing data platforms are identified. FAIR Implementation Profiles and associated roadmaps and machine-actionable metadata are developed in close collaboration between domain experts from the R&I WPs, WP7

Data Liaisons and the FAIR Implementation Team in use case or cluster-based working groups (facilitated by the Facilitators and Trainers who have been trained and certified as part of T7.1.2 by the Go FAIR Foundation in Y1 and Y2, and who constitute the FAIR Implementation Team).

Generic solutions and tools developed in the projects P7.2.2.a_Y1 and P7.2.2.b_Y1 (such as lists of variables, chemical identifiers, (meta)data validation tools, tools for harmonisation, conversion between standards, semantic annotation, FAIR publication, ...) will be repurposed for other domains. Domain-specific FAIR enabling resources (such as metadata schema, data templates, harmonisation standards) will further be elaborated and implemented. This approach allows systematic co-creation of domain-, use-case or project-specific roadmaps for development and implementation of FAIR metadata and data based on the current level of maturity of the specific case (e.g., RA is further advanced than NAMs).

Apart from P7.2.2.a_Y1 and P7.2.2.b_Y1, clusters and use cases selected in Y1 and Y2 are supported further in implementing their workflows, i.e.,

- making available scientific data sources for (re)use in regulatory risk assessment, i.e., development and implementation of user-friendly tools (interfaces) to make occurrence and hazard data available in formats supported by the CPDC (i.e., IPCHEM (meta)data formats (see P7.2.2.a and P7.2.2.b), IUCLID, OECD Harmonised templates, EFSA templates, ...); [Partners involved: ISS, UL-LACDR, NIVA, MU].
- addressing domain-specific data needs and related workplans and actions identified in Y2 that address the management of hazard and toxicological data that span across WP5 and WP6 and require cross-WP alignment (coordinated by UoB, with support from BfR (WP5) and UL-LACDR). These include:
 - Regulatory toxicology (EFSA, ECHA) where endpoints are well-defined: refinement of existing harmonised templates; [Partners involved: ISS, UL-LACDR, UOB, WR, MU].
 - updating of metadata, and development of new templates for novel *in vitro* endpoints and approaches as developed for NAMs (aligned with OECD requirements for validation of methods) [Partners involved: ISS, UL-LACDR, UOB, NIVA, MU, KWR].
 - Development of a community standard for documentation of toxicological study systems (animals, organisms, organoids, cell culture systems etc.) and accompanying sampling protocols, formalised via a CEN Workshop Agreement or other appropriate means [Partners involved: UOB, MU, UL-LACDR, TNO]
 - Collaboration with the FAIR AOP cluster on FAIRification of the AOP-wiki (<https://aopwiki.org/>) and development of the new "AOP-Wiki 3.0" and AOP-related terms and concepts; [Partners involved: IISPV, UOB, UG-PL, ISS, MU]
 - Workflows for documentation and FAIRification of omics / systems toxicology modelling data to support its integration into RA; this will be done in collaboration with the ASPIS cluster (<https://aspis-cluster.eu/>) and the ELIXIR Toxicology Community implementation project (<https://elixir-europe.org/communities/toxicology>). [Partners involved: TNO, INSERM, UoB, KI, UL-LACDR, IISPV].
 - Further elaboration of the workflow, templates and data repository for ecotoxicological data for broad use by the PARC community and beyond, and testing in dedicated use cases [Partners involved: NIVA, members of FIT]
- Metadata for MS NTS data, analytical workflows and data processing (cross-WP effort in

collaboration with EMBL) [Partners involved: MU, additional partners to be confirmed during Y2].

- Use cases on FAIR elements common to many projects: finetune and improve tools for metadata management, for schema-based validation of harmonised templates, for semantic annotation, taking into account new domains and use cases; [Partners involved: VITO, MU, additional T7.2 partners to be confirmed].
- Further elaboration and implementation of the tool for automated extraction of information for the KPI on FAIR data; [Partners involved: VITO, additional T7.2 partners to be confirmed during Y2].
- Depending on concrete workplans defined in Y2 and the progress in the respective WP8 Tasks, develop and implement workflows and tools to facilitate data availability and interoperability for tools developed in T8.1 - Safe and Sustainable by Design; T8.2 - Early Warning Systems and T8.3 - Integrative Modelling Network. [Partners involved: AUTH, WR, other WP7 partners to be determined during Y2].

The ongoing work will be coordinated and monitored by the FAIR Implementation Team [Partners involved: AUTH, GU-PL, ISSeP, JSI, MU, UL-LACDR, UOB, VITO], while the FAIR Steering team prioritises and assigns new work where needed. [Partners involved: VITO, UOB, IISPV, MU, TNO, UL-LACDR, WR]

All tools that are developed in 7.2.3 to facilitate FAIRification and reuse of data, will be made available for use in the FAIRification Toolbox via the PARC FAIR Data Hub

The progress of the work done in 7.2.3 will be reported in *D7.3 1st report on Data infrastructure, tools and services for FAIRification and reuse of chemical RA data*.

A7.2.4 Standards and harmonisation

[Lead: VITO, Partners involved: IISPV, JSI, MU, UBA, UOB, VITO, WR, NIJZ, NIVA, EV-ILVO, AUTH]

The activities are planned and followed up in the Semantic Implementation Team. [Partners involved: IISPV, JSI, MU, UBA, UOB, VITO, WR].

This activity supports harmonisation and FAIRification for the use cases in 7.2.3 by providing controlled vocabularies, ontologies, harmonised metadata and data standards. The combined bottom-up (use cases and projects) and top-down (community standards and shared ontologies) approaches will be used to further enrich the consolidated set of controlled vocabularies at PARC level as well as domain-specific standards. Deliberation with various data suppliers and data users in accordance with identified use cases and priorities will define choices for technical interfacing with established communities and existing data sources that are deemed relevant by the PARC stakeholders. At the same time, existing validation and harmonization tooling that lowers the barrier in adopting these standards and interfaces will be devoted for recommendation or new tools will be developed. [Partners involved: IISPV, JSI, MU, UBA, UOB, VITO, WR, NIVA, EV-ILVO, UG-PL].

A durable list of data, metadata and project standards will be compiled and published in appropriate repositories (PARC-independent ones, such as FAIRsharing.org or FAIR Connect and PARC-specific ones, such as the PARC Data Hub or PARCopedia (WP2)), providing guidance and background info to set up training on these standards (WP9) and supporting

projects with strong important collaborative components in adopting a standards-based approach (WP8) [Partners involved: IISPV, JSI, MU, UBA, UOB, VITO, WR, NIJZ, AUTH]

Lessons from the WorldFAIR Cross-domain Implementation Framework (CDIF) (<https://zenodo.org/record/7378109>) on an overarching interoperability framework (lingua franca) and recommendations for implementation, will be incorporated as a means to interoperate across the toxicants, HBM, Environment, Toxicology, CRA and SSbD domains of PARC. WorldFAIR recommendations will be applied / road-tested and where relevant integrated into PARC Data Hub and FAIRification toolbox [Partners involved: UoB, MU, VITO, UL-LACDR].

The progress of the work done in 7.2.4 will be reported in *D7.3 1st report on Data infrastructure, tools and services for FAIRification and reuse of chemical RA data*.

Task 7.3: Innovative analyses

Co-Leaders: IISPV (ES) and UOB (UK)

Partners: ANSES (FR), AUTH (EL), EV-ILVO (BE), IMROH (CR), INRS (FR), INSERM (FR), ISSeP (BE), JSI (SI), KWR (NL), MU (CZ), NIVA (NO), UFZ (DE), UL-LACDR (NL), UOB (UK), UU (SE), UZIS (CZ), VITO (BE), WR (NL)

All scoping studies and use cases performed in T7.3 will be reported in deliverable D7.4 1st Evaluation of innovative analytical approaches and uncertainty approaches for introduction in chemical RA.

A7.3.1 Innovative methods for combined analyses of FAIR (heterogeneous) data

(Partners involved: AUTH, VITO, IISPV, ANSES, UFZ, IMROH, INRS, UOB, UL-LACDR, UNIVIE, NIVA, MU, WR).

A.7.3.1.a Combined (meta-, Pooled) data analyses

In Y3, the outcome of the scoping study will be further tested with selected use cases to demonstrate and compare the selected methods. Based on the inventories of different statistical approaches and computational tools for meta- and pooled analysis (such as Network analysis (Bayesian Network (e.g. combined with expert knowledge), frequentist network and mixed comparison), Bayesian Hierarchical meta-analysis model, and hybrid models like multilevel meta-analysis and Structural Equation modelling), concrete planning and implementation of a first few use cases will already be started in Y2, and will lead to a preliminary evaluation of selected approaches and tools. A first set of guidelines /requirements/issues of selected approaches for different datasets to be included in meta-analysis will further be drafted. [Partners involved: AUTH, VITO, IISPV, KI, ANSES, IMROH, INRS, UOB, UL-LACDR, NIVA, MU].

A.7.3.1.b Methodologies to combine and integrate hazard and exposure-response information across and within evidence domains.

Also based on the results of the scoping study (completed in year 1-2), use cases will be started to integrate available exposure studies, human epidemiological studies, biomarker studies, experimental animal studies, and in vitro studies, e.g., using Bayesian techniques to integrate data for risk assessment. A comparable use cases will be set up to integrate heterogeneous data for aggregate exposure assessment.

Potential Use Cases (Partners involved: AUTH, VITO, UL-LACDR, IISPV, KI, ANSES, UFZ, IMROH, INRS, UOB, NIVA, MU, WR)

Within the framework of WP 7.3.1, we are contacting partners from the different PARC WPs to understand which types of heterogeneous data they have, and which issues they encounter for data integration. We will gather feedback covering the data types, research questions, and data-related and methodological issues, in order to gain a better understanding of what innovative statistical methods are needed for the integration of such data.

Proposed use cases involve the integration of different data sources within or across domains, and thus the variability and uncertainty of heterogeneous data need to be considered, which is consistent with the overall goal of T7.3 and a potential synergy with A7.3.2. We will further evaluate these potential case studies and extend their models to generate a refined approach for integrating incoming extensive, heterogeneous data input.

Use case 1 (Lead AUTH, Partners involved: VITO, INRS, IMROH, UoB): A first potential use case will combine metabolomics data from multiple cohorts and/or multiple technologies (e.g., LC-MS AND NMR). Epidemiological data, human biomonitoring data and metabolomics data will be integrated and linked with health outcomes. The plethora of tools mentioned in the scoping review completed in year 2 will be integrated into a pipeline that will collect this data and, by combining machine learning approaches as well, will derive and conclude to health outcomes.

Use case 2 (Lead VITO, Partners involved: AUTH, IISPV, JSI, WR, KWR): A second potential use case linked to T6.3.2 (Real-life mixtures project) is on multiple-exposure pathway analyses which can integrate multiple mediators and/or multiple outcomes. Current epidemiological analyses on health effects of mixture exposure are mostly limited to single outcome variables, whereas the integration of biomarker information can help to unravel biological mechanisms. Given the pleiotropic nature of e.g., inflammatory and endocrine responses to mixture exposure, and the high correlation between different effect biomarkers, there is a need for methods integrating high-dimensional exposure, biomarker, and health outcome data, enabling the assessment of combined effects and relative importance of the various mixture components and biomarkers in the pathway.

Use case 3 (Lead: UL-LACDR, Partners involved: UoB, IISPV, VITO): A Case study on multi-omics integration for in vitro assays including transcriptomics, metabolomics, and phenotypic imaging data. Non-animal in vitro toxicological studies combine typically multi-omics readouts namely transcriptomics, metabolomics and other functional readouts (imaging, plate reader, ©Seahorse, FACS, etc). In this case study, we will make use of several data sets generated by several consortia in which LU-LACDR was/is involved:

1. Dataset from RISK-HUNT3R using the HEPG2 test system exposed to a group of Drug-induced liver injury (DILI) substances. The effect of these chemicals was captured using targeted high-throughput transcriptomics (©TempO-Seq) and metabolomics combined with ©Seahorse measurements.

2. Dataset from EFSA using human Peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) from healthy volunteers exposed to reference compounds inducing specific stress responses. The effects will be captured using transcriptomics, dynamic imaging and FACS analysis.
3. Dataset from Exposome-Scan NL using the HepG2 test system exposed to a library of oxidative stress inducers. Imaging, metabolomics and transcriptomics data will be collected. Concentration-response effects of high throughput transcriptomics, metabolomics and functional imaging (using fluorescent reporter cells) will be assessed at different time points.
4. Data set from PARC WP5/task 5.2 using engineered hiPSC cells expressing fluorescent cell proliferation markers differentiated into mammary glands and exposed to a series of non-genotoxic carcinogens. Phenotypic image-based approaches will be complemented by high throughput targeted mRNA sequencing using ©TempO-Seq.
 - While much effort will be made in standardizing and harmonizing the data production and collection workflow, the integration tools mentioned in the scoping review will be used for these heterogeneous datasets.

Use case 4 (Lead: NIVA, Partners involved: IISPV): Case study to integrate heterogeneous environmental exposure and effects data into a (cumulative) risk assessment workflow by 1) Standardise and harmonize reporting of environmental exposure and ecotoxicological bioassay data into controlled vocabularies and ontologies (T7.2.2a), 2) Develop GUI based import formats and data repositories to FAIRify data for consistent reporting, mapping, transfer and linkage between data sources (T7.2.2a), 3) Develop data and metanalysis pipelines to integrate (A7.3.1), analyse and visualize heterogeneous data sets representative of Aggregated Exposure Pathways (AEPs) and Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) (A7.3.2, A7.3.3, A7.3.4) and 4) identify and parametrize selected Source to Outcome Pathways (STOPs) for environmentally- and regulatory-relevant exposure scenarios. The proposed work is anticipated to involve different environmental exposure scenarios, be organized as a multi-year initiative that aligns with activities in tasks 7.3.1-7.3.4 and in extension supports developing the PARCopedia model environment (WP8.3 and P8.3.2.a)

Use case 5 (Lead: UOB, Partners involved: IISPV) Enriching existing background knowledge resources for chemical risk assessment through multi-modal data analysis. This use case will develop a methodology and workflow that is bottom-up and can be applied across WPs / projects easily. It is a multi-year use-case that spans across Tasks 7.3.1-7.3.4 but is presented here as its overarching goal is development of enhanced methodologies for data FAIRification for risk assessment. Key steps will include:

5a. Development of an approach to enable generation of “provenance networks” for scientific datasets and facts through post hoc analysis, which can be considered as a means of 'retrospectively FAIRifying science' by establishing the provenance of data/facts/etc. Given that many of the PARC projects are using literature curated datasets / grey literature, this sub-task will also explore opportunities for tracking the spread of false information (e.g., down-playing toxicity of specific chemicals or sensationalisation of results, or identification of subsets of data that contribute to overfitting for example).

5b. Based on the landscape mapping performed in T7.2.1, prioritised pubmed / biomedical / toxicological databases will be parsed for relevant toxicological entities (based on the community agreed ontology / structured vocabulary developed in Task 7.2.2); Following this, UoB will use our novel methods for identifying significant associations between pairs or groups of terms, such as sequences of key events in adverse outcome pathways, or deviations from expected patterns of occurrence that might indicate alternative pathways, supporting also the collaboration with the AOP Cluster / development of AOP-Wiki 3.0;

5c. The next step will be enrichment of the putative AOPs with clinical / toxicological data and digital phenotyping. Inversely, the use case will explore whether AOP data could be used for healthcare tasks, e.g., differential diagnosis or supporting epidemiological analyses, as a means to bridge toxicological and medical datasets more effectively.

5d. A final step, through engagement with the breadth of PARC projects will be identification of demonstration adverse outcomes / diseases, whereby the workflow and tools developed will be benchmarked, documented and applied in complex real-world settings.

A7.3.2 Methods for uncertainty characterisation, propagation and quantification as a basis for harmonisation in RA (Partner Involved: IISPV, ANSES, KWR, MU, WR)

Following the initial conceptual design, planning, and primarily data collection in Y2, activities in Y3 will be detailed implementation of selected use cases. For their implementation and evaluation use cases identified in Y2 (still ongoing) for exposure, hazard, risk, health impact assessment, and IATAs in collaboration with WP4, WP5, and WP6, will further be refined and developed. Eventually relevant outcomes will be implemented in the PARC integrative model toolbox in collaboration with T8.3. This activity will focus on qualitative and quantitative estimation of uncertainties at the different steps of the domain specific process and methodological approaches used for uncertainty propagation. Domain specific use case groups have been selected and they will be working to define the scope of each use case study. The report will recommend promising methods for further evaluation and refinement if needed. [Partners involved: KWR, WR].

Following three use cases are currently implemented and will continue in Y3.

1. Assessment of uncertainty in PBK models of PFAS exposure in humans and reverse dosimetry (uncertainty in PFAS exposure) (Lead: MU, Partners involved: IISPV, WR)
2. Bioassay Trigger Value uncertainty (Lead: KWR, Partners involved: ANSES, IISPV), Trigger values are derived based on data of individually tested chemicals in a bioassay. Roughly, the lowest measured effect in a bioassay caused by a chemical with a near-health effect at that dose is taken as the trigger value. Above this value, an effect in a sample could in theory be induced by that chemical. In reality, many other chemicals can induce effects that are less harmful. Additionally, chemicals that induce a low effect in a bioassay may have health impacts in other endpoints than measured in the bioassay. This means that there is uncertainty in interpretation of the possible risks associated with a measured effect in a bioassay and the relation to the trigger value. The case will showcase methods to quantify these uncertainties.
3. Control Coefficient analysis of PBPK model (Lead: IISPV, Partners involved: TBD): Sensitivity coefficients quantify the effects of (small) changes in any parameter on any dependent variable, whereas a control coefficient quantifies the extent to which a catalytic/biochemical process determines a system variable. The objective of this use case is to develop the system biology approach that is called Metabolic Control Analysis (MCA)

for PBPK and investigate the control coefficients that are most relevant for a toxicokinetic system.

The planning of these use cases has already started in Y2 and detailed implementation will continue in Y3.

A7.3.3 Novel computational methods for integrating and extracting knowledge from non-structured data

Details per project:

- P7.3.3.a_Y3_ALT-IST_IISPV: Scoping study for tool development, challenges, and applications is completed. Methodological development started in year 2 will continue this year with the implementation in case study with WP 5.3 immunosuppression and adult neurotoxicity group. Text mining application for WP 6 will continue in year 3 as well. Tools developed during the scoping study will be released with articles. [Partners involved: IISPV (ES), UoB (UK), ANSES (FR), INSERM (FR), JSI (SI), AUTH (EL), MU (CZ), UL-LACDR (NL), KI (SE), NIVA (NO)]

Specific actions for year 3 include:

- Harmonization and integration of scoped text mining tools into a single platform to build a customized text mining tool. [Participants: IISPV, UoB]
- Development of a harmonised FAIR evidence representation framework for computed entity associations. [Participants: UOB/IISPV]
- Systematic evaluation of methods for deriving binary and typed relationships between biomedical / toxicological entities based on transactional occurrence data. [Participants: UOB/IISPV]
- Exploration of methods for involvement of knowledge graphs in identification of entity associations from transactional occurrence data. [Participants: UOB/IISPV]
- Mapping of other information source for integration. [Participants: UOB, IISPV]
- Building a consistent data exchange schema according to FAIR principle to integrate and assemble information from wider sources. [Participants: IISPV, UoB]
- Compiling data from mapped sources in the format of chosen schema for integration (especially in the context of the developed evidence metadata format).
- Development of FAIR AOP in collaboration with WP 7.1

Use case 2 (Partners involved: UL-LACDR). Gene expression data is characterized by some accepted ontologies at the gene/protein level (e.g., NCBI Gene, UniProt, ..) and some at the pathway or functional levels (e.g., Gene Ontology, WikiPathways, ..). However, both levels are at the moment sub-optimal to inform risk assessment as they are either too detailed and not informative (gene level) or redundant and not pertinent to the toxicological experiments (pathway and functional level). Gene co-expression networks defined on the basis of exposure-derived experiment represent a good starting point to obtain data that is fitting the risk assessment domain and that achieve data dimensionality reduction, however the annotation of such co-expression networks is at the moment not standardized but expert-based and time consuming. In Y3 we will develop an automated ontology naming application, including additional data sources for genes or gene sets. These would include compound modulation and pathology information, using existing datasets (e.g., DisGeNET) and text mining on literature and clinical trials. The to-be-developed FAIR (connection to 7.2.4) ontology will be tailored for risk assessment use and will

link to the information sources used (provenance). The ontology terms with knowledge on the function of individual genes and interactions between genes/proteins within modules can then be compared to existing literature and data repositories using text mining tools.

A7.3.4 Identify additional needs in PARC for innovative analyses and promising evolutions in the data science landscape, and translate them in use cases for evaluation

The objective of this activity is to identify emerging needs in PARC for innovative analyses on one hand, and promising innovative techniques on the other hand. For the current annual plan, scoping study done in Y2 will continue. Based on this implementation planning will be executed with the steps mentioned below with collaborating partners.

Use case 1 (7.3.4.a): Pharmacophore modelling using machine learning for screening Blood Brain Barrier (BBB) permeation of xenobiotics: This use case aims to investigate the effectiveness of different fingerprints generated based on pharmacophore modeling in deciphering the blood–brain barrier permeation of xenobiotics. With pharmacophore modeling, this study will explore the influence of the P-gp protein in the transportation process. Scoping and testing with limited data sources have been completed and the work is published (<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192013471>). Data collection and further model testing started in year 2 will continue in year 3 with specific focus on identifies chemical groups in the PARC. [Partners involved: IISPV, UFZ, JSI]

To achieve this objective, the use case will perform the following activities:

- The collection of chemical data from reviewed literature sources and databases, followed by a filtering and standardization process to obtain a stabilized 3D structure.
- A scaffold of the collected data will be generated to analyze the distribution of the core structure of the chemical responsible for permeability.
- Stabilization and hydration of the protein retrieved from the protein data bank (PDB) will be undertaken, for docking purposes.
- Different methods will be explored to generate pharmacophore fingerprints including receptor-based and ligand-based methods. The residue-based pharmacophore will be generated by docking the P-gp substrates and extracting the most common residues involved in the interaction. Whereas, the interaction-type pharmacophore will be generated using the docked chemical molecules, which will further be processed with the proLIF library to generate a 9-bit fingerprint and Rdkit.
- The generated fingerprint and classical fingerprint will then be trained on a classical algorithm, such as Support Vector Machine (SVM), RF (Random Forest), and naïve Bayes, for comparison. New generation of ML method like graph model will also be implemented for methodological comparison.

This use case has been developed in consultation with WP5 and WP8 and activity will be complemented with BBB experimental data generated in Task 5.3.4a (P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Kinetics_Fraunhofer) and the computational tools for early warning system in Task 8.2.

Use case 2: Scoping study of AI&ML-driven computational NAMs for use in NGRA: Activity 7.3.4 will also collaborate with A6.4.3 with a selected project P6.4.2.c_Y1_NAMAM_UT: AI&ML-driven computational NAMs for use in NGRA lead by UT (EE) and work on landscaping

and readiness of NAMs based on advanced AI&ML approaches for use in chemical RA. This activity is a collaborative activity between two WPs and WP7.3 will support and provide input to the planned activity of A6.4.2. Here the focus is on the documentation of the data feeding into these models, and of the predictions coming out, and how to ensure transparency of these and their FAIRness. [Partners involved: UFZ, JSI, IISPV,]

Scoping studies and use cases performed in T7.3 will be reported in deliverable D7.4 1st Evaluation of innovative analytical approaches and uncertainty approaches for introduction in chemical RA.

Deliverables

D7.3 1st report on Data infrastructure, tools and services for FAIRification and reuse of chemical RA data (including P7.2.2.a_Y1_chemicals-in-environment_MU_VITO, M36; P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO, M42) – Leader: VITO (M36)

D7.4 1st Evaluation of innovative analytical approaches and uncertainty approaches for introduction in chemical RA (P7.3.3.a_Y1_ALT-IST_IISPV, M60) – Leader: UU-IRAS (M36). The leader of this deliverable is replaced by IISPV.

Additional Deliverables: No additional deliverables – most WP7 activities in year 2 and year 3 will be reported in either D7.3 or D7.4.

WP N°	WP8														Lead Beneficiary	AUTH/UNINA			
WP title	Concepts and toolboxes																		
Partner N°	1	1.1	1.4	3.3	4	4.6	8	10.2	12	13.1	14	15	20	20.3	20.4	20.6	25	25.4	25.7
Partner short name	ANSES	INSERM	INERIS	BNN	VITO	ISSEP	MU	DTU	EEA	SYKE	TTL	UBA	ISS	IRFM	IUSS	UNINA	RIVM	UL-LACDR	WR
PM/ partner	3.8	7.2	0.5	1.5	2	0.5	25.5	2.1	3.8	5.8	5.1	4	1	16.3	14.7	2.5	19.1	1.9	26.2

Partner N°	25.8	26.3	26.4	26.5	27.2	28	29.2	31.3	34.5	34.6	35.8	35.12	36	36.3	36.4	43	51	52
Partner short name	WU-TOX	NILU	NIVA	NMBU	UG-PL	FMUL	DGS	NIC	IISPV	INSST	IVL	UU	AUTH	NKUA	UOC	EMPA	BUL	Cefas-Defra

PM/ partner	0.9	2.7	1	0.3	4	1.7	1	12.7	5.2	2	8.2	6	71.5	7.1	6	12.5	1.7	0.7
Start	M25					End			M36									

Objectives

The overall goal of WP8 is to support the development and consolidation of concepts and tools for chemical risk assessment, also considering Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) chemicals and materials and their operationalisation. The specific objectives of WP8 for year 3 are:

- Task 8.1: Complete the V1.0 of the SSbD toolbox and assess its applicability through case studies
- Task 8.2: Initiate the development of the PARC EWS and design a validation framework to support the EWS based on the completion of the identification framework
- Task 8.3: Implement case studies for further mapping the needs of the PARC model network, based also on the inventory of models and tools and to deliver the first beta version of the PARC model network

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 8.1: Safe and sustainable by design (SSbD)

Co-Leaders: RIVM (NL), EMPA (CH), AUTH (EL)

Partners: INERIS (FR), BNN (AT), MU (CZ), DTU (DK), SYKE (FI), TTL (FI), UBA (DE), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), IUSS (IT), UNINA (IT), NILU (NO), NMBU (NO), UG-PL (PL), FMUL (PT), NIC (SI), INSST (ES), IVL (SE), BUL (UK), Cefas-Defra (UK)

A8.1.1. Translate EC SSbD criteria & methodology towards operationalisation

In year 3, Activity 8.1.1 comprises two lines of action:

(a) timely communication approach for dialogue between PARC 8.1 and the EC (RIVM, EMPA, AUTH), other PARC WPs (AUTH, INERIS, UBA) and outside PARC (RIVM, EMPA, IVL), with the HE WP21-22 and WP23-24 projects working on SSbD, and

(b) advancing operationalization and non-technical support to the SSbD toolbox development.

The focus of this year will be the further development and refinement of the translation of the SSbD framework for operationalization (AUTH, RIVM, EMPA, IVL) towards updating the PARC SSbD toolbox. We have conceptually linked chemical innovation with the EU SSbD assessment methodology so far. We will refine our approach by implementing a novel and comprehensive co-creation process with representatives of EC, industry, scientists and regulators in tandem with experience gained from the use cases (activity 8.1.3). We will also make a first step toward linking assessment and design aspects of the SSbD framework in terms of tools and processes (AUTH, EMPA, IVL, RIVM). The output of these activities will be 3 peer reviewed articles detailing the various technical and process aspects, decisions and pathways in the innovation based SSbD approach implemented in the PARC SSbD toolbox. This activity will provide inputs to the

PARC SSbD toolbox workflow development (activity 8.1.2) and additional case study implementation (activity 8.1.3).

The work plan in year 3 includes the activities below:

- Continued discussion and interaction with industry (RIVM, AUTH, EMPA, IVL, Unina, IUSS). A two-way communication with potential users through software development ensures that the innovation context and user needs are accurately captured, while garnering wider acceptance for SSbD framework and toolbox. Through implementing a bespoke interview and focus group approach, we have arrived at many insights on chemical innovation and the operationalization of SSbD. These will be further updated by the identification of user expectations and requirements for the SSbD toolbox (AUTH, EMPA, IUSS), including feedback of the toolbox experience from various user groups. As a follow up, we will develop a workshop to seek user feedback on the translation of the SSbD framework for operationalization, toolbox features, workflow, user interface and the case studies.
- Regulators and risk assessors have vast experience in the application of safety assessment approaches and in the interpretation of results. In workshops we will interact with regulators and risk assessors to discuss the current developments in SSbD, the SSbD-toolbox and its possible uses. We will explore questions focused on the use of SSbD seen from a regulatory context, interpretation of SSbD-results in early development stages, and balancing the outcomes from a safety and sustainability point of view. The goal of the workshops is twofold: raising awareness on the topic of SSbD in the world of regulators and risk assessor and exploring questions and issues around early innovation/low TRL assessments (RIVM, AUTH, EMPA, IVL, Unina, IUSS).
- The PARC consortium and the broader community have vast collective experience on safety and sustainability assessment methods. We will engage in in-depth technical discussions with various experts on various safety, sustainability, and socioeconomic assessment methods to further deepen the technical credibility of the toolbox and allowing incorporation of methods that can soon be implemented in the toolbox.
- We shall build a collaboration scheme with newly funded projects under HE 2023-24 (in collaboration with WP3 and CT on synergies) in the chemical and nanomaterial domains (AUTH, RIVM). Moreover, new projects and their case studies could be invited to present their vision and goals in task 8.1 meetings and periodic project updates will be set up with a view to incorporate eventually novel methods/tools under development in these projects into the PARC SSbD toolbox. We shall collaborate with the IRISS project to this end.

A8.1.2. Toolbox development

Version 1.0 of the toolbox will be delivered in the end of year 3 (RIVM, EMPA, AUTH, BNN, MU, DTU, SYKE, IRFM, IUSS, UNINA, IVL) based (a) on the further experiences that will be obtained through the case studies performed in A8.1.3. and (b) from stakeholder input, with a particular focus on potential users of the toolbox (SMEs, industry etc). Additional state-of-the-art knowledge on developments and instruments applicable for exposure (WP4), hazard (WP5) and risk assessment (WP6) (RIVM, EMPA, AUTH, INERIS, ISS, IRFM, IUSS, UNINA, UG-PL, FMUL, NIC, INSST, IVL, BUL, Cefas-Defra) and sustainability assessment (AUTH, INERIS, BNN, MU,

DTU, SYKE, UBA, NILU, NMBU, NIC, INSST, IVL, BUL, EMPA) will be implemented. Additionally, the decision support approach will be further developed, incorporating various algorithms and tools to effectively support the multi criteria decision analysis (AUTH, EMPA, SYKE). The development of the toolbox will follow a concurrent engineering and iterative approach (AUTH, IUSS). Within Y3 (end of April 2025), version 1.0 of the SSbD toolbox will be completed (AUTH, IUSS, IVL, EMPA, IRFM, DTU, TTL, MU, RIVM), building on the current version 0.1 and further elaborating on the workflow of available tools for early and late innovation stages, with an emphasis on tools amenable for use by SMEs.

Detailed actions regarding the toolbox development will include the further identification and adaptation of existing tools, either within the PARC consortium (MU, AUTH, IRFM, UG, DTU, BUL, IUSS, FMUL, TTL, NILU, ISS, INSST, NMBU, IVL, CEFAS-Defra, RIVM), or outside PARC (EMPA, RIVM, IUSS, UNINA, BNN), as well as the development of new tools, aiming to fill the implementation gaps that will be highlighted by the case studies. Particular attention will also be paid to specific modules updating user requirements and functional specifications of the SSbD toolbox to accommodate occupational safety and health aspects (TTL, UNINA, AUTH), that are critical for Step 2 of the SSbD framework. In addition, additional models for assimilating results of NAMs (and in particular omics), such as bioinformatics and systems biology models (AUTH) will be incorporated in the array of available models.

It has also been made evident that the various tools to be included in the toolbox present vast differences among them regarding the programming language (Java, Python, acslxtreme, R) and user interface (web-based, software based). The solution to these technical obstacles will include the development of a docker container. The user interface will be web-based. In some cases (for specific tools) a client-side application may be needed, executed from the web browser's window that will guide the user through the SSbD toolbox. For authentication and authorization, we will strive for all PARC systems to have a single-sign-on (SSO). To this end, we consider Life Science Login (formerly ELIXIR AAI) as the most viable solution. Finally- a very critical part of the work- is the connection of the various tools on a technical level by developing workflow pipelines. For this purpose, linking the models will take stock of the input-output relationships that have been reviewed in Y2 and will be further explored through the case studies. Options to be developed, include the following elements:

- A separate manual pipeline, in which the user places the individual tools in sequence while collecting and mapping the inputs/outputs during the process. The manual pipeline requires a way to export and input data obtained for and needed by the tools.
- Automated pipelines will be developed; although this is a long-term development, efforts towards this direction will be initiated within the 3rd year of PARC. These pipelines might represent either a new “pipeline tool”, which could be a linking portal or dashboard or as a pipeline integrated in one of the existing tools. The automated pipeline requires that the tools have interfaces for automated running of the models.

Efforts for the FAIRification of the SSbD toolbox will continue in Year 3 – in particular this will allow future models to be readily used within the same framework on the basis of a standardized input / output protocol, in relation to the ongoing work of the ontologies group in PARC.

A critical part of the work regarding the successful operation of the toolbox, will be the link with various databases that will feed with data the models (AUTH, IUSS, RIVM, EMPA, IRFM). In this direction, additional collaboration efforts with WP7 will include the use of FAIRified data, while blockchain-based systems will promote secure data sharing initiatives, that are necessary for

industrial and SME users. Blockchain technology (or other equivalent options) also enables the tracking of data usage and reuse, providing evidence of the quality and reliability of the data while simultaneously ensuring the integrity of the data being analyzed.

A summary of the timeline of the toolbox development activities is outlined in the following Gantt Chart

Actions	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36
Development of MCDA module												
Inclusion of additional tools for chemical risk assessment												
Modules to assimilate NAMs												
Improved models for occupational exposure and health												
Link modelling tools outside PARC												
Additional models functionally linked using docker containers												
Develop pipelines for key safety assessment scenarios												
Continuous efforts for PARC toolbox FAIRification												
Development of blockchain-based system for data exchange												
Single-sign-on (SSO) autorisation system												
Update wizard												

A8.1.3. Towards operationalisation: Use case & indicators

Version 0.1 of the PARC SSbD toolbox, implemented during year 3 according to the feedback from stakeholders and the added value gained in the bisphenols use case will further be operationalized and applied in additional use cases in the field of task 8.1.3. The aim of such activities will be to operationalize the integration of the toolbox benefitting from the experience gained in selected case studies (IVL, AUTH, IUSS, UBA, FMUL, UNINA, TTL, EEA, KI, BNN, Cefas-Defra, RIVM). User feedback on the PARC SSbD toolbox v.0.1 will be retrieved on the performance of the toolbox in the respective case studies in order to gain deep inside into requirements useful to expand simple tools during the process (IVL, AUTH, IUSS). In order to accelerate both the toolbox development, as well as the methodological contributions from other WPs, SSbD will be part of the cross-WPs bisphenols case study. Additional case studies will be used for the toolbox development. Selection will be based on several criteria decided and discussed under task 8.1.3 activities, with a view to cover many different aspects and application situations specifically considering conditions rich, intermediate and poor in data alternatives. The work in year 3 will allow to develop and monitor additional use cases and indicators, supporting the follow-up actions resulting from the conclusions of year 2, taking stock of the input received from various stakeholder interactions or formed in WP3 (AUTH, UBA, EEA). Additional use cases will take stock of the PARC internal 8.1.3 survey, already established connection with external projects (Mistra SafeChem) and newly established SSbD HE projects. Focus of the use case selection will be on the specific policy need from a safety/sustainability point of view, specific needs for further toolbox development and testing, and availability of user-based test networks. In addition, beyond diverse chemical families chemical products and mixtures will be considered as well.

The definition of case studies as possible settings for testing the toolbox, will be based on the inventory of candidate case studies compiled during year 1 and 2. This is a gross list based on a literature search, a questionnaire to stakeholders in 8.1, reach-out to associated projects also through an internal survey promoted during year 1, e.g. IRISS and the JRC cases, and also an outreach to other WPs in PARC to identify candidate chemicals. Use cases in year 3, will be helpful to more deeply define i) features that makes a tool useful in the context of SSbD, i.e. to determine what criteria should be used when evaluating the tools; ii) information required at each stage of SSbD; iii) endpoints useful in SSbD. According to an iterative approach, specific attention will be enforced to define workflow and involvement of tools for early and late innovation stages, with an emphasis to be used by SMEs.

This plan will consider the barriers as well as incentives for implementation collated from stakeholders involved in the use cases (IVL, UBA, UNINA). Beyond aspects related to chemicals, materials and processes and how these result in safety and sustainability aspects, additional case study definition and execution will be planned, from the viewpoint of occupational safety and health (IVL, UNINA, TTL). During Y3, the inventory of relevant indicators to follow the progresses of sector applicability of the toolbox will be further evolved, accounting from the various interactions emerging from the Y2 experience within and outside PARC, including the indicator programme foreseen by EEA and in collaboration with Task 3.2.

We are aiming for 3-5 cases for each of the steps in the SSbD procedure. As it will possibly be difficult to identify case studies that can help us test the toolbox for all steps, some case studies may only be possible for one or the other step.

Specific actions will include:

1. Workshops to discuss and agree on case studies for the v.1.0 updated toolbox operationalization
Reach out to shortlisted cases and set up meetings to discuss opportunities for collaboration around the cases. If relevant, define new cases beyond those compiled and try to find collaboration partners, inside and outside PARC.
2. Define the amount of information needed in the dry-run with use cases when moving from the EC framework stage 1-5
3. Define the indicators to be considered in the use cases, taking into account the inventory of indicators in the JRC framework and in the tools revised to prepare the version 1.0 of the toolbox
4. Decide on the final selection and establish agreements with the external stakeholders
 - a. Establish working groups/task forces among the 8.1.3. stakeholders, related to each case study
 - b. Each Task force defines a work plan for the work to be carried out, e.g. scope of work, what tools to test from 8.1.2, time plan, resources to be committed
5. Carry out the work including reporting back/exchanging experiences

A8.1.4 Knowledge sharing & Education as key factors for efficient SSbD operationalization

Building on the results of Year 2, work on the establishment of the knowledge sharing platform on SSbD will be continued (RIVM, BNN, SYKE, TTL, UBA, UNINA, NMBU, FMUL, NIC, INSST, AUTH).

Based on the document analysis of existing proposals for enabling SSbD (RIVM, INSST, FMUL) and the survey on learning needs in collaboration with WP9 (UBA, RIVM, INSST, FMUL), a learning agenda (i.e. what must be imparted and how) is deduced which will support the selection of actual material for the different elements of the knowledge sharing platform with consideration of relevance, accuracy, focus and target. In Year 2 the central elements for the knowledge sharing platform were identified and initial work was performed on the criteria needed to select appropriate material according to these elements (UBA, RIVM, IUSS, UNINA, AUTH). Focus so far has been on criteria for education/training materials (RIVM); this work will be continued in Year 3. Preferred formats of gaining knowledge independently, education and training have been identified by the stakeholder survey in Year 2 (UBA, RIVM) and these will be considered for the decision on format- and structural features when selecting actual materials for knowledge sharing, education and training. Thus, in Year 3 creation and collection of actual content for knowledge sharing, including providing links for SSbD related information, regulation and legislation, test guidelines and standards, case studies and success stories as well as an online solution for announcing events will start. In addition, the selection of relevant SSbD educational and training material will be continued.

Work in Year 3 will also include the continuation of cooperation with Tasks 3.2 (website) and 2.2 (PARCopedia) which started in Year 1. PARCopedia will provide the technical support for discussions on the SSbD framework implementation with various stakeholders held by Task 8.1; Task 8.1 will provide input on the progress of the PARC work on SSbD, with a particular focus on the toolbox development. Discussions on how to structure and present the different elements of the knowledge sharing platform started internally in activity 8.1.4 in Year 2 and will be continued with discussions with Tasks 3.2 and Task 2.2 on the technical implementation the different elements of the knowledge sharing platform, either at the PARC website and (for those materials which afford registration) at PARCopedia. Once a concept on the format and structure of this two-hosted knowledge sharing platform is finalized, filling of the platform with actual material will be started. Within Task 8.1 close exchange will be continued, e.g. with Activity 8.1.2 on the interlinks of the knowledge sharing platform and the SSbD toolbox.

Further cooperation within PARC will be established, i.e. with regard to FAIR data and data management, and how to consider that in the SSbD knowledge sharing platform.

Collaboration with JRC and RTD with regard to establishing a series of joint training schools on SSbD ("bootcamp") started in Year 2 (RIVM, UBA, AUTH). A first bootcamp hosted by JRC took place in October 2023. This cooperation will be continued in Year 3. Together with WP9, training sessions on the SSbD implementation using the PARC SSbD toolbox will be organized. Networking with partners outside of PARC will also continue in Year 3 in order to strengthen their contribution to the knowledge sharing platform by their own information/training/education material but also to support each other with regard to build a user community (RIVM, UBA, UNINA, SYKE, IVL).

Task 8.2: Scientific and technical basis for an Early warning system (EWS) on chemical risks

Co-Leaders: SLU (SE), INSERM (FR)

Partners: INRAE (FR), AU (DK), UBA (DE), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), UniLU (LU), VUA (NL), WR (NL), NILU (NO), NMBU (NO), UG-PL (PL), DGS (PT), NIC (SI), IISPV (ES), INSST (ES), ORU (SE),

IVL (SE), SLV (SE), UMU (SE), EA (UK), AUTH (EL), EFET (EL), GCSL (EL) NKUA (EL), UOC (EL)

A8.2.1 EW monitoring tools

The EW monitoring tools will be further refined and updated for the matrices of the abiotic environment (in collaboration with Task 4.2) including indoor environment and food, humans (in collaboration with T4.1) and products (in collaboration with T8.1). Hereby, it will be attempted to integrate the different prioritization components as described in AWPY1 and AWPY2 into a comprehensive scheme. Toxicity and NTS methods will be integrated towards an EDA (SLU, ORU). Mixture toxicity data from human and ecotoxicity (ISS) will be linked to NTS data (SLU, NKUA) (WP5). NTS data will be uploaded to digital data banks, for example the NORMAN digital sampling freezing platform (NKUA, AU). A machine-learning driven non-targeted approach, which is based on the quantification of the potential toxicity of chemical features, will be implemented to evaluate early warning signals of chemical compounds in food for emerging risk identification (WFSR). The EW monitoring tools will be integrated with a computational framework (A8.2.4). Ultimately, the applicability and performance of the EW monitoring tools will be validated in case studies (A8.2.3).

A8.2.2: Identification framework

The prioritization framework will be further developed in Y3 also including the following activities: i) Connection with other prioritization work in PARC and elsewhere, ii) potential adjustments in the conceptual approach and the technical content, based on developments in Y2, iii) checks of its applicability (AU and others). Other WPs in PARC also involve prioritization activities, e.g. a prioritization scheme for monitoring studies such as source tracing in T4.2, where synergies may be possible. Furthermore, trend analysis in biotic and biota matrices as a prioritization tool will be further developed (NKUA, SLU, ORU, AU) (T4.1; T4.2). Likewise, relevant innovative methods (T4.3) and regulatory risk assessment methodologies (T6.4) will be integrated in the EWS approach. A joint workshop is planned (T4.2; T2.1) with relevant PARC partners and actors outside of PARC (e.g. prioritization working group of the NORMAN network) to explore possibilities of collaboration, towards a holistic PARC monitoring prioritization scheme that includes an EWS component. In collaboration with T8.2.1, the partners will review new scientific information of relevance for EWS and prepare a memo for internal use with potential updates of previously described concepts and technical EWS content. Focus points will include, but not be limited to, a) efficient links between monitoring data, innovative methods (e.g. non-target screening) and toxicity-based signals in an EWS concept, b) chains of actions from an EWS signal (also including discussions of potential ethical questions of data sharing) and c) potential obstacles encountered in the development process. The latter will also be linked to assessments of the applicability of the prioritization approach and the EWS framework, focusing on the needs and expectations of environmental agencies and other stakeholders. Studies into applicability will also be linked with the case studies in T8.2.3.

A8.2.3: Applicability and performance testing of EW toolbox

The applicability of an EWS will be tested through pilot case studies including one or several of the different EWS components, i.e. prioritization framework, EW monitoring tools, and computational framework. Initially, suitable cases for applicability testing will be listed and reviewed. At an early stage, the focus will be to select a proof-of-concept study on environmental exposure that includes tools like EDA, HRMS screening, trend analysis, source tracing and possibly retrospective analysis. In this sense, two case studies have already been decided,

namely a) the German suspended particulate matter (SPM) study, focusing on the analysis of environmental samples (SPM from river sampling in Germany, UBA) and b), the Greek fish study, where edible fish will be analysed for assessing human exposure to various chemicals, as well non-targeted screening analysis. Later case studies will include human exposure and consumer products, as well as the other identified sources of information of the EWS. The ultimate aim is to gather cases and data for the validation of the developed concept. A core group working on case studies has been identified (ORU, SLU, UBA, AU, EFET) and capacities (human and analytical) as well as available cases, data or samples will be identified during Y3. Connections with other tasks include T4.2 (environmental and multisource monitoring case studies of PFAS and EDCs) and T4.3 (Pan-European monitoring study on wastewater, use of sentinel species and other matrices (e.g. soil, sediment) in monitoring). The execution of the task will be done in close connection with other T8.2 subtasks, including computational tools, and prioritization (e.g. NTS data handling and analysis).

A8.2.4: Computational framework to support the EWS

The computational framework will be realized using existing computational components from text mining and data curation tools towards software platforms for exposure and effect assessment. That includes development of predictive models based on systems biology and optimization of AOP-helpFinder (Inserm). A challenge is the integration of different kinds of data including effects and distribution in the environment and in organisms. The scoring system is thus critical using estimated data to identify potential hazardous chemicals. The computational framework will be tested and finetuned with case studies tailored for assessing the components and analyzing strengths and weaknesses (UG-PL). It will also be important to integrate models developed in other work packages and to assess the applicability domains of the individual modules and the entire system. During year three the open web-platform for the computational EWS will be designed (AUTH, NKUA, UMU). The platform shall enable integration of models developed in other work packages of PARC including WP6 and integrate NTS data (NKUA, AU, SLU). Integration includes scoring of individual model output to reach an overall hazard score (NKUA). Case studies will enable testing of the pilot system and further improvement (AUTH, NKUA, UMU, AU, SLU). The development of the framework will also be dependent on stakeholder input and requests and thus an interaction forum will be initiated (UMU, IVL). There is a need to align with current and coming legislation to ensure the applicability of the EWS and that the output can be effectively used. This will be evaluated using the output of pilot studies (IVL).

Task 8.3 Integrative models

Co-Leaders: WR (NL), AUTH (EL)

Partners: ANSES (FR), INERIS (FR), ISSeP (BE), MU (CZ), DTU (DK), SYKE (FI), TTL (FI), IRFM (IT), IUSS (IT), UL-LACDR (NL), WU-TOX (NL), NIVA (NO), NMBU (NO), NIC (SI), IISPV (ES), INSST (ES), UU (SE), UOC (EL)

A.8.3.1: Design, implementation and application of the PARC integrative model network

Briefly, in year 3 the model network development (activity 8.3.1) will focus on two main actions as outlined in D8.3 and AD8.4. Primarily, the general framework for integrating various models used in chemical risk assessment will be further developed (AUTH, WR, IISPV, UU, NIVA, MU). Secondly, links between and improvement of models in practical case studies will be forged,

(AUTH, WR, ANSES, INERIS, ISSeP, MU, DTU, SYKE, TTL, IRFM, IUSS, UL-LACDR, WU-TOX, NIVA, NMBU, NIC, IISPV, INSST, UU, UOC), in particular the bisphenols case study in this activity (lead from T8.3: AUTH), case studies in T6.2 (lead from T8.3: WR), and a case study on uncertainty in PFAS exposure modeling from T7.3.2 (lead from T8.3: MU). Workflows that link models from different areas, particularly models for exposure assessment (including aggregate and cumulative exposure), HBM analysis, forward and reverse dosimetry (PBK modeling), QSAR, hazard characterization, and risk / health impact assessment will be constructed for each case study.

In more detail, the primary objective of the first line of action is to extend the general framework for model integration with respect to the main areas considered. It is divided into development of a conceptual and technical framework.

- a) Conceptual framework: further development of conceptual models across different domains and harmonization/integration of these across domains (WR, AUTH, ANSES, NIVA, IISPV) to obtain a PARC metamodel that describes all relevant entities for the risk assessment of chemicals.
- b) Technical framework: a set of minimum criteria for interoperability between modelling tools and interfacing with modeling tools and workflows will be extended (AUTH, WR, UU).

These developments will take into account (user) requirements generated from projects across PARC WPs (main links: T6.2, WP7, T8.1), and the Task 8.3 case study related to bisphenols (see below). In addition, user requirements from other stakeholders will be identified in a dedicated workshop that will be organized in Y3 (AUTH). Input on (future) PARC model network requirements will also follow from collaboration with WP2 (AUTH). Further development of general framework for model integration

The inventory of models/tools within the PARC consortium will be updated based on developments of the general framework for model integration, either by direct participation in T8.3 (ANSES, INERIS, ISSeP, MU, DTU, SYKE, TTL, IRFM, IUSS, UL-LACDR, WU-TOX, NIVA, NMBU, NIC, IISPV, INSST, UU, UOC) or by links with other PARC projects (AUTH, WR). Integration of the model inventory with the PARC data hub that is developed in WP7 will be explored (MU, WR).

In Y3, development of the PARC integrative model network will continue with the first beta version of the network planned by the end of Y3 and aims to fill gaps in methodological workflows to improve chemical risk evaluations and thus address current needs while moving towards NGRA. The case studies will serve as a basis for required model links (workflows) and testing/validating of the model network. This will bring together models from various areas of the chemical risk assessment domain, including aggregate and cumulative exposure assessment (WR, AUTH, ANSES), hazard characterization (IUSS, UL-LACDR, IRFM, WR) risk assessment (WR, AUTH), uncertainty analysis (MU, WR, IISPV), HBM analysis (AUTH, WR, MU, ANSES) and PBK models (AUTH, WR, INERIS, IISPV, IUSS, ANSES, MU), while also supporting projects of other WPs (link with 6.2.1, 6.2.2, 6.2.3 and 6.2.4) (WR, ANSES, INERIS, AUTH). In this process model platforms such as INTEGRA (AUTH), MCRA (WR), RSEXPo (ANSES) and VEGAHUB (IRFM) will be further incorporated to better cover important regulatory domains of chemical risk assessment. Moreover, model harmonization efforts (in association with WP7) will be evaluated and updated, including ongoing efforts on FAIR PBK models.

The case study of bisphenols (BPA and BPA alternatives) in A.8.3.1 will continue in Y3 (T8.3 lead: AUTH) with the collection of relevant data started in Y2 (AUTH). If required data are unavailable through other PARC WPs, available data from previous EU projects (HBM4EU, HEALS, CROME) will be used. Precise case-study needs for both models and modules will be mapped and translated to network needs, which will contribute to the first beta version of the PARC model network. Exposure estimates will combine bottom-up approaches (i.e., aggregation (AUTH, WR, NIVA), multisource (AUTH), multipathway (DTU, ANSES, NIVA, SYKE, NMBU), multiroute (INERIS, UoC, IUSS)) and top-down i.e., exposure reconstruction of available HBM data (AUTH, INERIS, IUSS, WR). Internal dosimetry models will be used to translate external exposure estimates into internal dosimetry metrics and exposure reconstruction from HBM data (AUTH, INERIS, IUSS, IISPV, WR) and to feed into quantitative in-vitro in-vivo extrapolations (INERIS, IISPV, IUSS, AUTH). Use of quantitative AOPs (qAOPs) will be considered and linked to the model network to describe the toxicodynamics after triggering of molecular initiating events (MIEs) and downstream key events in collaboration with T5.3 (AUTH, UL-LACDR, WU-TOX, IUSS).

Deliverables:

D8.5 1st Report on the testing and operability, uptake and impact of the PARC EWS – Leader: INSERM (M36)

D8.6 1st Report on the development and validation of the integrative models – Leader: WR (M36)

Additional Deliverables:

AD8.5: Update of the conceptual design of the SSbD toolbox based on stakeholder input and experience from the use cases and completion of the version 1.0 of the SSbD toolbox (M36, AUTH)

WP N°	WP9										Lead Beneficiary				ISCI/III/MU							
WP title	Building infrastructural and human capacities																					
Partner N°	1	1.1	1.2	1.4	1.7	1.10	1.11	2	3.8	3.9	4.6	5	6.1	8	8.2	10.1	10.3	15	17	20.3	21	22
Partner short name	ANSES	INSERM	INRAE	INERIS	ONIRIS	BRGM	LNE	SpF	UMIT	UNIVIE	ISSEP	SCIENSANO	IMROH	MU	VSCHT	AU	REGIONH-RH	UBA	NCPHP	IRFM	RSU	NPHSL
PM/partner	0.9	3	2.1	2.1	1.3	3.8	3.9	3	1	4.6	3.7	5.6	1	43.8	4.4	5	2	2.3	3	0.40	0.4	8.9

Partner N°	24	25.7	26	26.2	26.7	28	29	29.3	29.5	30	30.1	31	31.4	32	33	34	34.2	34.4	35.2	36	36.2	37	50
Partner short name	LNS	WR	NIPH	STAMI	UNN	FMJUL	INSA	ENSP	UAVR	SZU-SK	UK	JSI	ULFFA	NIJZ	CSIC	ISCI	FISABIO	FNS	KI	AUTH	GCSL	BPI	UKHSA

PM/partner	8.2	6	1.9	5.1	1.1	4.5	16.5	4	2.8	1.3	1.2	3.3	1	1.9	17.8	26.6	2	3.2	2	3.2	3.1	3.5	1
Start	M25								End						M36								

Objectives

The overall goal of WP9 is to further develop human capacities and existing and new infrastructures related to laboratory and monitoring networks including reference laboratories, join activities and exposure monitoring networks and databases. The specific objectives of WP9 for year 3 are:

- Task 9.1:
 - Finalize the overall architecture and best-fit solution(s) for building the information catalogues on laboratory networks in collaboration with T7.2 and T9.2
 - Keep the catalogues created on exposure laboratories prioritised in Y1 and Y2 up to date
 - Extend the catalogues to include additional laboratory networks (Y3 priority fields: soil and sediment, food and feed, and finish the ongoing HBM, air and water)
 - Detect needs for laboratory network strengthening and promotion
 - Define tools to promote and coordinate laboratory networks and start with their implementation
 - Implement the concept on the laboratory network dashboard within the PARC data Hub/PARC webpage
- Task 9.2:
 - Collaborate with T7.2 and T9.1 on developing the interactive platform presenting catalogues of HBM studies, cohorts, environmental projects, networks and other relevant information collected in T9.1 and 9.2
 - Continue with the inventory of environmental contamination resources (Y3 priority: water and sediment monitoring networks and projects, indoor studies and consumer products data)
 - Collaborate with relevant WPs and Tasks to collect information on and outcomes of the ongoing surveys
 - In collaboration with T7.2 and relevant WPs contribute to the development of the harmonised templates for future surveys
 - Interact with other WPs to identify the needs for future catalogues (toxicology, models etc.).
- Task 9.3:
 - Finalize the identification of inconsistencies and gaps in existing definitions, protocols/guidances and QA/QC criteria regarding sampling, quantitative chemical analysis, and toxicity testing/kinetic studies
 - Draft generic guidance documents on sampling, quantitative chemical analysis, and toxicity testing/kinetic studies as basic principles for use in WP4 and WP5
 - Align with and review project-specific WP4 and WP5 QA/QC activities
- Task 9.4:
 - In collaboration with training (scientific) coordinators, implement PARC

training plan for Y3, as defined in AD9.1.

- Provide the necessary logistical support to organizers of local training events.
- Update PARC website to feature information on (external) existing training of potential interest to partners and stakeholders.

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 9.1: Laboratory networking

Leader: ISCIII (ES)

A9.1.1 Identify existing laboratory networks, draw up and maintain up-to-date and active a database of the laboratory networks

Partners: NPHSL, SZU-SK, ANSES, AU, BPI, BRGM, CSIC, FISABIO, FMUL, INERIS, INSA, ISCIII, LNE, MU, NIPH, SCIENSANO, STAMI, FNS, VSCHT, GCSL, RSU, UK, ONIRIS

To update the networks already created (HBM), a communication channel will be established through the PARC website. In this way we will track the inclusion of new laboratories as well as the update of information of those already included. The same approach will be applied for the catalogues for the different domains of interest already addressed in Y1 and Y2; air, indoor and water. Given the complexity of the domain articles/consumer products, their catalogues will be stepwise approached from Y3.

In addition, we will start working on the environmental field of soil and sediment (postponed from Y2 to Y3) and food and feed. The first catalogues will be available by M36.

The information collected from the laboratory networks (including name, contact, country and substances and matrices analyzed) will be translated into a more useful and attractive format. The interactive map developed and hosted in the PARC website during Y2 will be updated and improved in Y3.

A9.1.2 Promote the development of new laboratory networks and support their consolidation

Partners: FISABIO, INERIS, AU, BRGM, FMUL, INSA, ISCIII, MU, NPHSL, LNS, NIPH, SCIENSANO, ISSeP, FNS, VSCHT, GCSL, NMBU

Based on the information of existing networks and their development status, experience, extension, etc. a detailed analysis will be done to identify the weak points that need to be improved/developed to achieve a better interaction among laboratories. Additionally, alternatives to the sustainability of the networks (out of research projects) will be explored. The list will serve as a living document and will be updated alongside the gradual creation of the networks.

A9.1.3 Facilitate the coordination and linkage of existing and new laboratory networks

Partners: CSIC, INERIS, BRGM, FMUL, INSA, LNE, MU, LNS, STAMI, ISCIII, ISSeP, FNS, VSCHT, GCSL, NMBU

Initial strategies and tools to achieve the coordination and linkage of the networks have been defined in Y2. During Y3, new strategies will be explored, and the first activities will be implemented (workshops, platform to exchange information, etc.).

A9.1.4 Develop an interactive tool (dashboard) to show the capacities of the laboratory networks

The information collected from the different laboratory networks will be included in a dashboard which will be part in the future of the PARC data hub developed in collaboration with Task 7.2 (ISCI, GCSSL, LNS, NMBU, FMUL). The concept, design and technical implementation of the dashboard have been established in Y2 in collaboration with Task 3.2, Task 7.2 and all the Task 9.1 partners. During Y3, the dashboard will be implemented on the PARC Data Hub/PARC webpage and will start running with the data collected in Y1-Y2. For the upcoming years, the dashboard will be fed continuously with updated information.

Task 9.2: Building exposure monitoring capacities

Leader: MU (CZ)

A9.2.1 Mapping of exposure monitoring capacities

Partners: ANSES, Inserm, Oniris, LNE, SpF, ISSeP, Sciensano, IMROH, MU, VSCHT, AU, NCPHP, NPHSL, LNS, UU-IRAS, STAMI, FMUL, INSA, ENSP, SZU-SK, CSIC, ISCI, AUTH, BPI, GCSSL

Mapping of the existing biomonitoring and environmental exposure monitoring networks initiated in the first two years in a close collaboration with WP 4.1 and 4.2 will continue in Y3. Together with WP7.2 and Task 9.1, a tool presenting the outcomes of ongoing surveys will be developed as an important part of the PARC Data Hub. Specific attention will be paid to the harmonisation of parameters (such as biomarkers) collected across various surveys. Surveys mapping capacities (networks, projects, databases) potentially providing data on Y3 priorities (water, sediment) will continue to be distributed with the aim of developing their catalogues by M36. New effort will be directed on development of harmonised templates for such surveys.

A9.2.2 Strengthening of exposure monitoring capacities

Partners: ANSES, LNE, SpF, ISSeP, Sciensano, IMROH, MU, VSCHT, AU, LNS, UU-IRAS, FMUL, INSA, ENSP, JSI, CSIC, ISCI, GCSSL

Joint development of PARC Data Hub with Task 9.1, WP7.2 and relevant WP4 partners will provide new tools not only for presenting data on existing biomonitoring and environmental monitoring networks, laboratories and databases but for assessment of gaps and future needs. This will provide a base for better targeting of research initiatives in WP4 but also for setting priorities and development of surveys in other WPs.

Task 9.3: Joint activities – harmonisation

Leader: WR (NL)

Partners: UNIVIE (AT), SCIENSANO (BE), MU (CZ), VSCHT (CZ), UBA (DE), RegionH (DK), AU (DK), CSIC (ES), ISCIII (ES), FNS (ES), INRAE (FR), ANSES (FR), BRGM (FR), INERIS (FR), LNE (FR), ONIRIS (FR), BPI (GR), GCSL (GR), LNS (LU), NIPH (NO), UNN (NO), STAMI (NO), NMBU (NO), INSA (PT), JSI (SI), NLZOH (SI)

Transversal activity: Towards harmonised QA/QC in laboratory testing

This activity focuses on quantitative confirmatory methods. Suspect- and non-target screening and bioanalytical assays are dealt with in T4.3. Based on the inventories on QA/QC regarding sampling, chemical analysis, and toxicity testing/toxicokinetics studies, five working groups (see below) will draft guidance documents on various QA/QC parameters with focus on sample types and substances/techniques prioritised/used in Y3-Y4 of WP4 and WP5. In this, existing generic international standards (e.g. IUPAC, Eurachem, ISO/IEC 17025, OECD) and existing domain-specific protocols are taken into account, and serve as a basis for more dedicated protocols/guidances (and where appropriate criteria) for laboratory tests performed in the frame of risk assessment. The guidance documents will be disseminated through PARC internal laboratory contact lists, and to the wider community/stakeholders via the PARC website and/or PARCopedia. On-line meetings foreseen in Y3: core group (WG co-leads) 2-3x, WG meetings (4-10 per WG), and T9.3 plenary 1-2x, possibly one in person.

WG-1: Overarching QA/QC working group on Sampling. Includes: fit-for-purpose sampling, passive sampling, pretreatment, storage/stability, artifacts, uncertainty. Lead: AU, LNE. Partners: ANSES-LSAI PCPPA, ONIRIS, INERIS, BRGM, LNE, Sciensano, MU, AU, LNS, STAMI, NMBU, UNN, INSA, JSI, CSIC, ISCIII, FNS, BPI.

WG-2: Overarching QA/QC working group on Performance criteria chemical analysis. Includes: limit of detection and quantification (LOD/LOQ), identification, trueness/precision criteria, calibration, validation, batch control, measurement uncertainty. Lead: MU. Partners: ANSES, INRAE, ONIRIS, INERIS, BRGM, LNE, UNIVIE, Sciensano, MU, VSCHT, RegionH, UBA, LNS, WR, NIPH, STAMI, NMBU, UNN, INSA, JSI, BPI, GCSL.

WG-3: Overarching QA/QC working group on Assessment of interlab comparability chemical analysis. Includes: (evaluation of) protocols for proficiency testing (PT/ICI/EQUAS), small-scale interlab comparisons, catalogue for PT providers, catalogue (C)RMs. Lead: ANSES, LNE. Partners: ANSES, ONIRIS, INERIS, BRGM, LNE, Sciensano, MU, VSCHT, UBA, LNS, WR, NIPH, INSA, JSI, CSIC, ISCIII, BPI, GCSL.

WG-4: Overarching QA/QC working group on Reporting and acceptability of results from chemical analysis. Includes: reporting requirements, normalisation of results, acceptability of lab data, criteria for qualification of labs. Lead: ONIRIS, LNS. Partners: ANSES, INRAE, ONIRIS, INERIS, BRGM, LNE, UNIVIE, Sciensano, MU, VSCHT, AU, UBA, LNS, WR, NIPH, NMBU, INSA, JSI, CSIC, BPI, GCSL.

WG-5: QA/QC Effect directed assays (EDA), moved from T9.3 to T4.3)

WG-6: Overarching QA/QC working group on Toxicity testing & kinetic studies. Includes: in vivo and in vitro test systems (novel approach methods, NAMs), reporting. Lead: NIPH, STAMI. Partners: ANSES, INERIS, Sciensano, LNS, WR, NIPH, STAMI, NMBU, INSA, FNS.

Task 9.4: Training

Leader: INSA (PT)

Partners: ANSES (FR), INRAE (FR), ONIRIS (FR), BRGM (FR), LNE (FR), UMIT (AT), Sciensano (BE), MU (CZ), VSCHT (CZ), IPA (DE), IRFM (IT), RSU (LV), NPHSL (LT), LNS (LU), STAMI (NO), NMBU (NO), ENSP (PT), UAVR (PT), JSI (SI), ULFFA (SI), NIJZ (SI), CSIC (ES), ISCIII (ES), FNS (ES), IMM-KI (SE), BPI (GR), GCSL (GR), UEF (FI)

Building on data obtained in the training needs assessment survey (D9.3), a training plan has been developed (AD9.1) to cover the topics identified by partners and stakeholders. The plan includes four in-person training courses to be carried out in Y3 (1. *FAIR data and databases*; 2. *Exposure Science and modelling*; 3. *Health Risk Assessment of Chemicals – principles and applications*; and 4. *Quality Assurance and Quality Control*), under the scientific coordination of different PARC partners, namely JSI, SI (courses 1 and 4), MU, CZ (course 2) and IMM-KI, SE (course 3) and aimed at both PARC partners and stakeholders. Additionally, a remote training course on *in silico models*, coordinated by IRFM, IT, is also planned for Y3. Supplementary training materials (e.g., a slide deck on new, non-invasive matrices) will also be made available. The local organizers of training events to be carried out under PARC will receive support from task 9.4 members, covering dissemination, registration, preparation and distribution of certificates, preparation, distribution of training evaluation surveys, and training evaluation assessment.

In parallel, information on external training (outside PARC) on relevant topics (i.e.: FAIR & Databases; Human Health; Risk Assessment; Statistics & Modelling; Transferable Skills; Hazard Assessment; Exposure Assessment; Policy and Regulation) will be continuously updated on PARC website.

Deliverables:

D9.4: 1st Generic guidance documents for QA/QC on sampling; chemical analysis; toxicity, & toxicokinetics studies – Leader: WR (New delivery date M36)".

D9.5: Report on Training events Y2 – Leader: INSA (New delivery date M30)

D9.6: Update 1 of the Generic guidance documents for QA/QC on sampling; chemical analysis; toxicity, & toxicokinetics studies – Leader: WR (M32), must be cancelled as the new delivery date for D9.4 is M36.

D9.7 Laboratory catalogue and network platform (dashboard) Y3 – Leader: ISCIII (M36)

D9.8 Catalogues on environmental and biomonitoring networks Y3 – Leader: MU (M36)

D9.9 Report on Training events Y3 – Leader: INSA (M36)

Additional Deliverables:

NA

Table 2.2.b: AWP Set of Activities

Activity No	Activity Title	Lead Participant No	Short name of lead participant	Person-Months	Start Month	End month
1	Coordination and management	1	ANSES	249.4	25	36
2	A common science-policy agenda	3/12	EAA/EEA	179.1	25	36
3	Synergies, collaborations and awareness	29/36.2	INSA/GCSL	181.8	25	36
4	Monitoring and exposure	15/2	UBA/SpF	1652.1	25	36
5	Hazard Assessment	16/1	BfR/ANSES	1875.9	25	36
6	Innovation in regulatory risk assessment	25/35.7	RIVM/KEMI	1595.2	25	36
7	FAIR Data	4/59	VITO/UOB	286.9	25	36
8	Concepts and toolboxes	36/20.6	AUTH/UNINA	288.9	25	36
9	Building infrastructural and human capacities	34/8	ISCI/III/MU	227.1	25	36
			TOTAL	6536.4		

Table 2.2.c: Additional Deliverables List

WP	AD N°	AD name	Lead participant Short name	Type[1]	Dissemination level[2]	Delivery date	Description
WP2	AD2.1	Status report on NGRAroute	BfR	R	PU	Initial due date M24, postponed M29	The scope of this AD was changed from a "first draft high-level NGRAroute roadmap" to a "status report on NGRAroute". The main reason for the delay is that events regarding the COM roadmap have unfolded more slowly than originally anticipated.
WP3	AD3.1	Report on risk communication activities	EFET	R	PU	M36	AD reporting the results of survey on risk communication.
WP4	AD4.2	Periodic report on analytical methods and measurements for exposure and effect biomarkers	ISCIII	R	PU	Initial due date M12, postponed M36	AD related to P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO, M52
WP4	AD4.3	Derivation of HBM-GVs – first set	UBA	R	PU	Initial due date M12, postponed M36	AD related to P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_DerivationofHBM-GVs_UBA, M36
WP4	AD4.8	Report on the occupational exposure in general population surveys: analysis of existing data and	TTL	R	PU	Initial due date M18, postponed M29	AD related to P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasability_TTL, M29

WP	AD N°	AD name	Lead participant Short name	Type[1]	Dissemination level[2]	Delivery date	Description
		recommendations for future general population studies					
WP4	AD4.9	Final report on the prioritization project	AU/INERIS	R	PU	M34	AD related to P4.2.b_Y2_MonitoringFrame_AU_INERIS, M30
WP4	AD4.10	Description of the study concept	AU/INERIS	R	PU	M36	AD related to P4.2.c_Y3_HumanExposure_INERIS_AU, M60
WP4	AD4.11	Progress report statistical analyses	VITO	R	PU	M36	AD related to P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO, M36
WP6	AD6.7	Technical report outlining the regulatory needs for ERA development areas	KEMI	R	PU	Initial due date M24, postponed M36	AD related to P6.4.4.a_Y1_CRNCS1_KEMI, M42
WP6	AD6.9	Report on draft IATAs and associated case studies	UL-LACDR	R	PU	Initial due date M24, postponed M30	AD related to P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM, M36; P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA_ED_UAntwerpen, M36; P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano, M36; P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR, M36

WP	AD N°	AD name	Lead participant Short name	Type[1]	Dissemination level[2]	Delivery date	Description
WP6	AD6.14	Report on current screening and enforcement structures	TUKES	R	PU	Initial due date M24, postponed M28	AD related to P6.4.3.a_Y1_SuProM_MU, M36
WP6	AD6.15	Report on existing database structures with recommended structures	MU	R	PU	Initial due date M24, postponed M36	AD related to P6.4.3.a_Y1_SuProM_MU, M36
WP6	AD6.16	Status of integration and use of NAMs in the EU chemical regulatory risk assessment landscape – a mapping exercise and gaps & needs analysis	UNIBAS	R	PU	Initial due date M24, postponed M36	AD related to P6.4.2.a_Y1_LandscapingSurv_UNIBA, M36; P6.4.2.b_Y1_NGRApractice_VKM_NIPH, M36; P6.4.2.c_Y1_NAMAM_UT, M36
WP6	AD6.19 ⁵	Technical report informing on factors and processes needed to be included in the ERA to obtain an improved balance between reduced complexity and	UFZ	R	PU	M36	AD related to P6.4.4.c_Y1_PPPEFF CS3_UFZ, M36

⁵ AD6.17 (Optimizing regulatory risk assessment and management of chemical mixtures in Europe) and AD6.18 (Dealing with mixtures in regulatory risk assessment through the use of monitoring data and NAMs) will be postponed from M36 to M40 due to the delay of the projects P6.4.1.a_Y1_OPREMIXCS1_BRUNEL_UGot and P6.4.1.b_Y1_MONAMMIXCS2_UFZ, delayed from M36 to M40.

WP	AD N°	AD name	Lead participant Short name	Type[1]	Dissemination level[2]	Delivery date	Description
		increased ecological realism					
WP6	AD6.20	Technical report on factors and processes needed to be included in robust aquatic exposure predictions for regulatory use, including an assessment of geographic representativeness	UFZ	R	PU	M36	AD related to P6.4.4.b_Y1_PPPEXPCS2_SLU
WP8	AD8.5	Update of the conceptual design of the SSbD toolbox based on stakeholder input and experience from the use cases and completion of the version 1.0 of the SSbD toolbox	AUTh	R	PU	M36	–

2.3 Resources to be committed

Table 2.3.a: Summary effort table

	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	Total PMs per partner
1-ANSES	124,5	12,0	1,0	54,9	75,2	78,0	24,7	3,8	0,9	374,9
1.1-INSERM	1,0	4,5	0,0	7,1	197,4	13,2	3,1	7,2	3,0	236,5
1.2-INRAE	0,8	0,0	0,0	85,3	70,4	33,9	0,0	0,0	2,1	192,4
1.3-CEA	0,0	0,0	0,0	11,9	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	11,9
1.4-INERIS	0,8	0,0	0,0	12,8	8,4	2,0	0,0	0,5	2,1	26,6
1.5-CNRS	0,0	0,0	0,0	2,8	23,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	25,8
1.6-INRS	0,0	0,0	0,0	14,8	12,6	3,0	1,5	0,0	0,0	31,9
1.7-ONIRIS	0,0	0,0	0,0	17,6	0,0	10,3	0,0	0,0	1,3	29,3
1.8-IRSN	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	2,0	5,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	7,5
1.9-OFB	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,0	0,0	14,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	15,5
1.10-BRGM	0,0	0,0	0,0	15,3	0,0	0,0	7,5	0,0	3,8	26,6
1.11-LNE	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,3	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	3,9	4,2
1.12-CSTB	0,0	0,0	0,0	11,2	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	11,2
1.13-EHESP	4,0	0,0	0,0	16,4	0,0	0,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	20,9
2-SpF	7,4	3,0	0,5	80,4	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	3,0	94,4
3-EAA	5,5	3,5	4,0	6,5	0,0	3,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	22,5
3.1-AGES	0,6	0,0	2,0	0,0	0,0	17,3	0,0	0,0	0,0	19,8
3.2-AIT	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	12,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	12,0
3.3-BNN	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,5	0,0	1,5
3.4-MUI	0,0	0,0	0,0	31,2	21,6	3,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	55,8
3.5-MUW	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0

	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	Total PMs per partner
3.6-UG-AT	0,0	1,0	0,0	4,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	5,0
3.7-UIBK	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	14,9	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	14,9
3.8-UMIT	0,0	0,0	2,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,0	3,0
3.9-UNIVIE	0,0	0,0	0,0	4,7	39,3	1,5	0,0	0,0	4,6	50,1
4-VITO	5,8	0,0	1,0	57,2	0,0	35,7	32,0	2,0	0,0	133,7
4.1-KU Leuven	0,0	0,0	0,0	11,9	10,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	21,9
4.2-DOMG	3,3	1,2	1,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	6,0
4.3-UH	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,0
4.4-PIH	0,0	0,0	0,0	6,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	6,0
4.5-OVAM	0,0	0,1	0,0	14,0	0,0	0,9	0,0	0,2	0,0	15,2
4.6-ISSeP	0,0	0,0	0,0	31,5	0,0	15,0	8,8	0,5	3,7	59,5
4.7-UAntwerpen	0,0	0,0	0,0	19,4	32,2	17,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	69,1
5-SCIENSA NO	0,9	0,0	0,0	18,4	33,3	63,6	0,0	0,0	5,6	121,7
5.1-UGent	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	14,2	15,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	29,2
5.2-EV-ILVO	0,0	1,0	0,0	0,9	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,9
5.3-VUB	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	22,0	13,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	35,5
6-CIPH	1,1	0,5	0,5	1,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	3,1
6.1-IMROH	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	2,0	0,0	1,0	3,0
7-MOH-CY/SGL	1,1	0,5	0,5	15,5	0,0	1,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	18,6
7.1-SHSO	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
8-MU	4,9	3,0	2,0	38,6	11,5	61,4	80,0	25,5	43,8	270,8

	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	Total PMs per partner
8.1-SZU-CZ	0,0	0,0	0,0	13,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	13,5
8.2-VSCHT	0,0	0,0	0,0	7,1	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	4,4	11,5
8.3-OU	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
8.4-JU	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,2	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,2
9-UZIS	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,6	0,0	0,0	0,6
10-DEPA	1,5	0,5	0,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	2,5
10.1-AU	0,8	0,0	0,0	40,5	11,0	10,6	0,0	0,0	5,0	67,9
10.2-DTU	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	44,5	24,5	0,0	2,1	0,0	71,1
10.3-REGION H	0,0	0,0	0,0	10,0	0,0	22,0	0,0	0,0	2,0	34,0
10.4-UCPH	0,0	0,0	0,0	12,3	0,0	7,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	19,3
10.5-SDU	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	34,4	4,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	38,4
11-HB	1,2	0,5	0,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	2,2
11.1-SOM	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
11.2-UT	0,0	0,0	0,0	12,0	0,0	18,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	30,0
12-EEA	3,0	15,0	13,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	3,8	0,0	34,8
13-THL	0,1	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,1
13.1-SYKES	0,0	0,0	0,0	6,1	0,0	3,0	0,0	5,8	0,0	14,9
14-TTL	1,2	0,5	0,5	27,0	1,9	9,2	0,0	5,1	0,0	45,3
14.1-FFA	0,0	0,0	0,0	4,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	4,5
14.2-Tukes	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	3,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	3,0
14.3-UOULU	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,5
15-UBA	5,4	3,7	2,8	70,7	0,0	30,4	5,5	4,0	2,3	124,7
15.1-BfG	0,0	0,0	0,0	13,5	9,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	23,0
15.2-UFZ	0,0	0,0	0,0	57,6	59,1	31,3	5,0	0,0	0,0	153,0
15.5-UOS	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0

	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	Total PMs per partner
15.6-KUM	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
16-BfR	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	8,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	8,5
16.1-Fraunhofer	0,0	0,0	0,0	7,3	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	7,3
16.2-KIT	7,7	18,3	0,9	0,0	122,9	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	149,7
16.3-IUF	0,0	0,0	0,0	12,7	13,9	7,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	34,1
16.4-IfADo	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	11,6	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	11,6
16.5-MLU	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	48,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	48,0
16.6-RPTU	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	12,0	12,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	24,0
16.7-TUB	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
16.8-UKON	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	12,0	31,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	43,0
16.9-TiHo	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,6	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,6
16.10-UHC	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	7,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	7,0
17-NCPHP	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	6,8	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	6,8
18-UI	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	9,8	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	9,8
19-MOH	2,6	5,5	14,0	12,0	27,7	0,0	0,0	0,0	3,0	64,8
20-ISS	1,5	0,7	1,0	9,0	0,0	2,3	0,0	0,0	0,0	14,5
20.1-ICPS	0,0	0,0	0,5	4,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	5,0
20.2-CNR-IRSA	0,0	0,0	0,0	13,6	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	13,6
20.3-IRFM	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	10,3	2,7	0,0	16,3	0,4	29,6
20.4-IUSS	0,3	0,0	2,0	0,0	0,0	6,5	0,0	14,7	0,0	23,5
20.5-UMIL	0,0	0,0	0,0	7,0	9,0	3,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	19,0

	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	Total PMs per partner
20.6-UNINA	3,0	0,0	0,1	1,8	0,0	0,0	0,0	2,5	0,0	7,4
20.7-UNIPD	0,0	0,0	0,0	2,0	0,0	1,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	3,0
21-RSU	1,2	0,5	0,5	31,3	0,0	2,0	0,0	0,0	0,4	35,9
21.1-UL	0,0	0,0	0,0	4,7	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	4,7
22-NPHSL	1,0	1,0	0,5	0,3	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	8,9	11,7
23-LSMU	0,0	0,0	0,0	6,7	0,0	3,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	10,3
24-LNS	2,5	0,0	1,5	65,8	0,0	6,5	0,0	0,0	8,2	84,5
24.1-LIH	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	27,6	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	27,6
24.2-LIST	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	4,0	9,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	13,0
24.3-UniLU	0,0	0,0	0,0	21,0	0,0	0,0	8,0	0,0	0,0	29,0
25-RIVM	5,2	0,5	2,0	0,0	16,4	52,8	0,0	19,1	0,0	96,0
25.1-KWR	0,0	0,0	0,0	3,2	0,0	3,7	1,1	0,0	0,0	8,1
25.2-TNO	0,5	0,0	0,0	0,5	0,0	8,1	4,1	0,0	0,0	13,3
25.3-RUMC	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
25.4-UL-LACDR	0,6	0,0	0,0	0,0	46,7	23,3	2,4	1,9	0,0	74,9
25.5-UU-IRAS	0,0	0,0	0,0	2,6	24,0	26,2	0,0	0,0	0,0	52,7
25.6-VUA	0,0	0,0	0,0	13,5	8,0	9,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	31,0
25.7-WR	0,0	0,0	0,0	14,0	9,6	6,5	1,3	26,2	6,0	63,5
25.8-WU-TOX	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	5,2	24,0	0,0	0,9	0,0	30,1
25.9-SRU	0,0	0,0	0,0	9,5	0,0	7,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	16,5
26-NIPH	1,2	1,0	0,5	34,9	56,5	23,6	2,0	0,0	1,9	121,6
26.1-IMR	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	7,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	7,5
26.2-STAMI	0,0	1,0	4,3	9,5	15,0	27,5	0,0	0,0	5,1	62,3
26.3-NILU	0,0	0,0	0,0	5,5	6,5	2,5	0,0	2,7	0,0	17,2

	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	Total PMs per partner
26.4-NIVA	0,2	0,1	0,0	0,0	14,2	11,4	4,0	1,0	0,0	30,9
26.5-NMBU	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,5	13,0	0,0	0,0	0,3	0,0	13,8
26.6-NVI	0,2	0,0	0,0	0,0	12,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	12,2
26.7-UNN	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,3	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,1	1,3
27-NIOM	2,2	2,2	1,9	35,3	0,0	20,4	0,0	0,0	0,0	61,9
27.1-IEP-NRI	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	10,7	9,8	0,0	0,0	0,0	20,5
27.2-UG-PL	0,0	0,0	0,0	5,6	18,6	16,5	4,1	4,0	0,0	48,7
27.3-WULS-SGGW	0,0	0,0	0,0	14,2	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	14,2
28-FMUL	0,0	0,0	4,6	0,0	0,0	5,0	0,0	1,7	4,5	15,8
28.1-PL	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
28.2-UM	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
29-INSA	6,0	14,0	35,2	33,2	40,2	13,3	0,0	0,0	16,5	158,4
29.1-APA	1,0	0,0	3,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	4,0
29.2-DGS	0,0	1,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,0	0,0	2,0
29.3-ENSP	0,0	4,0	3,0	2,2	0,0	4,1	0,0	0,0	4,0	17,3
29.4-UC	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	36,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	36,0
29.5-UAVR	0,0	0,0	2,4	0,0	6,5	11,2	0,0	0,0	2,8	22,9
30-SZU-SK	3,1	0,5	0,5	9,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,3	14,4
30.1-UK	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,2	1,2
31-JSI	0,5	0,7	1,5	48,6	7,0	5,4	29,7	0,0	3,3	96,7
31.1-GeoZS	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	7,8	0,0	0,0	0,0	7,8
31.2-NIB	0,0	0,0	3,0	0,0	33,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	36,5
31.3-NIC	0,0	0,0	1,5	0,0	37,5	0,0	0,0	12,7	0,0	51,7
31.4-ULFFA	0,0	0,0	0,0	6,8	12,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,0	19,8

	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	Total PMs per partner
31.5-MFUM	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,3	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,3
32-NIJZ	4,5	2,0	5,5	10,2	0,0	18,5	6,0	0,0	1,9	48,6
32.1-OI	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	5,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	5,5
32.2-NLZOH	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,2	0,0	0,1	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,3
32.3-ARSO	0,0	0,0	0,0	2,1	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	2,1
32.4-UKCMB	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
33- CSIC	0,8	0,0	0,0	32,7	77,0	54,0	0,0	0,0	17,8	182,3
33.1-ULPGC	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,4	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,4
33.2-UNAV	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	28,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	28,5
33.3-UGR	0,0	0,0	0,0	24,8	0,0	5,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	30,3
33.4-UPO	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	12,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	12,0
34-ISCIII	4,8	0,5	2,0	38,0	44,5	22,0	0,0	0,0	26,6	138,3
34.1-EASP	0,0	0,0	0,0	6,5	0,0	0,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	7,0
34.2-FISABIO	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	2,0	3,0
34.3-FINBA	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	25,3	0,0	0,0	0,0	25,3
34.4-FNS	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	3,2	3,2
34.5-IISPV	0,5	0,0	0,0	2,5	43,0	34,5	30,0	5,2	0,0	115,7
34.6-INSST	0,0	0,0	0,0	4,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	2,0	0,0	6,0
34.7-UCLM	0,0	0,0	0,0	6,5	0,0	36,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	42,5
34.8-UPV/EHU	0,0	0,0	0,0	8,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	8,5
35-SEPA	1,2	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,2
35.1-UGOT	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	25,2	0,0	0,0	0,0	25,2

	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	Total PMs per partner
35.2-KI	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,0	8,8	0,5	0,0	2,0	12,3
35.3-ULUND	0,0	0,0	0,0	4,4	0,0	2,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	6,3
35.4-ORU	0,0	0,0	0,0	11,9	0,0	3,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	14,9
35.5-RISE	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	16,6	0,0	0,0	0,0	16,6
35.6-SU	0,6	0,0	0,0	8,5	6,5	46,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	61,6
35.7-KEMI	3,4	0,0	1,0	0,0	0,0	17,3	0,0	0,0	0,0	21,7
35.8-IVL	0,2	0,0	0,0	11,4	0,0	9,2	0,0	8,2	0,0	29,0
35.9-SLV	1,0	0,0	0,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,5
35.10-SLU	0,0	0,0	0,0	17,0	34,0	22,1	0,0	0,0	0,0	73,1
35.11-UMU	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
35.12-UU	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	16,0	0,0	5,0	6,0	0,0	27,0
36-AUTH	5,6	29,0	10,0	16,0	21,0	43,0	7,0	71,5	3,2	202,3
36.1-EFET	0,0	0,0	5,5	1,9	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	7,4
36.2-GCSL	3,0	5,0	19,0	1,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	3,1	31,1
36.3-NKUA	0,0	0,0	11,2	35,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	7,1	0,0	53,8
36.4-UOC	0,0	0,0	3,9	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	6,0	0,0	9,9
37-BPI	0,6	0,0	2,5	15,0	46,1	40,5	0,0	0,0	3,5	108,1
38-FOPH	0,0	0,0	0,5	1,0	0,0	1,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	2,5
39-AGROSCOPE	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
40-UNISANTE	0,0	0,0	0,0	6,3	0,0	14,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	20,3
41-EAWAG	0,0	0,0	0,0	26,5	23,0	10,8	0,0	0,0	0,0	60,3
42-ETHZ	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0

	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	Total PMs per partner
43-EMPA	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	12,5	0,0	12,5
44-FOEN	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	5,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	5,0
45-USI	0,0	0,0	0,0	6,2	0,0	2,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	8,2
46-UNIBAS	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	23,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	23,0
47-SECO	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,4	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,4
48-ECHA	0,0	24,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	24,0
49-EFSA	0,0	5,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	4,1	2,0	0,0	0,0	11,1
50-UKHSA	2,0	0,0	2,0	3,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,0	8,5
51-BUL	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,7	0,0	1,7
52-Cefas-Defra	0,0	1,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,7	0,0	1,7
53-UKCEH	0,0	0,0	0,0	5,0	0,0	10,1	0,0	0,0	0,0	15,1
54-EA	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,5	0,5	0,4	0,0	0,0	0,0	2,4
55-HSE	0,0	0,0	0,0	5,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	5,0
56-IOM	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,1	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,1
57-UBAH	0,0	0,0	0,0	3,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	3,0
58-UNIABDN	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,5	0,2	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,7
59-UOB	3,0	9,0	1,0	0,0	18,0	26,5	5,0	0,0	0,0	62,5
60-UCL	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	2,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	2,0
61-EPA	1,2	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,2
Total PMs	249,4	179,1	181,8	1652,1	1875,9	1595,2	286,9	288,9	227,1	6536,4

Table 2.3.b: Other major cost items (travel, equipment, infrastructure, goods and services)

1 - ANSES	Cost (€)	Justification
Equipment	66 000	Equipment costs for a confocal microscope as part of P5.2.1.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	323 878	
Total	389 878	

1.3 - CEA	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	10 400	Consumables as part of project P4.3.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	6 760	
Total	17 160	
1.4 - INERIS	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	20 318	Cellular models, test items, cell culture consumables (medium, flasks) of P5.3.4.a_Y1 (20 318€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	17 995	
Total	38 313	
1.5 - CNRS	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 660	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 1 consortium meeting as part of Task 1.1 (830€) and 1 meeting as part of project P4.3.4.a_Y2 (830€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	28 990	
Total	30 650	
1.6 - INRS	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	21 000	Laboratory consumables including for HMRS analysis and other goods as part of projects P4.1.1.4.c_Y1, P4.3.1.b_Y1, P4.3.1.d_Y1, P4.3.2.b_Y2, and P6.2.1.b_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	31 730	
Total	52 730	
1.7 - ONIRIS	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	10 000	Consumables as part of projects P4.3.3.b_Y2 and P4.3.4.a_Y2
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	20 440	
Total	30 440	
1.9 - OFB	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	16 200	Travel and subsistence as part of P6.4.4.e_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	0	
Total	16 200	
3 - EAA	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	8 940	Consumables as part of project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1 (HBM survey)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	22 090	
Total	31 030	
3.2 - AIT	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	38 520	As part of project P5.2.1.e_Y1 : Consumables for stem cell media, growth factors, coating reagents, HPLC analysis, antibodies, qPCR, high-throughput qPCR chips, Western blot reagents, DNA-methylation EPIC

		arrays, cell culture plastics, spheroid chips ; and use of large research infrastructure
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 420	
Total	40 940	
3.4 - MUI	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	60 335	Consumables as part of projects P4.3.1.d, P4.3.2.c_Y3 and P5.2.1.d_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	50 160	
Total	110 495	
3.6 – UG-AT	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	4 600	Chemical consumables for analysis as part of project P4.3.3.b_Y2
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 330	
Total	6 930	
3.8 - UMIT	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	25 000	Meeting organisation costs for the Consortium meeting in May 2024 including Stakeholder Forum, International Board, and Governing Board
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 660	
Total	26 660	
3.9- UNIVIE	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	10 000	Consumables for project P4.3.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	50 600	
Total	60 600	
4.7 - UAntwerpen	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	43 569	Chemicals, purchase and maintenance of zebrafish transgenic lines, plastic consumables for zebrafish embryo exposures, kits and products for molecular and biochemical analyses, consumables for zebrafish housing, maintenance of zebrafish housing as part of projects P5.1.2.b_Y1, P5.2.1.b_Y1, P5.2.1.c_Y1 (41 569€) Consumables for LC-MS analysis as part of project P4.2.c_Y3 (2 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	43 569	
Total	86 986	
5.2 – EV-ILVO	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	1 375	Consumables and reagents for P4.3.1.b_Y1 and P4.3.4.a_Y2
Travel and subsistence	500	Travel and subsistence as part of P4.3.4.a_Y2
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 950	
Total	4 825	
5.3 - VUB	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	30 000	Running costs and consumables related to experiments in project P6.1.1.c_Y1

Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	32 750	
Total	62 750	
6 - CIPH	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 660	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend GSB and NHCP meetings
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 060	
Total	2 720	
6.1 - IMROH	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	6 780	Travel and subsistence for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 - 2 persons to attend 2 meetings in WP6 - 2 persons to attend 1 meeting in WP7 - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP9
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	830	
Total	7 610	
7 – MOH-CY / SGL	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	41 000	Consumables and costs for analysis as part of HBM surveys as part of task 4.1 and P4.1.1.2.a_Y1 Consumables for P4.2.C_Y3 and P6.2.3.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	10 920	
Total	51 920	
8.1 – SZU-CZ	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	10 000	Consumables and costs for analysis as part of HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 720	
Total	12 720	
8.2 - VSCHT	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	9 170	Consumables and chemicals, including consumables for LC-MS and GC-MS as part of projects P4.2.c_Y3, P4.3.2.c_Y3, and P4.3.4.a_Y2
Travel and subsistence	2 490	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 3 meetings as part of WP9
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	7660	
Total	19 320	
8.4 - JU	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	3 320	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 2 meetings as part of project P4.3.3.a_Y1 (1 660€), for 1 person to attend 1 meeting for task 4.1 (830€), and for 1 person to attend 1 meeting for WP1 (830€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	2 575	Consumables for analysis as part of projects P4.3.3.a_Y1 and P4.3.3.b_Y2
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	-	
Total	5 895	
9 - UZIS	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2 622	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 2 consortium meetings in WP7 (1 422€) and for 1 person to attend 2 National Hub Contact Points meetings in WP1 (1 200€)

Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	-	
Total	2 622	
10.1 - AU	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	5 000	Consumables and laboratory materials as part of project P5.3.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	68 455	
Total	73 455	
10.4 - UCPH	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	35 500	Consumables and materials for LC-MS analyses (7 500€), SFC-MS analyses (5 000€), GCxGC-MS analyses (10 000€), high throughput ecotox analyses (5 000€) as part of project P4.3.3.a_Y1 Skin cell model with human keratinocytes and human fibroblasts as part of project P6.4.1.c_Y3 (8 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	15 490	
Total	50 990	
11 - HB	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 060	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend to 1 meeting in WP1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	830	
Total	1 890	
13 - THL	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 060	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	-	
Total	1 060	
13.1 - SYKE	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	7 500	Costs for analyses as part of project P4.2.1.b_Y2
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	13 730	
Total	21 230	
14 - TTL	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	2 000	Consumables and other chemicals as part of project P4.3.2.b_Y2
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	44 680	
Total	46 680	
14.1 - FFA	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	1 000	Publications costs related to task 4.1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	5 183	
Total	6 183	
14.2 - Tukes	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2 400	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 2 meeting as part of project P6.4.3.a_Y1

Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 830	
Total	5 230	
15.6 - KUM	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	10 000	Lab chemicals, tips, tubes, microsampling devices (VAMS, DBS), Instrument consumables (argon, sample cups), etc. related to project P4.3.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	4 320	
Total	14 320	
16.1 - Fraunhofer	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	24 000	Consumables for analyses as part of projects P4.2.1.b_Y2 and P5.1.1.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	29 225	
Total	52 395	
16.2 - KIT	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	7 500	Consumables for project P5.3.1.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	9 330	
Total	16 830	
16.3 - IUF	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	40 000	Consumables for project P5.2.1.e_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	43 780	
Total	83 780	
16.4 - IfADO	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	12 000	Consumables for project P5.2.1.b_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	12 830	
Total	24 830	
16.8 - UKON	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	25 700	Consumables for project P5.2.1.e_Y1: reagents for toxicological test and reagents for cell culture (hPSC)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 890	
Total	22 720	
16.9 - TiHo	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	20 000	Consumables for project P5.2.1.e_Y1: Cell culture medium for stem cell culture, Cell culture plastic ware, cell culture medium additives, antibodies, chemicals
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 890	
Total	21 890	
17 - NCPHP	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	84 264	Reagents, consumables, kits, cell culture as part of project P5.2.1.d_Y1 and consumables for sampling as part of project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1

Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	20 477	
Total	104 741	
18 - UI	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	21 412	Consumables and costs for analysis as part of HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	11 065	
Total	32 477	
19 - MOH	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	10 706	Consumables and costs for analysis as part of HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 120	
Total	12 826	
20 - ISS	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	45 000	Consumables related to project P4.2.1.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	53 550	
Total	98 550	
20.5 - UMIL	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	20 381	Consumables for project P5.1.1.b_Y1: Chemicals, antibodies, ELISA kits, cell culture medium and supplements, buffy coats, etc
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	18 613	
Total	38 994	
20.6 – DPH-UNINA	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	5 357	Publications costs as WP8 co-leader
Travel and subsistence	2 950	Travel and subsistence costs for 1 person to attend 4 meetings in WP1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 490	
Total	10 797	
21 - RSU	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	48 690	Consumables and costs for analysis as part of HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1 (34 940€) Consumables for sample collection and storage of biological and industrial hygiene samples as part of project P4.1.1.4.c_Y1 (10 750€) Publications fees as part of project P6.3.2.a_Y1 (3 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	20 176	
Total	70 406	
21.1 - UL	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	4690	Consumables (reagents, tubes, micropipette tips, microfilters) as part of project P4.2.1.a_Y1 and P4.2.c_Y3
Travel and subsistence	2 180	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to 1 meeting for project P4.3.3.a_Y1 and P4.2.c_Y3
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2990	

Total	9860	
22 - NPHSL	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	6 500	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 6 meetings in WP9 and for 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 720	
Total	9 220	
23 - LSMU	Cost (€)	Justification
Equipment	10 000	Equipment costs for muffle furnace for project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1
Other Goods, Works & Services	2 000	Consumables and costs for analysis as part of HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	6 610	
Total	18 610	
24.1 - LIH	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	11 367	Consumables related to project P5.1.1.b_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	20 000	
Total	31 367	
25 - RIVM	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	30 000	Consumables for project P6.1.1.b_Y1 (30 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	108 020	
Total	138 020	
25.4 – UL-LACDR	Cost (€)	Justification
Equipment	100 000	Costs for microscopy, culture facility, flow cytometry, sequencing for projects P5.2.1.a_Y1 (37 500€), P5.3.1.a_Y1 (15 000€), P6.1.1.c_Y1 (23 750€) and P6.1.1.d_Y1 (23 750€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	69 250	Costs for Cell culture, molecular biology, microscopy, transcriptomics, chemicals, disposables, plastics for projects P5.2.1.a_Y1 and P6.1.1.c_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	69 560	
Total	238 810	
25.7 - WR	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	30 940	Consumables for project P4.3.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	74 976	
Total	105 916	
25.9 - SRU	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	5 625	Materials and consumables for collection and storage of biological and industrial hygiene samples as part of project P4.1.1.4.c_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	22 315	
Total	27 940	
26 - NIPH	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	139 500	Consumables such as natural toxins and kits, RNA seq kits, panel of antibodies for project P5.1.1.c_Y3 (45 000€), P5.2.1.e_Y1 (40 000€), P5.2.1.d_Y1 (25 000€), and P5.1.1.a_Y1 (15 000€)

		Publication costs for P6.4.2.b_Y1 and P6.2.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	153 875	
Total	293 375	
26.2 - STAMI	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	22 500	Lab consumables as part of project P5.1.1.a_Y1 and P6.1.1.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	80 610	
Total	103 110	
26.5 - NMBU	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	46 000	Costs for analyses as part of project P5.2.1.e_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	12 330	
Total	58 330	
27 - NIOM	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	21 412	Consumables and costs for analysis as part of HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	30 532	
Total	51 944	
27.1 – IEP-NRI	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	22 860	Costs for laboratory materials, reagents and services as part of WP5 including project P5.1.2.b_Y1 (18 940€) Conference fees and publications costs as part of WP6 including project P6.4.4.e_Y1 (3 920€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	10 420	
Total	33 280	
27.2 – UG-PL	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	15 150	Purchase of reagents, organisms for biotests, analytical standards of investigated chemicals, laboratory accessories such as e. g. pipette tips, well plates and microplates for (eco)toxicological tests or other usable laboratory accessories for projects P4.2.a_Y1, P4.3.3.a_Y1 and P5.1.2.b_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	18 555	
Total	33 705	
27.3 – WULS-SGGW	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	62 190	Consumables and standards, solvents, reagents, services for projects P4.1.1.4.d, P4.3.1.b_Y1, P4.3.2.b_Y2, and P4.3.3.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	5 010	
Total	67 200	
28 - FMUL	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	4 010	Travel and subsistence for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meetings in WP1 (1 060€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP2 (2 120€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP8 (830€)

Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	4 010	
Total	8 020	
29 - INSA	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	63 000	Consumables and costs for analysis as part of HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1 (50 000€) Organisation of training sessions as part of task 9.4 (13 000€)
Equipment	25 000	Laboratory equipment for implementation of project P5.1.1.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	109 795	
Total	197 795	
29.1 - APA	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	830	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 490	
Total	3 320	
29.2 - DGS	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	3 920	Travel and subsistence for: - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (900€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP2 (2 120€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP8 (900€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	830	
Total	4 750	
29.3 - ENSP	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	4 980	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 5 meetings in WP9
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	9 750	
Total	14 730	
29.5 - UAVR	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	5 000	Chemicals and consumables as part of project P5.1.2.b_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	12 450	
Total	17 450	
30 – SZU-SK	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	11 940	Consumables and costs for analysis as part of HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1 (8 940€) Publication costs in project P4.1.4.2.a_Y1 (3 000€)
Travel and subsistence	7 330	Travel and subsistence for: - 1 person to attend 4 meetings in WP4 (3 780€) - 1 person to attend 4 meetings in WP9 (3 550€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	4 380	
Total	23 650	
30.1 - UK	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2 720	Travel and subsistence for: - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4 (830€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP9 (1 060€)

Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	-	
Total	2 720	
31 - JSI	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	75 380	Chemicals and consumables for projects P4.3.3.a_Y1 (41 880€), P4.3.2.c_Y3 (33 500€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	62 000	
Total	137 380	
31.2 - NIB	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	40 150	Consumables such as plastic ware, chemicals, media for growth of bacteria and cell cultures, maintainance of fish, food for fish, S9 mix, specific antibodies, preamplification kits, assays for qPCR, etc. as part of projects P5.2.1.a_Y1 (24 000€) nad P5.1.2.b_Y1 (16 150€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	17 960	
Total	58 110	
31.3 - NIC	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	7 760	Consumables for project P5.1.2.b_Y1
Travel and subsistence	830	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP8
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	27 570	
Total	36 160	
31.4 – UL FFA	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	24 000	Consumables for projects P4.2.1.a_Y1, P5.1.1b_Y1, and P5.2.1.d_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	11 660	
Total	35 660	
31.5 - MFUM	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	830	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	-	
Total	830	
32.2 - NLZOH	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2 400	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 3 meetings in WP6
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	-	
Total	2 400	
33 – CSIC	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	71 795	Costs for consumables as part of projects P4.3.4_Y2 (19 795€), P6.2.1_b_Y1 (7 000€), P6.2.2.a_Y1 (20 000€), and P6.2.3.a_Y1(25 000€): solvents, reagents, standards, glassware and supplies of mass spectrometry and chromatography
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	95 361	
Total	167 156	
33.1 - ULPGC	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 660	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP4

Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	-	
Total	1 660	
33.2 - UNAV	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	19 000	Consumables and natural toxins for assays as part of projects P5.2.1.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	6 900	
Total	25 900	
33.3 - UGR	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	22 000	Consumables as part of projects P4.1.1.4.c_Y1, P4.3.2.a_Y1 and P6.2.3.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	21 150	
Total	43 150	
33.4 - UPO	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	13 773	Consumables (Reagents, plasticware, etc) for project P5.1.2.b_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 660	
Total	15 433	
34 - ISCIII	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	88 740	Buffer for training organization (2 trainings per year including organisation and trainer costs) in T9.4, temporarily allocated to WPL ISCIII Reagents and consumables for project P5.2.1.c_Y1 (18 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	83 436	
Total	172 176	
34.1 - EASP	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	8 586	Consumables and fieldwork costs for analysis as part of HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	4 080	
Total	12 666	
34.2 - FISABIO	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	830	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP9
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 960	
Total	2 790	
34.4 - FNS	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 660	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 and 1 meeting in WP9
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 100	
Total	3 760	
34.6 - INSST	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	6 360	Travel and subsistence for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2 persons to attend 1 meeting for project P4.1.1.4.c_Y1 (2 120€) - 1 person to attend 4 meetings in WP8 (4 240€)

Other Goods, Works & Services	5 000	Consumables (vials for urine collection, solvents for analysis by Gas-Chromatography, cooler box to keep samples, shipping costs of posting samples) and use of equipment (HS-GC-FID, TD-GC-FID) for project P4.1.1.4.c_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	3 020	
Total	14 380	
34.8 – UPV/EHU	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	8 586	Consumables and fieldwork costs for analysis as part of HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 120	
Total	10 706	
35.7- KEMI	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	7 678	Costs for the organisation of meetings related to task 6.3 (5 000€) Publication costs in task 6.3 (2 678€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	23 583	
Total	31 261	
35.8 - IVL	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	8 000	Consumables including chemicals and sampling materials as part of project P4.2.c_Y3
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	39 150	
Total	47 150	
35.10 - SLU	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	90 640	Consumables for analysis and sampling as part of projects P4.3.3.a_Y1 (42 500€), P4.3.4.a_Y2 (25 420€) and P5.1.2.b_Y1 (22 720€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	52 685	
Total	143 325	
35.12 - UU	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	25 488	Consumables for project P5.1.2.b_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	15 330	
Total	40 818	
36.1 - EFET	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	6 000	Travel and subsistence for 2 persons to attend 3 meetings in WP4
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 830	
Total	7 830	
36.2 - GCSL	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	24 820	Costs for the organisation of Stakeholder Forum meetings, International Board meetings and of SYNnet Forum meetings in WP3 (20 650 €) Consumables for project P4.3.4.a_Y2 (4 170€)
Travel and subsistence	12 010	Travel and subsistence for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 3 meetings in WP1 (2 600€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP2 (2 120€) - 1 person to attend 5 meetings in WP3 (4 110€) - 1 person to attend 4 meetings in WP9 (3 180€)

Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	18 430	
Total	55 260	
36.3 - NKUA	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	30 000	Consumables related to project P4.2.1.b_Y2
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	24 980	
Total	54 980	
37 - BPI	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	51 400	Consumables including for in vitro testing, molecular biology, lab materials, chemicals etc. for project P5.1. 1.1.a_Y1 (41 400€), and P6.1.1.b_Y1 (10 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	49 160	
Total	100 560	
61 - EPA	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	830	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 060	
Total	1 890	

Table 2.3.c: Overview of planned budget per project and per Work Package

Work Package 4

Task/Project ID	Budget allocated for Y3	% Budget allocated for Y3 / total WP budget allocated for Y3	Total Budget allocated	Total WP budget at proposal stage	% Project Total Budget allocated / Total WP budget at proposal
Projects	14 022 137,67	87,32%	47 613 868,56		40,31%
P4.1.1.2.a_Y1	2 597 813,34 €	16,18%	11 749 614,32 €		9,95%
P4.1.1.4.a_Y1	32 426,85 €	0,20%	79 743,82 €		0,07%
P4.1.1.4.b_Y1	21 233,75 €	0,13%	241 029,88 €		0,20%
P4.1.1.4.c_Y1	543 904,94 €	3,39%	1 037 619,53 €		0,88%
P4.1.1.4.d_Y1	725 113,43 €	4,52%	1 403 532,44 €		1,19%
P4.1.3.1.a_Y1	357 825,91 €	2,23%	793 027,29 €		0,67%
P4.1.3.3.a_Y1	588 275,03 €	3,66%	2 334 386,24 €		1,98%
P4.1.4.2.a_Y1	573 548,45 €	3,57%	1 474 049,25 €		1,25%
P4.1.5.a_Y1	114 970,97 €	0,72%	584 625,87 €		0,49%
P4.2.1.a_Y1	2 456 142,84 €	15,30%	7 316 904,54 €		6,19%
P4.2.1.b_Y2	761 546,24 €	4,74%	2 362 738,37 €		2,00%
P4.2.c_Y3	930 109,13 €	5,79%	3 641 233,72 €		3,08%
P4.3.1.a_Y1	- €	0,00%	259 035,98 €		0,22%
P4.3.1.b_Y1	268 424,81 €	1,67%	729 918,26 €		0,62%
P4.3.1.c_Y1	62 465,05 €	0,39%	426 147,86 €		0,36%
P4.3.1.d_Y1	382 594,28 €	2,38%	1 386 822,18 €		1,17%
P4.3.2.a_Y1	946 810,09 €	5,90%	3 330 501,47 €		2,82%
P4.3.2.b_Y2	324 547,35 €	2,02%	1 044 734,54 €		0,88%
P4.3.2.c_Y3	466 704,23 €	2,91%	2 157 144,91 €		1,83%
P4.3.3.a_Y1	1 050 443,18 €	6,54%	2 598 548,75 €		2,20%
P4.3.3.b_Y2	337 453,98 €	2,10%	1 262 748,10 €		1,07%
P4.3.4.a_Y2	479 783,83 €	2,99%	1 399 761,25 €		1,18%

Transversal activities	2 036 066,27	12,68%	13 377 700,68		11,33%
Task 4.1	1 692 043,46 €	10,54%	10 925 832,20 €		9,25%
Task 4.2	289 680,12 €	1,80%	2 033 472,68 €		1,72%
Task 4.3	54 342,70 €	0,34%	418 395,81 €		0,35%
TOTAL WP4	16 058 203,94	100,00%	60 991 569,24	118 124 452,00	51,63%

Work Package 5

Task/Project ID	Budget allocated for Y3	% Budget allocated for Y3 / total WP budget allocated for Y3	Total Budget allocated	Total WP budget at proposal stage	% Project Total Budget allocated / Total WP budget at proposal
Projects	15 545 250,54	92,14%	50 255 335,26		52,02%
P5.1.1.a_Y1	1 589 442,70	9,42%	4 984 130,17		5,16%
P5.1.1.b_Y1	1 057 087,99	6,27%	3 562 262,66		3,69%
P5.1.1.c_Y3	638 666,59	3,79%	1 312 322,21		1,36%
P5.1.2.a_Y1	173 479,38	1,03%	501 413,84		0,52%
P5.1.2.b_Y1	2 409 221,84	14,28%	8 108 156,77		8,39%
P5.2.1.a_Y1	1 596 779,88	9,46%	6 181 076,19		6,40%
P5.2.1.b_Y1	690 824,79	4,09%	2 316 391,83		2,40%
P5.2.1.c_Y1	1 086 665,76	6,44%	3 425 417,26		3,55%
P5.2.1.d_Y1	1 687 059,91	10,00%	5 260 680,94		5,45%
P5.2.1.e_Y1	1 600 576,29	9,49%	4 803 408,96		4,97%
P5.3.1.a_Y1	958 816,63	5,68%	3 302 200,10		3,42%
P5.3.2.a_Y1	975 121,93	5,78%	3 315 845,04		3,43%
P5.3.4.a_Y1	1 081 506,87	6,41%	3 182 029,30		3,29%
Transversal activities	1 326 812,20	7,86%	9 583 689,11		9,92%
Task 5.1	500 394,25	2,97%	3 627 370,98		3,75%
Task 5.2	540 775,17	3,21%	3 812 017,87		3,95%
Task 5.3	285 642,77	1,69%	2 144 300,26		2,22%
TOTAL WP5	16 872 062,74	100,00%	59 839 024,37	96 602 616,00	61,94%

Work Package 6

Task/Project ID	Budget allocated for Y3	% Budget allocated for Y3 / total WP budget allocated for Y3	Total Budget allocated	Total WP budget at proposal stage	% Project Total Budget allocated / Total WP budget at proposal
Projects	12 470 896,29	93,74%	42 366 106,94		57,74%
P6.1.1.a_Y1	395 291,75	2,97%	1 184 329,66		1,61%
P6.1.1.b_Y1	796 880,43	5,99%	2 241 553,63		3,05%
P6.1.1.c_Y1	1 029 328,40	7,74%	2 556 713,15		3,48%
P6.1.1.d_Y1	499 815,41	3,76%	1 412 667,32		1,93%
P6.2.1.a_Y1	387 856,40	2,92%	1 055 440,69		1,44%
P6.2.1.b_Y1	967 434,79	7,27%	3 700 511,37		5,04%
P6.2.2.a_Y1	761 344,78	5,72%	2 751 203,72		3,75%
P6.2.3.a_Y1	1 959 955,06	14,73%	7 106 697,78		9,68%
P6.2.4.a_Y1	360 540,82	2,71%	2 036 006,00		2,77%
P6.2.4.b_Y1	474 670,44	3,57%	2 859 059,17		3,90%
P6.2.4.c_Y1	221 232,65	1,66%	861 107,64		1,17%
P6.2.4.d_Y1	158 771,94	1,19%	613 187,40		0,84%
P6.3.1.a_Y1	250 615,00	1,88%	860 122,63		1,17%
P6.3.1.b_Y1	425 757,94	3,20%	1 724 756,87		2,35%
P6.3.2.a_Y1	501 426,89	3,77%	1 797 348,71		2,45%
P6.4.1.a_Y1	490 128,52	3,68%	1 238 928,15		1,69%
P6.4.1.b_Y1	220 330,52	1,66%	696 267,90		0,95%
P6.4.1.c_Y3	262 488,13	1,97%	949 625,00		1,29%
P6.4.2.a_Y1	84 515,94	0,64%	225 291,58		0,31%
P6.4.2.b_Y1	152 781,38	1,15%	445 885,56		0,61%
P6.4.2.c_Y1	138 673,94	1,04%	385 203,69		0,52%
P6.4.3.a_Y1	272 554,38	2,05%	702 020,63		0,96%
P6.4.3.b_Y3	228 256,38	1,72%	1 029 618,63		1,40%
P6.4.4.a_Y1	232 233,36	1,75%	781 891,58		1,07%
P6.4.4.b_Y1	224 698,38	1,69%	614 834,24		0,84%
P6.4.4.c_Y1	282 811,56	2,13%	657 419,06		0,90%
P6.4.4.d_Y1	160 040,45	1,20%	603 079,96		0,82%
P6.4.4.e_Y1	530 460,70	3,99%	1 275 335,23		1,74%
Transversal activities	832 518,80	6,26%	7 100 042,31		9,68%
Task 6.1	202 514,38	1,52%	1 900 406,69		2,59%
Task 6.2	143 843,22	1,08%	1 597 543,72		2,18%
Task 6.3	106 406,84	0,80%	768 367,55		1,05%
Task 6.4	379 754,37	2,85%	2 833 724,35		3,86%
TOTAL WP6	13 303 415,09	100,00%	49 466 149,25	73 379 540,00	67,41%

Work Package 7

Task/Project ID	Budget allocated for Y3	% Budget allocated for Y3 / total WP budget allocated for Y3	Total Budget allocated	Total WP budget at proposal stage	% Project Total Budget allocated / Total WP budget at proposal
Projects	1 762 852,99	65,98%	4 870 385,41		22,25%
P7.2.2.a_Y1	763 353,12	28,57%	2 034 313,74		9,29%
P7.2.2.b_Y1	764 481,93	28,61%	1 887 277,75		8,62%
P7.3.3.a_Y1	235 017,94	8,80%	948 793,91		4,33%
Transversal activities	908 781,92	34,02%	7 562 888,71		34,55%
Task 7.1	159 184,83	5,96%	1 291 268,67		5,90%
Task 7.2	398 239,20	14,91%	3 254 621,85		14,87%
Task 7.3	351 357,90	13,15%	3 016 998,19		13,78%
TOTAL WP7	2 671 634,91	100,00%	12 433 274,12	21 889 938,00	56,80%

Annex I AWP Y3

PARC PROJECT PORTFOLIO

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WP4 Monitoring and exposure – 21 PROJECTS

Guided by regulatory needs, WP4 aims to develop and improve the chemical monitoring and exposure assessment capacities in Europe as depicted in figure 1. The overall goal is a better understanding of the environmental and human exposure to chemicals from multiple sources including pathways of exposure between the environment and humans. In support of a “one substance, one assessment approach” new monitoring approaches will be applied to complement existing monitoring schemes. Robust, reliable and fit-for-purpose innovative tools and methods will be developed, primarily to support and facilitate exposure assessment for vulnerable sub-populations and the early warning detection of chemicals of emerging concern. The work under WP4 is divided into three tasks that address the objectives of developing a) the human biomonitoring platform initiated in HBM4EU, b) environmental and multisource monitoring, and c) innovative methods and tools for monitoring.

Chemical monitoring guided by regulatory challenges

Fig 1: WP4 General approach and vision

T4.1 Human Biomonitoring – 9 PROJECTS

A HBM survey targeting the general population will constitute the basis of a well aligned human biomonitoring (HBM) surveillance programme for chemical exposure of European citizens and will generate internal exposure data (see Fig.2). Statistically derived internal exposure reference values will allow for the evaluation of spatial and temporal trends in chemical exposure and monitoring of the impact of regulations and the EU’s Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability. In addition, targeted HBM surveys will address specific research and policy questions related to vulnerable groups (young children, pregnant women), highly exposed groups (workers, hotspot residents) or time trends. Priorities will be identified in cooperation with WP2 (‘A common science-policy agenda’). Further to the work achieved in HBM4EU (<https://www.hbm4eu.eu>) and in coordination with WP9 (‘Building infrastructural and human capacities’), activities are being designed and implemented to ensure the quality and comparability of the HBM results. Harmonisation and improvement of analytical methods across laboratories will be implemented, defining reference analytical methods when possible. Special efforts will also be devoted into developing useful tools for the improvement of the HBM laboratory network. Task 4.1 will further develop the HBM4EU strategy to derive Health-Based Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) for the general and/or the occupational population. Effect biomarkers will complement exposure biomarkers to evaluate associations between chemical exposure and adverse health effects. Issues related to the linkage of HBM, health examination, occupational and dietary surveys will be identified and solved with support of WP7 (‘FAIR Data’). In collaboration with WP2 co-leaders and partners, the ultimate goal of this task is to prepare a long-term sustainable HBM and surveillance system for exposure to chemicals in Europe.

PARC Aligned Studies

	Children 6-11 yrs.	Teenagers 12-17 yrs.	Adults 18-39 yrs.
Min # countries	11	11	11
Min #participants	3300	3300	3300

Sex	SES socio-economic status	Subject living environment
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inhabitants of ✓ Low ✓ Medium ✓ high density communities 		

Fig 2: PARC Aligned Studies

A4.1.1 Design, alignment and fieldwork of HBM studies – 5 PROJECTS

S4.1.1.1 Development of supporting materials for harmonized EU HBM conduct

No project submitted at present.

S4.1.1.2 General population survey – 1 PROJECT

P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO

Project Title	General population human biomonitoring survey		
Project	GenHBMSurvey		
Acronym (15 letters max)			
Project Manager	Liese Gilles	VITO	Belgium
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Deputy Project manager	Susana Pedraza Diaz	ISCIII	Spain
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Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	81
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.1.2
Project Id	P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

This project is of relevance for all regulatory frameworks governing chemical production, use, environmental release, and exposure in various contexts, including those aimed at safeguarding environmental and human health.

Demonstrating the effectiveness of existing policies is vital for public trust and increasing transparency towards industry and stakeholders.

In this project biomarkers of chemical pollutants will be assessed in human biological samples (urine,

blood, hair) of the general EU population. This European-wide Human biomonitoring, conducted through harmonized approaches and quality assured analytical methods, provides coherent data on priority substances in different European regions. Human biomonitoring results from HBM4EU and PARC provide a baseline and time trends against which to track the efficacy of the European Green Deal's Zero Pollution Action Plan and the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (PARC HBM data will for instance feed into ZPA and CSS indicators).

Comparing human biomonitoring data from across Europe can highlight regional differences linked to variations in environmental quality, climate, diet, consumer behavior and lifestyle (see expected outputs). This project will also be identifying exposure to chemicals of emerging concern, including substitutes for banned substances, in the population can serve as a warning of undetected risk. Measuring effect biomarkers and studying associations with health outcome data will provide insight into the extent to which chemicals and substitutes have an impact on health and support chemical grouping approaches and avoidance of regrettable substitution.

Main expected outputs of the project

Data gaps filled by this project are expected to include:

- New internal aggregate and mixture exposure data and reference values for prioritized chemicals for all four geographical regions of Europe.
- Spatial and temporal trends in chemical exposure.
- Increased understanding of the sources and pathways of human exposure.
- Associations of exposures with (early) adverse effects and health impact.
- Identification of emerging chemicals of concern.
- An understanding of population exposure and the exposure of vulnerable groups against health-based human biomonitoring guidance values
- Advance methodologies for assessing health effects due to exposure to chemical mixtures through real-life co-exposure assessment.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project will support the discoverability, accessibility and availability of high quality, reliable and coherent datasets on human exposure to chemicals at European level, supporting the sharing and reusing of human biomonitoring data across legislative silos. The HBM data can support time trend development and evaluation of policy efficacy (e.g., effect of REACH restrictions on exposure levels). Baseline human exposure data also allow comparison with international chemical monitoring programs such as NHANES and CDC. In addition, data on internal exposure generated by human biomonitoring provide a complete picture of human exposure and can be used to enhance chemical risk assessment by providing information on actual human exposure via multiple exposure pathways likely to be regulated under separate policy silos. An understanding of the contribution that different exposure routes make to the overall exposure (taking into account differences in exposure modifiers, such as age and gender, as well as profession) provides the starting point for deciding on risk management measures under legislative silos. As such, this project contributes to the 'one substance, one assessment' approach included in the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability. In addition, identifying upstream exposure routes in various material flows - including in consumer products, via diet and in the occupational setting - can inform targeted efforts to minimize exposure by eliminating chemicals from material flows. Over the long term, the availability of information on exposure to chemicals in specific material flows, including products, will stimulate the production of safer chemicals, products and materials.

The results of the general population survey can be used by different stakeholders:

- ✓ PARC project partners, Governing Board members (responsible for RA at EU/national/regional level), EU agencies, and the scientific community: input for exposure science, modelling, risk assessment, health impact assessment; monitor the impact of implementation of the EU's chemicals strategy for sustainability

- ✓ Policy makers/regulators/OECD, WHO, UN: deriving policy recommendations for reduction of exposure, use of articles, chemicals production and release; evaluating the efficiency of regulation or the need for further action.
- ✓ Citizens: better understanding and awareness of exposure and risk; recommendations for lifestyle and prevention.
- ✓ Industrial hygienists, occupational physicians, workers, trade unions: release to the environment via production processes; worker exposure and protection.

Key words: Human biomonitoring (HBM), internal exposure levels, determinants of exposure, exposure-effect associations

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project responds to the PARC operational objective OO8: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes.

The project contributes to the aim of T4.1 to perform an HBM survey targeting the general population which will form the basis of a well aligned HBM surveillance programme for chemical exposure of European citizens and will generate baseline internal exposure data. This project will deliver the statistically derived internal exposure reference values that will allow for evaluation of spatial and temporal trends in chemical exposure and monitoring of the impact of regulations and the EU’s chemicals strategy for sustainability. As part of this project biomarkers of chemical exposure will be analysed in human samples from the General population (children 6-11 (N = ±3300-3500), teenagers 12-17 (N = ±2650-2750) and adults 18-39 (N = ± 4600-4750)). By collecting and generating HBM data for PARC priority chemicals and exposure scenarios across Europe, the project will contribute to SO2 “European and national RA entities and their scientific networks carry out a joint R&I program to respond to the agreed priorities in chemicals risk assessment”. The project will support the understanding of the contribution of chemicals as upstream determinants of diseases, to the reduction of environmental and human health impact of exposure to hazardous chemicals, and as such to the improvement of the protection of environmental and citizen’s health, and awareness of citizens and professionals about risks of chemical exposures.

This project will deliver new HBM data with EU wide coverage for the period 2023-2026, building on existing capacity. The partners responsible for HBM conduct in their country/region are supported by this project and HBM practices are harmonized.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- Other T4.1 projects:
 - ✓ P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO
 - ✓ P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_DerivationofHBM-GVs_UBA
 - ✓ P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO
 - ✓ Link human biomonitoring studies to health examination and dietary surveys
 - ✓ P4.1.1.4b_Y1_SentinelSystem_KULeuven
 - ✓ Targeted surveys
 - ✓ P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthCareSurvey_TTL_SRU
 - ✓ P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL
 - ✓ P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasability_TTL
 - ✓ P4.1.5.a_Y1_SustainHBMSystem_VITO
- T4.2: analyse associations between sources, external exposure data and internal exposure
- T4.3: development and proof of concept of innovative tools and methods
- WP1: indicators to monitor progress and impact
- WP2: priority setting and uptake into policy
- WP3: communication and dissemination of results
- WP5: identification of effect biomarkers relevant for specific chemicals, age groups and health outcomes

- T6.2 projects: internal exposure data can be used to feed into aggregate and internal-external exposure modelling, mixture risk assessment, and health impact assessment/burden of disease
 - ✓ Strategy for aggregate exposure from general life and occupational exposures
 - ✓ Developing, performing and validation of source to dose modelling including selected case studies
 - ✓ Refinement and development of PBPK models for risk assessment
 - ✓ Real-life mixtures assessment
 - ✓ Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies
 - ✓ Inventory of HIA data for PARC priority chemicals
 - ✓ Case studies on health impact assessment
 - ✓ Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators
- WP7: FAIR and sustainable storage of HBM data; innovative data analysis
- WP8: Early Warning System
- WP9:
 - ✓ inventory of HBM/HES studies (T9.2) that will support the identification of the opportunities in the HBM survey
 - ✓ laboratory networks (T9.1) as an essential key in the QA/QC programme organization (T9.3) and implementation as well as in the analysis of the samples
 - ✓ training activities (T9.4) that can cover issues related to all the study phases (sampling, chemical analysis, statistical analysis, etc.).

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU legacy: the project will build further on experiences, results, materials, and networks developed within HBM4EU
- European Human Exposome Network (EHEN) projects
- National/regional studies participating in the general survey
- Exposure levels observed in the survey can be compared with levels from other international HBM surveys such as CHMS (Canada), NHANES (US)...

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D4.3; D4.8; D4.12: Progress report on the general survey (M36; 48; 60)

D4.13: Concluding report summarizing the outcome of all studies for a future monitoring approach (M81)

Partners List:

Core partners: VITO (BE), ISCIII (ES), SPF (FR), UBA (DE), LNS (LU), RegionH (DK), INSA (PT).

Partners involved in statistical analysis of the data: ANSES (FR), AU (DK), AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), EASP (ES), INRAE (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), INSERM (FR), IPA (DE), ISCIII (ES), ISSeP (BE), JSI (SI), LNS (LU), LSMU (LT), MU (CZ), NIJZ (SI), NIPH (NO), PIH (BE), Sciensano (BE), SLU, SPF (FR), SZU-SK (SK), UBA (DE), UGR (ES), UH (BE), UNIVIE (AT), UU-IRAS (NL), VITO (BE).

Partners involved in study conduct: AUTH (EL), EAA(AT), EASP (ES), INSA (PT), ISCIII (ES), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), JSI (SI), LNS (LU), LSMU (LT), MOH-CY/SGL (CY), MOH-IL (IL), NIOM (PL), NIPH (NO), NCPHP (HU), NIJZ (SI), PIH (BE), RegionH (DK), RIVM (NL), RSU (LV), SPF (FR), SZU-CZ (CZ), UI (IS), UKHSA (UK), University Tartu/ Health Board (EE), UPV/EHU (ES), VITO (BE), WULS (PL)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029 (M81)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 25 PM

Expected ODC (Other direct costs: travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables) for the third year of the project: 29 269 €

S4.1.1.3 Targeted surveys

No project submitted at present.

S4.1.1.4 Occupational surveys – 4 PROJECTS

P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasibility_TTL

Project Title	Feasibility study to evaluate occupational exposure in general surveys		
Project	OccupFeasibility		
Acronym (15 letters max)			
Project Manager	Tiina Santonen tiina.santonen@ttl.fi	Finnish Institute of Occupational Health	Finland
Deputy Project manager	-	-	-
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	29*
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.1
Project Id	P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasibility_TTL		

*The project has been delayed from M18 to M29

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The main idea of this project is to develop an approach to investigate if it is possible to analyse the data from HBM4EU general population studies to identify occupationally exposed groups, and to evaluate how general (adult) population studies can identify possible higher exposure of occupationally exposed groups. This will be done for selected HBM4EU priority chemicals, which are cadmium, PAHs and bisphenols that has been measured in HBM4EU aligned studies in adult population.

Thus, **the main scope of the project** is to analyse the existing (HBM4EU) biomonitoring data for its further use in the identification of occupational exposures.

The project is designed as a feasibility study with limited duration and resources.

The project aims to improve the use of HBM data to explore predictor variables that impact the exposure levels measured and thus contribute also to some of the variability observed. The results of the feasibility project can be used in general population HBM studies planned to be performed under WP4. Thus, one of the main user groups of the project results will be researchers performing general population HBM studies.

The regulatory processes the project can support are mainly REACH and OSH processes. When general population HBM data is used for the exposure assessment it is important to understand the main sources of exposure. When performing general population risk assessment, potential confounding effect of occupational exposure needs to be identified and eliminated, if present. On the other hand, the data may contribute to the occupational exposure assessment under REACH or OSH processes. When setting reference values (or BGVs under ECHA OEL process) to distinguish occupational exposure from background (environmental, consumer) exposure, it is important to ensure that the background levels are not confounded with occupational exposure. In addition, it would be useful if general population studies can be used to screen less well-known occupational exposures to target potential regulatory actions to these exposures.

The selected substances (bisphenols, Cd, PAHs and Cr) are relevant since these compounds are currently under consideration either under REACH restrictions or under CMRD.

As this is designed as a feasibility study to proof the concept there is currently no need for alignment the timeline with policy's agenda.

Main expected outputs of the project

The main output will be recommendations on the use of occupation-related information from general population studies:

- Is it possible to identify some occupational groups and their exposure from the general population data? How much occupational exposure may contribute to explain the highest percentiles of exposure values in general population surveys?
- How should information on occupations be analysed in general population studies?
- Can analysis of population surveys be used to screen possible less well-known occupational exposures?

In addition, the project will provide recommendations for future general population studies for the collection of data relevant for the identification of occupational exposure from general population data.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

If successful, the information generated in this project may contribute to the occupational exposure assessment under REACH or OSH processes. It is also expected to contribute to the design and analysis of future general population HBM studies.

Key words: occupational exposure, HBM, general population, aligned studies, Cd, BPA, PAH, Cr

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

P4.1.1.4.a addresses especially operational objectives OO7 (Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA) and OO10 (Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA). In this project, existing human biomonitoring data on priority compounds is used to identify the possible occupational origin of the chemical exposures trying to understand how much occupational exposure contributes to general, adult population total exposure to different compounds and whether it is possible to identify possibly new occupational exposure sources from general population survey datasets. Thus, it responds to the need to better understand exposure sources in order to refine risk assessment. In the project, new advanced data analyses are performed for the identification of occupational exposure. The results can be used in the RA of the chemicals.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project is highly linked to other activities within WP4, specifically aligned studies planned under WP4. It can provide recommendations to be considered in PARC aligned HBM studies. Thus, PARC WP4 projects it is closely linked include:

- Project: P4.1.1.2.a General population HBM survey
- Project: P4.1.1.4.b Assessment of exposure through a sentinel surveillance system
- Project: P4.1.5.a Preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe

It also links to WP6 and especially to activities related to aggregated exposure assessment from different sources (task 6.2.1), WP7 on FAIR data and can also possibly feed in to WP8 toolboxes.

Links outside PARC

Outside PARC it is closely related to HBM4EU, since it will analyse the data collected/generated within HBM4EU.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD4.8. Report on the occupational exposure in general population surveys: analysis of existing data and recommendations for future general population studies (new delivery date M29). This deliverable describes the availability of occupational information in the existing general population datasets and gives an overview on the usefulness of this data in the identification of potential occupational exposed groups and final recommendations for the future studies.

Partners List:

TTL (FI), SpF (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), LSMU (LT)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/09/2024 (M29)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 4 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 0 €

P4.1.1.4.b_Y1_SentinelSystem_KULeuven

Project Title	Assessment of exposure to substances of high concern in the working population through a sentinel surveillance system: Mapping and preparation of proof-of-concept		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	SentinelSystem		
Project Manager	Lode Godderis Lode.godderis@kuleuven.be	KULeuven	Belgium
Deputy Project manager	Emine Aktas Bajalan emine.aktasbajalan@kuleuven.be	-	-
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36*
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.1.4
Project Id	P4.1.1.4.b_Y1_SentinelSystem_KULeuven		

*The project has been broken down at M36 to assess what has been achieved. If the review is positive, there will be two project phases M1-M36 and M37-M81.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

A Sentinel Surveillance System in occupational settings is a strategic and cost-effective for monitoring health issues related to environmental and occupational exposure via motivated and well-trained occupational physicians (OP) and nurses (ON). It contains the selection of specific locations where data on occupational and environmental health conditions are systematically gathered together with exposure data of substances of high concern. This approach allows both for the continuous monitoring and follow-up of the occurrence and prevalence of specific health conditions and exposure levels within specific populations such as workers and for setting up fast dedicated and targeted study to assess exposure to specific agents. The sentinel surveillance system has already been used successfully to collect information on occupational exposures to, for example, hazardous chemicals, solvent and metals and it has been found a valid method to collect epidemiological health data on for example infectious diseases. For instance, it has been used in the Hazardous chemical Products Register for Occupational use in Belgium (PROBE) study, to collect data about the exposure of workers to dangerous chemicals based on their hazardous properties in work environment such as benzene, toluene, diesel exhaust and wood dust, etc. Also, the French Surveillance Medicale des Risques (SUMER) study, a national cross-sectional survey of occupational risks, collected good-quality exposure data to carcinogenic, mutagenic, and reprotoxic chemicals such as diesel engine exhaust, wood dust, crystalline silica, and etc. by use of sentinel surveillance.

By closely monitoring the data from sentinel system, public health authorities, health care professionals and employers can detect potential health risks, exposures, and work-related diseases, take timely action, follow-up the exposure and workers health, and implement appropriate preventive measures.

This project aims to explore, design, test feasibility and implement a European sentinel surveillance system to support human biomonitoring (HBM) surveys and to assess the exposure of a representative sample of European working population exposed to substances of high concern via motivated and specifically trained OP/nurses about sentinel approach and HBM. The project has the capacity to primarily support regulatory processes related to REACH (Registration, Evaluation, Authorization, and Restriction of Chemicals) and OSH (Occupational Safety and Health).

Main expected outputs of the project

The REACH regulation's role in assessing the potential risks posed by chemicals and proposing risk management measures is pivotal for safeguarding not only the environment but also the health of workers who encounter these substances in their occupational environment. In parallel, the concept of a Sentinel Surveillance System has emerged as a dynamic approach to safeguard occupational health according to OSH regulation. By systematically monitoring working populations environments and the health of workers who are exposed to high concern substance, this system offers a robust framework for early detection of hazards, preemptive interventions, and data-driven decision-making.

The main outputs and impacts expected from the project are:

- Provide EU relevant data on exposures to high concern substance in working population to be used as scientific evidence to support several actions at different levels, namely: companies and workers level, country level and, also, EU policy level for adaptation and/or create new policies if considered needed.
- Development of national roadmaps for environmental and occupational bio-monitoring in partner countries
- Development of capacity building material and programs to train OP/ON
- Development of a sentinel surveillance network. In the sentinel system approach, the trained OP, or ONs will form a wide network that can be immediately activated for future studies related to HBM in occupational settings or in the working populations. This will help us gather more information and make workplaces and environment safer.
- Evaluate the usefulness of sentinel system approach as a methodology and an approach to assess complex exposures. This system acts as an essential bridge between occupational, environmental and broader health and safety regulations.
- Identify the project outputs value as a contribute for identifying exposure scenarios at the general population level.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The primary rationale behind initiating this feasibility study lies in optimizing the utilization of existing Human Biomonitoring (HBM) data and gaining deeper insights into the role of occupational exposure in contributing to the background variability observed in biomarker levels within the HBM data in occupational settings in specific targeted working populations. One of the key outcomes expected from this study is the potential revelation of new, previously unnoticed occupational exposure pathways. This approach can prove invaluable for strengthening measures to protect workers from previously unrecognized health risks and occupational exposures, ultimately contributing to the overarching goal of safeguarding worker health and prevent exposure through the development of targeted strategies.

Key advantages and expected impacts of a sentinel surveillance approach are:

- More samples and data can be gathered,
- Decrease the financial burden of environmental related diseases, and WRDs,
- Help to establish causality with regard to work in cases of links between new exposures and WRDs,
- Contribute to the timely identification and prevention of such WRDs, and ability to trigger timely preventive actions
- Allows for the continuous monitoring of the occurrence and prevalence of specific health conditions and exposure levels within in specific populations

- Serve as an early warning system or alert system for emerging outbreaks, exposures to new substances health effects in workplaces
- Improve the importance of cooperating and exchanging data related to exposure to substances of high concern within the EU.
- Policy makers, EU and national regulators, EU agencies (EU OSHA): These stakeholders will be involved in the development of additional further regulations and guidance, as well as assessing the effectiveness of existing regulations.
- Workers and trade unions, employees, industrial hygienists, occupational physicians and nurses: better understanding and awareness of exposure and risk; recommendations for risk management.

From an international standpoint, it is believed that the establishment and utilization of sentinel surveillance groups in various countries and providing training to physicians or other healthcare providers including the assessment process of occupational and environmental exposure hold promise as a potential means to gather more reliable information and facilitate comparisons of data across countries.

Key words: Occupational exposure, sentinel surveillance system, high risk companies, chemical exposure, biomonitoring

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The current project intends to use mainly HBM data to evaluate working population exposure to high concern substances, following the approaches already used in the occupational studies of the HBM4EU. By facilitating the recruitment of European working adult participants for the PARC Occupational Survey and the collection of data and samples, this project will contribute to all objectives and regulatory frameworks that are of relevance for the Occupational Studies in specific targeted sample. This project will additionally support the Health & Safety at Work – EU Strategic Framework (2021-2027), which aims to maintain and improve the high health & safety standards for EU workers and will help to prepare for new crises and threats. By creating data on aggregated exposure from multiple sources the project supports EU zero pollution agenda, EU one-substance-one evaluation goals and exposome network/projects

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP2 Knowledge management and uptake into policy

WP4, the project is linked to all other WP4.1 activities and projects,

- T4.1.1d Occupational HBM surveys (sharing e.g. some standard operating procedures (SOPs))
- T4.1.1d Feasibility study to evaluate occupational exposure in general surveys
- T4.1.1a Development of supporting materials for the HBM surveys (SPOs, health related measurement, questionnaires)
- T 4.1.3 Roadmap to explore the links between prioritized chemical substances exposures and health concerns (questionnaire and protocol for health measurements/sample collection)
- T4.1.5 Design of a sustainable EU-wide HBM surveillance system

WP 3.2 Communication, dissemination and synergies :

Awareness raising campaigns will be carried out by using targeted communication materials on the impact of environmental and occupational exposures on human health.

WP 7 FAIR Data, strengthens exchange and reuse of research and regulatory data

Sentinel Surveillance System will follow the WP7 directions to access, storage and analysis of data, and the interfacing with the modelling and analysis tools procedures and guidance.

WP 9.4 Training: An online training module is needed for the recruited occupational physicians/nurses. This online training module will contain information about the sentinel system, recruitment of workers, sample collection, questionnaires, chemicals, etc.

Links outside PARC

Numerous countries have embraced the utilization of sentinel surveillance systems in occupational settings as a proactive approach to safeguarding worker health and mitigating potential hazards. In Belgium, the

PROBE (Hazardous chemical Products Register for Occupational use in Belgium) was set up to assess the occupational exposure of workers to a selection of hazardous chemicals. In the “Peilstation Intensief Melden” (PIM) study (The Netherlands), a group of motivated and trained OP reported occupational diseases by using a sentinel surveillance system. The French Surveillance Medicale des Risques (SUMER) study, a national cross-sectional survey of occupational risks, collected good-quality exposure data through the sentinel system. In the BIOAMBIENT.ES project reports conducted in Spain, a national-level HBM study on environmental pollutants to estimate levels of heavy metals, persistent organic pollutants, and other substances in the Spanish active workforce. Also, it is closely related to HBM4EU, since it will analyze the data generated within HBM4EU.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D4.13: Concluding report summarizing the outcome of all studies for a future monitoring approach (M81)

Partners List:

KU Leuven (Belgium), INSA (Portugal), ENSP-UNL (Portugal), UNINA (Italy), MU (Czech Republic), RSU (Latvia), SpF (France), UGR (Spain), NIOM (Poland), SRU (The Netherlands), AU (Denmark), LNS (Luxembourg), STM (Luxembourg), STI (Luxembourg), UNISANTE (Switzerland), ULUND (Sweden), BPI (Greece).

Schedule for the first period of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Costs (M1-M81)

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 1.3 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 2350 €

P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthCareSurvey_TTL_SRU

Project	Occupational survey in the healthcare sector		
Title	HealthcareSurvey		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	HealthcareSurvey		
Project Manager	tiina.santonen@ttl.fi	Finnish Institute of Occupational Health	Finland
Deputy Project manager	paul.scheepers@ru.nl	Stichting Radboud University	Netherlands
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	48M
PARC (Month number)	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.1
Project Id	P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthcareSurvey_TTL_SRU		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

In this project we will perform a cross sectional study in the hospital-based healthcare to assess the exposure and risks to priority chemicals of concern by using exposure and effect biomonitoring. This will contribute to further improvement of healthy and safe working conditions. The project will target the following chemicals:

- Hazardous medicinal products (including cytotoxic drugs)

- Inhalation anaesthetics
- Disinfectant and cleaning products (including biocides)

The project aims are to introduce human biomonitoring as an approach to study both exposure and effects related to the use of chemicals in hospital-based healthcare. This will lead to more awareness and better understanding of how work practices contribute to internal exposure to chemicals and how these practices can be further improved to reduce uptake of these chemicals. We aim for 20-24 hospitals in 10-12 EU member states.

More specifically the project aims to:

1. Identify chemical exposures of concern and relevant exposure scenarios in the hospital-based healthcare;
2. Study how human biological monitoring (HBM) can inform chemical risk assessment of hazardous medicinal products, inhalation anaesthetics, disinfection products and cleaning products (biocides);
3. Contribute to the further improvement of healthy and safe working conditions
4. Study contributions from different sources of exposure, also outside work, in assessment of aggregated exposure;
5. Develop HBM-based approaches for the assessment and management of chemical exposures in hospital-based healthcare.

The regulatory processes

In 2019 it was agreed that hazardous drugs, including cytotoxic drugs, should adhere to minimum requirements for the protection of health and safety of workers, in particular those provided for in the Council Directive 98/24/EC and in the Carcinogens and Mutagens Directive 2004/37/EC (CMD). Development of a new guidance to support the implementation of safe use of hazardous medicinal products at work is currently ongoing based on a previous evaluation (European Commission, 2021). In December 2021, the European Parliament proposed to bring reprotoxic chemicals under the remit of the CMD. This will require further development of protocols for measurement of chemical exposures on the workplace, especially for periods of higher susceptibility such as during pregnancy.

Main expected outputs of the project

- A dataset describing the current exposure to selected chemicals in approximately 20-24 hospitals in approximately 10-12 EU Member States
- An improved understanding of how current work practices in the hospital-based healthcare translate to internal exposure to selected chemicals
- Recommendations for policy changes in line with current and new health and safety procedures and sustainability programmes on national and EU level

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

- For workers, employers, occupational hygienists and occupational physicians: better understanding and increased awareness of the potential health risk of chemical exposures;
- Recommendations for risk management leading to improved work practices
- The scientific community and primarily other partners in PARC: potential added value of HBM approach as input for risk assessment and health impact assessment
- For policymakers, EU and national regulators, EU Agencies (EU OSHA): evaluating the efficiency of current regulations and further development of these existing regulations and implementation of the new harmonised guidance on safe use of HMPs including cytotoxic drugs.

Key words: occupational exposure, hospital, risk management measures, hazardous medicinal products, cytotoxic drugs, inhalation anaesthetics, disinfection, cleaning, biocides

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

T4.1 on human biomonitoring aims at measuring total exposure to priority compounds in humans considering different sources, chemical fates & exposure pathways. The current project uses HBM data and tries to understand how much occupational exposure contributes to general, adult population total exposure

to different compounds and whether it is possible to identify possibly new occupational exposure sources from general population survey datasets.

The healthcare survey is an occupational study that contributes to increased understanding/ awareness of the chemicals used in the hospital-based healthcare setting (OO6: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen's understanding/awareness of chemical RA). It has been designed to support the recent policy actions under EU CMRD (carcinogens, mutagens and reproductive toxic substances directive), with the recent inclusion of hazardous medicinal products. Based on the prior experience on occupational studies performed in HBM4EU we will introduce established and innovative biomarkers of exposure and effect related to selected priority chemicals (hazardous medicinal products, inhalation anaesthetics and disinfection/cleaning products). For this we will develop a network of laboratories and research centers in 10 countries (OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres). We expect that our results will support health and safety policy, including the development of biological guidance values (OO8: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project is linked to other activities within WP4, specifically aligned studies planned under WP4. It can provide recommendations to be considered in PARC aligned HBM studies. Thus, PARC WP4 projects it is closely linked include:

- Project: P4.1.1.2.a General population HBM survey
- Project: P4.1.1.4.b Assessment of exposure through a sentinel surveillance system
- Project: P4.1.1.4.d Occupational survey in waste management
- Project: P4.3.2.b Proof-of-concept of innovative sampling and HRMS based screening methods for exploring occupational exposure to chemicals of emerging concern.
- Project: P4.1.3.3.a Roadmap from exposure to health

In addition, close collaboration is made with following activities/projects within T4.1:

- T4.1.1.1 activity related to development of supporting materials for fieldwork
- T4.1.2 on QA and analytics related to selection of laboratories
- T4.1.4 related to statistical data analyses

This also links to WP6 and especially to activities related to aggregate exposure from multiple sources and routes of exposure for the general population and workers (task 6.2.1) and mixture risk assessment (task 6.2.3). Since the exposure of health care personnel typically consists of mixed exposure to several compounds, the data collected can be used as a case study in 6.2.3.

Links outside PARC

- Previous HBM4EU occupational studies on chromates, e-waste and diisocyanates
- EU-OSHA funded project aiming to provide a practical guidance on preventing and reducing occupational exposure to HMPs, including cytotoxic drugs
- Inhalation anaesthetics study funded by the social fund of the Netherlands Federation of Academic Hospitals (Project number F2491)
- Ethanol exposure assessment study funded by the social fund of the Netherlands Federation of Academic Hospitals (Project number F2492)
- Masarykova Univerzita (MU). National network of monitoring of drugs in the hospitals and pharmacies in Czech Republic and Slovakia (see: <https://www.cytostatika.cz/>)

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D4.7 Progress report on occupational surveys (M48).

Partners List:

TTL (FI), SRU (NL), MU (CZ), AU (DK), UGR (ES), INRS (FR), ISS (IT), UMIL (IT), UNINA (IT), UNIPD (IT), RSU (LV), LNS (LU), SGGW (PL), ENSP (PT), HSE (UK), IOM (UK), UGR (ES), INSST (ES)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 21 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 31 649 €

P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL

Project Title	Occupational survey in the waste management sector		
Project	Occup_Waste		
Acronym (15 letters max)			
Project Manager	Tiina Santonen tiina.santonen@ttl.fi	Finnish Institute of Occupational Health	Finland
Deputy Project manager	Susana Viegas Susana.viegas@ensp.unl.pt	ENSP-UNL NOVA National School of Public Health	Portugal
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	48
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1
Project Id	P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP-TTL		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The European Commission adopted a new Circular Economy Action Plan - one of the main building blocks of the European Green Deal, Europe's new agenda for sustainable growth. With measures along the entire life cycle of products, the new Action Plan aims to make EU economy fit for a green future, strengthen competitiveness while protecting the environment and provide new rights to consumers (EC, 2020). As Europe moves towards a more circular economy, the product of today will become the raw material of tomorrow. The waste management sector is expected to play a pivotal role in this development.

Based on this, an increase is expected of the number of workers involved in processes and tasks related with waste streams where the potential for circularity is high. Some of these waste streams are for instance electronics, batteries and vehicles, plastics, textiles, general household, and construction and buildings materials. The reuse and recycling of these materials could result in an increase of exposure (e.g., metals, flame retardants, phthalates) of workers involved in different steps of the waste processing chain such as collection, sorting, dismantling, shredding and further pre-processing and purification of waste components to allow their use as raw materials in different processes and industries (e.g., textile, plastics - and also PVC, furniture, construction). Additionally, the increase in waste volumes and complexity may reduce the capability of the sector to process waste safely.

In the scope of HBM4EU project an exploratory study in occupational exposures in electrical and electronic waste (E-waste) processing was developed and a study protocol using a cross sectional survey design to study worker's exposures and compare these to the exposure of non-exposed individuals preferably was implemented (Scheepers et al., 2021). This study protocol can be adapted to future European-wide occupational studies developed in the scope of PARC such as the one described here.

Overall, the project aims to understand waste management workers exposure to chemicals since new materials in the waste stream may pose additional risks to waste sector workers. The waste streams that will be the focus of this study are the e-waste and plastics (household and industry).

The regulatory processes the project can support are mainly REACH and OSH processes. When general population HBM data is used for the exposure assessment it is important to understand the main sources of

exposure. On the other hand, the data may contribute to the occupational exposure assessment under REACH or OSH processes.

Main expected outputs of the project

The main outputs and impacts expected from the project are:

- Provide EU relevant data on chemical exposures in the e-waste and plastics (household and industrial) waste streams to be used as scientific evidence to support several actions at different levels, namely: companies and workers level, country level and, also, EU policy level for adaptation and/or create new policies if considered needed.
- Evaluate the usefulness of BM as a tool to assess complex exposures such as the ones that can happen in these occupational settings.
- Identify the project outputs value as a contribution for identifying exposure scenarios at the general population level.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The results of the survey can be used by different stakeholders:

- PARC project partners and the scientific community: input for exposure science, modelling, risk assessment, health impact assessment; monitoring of the impact of implementation of the EU OSH directives
- Policy makers, EU and national regulators, EU Agencies (EU OSHA): deriving further regulation and guidance, evaluating the efficiency of current regulations.
- Workers and trade unions, industrial hygienists, occupational physicians: better understanding and awareness of exposure and risk; recommendations for risk management.

Key words: occupational exposure, HBM, waste management, circular economy

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives OO4: Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge, OO7: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA, OO8: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes, OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC's results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA, OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres and OO13: Build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical RA.

The project will foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge since it will provide EU relevant data on chemical exposures and risk assessment in the e-waste and plastics (household and industrial) waste streams to be used as scientific evidence to support several actions at different levels, namely : companies and workers level, country level and, also, EU policy level for adaptation and/or create new policies if considered needed in different regulatory frameworks (e.g. OSHA, Environment, REACH). The project will also boost the existing networks of laboratories and research centres and develop new ones and it will contribute to build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical RA.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Considering the data that will be produced by the project it can be linked to WP2 (Knowledge management and uptake into policy) and with WP3 (Synergies and collaborations). Also, WP5 (Hazard Assessment), particularly with the tasks developed in the scope of characterizing AOPs and relevant effect biomarkers since the project will also integrate the Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOPs) approach to allow a better understanding of the mechanism of action of the chemicals and mixtures and to select the most suitable biomarkers of effect to be used. Within WP4, the project is linked to all other WP4.1 activities and projects, especially to Occupational survey on health care workers (sharing e.g. some standard operating procedures (SOPs)), on the development of survey materials (4.1.1.1), project

P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO on roadmap from exposure to health (4.1.3.3), QA and analytical activities (4.1.2), statistical data analysis activities (4.1.4). In addition, the project is linked to taskWP4.3: Innovative sampling methods and metabolomic studies since these new methods are planned to be tested within the project.

Additionally, this project will have several linkages with WP6 (innovation in regulatory risk assessment) where the exposure to several substances will trigger multiple collaborations such as development and use of integrative models to determine and quantify the internal exposure to chemicals from different routes and sources of exposure and to combine several routes and sources of exposure and/or exposures obtained from different methodologies. The data generated within this project can be used for the assessment of risks of mixed exposure to multiple hazardous substances within waste management sector. Along the same lines, links with WP9 (capacities) will probably emerge when planning the study and also in a later stage, when the data will start to become available and used for training and capacity building purposes.

Links outside PARC

The EU-OSHA's is developing a third foresight cycle that looks at changes in work that may result from the EU's transition to a circular economy (CE) and the potential impact on occupational safety and health (OSH) (<https://osha.europa.eu/en/emerging-risks/circular-economy>). Our project, developed in the scope of PARC, will provide useful information to streamline this objective. Additionally, our project will continue the work developed in the scope of HBM4EU Project, particularly in what concerns to the E-Waste study since it intends to use the samples (biomonitoring and industrial hygiene samples) already collected and look for other substances that were not targeted in the E-Waste study (Scheepers et al., 2021). These are for instance cobalt and antimony due to their possible presence in this type of waste and the need of exposure data already recognize in the IARC evaluation developed recently (Karagas et al., 2022). Additionally, for those results of E-waste study that were not possible to be analysed in detail during HBM4EU, an extensive statistical analysis will be performed for the further refinement of waste management study design to be developed in PARC.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D4.7: First Progress report on occupational surveys (M48).

Partners List:

ENSP (Portugal); AU(Denmark); ISS (Italy); UNIPD (Italy); UMIL (Italy); UNINA (Italy); WULS (Poland); ULUND (Sweden); STAMI (Norway); AUTH (Greece); INSA (Portugal); TTL (Finland); LNS (Luxembourg); MOH-CY (Cyprus); NIOM (Poland); IOM (UK); HSE (UK); UGranada (ES).

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/09/2025 (M42)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 39 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 85 805 €

S4.1.1.5 Implementation of innovative methods

No project submitted at present.

A4.1.2 Laboratory analysis and quality assurance

No project submitted at present.

A4.1.3 Link exposure and health related information – 2 PROJECTS

S4.1.3.1 Propose health-based HBM guidance values – 1 PROJECT

P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_DerivationofHBM-GVs_UBA

Project Title	Propose health-based HBM guidance values (HBM-GVs)		
Project	P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_DerivationofHBM-GVs_UBA		
Acronym (15 letters max)			
Project Manager	Petra Apel	UBA	Germany
Deputy Project manager	Petra.apel@uba.de		
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	36*
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.3.1
Project Id	P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_DerivationofHBM-GVs_UBA		

*The project has been broken down at M36 to assess what has been achieved. If the review is positive, there will be two project phases M1-M36 and M37-M81.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Task 4.1 includes human biomonitoring (HBM) to support EU chemicals policy. As a prerequisite for a health-related interpretation of HBM results, guideline values are needed that have been derived epidemiologically or toxicologically and relate directly to measured human exposure. The purpose of the present project is therefore to derive and agree on further such values for priority substances identified within PARC for which specific exposure biomarkers are defined in sub-task 4.1.2. Consensus on these values should be reached within the PARC project to achieve broad scientific acceptance for these values and to ensure a harmonized assessment of HBM results. It is envisaged that the values will be agreed in stages, first at the 4.1.3.1.a project level and then via NHC and NHCPs within a wider circle of experts involved in PARC. HBM-GVs for the general population and/or workers are generally intended to be derived according to the agreed strategy for deriving HBM-GVs (Apel et al., 2020), but continuous development of the strategy is planned and will be taken into account when deriving the values. In individual cases, PBPK/TK modelling may be necessary and corresponding results would then have to be made available within PARC. Cooperation with sub-task 5.3.4 should be sought in this regard. A level of confidence should be attributed to the derived HBM-GVs.

Main expected outputs of the project

Over the course of the seven-year PARC project, a set of HBM-GVs will be successively established. These assessment tools can then be used for health-related risk assessment of survey results in the general population and in the workplace. At the beginning of the third PARC year, a review should be conducted within PARC to determine whether the approaches to substance prioritization, human biomonitoring guidance value (HBM-GV) derivation, and common benchmark agreement need to be adjusted.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Comparison of PARC HBM data with HBM-GVs allow statements on whether citizens or subpopulations in European regions are at risk of health effects and whether measures for risk mitigation have to be recommended or adapted. With the help of further information e.g. on marketing and findings from HBM accompanying questionnaires on individual product use, the use of HBM-GVs as an assessment tool can have an improving effect on regulations for food, cosmetics, etc. HBM-GVs can also be used to assess local event-related HBM investigations.

Furthermore, HBM-GVs can also be used to develop impact indicators that illustrate physical exposure and possible health risks in a simple and easily accessible way, helping to inform a wider audience (e.g. citizens). HBM-GVs can also be used as a basis for risk assessment of mixtures, e.g. by applying the hazard index approach or mixture assessment/ allocation factors.

Key words: health-based human biomonitoring guidance values, human biomonitoring guidance values, HBM-GVs, risk assessment

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives OO4: Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge, OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives, OO6: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen’s understanding/awareness of chemical RA, OO7: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA, OO8: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes, OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA, OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake and OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC’s results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA.

Based on survey data, HBM-GVs make it possible to check whether the risk assessments and risk reduction measures carried out in the context of substance and product regulation or in the workplace are appropriate or need to be corrected (operational objective OO4, OO8, OO9, OO10, OO12). In line with the description of action (DoA), the HBM-GVs as project results could also contribute to potential PARC responses to new and urgent needs for information at EU and national level (operational objective OO6). Cooperation with other international R&I initiatives in the field of biomonitoring and chemical risk assessment will also be promoted (operational objective OO5).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- 4.1.4 data management and analysis
- 5.1.1 Closing data gaps of concern for human health
- 5.3.2 AOP development based on integration
- 5.3.4 PBTk models and quantitative systems toxicology
- 6.2.3 Mixture exposure and risk assessment
- 6.2.4 Human health impact assessment and risk indicators
- 6.3.1 Substance and effect specific reviews

WP7: Fair data

Links outside PARC

1. National activities on human biomonitoring assessment values: e.g. German HBM Commission (HBM values); Health Canada (biomonitoring equivalents); ANSES, TTL i.a. (OELs)
2. OECD activities on deriving occupational biomonitoring levels
3. i-HBM activities on collecting and comparing human biomonitoring assessment values
4. EFSA/ECHA activities

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD4.3 Derivation of HBM-GVs - first set (new delivery date M36)

Partners List:

ANSES (FR), AUTH (GR), MOH-IL (IL), NIJZ (SI), NIPH (NO), TTL (FI), SRU (NL), UBA (DE), Unisante (CH), Uni Oulo (FI)

Schedule for the first period of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/ 2025 (M36)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 28 PM
 Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 17 188 €

S4.1.3.2 Identify effect biomarkers for prioritized chemicals, populations and health outcomes

No project submitted at present.

S4.1.3.3 Link HBM studies to health examination and dietary studies – 1 PROJECT

P4.1.3.3.a Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO

Project Title	Roadmap to explore the links between prioritized chemical substances exposure and health concerns		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth		
Project Manager	PARC-SpFrance@santepubliquefrance.fr	SpF	France
	Sylvie Remy Sylvie.remy@vito.be		
Deputy Project manager	-kirsten.baken@vito.be	VITO	Belgium
	For effect biomarkers : Andrea Rodríguez Carrillo (andrea.rodriguezcarriollo@vito.be)	VITO	Belgium
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	52
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/ Sub-activity:	4.1.3.2 and 4.1.3.3
Project Id	P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Building on HBM4EU recommendations for further implementation of traditional and novel effect biomarkers in HBM studies and the linkage of HBM and health examination surveys (HES), this project aims to develop a roadmap that identifies concrete actions to undertake to foster investigations on the link between chemical exposures and health outcomes through biomarkers of effect. The project will be conducted in a two-step approach; I. first, the integration of standardized effect biomarker and health measurements and questionnaires in HBM surveys conducted under T4.1.1 – HBM surveys design; II. Second, a feasibility study to explore the possibility to assess past exposures to prioritized chemicals and determine effect biomarkers levels from biobanked samples collected earlier in cohorts and evaluate the prospective associations with health outcomes that will be collected under PARC. A case study will be applied to a specific PARC priority substance through retrospective analysis. This project will establish a core strategy for linking past exposures to current health effects, and create a baseline assessment that will guide future surveys combining biomonitoring and health examinations. In that capacity, the project will deliver tools and information for measuring exposure and health-effect biomarkers that could be used alongside the classical toxicological, regulatory framework-driven risk assessment.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Roadmap for exploration of the links between HBM data and existing health outcome
- Supporting materials for PARC surveys:

- Scoping document of a list of health measurements to be included in the HBM/HES surveys including standardized procedures and materials for collecting health, dietary and occupational data
- Effect biomarker implementation plan for PARC surveys
- Investigation of the links between exposure and adverse health outcomes, from analyses of biobanked samples within Health examination cohorts

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The results and data of this project are of interest to:

- PARC project partners
- Governing Board members
- EU commission and agencies
- EU national bodies
- Broader scientific community
- Policy makers and regulators

The generated information materials will provide tools for a more comprehensive and integrative biomonitoring of chemical exposure in Europe and ascertain to study relationships among risk factors, health promotion and protection behaviors, and health status.

Key words: Human biomonitoring, biomarkers of effect, health outcome assessment, Molecular epidemiology

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives **OO7**: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA, **OO8**: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes, **OO12**: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake, **OO9**: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC's results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA.

T4.1: Effect biomarkers will complement exposure biomarkers, if input to regulatory needs can be derived, to evaluate associations between chemical exposure and adverse effects (LNS, SpF, UGR, VITO). Issues related to the linkage of HBM, health examination, occupational and dietary surveys will be identified and solved with support of WP7 (RSU, SpF).

Through the activities on exposure monitoring and toxicology, the Partnership will foster a better understanding the health impacts of exposures and, thereby, indirectly contribute with evidence for health cost estimations.

This project will contribute to SO2 “European and national RA entities and their scientific networks carry out a joint R&I programme to respond to the agreed priorities in chemicals risk assessment”. The project will support the understanding of the contribution of chemicals as upstream determinants of diseases, to the reduction of environmental and human health impact of exposure to hazardous chemicals, and as such to the improvement of the protection of environmental and citizen's health, and awareness of citizens and professionals about risks of chemical exposures.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

This project is mainly linked to T4.1 activities:

- General Survey
- Targeted surveys
- Occupational surveys
- Definition of standardised materials (questionnaires, protocols, etc.)
- Preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe
- Data management and analysis

WP2: Prioritization of substances and uptake into policy

WP7: FAIR data management and technical issues related to the linkage of HBM and HES

WP9: Inventory of HBM/HES studies that will support the identification of the opportunities in the HBM survey

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU legacy: the project will build further on experiences, results and materials developed within HBM4EU
- European Human Exposome Network (EHEN)
- OECD interdisciplinary activity ‘Addressing combined exposures and effects by using Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) knowledge in combination with relevant effect-biomarkers’
- OECD expert group related to Working Parties on Hazard and Exposure Assessments (WPHA/WPEA)

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

There is no specific PARC deliverable for this project. The results will feed into T4.1 deliverables

- MS10 Finalisation of study design for the HBM surveys (M12)
- AD4.1 Periodic report on available supporting materials for HBM studies (M12)
- AD4.2 Periodic report on analytical methods and measurements for exposure and effect biomarkers (new delivery date M36)
- D4.3 1st Progress report on the general survey (M36)
- D4.8 2nd Progress report on the general survey (M48)
- D4.12 3rd Progress report on the general survey (M60)
- D2.22 2nd PARC sustainability report (M81) contribution with the final strategy for a sustainable and centrally coordinated HBM programme for Europe

Partners List:

SpF (France), VITO (Belgium), AU (Denmark), AUTH (Greece), BPI (Greece), CEA (France), CSIC (Spain), EAA (Austria), EHESP (France), Fraunhofer (Germany), KI/IMM KI (Sweden), INRS (France), INSA (Portugal), INSERM (France), INSST (Spain), ISCIII (Spain), ISS (Italy), JSI (Slovenia), KULeuven (Belgium), LNS (Luxembourg), LSMU (Lithuania), MU (Czech Republic), NIJZ (Slovenia), NIOM (Poland), NLZOH (Slovenia), UKHSA (England), SRU (Netherlands), RSU (Latvia), Sciensano (Belgium), SECO (Switzerland), STAMI (Norway), TTL (Finland), UBA (Germany), Ugent (Belgium), UGR (Spain), ULPGC (Spain), UNINA (Italy), UNIPD (Italy), UOC (Greece), UOULU (Finland), USI (Switzerland), UU-IRAS (Netherlands), WULS-SGGW (Poland)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/08/2026 (M52)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 77 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 17 179 €

A4.1.4 Data Management and analysis – 1 PROJECT

S4.1.4.1 Data management

No project submitted at present.

S4.1.4.2 Data analysis – 1 PROJECT

P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO

Project Title	Further analysis of the data generated within HBM4EU		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	DataAnalysisHBM4EU		
Project Manager	Eva Govarts Eva.govarts@vito.be	VITO	Belgium
Deputy Project manager	-	-	-
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.4.2
Project Id	P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Within the context of the HBM4EU project, a large range of human biomonitoring data has been generated via the HBM4EU Aligned Studies in adults, teenagers and children, occupational studies (chromium VI, diisocyanates and e-waste), the MOM-study (mercury exposure during pregnancy) and the SPECIMEN study (pesticide hotspots). Much useful information has already been obtained during HBM4EU and more publications are expected to be out soon. It is nevertheless foreseen that research questions will remain or will emerge from the data analysis, and not all the generated data are analysed. In order to make optimal use of the available HBM4EU data and use the results to feed into the design of HBM studies planned under PARC, further statistical analyses will be performed on HBM4EU data. More information can be generated on exposure sources and routes, exposure-effect and pathway analyses.

The project is of relevance for all regulatory frameworks restricting the production, use, environmental release, and environmental/dietary/consumer product exposure of chemicals, as well as frameworks targeted to environmental, human and worker health protection. Europe's zero-pollution agenda should depart from an understanding of how the bodies of European citizens are polluted with synthetic chemicals, and make reducing the chemical body burden and associated health impacts a key priority. Measuring exposure and effect biomarkers in human biomonitoring studies will provide insight into the extent to which chemicals and substitutes have an impact on health, and support chemical grouping approaches and avoidance of regrettable substitution.

Main expected outputs of the project

Output will be generated with regard to exposure sources and routes and exposure-effect and pathway analyses. More information will be obtained on exposure sources and routes by linking HBM data with external exposure (e.g. products/articles, environmental monitoring, lifestyle, food consumption patterns) data (measured, estimated or modelled), both on individual level (as gathered by the HBM studies) as well as obtained on an aggregated level within the time frame of the HBM sampling. Results on exposure-effect associations and exposure-effect pathways will be obtained from the further analyses of data generated within the HBM4EU Aligned Studies. The results coming out of this project will be published in scientific peer-reviewed publications, and communicated and disseminated to the general public, the PARC consortium and policy makers for regulatory uptake.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The results of the data analyses planned in this project can be used by different stakeholders:

- Policy makers/regulators/OECD, WHO, UN
 Feed into policies for reduction of exposure, use of products/articles, chemicals production and release; support risk assessment and mitigation for known and

emerging chemicals; support evaluation of the efficiency of regulation or the need for further action.

- EC, EU agencies, member states, and the scientific community
Input for exposure and hazard evaluation, modelling, risk assessment, health impact assessment; feed into monitoring of the impact of implementation of the EU's chemicals strategy for sustainability and zero pollution action plan.
- Industrial hygienists, occupational physicians, workers, trade unions
Release to the environment via production processes; worker exposure and protection.
- Citizens
Better understanding and awareness of exposure and risk; recommendations for lifestyle and prevention.

Key words: Human Biomonitoring, HBM4EU, exposure routes, exposure-effect analyses, health effects, effect biomarkers, pathways.

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives OO4: Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge, OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives, OO6: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen's understanding/awareness of chemical RA, OO8: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes, OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA, OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres and OO13: Build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical RA.

The results of the project link to the overall goal of WP4 in observing different sources, chemical fates and exposure pathways.

For the analyses of exposure sources and routes, geospatial information should be derived based on the geolocation of the participants or an aggregated level as NUTS. For this, the project will get support from partners involved in the R&I funded European Human Exposome Network (EHEN). Training will be organised for the study data owners to derive these geospatial variables for their participants. The data for this project will be shared via the PEH Data Platform initiated within HBM4EU. The newly generated data (geospatial information as environmental data) will be added to this PEH Data Platform as well. A network of research centres will be built to explore the exposure sources/routes and exposure-effect analyses. The results coming out of this project will be communicated and disseminated to the general public, the PARC consortium and policy makers for regulatory uptake.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Links to other Work package/Tasks/Activities:

- WP2: priority setting and uptake into policy
- WP3: communication on results data analyses with regard to specific research questions
- T4.1: design of general, targeted and occupational HBM surveys
- T4.2: external exposure data
- T6.2: exposure routes (modelling) and exposure-effect associations (risk and health impact assessment)
- WP7: linking of data sources and routes, data management plan, case study HBM data, innovative data analysis
- WP9: maybe training is needed on data analysis

Links to other projects:

- P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO
- P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasability_TTL
- P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_Occuphealthcare_TTL_SRU
- P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL

- P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMHES_SpF_VITO
- P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM
- P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU legacy: the project will perform further analyses on data generated and collected within HBM4EU
- European Human Exposome Network (EHEN) projects

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

Deliverable D7.1 Data management plan (M6)

Milestone MS7 Establishment of working groups (M12) by establishing a statistical working group with experts on HBM data analysis

AD4.11. Progress report statistical analyses (M36)

Partners List:

Project manager: VITO (Belgium)

Project team: AU (Denmark), AUTH (Greece), BPI (Greece), EASP (Spain), INRAE (France), INRS (France), INSA (Portugal), INSERM (France), ISCIII (Spain), ISSeP (Belgium), JSI (Slovenia), LNS (Luxembourg), LSMU (Lithuania), MU (Czech Republic), NIJZ (Slovenia), NIPH (Norway), Sciensano (Belgium), SPF (France), SZU-SK (Slovakia), TTL (Finland), UBA (Germany), UGR (Spain), UNIVIE (Austria), UU-IRAS (Netherlands), VITO (Belgium)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05:2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 55 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 43 951 €

A4.1.5 Preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe – 1 PROJECT

P4.1.5.a_Y1_SustainHBMSystem_VITO

Project Title	Preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	SustainHBMSystem		
Project Manager	Liese Gilles liese.gilles@vito.be	VITO	Belgium
Deputy Project manager	-	-	-
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	66*
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.5
Project Id	P4.1.5.a_Y1_SustainHBMSystem_VITO		

* The project has been broken down at M66 (that corresponds to the Final strategy for a sustainable and centrally coordinated HBM program for Europe report). As the implementation of the EU HBM survey will not depend on PARC but on decision taken at that time about the follow up of PARC. A new projet could follow for the period M67-M81 after having reviewed what has been achieved and if the evaluation is positive.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The general population human biomonitoring (HBM) survey under T4.1 (P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO), running from 2022-2028, will form the basis for chemical exposure assessment of European citizens within PARC. While the aim is to advance the concept of the HBM4EU Aligned Studies in the PARC general population survey, further steps towards implementation of a long-term sustainable HBM framework for exposure to chemicals within Europe will in parallel be taken in this project.

A long-term sustainable and inclusive HBM surveillance system for exposure to chemicals within Europe to succeed the PARC general population survey will be prepared. This system will build further on scenarios explored and recommendations developed under HBM4EU and take lessons learned from the HBM4EU Aligned Studies and PARC general survey and innovative approaches developed under various PARC Tasks into account. In addition, experts in charge of HBM surveys conducted in Europe, the USA, Canada, Japan, South Korea and Australia will be consulted. By 2028, a final concept should be ready for implementation to guide and support the HBM survey that succeeds the general survey under PARC.

The sustainable HBM system should allow to obtain truly representative and maximally harmonized exposure data for Europe to provide useful results for policy makers and to answer the information needs of citizens. The relevance of HBM results will be increased by optimisation of the number of countries and subjects to be included and samples to be collected and analysed, for instance via reduction of costs and increased efficiency of fieldwork. Harmonization will be maximized via upfront alignment of studies and application of guidelines/protocols/SOPs/supporting materials.

The project is of relevance for all regulatory frameworks restricting the production, use, environmental release, and environmental/dietary/consumer product exposure of chemicals, as well as frameworks targeted to environmental and human health protection. The exact regulatory processes and frameworks for which future EU wide HBM campaigns will provide input will depend on the regulatory strategies and questions that are most prominent at that specific point of time.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project will deliver a blueprint for a sustainable long-term Human biomonitoring program in Europe for implementation after PARC.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The results of a European HBM surveillance system with regular frequency can be used by different stakeholders:

- Policy makers/regulators/OECD, WHO, UN
 Feed into policies for reduction of exposure, use of products/articles, chemicals production and release; support risk assessment and mitigation for known and emerging chemicals; support evaluation of the efficiency of regulation or the need for further action.
- EC, EU agencies, member states, and the scientific community
 Input for exposure and hazard evaluation, modelling, risk assessment, health impact assessment; feed into monitoring of the impact of implementation of the EU's chemicals strategy for sustainability.
- Citizens
 Better understanding and awareness of exposure and risk; recommendations for lifestyle and prevention.

Baseline human exposure data will be suited for comparison with international chemical monitoring programs such as NHANES and CDC.

Key words: sustainable HBM programme, Europe, Harmonized, chemical RA toolbox.

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project responds to the PARC operational objective OO8: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes

The project will prepare the development of a sustainable HBM surveillance programme for chemical exposure of European citizens.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Links to other Work package/Tasks/Activities:

WP4:

T4.1: general population HBM survey

T4.2 & T6.2: associations between sources, external exposure to (mixtures of) chemicals and internal exposure

T4.3: development and proof of concept of innovative tools and methods

WP2: prioritization, sustainability and exit strategy

WP3: synergies

WP5: effect biomarkers

WP7: FAIR data

WP8: early warning system

WP9: capacities and infrastructure

National Hubs: implementation of the framework

Links to other projects:

P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO

P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO

P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMHES_SpF_VITO

P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU legacy: the project will build further on experiences, results, materials, and networks developed within HBM4EU
- National/regional studies participating in the general survey
- International key players in HBM research such as CDC (NHANES), Health Canada (CHMS), Japan, South Korea, Australia
- ISES HBM working groups

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D2.22: 2nd PARC sustainability report (M81).

Partners List: UBA (Germany), LNS (Luxembourg), ISCIII (Spain), VITO (Belgium), SPF (France), INSA (Portugal), LSMU (Latvia), FOPH (Switzerland), NIPH (Norway), SZU-CZ (Czech Republic), MOH-CY (Cyprus)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2027 (M66)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 9 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 7 800 €

T4.2 Environmental and Multisource Monitoring – 3 PROJECTS

Monitoring studies will be performed in EU-wide collaborative initiatives to generate environmental data according to regulatory needs and to fill in gaps in exposure data for an integrated assessment of pollution affecting environmental and human health. The steps in the T4.2 monitoring projects are outlined in Fig. 3 and will be established and tested in a Pilot Project on PFAS and Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals (Fig. 4). Based on a review of existing knowledge, activities and infrastructure of chemical analysis in the

environment, Task 4.2 will design and conduct monitoring activities with the aim to track the source and route of chemical exposure, which will also support the development of an early warning system in WP8 (‘Concepts and Toolboxes’). This includes defining a sampling strategy, also considering existing samples and sampling programmes, and selecting analytes and methods (see Fig 3).

Fig 3: PARC environmental monitoring strategy

Particular attention will be paid to a QA/QC concept (in collaboration with the T9.3). Data analysis will develop and apply state-of-the-art methods. The exploitation of the data could include spatial analysis of exposure levels, input data for exposure factors, evaluation of time trends, and comparison with benchmark values for environmental and human health protection, mixture toxicity assessment, and integration of chemical data and bioanalytical responses. In collaboration with Task 2.1, a feedback mechanism will be established to analyse whether or not the regulatory needs were met and whether new issues of scientific and/or regulatory significance emerge which should feed into new monitoring activities. Task 4.2 also works on the development and implementation of a prioritisation process to define chemicals/matrices/endpoints for future monitoring studies (see Fig 4). A third project on the human exposure to organic contaminants from non-food environmental sources is started in Year 3, connecting environmental monitoring with human biomonitoring in T4.1.

Fig 4: Summary of the three projects started in T4.2

P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU

Project Title	Establishment of the overall process of environmental and multisource monitoring with the help of a pilot study addressing PFAS and endocrine disruptors		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	EDC and PFAS pilot		
Project Manager	Katrin Vorkamp kvo@envs.au.dk	Aarhus University	Denmark
	Valeria Dulio Valeria.dulio@ineris.fr	INERIS	France
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.2.1
Project Id	P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Establishing a process for environmental and multisource monitoring is a key component in PARC. It has the purpose of supporting the EU chemical risk assessment in relation to policy needs identified in the field of i) environmental ecosystems and ii) human exposure, with a strong link to human biomonitoring. Together with the prerequisite of building on existing structures and knowledge, these objectives make environmental and multisource monitoring a complex task in PARC, which needs highly optimized processes to be fully beneficial.

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs) are two compound groups of regulatory interest due to concerns about persistence, mobility and toxicity (PFAS) and toxicity (EDCs), potentially in combination with other undesired properties and effects. There is a need for long-term monitoring of these compounds in different matrices to characterise their sources and current exposure levels, and evaluate the effect of risk-reducing measures in support of the EU's Zero Pollution ambition.

A pilot project focussing on per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and endocrine disrupting compounds (EDCs) was started in Year 1 with the purpose of establishing and validating environmental monitoring structures, including a review of state-of-the-art methods as well as the design of a monitoring study for the long-term work in T4.2. This project will continue in Year 2 with a focus on the actual monitoring study to be performed, and will proceed into Year 3 for data analysis and transfer until the formulation of lessons learnt as part of a feedback mechanism.

Main expected outputs of the project

The main outputs of the project will include:

1. Review of existing knowledge for the list of candidate EDCs and PFAS (Y1):
 - Characterisation of compound classes, exploration of possibilities of grouping
 - Review of analytical methods
 - Survey for inventory of available data and on-going monitoring studies
2. A study design (Y1 and Y2), followed by a more detailed monitoring plan targeting i) PFAS in the freshwater environment and ii) EDCs in a multicompartiment approach, including:
 - target compounds
 - analytical approaches also involving suspect and non-target screening, sum parameters (for PFAS) and effect-based methods (for EDCs)
 - the QA/QC concept
 - criteria for selection of laboratories with documented expertise in the field of the project
3. Monitoring data in Y2

4. Establishment of a feedback mechanism in Y3 that also addresses lessons learnt, with a view to adjustments in the task structure and workflows for future monitoring projects in PARC (Y3).

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

End-users: DG ENV, national environment agencies, ECHA, EEA.

Expected impact:

- Combination of existing and new monitoring data for the establishment of a baseline for two prioritised compound groups (PFAS and EDCs) that pose a risk to European environmental ecosystems in support of:
 - o EU water legislation, in particular for improvement of lists of priority pollutants, e.g. List of Priority Substances under the Water Framework Directive (WFD), Groundwater Directive (GWD), Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), etc.)
 - o EU Soil Strategy
 - o assessment of the effectiveness chemical management measures (e.g. ECHA PFAS restriction proposal).
- comprehensive assessment of environmental contamination by EDCs in terms of effect-based assessment for a broad spectrum of species-specific endocrine activities, representative of different modes of action, thereby identifying the links between observed ED activities and sources of emission of biologically active EDCs (REACH, CLP).
- Implementation of new monitoring schemes for PFAS as a whole family, including non-target and aspecific methods (TOF and TOP assays) (to support risk assessment under Drinking Water Directive approach and the ECHA PFAS restriction proposal).

Key words: Pilot study, EDCs, PFAS, environmental monitoring, knowledge gaps, freshwater, multicompartment

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives, OO6: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen's understanding/awareness of chemical RA, OO7: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA, OO8: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes and OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres.

This project is tightly intertwined with the PARC overall aim to strengthen the EU's capacity for chemical risk assessment to protect human health and the environment, as well as closely linked to projects developing innovative models and concepts for chemical risk assessments. The project will *develop, test and validate a workflow* for the design and operation of further monitoring campaigns in PARC, thereby ensuring that the future environmental and multisource monitoring will be designed based on complete and up-to-date information, answering the identified regulatory needs (e.g. Lack of consideration of mixture effects, lack of consideration of PFAS precursors for risk assessment and regulatory monitoring). Among other activities, the project will test effect-based methods for EDCs and method combinations of PFAS target analysis, screening and sum parameters. While this project is based on regulatory needs identified prior to the start of the project, future projects will include a prioritisation step, in close collaboration with T2.1.

The project will promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives by applying *innovative methods*. The *analytical monitoring work* will contribute to consolidate existing and develop new *networks of laboratories and research centres*. The project will also include a *feedback mechanism*, with a review function for prioritisation, which will foster *regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge*. The above-mentioned steps will be tested on the two case studies (PFAS and EDCs) of this pilot project, thereby supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes already identified under HBM4EU.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- Collaboration with T2.3, T4.1, T4.3, WP7 and T9.2 in the review of existing knowledge and infrastructure, which has the purpose to avoid duplication by re-using existing data, samples and other experiences.
- Collaboration with T4.1, T4.3 and WP9 to support the definition of the QA/QC concept, application of innovative methods, criteria for selection of laboratories.
- Contacts to T4.1, T6.2 and WP7 regarding data analysis and data management and transfer.

Links outside PARC

PFAS have been amongst the prioritized substances in HBM4EU and were addressed as a priority group of chemicals under the recent Horizon 2020 European Green Deal Call (January 2021). Three research projects have been funded under this call: PROMISCES, ZEROPM and SCENARIOS.

The same considerations apply to EDCs, which are an obvious example of mixture exposure, as addressed under Area 8.2: “Fostering regulatory science to address combined exposures to industrial chemicals and pharmaceuticals: from science to evidence-based policies”. Three research projects have been approved for funding under this call: ALTERNATIVE, LIFESAVER and PANORAMIX, which can provide relevant inputs to this PARC pilot project.

Relevant collaboration opportunities are also identified with the outcomes of the LIFE APEX project, in particular as regards the procedures for sample exchange, protocols for sample preparation and storage, etc. The NORMAN network will be invited to contribute, whenever relevant, in the activities of the PARC project. Links will also be established to national/regional monitoring activities, according to the prerequisite of building on existing knowledge and infrastructure, e.g. reusing samples or linking activities to existing sample stations.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD4.4 Procedures for agreement on transparent use of existing data, access to samples and involvement of external laboratories (M24)

AD4.5. Technical specifications of the study (project design, hypothesis and research question as well as analytical procedures including QA/QC and data flows) (M12)

D4.4. 1st Progress report on on-going monitoring projects (M36)

Partners List:

INERIS (FR), AU (DK), INRAE (FR), MU (CZ), SYKE (FI), UBA (DE), CNR-IRSA (IT), IVL (SE), NKUA (GR), ANSES (FR), BRGM (FR), CSTB (FR), SpF (FR), OVAM (BE), ISSeP (BE), Uantwerpen (BE), LNS (LU), VUA (NE), NILU (NO), JSI (SL), UL FFA (SL), ARSO (SL), ISCIII (ES), FISABIO (ES), UCLM (ES), EA (UK), UKCEH (UK), EFET (GR), BPI (GR), Sciensano (BE), BfG (DE), UFZ (DE), SLU (SE), Eawag (CH), CEH (UK), CNRS (FR), CSTB (FR), EV-ILVO (BE), Fraunhofer-IME (DE), ISS (IT), INSERM (FR), NIJZ (SI), NMBU (NO), ONIRIS (FR), OFB (FR), UniLu (LU), VITO (BE), VSCHT (CZ).

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 277 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 359 049 €

P4.2.b_Y2_ENVMonitoringframe_AU_INERIS

Project Title	Applications of a framework for priority setting in environmental and multi-source monitoring
Project	Monitoringframe
Acronym (15 letters max)	

Project Managers	Katrin Vorkamp kvo@envs.au.dk Valeria Dulio Valeria.dulio@ineris.fr	Aarhus University INERIS	Denmark France
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	13	Expected duration	18
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.2.1
Project Id	P4.2.b_Y2_Monitoringframe_AU_INERIS		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Monitoring environmental pollutants is crucial, for example to characterise their sources, to assess human and ecosystems exposure, and to identify compounds that need more stringent post-authorisation regulation or a full ban. Monitoring data are also instrumental to evaluate the effect of risk-reducing measures in support of the EU's Zero Pollution ambition. However, monitoring studies and/or control campaigns are costly and time-consuming ventures, and there is a need to optimise these efforts and focus them on the most relevant groups of compounds/matrices/endpoints. Prioritization steps should also ensure that no important chemicals are overlooked in a monitoring plan. This project will particularly focus on poorly- and/or non-adequately monitored (groups of) chemicals and unintentional mixtures of emerging concern. The aim is to develop an impartial, transparent, and reproducible framework to dynamically prioritize chemicals or groups of chemicals, matrices and endpoints for which focused monitoring projects need to be developed. The dynamic framework enables its application to be adapted to regulatory needs and questions, with the ability to respond to new and emerging risks.

The full project comprises of six tasks (a) to f), see below). It has to be noted that tasks a) to c), which relate to the development of the framework, are already part of the AWP for Year 1, while tasks d) to f), which relate to the testing and implementation of the system, will start in Year 2 and are the main focus of this project proposal.

- a) **Compilation of regulatory needs for monitoring**
(in collaboration with T2.1, T6.3 and National Hub Co-coordinators)
- b) **Mapping of existing prioritisation schemes and scoring systems**
(in collaboration with T6.4 and T8.2)
- c) **Development of a prioritisation framework for T4.2**
co-creation process through a series of sequential workshops (three workshops planned) with PARC partners and stakeholders, using the Delphi method
- d) **Configuration and deployment of an automated on-line tool supporting the prioritisation framework**
for exploitation of large lists of substances and datasets from different sources (cf. as available in the NORMAN Database System, WISE at EEA or IPCHEM at JRC). _The results of the prioritization tool developed in T4.2 will be made available on the PARC website. The existing prioritisation tool of the NORMAN Network might be a relevant starting point
- e) **Test of the prioritisation framework on small case study(ies)**
iterative improvements and fine tuning will be carried out based on provided feedback. Case studies could include wastewater samples, for further discussion and decision at the planned workshop.
- f) **Application of the prioritisation framework to address regulatory needs**
as defined in the first phase of the project, potentially updated after consultation with the competent authorities, with the purpose of describing the target of new monitoring studies for further work in PARC.

Main expected outputs of the project:

Altogether, including the preparatory phase (see AWP Year 1, T4.2.1 M1-M12), the project will deliver:

1. An inventory of existing prioritisation schemes and regulatory contexts they could be used for.

2. A qualitative Prioritisation Framework that allows the classification of environmental contaminants into action categories (depending on regulatory actions needed and identified areas of concern)
3. Lists of priority (groups of) substances based on identified areas of concern (e.g. hazards, potential risks, ubiquity etc.), using a quantitative scoring system for ranking
4. Lists of specific monitoring actions/campaigns in response to existing regulatory needs (e.g. source identification, compliance checking of emission limits, effectiveness evaluations of specific regulations including substitution measures, occurrence in specific compartments or matrices), also addressing knowledge gaps (e.g. new matrices to be monitored or assessed)

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

Impact expected to support current regulation and/or applied risk assessment (RA) will include among others:

- Categorisation and prioritisation of compounds that pose a risk to European freshwater systems (i.e. List of Priority Substances under the Water Framework Directive (WFD)), and marine environment (Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD))
- Categorisation and prioritisation of Substances of Very High Concern (SVHC) under REACH, for which further regulatory actions are needed (e.g. compounds that have hazardous properties, such as PBT, ED, CMR and that are found in the environment).

The framework will be based on and consider scientifically established prioritisation schemes, both international (e.g. OECD U.S. EPA) and European approaches (e.g. STE methodology (Spatial, Temporal and Extent factors of PNEC exceedances) from JRC in the context of the WFD, the prioritisation approaches from NORMAN or the Nordic Council of Ministers), thereby ensuring an efficient and relevant prioritisation approach, applicable for future monitoring projects on different geographical scales. The initial inventory will also include results of other projects, e.g. SOLUTIONS and GlobAQUA. However, these projects were developed as conceptual approaches rather than operational tools with a focus on the water phase. The approach proposed in this project aims to go beyond this scope as it is going to cover multiple and endpoints relevant for both human and environmental health.

Overall, the ambition is to define a cross-regulation and cross-compartment prioritization mechanism where the selection of chemicals/matrices/endpoints (effects) would be based on multiple lines of evidence. The prioritization mechanism should also serve the function of Early Warning System (developed in synergy with PARC T8.2). In this context in particular, it will be relevant to also consider time trends, i.e. whether about the environmental concentration or the use of a chemical is increasing over time. Moreover, the framework should consider both the hazard and risk of chemicals. The prioritisation of many individual chemicals might also be used for grouping approaches with a view to joint regulations. Finally, effect-based methods could be applied to address unknown compounds or additive effects that might be overlooked when considering individual chemicals only.

Key words: Prioritisation, risks, hazards, monitoring, matrix, endpoints, groups of compounds, emerging contaminants, regulatory needs, knowledge gaps, environmental compartments

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives OO3: Define common R&I strategies with transparent criteria and a prioritisation strategy, OO4: Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge, OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives, OO7: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA, OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA, OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake and OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC's results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA.

The proposed project is tightly intertwined with the PARC overall aim to strengthen the EU's capacity for sound chemical risk assessment, by generating lists of (groups of) substances for specific actions in response to identified knowledge gaps/regulatory needs to protect human health and the environment.

Moreover, the project is also closely linked to developing innovative models and concepts fit for future chemical risk assessments by producing an impartial, transparent approach for planning proposals for monitoring studies in PARC and beyond.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

- T2.1. Develop & implement prioritisation strategy
- T4.1 Human exposure via the environment
- T6.2 Integrative exposure & risk assessment
- T6.3 Regulatory needs
- T7.2 Data libraries
- T8.2 Early Warning System

Links outside PARC:

A wide range of initiatives involved in the prioritization of chemicals for monitoring purposes will be addressed in this project. These will be systematized in the inventory as a first activity prior to development of the actual prioritization framework. NORMAN will be a relevant source of information, including the action categories approach and the SUSDAT list of the NORMAN Database System. Links to prioritization activities by other groups and organizations (e.g. JRC, Nordic Council of Ministers, USEPA) will be explored as part of the inventory, as outlined above. The NORMAN methodology will be a starting point for the further development of a new prioritisation scheme in PARC, including elements and approaches from other available sources as decided by the project group. Interested stakeholders, e.g. CHEMSEC or PARC Activities (e.g. 8.2.2: Prioritization framework) and their approaches will be included as considered useful in the project.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

- D4.1. Description of a mechanism for selection of chemicals / matrices / endpoints for projects (M20)
- AD4.9. Final report on the prioritization project (M34)

Partners List:

UBA (DE), INERIS (FR), AU (DK), SLU (SE), ANSES (FR), ARSO (SL), BPI (EL), CEH (UK), CNRS (FR), CNR-IRSA (FR), CSIC (ES), CSTB (FR), EAWAG (CH), Fraunhofer-IME (DE), INRAE (FR), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), IVL (SE), JSI (SL), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), NILU (NO), NKUA (EL), ONIRIS (FR), OVAM (BE), Sciensano (BE), SpF (FR), SYKE, UAntwerpen, UFZ (DE), ULFFA (SL), VUA (NL)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2023 (M13)
 Expected ending date: 31/10/2024 (M30)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project (third year of PARC): 63.5 PM
 Expected ODC for the second year of the project (third year of PARC): 178 975 €

P4.2.c_Y3_Human exposure_INERIS_AU

Project Title	Human exposure to organic contaminants from non-food environmental sources		
Project	Human exposure		
Acronym (15 letters max)			
Project Managers	Matteo Creta Matteo.Creta@lns.etat.lu Ruth Moeller Ruth.Moeller@lns.etat.lu Maria-José Rueda-Lopez Maria-Jose.Rueda-Lopez@cstb.fr	LNS; CSTB; AU; INERIS; NILU	Luxembourg; France; Denmark; Norway

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Expected starting date	M25	Expected duration (months)	48
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	WP4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	T4.2
Project Id	P4.2.c_Y3_Human exposure_INERIS_AU		

Status: Initiation

Summary of the project

Humans are exposed to organic contaminants from a variety of sources. While food is recognized as an important exposure source and subject to systematic risk assessment regarding chemical exposure of the general population, other sources are generally studied to a lesser degree, although some of them are known to be significant. For example, dust was identified as the “missing link” in the human exposure to brominated flame retardants after original focus on exposure through food (Jones-Otazo et al., 2005). In general, dust accumulates many semi-volatile contaminants emitted in the indoor environment including less persistent compounds, such as phthalates, that do not typically accumulate in food chains (Zhu et al., 2023). The inhalation of indoor air might lead to an exposure to more volatile compounds, such as fluorotelomer alcohols (FTOHs), which can be transformed to perfluorocarboxylic acids (PFCAs) after uptake (Schlummer et al., 2013). Dermal uptake can occur from direct contact with consumer products and indoor surfaces (Frederiksen et al., 2018). Other relevant exposure sources include drinking water, especially for water-soluble compounds (Domingo and Nadal, 2019). For children, ingestion of soil has repeatedly been reported (van Wijnen et al., 1990), although it will likely not be a permanent exposure situation. Although non-food sources have been recognized as potentially significant for human exposure to a variety of chemicals, and guidelines for exposure determination through these pathways exist (ECHA, 2016), they are not monitored or assessed in the same comprehensive and systematic way as food-related exposure sources.

The proposed project is intended to support the T4.1 General Human Biomonitoring Survey (also called the “PARC aligned studies”) within the T4.1 project on the General Population Survey (P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO) with exposure data from environmental samples. The project is a proof of concept, testing the hypothesis that some internal exposure biomarkers can be linked to external exposure data other than food, leading to improved interpretability of the internal exposure data. Food as an exposure source is widely recognized and can be included in this study on the basis of existing data, e.g. from national and/or European monitoring efforts. However, the use of chemicals in consumer products presents a more complex situation where non-food pathways may play a greater role than anticipated so far. For brominated flame retardants, for example, correlations between dust and human plasma were shown (Frederiksen et al., 2010). Recent studies on contributions from different exposure pathways to PFAS in human serum confirmed food as the major exposure source, but also identified dust and indoor air as significant contributors, as well as a large individual variation (Poothong et al., 2020). This variation is specifically addressed in the study approach linking human and environmental samples for the same individuals.

The selected chemicals will be related to the prioritised chemicals in T4.1 (i.e. phthalates, bisphenols, PFAS, pesticides), but also include additional compounds known to be important pollutants in the respective matrices, e.g. flame retardants, non-phthalate plasticizers or chlorinated paraffins in the indoor environment, as well as the identification of compounds in suspect and/or non-target screening approaches.

The overall study outline is visualized in Figure 5, consisting of a substantial cross-section with T4.1 as well as task-specific activities. In order to reduce dependency on sampling possibilities in T4.1, the study will also use existing samples (of dust and soil) and complementary sampling to study the exposure from non-food sources. This is a relevant research and monitoring topic in itself, even if the samples do not directly reflect exposure of the specific study participants in the T4.1 General Survey. Given the large variability that has been documented for chemicals in dust (Vorkamp et al., 2011; Zhu et al., 2023), a broader approach including existing samples will improve the possibilities of establishing mean levels for e.g. spatial comparisons, and of setting the individual's exposure into a broader perspective.

Although some national regulatory frameworks exist for e.g. indoor air quality in public buildings and labelling of construction materials, the indoor environment is not addressed in a dedicated European framework or covered by an EU-wide systematic monitoring programme. As such, the project does not address a specific regulatory topic or body, but will provide data for a better assessment of a not previously systematized field, which can be combined with food-based data in an integrative exposure assessment approach. Several typical indoor contaminants are regulated under e.g. REACH, including the list of Substances of Very High Concern (SVHC) and the Biocidal Product Regulation. PFAS are subject of the recent restriction proposal submitted to the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) and also an important parameter in the EU Drinking Water Directive (EU/2020/2184), alongside many other problematic chemicals, such as pesticides, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and chlorinated solvents. Pesticides are regulated under the Regulation for Plant Protection Products (1107/2009). Chemicals in cosmetics are addressed under the Regulation for Cosmetic Products. Exposure to chemicals from soil is relevant for the recently proposed Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience. Thus, the project will contribute to improvements of cross-regulatory assessments of relevance to several regulatory bodies, thus stimulating important steps towards “one substance-one assessment” approaches. The connection with T4.1 General Human Biomonitoring Survey explores possibilities of more holistic risk assessments in a One Health approach.

Identification of exposure to chemicals of emerging concern, including substitutes for banned substances, can serve as a warning of risks that may have been overlooked. As the project has a direct supporting function for the General Human Biomonitoring Survey under T4.1, it also supports the policies and regulatory initiatives in the focus of the General Survey.

Fig. 5: Conceptual study outline in support of the General Human Biomonitoring Survey in T4.1. The extent of the cross-section will be decided in preparatory meetings with T4.1 and depend on the obtainability of exposure samples linked to the T4.1 General Human Biomonitoring Survey.

Main expected outputs of the project:

The project aims to generate exposure data on relevant non-food exposure pathways for chemicals prioritised in T4.1 and for the individuals involved in the T4.1 General Human Biomonitoring Survey, to the extent that the collection of environmental samples is feasible within this project. These samples will include indoor dust, indoor air, drinking water and soil (from participants' gardens). Details on approach and practicalities are given under “Actions planned” below. Thus, the project will test the concept of linking internal exposure biomarkers to external exposure data from exposure media other than food. If successful, this link will support the interpretation of the internal exposure data obtained in the General Human Biomonitoring Survey. It will be a strength of this project that these data will be obtained in a harmonized and standardized manner.

Beyond the connection with T4.1, the project also aims to

- Generate data on chemicals of importance for specific exposure pathways, for example flame retardants in indoor air and dust, plastic additives in consumer products etc. The extent of these supplementary analyses depends on budgets, sample availability and analytical expertise in the project group and will be further defined in the preparatory phase of the project. These analyses refer to the project part that does not overlap with T4.1 (Fig. 5), but could also link to national studies potentially including more biomarkers than those prioritised in T4.1. The task-specific project part will be developed as a potential standalone project, should the strong interlinkage with T4.1 present difficulties (e.g. in terms of timelines, additional sample collections etc.).
- Obtain supplementary information from existing samples from other locations, since project partners in T4.2 have access to environmental specimen banks including dust and soil samples. These will be catalogued and addressed with regard to potential use in the project, e.g. for spatial comparisons. Likewise, complementary sampling of non-stored matrices (drinking water, indoor air) can be considered. Geographical differences have been shown for chemicals in indoor air and dust in Europe (e.g. Esplugas et al., 2022). However, given the large variability that has been documented for semi-volatile organic chemicals in indoor air and dust (Vorkamp et al., 2011), a relatively large number of samples is necessary to establish robust mean values and their variation between locations. In order to improve representativeness, the project will also include existing samples and/or additionally collected samples, to the extent feasible in the overall project plan and budget. This will also allow better assessment of the individual's exposure situation in the cross-sectional part of the study with T4.1.
- Identify other compounds in suspect and non-target screening approaches, with connections to Early Warning Systems in PARC (T8.2) and potential indications of new relevant biomarkers in T4.1. This part offers further collaboration possibilities with T4.3.
- Work towards reference values (primarily dust and air), based on the statistical distributions of measured chemical concentrations in a matrix (AGÖF, 2013). These are statistically derived and not toxicity-based reference values.

As mentioned above, it is important to plan this part of the study carefully to reduce dependency on sampling campaigns in relation to T4.1 which may carry currently unknown obstacles (e.g. non-compatible timelines, limitations for additional sampling due to ethical approval etc.).

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

If successful in linking internal and external exposure measurements, this project will allow to study associations between internal and external exposure for a variety of chemicals, age groups and European countries, and thus identify relevant non-food exposure pathways. Information on exposure of food can be included on the basis of existing data. However, food monitoring is relatively well-established and coordinated with EFSA as the central European authority, whereas some non-food exposure pathways, in particular the indoor environment, have only been subject to specifically dedicated research projects. As previous studies have shown associations between chemicals in e.g. dust and human blood (Frederiksen et al., 2010) or otherwise identified indoor air and dust as a non-negligible exposure source (Fridén et al., 2011), a complete assessment of human exposure needs more focus on non-food exposure sources and pathways. The process will contribute to the intended integration of human and environmental monitoring in WP4 and the One Health approach envisioned in PARC, improving the understanding of human exposure and providing data for more holistic risk assessment approaches. This will be of particular interest for policy makers in chemicals management and for the scientific community within and beyond PARC.

Furthermore, the draft reference values for air and dust which will be derived using statistical approaches as well as the identifications of new compounds in specific exposure media will be particularly relevant for regulatory bodies. The envisaged reference values are purely statistical values (P50, P90 etc.) indicating whether an indoor dust or air concentration is within the typical range measured in a building. This has been applied to Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) in indoor air (AGÖF, 2013) and is useful where no health-based guidance values exist. The World Health Organization (WHO) has published guidelines for Indoor Air Quality, but they remain limited to a very small number of substances. Given the large variability

of indoor concentrations of semi-volatile organic compounds, statistical approaches need a certain number of samples to result in reliable draft reference values.

The chemicals covered by this study are currently addressed in a variety of directives and policy frameworks, with examples given above. This study will contribute to overcoming silo-approaches and will work towards “one substance-one assessment” solutions. It is important to note that the project will not target a specific regulatory topic or body, but provide data for an integrative assessment of human exposure which has been systematized for food, but not for other exposure sources of potentially similar or even higher importance.

Finally, the project will liaise with WP6 with regard to consumer products as a potential direct and indirect exposure source, i.e. via direct contact and emissions to the environment. Chemical analyses might be included, to the extent methodologies are available, and literature data will be collected. Therefore, we also expect an interest from the manufacturing industry and trade organizations in relevant fields.

Even if the intended close link to T4.1 has to be reduced because of potential practical limitations, the study will deliver these important outcomes of the task-specific standalone part, i.e. draft reference values, identification of new compounds, knowledge of chemicals in consumer products, and related inputs towards “one substance-one assessment” approaches.

Key words: Articles, BPA (analogues), emerging chemicals, environmental monitoring, exposure routes, human exposure, multi-source exposure

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives: OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives, OO7: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA, OO8: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes, OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA, OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake and OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres.

The project will contribute to each of the specific objectives in PARC, due to the cross-cutting nature of the project. Under SO1 (cross-disciplinary network to set priorities for R&I in chemical RA), we expect contributions to OO5, for example via the interface with the Horizon Europe cluster IDEAL, as further described below. We expect the project to contribute to all operational objectives under SO2 (carry out a joint R&I programme to respond to the agreed priorities in chemical RA). The project relates to OO7 as it will contribute to a work programme that includes needs of integration of human and environmental monitoring approaches in chemical risk assessment. It directly responds to OO8 extending the Human Biomonitoring platform (to external exposure data) and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes. As in all projects in T4.2, FAIR data practices will be implemented and complex data will be analysed, with possibilities of testing and applying innovative concepts (OO10). The project will be linked to the Early Warning System via the close connection established between T4.2 and T8.2 in ongoing projects. Specifically, the use of suspect and non-target screening approaches intended for this project links directly with the strategies for an Early Warning System in T8.2. Thus, information on newly identified compounds can be provided in a one-off initiative, for example for one of the case studies in T8.2. Furthermore, the monitoring strategy to be developed in this project can be incorporated in an Early Warning System for future studies on non-food human exposure sources. The project will provide information for use in integrative risk assessment, both explicitly mentioned under OO12, by integrating human and environmental monitoring data and approaches across compounds and matrices. We also see a contribution to SO3 (access to R&I capacities required to implement innovative chemical RA), in particular OO11. In close collaboration with WP9, the project will consolidate and extend existing networks and contacts between laboratories in the field of environmental analyses. Several partners in T4.2 have expertise in the analysis of environmental contaminants in the indoor environment and/or drinking water and soil.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Besides its focus on environmental monitoring, the project will establish a substantial cross-section with T4.1 to test the concept that internal exposure data generated in the General Human Biomonitoring Survey can be linked to external exposure data from non-food sources (Fig. 5). Statistically derived external exposure reference values (dust, air) will complement internal exposure reference values and allow the evaluation of spatial and temporal trends in chemical exposure, also with a view to effectiveness evaluations of regulatory efforts. Emerging substances can be identified for future selection of HBM exposure biomarkers and regulatory risk management needs.

The generated dataset will be of interest also to exposure models developed in WP6 to predict the correlation between environmental and internal concentrations. Specifically, the PFAS data obtained in this project will support the aggregate PFAS exposure model developed in T6.2. Currently, there is a significant lack of data regarding the sources and indoor concentrations of PFAS, to run and validate this model.

An obvious link exists with T4.3 since the project will also apply innovative techniques such as suspect and non-target screening. Further fields of collaboration will be elucidated over the course of the project. Collaborations with WP7 and T9.3 are foreseen in the fields of data analysis and transfer and the project's QA/QC concept, respectively. Furthermore, T4.2 has a close collaboration with T8.2 where mutual information exchange is ongoing and should also be continued in this project. Given the obvious link to the IDEAL cluster which also includes involvement of several T4.2 partners, potential information exchange and collaborations will involve T3.2.

Links outside PARC:

The importance of indoor air quality in the context of human exposure and health has been internationally recognised. The cluster IDEAL includes several Horizon Europe projects that address this topic. It will provide data, exposure assessment strategies and policy advice at the interface of the current project. Several T4.2 partners are involved in the IDEAL cluster and can make relevant connections.

The NORMAN network has a working group on ambient and indoor air, also working on dust as a relevant exposure matrix, where emerging substances and techniques are addressed, which will also be of interest to this project. NORMAN also has extensive experience with water monitoring, which will be beneficial for the drinking water part of this study. Projects in the European Human Exposome Network (EHEN) would be relevant to connect with this study. Furthermore, the project will be linked to the national and regional studies participating in the T4.1 General Human Biomonitoring Survey.

Given the importance and knowledge gaps in the field of PFAS occurrence and exposure, several European countries have established dedicated PFAS expert groups and developed PFAS action plans, for example aiming at efficient production of scientific knowledge and easier access to information for citizens. The project will also support these initiatives.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD4.10: Description of the study concept, including i) collaborative component with T4.1; ii) complementary work to complete the external exposure study; iii) selected compounds and iv) summary of sampling techniques and analytical methods (M36). The integration of human biomonitoring and external exposure monitoring is considered relevant for risk assessment and regulatory work in more holistic approaches, including a One Health concept.

AD4.14. The overall project report will provide relevant data aiming at links between internal and external exposure for the same individual, concentrations of prioritized chemicals in non-food exposure media and new knowledge and experiences in integrative approaches. Since only few studies exist that link human and environmental monitoring, the project will provide relevant new information for risk assessors and policy makers, also at the methodological and conceptual level (M72).

Partners List:

Project co-leading group: AU (Denmark), INERIS (France), LNS (Luxembourg), CSBT (France), NILU (Norway)

Key contributors: VITO (Belgium), MU (Czech Republic), UBA (Germany), IVL (Sweden), AUTH

(Greece), NKUA (Greece), key contributors involved in collecting the environmental samples in the General HBM Survey

Extended group: BRGM (France), ISCIII (Spain), IDAEA-CSIC (Spain), ISSeP (Belgium), JSI (Slovenia), OVAM (Belgium), UAntwerp (Belgium), UL (Latvia), UniLU (Luxembourg), VSCHT (Czech Republic), UPV/EHU (Spain), ISS (Italy), MO-CY/SBL (Cyprus), RSU (Latvia)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2024 (M25)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2028 (M72)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project (third year of PARC): 83 PM

Expected ODC for the first year of the project (third year of PARC): This information will be collected as part of the project for Landmark L4 (M36). The reason is that practical details affecting ODCs (e.g. number of samples, chemical analysis) will be defined as part of the project.

T4.3 Innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys – 9 PROJECTS

Innovative (self-)sampling approaches will be evaluated for applicability in large scale monitoring programmes and specific surveys addressing population groups such as the occupational population. Innovative high-throughput *in vitro* and/or *in vivo* bioassays for effect-based environmental and human exposure monitoring will be improved. Suspect Screening approaches will be harmonised across the environment-food-HBM communities in terms of definitions, objectives supporting policy context, and technical implementation. Non-Targeted Screening approaches will be promoted and harmonised to complement multiple exposure assessment across the environmental, food safety and HBM fields and to comply with regulatory needs. These innovative approaches will be evaluated through complementary proof-of-concepts each dealing with a given particular new sampling and measurement approach applied to a given exposure/sample type and sub-population.

Fig 6: Projects structuration under Task 4.3

Fig 7: T4.3 Projects timeline

A4.3.1 Transversal actions –3 PROJECTS

P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02-QAQC_WR

Project Title	QA/QC requirements for HRMS and EDA-based screening approaches in environmental, food and human matrices		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	QA/QC for HRMS and EDA		
Project Manager	Rosalie Nijssen rosalie.nijssen@wur.nl	WR (WFSR)	NL
Deputy Project manager	Karsten Beekmann Karsten.beekmann@wur.nl	-	-
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	60*
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.1
Project Id	P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QAQC_WR		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M60

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Suspect and non-target screening (SS/NTS) is a key component in PARC to find chemicals beyond the currently known and prioritised ones. The chemical and biological effect-based approaches for SS/NTS are relatively new and quality assurance and quality control is not yet well established and harmonised. This project will consist to develop a transversal action aiming at defining minimal common quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC) requirements to be used specifically for chemical suspect and non-targeted screening methods (SS/NTS) based on chromatography coupled to high resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) and biological effect-directed assays (EDA). This project will inventory the existing QA/QC procedures, guidelines, proposals (and interpretations thereof) in the food, environmental and human biomonitoring (HBM) domains, identify inconsistencies and gaps, and aims to align and establish procedures and criteria across the application domains.

Main expected outputs of the project

- 1) More consistent and comparable data from suspect- and non-target screening methods generated by multiple laboratories (within application domains)
- 2) Implementation of harmonised approaches across application domains (environment, HBM, food)

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The proposed project appears as a necessary follow-up of the work achieved under HBM4EU, where a number of QA/QC provisions, guidance SOP, and supporting template for QA/QC data analysis were produced in the particular context of the Specimen Study (pesticide screening in 2000 human urine samples from 5 countries by 5 different laboratories). From that basis, the goal of the present project is to deliver to end-users interested to implement those innovative screening approaches an extended and consolidated QA/QC framework to be applied more globally for a wide range of different applications within the environmental-food-HBM communities. This medium-term perspective should benefit a number of end-users and stakeholders through improvement of data quality / comparability.

Key words:

Quality Control, Quality Assurance, suspect screening, non-target screening, identification, effect-directed assays

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives, OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC's results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA and OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres.

This project will deal with necessary QA/QC provisions specifically dedicated to the innovative approaches developed under task 4.3. Indeed, the analytical chemistry community has developed for many years appropriate QA/QC provisions for assessing the performance of conventional targeted methods applied to environmental, food or human matrices. The situation is less mature for emerging and innovative approaches where the objectives differ from the previous ones. A main need for qualitative (or semi-quantitative) suspect and non-targeted approaches relies on the precise and transparent documentation of the method application range, i.e., the contour of the accessible markers of exposure, in order to possibly compare and well interpret the results obtained by different methods. This workline was explicitly included in the task 4.3 DoA.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project is very closely linked to WP9/task 9.3, and WP4, specifically to the QA/QC activities therein (T4.1.2, T4.2.4). Several experts/key contributors from these tasks are also involved in the present project 4.3_T02 that will permit to establish this necessary articulation. While in T9.3 overarching frameworks are set, this activity focusses specifically on HRMS and EDA based screening methods, and for that the generation of experimental- and experience-based QA/QC criteria and requirements, and establishing QA/QC programs of SS/NTS and EDA. Prioritised substance groups in activities in T4.1 and T4.2 are taken into account with respect to type of chemicals addressed (e.g., PFAS and endocrine disruptors, EDCs), and possible integration of QA/QC programs (e.g. proficiency testing using the same control materials in both target and screening methods).

Links outside PARC:

Within the below mentioned projects and already existing regulations/guidance documents, QA/QC for screening methods has been (partially) addressed to various levels of detail. This project will link with and build forth on these projects:

HBM4EU (<https://www.hbm4eu.eu/>)

NORMAN (<https://www.norman-network.com/?q=Home>)

MetroFood (<https://www.metrofood.eu/>)

JRC (<https://crm.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>)

EU-TOXRISK/RISKHUNT3R (<https://www.eu-toxrisk.eu/>)

Food screening regulations, e.g., dioxins Calux Commission Regulation (EU) 2017/644

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD4.5: Technical specifications of the study (project design, hypothesis and research question as well as analytical procedures including QA/QC and data flows) (M12)

AD4.12: General guideline for QA/QC in non-target screening (M60)

MS7: Establishment of working groups (M12)

Partners List:

Lead: WR (NL). Partners: INRAE (FR), ANSES (FR), AU (DK), BfG (DE), BRGM (FR), EAWAG (CH), EHESP (FR), INRS (FR), JSI (SI), KWR (NL), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), MUI (AU), ORU-MTM (SE), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (UA), UBA (DE), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), AUTH (GR), EV-ILVO (BE), CSIC (ES), LNE (FR) NILU (NO), WULS (PL)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2027 (M60)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 20 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 41 565 €

P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03_EWStools_SLU

Project Title	Illustrating the usefulness of innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to early warning system and harmonized framework from environment-food-human		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Early Warning System Tools		
Project Manager	Lutz Ahrens Lutz.ahrens@slu.se	SLU	Sweden
Deputy Project manager	Georgios Niarchos georgios.niarchos@slu.se	SLU	Sweden
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	60
PARC Workpackage number	4.3	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.1.c
Project Id	P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03_EWStools_SLU		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Establishment of an early warning system (EWS) for identification of new and existing potentially hazardous substances is a key component in PARC and current EU regulatory actions. For prioritization of new chemicals, several tools have been developed that can be used in combination or independently, among which suspect and non-targeted screening coupled to effect directed analyses approaches. This project will support the development of EWS under WP8 (task 8.2) by ensuring that data generated through those innovative methods can be used to identify and prioritize hazardous substances in human, food and environmental matrices that may be associated with a potential risk. The project will illustrate the usefulness of early warning monitoring tools both for environmental samples (e.g. soil, sediment, sludge, dust), human samples (e.g. blood), food (incl. drinking water) and products (incl. waste streams, recycled products). The project will identify in particular chemical properties, toxicological endpoints and HRMS features relevant for the EWS, initially with the purpose to gather all necessary ones, and then identify criteria to assign relative weights to each parameter and endpoint.

Main expected outputs of the project

Review already existing information related to innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as early warning monitoring tools
 Contribute/formulate criteria for categorizing annotated data to be integrated in the EWS format.
 Elaborate a proof-of-concept illustrating (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to EWS.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project will generate proofs-of-concepts and tools of relevance to risk assessors and policy makers at national and EU level. Innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches are of utmost importance for identification of new and existing potentially hazardous substances at an early stage. Cutting edge tools will be conceptualized and illustrated for establishment of an EWS. End-users include ECHA, EFSA, EEA, national environmental and chemical agencies, national food safety authorities, NORMAN, researchers, industry, NGOs, national consumer protection organizations and the general public.

Key words:

Early warning system (EWS); early warning monitoring tools; Effect-Directed Analysis (EDA); suspect and non-targeted screening (NTS); high resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS); innovative sampling

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives OO3: Define common R&I strategies with transparent criteria and a prioritisation strategy, OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives, OO7: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA, OO8: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes, OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA, OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake, OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC’s results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA, OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres and OO13: Build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical RA.

The project will establish a proof-of-concept illustration of innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to early warning systems and harmonized framework from environment-food-human. This will ensure that the generated data can be used to support the development of early warning systems under WP8 to communicate risks, facilitate awareness of risks and disseminate warnings to inform risk assessors and risk managers at an early stage of future challenges or emerging risks, linked to other activities and future projects in PARC.

For the development of a proof-of-concept early warning system, criteria for a prioritization strategy for hazardous chemicals will be defined in cooperation with other R&I initiatives. The concept of early warning system tools and towards an early warning system will be shared within the joint R&I programme. The results coming out of this project will be communicated and disseminated to the general public, the PARC consortium and policy makers for regulatory uptake.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP4:

- 4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01_Concept Paper_MU: Alignment of objectives / purposes of SS/NTS/EDA
- 4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QA/QC Issues_WR: Ensure quality of the generated data
- 4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04_Data Processing Workflow_EHESP: Support annotation of generated data
- 4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE: Ensure useful output for EWS
- 4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02_Occupational exposure_INRS: Ensure useful output for EWS
- 4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03_Other complementary studies_JSI: Ensure useful output for EWS
- 4.3/4.3.3/P4.3.3.a_Y1_E01-WBE_UFZ-UBATH: Ensure useful output for EWS
- 4.3/4.3.3/P4.3.3.b_Y2_E02-Sentinel animals_ONIRIS: Ensure useful output for EWS

WP5: Effect-directed tools based on bioassays using new approach methodologies (NAMs).
 WP7: Definition of specific requirements for SS/NTS/EDA data management (retrospective use, repository...). FAIR Data libraries.
 WP8: Conceptualization of an Early Warning System (EWS) from sampling/NTS/EDA methods in humans, environment, food and products combining exposure and hazard data. Computational methods for text mining, data curation and hazard scoring.
 WP9: Contribution to harmonised QA/QC and training for SS/NTS/EDA approaches.

Links outside PARC:

[HBM4EU](#) (data, models), [HEALS](#), [CROME-Life](#), UBA [NTS Portal with BfG](#) (Water, suspended matter), [NORMAN Network](#) activities, DG ENV Early Warning System project

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D.4.10. 3rd Proof-of-concept assessing the usefulness of innovative (self-) sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches (M60)

Partners List:

SLU (SE), INRAE (FR), VUA (NL), ANSES (FR), BRGM (FR), EAWAG (CH), JSI (SI), MUI (AT), ORU-MTM (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), UBA (DE), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), UniLU (LU), AUTH (GR), ISS (IT), NILU (NO)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)
 Expected ending date: 30/04/2027 (M60)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 7 PM
 Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 5 995 €

P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04-Data Processing Workflow_EHESP

Project Title	Establishment of necessary advanced data processing methodologies and bioinformatic tools for NTS. Identify gaps / necessary methodological improvements for retrospective use of NTS HRMS data (digital sample freezing platform) and EU capacity in terms of centralized data repository		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Data processing workflow		
Project Manager	Arthur David	EHESP	FR
Deputy Project manager	Arthur.david@ehesp.fr	-	-
	Jade Chaker	-	-
	jade.chaker@ehesp.fr		
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	60
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.1
Project Id	P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04-Data processing workflow_EHESP		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project:

Considering the vast amount of chemicals present on the market, there is currently a substantial lack of data on human and environmental exposure to these chemicals, preventing the implementation of efficient

regulatory approaches by policy makers with regard to the risk assessment of such complex real-life mixtures. Hence, suspect screening and non-targeted analyses based on high-resolution offer great promises to identify emerging and chemical mixtures without a priori. The lack of comprehensive and user-friendly automated pipeline for suspect (SS) and non-targeted screening (NTS) data processing however appears as a crucial issue and current major bottleneck for efficient implementation of these approaches. Indeed, a wide range of software tools are today available to perform one or several components of such data processing and extraction of the useful information from the raw data, including peak picking, peak alignment, and annotation. But still no consensual guidelines were proposed regarding both a preferable selection from this panel of existing tool or their fine appropriate parameterization in the context of NTS. Overall, an integrated, sustainable, and open access solution permitting to perform all these necessary steps with sufficient QA/QC consolidation for support to policy application and sufficient high throughput capacity for application to large scale cohorts, is still lacking and is urgently needed.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Buildt a strong and dynamic consortium within the environment-food safety-HBM scientific communities to harmonize and mutualize the current and future resources
 - Updated CECScreen database with the aim to improve the annotation quality
 - Pursued development of an extended, unified, sustainable and open access European MS reference library through the collaborative generation of MS and MS/MS reference spectra
 - Developed comprehensive and user-friendly automated pipeline for SS and NTS
 - Defined appropriate quality strategies to ensure retrospective analyses/early warning system
 - Developed / improved appropriate data processing workflow dedicated to bioassay data

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project appears as a pre-requisite methodological development related activity, expected to provide at medium term (4 years) new consolidated ground to implement SS/NTS approaches at larger scale and provide new data on human and environmental exposure for policy makers. This medium-term perspective should benefit a number of end-users including laboratories aiming to implement those new analytical approaches (capacity building within the EU), as well as actors aiming to build and use early warning systems for which the expected new exposure data generation capabilities will represent a significant input, including sanitary agencies, risk assessors, and public health authorities.

Key words:

Suspect screening; non-targeted screening; data processing, annotation, user-friendly workflow; CECScreen database; reference library; marker identification; automation

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives, OO7: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA, OO8: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes, OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA, OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake and OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres.

The development of this comprehensive and user-friendly automated pipeline for SS and NTS is a necessary step for all the projects that will use these strategies in WP4 and other related WPs. Following the work done in HBM4EU, the development of an extended, unified, sustainable and open access European MS reference library as a key stone of the annotation workflow underlying to these HRMS-based suspect screening approaches applied across the environment-food-human continuum is clearly part of the defined DoA for task 4.3, as well as the establishment of necessary advanced data processing methodologies and bioinformatic tools for better efficiency and deployment of NTS (e.g. inspired from the Workflow for Metabolomics W4M/Galaxy user friendly environment).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP4:

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01_Concept Paper_MU: Alignment of objectives / purposes of SS/NTS/EDA

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QA/QC Issues_WR: Ensure quality of the generated data

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE: Mutualized resources / harmonization

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02_Occupational exposure_INRS: Mutualized resources / harmonization

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03_Other complementary studies_JSI: Mutualized resources / harmonization

4.3/4.3.3/P4.3.3.a_Y1_E01-WBE_UFZ-UBATH: Mutualized resources / harmonization

4.3/4.3.3/P4.3.3.b_Y2_E02-Sentinel animals_ONIRIS: Mutualized resources / harmonization

WP7: Definition of specific requirements for SS/NTS/EDA data management (retrospective use, repository...)

WP9: Contribution to harmonised QA/QC and training for SS/NTS/EDA approaches

Links outside PARC

Continuity with regard to HBM4EU WP16 related activities that has developed basis of harmonisation and development for suspect and non-targeted screening but without considering the related innovative sampling approaches considered in the present project.

NORMAN (<https://www.norman-network.com/?q=Home>), JRC (<https://crm.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>)

France-Exposome, Institut Français de Bioinformatique (IFB, ELIXIR-FR, <https://www.france-bioinformatique.fr/elixir-fr/>), ELIXIR and EIRENE infrastructures.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D.4.9 Workflow for data processing and annotation of HRMS based chemical profiles generated from suspect/NTS approaches (M54).

Partners List:

EHESP (FR), INRAE (FR), VUA (NL), ANSES (FR), INRS (FR), JSI (SI), KWR (DE), MU (CE), MUI (AT), Oniris (FR), UBA (DE), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), UniLU (LU), WR (NL)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2027 (M60)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 49 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 47 877 €

A4.3.2 Human samples based proof-of-concepts – 3 PROJECTS

P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE

Project Title	Proof-of-concept of innovative sampling and HRMS based / EDA screening methods for exploring human perinatal exposure to chemicals of emerging concern		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Perinatal exposure		
Project Manager	Jean-Philippe Antignac jean-philippe.antignac@inrae.fr	INRAE	FR
Deputy Project manager	Tarek Moufawad Tarek.moufawad@oniris-nantes.fr	INRAE	FR
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	48
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.2
Project Id	P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Capturing the complex real human chemical exposure requires new conceptual frameworks and innovative methodological approaches. These ones, from sampling to exposure data generation and analysis, are however requiring a better consolidated development and a better documented performance assessment before large scale implementation in human cohorts. As formulated by several agencies (e.g., EFSA), early stage human exposure appears in particular as a high concern not yet well addressed, both in terms of risk assessment and link to health impact at latest stages (DoHAD concept). New sampling methods (e.g., silicone wristbands and/or dried blood spots (DBS)), compatible with the non-invasiveness and restricted sample requirements typically expected for those sub-populations represent potentially relevant options to be considered in that context. Suspect and non-targeted screening approaches (SS/NTS) based on high resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) coupled to effect directed analysis (EDA) are another new trend in analytical laboratories with high potential. The aim of this project is to develop and conduct a proof-of-concept permitting to assess the performances, and illustrate the usefulness, of those innovative methods, as complementary to conventional and targeted approaches, with a focus on human samples collected from mother-newborn/child individuals. By definition screening approaches should permit to capture simultaneously various substances from different classes, relying on the global prioritization strategy from WP2, including both non persistent and persistent organic chemicals of emerging concern.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Characterization of advantages/limitations of innovative approaches compared to conventional ones
- Scientifically supported prioritisation of some of them for short term implementation
- Paved way for further developments/improvements needed for long term implementation
- Identification of relevant markers/matrices combinations for perinatal exposure assessment
- Documenting real life mixtures associated to perinatal chemical exposure
- Prioritization of further targeted developments focused on particular exposure markers evidenced
- Contribution to feed early warning system through an established link between tasks 4.3 and 8.2

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The proposed project appears as a pre-required methodological development activity, expected to provide at medium term (4 years) consolidated bases for implementing a set of innovative sampling and exposure measurement approaches for HBM. This medium-term perspective should benefit a number of end-users including laboratories aiming to implement those new analytical approaches (capacity building), as well as actors aiming to build and use early warning systems for which the expected new exposure data generation capabilities will represent a significant input, including sanitary agencies, risk assessors, and public health authorities.

Key words:

Biomonitoring, perinatal exposure, innovative methods, dry blood spots, silicone wristbands, suspect screening, non-targeted screening, effect-directed analysis, real-life mixtures, emerging chemicals

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives OO3: Define common R&I strategies with transparent criteria and a prioritisation strateg, OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives, OO6: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen's understanding/awareness of chemical RA, OO7: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA, OO8: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes, OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake and OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres.

Conventional sampling and targeted quantitative analytical methods are already available to support environmental, food and human monitoring, risk assessment, and risk management decisions. However, these approaches sometimes suffer from a lack of sensitivity to characterize lowest exposed populations,

face some limitations for large scale implementation, and only capture a limited number of a priori known and selected markers of exposure. From this global picture, a specific concern formulated by several agencies (e.g., EFSA) is related to a need for a better characterization of exposure for particularly vulnerable sub-populations, notably new-borns and young children. Human foetal exposure also appears as a not yet well addressed high concern in the context of linking this early exposure to human health impact at latest stages (DoHAD concept). This project is aiming to contribute addressing those issues related to the PARC objectives and DoA.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP4:

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01_Concept Paper_MU: Alignment of objectives / purposes of SS/NTS/EDA

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QA/QC Issues_WR: Ensure quality of the generated data

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03_Early Warning System_SLU: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04_Data Processing Workflow_EHESP: Support annotation of generated data

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02_Occupational exposure_INRS: Mutualized resources / harmonization

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03_Other complementary studies_JSI: Mutualized resources / harmonization

4.1/4.1.1: Pro/con expert review and analysis, QAQC consolidation and implementation of DBS/SWB

WP6: Potential use of some of the generated new exposure data from SS/NTS/EDA for mixture modelling

WP7: Definition of specific requirements for SS/NTS/EDA data management (retrospective use, repository...)

WP8: Potential use of some of the generated new exposure data from SS/NTS/EDA for early warning system

WP9: Contribution to harmonised QA/QC and training for SS/NTS/EDA approaches

Links outside PARC

Continuity with regard to HBM4EU WP16 related activities that has developed bases of harmonisation and development for suspect and non-targeted screening but without considering the related innovative sampling approaches considered in the present project.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D.4.5: 2nd Proof-of-concept illustrating the usefulness of innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to early warning system and risk assessment for human monitoring (M48).

Partners List:

INRAE (FR), EHESP (FR), CEA (FR), VUA (NL), KUM (DE), UNIVIE (AT), UFZ (DE), WR (NL), JSI (SI), MUI (AT), UAntwerpen (BE), UGR (SP), AU (DK), UniLU (LU), LNS (LU), UNIADBN (UK), MU (CZ), ISPV (SP), VSCHT (CZ), BPI (GR), VITO (BE), CSIC (SP), ISCII (SP), ISS (SP), SU (SE), AUTH (GR)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 90 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 202 225 €

P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02-Occupational exposure_INRS

Project Title	Proof-of-concept of innovative sampling and HRMS based / EDA screening methods for exploring occupational exposure to chemicals of emerging concern.
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Occupational exposure

Project Manager	Sophie Ndaw, sophie.ndaw@inrs.fr Radu Duca, radu.duca@lns.etat.lu	INRS LNS	FR Lux
Deputy Project manager	Baninia Habchi, baninia.habchi@inrs.fr Ogier Hanser, ogier.hanser@inrs.fr	INRS	FR
Expected starting date	13	Expected duration	48
PARC (Month number)		PARC Task/Activity/Su b-activity:	4.3.2
PARC Workpackage number	4		
Project Id	P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02-Occupational exposure_INRS		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project:

In the workplace, most workers are co-exposed to various chemicals at the same time and same place. More, the European Commission adopted a new Circular Economy Action Plan where Europe moves towards a more circular economy. The reuse and recycling of materials could result in an increase of exposure of workers involved in different steps of the waste processing chain. Innovative approaches are needed for better characterizing the nature and effects of those multiple exposure on workers' health since the conventional targeted analysis are limited to *a priori* known biomarkers. Suspect and non-targeted screening approaches (SS/NTS) enabling the detection of biomarkers of exposures and effects and coupled to new sampling methods such as dried blood spots (DBS) and silicone wristbands (SWB) represent promising new options and solutions in this context. However, these approaches are not yet widely applied in the field of human exposure assessment and biomonitoring. Both improvement and harmonization are needed before implementing these novel approaches in EU to support policy and prevention actors. The aim of this project is to develop and conduct a proof-of-concept permitting to assess the performances, and illustrate the usefulness, of those innovative methods, as complementary to conventional and targeted approaches, for particular assessment of occupational exposure.

Main expected outputs of the project:

- Characterization of advantages/limitations of innovative approaches compared to conventional ones
- Validation of innovative approaches by using selected case studies
- Scientifically and regulatory supported prioritisation of some of them for short term implementation
- Roadmap for further developments/improvements needed for long-term implementation
- Identification of relevant markers/matrices combinations for occupational exposure assessment
- Contributing to document real life mixtures associated to occupational chemical exposure, for waste management and health care sectors
- Prioritization of further targeted developments focused on particular exposure markers evidenced
- Contribution to feed the developed early warning systems through an established link between tasks 4.3 and 8.2.

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

The results of the survey should benefit to different stakeholders:

- consolidated bases for implementing a set of innovative sampling and exposure measurement approaches, which will benefit to a number of end-users including laboratories (capacity building), as well as actors aiming to build and use early warning systems for which the expected new exposure data generation capabilities will represent a significant input;
- For workers, employers, occupational hygienists and occupational physicians: better understanding and increased awareness of the potential health risk of emerging chemicals exposures, further recommendations for risk management.
- The scientific community and primarily other partners in PARC: potential added value of HBM

approach as input for further risk assessment and health impact assessment related mainly to emerging chemicals of concerned or unknown potential process related occurring chemicals.

- On a longer term, policy makers, EU and national regulators, EU Agencies (EU OSHA): deriving further regulation and guidance, evaluating the efficiency of current regulations.

Key words: Biomonitoring, occupational exposure, innovative methods, dried blood spots (DBS), silicone wristbands (SWB), suspect screening, non-targeted screening, exposures and effect biomarkers, real-life mixtures, emerging chemicals

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives OO2: Expand long-term sustainable network of National Hubs (NH), OO3: Define common R&I strategies with transparent criteria and a prioritisation strateg, OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives, OO6: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen’s understanding/awareness of chemical RA, OO7: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA, OO8: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes, OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres and OO13: Build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical RA.

The main objectives of this project consist of developing a proof-of-concept for illustrating the suitability of innovative methodological approaches such as SS/NTS and innovative sampling methods for occupational exposure assessment in Europe. Furthermore, this project contributes and improves the chemical risk assessment by studying the samples collected under Occupational survey projects (T4.1.1.4): P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP-TTL and P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthcareSurvey_TTL_SRU including regulated compounds, banned compounds and new/emerging compounds, potentially formed along the production process. In addition, a new network of laboratories and research centers will be developed and coordinated by the 15 European institutions participating in this project and each partner will be involved in the respective National Hubs (NH).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

WP4: 4.1.1/T4.1.1.5 occupational surveys:

- Identification of the partners involved in the sample collection
- Identification of suitable case studies to test and validate the innovative sampling methods from T4.3_H02
- Identification of cohorts required for the proposed project (type, volume, number, collection method, etc.)
- Organisation and management of the sampling collection in collaboration with task 4.3.
- QAQC consolidation between tasks 4.3 and 4.1 through the establishment of a specific working group in charge of evaluating advantages / limitations, necessary caution before use and implementation etc...
- Preliminary test / possible improvement before applying to real samples.
- Contribution to the evaluation of innovative sampling methods and suspect / non-targeted screening approaches based on the comparison with exposure markers obtained with conventional targeted methods

4.3.1. Transversal:

- 4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01_Concept Paper_MU: Alignment of objectives / purposes of innovative sampling approaches
- 4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QA/QC Issues_WR: Ensure quality of the generated data
- 4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04_Data Processing Workflow_EHESP: Support annotation of generated data
- 4.3.2. Human based proof-of-concept
- 4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01_Perinatal exposure_INRAE: Mutualized resources / harmonization

- 4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03_Other complementary studies_JSI: Mutualized resources / harmonization

WP6: Potential use of the generated new exposure data from innovative sampling approaches coupled to SS/NTS for exposure assessment in regulatory risk assessment

WP7: Definition of specific requirements for innovative sampling approaches coupled to SS/NTS/EDA data management (retrospective use, repository...)

WP8: Potential use of the generated new exposure data from innovative sampling approaches coupled to SS/NTS for early warning systems

WP9: Contribution to harmonised QA/QC and training for innovative sampling approaches coupled to SS/NTS approaches

Links outside PARC:

- HBM4EU legacy: WP8 of the HBM4EU project conducted studies on occupational exposure among chromate workers, e-waste workers and diisocyanate-involved workers. In those studies, multiple occupational exposures have been shown, which highlighted the need of novel methods to access poly-exposures. The present project is aiming to capitalize on those HBM4EU results to expand its scope. Various exposome research projects (amongst which EPHOR) develop innovative sampling approaches for occupational exposure assessment that are very relevant for this task.

- EU-OSHA funded project aiming to provide a practical guidance on preventing and reducing occupational exposure to HMPs, including cytotoxic drugs

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

D.4.10. 3rd Proof-of-concept assessing the usefulness of innovative (self-) sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches (M60)

Partners list: INRS (FR), LNS (LU), WULS-SGGW (PL), INRAE (FR), MUI (AT), UGR (SP), STAMI (NO), TNO (NL), UAntwerpen (BE), TTL (FI), MU (CZ), JSI (SI), WR (NL), BPI (GR), AUTH (GR)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2023 (M13)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2027 (M60)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project (third year of PARC): 19 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project (third year of PARC): 109 862 €

P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03-Complementary developments_JSI-UAntwerpen

Project Title	Complementary developments regarding the application of HRMS based / EDA screening methods on human samples		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	H03_Complementary developments		
Project Manager	Tina Kosjek tina.kosjek@ijs.si	JSI	SI
Deputy Project manager	Alexander van Nuijs alexander.vannuijs@uantwerpen.be	UAntwerpen	BE
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M25	Expected duration (months)	48
PARC Workpackage number	WP4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.2
Project Id	P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03-Complementary developments_JSI		

Status: Initiation

Summary of the project

Accurately capturing the intricacies of real-life human chemical exposure demands the introduction of novel conceptual frameworks (e.g. Exposome concept) and innovative methodological approaches (e.g. alternatives matrices, new instrumental techniques, suspect/non-targeted screening, effect-directed analyses (SS/NTS/EDA)). However, before a widescale implementation of these novel approaches within human cohorts, they still require a consolidated development and harmonization process, as well as a thorough performance assessment including the design of sampling, sample treatment, and subsequent generation and analysis of exposure data. A number of issues related to the challenges and application of those innovative methods to human samples are covered by already running Task 4.3 H01 and H02 projects, respectively focused on perinatal and occupational exposure. However, the extent of methodological aspects to be investigated and not yet considered in the previous projects, as well as a wish of direct connection between this task 4.3 component of the PARC project and the aligned studies developed within task 4.1, motivated the elaboration of the present additional project.

Policy-driven demand for more effective preventive measures calls for monitoring exposure trends and expanding our understanding of the chemical exposome, including broadening compound coverage and relating biomarkers to matrices. The justification for this expanded effort lies in the inherent limitations of current regulatory frameworks to keep pace with the dynamic landscape of the chemical space. The ever-growing pool of emerging contaminants introduces potential hazards that may go unnoticed within the confines of traditional monitoring approaches. By proactively contributing to the recognition of early warning signals, this project plays an important role in identifying chemical hazards that may otherwise escape detection. This not only supplements existing frameworks but also contributes to the continual evolution of regulatory practices. The project's broader compound coverage and correlation of biomarkers to matrices provide nuanced insights beyond what current sources offer. In the long term, our efforts aim to foster a more adaptable and responsive regulatory environment, ultimately advancing the overarching goal of ensuring the safe use of chemicals in a dynamically changing landscape. In this context, alternative matrices suited for non-invasive sampling and covering different detection windows offer the potential. Additionally, suspect and non-targeted screening approaches represent a cutting-edge trend that promises simultaneous capturing of substances from different classes, including persistent and nonpersistent organic chemicals of emerging concern. Globally, the support to policy rationale of the present project relies to the need for accelerating and improving the practical implementation of SS/NTS/EDA as a contribution to substance prioritization and early warning system. The SS/NTS/EDA methodologies are complementary screening techniques that can be employed in various combinations, either simultaneously or sequentially, based on the capabilities and resources of individual laboratories. They collectively represent Tier 1 in exposure assessment that informs subsequent targeted analyses, aiding in risk assessment and management strategies.

In this view, the primary project objective is to evaluate the effectiveness of complementary methodological strategies not yet covered in the previous task 4.3 projects, including orthogonal liquid chromatography separation systems (e.g. HILIC adapted to several highly polar compounds/metabolites (NMR is not suited due to insufficient LOD)), alternative sample preparation protocols directly impacting the analytical results (e.g. deconjugation, phospholipid removal), and the use of alternative non-invasive matrices (e.g. hair or saliva), finally leading to potential additional SOPs of interest. Another goal is to build on the key findings and lessons learned from PARC T4.3 cross-cutting projects, especially those related to quality assurance, quality control (QA/QC) and data processing challenges. We aim to use these insights as a practical way to demonstrate their value by applying them to new sets of samples. To that end, a direct link will be established to PARC task 4.1 aligned studies to source a set of supporting samples already planned to be analysed through conventional targeted methods. This proposed add-on aims at improving the range of detected compounds in the same samples (blood, urine) through HRMS-based profiling methods.

Main expected outputs of the project:

- Comprehensive synthesis of existing knowledge regarding innovative methodological approaches, including sampling (hair and saliva), sample preparation (deconjugation, phospholipid removal),

and instrumental analysis (HILIC chromatography). By highlighting the known advantages and limitations of these innovative approaches, we aim to demonstrate their potential in supplementing the traditional chemical monitoring methods. This synthesis is particularly geared toward informing policy targets and aiding in the identification of substances that demand specific attention from regulatory authorities, aligning with PARC's overarching science-to-policy objectives.

- Specific methodological developments and assessment activities to address the gaps in knowledge.
- Provide recommendations that confirm their use in relevant application areas and promote the harmonized implementation of these techniques.
- Development of a decision-ready proposal focusing on samples from T4.1 aligned studies to be used as a proof-of-concept and corresponding budget refinement
- Proof-of-concept illustrating the usefulness of these complementary approaches by using selected case studies supported by human samples originated from T4.1 aligned studies.
- Identification of relevant markers and matrices for more comprehensive exposure assessment
- Scientifically and regulatory supported prioritisation of selected complementary approaches for short-term implementation. The prioritization will be achieved through compiling the synthesis of existing knowledge and the results from the “Initial investigations” activity assessing alternative matrices, complementary sample preparations, and HILIC separation. Then, the most suitable complementary approach or matrix will be selected based on the criteria such as number, complementarity of chemical space or detection window, and the potential hazard of additional biomarkers of exposure to be identified. Documented SOPs built on the achieved methodological work, aiming at facilitating the implementation of those selected and harmonized protocols for SS/NTS/EDA applied to human samples in European laboratories
- Contribution to feed the early warning systems under development through an established link between tasks 4.3 and 8.2

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

- The project acts towards supporting method harmonization, enhancing networking, interlinking and interdisciplinarity, particularly between partners of PARC and towards capacity building in the scientific community.
- Expected new and complementary exposure data will present an input to early warning systems.
- Improved understanding and increased awareness of the potential health risk deriving from the exposure to the chemicals of emerging concern and further recommendations for risk management.
- Enhanced possibility for large-scale HBM using non-invasive sampling methods as well as for monitoring of particularly vulnerable subpopulations such as neonates, toddlers and elderly.
- Potential added value of HBM approach as input for further risk assessment and health impact assessment.
- Policy makers, EU and national regulators, EU agencies will be able to derive further regulation and guidance, evaluating the efficiency of current regulations.
- Broadened compound coverage and improved ability to monitor trends in exposure will lead to a better understanding of chemical exposome and leverage the definition of more efficient prevention measures.

Key words: Biological samples, biomarkers, human biomonitoring (HBM), suspect screening (SS), non-targeted screening (NTS), effect-directed analysis (EDA), real-life mixtures, emerging chemicals, high resolution mass spectrometry, human exposure, aligned studies, harmonisation, human relevance, regulatory relevance, innovative methods, Quality Control / Quality Assurance (QA/QC)

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

The project respond to the PARC operational objectives OO8: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes, OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC's results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative

approaches to RA and OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres.

The project addresses the need for improved chemical safety and risk assessment by overcoming limitations in conventional methods. Leveraging innovative tools, it identifies substances requiring attention from regulatory authorities, aiming for harmonized implementation in large-scale HBM contributing to OO8. Additionally, it showcases practical applications from PARC T4.3 projects, emphasizing QA/QC and data processing, thereby contributing to standardization and validation processes for innovative risk assessment approaches (OO9). With 23 partners, the project strengthens existing collaborations and forges new ones, collectively advancing chemical safety, enriching risk assessment methodologies, and supporting regulatory decision-making for public health (OO11).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

WP4:

4.1: Pro/con expert review and analysis, Collaboration established and ongoing from the beginning, i.e. from the initial project co-building phase, Capitalizing on biobanked samples of hair or saliva from 4.1 aligned studies, QAQC consolidation.

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01_Concept Paper_MU: Alignment of objectives / purposes of SS/NTS/EDA

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QA/QC Issues_WR: Ensure quality of the generated data

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03_Early Warning System_SLU: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04_Data Processing Workflow_EHESP: Support annotation of generated data

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.c_Y1_H01_Perinatal exposure_INRAE: Lessons learned / harmonization of QAQC, reporting, annotation workflow / complementarity of approaches

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02_Occupational exposure_INRS: Lessons learned / harmonization of QAQC, reporting, annotation workflow / complementarity of approaches

WP6: Potential use of some of the generated new exposure data from SS/NTS/EDA for mixture modelling

WP7: Definition of specific requirements for SS/NTS/EDA data management (retrospective use, repository...)

WP8: Potential use of some of the generated new exposure data from SS/NTS/EDA for early warning system

WP9: Contribution to harmonised QA/QC and training for SS/NTS/EDA approaches

Links outside PARC:

Continuity with regard to HBM4EU WP16 related activities that has provided a basis of harmonization and development for suspect and non-targeted screening but without considering the complementary developments of the present project.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD4.13: Proof-of-concept on the application of the complementary approaches/matrices to real samples from HBM surveys (M70)

Partners List:

Leads: JSI (SI), UAntwerpen (BE), Participants: AUTH (GR), BPI (GR), CEA (FR), IISPV (ES), ISCIII (ES), ISS (IT), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), SU (SE), UFZ (DE), VITO (BE), VSCHT (CZ), VUA (NL), WR (NL), WULS (PL), INRAE (FR), CNRS (FR), CSIC (ES), INRS (FR), AU (DK)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2024 (M25)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2028 (M72)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project (third year of PARC): to be determined

Expected ODC for the first year of the project (third year of PARC): to be determined

A4.3.3 Environment samples based proof-of-concepts – 2 PROJECTS

P4.3.3.a_Y1_EO1-Wastewater based epidemiology_UFZ-UBATH

Project Title	Mining chemical information from wastewater treatment plants for I. human community (<i>wastewater fingerprinting for community wide human exposure assessment</i>) and II. environmental exposure assessment (<i>screening of wastewater treatment plant effluents to assess the release of Chemicals of Emerging Concern into the water cycle</i>).		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Wastewater based epidemiology		
Project Manager	Werner Brack werner.brack@ufz.de	UFZ	DE
Deputy Project manager	Barbara Kasprzyk-Hordern bkh20@bath.ac.uk	UBATH	UK
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	48*
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.3
Project Id	P4.3.3.a_Y1_EO1-Wastewater-based epidemiology_UFZ-UBATH		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M48

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Wastewater can serve as a source of information with respect to human exposure, by measuring specific human metabolites in raw sewage (wastewater-based epidemiology – WBE). WWTPs are a main source for complex mixtures of chemicals in surface water, impacting the environment and human health (e.g., via drinking water). This project addresses both human and environmental exposure, focusing on (i) wastewater fingerprinting for community wide human exposure assessment and (ii) on screening of WWTP effluents to assess the release of Chemicals of Emerging Concern (CECs) into the water cycle. The development of wastewater-based epidemiology (WBE) as well as the screening of effluents using suspect and nontarget screening (SS/NTS) approaches and effect-directed analysis (EDA) will deliver innovative methods for community wide human exposure assessment, environmental exposure assessment and the identification of CECs of (eco-)toxicological concern. The European-scale monitoring data generated by these methods as well as a re-evaluation of existing data will greatly improve our knowledge on CECs in wastewater and their primary sources as a basis for the revision of the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive with regard to reducing CEC emissions, providing candidate compounds and information on their sources for priority/river-basin-specific chemicals in the context of the Water Framework Directive, and providing information on chemical mixtures for the revision of REACH with regard to environmental mixture concerns.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Innovative screening / targeted methods for community-wide chemical exposure assessment by WBE
- Innovative screening methods and workflows for environmental exposure assessment of wastewater
- Europe-wide human community exposure patterns via targeted and non-targeted WBE
- Wastewater and source patterns representing typical emission scenarios in Europe
- Prioritisation of compounds of concern emitted with wastewater for further assessment

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

We will develop innovative analytical approaches that will define future approaches to exposure studies, both in the context of environmental and public health. This project is potentially transformative for several stakeholder groups including, regulatory sectors (e.g. water quality/control authorities) and public health agencies.

Key words

wastewater, wastewater-based epidemiology, suspect and nontarget screening, compound prioritization, community exposure assessment, mixture risk drivers, effect-directed analysis

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives, OO8: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes, OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA, OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake, OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC's results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA and OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres.

The project provides human exposure (via WBE), environmental and multisource monitoring data for regulatory purposes from the mining of existing HRMS-based datasets and Pan-European monitoring studies (OO8, OO10). The project enhances the collaboration between the partners conducting WBE and wastewater monitoring through consolidated and harmonised analytical and data processing workflows (OO11). Developing a proof-of-concept for illustrating the capacities of SS/NTS/EDA approaches in the particular case of environmental monitoring as an innovative approach feeding into regulatory risk assessment (OO12, OO9).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The proposed project will be closely linked to Tasks 4.1 (Human exposure assessment) and 4.2 (Environmental and multisource monitoring) especially P4.2.c_Y3_(Human exposure_INERIS_AU Project Title, Human exposure to organic contaminants from non-food environmental sources) providing innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys supporting these tasks. This project will inform on toxicity data gaps of concern based on realistic human and environmental exposure (Task 5.1) and will closely collaborate with Task 5.2 on innovative tools for toxicity testing, filtering Task 5.2 tools for methods useful for effect-directed analysis. The project will provide valuable measured human and environmental exposure information as input to Task 6.2. The project will also feed in directly into Task 8.2 aiming at the establishment of an early warning system.

Links outside PARC

Within the EU Horizon 2020 COST action SCORE (www.score-cost.eu), activities in the field of WBE are initiated and coordinated. While the main focus was on illicit drugs, the focus is shifting towards current, in-use compounds to investigate patterns of factors related to lifestyle, disease and environment. Hydra-EWS: Marie Curie initiative led by University of Bath (UBAH), in which connection with task 4.3 is already made, possibly providing synergy. E-PRTR programme (<https://industry.eea.europa.eu/#/home>) VANDALF: National Danish project aiming to develop and implement a risk assessment platform based on NTS and effect-based methods to identify CECs in wastewater, will be closely linked through the involvement of the coordinator UPCH. NORMAN network: Strong collaboration and exchange, use of and exchange with NORMAN database system.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D4.2 1st Proof-of-concept assessing the usefulness of innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches (will be postponed from M35 to M48)

Partners List: UFZ (DE), UBATH (UK), MUI (AT), UCPH (DK), EAWAG (CH), IRFM (IT), ORU-MTM (SE), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), JSI (SI), KWR (NL), UniLU (LU), VUA (NL), ISS (SP),

INERIS (FR), BfG (DE), UL-FFA (SI), BRGM (FR), WULS-SGGW (PL), JU (CZ), MU (CZ), INRAE (FR), OFB (FR), UL (PL), VITO (BE)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 111 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 178 275 €

P4.3.3.b_Y2_EO2-Sentinel animals_ONIRIS

Project Title	Proof-of-concept of innovative sampling and HRMS based / EDA screening methods for exploring chemicals of emerging concern in sentinel animal species		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Sentinel animals		
Project Manager	Ronan CARIOU ronan.cariou@oniris-nantes.fr	ONIRIS	FR
Deputy Project manager	Gaud DERVILLY gaud.dervilly@oniris-nantes.fr	ONIRIS	FR
Expected starting date	13	Expected duration	48
PARC (Month number)		PARC	4.3.3
PARC Workpackage number	P4	Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	
Project Id	P4.3.3.b_Y2_EO2-Sentinel animals_ONIRIS		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project:

Capturing the complex real chemical exposure of human and/or in the environment requires new conceptual frameworks and innovative methodological approaches. Suspect and non-targeted screening approaches (SS/NTS) based on high resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) coupled to effect directed analysis (EDA) are a promising trend developed within PARC T4.3 in that purpose. Within the One Health concept, animal sentinel species can serve as a source of useful information with respect to both human exposure to chemical hazards through the food chain and ecotoxicological considerations related to the environment. Species with bioaccumulation capacities especially appears of interest for SS/NTS screening of chemicals based on higher concentration levels than those observed in human biological matrices. Selected species will cover marine and terrestrial environments. Candidate species are marine mammals, molluscs, gulls, pigeons, raptors and bees. The sample sourcing of such sentinel species also stands as less laborious compared to human matrices, especially if already available in a specimen bank. The aim of this project is to develop and conduct a proof-of-concept permitting to assess then relevance of animal sentinel species upon applying those innovative methods, as complementary to conventional and targeted approaches. It will feed the early warning system on chemicals of emerging concern, the end-users being the food and environment policy makers.

Main expected outputs of the project:

- Documented advantages/limitations of innovative approaches compared to conventional ones
- Scientifically supported prioritisation of some animal species for short term implementation
- Paved way for further developments/improvements needed for long term implementation
- Documentation of real-life mixtures associated to environmental health and human food chain

- Prioritization of further targeted developments focused on particular exposure markers evidenced
- Contribution to feed early warning system through an established link between tasks 4.3 and 8.2
- General food law and environment policy makers aware of the main findings

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

The proposed project appears as a pre-required methodological development activity, expected to provide eventually a list of exposure markers pinpointing potential chemicals of emerging concern. This perspective should benefit a number of end-users including laboratories aiming to implement those new analytical approaches (capacity building), as well as actors aiming to build and use early warning systems for which the expected new exposure data generation capabilities will represent a significant input.

Policies related to the human food chain are a first target. It includes the general food law (Reg 178/2002), as well as the recently revised official control regulation (Reg 2017/625) and other regulations for business operators (Reg183/2005 Reg 852/2004, Reg 853/2004). For example, EFSA recently noted in its opinion on PFASs (doi: 10.2903/j.efsa.2020.6223) that a representative set of occurrence data are still lacking for many foods and, therefore, recommended to gather such data for a wide range PFASs in a broad range of widely consumed foods. Consequently, it is advised in the Commission Recommendation 2022/1431 that Member States should also consider testing for the presence in food of emerging PFASs, in addition to the 4+18 cited.

Policies related to the environmental aspects are another target. It includes the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (Dir 2008/56/EC) in which Qualitative descriptors for determining good environmental status n°8 and n°9 deal with contaminants giving rise to pollution or concern for human consumption. Such approach is also about to be extended to terrestrial environments according to a current proposal for a Nature Restoration Law.

Key words:

Sentinel species, human food chain, environmental health, innovative methods, suspect screening, non-targeted screening, effect-directed analysis, real-life mixtures, emerging chemicals

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives OO3: Define common R&I strategies with transparent criteria and a prioritisation strategy, OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives, OO7: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA, OO8: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes and OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake.

Conventional sampling and targeted quantitative analytical methods are already available to support environmental, food and human monitoring, risk assessment, and risk management decisions. However, these approaches sometimes suffer from a lack of sensitivity to characterize lowest exposed populations, face some limitations for large-scale implementation, and only capture a limited number of *a priori* known and selected markers of exposure. Developing a proof-of-concept for illustrating the capacities of SS/NTS/EDA approaches in the particular case of sentinel animal species is directly connected to task 4.3 DoA, in particular with regard to fostering collaboration of environmental, food safety and HBM communities.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects) (between 2-8 lines):

WP4:

4.1: Check Human internal exposure to highlighted exposure markers

4.2/4.2.2/P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU: Mutualized resources

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01_Concept Paper_MU: Alignment of objectives / purposes of SS/NTS/EDA

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QA/QC Issues_WR: Ensure quality of the generated data

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03_Early Warning System_SLU: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04_Data Processing Workflow_EHESP: Support annotation of generated data

WP6: Potential use of some of the generated new exposure data from SS/NTS/EDA for mixture modelling

WP7: Definition of specific requirements for SS/NTS/EDA data management (retrospective use, repository...)

WP8: Potential use of some of the generated new exposure data from SS/NTS/EDA for early warning system

Links outside PARC:

Tight connexions with the Norman network and Life Apex consortium for taking advantage of existing tools developed for monitoring the environment and top food chain biota, respectively. It includes sample handling, QA/QC procedures and highly visible data repositories. There will be discussion with biodiversa + on possible collaboration.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

D4.14. Final report on the application of new exposure assessment approaches (i.e. from sampling to data interpretation) to support regulatory needs (i.e. lessons learnt and conclusions/perspective for sustainable follow-up) (M81).

Partners list: ONIRIS (FR), ANSES (FR), AU (DK), BfR (DE), EAWAG (CH), CSIC (SP), INRAE (FR), JSI (SI), JU (CZ), OFB (FR), ORU-MTM (SE), SU (SE), UFZ (DE), UG-AT (AT), VUA (NL).

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2023 (M13)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2027 (M60)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project (third year of PARC): 38 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project (third year of PARC): 74 906 €

A4.3.4 Food samples based proof-of-concepts – 1 PROJECT

P4.3.4.a_Y2_F02- Food items exposure _ANSES

Project Title	Complementary developments regarding the application of HRMS based/EDA screening methods on food samples		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	F02-Food items exposure		
Project Manager	Julien Parinet julien.parinet@anses.fr	ANSES	France
Deputy Project manager	Sophie Mompelat sophie.mompelat@anses.fr	ANSES	France
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	13	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.4
Project Id	P4.3.4.a_Y2_F02- Food items exposure _ANSES		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project:

Suspect and non-targeted screening approaches (SS/NTS) based on high resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS), and Effect-Directed Analysis (EDA) combined with HRMS, represent a revolution in the field of monitoring chemicals present or potentially present in food, allowing to cover a much larger chemical range than the approaches used until now (low resolution) in the regulatory field. However, the application of these innovative approaches in food is still limited. In addition, the performances of SS/NTS/EDA approaches need to be better assessed in order to be adapted to a regulatory context and harmonisation. This project aims to develop and to qualitatively and quantitatively compare various analytical strategies and

workflows (from food sample preparation to data acquisition and data processing) in order to identify their complementarities or overlap in terms of captured exposure markers (known, emerging and unknown chemicals) in food. A preliminary step will consist in the selection of specific food items related to particular risk situations for both general and particularly vulnerable populations (*e.g.* infant food), as highlighted by EFSA as a major issue for risk assessment. The aim of this project is to develop and conduct a proof-of-concept permitting to assess the relevance of the implementation of such developed screening methods as part of the monitoring and control plans. This would allow to identify original contaminant mixtures from field data. The longitudinal follow-up of the data generated by these means would also allow highlighting both emergences (unregulated substances) and misuses (regulated substances). It will feed and help to structure the early warning system on chemicals of emerging concern, the end-users being the food policy makers.

Main expected outputs of the project:

- Characterization of advantages/limitations of innovative approaches compared to conventional ones through the evaluation of the chemical coverage potential of different SS/NTS/EDA methods
- Qualitative and quantitative assessment of the performances of the developed SS/NTS/EDA methods in order to implement one or more methods that will cover the largest possible chemical range and thus limit the failure to detect hazardous substances potentially present in a sample
- Definition of the needs for further developments/improvements for long-term implementation
- Generation of FAIR data to support the monitoring of real-life mixtures, and especially to support the exposure assessment of vulnerable population groups (*e.g.* children)
- Contribution to feed early warning system through an established link between tasks 4.3 and 8.2
- Awareness of general food law policy makers regarding key findings of the project and the data generated

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

By providing a clearer picture of the complementarity and performances of the methods compared in this project, the project should open the door to the integration of new innovative methods and tools needed for a more exhaustive monitoring for end-users, including the laboratories in charge of implementing control methods. Actors from the early warning systems will also benefit from the innovative methods capabilities to generate external exposure data. The production of field data through the application of these new tools will allow risk assessors and risk managers to have a broader view of the real-life chemical mixtures to which consumers are exposed. This will provide scientific data for guiding further toxicological studies and hence support the paradigm shift in risk assessment of these chemical mixtures.

Policies related to the human food chain are a first target. It includes the general food law (Reg 178/2002), and official control regulation (Reg 2017/625) as well as specific food laws such as Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006, Regulation (EC) No 396/2005, Regulation (EC) No 1935/2004.

Key words:

Monitoring, food, innovative methods, suspect screening, non-targeted screening, effect-directed analysis, real-life mixtures, emerging chemicals

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives OO1: Set-up and operate a high-level group to strategically steer PARC, OO2: Expand long-term sustainable network of National Hubs (NH), OO3: Define common R&I strategies with transparent criteria and a prioritisation strategy, OO4: Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge, OO6: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen's understanding/awareness of chemical RA, OO8: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes, OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA, OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres and OO13: Build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical RA.

Food monitoring is supported by the use of targeted analytical methods focusing on a selection of a relatively limited number of chemicals, compared to the number and diversity of chemicals constantly appearing on the market. The development of new and innovative analytical approaches is needed to support and renew the monitoring of the actual complex chemical mixtures in food to which consumers are exposed. The improvement and provision of new methods and tools is therefore a prerequisite to meet the need, formulated by European agencies (including EFSA) and in the EC Roadmap for the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability, for a paradigm shift in exposure/risk assessment and the establishment of an early warning system. This project aims to contribute to the fulfilment of these needs as expressed in the PARC's objectives and DoA.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

WP4:

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01_Concept Paper_MU: Alignment of objectives / purposes of SS/NTS/EDA

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QA/QC Issues_WR: Ensure quality of the generated data

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03_Early Warning System_SLU: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04_Data Processing Workflow_EHESP: Support annotation of generated data

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.2.b_Y2_E02_Sentinel animals_ONIRIS: Mutualized resources / harmonization

WP6: Potential use of some of the generated new exposure data from SS/NTS/EDA for mixture modelling

WP7: Definition of specific requirements for SS/NTS/EDA data management (retrospective use, repository...)

WP8: Potential use of some of the generated new exposure data from SS/NTS/EDA for early warning system

WP9: Contribution to harmonised QA/QC and training for SS/NTS/EDA approaches

Links outside PARC:

In order to carry out the project, it would be preferable to capitalize on the projects already initiated by the partners in the margin of PARC. As such, there will be links between this task and French TDS3, ANR AlimOmic, PhD Emergexpo, PhDs and other projects conducted by the contributing partners.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

D4.10. 3rd Proof-of-concept assessing the usefulness of innovative (self-) sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches (M60)

Partners list: ANSES (FR), INRAE (FR), VUA (NL), BfG (DE), CEA (FR), CNRS (FR), EAWAG (CH), CSIC (SP), ISS (IT), JSI (SI), MUI (AT), Oniris (FR), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), UL-FFA (SL), VSCHT (CZ), WR (NL), WULS (PL), EV-ILVO (BEL), GCSL (GR).

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2023 (M13)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project (third year of PARC): 41 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project (third year of PARC): 260 231 €

WP5 Hazard Assessment - 13 PROJECTS

The overall goal of WP5 is to overcome the major challenges in hazard assessment for human and environmental health. The specific objectives are:

- a) to close data gaps identified by key stakeholders;
- b) to improve the current hazard characterisation paradigm by establishing comprehensive testing strategies, thereby promoting the availability and applicability of new approach methodologies (NAMs) in risk assessment;
- c) to contribute to the improvement of mechanistic understanding of toxicity by analysing all available data and applying systems toxicology approaches and taking into account AOPs and to improve modelling approaches such as PBPK modelling. The work envisaged is divided into three tasks: T5.1, T5.2 and T5.3

Fig 8: WP5 contribution: Hazard assessment

T5.1 Toxicity testing addressing data gaps of concern 5 PROJECTS

This task aims to investigate and close existing data gaps through toxicity testing. The following groups of substances have been selected for the first round of testing: natural toxins, in particular the mycotoxins enniatins and those derived from *Alternaria* -their presence in food products is of concern-, as well as alternatives to BPA. Activities on toxins will address existing data gaps left open by regulatory data requirements, such as toxicokinetics data or comprehensive studies like the Extended One-Generation Reproductive Toxicity study (OECD 2018a). The latter study is also envisaged for other groups of substances of concern, which may include synthetic contaminants such as BPA alternatives/analouges not assessed by industry for authorisation or PFAS (per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances).

A5.1.1 Closing data gaps of concern for human health – 3 PROJECTS

P5.1.1.a_Y1_Toxins_BfR_UNIVIE

Project Title	Hazard identification and hazard characterisation of the mycotoxins enniatins and <i>Alternaria</i> toxins in order to close data gaps and improve risk assessment for human health		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Toxins		
Project Manager	Doris Marko doris.marko@univie.ac.at	UNIVIE	Austria

Project manager	Jessica Dietrich jessica.dietrich@bfr.bund.de	BfR	Germany
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	48*
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.1.1
Project Id	P5.1.1.a_Y1_Toxins_BfR_UNIVIE		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M48

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Natural toxins have no manufacturer or supplier that is responsible for providing hazard data. Due to climate changes, the human exposure to natural toxins will likely increase and regulatory agencies have asked for more hazard data to improve the risk assessment. This will ultimately result in recommendations on which natural toxins should be closely monitored in food feed and food products (Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006) in order to prevent adverse human health effects and setting maximum levels in food and feed based on knowledge.

For example, EFSA's CONTAM Panel stated that there might be a health concern regarding chronic exposure to the natural toxin enniatins however there is insufficient data to assess the risk on chronic exposure¹. Also, in the case of another natural toxins *Alternaria*, the scientific Panel was not able to conduct a systematic risk assessment due to the lack of data. Additionally, for both enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins major data gaps were identified in toxicity data in a recent report from the Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and the Environment (VKM et al., 2019)².

All the above-mentioned underlines that further research, in terms of hazard identification and characterization, is required for both toxins: enniatins and *Alternaria*. This project initially focuses on these two emerging mycotoxins, with pressing regulatory need for more specific hazard data: i.e., enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins. Preferably, the studies will be performed according to OECD test guidelines, but in some cases no guidelines are available to address the specific endpoints and NAMs will be employed.

Main expected outputs of the project

The study will provide urgently needed *in vitro* data and identify critical toxicological effects of enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins. The data is necessary for subsequent *in vivo* studies which are required to establish health-based guidance values and to perform an appropriate risk assessment and provide an efficient consumer protection.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project will generate toxicological data (mainly focusing on hazard identification and characterization), aiming at incorporating it in risk assessment performed in EU Agencies to set health-based guidance values that could therefore trigger the establishment of maximal levels in food in the context of Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006.

Key words: Natural toxins, *Alternaria* toxins, enniatins, mycotoxins, genotoxicity, endocrine effects, immunotoxicology, *in vitro*, *in silico*

¹ EFSA CONTAM, *Scientific Opinion on the risks to human and animal health related to the presence of beauvericin and enniatins in food and feed*, EFSA Journal, 2014, 12(8): 3802

² VKM, Inger-Lise Steffensen, Christiane Kruse Fæste, Trine Husøy, Helle Katrine Knutsen, Gro Haarklou Mathisen, Robin Ørnstrud, Angelika Agdestein, Johanna Bodin, Edel Elvevoll, Dag O. Hessen, Merete Hofshagen, Åshild Krogdahl, Asbjørn Magne Nilsen, Trond Rafoss, Taran Skjerdal, Gaute Velle, Yngvild Wasteson, Gro-Ingunn Hemre, Vigdis Vandvik, Jan Alexander (2019). Ranking of substances for monitoring in foods, drinks and dietary supplements

- based on risk and knowledge gaps. Scientific Opinion of the Scientific Steering Committee of the Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and Environment. VKM report 2019:13, ISBN: 978-82-8259-329-8, ISSN: 2535-4019. Available at <https://vkm.no/>

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives OO3: Define common R&I strategies with transparent criteria and a prioritisation strategy, OO4: Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge, OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives, OO6: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen's understanding/awareness of chemical RA, OO7: Develop/implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA, OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA and OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres.

The project was designed in order to fill data gaps regarding the main representatives of emerging mycotoxins groups of enniatins and Alternaria toxins as defined by EFSA. The results are needed to identify critical toxicological effects for subsequent in vivo studies which are needed to establish health-based guidance values and to perform an appropriate risk assessment and provide an efficient consumer protection. A working group was formed in which specialists on Alternaria and enniatins were combined with specialists in genotoxic, endocrine effects and immunotoxicological endpoints in order to design and deliver a program of studies. Review papers are in progress to summarise the existing data. Frequent meetings were held in order to share as much relevant information as possible. The long-term objective is to establish a European network of scientists interested and having experience in studying natural toxins.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- WP4: Human exposure to the mycotoxins will be monitored in WP4. Analytical support in measuring the test items in test media is needed in order to support PBPK and IVIVE modelling.
- WP5: T5.2 and T5.3: The test items will also be studied in selected NAMs in T5.2 (Cf. project on immunotoxicology P5.2.1.d). Data that will be generated on kinetics and toxicity will be used in task 5.3 in order to improve and expand existing models (AOP and PBK).
- WP6: Hazard data generated will be used in WP6 to build IATAs. Since most mycotoxins will be present in food and feed as mixtures, selected mixtures will also be tested. Relative Potency Factors could therefore be derived where possible and will provide important support for the assessments of risks of mixtures.
- WP7: T7.3: data and text mining, data provision Data management plan

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU
- EFSA- link to the Scientific Committee and Emerging Risks Unit European Food Safety Authority, Parma, Italy, through prof. George Kass. Also, Hans Steinkeller from feed and contaminants unit was interested in especially the results from the enniatins toxicology program.
- OECD project Using Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOP) to address combined exposures to chemicals with relevant effect-biomarkers. 2022-2025

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D5.1: 1st NAMs Report (M18)
 D5.3: 1st new AOPs Report (M24)
 D5.4: 1st Closing data Gaps Report (M36)
 D5.11. 2nd closing data gaps report (M54)

Partners List:

BfR (Germany), UNIVIE (Austria), BPI (Greece), IBMT (Germany), IMR (Norway), INRS (France), ANSES (France), INSA (Portugal), NIB (Slovenia), NIPH (Norway), Sciensano (Belgium), STAMI (Norway), UNAV (Spain), NVI (Norway), WU-TOX (Netherlands), ISS (Italy), NVI (Norway)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)
 Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 157 PM
 Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 243 135 €

P5.1.1.b_Y1_BPA_HumTox_BfR

Project Title	Hazard assessment of bisphenol A alternatives to close data gaps of concern for human health and improve their risk assessment		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	BPA_HumTox		
Project Manager	Kiara Aiello Kiara.Aiello-Holden@BfR.Bund.de	BfR	Germany
Deputy Project manager	1. Endocrine Disruptors: Sabrina Tait and Catherine Viguié 2. Developmental Neurotoxicity Sakina Mhaouty-Kodja 3. Immunotoxicity: Emanuela Corsini 4. Carcinogenicity: Maria Jaoa Silva 5. Metabolism: Daniel Zalko and Emanuela Testai	1. ISS INRAE 2. CNRS 3. UMIL 4. INSA 5. INRAE ISS	Italy France France Italy Portugal France Italy
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	54*
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.1.1
Project Id	P5.1.1.b_Y1_HumanTox_BfR		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M54

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Due to the restrictions on the use of bisphenol A (BPA) in consumer products, which is the most widely used and studied bisphenol, a number of BPA substitutes have emerged. For most BPA alternatives, information on potential effects on relevant endpoints for human health is either missing or too limited for a sound hazard assessment/characterization. BPA alternatives are already being found in humans and the environment and have raised concerns in a regulatory context. With the upcoming restrictions on BPA, BPA’s alternatives’ tonnages and frequencies of use are expected to severely increase in the coming years. Therefore, this project aims to fill the identified data gaps, and providing a complete data set for at least four relevant BPA alternatives. The selected alternatives were identified in an ad hoc Workshop together with ECHA and EFSA, following a tiered approach (Details on the prioritization basis can be found at AD5.1, [Deliverables page | Parc \(eu-parc.eu\)](#)). We will fill the knowledge gaps on human health on the following five toxicological endpoints:

1. Endocrine Disruptors;
2. Developmental Neurotoxicity;
3. Immunotoxicity;
4. Non-genotoxic Carcinogenicity;

5. Metabolism (biotransformation, potential bioactivation pathways, toxicokinetics).

This project will also contribute to the identification of molecular biomarkers to develop a method to rapidly predict the possible effects of BPA alternatives. The identification of molecular biomarkers enables the determination of the mechanism(s) through which BPA alternatives act; identifying the key steps of their modes of action will be a key driver in the synergy between Work Package 5 and 6 regarding the improvement/production of Adverse Outcome Pathways.

Main expected outputs of the project

Fill the identified data gaps on human health and provide a complete data set for at least four relevant BPA alternatives on the five toxicological endpoints stated previously.

The data obtained will provide modelers with input for PBPK and QIVIVE models and/or AOP development as well as a trigger for further higher-tier investigations.

Furthermore, the results to be obtained in this project will provide risk assessors with screening-level information that feeds mainly into the hazard assessment component of risk assessment. Our project's data will help to decide if specific BPA alternatives are potential regrettable substitution if e.g., their ED potential is higher than that of BPA. In that sense, the data will be supporting information for regulatory processes. This will contribute significantly to the enhanced protection of public health and requirements for safe food, consumer products and drinking water.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The Project will provide *in vitro* data on a set of toxicological endpoints for BPA alternatives that have not been assessed by the industry, to support assessors in conducting an adequate risk assessment and implementing CLP classifications.

With this project we will address the concern of the general population regarding this kind of substances, contributing to the production of safe products, such as plastic bottles, food cans and cash receipts, therefore minimizing the risk of adverse effects for end users.

Key words:

BPA analogues, risk assessment, endocrine disruptors, developmental neurotoxicity, immunotoxicity, metabolism, kinetics, *in vitro* methods, cognitive impairment, carcinogenicity

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives OO3: Define common R&I strategies with transparent criteria and a prioritisation strategy, OO4: Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge, OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives, OO6: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen's understanding/awareness of chemical RA, OO7: Develop/implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA, OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA and OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres.

A significant contribution to the PARC project will be made, providing useful data regarding BPA alternatives for both general awareness as well as for the needs of regulatory bodies. The data will provide also input for modellers working in PARC to build an experimental strategy relying only on NAMs.

A working group was formed in which specialists on BPA alternatives were combined with specialists in genotoxic and non-genotoxic carcinogenesis, endocrine disruption, developmental neurotoxicology, and immunotoxicological endpoints in order to deliver a program of studies. Frequent meetings were held in order to share as much relevant information as possible. A Workshop between WP/T leaders, project partners, EFSA and ECHA was organized to build a list of priority BPA alternatives for study (AD5.1), considering the regulatory gaps and needs.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- WP4: Elucidation of the structure of yet unknown metabolites of BPA alternatives that may be used as potential biomarkers of exposure and related effect biomarkers
- WP5; Task 5.1, Task 5.2 and Task 5.3:

- Task 5.2 Human Tox: we are working together with P5.2.1.e to fill up BPA alt data gaps using the established DNT IVB.
 Other WP5 project working with BPA alternatives in Task 5.1 and 5.2 Environment is P5.1.2.b joint project with A5.2.2.
- We will share with projects in WP5 working with BPA Alt. the information regarding the production of major BPA alternatives metabolites for toxicological screening, notably as regards their potential to activate Nuclear Receptors (NR); Characterization of bioactivation pathways mechanistically involved in the onset of endpoints such as immune-toxicity and genotoxicity.
- Mechanistic data generated will be used in the development of AOPs (e.g., DNT endpoint in A5.2.3.2)
- We are also working closely with PBPK modelers in A5.3.4 to share the data produced (Km, Vmax, hepatic clearance)
- WP6: Hazard data is expected to feed into IATA building. Potency factors will be derived for the assessment of mixture effects.
- WP7: Task 7.3: data and text mining, data provision Data management plan

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU
- EURION as regards the endpoint 5. Metabolism, on the metabolic fate of BPA analogues, the proposed project relies on the use of the human HepaRG cell line, a relevant human hepatic model displaying a broad panel of XMEs, also currently used in H2020 EURION by INRAE in the context of the GOLIATH project (Augmentation of the applicability domain of the CYP induction test method: OECD draft TG, TM2009-14, for EDCs/MDCs). Such studies will enhance the possibility to interpret results obtained in PARC in the most accurate manner, while no overlap in activities is foreseen.
- National Italian project: PRIN2017 ‘Endocrine disruptors: investigation of the effects on the immune and nervous systems (EDoNIS)’ Ref N. 2017MLC3NF
- Interaction and use of data in the forthcoming “Cluster 1 – Health “Topics WP 2023-2024 (2. Developmental neurotoxicity and 2.03 on Endocrine Disruptors)
- RIVM, Health Canada: Activities are coordinated with BPA alternatives projects initiated at RIVM and meetings to build synergies started recently with Health Canada (July 2023)

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

- AD5.1: List of Prioritized BPA alternatives for WP5 Hazard Assessment activities. Workshop report (M9)
- D5.1: 1st NAMs Report (M18)
- D5.3: 1st new AOPs Report (M24)
- D5.4: 1st Closing data Gaps Report (M36)
- D5.11: 2nd closing data gaps report (M54)

Partners List:

BfR (Germany), INRAE (France), IBMT Fraunhofer (Germany), ISS (Italy), INRS (France), UMIL (Italy), ULFFA (Slovenia), ISCIII (Spain), CNRS (France), TTL (Finland), MUI (Austria), LIH (Luxembourg), INSA (Portugal), NILU (Norway)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)
 Expected ending date: 31/10/2026 (M54)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 110 PM
 Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 145 718 €

P5.1.1.c_Y3_TG+ EnnB1_ANSES

Project Title	TG+ Enniatin B1		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	TG+ EnnB1		
Project Manager	Thalia de Castelbajac thalia.decastelbajac@anses.fr	Anses	France
Deputy Project manager	Gilles Rivière Gilles.RIVIERE@anses.fr	Anses	France
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M25	Expected duration (months)	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.1.1
Project Id	P5.1.1.c_Y3_TG+ EnnB1_ANSES		

Status: Initiation

Summary of the project

Enniatins are mycotoxins produced by *Fusarium* species, and are common contaminants of food and feed, mainly cereal grains and cereal by-products.

In 2014, in its “Scientific Opinion on the risks to human and animal health related to the presence of beauvericin and enniatins in food and feed,” EFSA stated that “Given the lack of relevant toxicity data, a risk assessment was not possible,” and that “To perform a human risk assessment, in vivo toxicity data on beauvericin and enniatins are needed. A study investigating possible health effects likely to arise from repeated exposure (i.e. 90-day study), (...), is required.” (EFSA, 2014). Among the “emerging” mycotoxins, enniatin B1 is one of the most prevalent compounds found in food.

To fill this data gap identified by EFSA, we are planning to conduct a TG+ study as a proof of concept, which consists in performing an OECD test guideline-conform animal study (TG 408: “Repeated Dose 90-Day Oral Toxicity Study in Rodents,” in feed, in rats), and in addition to the endpoints required by the test guideline, additional parameters will be investigated, such as toxicogenomics, without the necessity to include additional animals. TG+ studies, or ‘omics-enhanced in vivo studies’ have been described by ECHA as “necessary for further development of NAM methodology for hazard/risk assessment” (ECHA, 2023).

In parallel with the TG+ study, as a proof of concept, an omics-enhanced 5-day study will also be conducted (5-day, repeat oral dosing, transcriptomics rodent assay).

Additionally, in both studies, as many materials as possible will be collected that can be used for NAMs development and improvement in order to compare the results from NAMs-based assays and current methods, and ultimately help facilitate the regulatory acceptance of NAMs.

Main expected outputs of the project:

- In vivo data gaps to be filled on enniatins B1
- Development of NAMs and demonstration of robustness of alternative methods (TG+ study, NAMs, 5-day + omics study...).

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

An in vivo data gap concerning enniatin B1 has been identified by EFSA to make a risk assessment decision. This project would fill this data gap, while increasing confidence in the TG+ concept, that has been mentioned by ECHA as “necessary for further development of NAM methodology for hazard/risk assessment” (ECHA, 2023). Additionally, as many materials as possible will be collected from this TG+ study so that WP5 partners can develop/optimize NAMs.

A number of in vitro and NAM-based tests are currently being performed to study the hazards of enniatin B1 project 5.1.1a and 5.2.1.d. The results of those tests will be compared to the results of the TG study to demonstrate the robustness of such methods.

This project will also build confidence in the 5d + omics approach, which is increasingly being used by the US EPA.

Key words: NAMs, data gaps, human health, hazard assessment, toxicological endpoints, in vivo, 90-d

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

The project responds to the following PARC operational objectives:

OO4: Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge – this project will fill up a data gap identified by EFSA (Efsa, 2014). There is an ongoing dialogue with EFSA regarding this knowledge gap.

OO6: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen’s understanding/awareness of chemical RA – scientific publications

OO7: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA- development of assessment methodologies for new mechanistic data streams and application of omics data for RA will contribute to innovation in complex data analysis for RA.

OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA – production, storage and use of data following FAIR principles

OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake – NAMs will be developed/optimized as part of this project, and confidence in NAMs and innovative concepts such as the 5d and TG+ studies will be increased.

OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC’s results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA. - including innovative methods alongside a traditional TG study to fill up a data gap identified by a European agency will facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC’s results in regulatory RA processes.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP5 T5.1, 5.2, 5.3 - work on enniatin B1 is already being performed in those tasks and will complement the work done in this project

WP6 - NAMs, AOPs

Links outside PARC:

EFSA – data gap was identified by EFSA (EFSA, 2014)

ECHA – TG+ study concept promoted by ECHA

US EPA – 5d study + omics is a concept that has been developed and is being increasingly used by US EPA

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

D5.4: 1st Closing data gaps report (M36)

D5.5: 2nd New approach methodologies report (new delivery date M48)

D5.8: 3rd New approach methodologies report (M60)

D5.11: 2nd Closing data gaps report (M54)

Partners List: ANSES (France), ANSES Fougères (France), BfR (Germany), NIPH (Norway), INSA (Portugal), NGere-INSERM (France), TUB (Germany)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2024 (M25)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2027 (M60)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project (third year of PARC): 4.5 PM (to be completed)

Expected ODC for the first year of the project (third year of PARC): 37 200 € (to be completed)

A5.1.2 Toxicity assessment addressing data gaps of concern (Environment) – 2 PROJECTS

P5.1.2.a_Y1_NaturalToxinsAqua_UGent

Project Title	Toxicity assessment of naturally occurring toxins on aquatic organisms		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	AquaToxins		
Project Manager	Jana Asselman Jana.asselman@ugent.be	Ghent University	Belgium
Deputy Project manager	Stefan Örn stefan.orn@slu.se	SLU	Sweden
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.1.2
Project Id	P5.1.2.a_Y1_NaturalToxinsAqua_UGent		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Natural toxins are under EU regulations for human health and certain threshold values are set for safe human consumption. However, from an environmental health perspective, there are no ‘predictive no effect concentrations’ (PNECs) available indicating safe exposure levels for aquatic species. By studying the effects of natural toxins on aquatic organisms, like invertebrates and microalgae, the need for regulations and mitigation measures can be properly evaluated depending on the risks. This is because within aquatic ecosystems, invertebrates take up a crucial position in the food chain and the overall ecosystem as primary consumers and food sources for higher trophic levels. Microalgae are the food source for these invertebrates, being a lower level of the trophic chain. Therefore, this project investigates the toxicity of naturally occurring toxins on aquatic organisms, specifically invertebrates and microalgae.

From a regulatory perspective, results from this project can also be integrated into the EU guidelines to achieve good environmental status for marine and freshwater environments (marine framework directive and water framework directive). The results also serve as a basis for the further regulation of nitrogen and phosphorus pollution within the EU, as these contribute to eutrophication and are seen as a key driver in ‘harmful algae bloom’ (HAB) formation.

Further details can be found here:

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2013.12.001>

<https://doi.org/10.1002/mnfr.200600185>

<https://doi.org/10.3390/md11103689>

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10646-016-1633-y>

Main expected outputs of the project

The project will contribute significantly to the effect assessment of natural toxins in aquatic ecosystems using standard OECD testing procedures that can be directly linked to risk assessment approaches. Particularly, the project will also provide comprehensive information on the ecotoxicity of natural toxins in mixtures using standard OECD tests and therefore contribute to a more realistic risk assessment of natural toxins and their impact on achieving good environmental status (*i.e.* water framework directive and marine framework directive).

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Although toxicological knowledge in invertebrate species may remain overlooked, they account for 95% of all species, and they are highly sensitive targets of hazardous chemicals. The common presence of natural toxins in aquatic environments is a factor overlooked in risk assessment of other regulated chemicals. There is a lack of knowledge regarding how toxins behave in mixtures with other chemical substances. The project will fill this data gap and the results can, together with public available data from the literature, serve as a

basis to derive PNECs for aquatic species. The project will generate direct insights on the life history effects of natural toxins in single and mixture exposures in several keystone aquatic species across freshwater and marine habitats. As such, the project will be helpful to other scientists and regulators studying the impact of natural toxins, including interactions with other chemicals, in the aquatic environment.

Key words: natural toxins, aquatic ecosystems, invertebrates, algae, ecotoxicology

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives OO3: Define common R&I strategies with transparent criteria and a prioritisation strategy, OO4: Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge, OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives, OO6: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen's understanding/awareness of chemical RA, OO7: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA, OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA, OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC's results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA. and OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres.

The project will contribute to research knowledge for uptake of natural toxins, both in single as in mixture form, into regulatory assessment. The project results will provide a clear insight on the need to include natural toxins as key priority or emerging challenge. From a regulatory perspective, aquatic natural toxins are not currently assessed per se, although environmental status descriptors are significantly impacted by the presence of natural toxins. By assessing the ecotoxicity of single and mixtures –natural toxins can significantly impact the toxicity of regulated chemicals- of toxins using standard OECD testing procedures, this project will provide data that can be integrated in EU guidelines relating to the Marine and Water Framework Directives. The project results will provide a clear insight on the need to include natural toxins as key priority or emerging challenge. The data generated as part of this project will be useful to other projects within Workpackage 5, and cooperation is likely to take place with Workpackages 4 and 6. Six reports are planned in order to disseminate the findings of this project.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

- WP4: Task 4.2 Environmental and multisource monitoring. WP4 can provide potential exposure assessments supplementing the effect assessment done here.
- WP5: The data from our project may serve as input for Task 5.3, and also as potential alternative vertebrate testing methods relevant to T5.2
- WP6: Task 6.1, 6.2, 6.4 and others: Data input for regulatory/risk assessment
- WP7: Task 7.3: data and text mining, data provision Data management plan

Links outside PARC

At this point, there are no ongoing interactions with national or international activities, which are also not taking place (as far as the partners are aware). However, the partners can build on extensive available published data which will be leveraged to ensure no duplicate work is done.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D5.4: 1st Closing data Gaps Report (M36)

Partners List:

Ghent University, UGent (Belgium), Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, SLU (Sweden), University of Aveiro, UAVR (Portugal)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 18 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 32 156 €

P5.1.2.b_Y1_BPAalternatives_BPI_MU

Project Title	BPA alternatives and associated mixtures (data gaps and NAM development)		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Bisphenols_ENV		
Project Manager	Ludek Blaha (ludek.blaha@recetox.muni.cz) Ondřej Adamovský (ondrej.adamovsky@recetox.muni.cz)	Masarykova univerzita (MU)	Czech Republic
Deputy Project manager	Katerina Kyriakopoulou (k.kyriakopoulou@bpi.gr)	Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI)	Greece
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48*
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.1.2 5.2.2
Project Id	P5.1.2.b_Y1_BPAalternatives_BPI_MU		

*The project has been delayed from M42 to M48

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The concerns regarding the potential adverse effects of bisphenol A (BPA) and tight restrictions of BPA in many countries has led to the development of alternative chemicals (*e.g.*, BPZ, BPE, BPS-MAE, BPP, BPAP, BPB, BPC, BPS, BPF, BPAF) resulting in emerging environmental contaminants found worldwide in various environmental components including water, sediment, sludge, soil, indoor dust and air. In addition, the use of BPA alternatives will be increased in the following years, since the use of BPA should be significantly reduced based on the upcoming EFSA scientific opinion in which EFSA has re-evaluated the risks from BPA in food and propose a lower tolerable daily intake (TDI) than the one previously set. Regarding their properties most bisphenols are characterized as toxic (or very toxic) to aquatic organisms, have been shown to exhibit adverse effects on the endocrine, reproduction, metabolism and immune system in different species and some of them are persistent, mobile or bioaccumulative and are characterized as PBT/vPvB or PMT/vPvM). In parallel, BPA alternatives are molecules regulated under REACH and their chemical safety assessment is carried out at different levels of comprehensiveness according to the specific data requirements based on the tonnage levels in which the substance is produced. These data are not always adequate to assess the potential adverse effects of BPA alternatives not only on human health but also on non-mammalian species, also considering the widespread use of many bisphenols and the possibility of exposure in the environment.

Finally, the current regulatory risk assessment focuses on single chemicals, widely disregarding potential adverse effects of mixtures of BPA alternatives on different organisms, especially after long-term exposure to environmentally realistic concentrations. Consequently, the assessment of combined effects of BPA alternatives and chemicals in general is recognized as one of the major needs in chemical risk assessment and this need has been highlighted in the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, in the European Green Deal and in PARC / HBM4EU prioritization survey.

Therefore, this project aims to fill the data gaps concerning the BPA alternatives (activities i and ii) and will serve as a platform for development of NAMs (activities iii-v).

Main expected outputs of the project

The specific aims and the relevant expected outputs of this project are the following:

- Investigation of the potential adverse effects (*e.g.*, apical endpoints such as mortality, effects related to the anticipated mode of action or MIE, effects on reproduction, effects on endocrine system) of certain

individual substances and “real-life” mixtures of BPA alternatives on non-mammalian organisms belonging to different taxa (*activity i and ii*)

- Development of *in silico* and modelling tools for hazard assessment of BPA alternatives to ultimately support grouping of substances and read-across approaches based on NAMs (*activity iii*).
- Development / advancing invertebrates’ models as NAMs for the hazard assessment of BPA alternatives and/or other prioritized chemicals (*activity iv*)
- Development / advancing alternative 3R-compatible vertebrate aquatic models for environmental hazard assessment of BPA alternatives and other prioritized chemicals (*activity v*)

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project will provide *in vivo* and *in vitro* toxicological data for BPA alternatives relevant for different endpoints (e.g. endocrine disruption, reproduction, etc) and several species, that have not been assessed by the industry since they are not included in the specific data requirements under REACH. The project will also bring new data regarding the toxicity of BPA alternatives, as this topic is largely unexplored. Moreover, the project will contribute to the development of NAMs. Therefore, the project aims to assist risk assessors, Member State Regulatory Authorities, EU agencies and other relevant stakeholders in conducting hazard/risk assessment.

Key words: data gaps, NAMs, BPA alternatives, *in silico*, *in vivo*, *in vitro*

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project will contribute to the investigation and closing of data gaps regarding the hazard assessment of priority chemicals - bisphenols (single compounds and chemicals) with focus on the environment (Activity 5.1.2). In addition, this project will contribute to the development of innovative methodologies (NAMs) that will directly contribute to hazard identification and risk assessment not only for BPA alternatives but also for other chemicals (Activity 5.2.2). The project will mainly contribute to the PARC operational objectives OO4, OO7 and OO9 by developing and implementing R&I work programs based on priorities set and generating results and knowledge to support the use of new approaches and methods, fill data gaps in BPA alternatives hazard assessment, and by development of tools and methods to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC results in regulatory RA processes.

The project will also contribute to the PARC operational objectives by providing input to priority-setting (OO3), promote cooperation with other relevant R&I initiatives (OO5), develop new networks of laboratories (OO11), contribute to communication and dissemination of the results (OO6) and implement FAIR data practices to enable open science (OO10).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP4: T4.2.1 and T4.2.2 - incorporation of environmental monitoring data into BPA selection process.

WP5: All tasks T5.1, 5.2, 5.3 - data derived in 5.1 and 5.2 will be valuable for AOP development / modeling in 5.3.

WP6: T6.1, 6.2 and others - discussion regarding building NAM confidence for regulatory purposes.

WP7: Data management – bilateral discussion regarding proper data storage and management.

WP3 and WP9: will be contacted for identification of synergies.

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU: Information on exposure and real-life mixtures will be taken from information provided by HBM4EU.
- POlySAFE: French national program on assessment of plastic alternatives for food containers (Coordinated by CNRS)
- Precision Tox: A link to Precision Tox will be established to benefit from the 5-species 250 substances toxicogenomic approach, to create synergies and to avoid duplication of work.
- PRORISK: The activity will be synergized by sharing predicted and experimentally derived environmental hazard data to a novel integrative risk assessment platform developed in PRORISK (<https://prorisk-itn.eu/>) that links chemical-biological interactions, through AOPs, effects on organisms

and populations up to predictions of risks for ecosystem services and the socio-economic costs of environmental damage.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

- AD5.1: List of Prioritized BPA alternatives for WP5 Hazard Assessment activities. Workshop report (M9)
- AD5.3: List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints (M12)
- D5.1: 1st NAMs Report (M18)
- D5.4: 1st Closing data Gaps Report (M36)
- D5.5.: 2nd New approach methodologies report (new delivery date M48)
- D5.11: 2nd closing data gaps report (M54)

Partners List:

BPI (Greece), SLU (Sweden), IISPV (Spain), SDU (Denmark), INERIS (France), NIB (Slovenia), IEP-NRI (Poland), UU (Sweden), UG-PL (Poland), UAVR (Portugal), EAWAG (Switzerland), NIVA (Norway), MU (Czechia), NIC (Slovenia), UFZ (Germany), BFG (Germany), UPO (Spain), UAntwerpen (Belgium), CNRS (France), MUI (Austria), SU (Sweden), INRAE (France), Cefas-Defra (UK).

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)
 Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 354 PM
 Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 403 592 €

T5.2 Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling - 5 PROJECTS

The focus of this task is on the improvement of the current hazard characterisation paradigm by establishing comprehensive testing strategies that logically combine novel methods with well-established approaches, preferably in a tiered manner. In brief, this task will evaluate the relevance and readiness of new technologies, e.g., genomic, transcriptomic, proteomic, high-content analysis microscopy, high resolution mass spectrometry, and human inducible pluripotent stem cell technology, for the assessment of (eco)toxicological endpoints such as non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, immunotoxicity, endocrine disruption and (developmental) neurotoxicity, thereby leveraging OECD’s and PARC’s AOP frameworks. Also, test methods, tools and methodologies will be developed to identify drivers of toxicity in mixtures and to support the grouping of chemicals, including the application of read-across. Furthermore, this task aims for the development and application of predictive *in vitro* and *in silico* tools to identify and characterise specific hazards. Through close collaboration with human biomonitoring communities in- and outside PARC, methods and computational approaches will be developed to study the metabolism of chemical substances in different biological (test) systems or matrices (e.g., cells, organoids, organs, blood) for comparison between species.

A5.2.1 Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling – 5 PROJECTS

P5.2.1.a_Y1_NGTXCs_INRAE

Project Title	Non-genotoxic carcinogens		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	NGTXCs		
Project Manager 1	Marc Audebert marc.audebert@inrae.fr	INRAE	France
Project Manager 2	Michael Oelgeschläger Michael.Oelgeschlaeger@bfr.bund.de	BfR	Germany
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	60

PARC (Month number)		PARC	5.2.1
PARC Workpackage number	5	Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	
Project Id	P5.2.1.a_Y1_NGTXC _s _INRAE		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project:

A range of organ and cellular model systems (including liver, breast, colon, adipocytes) will be investigated with innovative human-relevant NAMs, including state of the art transcriptomic approaches, high-content analysis, cell painting, epigenetics and high-throughput-compatible reporter systems addressing well established and relevant mechanisms of carcinogenesis, such as (oxidative) stress, epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT), inflammation, changes in metabolism, epigenetic marks or nuclear receptors signaling as well as proliferation. In addition, experimental approaches will be complemented by the optimization of *in silico* tools for the identification of NGTxCs to address the assay needs for the development of an NGTxCs IATA in cooperation with WP6.1 and ongoing activities at EU (e.g. RISK-HUNT3R) and OECD level. The project will improve our knowledge of the relationships between a range of different substances specific for distinct adverse outcome pathways that ultimately lead to cancer. In addition, methods with increasing complexity, from 2D cell culture up to 3D spheroids and zebrafish embryo's as a simple vertebrate model system are used in the project. Zebrafish will be used in order to have a whole organism included that also provides some metabolic activity. The use of NAMs with increasing levels of complexity will facilitate the integration of the physiological and toxicological relevant information with respect to adversity in order to inform about potential carcinogens and to improve chemical assessment and regulation. Here, the comparative analysis of the various assays in this project will also facilitate the characterisation of the applicability domain and limitation of each method. The project will align with AOPs and IATA work under Task 5.3 as well as T6.1 and takes into account the ongoing work of the OECD expert group on NGTxCs as well as current EU initiatives (e.g. RISK-HUNT3R). Further details of this project can be found here <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/ftox.2023.1220998/full>

Main expected outputs of the project

To develop internationally acceptable *in vitro* testing batteries (NAMs) and IATAs, the test methods (including *in silico* prediction tools) will be subject to testing of a sufficiently large set of reference compounds, including prioritized PARC compounds, to allow the evaluation of reliability and relevance taking into account sensitivity and specificity of the various systems as well as their complementarity detecting different MoAs involved on non-genotoxic carcinogenicity. The more complex systems will be further developed and optimized to allow a more physiological evaluation of activity for a subset of the reference compounds.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project will be particularly helpful from a risk assessor's as well as applicants from industry because the innovative, rapid, reliable and cost-efficient methods developed therein will allow an efficient and relevant mechanistic NGTxCs hazard analysis of a high number of substances and mixtures thus contributing to detection of hazardous substances well as product optimization following the zero pollution ambition of the green deal and the chemicals strategy for sustainability.

Key words: Carcinogenesis, 3D cell models, OMICs, MoA, risk assessment

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives OO3: Define common R&I strategies with transparent criteria and a prioritisation strategy, OO4: Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge, OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives, OO6: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen's understanding/awareness of chemical RA, OO7: Develop/implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA, OO10: Implement

FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA, OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake, OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC’s results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA and OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres.

The composition of the consortium ensures efficient communication with other PARC Work Packages, National Hubs, research initiatives (Horizon projects), and the OECD. The consortium has already connected various labs from different European countries and is in contact with additional laboratories. (SO1, OO4, and OO5; SO2, OO7; SO3, OO11).

Concerning SO2, OO10 This project will cooperate with WP 9 to ensure FAIR data practices.

The main aim is to develop new approaches and innovative concepts to detect and evaluate potential NGTxC /carcinogens considering current practices of standardization and aims at the validation of some methods in cooperation with external activities. (SO2, OO12; SO3, OO9).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- WP2 and WP3: The priorities regarding the various regulatory frameworks to be addressed will be confirmed in close collaboration with WP2 “A common science-policy agenda” and WP3 “Synergies, collaboration and awareness”.
- WP5 and WP6: We will closely collaborate with WP5 “Hazard assessment” and with WP6 “Innovation in regulatory risk assessment” on topics related to NGTXCs and IATA development. These topics include:
 - a) mapping of existing AOPs and associated NAMs for non-genotoxic carcinogenicity;
 - b) interaction with the other A5.2.1 subjects related to endocrine disruption and immunotoxicity endpoints;
 - c) development of (quantitative) AOP networks using, among others, data generated in WP5;
 - d) evaluation of NGTXCs IATA through case studies in WP6.
- WP7: The data generated in the project itself as well as the case studies also provide a link to WP7 “FAIR data”, in which analysis of the uncertainties associated with the IATA will be one of the use cases.
- WP9: this work relates to WP9 “Capacities”, since valuable learnings will be taken up in relevant training courses.

Links outside PARC

- H2020 Projects: This project is closely linked to ongoing H2020 projects, in particular the ASPIS and the EURION clusters,
- OECD activities, including the work of the OECD Advisory Group on Emerging Science in Chemicals Assessment (ESCA), the OECD Working Party for Hazard Assessment (WPHA) as well as and the OECD NGTXCs expert group.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.2: M12 (April 2023) - Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted. Associated Task: T5.1 Leader of the deliverable: ANSES, BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: BPI/NIPH/INSA. It was planned that the project managers would contribute to this deliverable, but in the end it was not necessary.

AD5.3: M12 (April 2023) - List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints. Associated Task T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: DTU, VUB. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

D5.1: M18 (October 2023) - 1st NAMs Report. Associated Task: T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

D5.3: M24 (April 2024) - 1st new AOPs Report. Associated Task: T5.3. Leader of the deliverable: INSERM. Associated Task co-leaders: UL-LACDR/SCIENSANO/Fraunhofer.

D5.5: M48 (April 2026) - 2nd New approach methodologies report. Associated Task: T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

D5.8: M60 (April 2027) - 3rd New approach methodologies report. Associated Task: T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

Partners List:

INRAE (FR); BfR (DE); ANSES (FR); INSERM (FR); NIB (SI); UL-LACDR (NL); UNAV (ES); IRFM (IT); RIVM (NL); RPTU (DE); NILU (NO); MU (CZ)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2027 (M60)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 202 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 390 319 €

P5.2.1.b_Y1_MD-EDC_BfR

Project Title	Metabolic Endocrine Disruption		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	MD-EDC		
Project Manager	Albert Braeuning Albert.braeuning@bfr.bund.de	BfR	Germany
Deputy Project manager	Daniel Zalko daniel.zalko@inrae.fr	INRAE In kind contribution	France
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48*
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.2.1
Project Id	P5.2.1.b_Y1_MD-EDC_BfR		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M48

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Over the past decade, progress in endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDC) research has demonstrated that one specific adverse effect of a number of EDC is their capability to induce a lasting disruption of endogenous metabolism. These substances, referred as "metabolism disrupting chemicals" (MDC) are largely suspected to contribute to the incidence of obesity and related metabolic disorders such as type II diabetes and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, in association with genetic factors, nutrition and lifestyle. Nowadays, more than 50 million people in Europe suffer from metabolic disorders with the role of environmental stressors (either man-made or natural chemicals) being increasingly recognized.

Despite MDC being suspected to play a major role in the worldwide epidemics of metabolic disorders, there are currently no specific regulatory *in vivo* or *in vitro* tests allowing to identify their adverse effects. The WHO/IPSC (2002) presents specific criteria that should be fulfilled for a substance to be considered as an EDC, but no criteria are established for MDC yet. The WHO/IPSC (2002) EDC criteria could be considered to apply to MDC too. From a regulatory perspective (e.g., with respect to the fields of pesticides or chemicals regulation), it is thus of paramount importance to validate methodologies allowing to identify and assess MDC-associated risks. Therefore, this project will focus on the development of new approach methodologies (NAM) facilitating regulators to identify and assess MDC-associated risks.

Further details of this project can be found here

<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/ftox.2023.1212509/full>

Main expected outputs of the project

A comprehensive exploration of Nuclear Receptor (NR)-driven effects will be carried out using stably transfected cell lines, expanding the on-going prevalidation of transient cell lines in EURION. An extended spectrum of substances will be assessed for priority families, including major metabolites and breakdown molecules, allowing further Modes of Action (MoA) exploration, as well as adverse outcome pathway (AOP) and read-across development. We will develop NAMs encompassing hepatic and non-hepatic *in vitro* systems including multi-tissue cross-talk, opening the road for a refined assessment of the obesogenic effects of MDC. This will involve a deep mechanistic exploration of key cellular pathways using human *in vitro* models, as well as parallel additional 3R-compliant models and novel methods, including imagery. New developments enabling the proposal of accurate NAMs based on human as well as non-human models will enable to close major data gaps in the field of metabolic disruption, in close connection with other PARC topics, tasks and WPs. The developed and (pre-)validated *in vitro* test systems will allow for the identification of endocrine metabolic disrupting chemicals (MDC) and thus direct impact on regulatory decisions related to endocrine activities of compounds. Moreover, the work carried out with specific compound classes (e.g., bisphenol derivatives) will impact on the risk assessment of these classes of compounds.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Currently, there exists no regulatory test guidelines, approaches or testing strategies for MDCs. The sheer need for tests development in the field of metabolic disorders has been highlighted in recent work commissioned by DG Environment. In this project section, new methods will be developed for identifying MDC, with outcomes expected to be of great use for risk assessors. Work will be focused on projects aiming at a comprehensive exploration of NR-driven effects using stably transfected cell lines, expanding the on-going pre-validation of transient cell lines. An extended spectrum of substances will be assessed for priority families, including major metabolites and breakdown molecules, allowing further MoA exploration, AOP and read-across development. We will develop NAMs encompassing hepatic and non-hepatic *in vitro* systems including multi-tissue cross-talk, to open the road for a refined assessment of the obesogenic effects of MDC. This will involve a deep mechanistic exploration of key cellular pathways using human *in vitro* models, but also additional 3R-compliant models and novel methods, including imagery. The goal is to produce new developments enabling the proposal of accurate NAMs based on human as well as non-human models, so to close major data gaps in the field of MDC, in close connection with other PARC topics, tasks and WPs.

Key words:

Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals, EDC, Metabolism Disrupting Chemicals, MDC, metabolic disruption, obesity, energy metabolism, fatty acid metabolism, metabolic disorders, metabolism, cellular signalling, NAM

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives, OO7: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA, OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA, OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake, OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC's results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA and OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres and OO13: Build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical RA.

The project is directly related to the PARC DoA, as it is directed towards the development of new approach methods to allow for animal-free testing of compounds. The tests to be developed to detect metabolic disruption will close a gap for which until now no specific test systems or guidelines are in place. Thereby the project will directly contribute to improved risk assessment and an elevated level of consumer protection in the EU.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- WP2, Task 2.1: complementarity with guideline tests
- WP5, P5.1.1.b: link with the assessment of the fate of model EDs/MDCs and availability of major metabolites for testing.
- Task 5.2.2: link with environmental package whenever EDs are involved (e.g. data from fish can be used to inform on potential risks for human health; this is done in collaboration with Task 5.3 and Task 6.1).
- The EDC/MDC section of Task 5.2, Activity 5.2.1 Human Health, will enhance synergies and avoid overlaps with ongoing projects such as EURION, by building on knowledge and experimental systems already established or in development, but with a focus on experimental systems not yet primarily addressed in these projects, as well as by extending the spectrum of MDC and focusing on priority-listed families of substances.
- Task 5.3: use of NAMs for AOP development and effect marker validation
- WP6, Task 6.1: use of NAMs for toxicity testing
- Task 6.3: several case studies concerning with EDs

Links outside PARC

- H2020 projects HBM4EU & EDCmixrisk: compound selection.
- H2020 project cluster EURION (esp. projects GOLIATH, OBERON and EDCmet): compound selection, complementary test systems (duplication of work is avoided by focusing on other target organs and tissues), synergies in AOP and IATA development.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.3: M12 (April 2023) - List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints. Associated Task T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: DTU, VUB. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

D5.1: M18 (October 2023) - 1st NAMs Report. Associated Task: T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

D5.4: M36 (April 2025) - 1st Closing data Gaps Report. Associated Task: T5.1. Leader of the deliverable: ANSES, BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: BPI/NIPH/INSA.

D5.5: M48 (April 2026) - 2nd New approach methodologies report. Associated Task: T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

Partners List:

BfR (DE); INSERM (FR); UU IRAS (NL); U Antwerpen (BE); UU (SE); UIBK (AT); UFZ (DE); IfADo (DE); INRAE (FR)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 99 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 101 155 €

P5.2.1.c_Y1_EDThDisruption_DTU

Project Title	T5.2a_Endocrine disruptors – Thyroid hormone system disruption		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	ED-Thyro		
Project Manager	Louise Ramhøj	DTU	Denmark
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Deputy Project manager	Tamara Vanhaecke	VUB	Denmark
	Tamara.Vanhaecke@vub.be		
	Terje Svingen	DTU	
	tesv@food.dtu.dk		

Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	48
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.2.1
Project Id	P5.2.1.c_Y1_EDThDisruption_DTU		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) has adopted the revised OECD Guidance Document 150 (OECD 2018) in its regulatory guidance for evaluating biocides and pesticides for ED activity. Despite these relatively recent advances, current test strategies and regulations are inadequate with regard to specifically identifying thyroid hormone system disruptors (THSDs). Some *in vitro* assays (non-OECD TGs) for certain Molecular Initiation Events (MIEs) relevant for THSD are available and are currently in the process of regulatory validation (<https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/science-update/vitro-methods-detection-thyroid-disruptors>). However, there is still a pressing need to develop more extensive test batteries of NAMs that cover a broader range of Key Events (KEs) i.e. from MIE to Adverse Outcomes (AO). The goal of this project is to help fill this gap by gaining more mechanistic knowledge on THSD for targeted NAM development. In addition, this project will also help to understand key species differences in THSD, as well as *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation by performing targeted *in vivo* rodent studies, *in silico* assays, human relevant stem cell-derived *in vitro* systems, and utilizing zebrafish as a unique non-mammalian whole organism model fit for THSD identification. The use of *in vivo* studies (e.g. rodents) is still required to elucidate the KEs responsible for THSD-mediated adverse outcomes in order to facilitate the development of NAMs predictive of human health effects, as this causal knowledge is still unknown. In particular, rodent studies are performed to delineate toxicogenomic effects across target organs in a complex developing organism, with this information envisioned to help target biomarkers of mechanisms of action that can be exploited for further NAMs development relying on e.g. human-derived cell-based assays. Further details of this project can be found here

<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/ftox.2023.1189303/full>

Main expected outputs of the project

Studies will be conducted that are aimed specifically at characterizing new mechanistic knowledge to enable the development of relevant NAMs. Especially the identification of upstream MIEs or KEs for downstream AOs relevant for THSD effect outcomes, Once identified, specific KEs can be targeted for NAMs development to increase the predictive power of non-animal test data for hazard identification and/or risk assessment purposes. The project thus focusses on points of vulnerability along the TH signalling pathway to chemical perturbation. For NAMs development, the project will examine direct versus indirect perturbation of the TH axis by exogenous agents; build a novel developmental stem cell-based assay with human relevance; characterize further the evolutionary conservation of the THS axis in order to make better use of non-human NAMS (e.g. fish, invertebrates) to inform on human health risks. New knowledge and NAMs will better enable development of a robust IATA specific for THSD.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project will deliver valuable contributions to chemical safety assessors and regulators by providing evidence-based mechanistic knowledge for THSD that will enable better use of non-vertebrate animal test data for decision making. This will contribute greatly to the detection of hazardous chemical substances with focus on EDs and THSDs, thus adhering to the zero-pollution ambition of the Green Deal, as well as the Chemicals Strategy set out by the European Commission. Other end-users such as the chemical and cosmetic industry will benefit from gathered knowledge and developed test methods and strategies, as they may themselves adopt new and improved alternative test methods for a more rapid, reliable and cost-efficient internal testing regimen.

The long-term benefit for stakeholders will be a sizeable reduction in animals used for safety testing of chemical and cosmetic substances. Stakeholders will also benefit by minimizing exposure to unwanted THSDs, possibly leading to improved public health.

Key words: Thyroid hormone system disruptors; T3; T4; endocrine; brain; liver; risk assessment

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives OO3: Define common R&I strategies with transparent criteria and a prioritisation strategy, OO4: Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge, OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives, OO6: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen's understanding/awareness of chemical RA, OO7: Develop/implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA, OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA, OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake, OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC's results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA and OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres.

The project supports innovation by providing novel mechanistic knowledge that will be exploited for developing novel NAMs for THSD testing. The project will close much needed regulatory test-method and scientific gaps related to the thyroid hormone system and as such contribute towards improved regulation and consumer protection for THSD compounds. Cooperation with other R&I initiatives is assured through collaboration with other PARC activities related to NAMs (activity 5.2.2), systems biology (task 5.3) and IATA development and risk assessment (tasks 6.1 and 6.3). FAIR data practice is ensured through WP9 cooperation. Communication of the project results to the research community will be done via publication in peer-reviewed journals and participation in congresses.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- WP2 Task 2.1: complementarity with guideline tests
- WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness
- WP5: A5.2.2: link with environmental package whenever EDs and THDs are involved (e.g. data from fish can be used to inform on potential risks for human health; this is done in collaboration with A5.2.2, 5.3 and 6.1).
- Task 5.3: use of NAMs for AOP development and effect marker validation
- WP6 Task 6.1: use of NAMs for toxicity testing. Task 6.3: several case studies of which some concerned with EDs and THSDs (e.g., case study 10)
- WP7: Data management plan
- WP9: Training, laboratory network

Links outside PARC

- H2020 projects – EURION cluster: ATHENA project, SCREENED project and ERGO project
- Green Deal projects: PANORAMIX project

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.2: M12 (April 2023) - Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted. Associated Task: T5.1 Leader of the deliverable: ANSES, BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: BPI/NIPH/INSA. It was planned that the project managers would contribute to this deliverable, but in the end it was not necessary.

AD5.3: M12 (April 2023) - List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints. Associated Task T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: DTU, VUB. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU

D5.1: M18 (October 2023) - 1st NAMs Report. Associated Task: T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

D5.3: M24 (April 2024) - 1st new AOPs Report. Associated Task: T5.3. Leader of the deliverable: INSERM. Associated Task co-leaders: UL-LACDR/SCIENSANO/Fraunhofer.

D5.5: M48 (April 2026) - 2nd New approach methodologies report. Associated Task: T5.2. Leader of the

deliverable: BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

Partners List:

DTU (Denmark); VUB (Belgium), BfR (Germany); SDU (Denmark); UAntwerpen (Belgium); VUA (Netherlands); ISCIII (Spain); INSERM (France)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 126 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 148 079 €

P5.2.1.d_Y1_Immunotox_Inserm

Project Title	Immunotoxicity		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Immunotox		
Project Manager	Etienne Blanc etienne.blanc@u-paris.fr	Inserm	France
Deputy Project manager	Saadia Kerdine saadia.kerdine-romer@u-psud.fr	Université Paris Sud	France
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48*
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.2.1
Project Id	P5.2.1.d_Y1_Immunotox_Inserm		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M48

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

During the first three years of PARC and in line with regulatory needs we will develop research aiming at characterizing new NAMs addressing three major endpoints in immunotoxicity: organ-related immunotoxicity with a focus on respiratory toxicity and sensitization; immunosuppression, in particular through response to vaccination; characterizing new models for cellular immunotoxicity assessing key events. The major outcome will be the development of NAMs in these immunotoxicity areas. For this, reference chemicals will be used and once the NAMs are developed, PARC priority substances will be tested when relevant. These new NAMs will be used for the development of Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) (task 5.3) and the development of Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) (task 6.1).

Regulatory relevance:

- REACH: several immune related outcomes are relevant for REACH: skin sensitization, respiratory sensitization, immunosuppression. Currently under REACH, the immunotoxicity investigations are triggered based on repeated dose toxicity studies (28- or 90-day) in case there are some indications of

immunotoxicity. If indications of immunosuppression are seen, one can include e.g. Cohort 3 into the study design of EOGRTS (developmental immunotoxicity) or request to have an immunotoxicity investigation included in a standard repeated dose toxicity study (adult immunotoxicity).

- CLP (Reg EC 1272/2008): While respiratory sensitization is mentioned as a hazard in the CLP regulation, it is acknowledged, that there is no respective method to detect respiratory sensitizers. Hence, a need to develop methods to detect respiratory sensitizers is recognized. On top of that the CLP regulation foresees that non-animal testing is conducted wherever possible, implying support for the development of NAMs.
- Plant protection products (Reg EC 1107/2009) and biocides (Reg EC 528/2012): Sensitization is analysed as part of the data requirements for PPP and biocides. The need to develop methods for respiratory sensitization as well as alternative testing strategies is recognized.
- Cosmetic products: skin sensitization
- Food contact materials (Regulation (EC) No 1935/2004): allergenicity
- Food contaminants (Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006) and enzymes (Regulation (EC) No 1332/2008): allergenicity
- Chemicals strategy: Immunotoxicity is listed as one of the top priority hazard classes in the chemicals strategy (COM(2020) 667 final, 2020).

Main expected outputs of the project

This project will deliver a set of *in vitro* systems that allow the assay of key events in the immune system function or dysfunction. New parameters will be developed to better explore the immune system cellular content and activity, cytokine and antibody production and release, as well as the effect of signaling. Different primary cell systems and cell lines as well as epithelial and immune cell co-cultures will be characterized. Depending on the advancement of the work on the characterization of the NAMs, interlaboratory validation can be considered. A specific discussion on this topic will be held in fall. Before that, in June/July, a list of reference compounds will be decided within labs working on the same topics and/or same models, which could be used for the interlaboratory testing process. In fact, first we thought to perform this pre-validation within the project (5.2.1d and perhaps other labs within WP5 working on immunotox (mycotoxin group and Bisphenol Alternative group)). This will push ourselves to produce SOP and will challenge the NAM before going to a more official and formal process (through for example EU-NETVAL network). This subject will also probably be part of the new immunotox project for Y4/7.

The global aim is to provide task 5.3 and WP6 with assays and data that will support the build-up of AOPs and IATAs through a better characterization of key events in NAMs. For example, if we show that chemicals that activate a receptor, also induce the expression of cytokine genes in an immune cell, this will support the relationship between receptor activation (MIE) and cytokine production (KE) and therefore the build up of an AOP.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project will be helpful from a risk assessor's perspective because the innovative methods developed therein will allow rapid mechanistic hazard analysis of a high number of substances thus contributing to detection of hazardous substances, to the Zero Pollution Ambition of the Green Deal and to The Chemicals Strategy. Additionally, the methods will be able to screen mixtures thus contributing to the aforementioned EU strategies. In addition, the project will be helpful to other end-users like applicants from industry as *in vitro* methods they will be rapid, reliable and cost efficient. Stakeholders will see benefits in the reduction of animal testing, the identification and regulation of hazardous substances and ultimately in the benefits for public health ultimately resulting from the regulatory implementation of the assays.

Key words: immunotoxicity, sensitization, immunosuppression, vaccination, inflammation, NAMs, tests, AOPs

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives OO3: Define common R&I strategies with

transparent criteria and a prioritisation strategy, OO4: Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge, OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives, OO6: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen's understanding/awareness of chemical RA, OO7: Develop/implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA, OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA, OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake, OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC's results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA and OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres.

The aim of PARC is to develop new toxicity tests in compliance with the 3R concept, particularly in outcomes that have been prioritized in the chemical strategy for sustainability. Immunotoxicity is one of these outcomes and this project directly addresses this objective. By developing new NAMs that are biologically and regulatorily relevant, this project addresses the PARC objective of developing new models and innovative concepts for regulatory risk assessment. A working group was set up around four major themes: respiratory immunotoxicity and sensitization, immunosuppression including response to vaccination, immunostimulation, and barrier immunity.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- WP2, Task 2.1: complementarity with guidelines tests
- WP4, Task 4.1: immunotoxicity studies in human (the COVID-19 vaccination study)
- WP5, Task 5.2: complementarity with environmental immunotoxicity, Task 5.3: use of NAMs for AOP development and effect marker validation
- WP6, Task 6.1: use of NAM for IATA/DA validation for regulatory purposes: NAM will be developed that feed into these IATAs.

Links outside PARC

H2020 project on persistent and mobile chemicals (PFAS), EHEN projects on immune effects of the exposome: Hedimed and Eximious, EURION projects, including Oberon, Goliath, EDCmet, ASPIS projects including Ontox, RISKHUNT3R, PrecisionTox, Polyrisk, Aurora, VHP4Safety, MOMENTUM, EFSA (sensitization)

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.2: M12 (April 2023) - Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted. Associated Task: T5.1 Leader of the deliverable: ANSES, BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: BPI/NIPH/INSA. It was planned that the project managers would contribute to this deliverable, but in the end it was not necessary.

AD5.3: M12 (April 2023) - List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints. Associated Task T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: DTU, VUB. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU

D5.1: M18 (October 2023) - 1st NAMs Report. Associated Task: T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

D5.5: M48 (April 2026) - 2nd New approach methodologies report. Associated Task: T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

Partners List:

INSERM (France), NIPH (Norway), MUI (Austria), NCPHP (Hungary), RIVM (Netherlands), IRAS (Netherlands), UL-FFA (Slovenia), INSA (Portugal), UFZ (Germany), WR (Netherlands), LIH (Luxemburg), LIST (Luxemburg)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 155 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 495 226 €

P5.2.1.e_Y1_DNT-ANT_UFZ_IUF_NIPH

Project Title	Neurotoxicity		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	DNT / NT		
Project Manager	Tamara Tal tamara.tal@ufz.de	UFZ	Germany
Deputy Project manager	Kristina Bartmann Kristina.bartmann@iuf-duesseldorf.de Oddvar Myhre Oddvar.Myhre@fhi.no Ellen Fritsche //Joëlle Rüegg joelle.ruegg@ebc.uu.se	IUF/NIPH (from Q2 2023)	Germany/Norway
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	48*
PARC (Month number)		PARC	5.2.1
PARC Workpackage number	5	Task/Activity/ Sub-activity:	
Project Id	P5.2.1.e_Y1_DNT-ANT_UFZ_IUF_NIPH (from Q2 2023) P5.2.1.e_Y1_DNT-ANT_UFZ_IUF_UU (until Q2 2023)		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M48

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Developmental (DNT) and acute (ANT) neurotoxicity are currently assessed via different OECD guideline studies and with different REACH standard information requirements (see details in Annex 1). DNT/ANT guideline studies are extraordinarily resource-intensive and therefore not suited for studying adverse effects of large numbers of chemicals. Therefore, there is international consensus, strongly supported by EFSA and the OECD (1), that DNT testing must be faster and more human-relevant by implementing an alternative DNT testing battery for regulatory purposes. The current state-of-the-art is the use of an DNT *in vitro* test battery (DNT IVB) comprised of several human- and rat-based *in vitro* test methods covering key neurodevelopmental processes, e.g., neural progenitor cell proliferation, differentiation of neurons and oligodendrocytes, and apoptosis. While this represents a step forward towards establishing an alternative DNT testing regime, there are gaps in the DNTIVB including human synaptogenesis, human neural network formation, myelination, and behavioral correlates for the rodent *in vivo* studies including behavior, sensory function, learning and memory endpoints.

The main goal of 5.2.1e is to build second generation NAMs that fill these gaps. To demonstrate the potential added value of the NAMs, the same set of chemicals will be tested across the DNTIVB and 5.2.1e NAMs. Based on these comparative data of hazard classification and potency determinations, we will ultimately make recommendations about the potential inclusion of second generation NAMs in a second generation of the DNTIVB. An additional goal of 5.2.1e is to generate a test battery for acute/adult neurotoxicity (ANT).

Main expected outputs of the project

- New NAMs that fill the current DNT *in vitro* testing battery (IVB) gaps. Here, test methods will be set up from existing test systems (human stem cell-based systems, zebrafish).
- New NAMs for ANT. Current test systems will be used for test method set-up (human stem cell-based systems, zebrafish).

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

- Additional IVB NAMs developed for DNT/ANT will provide risk assessors with rapid mechanistic hazard analysis supporting the green deal and the chemicals strategy.
- Mixture screening in these NAMs contributing to the aforementioned EU strategies.
- Industry will be strongly supported by developed NAMs as they will serve as valid tools for pre-screening and in-house prioritization based on rapid, reliable and cost-efficient methods.
- NGOs and consumers will see benefits in the reduction of animal testing, identification and regulation of hazardous substances and ultimately, in the benefits for public health upon regulatory implementation of the assays.

Keywords: Developmental neurotoxicity (DNT), Acute neurotoxicity (ANT), Alternative DNT testing battery, *in vitro* testing battery (IVB), New Approach methodologies (NAMs)

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

In the EU Green Deal strategy, the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability specifically mentions neurotoxicity (DNT/ANT) as well as endocrine disruption-related developmental neurotoxicity (ED-DNT) as critical outcomes. Moreover, mental and behavioral health are part of the children’s health protection policy. Due to large data gaps, DNT has been recognized as a serious public health concern by many countries and regulatory agencies world-wide. The OECD provides the umbrella for current regulatory DNT efforts including the production of a guidance document for regulatory use of the DNT IVB. Within PARC, gaps within the DNT IVB will be closed and an ANT IVB will be established.

5.2.1.e will generate transparent criteria for inclusion of NAMs in a testing battery for DNT/ANT hazard identification and chemical prioritisation. Via interaction with WP6 partners, we will actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge. 5.2.1.e members are part of multiple other tasks and projects and will work to promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives. (SO 003, 004, 009, 0011, 0012). Project members are engaged in EU-level projects with public dissemination mechanisms. Members will additionally interact with the public via social media and press releases describing our work. (SO 005, 006). All members will release underlying data upon publication, in line with FAIR data practices (SO 0010). We will develop ANT/DNT NAM-based testing strategies to revolutionize RA for neurotoxic chemicals and work with RA's to proactively address concerns and promote implementation.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- WP4: Make use of results from human biomonitoring studies for prioritizing hazard assessment.
- WP5, T5.1. Toxicity testing to address chemicals of concern. T5.3: Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs that are relevant for DNT/ANT.
- WP6, T6.1: Delivering IATAs ready for regulatory application. WP 5.2 will provide data, tools and concepts to improve risk assessment in general. DNT (ANT is to be clarified) is a priority area for developing qAOP but not in the first round (ED, non-genotoxic carcinogenesis and liver are first).
- WP7: Data management plan. We will link with WP7 to make our data available, as soon as possible, for regulators, external researchers, and public. We need access to a database where we can store data, with immediate access for regulators and embargo dates for public use.

Links outside PARC

ENDpoiNTs and other projects within the EURION cluster. In ENDpoiNTs, a battery of assays (in silico, in vitro and in vivo) are developed that detect ED-induced DNT.

- ONTOX, Precisiontox and RiskHunter of the ASPIS cluster.
- H2020 Panoramix (panoramix-h2020.eu)
- US-EPA for common data analysis and DNT IVB assembly.
- ATHLETE project of the European Human Exposome Network (EHEN) cluster (athleteproject.eu).
- VHP4safety Virtual Human Platform for Safety Assessment – VHP4Safety
- Human Biomonitoring Plattform Austria

- EFSA Brain Health Consortium

Key PARC Deliverables (and Milestones to which the project contributes)

AD5.2: M12 (April 2023) - Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted. Associated Task: T5.1 Leader of the deliverable: ANSES, BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: BPI/NIPH/INSA. It was planned that the project managers would contribute to this deliverable, but in the end it was not necessary.

AD5.3: M12 (April 2023) - List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints. Associated Task T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: DTU, VUB. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

D5.1: M18 (October 2023) - 1st NAMs Report. Associated Task: T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

D5.5: M48 (April 2026) - 2nd New approach methodologies report. Associated Task: T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

Partners List:

INSERM-UBX (FR); UU (SE); NIPH (NO); IUF (DE); UKON (DE); RIVM (NL); UFZ (DE); ISCIII (ES); TiHo (DE); AIT (AT); NMBU (NO); UG-PL (PL); BfR (DE); UOB (UK)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 149 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 250 415 €

A5.2.2 Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling for Environmental Toxicology / Ecotoxicology

No project submitted at present.

T5.3 Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs - 3 PROJECTS

This task will contribute to the development of AOPs and provide data for the improvement of Physiologically Based Toxicokinetic (PBK) models. It further aims to integrate relevant human disease models and develop concepts facilitating *in vitro* - *in vivo* extrapolation (IVIVE). For this, systems biology methodology will be applied to *in silico*, *in vivo* and *in vitro* data (biochemical data, omics, endpoints). New data generated in tasks 5.1 and 5.2 as well as relevant data from databases will be mapped to existing (networks of) AOPs, with the aim to hypothesise adverse outcomes. Available literature will be automatically explored to fill gaps in AOPs and to link priority chemicals to events in AOPs using text mining and network analysis tools. This will support the identification and biological characterisation of effect markers that can, later on, be used in WP4. Using bioinformatic tools, this will allow informing human disease mechanisms based on omics and other information. Gaps in pathophysiological knowledge will then be filled by using datasets from existing human biobanks.

Regarding PBK models and quantitative systems toxicology, task 5.3 aim to develop IVIVE-PBK models, to characterise the impact and predictivity of *in vitro* Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion (ADME) parameters, to quantify the uncertainty by comparing to *in vivo* studies and to collaborate with WP6 on a wide range of case studies. Toxicokinetic parameters will be generated for all WP5 test compounds using the appropriate *in vitro* test systems, *in silico* predictions and analytical measurements. PBK modelling will be used to estimate internal exposure and to compare this to Points of Departure derived from *in vitro* mechanistic NAM assays for priority chemicals and pathways. Integration of toxicokinetic and toxicodynamic models in quantitative systems toxicology models will improve adverse outcome prediction.

A5.3.1 Prioritized NAM-based mechanistic hazard characterization – 1 PROJECT

P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR

Project Title	Systems toxicology approaches for mechanism-based chemical safety assessment.		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	SysTox		
Project Manager	Bob van de Water water_b@lacdr.leidenuniv.nl	UL-LACDR	NL
Deputy Project manager	Olivier Taboureau olivier.taboureau@u-paris.fr	INSERM	FR
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48*
PARC Work package number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.3.1 and 5.3.3
Project Id	P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M48

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The SysTox project is part of WP5 and reflect the activities of T5.3.1 and T5.3.3. The objective is to support the chemical risk assessment in the AOP framework, with the evaluation of mechanistic data for a quantitative hazard characterization through new approach methods (NAMs). Mapping and quantifying MIE activity and KE activation is essential for the ultimate application of the AOP framework in chemical safety assessment. Systems toxicology involves the holistic quantitative assessment of perturbations of biological systems by chemicals and typically involves omics approaches, including transcriptomics and metabolomics. To derive confidence in the application of NAM-based omics data, there is a necessity to determine the relevance of *in vitro* omics data with the *in vivo* situation. Various bioinformatics approaches are available to uncover hazard. There is a need to understand the validity of each method with respect to the qualitative and quantitative characterization of hazards. In this project we will validate innovative *in silico* and bioinformatics approaches for quantitative chemical hazard assessment and will be evaluated in this project. We will also address the human *in vivo* relevance of *in vitro* findings. The ultimate aim is that a quantitative assessment of hazard will contribute to classification of chemicals for specific health effects related to EDC, immunosuppression, DNT, NonGenotoxic carcinogenesis, areas that are of critical relevance for PARC.

Main expected outputs of the project

We will establish innovative approaches for mechanism-based hazard assessment based on *in silico* prediction and omics approaches. This will involve both QSAR-based prediction of critical MIE activation as well as quantitative assessment of KE activation based on omics data. In addition, we will provide confidence in the relevance of *in vitro* transcriptomics responses with respect to responses occurring in the human *in vivo* situation. Results of this project should help to prioritize accurate and robust omics-bases prediction for critical toxicological endpoints in chemical risk assessment.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The outcome of the project will be interactive online systems toxicology tools that will allow rapid mechanistic understanding of novel omics data. The tools will be helpful to end-users like applicants from industry and regulatory agencies, since it will allow a cross-sector application of systems toxicology in a structured manner using similar bioinformatics tools. This will allow commonalities in the understanding of omics technologies in a quantitative manner for determination of point-of-departure for risk assessment. Stakeholders will also see benefits in the reduction of animal testing. Finally, the results of our project will

allow for the regulatory implementation of omics strategies and, thereby, for the efficient mechanism-based identification and regulation of hazardous substances that will benefit public health from.

Key words:

Omics, transcriptomics, systems toxicology, gene network, key events, human translation

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives 003 (Define common R&I strategies with transparent criteria and a prioritisation strategy), 004 (Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge), 005 (Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives), 006 (Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen’s understanding/awareness of chemical RA), 007 (Develop/implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA), 0010 (Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA), 0012 (Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake) and 009 (Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC’s results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA).

The SysTox project directly links to the DoA of WP5 T5.3: Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs. This project will ultimately lead to the development of NGRA tools that integrate human-relevant test methods, using *in vitro* and *in silico* approaches to provide quantitative mechanistic information on modes of action, and that allow the rapid mechanistic understanding of novel omics data. As such, it will establish an initial framework for the application of omics data in a regulatory setting. Collaboration is taking place within and outside of Workpackage 5. A workshop on systems toxicology aiming to identify relevant datasets to be used in case studies was organized in January 2022, and benefitted from the regulatory insight of EFSA and the BfR. Three reports will be produced to disseminate the results of this project.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The SysTox project is linked to the following tasks:

- WP4, Task 4.1: human studies and effect markers: translate candidate biomarkers from SysTox studies to human biomonitoring effect markers.
- WP5, Task 5.1, 5.2: complementarity with gap filling studies (5.1) and experimental studies and NAM development (5.2): data from T5.1 and T5.2 will be used in case study.
 Activity 5.3.2: use of NAM data for AOP development and effect marker validation: findings from SysTox project can be used in Project 5.3.2.
- WP6, Task 6.1: development of qAOPs and IATA validation: information from SysTox can be used for data gap filling for qAOP development.
 Task 6.2: mixture effects: mixture effects can be quantitatively addressed through SysTox tools
- WP7, Task 7.3: data and text mining: data provision
- WP8: SysTox bioinformatics tools can be integrated in toolbox
- WP9: training of bioinformatics tools for regulators

Links outside PARC

The project will liaise with the below projects, clusters and initiatives to identify datasets that will be of importance for the SysTox project. Focus will be on omics datasets. This includes interactions with:

- EURION cluster
- EHEN projects on immune/neuro effects of the exposome: Hedimed and Eximious
- EU-ToxRisk project
- ASPIS cluster projects on application of NAM for chemical safety assessment: RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX, PrecisionTOX.
- H2020 green deal project on persistent and mobile chemicals (PFAS)
- OECD - Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics (EAGMST) and the OECD Working Party for Hazard Assessment (WPHA)

- US EPA and US NIEHS/NTP

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.4: Inventory of omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public domain repositories for all PARC selected adverse outcomes and mapping of the available information sources and datasets related to human pathophysiology focusing on the prioritised endpoints (M14)

AD5.7: Draft strategy for the development of bioinformatics tools that are needed to link omics data and other mechanistic information to human relevant disease mechanisms (M18).

D5.3: 1st new AOPs Report (M24)

D5.4: 1st Closing data Gaps Report (M36)

D5.7. 2nd new AOPs report (will change the title to englobe also systems toxicology) (M48)

Partners List

UL-LACDR (NL), INSERM (FR), Ugent (BE), MUI (AT), ISCIII (ES), ISS (IT), BPI (GR), KIT (DE), NCPHP (NO), WR (NL), Sciensano (BE), NIPH (HU), UNIABDN (UK), UFZ (DE), UG-PL (PL), IRFM (IT), UIBK (AT), UMIL (IT), AUTH (GR), IISPV (ES), UOB (UK).

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 135 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 104 635 €

A5.3.2 AOP development based on integration – 1 PROJECT

P5.3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_Inserm

Project Title	AOP Development		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	AOP		
Project Manager	Karine Audouze karine.audouze@u-paris.fr	Inserm	France
Deputy Project manager	Birgit Mertens birgit.mertens@sciensano.be	Sciensano	Belgique
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48*
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.3.2
Project Id	P5.3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_Inserm		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M48

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

New approach methodologies (NAMs) provide a large diversity and amount of data that are very challenging, if not impossible to implement in regulatory applications or mechanistic toxicology unless they are integrated and represented in a useful and widely accepted framework. Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) fulfill all requirements for providing such a framework. AOPs describe the causal relationships

between molecular initiating events (MIEs), subsequent key events (KEs) at different biological levels and ultimately adverse outcomes (AOs). They are developed by integrating and connecting data from various sources i.e. databases and scientific literature, in a logical sequence of causally-linked events.

However, at present, AOPs for important regulatory endpoints are lacking or insufficiently developed. Therefore, in this project, we aim to tackle this regulatory challenge by developing comprehensive AOPs that cover mechanisms underlying regulatory relevant AOs such as immunotoxicology, neurotoxicology, non-genotoxic carcinogenesis, endocrine disruption and metabolic disruption. Different groups will first identify available AOPs (if any), gaps in knowledge, and will develop AOPs related to these outcomes using transparent and consistent methodologies, and following the FAIR data principles. One group will focus on methodologies and tools for AOP development, and another group will identify putative effect markers based on available AOPs. By providing a framework for the use of NAMs and/or development of integrated approaches to testing and assessment (IATA) for high-priority endpoints, the project will have an impact on legislations for chemicals (REACH and CLP), plant protection products and biocides, cosmetic products and food (food additives, food contaminants and food contact materials).

The work in this project will also address the EFSA Roadmap for Action on New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) in Risk Assessment by refining the existing AOP inventory and developing additional AOPs, advanced cell culture models and facilitating data integration. The development and characterisation of advanced *in vitro* NAMs including integration of AOPs will entail a major step towards Next Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA). These will also prepare solid ground for further development of quantitative AOPs by pointing out where the data is missing and needs to be generated.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project will be helpful from a risk assessor's perspective because the AOPs will support the further development and implementation of innovative methods to rapidly analyze the mechanistic hazard of a high number of substances thus contributing to detection of hazardous substances and to the zero-pollution ambition of the green deal and the chemicals strategy for sustainability. Additionally, AOPs developed in this project will be used to define assessment groups and to group chemicals (sharing the same MoA/AOP or not) in a step-wise approach, facilitating the assessment of mixtures thus also contributing to the aforementioned EU strategies. AOPs are currently already used by different agencies to support hazard identification. They are the basis for IATA development and for the identification of relevant effect markers. Ultimately, the project will help to increase confidence in the AOPs, NAMs and IATAs and facilitate their use to inform the various steps in the risk assessment process.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The developed AOPs will be helpful to end-users like applicants from industry because they provide a framework to structure regulatory relevant mechanistic information and facilitate targeted testing with NAMs in a rapid, reliable and cost-efficient way. Stakeholders will see benefits in the reduction of animal testing, the identification and regulation of hazardous substances and ultimately in the benefits for public health resulting from the regulatory implementation of the assays. Other possible outcomes:

- Develop protocols and tools to optimize and harmonize data collection, appraisal, synthesis and visualization based on artificial intelligence supporting AOP development;
- Acquire available and most recent information on toxicity pathways leading to immune and hormonal dysregulation, neurotoxicity and non-genotoxic carcinogenesis, including chemicals able to interfere with all the identified pathways;
- Identify missing data, inconsistencies and scientific gaps that might affect extrapolation in a regulatory setting;
- Link to the AOP-Wiki database contributing to the AOP- Knowledge Base project launched by OECD
- Provide a framework for the identification of biomarkers of effect, the targeted development/improvement of NAMs and the design of AOP-based IATAs (cfr. PARC T6.1).

Key words:

AOP, method, immunotoxicology, neurotoxicology, non-genotoxic carcinogenesis, endocrine disruption, metabolic disruption, development, artificial intelligence (AI)

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives 003 (Define common R&I strategies with transparent criteria and a prioritisation strategy), 004 (Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge), 005 (Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives), 006 (Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen’s understanding/awareness of chemical RA), 007 (Develop/implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA), 0010 (Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA), 0012 (Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake), 009 (Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC’s results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA) and 0011 (Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres).

Regulatory uptake will be fostered through the identification of missing data, inconsistencies and scientific gaps that might affect extrapolation in a regulatory setting. Innovation in complex data analysis for RA will take place through, namely, the development of protocols aiming to optimize data collection, appraisal, synthesis and visualization based on artificial intelligence (AI). Cooperation with other R&I initiatives is a core element of this project, as there will be a sustained collaboration with PARC activities related to NAMs (task 5.2), systems biology (activities 5.3.1, 5.3.3), and IATA development and risk assessment (task 6.1).
<mailto:parc@anses.fr>

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- WP2, Task 2.1: complementarity with guidelines tests
- WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness
- WP4, Task 4.1: Human studies and effect markers
- WP5, Task 5.2, 5.1: complementarity with experimental studies and NAM development. Task 5.3: use of NAMs for AOP development and effect marker validation
- WP6, Task 6.1: development of qAOPs and IATA validation, Task 6.2: mixture effects, Task 6.3: text mining
- WP7, Task 7.3: data and text mining. Data management plan (AOP data FAIRness)
- WP8, Task 8.2: emerging chemicals
- WP9: Training

Links outside PARC

- H2020 Green Deal Projects: ALTERNATIVE, PROMISCES, LIFESAVER, SCENARIOS, PANORAMIX, ZeroPM
- EURION: European Cluster to improve identification of Endocrine Disruptors
- EHEN projects on immune/neuro effects of the exposome: Hedimed and Eximious
- EU-ToxRisk project
- ASPIS cluster projects on application of NAM for chemical safety assessment: RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX, PrecisionTOX.
- OECD: OECD Working Group of National Co-ordinators of the TGs programme (WNT), OECD Advisory Group on Emerging Science in Chemicals Assessment (ESCA; previous EAGMST), OECD Working Party for Hazard Assessment (WPHA) and different OECD Working Groups
- US EPA and US NIEHS/NTP
- EFSA, ECHA, SCCS, EEA
- PEPPER

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.4: Inventory of omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public domain repositories

for all PARC selected adverse outcomes and mapping of the available information sources and datasets related to human pathophysiology focusing on the prioritised endpoints (M14)

AD5.5: Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (M12)

D5.7. 2nd new AOPs report (will change the title to englobe also systems toxicology) (M48)

Partners List:

ACES or SU (SE); AU (DK); AUTH (GR); BfG (DE); BPI (GR); DTU (DK); IISPV (ES); Inserm (FR); IRSN (FR); ISS (IT); KI (SE); KIT (DE); KU-Leuven (BE); LIST (LU), MUI (AT); NILU (NO); NIPH (NO); NCPHP (HU); UG-PL (PL); SDU (DK); Sciensano (BE); UAntwerpen (BE); UGent (BE); UKK/UoC (DE); UIBK (AT); UL-LACDR (NL); UMIL (IT); UNIVIE (AT); WR (NL), Cefas-Defra (UK)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 115 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 42 567 €

A5.3.3 Translation to human pathophysiology

No project submitted at present.

A5.3.4 PBTK models and quantitative systems toxicology – 1 PROJECT

P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Kinetics_Fraunhofer

Project Title	PBK models and quantitative systems toxicology		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	PBK_Kinetics		
Project Manager	Sylvia Escher sylvia.escher@item.fraunhofer.de	ITEM	DE
Deputy Project manager	Georg Aichinger georg.aichinger@hest.ethz.ch	ETHZ	Swiss
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	48*
PARC (Month number)		PARC	5.3.4
PARC Workpackage number	5	Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	
Project Id	P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Kinetics_Fraunhofer		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M48

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The aim of this project is to fill data and knowledge gaps in the area of kinetic modelling. To achieve this, project P5.3.4 will develop physiologically based kinetic (PBK) models, which are informed by mainly NAM data. In addition, we will integrate PBK models with AOPs as a basis for quantitative system toxicology. Several conceptual and data gaps will be addressed, such as i) individual human variability in bioavailable concentrations; ii) the impact of the human microbiome on the metabolism of xenobiotics iii)

transport across the blood brain barrier; and iv) uptake of inhalable compounds via the respiratory tract. This project will refine and establish in a bottom-up approach generic models that describe Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, and Excretion (ADME) of chemicals in the human organism on the basis of compartments defined by physiological parameters. The developed models will facilitate quantitative *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation in a reliable way to produce data of direct value for chemical risk assessment. Compound-specific input data will be derived by the validation and use of *in silico* and *in vitro* ADME approaches. For the initial phase, 9 case studies were defined, focusing on the expansion or refinement of physiologically-based kinetic (PBK) models using data-rich model compounds or the generation of predictive PBK models for PARC priority compounds. We aim to establish an initial framework for the application of qIVIVE-PBK models in a regulatory setting, so that a quantitative assessment of hazard will be possible starting from the *in vitro* hazard identification in e.g. AP.3.1 and AP.3.3. This work will therefore contribute to characterise the hazard of chemicals for specific health effects e.g. in the area of endocrine disruptive compounds (EDC), immunosuppression, DNT and non genotoxic carcinogenesis.

Main expected outputs of the project

We will have established innovative approaches to characterize the ADME processes of priority compounds by integrating *in silico* prediction and *in vitro* ADME data into PBK models for oral and inhalation exposures, accounting for uncertainty linked to relevant biological processes.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

By establishing innovative IVIVE-PBK models, this project will have an important impact on the integration of NAM-based approaches into regulatory risk assessment. IVIVE-PBK models are needed for the extrapolation from the *in vitro* benchmark concentration to a human equivalent concentration or dose. This will enable users to determine a point of departure (PoD) from NAM based RA. Thereby the project links directly to the project P5.3.1 and P5.3.2 in T5.3 and the IATAs developed in WP6. In addition, the project will show the applicability and by this will promote use of *in vitro* and *in silico* ADME data in PBK models for predicting human plasma and tissue concentrations. In addition, the project will be helpful to other end-users like applicants from industry since it will allow a cross-sector application of kinetic modelling in a structured manner using similar PBK models. Models will be made available by publications and other suitable platforms as e.g. provided by WP7.

Key words:

in vitro ADME models, *in silico* ADME models, physiologically based kinetic modelling, oral, inhalation, human equivalent concentration/dose, microbiome metabolism, transport processes

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives 003 (Define common R&I strategies with transparent criteria and a prioritisation strategy), 004 (Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge), 005 (Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives), 006 (Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen's understanding/awareness of chemical RA), 007 (Develop/implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA), 0010 (Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA), 0012 (Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake), 009 (Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC's results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA) and 0011 (Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres).

The PBK_kinetic project directly links to the DoA of WP5 T5.3: Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs. Next generation risk assessment relies on NAM based hazard identification and characterization. PBK modelling is a central key element of NGRA, as it will be used for quantitative *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation (qIVIVE), deriving equivalent plasma and tissue concentrations which serve as a NAM based point of departure for risk assessment. Project 5.3.4 will close data and knowledge gaps in PBK modeling by using case studies. These case studies will be used to i) discuss the workflow for implementing PBK models and qIVIVE into regulatory decision making, ii) outline remaining uncertainties

but also advantages compared to the current hazard assessment paradigm iii) to close data gaps for PARC priority compounds. P5.3.4 core team will connect to other European projects, like e.g. ASPIS and in particular RiskHunt3R to promote the development of a harmonized internal exposure framework. Data and modelling work are dedicated to FAIR data principles.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The PBK_kinetic project is linked to the following tasks:

- WP5, Task 5.1, 5.2: complementarity with gap filling studies (5.1) and experimental *in vitro* ADME studies (5.2): data from T5.1 and T5.2 will be used in case studies to develop and validate IVIVE-PBK approaches.
- WP6, Task 6.1: development of qAOPs and PBK models to be integrated into IATAs. Information from PBK_Kinetics can be used for qIVIVE and for qAOP development.
- WP7, Task 7.3: Data and text mining: data provision
- WP8: PBK_Kinetics bioinformatics tools can be integrated in toolbox
- WP9: training of PBK models for regulators

Links outside PARC

The project will liaise with the below projects, clusters and initiatives to identify datasets that will be of importance for the PBK_kinetic project. Focus will be on *in vitro*, *in silico* ADME model data, PBK modelling approaches as well as concepts for tiered testing strategies, starting from simple to more complex testing. This includes interactions with:

- EURION cluster
- EHEN projects on immune/neuro effects of the exposome: Hedimed and Eximious
- EU-ToxRisk project
- ASPIS cluster projects on application of NAM for chemical safety assessment: RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX, PrecisionTOX.
- H2020 green deal project on persistent and mobile chemicals (PFAS) like ZeroPM
- OECD – IATA case studies
- EFSA ADME4NGRA
- US EPA and US NIEHS/NTP

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D5.2: 1st new PBK models report (new delivery date M36)

D5.6: 2nd new PBK models report (M48)

Partners List:

ANSES (FR); ETHZ (CHE); IISPV (ES); INERIS (FR); Inserm (FR); ISCIII (ES); ISS (IT); ITEM-Fraunhofer (DE); NVI (NO); UKK/UoC (DE); UIBK (AT); UNIVIE (AT); WR (NL); WU-Tox (NL); EA (UK), AUTH (EL), UFZ (DE), Cefas-Defra (UK), NIPH (NO), Unisanté (CH), STAMI (NO)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 123 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 140 376 €

WP6 Innovation in regulatory risk assessment – 28 PROJECTS

The overall goal of WP6 is to drive innovation in regulatory RA by strengthening its scientific basis, with implementation of NGRA as ultimate goal.

The specific objectives are:

- To deliver IATAs for a selected set of human health effects, developed in close collaboration with relevant stakeholders and proven to be applicable through dedicated case studies
- To perform integrative RA based on internal and external exposure of humans exposed to chemicals and mixtures thereof *via* different routes of exposure, including the workplace
- To evaluate and map current methodologies employed in regulatory RA across sectors
- To identify gaps and needs in methodological knowledge
- To develop and foster the uptake of innovative, effective and protective regulatory RA approaches and methodologies
- To develop a framework to assess exposure of and facilitate enforcement of chemicals in articles and materials on the EU-market.

The work in WP6 is divided into four tasks:

T6.1 Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment of Chemicals 4 PROJECTS

The goal of this task is to establish IATAs, to be used for different European regulations on chemical safety for different industry sectors as well as for the CLP Regulation. The IATAs will be developed for a selected set of health effects (e.g. liver toxicity, genotoxicity, endocrine disruption). To provide a strong mechanistic basis for IATA development, existing and newly developed AOPs for selected health effects will be combined into AOP networks. Wherever possible and relevant, Key Event Relationships will be quantitated by applying computational methodologies. IATAs will be developed in close collaboration with stakeholders including OECD and through various cycles of optimisation. In addition, systematic quantitative determination of the uncertainty of application of a combined set of NAMs in an IATA will provide insight in the overall confidence for the application of a selected test battery for respective IATAs.

Fig 9: WP5.3_WP6.1 interactions on AOPs: IATA Development

A6.1.1 Development of IATAs for regulatory purposes – 4 PROJECTS

P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM

Project Title	Workflow for Human Relevance Assessment of AOPs and Associated New Approach Methodologies		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Human Relevance		
Project Manager	Mirjam Luijten Mirjam.luijten@rivm.nl	RIVM	NL
Deputy Project manager	Elisavet Renieri elisavet_renieri@hotmail.com	AUTH	GR
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.1.1
Project Id	P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The goal of Task 6.1 (T6.1) in PARC is to deliver Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATA) for a selected set of health effects. The majority of the IATAs will focus on human health, which will be developed and evaluated in close collaboration with relevant stakeholders. Key elements of an IATA include Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) and new approach methodologies (NAMs). This project is focused on the assessment of human relevance of AOPs and the relevance of NAMs related to the key events (KEs) or key event relationships (KERs) of the pathway under study. Such assessment requires a harmonized and accepted workflow. A framework for analysis of mode of action (MOA)/human relevance has been developed in initiatives of WHO/IPCS. In spite of detailed methodological instructions, additionally provided templates and case studies, application of the framework in practice, including the analysis of species concordance, remains challenging. Therefore, this project aims to further optimize an existing draft workflow (v0.1) that was developed based on the WHO/IPCS framework. The refinements will be done in close collaboration with WHO, OECD and other international and regulatory organizations, to ensure its readiness for regulatory implementation. The goal is to establish a harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment and to demonstrate its applicability through dedicated case studies. The resulting assessments will directly feed into IATAs developed in PARC.

Main expected outputs of the project

The main output of the project is a pragmatic, harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of both AOPs and its associated NAMs, accompanied by a set of case studies demonstrating how the workflow can be applied.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

A pragmatic, harmonized workflow for the assessment of human relevance of AOPs will inform on which networks of AOPs should be covered by an IATA for human health risk assessment, while assessment of the relevance of NAMs related to the key events (KEs) or key event relationships (KERs) of the pathways under study will inform on which NAMs are well suited to be used for a regulatory assessment. Together, this information is highly valuable for end-users and other stakeholders.

Key words

human relevance, Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs), toxicological mechanisms, New Approach Methodologies (NAMs), weight of evidence, Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATA)

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project responds to Specific objective 3 (SO3) “European risk assessors, their scientific network and the wider stakeholder community have access to the R&I capacities required to implement innovative chemical RA”, and more specifically to Operational Objective 9 “Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA”.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project is directly linked to the following PARC projects:

- P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA-ED_UAntwerpen
- P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA-GENTOX_Sciensano
- P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA-STOT_UL-LACDR

To maximize synergy across the T6.1 projects, core teams addressing common elements will be established. These core teams include “AOP networks”, “Quantitative AOPs”, and “IATA development/evaluation”. The project team involved in the project on human relevance will closely collaborate with the other three projects, in particular with the core teams on AOP networks and quantitative AOPs.

WP2, A common science-policy agenda: Achievement of regulatory readiness of the workflow for human relevance assessment will require dedicated discussions with various international regulatory bodies, to ensure that regulatory needs are being addressed.

WP3, Synergies, Communication and awareness: The development of a workflow that is ready for regulatory implementation will strongly benefit from raising awareness, proper communication of the (draft) workflow and collecting feedback from stakeholders by WP3.

WP7, Data management plan: see below for the section Data Management.

WP9, Training, laboratory network: Implementation of the workflow in regulatory processes will be greatly facilitated by training courses, developed as a joint activity of WPs 9 and 6.

Links outside PARC

The project will build on, among others, the Mode of Action/Human Relevance framework developed by the WHO/IPCS. It is also closely linked to the OECD AOP programme and IATA case studies. In that context, regular interactions with the OECD Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics (EAGMST) and the OECD Working Party for Hazard Assessment (WPHA) are foreseen. Additionally, human relevance assessment is a topic of high interest to ILMERAC and the project will benefit from guidance documents on weight of evidence and uncertainty developed by e.g., EFSA.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

The output from this project will substantially contribute to the following key deliverables/additional deliverables/milestones of WP6:

- D6.5; D6.12: Reports on IATAs and associated case studies (M42; M81)
- D6.11: Harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs (M72)
- AD5.5: Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (M12; INSERM)
- AD6.9: Report on draft IATAs and associated case studies (new delivery date M30; UL-LACDR)

Partners List:

AUTH (GR); RIVM (NL); ENSP-UNL (PT); BPI (GR); WU-TOX (NL); NIPH (NO); STAMI (NO); ISS (IT); IISPV (ES); LIST (LU); IRSN (FR)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Cost:

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 41 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 60 971 €

P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA-ED_UAntwerpen

Project Title	Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) for Endocrine Disruption		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	IATA-ED		
Project Manager	Dries Knapen	UAntwerpen	BE
Deputy Project manager	Miriam Jacobs	UKHSA	UK
	Miriam.Jacobs@ukhsa.gov.uk		
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.1.1
Project Id	P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA-ED_UAntwerpen		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The goal of this project is to deliver Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) for endocrine disruption (ED), one of the health effects prioritized in the EU Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability. Criteria for the identification of endocrine disrupting compounds (EDCs) have been stipulated for the Biocidal or Plant Protection Products Regulation and a guidance document, i.e., “Guidance for the identification of EDCs in the context of Regulations (EU) No 825/2012 and (EC) No 1107/2009”, was written to guide identification of EDCs to comply with these obligations. In addition, other regulations (e.g., REACH, Cosmetic regulation) also require information on the ED potential of chemicals. The OECD guidance document 150 provides guidance on the use of standardised TGs for evaluating EDCs, but this does not provide details of assays. Therefore, there is an urgent need to develop IATAs for identifying EDCs both in a human and environmental health context. This will structure, identify key gaps and facilitate direct regulatory application of PARC outcomes. Thyroid hormone system disruption (THSD) and anti-androgenic (AA) adverse effects have been prioritized for IATA development in this project. To ensure that the IATAs will address regulatory needs, they will be developed in close collaboration with relevant stakeholders and evaluated through dedicated case studies. A modular approach is envisioned to allow for tailoring an IATA to specific regulatory needs. This is already being developed with ECHA for an OECD IATA project, and a similar model will be followed.

Main expected outputs of the project

The first expected results are IATAs for THSD and AA action. These modalities have been selected as priorities in T5.3.2 working on AOP development and T6.1 working on IATA development, based on the recent and ongoing international efforts in developing AOPs and (pre)validating NAMs in these areas (e.g., conducted at the JRC, the Pepper platform, the USEPA, and within the EURION cluster). Following the completion of the EURION projects (Goliath, Oberon, edcmet) in June 2024, further metabolic disruption IATA work may be considered as a next priority.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Regulatory strategies for identifying endocrine disrupting chemicals in line with the advancing legislation in this context are mostly lacking. This project will ultimately enable better regulatory decision making and significantly improve the hazard identification of endocrine disrupting chemicals with the long-term aim to limit exposure and improve human as well as environmental health. The use of predictive methods and NAMs will significantly reduce the need for long-term, low-throughput and costly toxicity tests requiring large numbers of animals, thus contributing to the replacement of animal tests.

Key words

Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATA), Endocrine disruption (ED), Thyroid hormone system disruption (THSD), Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP), Risk assessment

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project responds to Specific objective 3 (SO3) “European risk assessors, their scientific network and the wider stakeholder community have access to the R&I capacities required to implement innovative chemical RA”, and more specifically to Operational Objective 9 “Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA”.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

In addition to the current project, T6.1 includes three closely linked projects related to IATA development: P6.1.1.a on Human Relevance assessment of AOPs and NAMs, P6.1.1.c on IATA-GENOTOX and P6.1.1.d on IATA-STOT (Systemic Target Organ Toxicity). Project leader meetings are organized on a regular basis to align the overall IATA development approach across projects. The project also closely collaborates with T5.3.2 on AOP development through shared leadership and partners. Specifically for ED, T5.3.2 Specialty Group 2, co-lead by D. Knapen (also co-lead of the current project) and H. Holbech, performs AOP development in the area of endocrine and metabolic disruption and has established priorities using feedback from the current project on the relevance for IATA development. A similar interaction exists with T5.2 working on the development of NAMs such that existing and newly developed AOPs and NAMs can be used for IATA development. Priorities regarding regulatory frameworks to be addressed are discussed with stakeholders (primarily ECHA and EFSA, but in some cases this may be extended to include the relevant OECD groups) in close collaboration with WP2 and WP3. For the evaluation of IATAs through case studies, we will collaborate with T6.2 – T6.4 and WP7 “FAIR data”, in which analysis of the uncertainties associated with the IATA will be one of the used cases. Lastly, this work relates to WP9 “Capacities”, since valuable learnings will be taken up in relevant training courses.

Links outside PARC

This task interacts with ongoing international activities, such as the preliminary validation of in vitro assays for the detection of THSD coordinated by EURL-ECVAM in the JRC-NETVAL study, as well as the critical evaluation and recommendations of THSD test method readiness for further validation performed by the OECD Thyroid Disruption Methods EG (TDM EG). Indeed, it is planned to invite ECHA to the next (or dedicated) OECD TMD EG meeting with a view to hearing from ECHA with respect to their regulatory and legislative needs and increase mutual understanding. Also, there is active collaboration with the EURION cluster (especially ERGO, ATHENA, SCREENED and FREIA focusing on THSD and anti-androgen effects) to assess which NAMs will be ready for regulatory validation and subsequent application. The project is linked to multiple activities ongoing at OECD in relation to THSD AOP development (several projects on the AOP development programme), the inclusion of thyroid endpoints in OECD fish Test Guidelines (Project 2.64 on the OECD Test Guidelines work plan) and IATA case studies. As such, regular interactions as deemed relevant are foreseen with the Advisory Group on Emerging Science in Chemicals Assessment (ESCA), the OECD Task Force on Endocrine Disrupters Testing and Assessment (EDTA), the Validation Management Group for Ecotoxicity Testing (VMG-Eco) as well as the OECD Working Party for Hazard Assessment (WPHA) and the Working Group on National Coordinators to the OECD Test Guideline Programme. Furthermore, links with NC3Rs on a recently-launched CRACK-IT challenge

related to THSD testing in fish and with the USEPA that has recently expressed an interest in collaborating will be explored.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

The output from this project will substantially contribute to the following key deliverables of WP6:

- D6.5; D6.12: Reports on IATAs and associated case studies (M42; M81; Sciensano)
- D6.11: Harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs (M72, RIVM)
- AD5.5 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (M12; INSERM)
- AD6.9: Report on draft IATAs and associated case studies (new delivery date M30; UL-LACDR)

Partners List:

UAntwerpen (Belgium); UKHSA (United Kingdom); MU (Czechia); AUTH (Greece); UGent (Belgium); INSERM (France); UL-LACDR (Netherlands); RIVM (Netherlands); ISS (Italy); DTU (Denmark); SDU (Denmark); LIST (Luxembourg); BPI (Greece); UG-PL (Poland); IISPV (Spain); STAMI (Norway); KI (Sweden); IRFM (Italy); ENSP-UNL (Portugal); Sciensano (Belgium); CEFAS-DEFRA (UK), UU-IRAS (NL), JRC (EU) (collaborating organisation)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Cost:

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 89 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 112 221 €

P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano

Project Title	Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) for Genotoxicity		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	IATA-GENTOX		
Project Manager 1	Birgit Mertens birgit.mertens@sciensano.be	Sciensano	BE
Project manager 2	Marc Audebert marc.audebert@inra.fr	INRAE	FR
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.1.1
Project Id	P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The goal of Task 6.1 (T6.1) in PARC is to deliver Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATA) for a selected set of health effects. The majority of the IATAs will focus on human health; however, environmental health will also be addressed in some projects. To ensure that the IATA will address regulatory needs, they will be developed in close collaboration with relevant stakeholders and evaluated through dedicated case studies. This project is focused on IATA development for genotoxicity, one of the health effects that has been prioritized in the EU Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability. Moreover,

genotoxicity is considered a low-hanging fruit for IATA development based on existing data and available test systems. The test strategies for genotoxicity that are in place under the current regulations for the different regulatory frameworks are somewhat similar but often rely on animal testing, and do not integrate NAMs such as 3D comet and micronucleus assays, ToxTracker®, the γ H2Ax/pH3 method or transcriptomic-based gene expression biomarkers (e.g. TGx-DDI and GENOMARK). By delivering an IATA, the project aims to move towards the assessment of genotoxicity without the use of animals.

Main expected outputs of the project

The main expected output of the project is an AOP-based IATA for genotoxicity. This will include an overview of the test methods and assays that can be applied and a (partially) quantitative AOP framework for this endpoint. Information on absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion (ADME) will also be integrated through collaboration with T5.3. The applicability of the IATA will be demonstrated by means of case studies. A first set of case studies will involve known (non-)genotoxicants to evaluate the overall structure and performance of the IATA. More complex compounds will be selected in close collaboration with regulatory agencies such as ECHA and EFSA for the second set of case studies. Overall, this project will provide a conceptual framework for the application of an AOP-based IATA for the assessment of genotoxicity that can be included for future assessment.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project impact on stakeholders and end-users will involve a defined IATA for genotoxicity that can be applied for safety testing. It will allow insight in a defined testing approach including the test methods to assess this endpoint without the use of animals. The IATA framework could benefit all EU agencies dealing with genotoxicity assessment (e.g. EFSA, ECHA and EMA), as well as a plethora of regulations addressing this hazard class (REACH, CLP, PPP, etc.), thus contributing to the harmonization of data requirements among EU agencies. Case study compounds will be carefully selected in collaboration with the regulatory agencies to ensure that, wherever necessary, regulation-specific issues are addressed. Regarding REACH, the outcome of this project might have an impact on the revision of the testing requirements, although this will depend on the timeline of the REACH revision and the project. Furthermore, the utility and applicability of a shift towards a more quantitative approach for assessment of genetic toxicity hazard will be explored (e.g. by analysis of genotoxicity data with the benchmark dose modelling (BMD) approach).

Key words

Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATA), genotoxicity, DNA damage, gene mutations, chromosome damage, (quantitative) Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP), key events

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project responds to Specific objective 3 (SO3) “European risk assessors, their scientific network and the wider stakeholder community have access to the R&I capacities required to implement innovative chemical RA”, and more specifically to Operational Objective 9 “Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA”.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

For T6.1 the project is linked to the three other T6.1 projects in PARC:

1. P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM
2. P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA_ED_UAntwerpen
3. P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR

To maximize synergy across the T6.1 projects, core teams addressing common elements will be established. These core teams include “AOP networks”, “Quantitative AOPs”, and “IATA development/evaluation”. The project team involved in the project on human relevance will closely collaborate with the other three projects, in particular with the core teams on AOP networks and quantitative AOPs.

The work described in this project is connected to other WPs in PARC, in multiple ways.

Firstly, the proposed priorities regarding regulatory frameworks to be addressed will be confirmed with stakeholders in close collaboration with WP2 “A common science-policy agenda” and WP3 “Synergies,

collaboration and awareness”. Secondly, we will closely collaborate with WP5 “Hazard assessment” on various topics related to IATA development. These topics include: a) mapping of existing AOPs and associated NAMs for genotoxicity; b) development of (quantitative) AOP networks using, among others, data generated in WP5 (e.g. data generated with toxins); c) linkage to QIVIVE and PBK modeling (T5.3) and evaluation of IATA through case studies. Within WP6, the case study *T6.3_CS11: Analysis and evaluation of genotoxicity and carcinogenicity assessment across legislations, with a special focus on (Q)SAR based approaches* will be particularly relevant for the mapping of existing AOPs but also for the evaluation of IATA through case studies, we will closely collaborate with T6.2, T6.3 and T6.4. The case studies also provide a link to WP7 “FAIR data”, in which analysis of the uncertainties associated with the IATA will be one of the use cases. Integrative models developed in T8.3 of WP8 will be considered as well. Lastly, this work relates to WP9 “Capacities”, since valuable learnings will be taken up in relevant training courses.

Links outside PARC

The project is closely linked to work done by the HESI Genetic Toxicology Technical Committee (GTTC), on AOP development and Next Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA). It is also linked to work ongoing at OECD, in relation to NAMs for genotoxicity (e.g. 3D comet and micronucleus assays, ToxTracker®, the yH2Ax/pH3 method and miniaturized versions of the bacterial reverse gene mutation test), AOP development (OECD AOP programme) and IATA case studies. As such, regular interactions with the OECD Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics (EAGMST) and the OECD Working Party for Hazard Assessment are foreseen. The link with the work on AOP development for radiation effects done within the context of the MELODI project will also be investigated. Finally, wherever applicable and relevant, a link to ongoing activities on IATAs for non-genotoxic carcinogenicity will be made as well.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

The output from this project will substantially contribute to the following key deliverables of WP6:

- D6.5; D6.12: Reports on IATAs and associated case studies (M42; M81; Sciensano)
- D6.11: Harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs (M72, RIVM)
- AD5.5 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (M12; INSERM)
- AD6.9: Report on draft IATAs and associated case studies (new delivery date M30; UL-LACDR)

Partners List

Sciensano (BE), INRAE (FR), VUB (BE), UL-LACDR (NL), WU-TOX (NL), ISS (IT), IBMT (DE), UG-PL (PL), STAMI (NO), LIST (LU), BPI (GR), IRSN (FR), RIVM (NL), KWR (NL), NILU (NO), IRFM (IT), MUI (AT), NIPH (NO), WR (NL).

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Cost:

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 104 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 182 966 €

P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR

Project Title	Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) for Systemic Target Organ Toxicity		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	IATA-STOT		
Project Manager	Bob van de Water water_b@lacdr.leidenuniv.nl	UL-LACDR	NL
Deputy Project manager	Joost Beltman j.b.beltman@lacdr.leidenuniv.nl	UL-LACDR	NL
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.1.1
Project Id	P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The goal of Task 6.1 (T6.1) in PARC is to deliver Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) for a selected set of health effects. The majority of the IATAs will focus on human health; however, environmental health will also be addressed in some projects. To ensure that the IATA will address regulatory needs, they will be developed in close collaboration with relevant stakeholders and evaluated through dedicated case studies. This project is focused on IATA development for specific target organ toxicity (STOT). The project will initially focus on liver toxicity, and at a later stage, but in parallel, other types of target organ toxicity will be started such as respiratory toxicity. Liver toxicity is the most often observed toxic effect in 90-day studies and also considered low-hanging fruit for IATA development based on existing data and liver test systems. Yet, liver toxicity is complex and involves different end-points that typically have different mechanisms as well as time course for development. An initial focus will be on liver fibrosis as a critical endpoint. In contrast, for respiratory toxicity there is a need for IATA development and implementation/application of scientifically developed in vitro methods. Lung fibrosis is an important human health end-point and we will consider how an IATA for liver fibrosis could be generalized to other target organs, including lung fibrosis. Note that liver fibrosis is typically a late event following chemical exposure, in part because multiple cell types are involved, and we intend to develop and include appropriate culture systems to properly deal with this issue. Such a system should in principle allow for both single exposure (SE) and repeated exposure (RE) testing, and while the project is running, we will decide on which of these aspects to focus, depending on the challenges related to SE and RE.

Main expected outputs of the project

The main expected output of the project is an IATA for liver toxicity with an initial focus on liver fibrosis that is based on an AOP framework. This will include an overview of the test methods and assays that can be applied and a quantification AOP framework for this endpoint. This project will provide a conceptual framework for the application of an AOP-based IATA for the assessment of STOT that can be included for future assessment of systemic toxicity. The case study of the project will demonstrate the applicability of the established IATA.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

There is currently no IATA for liver toxicity. The project impact on stakeholders and end-users will involve a defined IATA for liver fibrosis that can be applied for safety testing. It will allow insight in a defined testing approach including the test methods to assess this end-point without the use of animals. An IATA for liver fibrosis represents only an initial step in the development of a comprehensive IATA approach that would meet the standard information requirements under REACH (acute, sub-acute and sub-chronic

repeated dose toxicity), as these requirements go beyond studying liver effects. Nevertheless, such an IATA will partially inform the information requirements needed for STOT Single Exposure (SE) and STOT Repeated Exposure (RE) classification as defined under REACH. These include respectively 8.5.1 (acute toxicity - annex VII), 8.5.2 or 8.5.3 (acute toxicity - annex VIII), and 8.6.1 (short-term repeated dose toxicity study, 28 days - annex VIII), 8.6.2. sub-chronic toxicity study (90-day) (annex IX). Note that in this project we intend to produce a quantitative assessment of the involved assays in relation to the adverse outcome, which is an important aspect for STOT SE and STOT RE classification.

Key words

Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATA), systemic toxicity, liver, fibrosis, (quantitative) Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP), key events

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project responds to Specific objective 3 (SO3) “European risk assessors, their scientific network and the wider stakeholder community have access to the R&I capacities required to implement innovative chemical RA”, and more specifically to Operational Objective 9 “Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA”.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project is linked within the following PARC activities:

For T6.1 the project is linked to three other projects in T6.1:

1. P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM
2. P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA_ED_UAntwerpen
3. P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano

To maximize synergy across the T6.1 projects, core teams addressing common elements will be established. These core teams include “AOP networks”, “Quantitative AOPs”, and “IATA development/evaluation”. The project team involved in the project on human relevance will closely collaborate with the other three projects, in particular with the core teams on AOP networks and quantitative AOPs.

The work described in this project is connected to other WPs in PARC, in multiple ways.

Firstly, the proposed priorities regarding regulatory frameworks to be addressed will be confirmed with stakeholders in close collaboration with WP2 “A common science-policy agenda” and WP3 “Synergies, collaboration and awareness”. Secondly, we will closely collaborate with WP5 “Hazard assessment” on various topics related to IATA development. These topics include: a) mapping of existing AOPs and associated NAMs for endocrine disruption; b) development of (quantitative) AOP networks using, among others, data generated in WP5; c) linkage to QIVIVE and PBK modeling (T5.3); and c) evaluation of IATA through case studies. For the latter, we will also closely collaborate with T6.2 – T6.4. The case studies also provide a link to WP7 “FAIR data”, in which analysis of the uncertainties associated with the IATA will be one of the use cases. Lastly, this work relates to WP9 “Capacities”, since valuable learnings will be taken up in relevant training courses.

Links outside PARC

Furthermore, the project is closely linked to the Horizon2020 projects EU-ToxRisk, RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX and PrecisionTox, and to work ongoing at OECD in relation to AOP development (OECD AOP programme) and IATA case studies. As such, regular interactions with the OECD Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics (EAGMST) and the OECD Working Party for Hazard Assessment (WPHA) are foreseen.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

The output from this project will substantially contribute to the following key deliverables of WP6:

- D6.5; D6.12: Reports on IATAs and associated case studies (M42; M81; Sciensano)
- D6.11: Harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs (M72, RIVM)

- AD5.5 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (M12; INSERM)
- AD6.9: Report on draft IATAs and associated case studies (new delivery date M30; UL-LACDR)

Partners List

UL-LACDR (NL), WU-TOX (L), INSERM (FR), Ugent (BE), AUTH (GR), MU (CZ), IISPV (ES), STAMI (NO), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), WFSR (NL).

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Cost:

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 48 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 94 084 €

A6.1.2 Evaluation of IATAs through case studies

This activity is incorporated in the projects listed under A6.1.1.

A6.1.3 Stakeholder engagement

This activity is incorporated in the projects listed under A6.1.1.

T6.2 Integrative exposure and risk assessment - 8 PROJECTS

The aim of this task is to develop innovative and practical approaches for human health risk and impact assessment of single, aggregated and combined exposure to chemicals *via* multiple sources across regulatory silos and routes during lifetime. Relative contributions of sources and routes will be determined. Living and working environment as well as chemical transfer from soil to water, food, and air and migration from consumer products, articles and materials will be integrated. For estimating and reconstructing chemical exposure through life, accounting for varying exposure scenarios and physiological and biochemical characteristics over time, PBK models will be developed. Simulations of concentrations in target tissues will be linked to AOPs and IATAs. Finally, data availability and methodologies to perform health impact and cost-benefit assessment for prioritised chemicals, exposure routes, windows of exposure, subpopulations, geographical locations, and health outcomes will be improved.

Innovative methods, tools and concepts to perform integrative risk and health impact assessments : combining data and methods from different approaches and disciplines

Fig 10: W6.2: Risk and health Impact Assessment

A6.2.1 Aggregate exposure from multiple sources and routes for general population and workers – 2 PROJECTS

P6.2.1.a_Y1_SourcetoDose_VITO

Project Title	Developing, performing and validation of source to dose modelling including selected case studies		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	SourcetoDose		
Project Manager	Katleen De Brouwere katleen.debrouwere@vito.be	VITO	BE
Deputy Project manager	Radu Duca radu.duca@lns.etat.lu	LNS	LU
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.1
Project Id	P6.2.1.a_Y1_SourcetoDose_VITO		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

This project aims to model from sources to doses, the human exposure of general population to chemicals, potentially arising from a variety of sources and routes. Sources include different types: environmental sources including 1) emissions from industrial facilities, traffic and households, etc. 2) diffuse environmental sources (e.g., historical soil contamination, water etc), and 3) consumer sources present in our everyday life, (e.g., construction products, household products, etc.) potentially releasing chemicals that may enter our bodies.

It is anticipated that for some source and route of exposure, models do exist, but are (overly) conservative in nature because of their intended uses for screening purposes. However, when it comes to combination of exposures from different sources into an aggregated exposure (and comparison with HBM values) and health impact assessment, realistic external exposure models are crucial, and needed for policy makers (e.g., in view of comparing impact of different policy or risk management options).

This project is connected to the project on aggregate exposure modelling. The scope of this project will be routes and sources for which realistic exposure models are currently lacking. Where models are lacking, they will be developed. Where possible, we will rely on existing models and improve them in order to shift from screening models to higher tier models generating realistic exposure estimates.

This project focus is on modelling as a complementary tool to human biomonitoring, for the general population (occupational exposure is out of scope). Case studies will be tailored toward chemical classes in line with PARC projects (e.g., case studies on PFAS, flame retardants, metals, pesticides).

The ultimate goal is to come up with robust, mechanistic model(s) and tools which are, at the same time relatively simple in use for risk assessors.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Improvement of existing models for generating realistic exposure assessment for selected consumer articles or products, and environmental sources
- Development of new model(s) for routes and sources for which there is currently a lack of models (for selected sources)
- Transcription of the conceptual model(s) to T8.3

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The role of modelling in aggregate exposure assessment is that modelling offers a complementary tool to human biomonitoring to perform chemical risk assessment.

This project will make it possible to end-users to perform risk assessment for chemicals (environment and consumer exposure) covered in this project. It will offer end-users the opportunity 1) to expand the assessment to other groups not included in HBM studies ((e.g. specific age groups, vulnerable groups), 2) to assess the relative contribution of different sources and exposure routes (given that that the models will generate realistic exposure estimates for each source and route), and 3) to calculate the impact of risk management options (e.g. predicting impact of restrictions, mitigations). The latter can inform policy makers about the most efficient risk management strategies thus allowing for better informed decision making.

Key words: human exposure, modelling, consumer exposure, exposure *via* the environment, realistic exposure modelling, migration, articles

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

OO5: The project will identify data required for source to dose modelling for priority chemicals and exposure scenarios across Europe. The project will use data and knowledge generated and published by other past and ongoing R&I projects and initiatives.

OO7: Based on data gaps that appear from the data and models inventories, studies to fill these gaps may be initiated.

OO8: The project will support the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes, since environmental and multisource data are key elements for parameterization and/or verification of source to dose models.

OO10: As the project will use data that are generated outside PARC and by other PARC projects, and will generate data that can be used by other activities in and outside of PARC, implementation of FAIR data practices is a prerequisite.

OO13: The project will be developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes regarding source to dose models.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- Connection with T4.1 (HBM data from T.4.1 will be used to validate the model outcome)
- Connection with A6.2.1 Interoperability of models for aggregate exposures:
 - gaps identified will steer the priorities in 6.2.1
 - model outcomes generated in this project can be included in aggregate exposure modelling in 6.2.1.
- Connection with T8.3: outcome (model) will be taken up in T8.3
- Project “Strategy for aggregate exposure from general life and occupational exposures” (project P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES)
- Projects from T8.3

Links outside PARC

This project will start from the work of previous initiatives such as the ones from ISES Europe and the REACH Exposure Expert Group (REEG), HBM4EU (WP 12), and 7th FP projects (e.g., 4-FUN)

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

- AD6.3. Roadmap on aggregated exposure strategy through different living environments sources and routes (M12)
- D6.1. 1st Report on aggregate exposure for general population and workers, and source to dose models applied to case studies (M36)

Partners List:

VITO (BE); RIVM (NL); ANSES (FR); LNS (LU); IVV (DE); CSTB (FR); KWR (NL); IVL (SW); NIJZ (SI); FOPH (CH); GeoZS (SI); FMUL (PT), UoB (UK), IISPV (ES)

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/25 (M36)

Cost:

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 33 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 20 525 €

P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_AnSES

Project Title	Strategy for aggregate exposure from general life and occupational exposures		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Aggregate		
Project Manager	Crépet Amélie amelie.crepet@anses.fr	ANSES	France
Deputy Project manager	David Vernez david.vernez@unisante.ch	UNISANTE	Switzerland
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.1
Project Id	P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

In the context of a compartmentalized view of risk assessment, this project aims to advance knowledge on the combination of various exposure environments including occupational and general life exposures. It will help to propose a more integrative risk assessment and management crossing regulatory silos. This project will draw up the strategy to aggregate exposures from multiple sources and routes in considering both general life and occupational exposures. It is divided into three parts. The first one aims to review available models, tools and data and draw a functional design for model connection. The second part is to work on methods and criteria to perform aggregate exposure and the last part is to organize and start the relevant case studies selected from the defined criteria and PARC priorities. Building from current knowledge, this project is an important step to propose advanced aggregate exposures assessment from multiple sources and routes. It will provide a better understanding of the main sources and routes of exposure during occupational and general life to support effective risk management measures.

Main expected outputs of the project

The outputs for model interoperability and data inventory part are: selection of models for further analysis, models and tools description with their structural analysis, functional design for model connection for T8.3, data inventory for T7.1 and data gaps to be feed by T4.1 and T4.2. The outputs for methods for aggregate exposure part are: strategy and roadmap for aggregate risk assessment, innovative methods to perform aggregate risk assessment, criteria for prioritisation of case studies and advance knowledge on the combination of various exposure environments including occupational and general life exposures. The outputs for case studies for aggregate exposure part are: selection of relevant case studies of aggregate exposure including general life and occupational exposures, aggregated exposure results and prioritization of main sources and routes of exposure from general life and occupational environments.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Provide tools to facilitate comparisons between entry routes and exposure situations and, ultimately, prioritize areas for action and prevention. This project will also make it possible to end-users to perform risk assessment from several sources and routes of exposure. It will make possible to account for both general life and work activities in risk assessment. Concrete case studies will be conducted for prioritized chemicals.

Key words: Aggregate exposure, multiple sources, multiple routes, risk mitigations, occupational exposures, general life exposures, consumer exposure, environmental exposure.

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project responds to the PARC operational objectives OO4: Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge, OO6: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen's understanding/awareness of chemical RA, OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake, OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC's results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA and OO13: Build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical RA. This project will develop methods, toolboxes, and organize relevant data to combine exposure from various environments including occupational and general life exposures. In identifying main sources and routes of exposure during occupational and general life, the output of the project will help to prioritize risk management measures. Training to the new methods and tools will be proposed with T8.3 to the different stakeholders.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

This project is also strongly connected to other projects from T6.2. As example aggregate exposures can be used as input in mixture (P6.2.3) and health impact projects (P6.2.4). The output of the sources to dose (P6.2.1.a) and PBPK projects (P6.2.2.a) can be used as input of this project.

This project will be strongly connected to the T8.3 on integrative models in involving the task leader WR-BIOM. The objective is to deliver the functional design to task T8.3 for its implementation.

The data inventory will be conducted in connection with the T4.1 and T4.2 and the results of the data gap analysis will be discussed with the leaders to see how they can be handled.

A connection with T7.3 on methods to combine data to account for uncertainty will be also done as aggregate exposure can be a good case study.
 It can also propose input for training in WP9.

Links outside PARC

This project will start from the work of previous initiatives such as the ones from ISES Europe and the REACH Exposure Expert Group (REEG). It is also linked to the Scientific Committee Consumer Safety.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.3. Roadmap on aggregated exposure strategy through different living environments sources and routes (including inventory of databases, models and tools (M12)

D6.1. 1st Report on aggregate exposure for general population and workers, and source to dose models applied to case studies (M36)

AD6.21. Report describing the results of the aggregate strategy and its application (M48)

Partners List: ANSES (FR), UNISANTE (CH), RIVM (NL), VITO (BE), UU (SE), NIOM (PL), INSA (PT), TNO (NL), NIJZ (SI), AU (DK), TTL (FI), SRU (NL), GeoZS (SI), LNS (LU), ISSeP (BE), CSTB (FR), EFSA (EU), MU (CZ), WR-BIOM (NL), CSIC (ES), INRS (FR), NIPH (NO), KWR (NL), IVL (SE), ISCII (ES), FOPH (CH), STAMI (NO), FMUL (PT), ENSP-UNL (PT), UOB (UK), BPI (EL), AUTH (EL).

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Cost:

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 109 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 94 125 €

A6.2.2 Modelling exposure through life – 1 PROJECT

P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPk_INERIS_AUTH

Project Title	Refinement and development of PBPk models for human risk assessment		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	PBPk		
Project Manager	Aude RATIER aude.ratier@ineris.fr	INERIS	France
Deputy Project manager	Spyros KARAKITSIOS spyros.karakitsios@gmail.com	AUTH	Greece
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.2
Project Id	P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPk_INERIS_AUTH		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic (PBPk) models are essential tools in toxicokinetic modelling and risk assessment as they describe the Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, and Excretion (ADME) processes in the human body. PBPk models are able to focus on the effective dose at the target site, providing a better characterization of the relationship between exposure dose and adverse effects (Andersen, 1995; Verner et al., 2010). Given the growing interest in using PBPk models in the risk assessment process, guidelines for appropriate extrapolations of species, doses, and exposure scenarios have been proposed. The mechanistic basis of PBPk models is well adapted to toxicological risk assessment (US EPA, 2006; IPCS, 2010; OECD, 2021), in particular for dealing with extrapolations inherent to these domains (in vitro to in vivo, laboratory animals to humans, various exposure or dosing schemes, etc.). The HBM4EU project reviewed available PBPk models for several compounds, highlighting a lack of toxicokinetic data for many prioritized compounds and a lack of models for sensitive populations such as pregnant women and their fetuses, newborns, young children, or the elderly. In this PARC project, PBPk models will be refined or developed to address population sub-group sensitivities, integrating multiple exposure routes and sources, and interpreting human biomonitoring data. Different sources of data will be used (either from literature or from synergies with WP5) for refining or developing PBPk models necessary for the use of internal dose metrics for risk assessment.

Main expected outputs of the project

PBPk models will be refined or developed to address population sub-group sensitivities, integrating multiple exposure routes (oral ingestion, inhalation, and dermal contact) and sources (occupational, consumer, and environmental), and new matrices of exposure predictive of specific exposure (e.g., hair or meconium for newborns). These models will be applied to biomonitoring data for one chemical or mixtures and will help to interpret them. The experimental needs with WP5 will be identified, and QSAR models will be used to obtain parameters related to kinetics and partitioning. The models developed in this task will be interoperable (in collaboration with WP7 and WP8) with open platform used for risk assessment.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

As PBPk models are tools used to support risk assessors and managers, it is essential to provide models that are adapted to their requirements and that follow the most up-to-date guidance, e.g., the OECD document on the characterisation, validation and reporting of PBPk models for regulatory purposes (Series on Testing and Assessment No. 331, ENV/CBC/MONO(2021)1). This project within PARC will focus on

the refinement or development of PBPK models for prioritized compounds and mixtures, e.g., with limited information, sensitive populations, and the aggregation of the various exposures. The models that will be proposed will be made interoperable (in collaboration with WP7 and WP8) with other modules in integrative open platforms used for risk assessment.

Key words: PBK models; multi-route exposures; lifelong exposure; sensitive human sub-groups; metabolic interactions; barrier models.

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project responds to the PARC objectives OO5: the project will identify models for priority chemicals and sub-groups of population for which refine RA is needed across Europe. The project will use data and knowledge generated and published by other past and ongoing R&I projects and initiatives, OO7: Based on data gaps that appear from the PBK models inventory, studies to fill these gaps may be initiated, OO10: Implementation of FAIR data practices is a prerequisite. PBK models will be developed or implemented under the FAIR principles and OO12: PBK models will be developed to answer or to suggest innovative concepts for RA, and will be available on toolboxes to promote their acceptability.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Activities undertaken in WP5 (Tasks 5.1, 5.2, 5.3) for the generation of toxicokinetic data and the development of AOP, WP8 (Task 8.3) for the model integration in an open platform, WP4 for the availability of HBM data.

WP6: Other T6.2 projects that aim to link internal and external exposures from multiple sources (6.2.1) and for mixtures (6.2.3):

- Strategy for aggregate exposure in order to confirm external exposure assessment with HBM data.
- New risk assessment and exposome methodologies to reduce exposure and risk of real-life mixtures

Links outside PARC

Bisphenols, PFAS, pesticides, metals and mycotoxins have been priority compounds among the HBM4EU project and modelling efforts, as well as review of existing models and identification of gaps has been carried out.

Some compounds are also endocrine disruptor compounds that are studied in the EURION cluster, specifically in the OBERON project.

Links to the exposome projects, such as ATHLETE.

The work in this area that is ongoing outside Europe is also considered (*e.g.*, US EPA).

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.4: Inventory of PBK models for assessing the internal exposure through life and for in-vitro-to-in-vivo extrapolation (M12)

D6.2: 1st Report on innovative methods based on PBK models (M36)

AD6.22: Case studies of the application of refined/developed PBPK models in the risk assessment process (M48)

Partners List: INERIS (France), AUTH (Greece), IISPV (Spain), ANSES (France), RIVM (Netherlands), SLU (Sweden), NIPH (Norway), VITO (Belgium), WR-BIOM (Netherlands), WR-WFSR (Netherlands), IRFM (Italy), IVL (Sweden), TNO (Netherlands)

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Cost:

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 93 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 70 437 €

A6.2.3 Mixture exposure and risk assessment – 1 PROJECT

P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM

Project Title	New risk assessment and exposome methodologies to reduce exposure and risk of real-life mixtures		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	RealLifeMixtures		
Project Manager	Jacob Van Klaveren jacob.van.klaveren@rivm.nl	RIVM	Netherlands
Deputy Project manager	Amélie Crépet Amelie.crepet@anses.fr	Anses	France
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.3
Project Id	P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The mixture concerns are reflected in the prioritisation process and were ranked as a high priority for many stakeholders and Member States. Furthermore, there is a need to regulate chemicals in such a manner that potential mixture effects are already considered in the registration or authorisation process (prospective risk assessment of mixtures).

The project will build on scientific progress made on mixture risk assessment, by international organisations (such as EFSA, EEA and ECHA, EC-JRC, OECD), regarding hazard-based grouping of chemical and statistical approaches developed in previous project such as Euromix, HBM4EU and the EHEN exposome projects. The project combines risk assessment and epidemiological approaches to support scientific needs from Member States, DG SANTE and DG Environment. It will integrate the needs identified in the Chemical Strategy and the linked EC Policy Document SWD 250 final STAFF WORKING DOCUMENT Progress report on the assessment and management of combined exposures to multiple chemicals (chemical mixtures) and associated risks.

The main objectives of the projects are to:

- Build a common strategy to perform human risk assessment to chemical mixtures
- Integrate exposome and risk assessment approaches
- Prioritize real-life mixtures from HBM data
- Develop hazard and kinetic information on prioritized mixtures
- Study the link between mixture biomarkers of exposures and effects
- Perform mixture risk assessment for prioritized mixtures

Main expected outputs of the project

- Prioritisation methods and/or grouping approaches to select the components to be considered;
- Options to use (eco)toxicity and exposure data on the single components to predict mixture hazard and/or risks, through component-based approaches based on dose additivity;
- Tiered approaches bringing together advances made for mixtures in regulatory risk assessment and in the field of exposome to refine the assessment depending on the availability and quality of exposure and hazard data

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

- EFSA, ECHA and EEA in future scientific opinions on risk assessment of mixtures

- EU Member States in communication towards stakeholders and the general public
- Industry addressing the risk of mixtures when assessing the risk of new chemicals before entering the market

The project includes training activities for end-users that will be organised by WP3 and WP9.

Key words: Mixture, HBM, co-exposure, health effects, AOP, RPF, PBPK, risk assessment

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project responds to the PARC operational objectives OO4: Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge, OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives, OO6: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen's understanding/awareness of chemical RA, OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake, OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC's results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA and OO13: Build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical RA.

Real-life mixture project will fill-in basic science gaps to explore how human bio-monitoring can be used in practice for mixture risk assessment. The project is developing a strategy to perform mixture risk assessment (MRA) in three main steps: 1) Prioritisation of mixtures considering regulatory priorities 2) Collection and organisation of HBM and hazard data, and 3) Mixture risk assessment for prioritised mixtures and effects. The collected data and the developed approaches will be integrated in the MCRA toolbox which is a web-based computational environment addressing chemical mixtures and their hazard, exposure and risk assessment for health effects. Finally, the project will deliver methods, tools and practical results on prioritized chemical families and effects that will serve regulators to move forward on mixture questions

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

This project has strong connection with:

- WP1 : management and indicators
- WP2: priority setting and uptake into policy
- WP3: communication and dissemination of results
- WP4:
 - Derivation of health-based HBM guidance values
 - Link human biomonitoring studies to health examination and dietary surveys
- WP5: further hazard characterisation for mycotoxins, PFAS and heavy metals
- WP7: link with external data sources (e.g., IPCHEM, Tox data or EFSA data)
- WP8 : task 8.3 integrative models

This project is strongly connected to other projects from T6.2. For, example aggregate exposures (T6.2.1) can be used as input in this project and development from PBPK projects (T6.2.2) will be directly applied in the context of mixture. This project is cooperating with T4.1 (generation of HBM data), WP7 (data formatting and data organisation) and T8.3 (integrative model development).

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU legacy: the project will build further on experiences, results, materials, and networks developed within HBM4EU
- EuroMix legacy and EuroMix follow-up: make use of the MCRA software developed in the EuroMix project
- Green Deal projects addressing PFAS and mixtures (e.g., awarded projects as PANORAMIX for mixtures) and SPRINT (pesticides).
- EFSA RACEMIC Roadmap for the Risk Assessment of Combined Exposure to Multiple Chemicals.
- DG SANTE and EFSA-RIVM partnership on Regulatory implementation of dietary risk assessment of pesticide mixtures.
- OECD activity effect biomarkers/AOPs

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.3. 1st Report on innovative approaches for real-life mixture RA (M36)

AD6.5. Report describing co-occurrence probabilities of chemicals forming real life mixtures of the selected HBM studies across Europe and overview of the kinetic and grouping aspects of prioritised mixtures (M12)

AD6.23 Report describing the results of the mixture RA strategy and its application (M48) was deleted from the Project Description Document.

Partners List:

ANSES (FR), RIVM (NL), AU-PH (DK), AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), IDAEA-CSIC (ES), IISPV (ES), UGR (ES), DTU (DK), EASP (ES), EFSA (EU), EHESP (FR), FINBA (ES), ICPS (IT), JSI (SI), INERIS (FR), INSERM (FR), ISCIH (ES), IVL (SE), LNS (LU), MOHCY/SGL (CY), MU Recetox (CZ), NIJZ (SI), NIPH (NO), SRU (NL), SLU (SE), STAMI (NO), Swiss SECO (CH), TTL (FI), UBA (DE), UGPL (PL), UNIPD (IT), UU-IRAS (NL), VITO (BE), WR (NL), INRAE (FR), KWR (NL), FMUL (PT), GeoZS (SI), UNIVIE (AT), IRFM (IT), IPA (DE)

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Cost:

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 225 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 154 922 €

A6.2.4 Human health impact assessment and risk indicators – 4 PROJECTS

P6.2.4.a_Y1_HIADDataAvailability_VITO

Project Title	Collection and generation of data for HIA of PARC priority chemicals		
Project	HIADDataAvailability		
Acronym (15 letters max)			
Project Manager	Jurgen Buekers	VITO	BE
	jurgen.buekers@vito.be		
Deputy Project manager	Jelle Vlaanderen	UU-IRAS	NL
	J.J.Vlaanderen@uu.nl		
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	66*
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.4
Project Id	P6.2.4.a_Y1_HIADDataAvailability_VITO		

* The project has been broken at M66 (that corresponds to the last landmark of the project) to assess what has been achieved and if the review is positive then then this project could go on until M81.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Availability of data on external or internal exposure (including variation per geographical location and socioeconomic status), health outcomes (based on mode of action and dose-response data from toxicological as well as epidemiological studies), relative risk, disease incidence or prevalence, and demographic data are a prerequisite to perform Health impact assessment (HIA) for chemical exposures

prioritized in PARC. However, data required to perform EBD or HIA are often incomplete. This project will evaluate and increase the availability of data for EBD or HIA for PARC priority substances for specific or aggregated exposure routes, windows of exposure, vulnerable populations, occupational settings, geographical locations, age groups, health outcomes etc. Increased availability of suitable data for EBD or HIA calculations for specific exposure scenarios will facilitate health impact assessments to be used by regulators for evaluation and prioritization exercises. This task supports the 1st and 3rd flagship of the Zero Pollution Action being reducing health inequalities as pollution has no equal impact across society and better monitor the impact of chemicals on our health and progress towards pollution relevant targets set under the ZPA and CSS.

This project is part of four interrelated projects on health impact assessment. Together with results of the project on ‘Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies’, the results will serve as input for the projects ‘Case studies on health impact assessment’ and ‘Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators’. The project case studies (6.2.4.c) forms the central starting point to which other projects (6.2.4.a data availability, 6.2.4.b methodologies, 6.2.4.d indicators) are linked (see Fig 11).

Fig 11. Interrelationship between different 6.2.4 projects

Main expected outputs of the project

The inventory and collection or generation of data required for health impact assessment of chemicals and exposure scenarios (specific or aggregated exposure routes, windows of exposure, vulnerable populations, occupational settings, geographical locations, age groups etc.) prioritized in PARC will be linked to the case studies which is a recurring activity every year.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Risk assessment (RA), Burden of Disease (BoD) calculations, health impact assessment (HIA), and (social) cost benefit analyses ((S)CBA) inform stakeholders and policymakers to help protect and eventually improve human health. The EU Green Deal, in particular the Zero Pollution Ambition policy, in which the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability is a cornerstone, aims at reducing the planetary health impact from chemical exposures. HIA and SCBA allow to objectify the impact of current chemical exposure on health in EU populations, prioritize preventive or mitigatory actions to be taken, and estimate the environmental burden of disease and costs avoided as a result of EU policies and regulations.

Key words: Health impact assessment (HIA), data gaps

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

OO5: The project will identify data required for EBD or HIA calculations for priority chemicals and exposure scenarios across Europe that are generated and published by other past and ongoing projects and initiatives.

OO6. The project will disseminate results case studies through scientific publication taking into account the FAIR data principle.

OO7: Based on data gaps that appear from the data inventory, exposure or hazard data generation and derivation of population-specific exposures may be initiated.

OO10: As the project will use data that are generated outside PARC and by other PARC projects, and will generate data that can be used by other activities in and outside of PARC, implementation of FAIR data

practices is a prerequisite.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- Measured or modelled internal and external exposure data will be collected in cooperation with WP3, WP4, WP8 and other T6.2 activities and with support from WP7
- Exposure-effect data may be generated by WP4 (epidemiological studies) and in WP5 (toxicity studies)
- T4.1.3 and WP9 will be consulted for information on health data registers
- Projects inside PARC :
 - P6.2.4.b Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies
 - P6.2.4.c Case studies on health impact assessment
 - P6.2.4.d Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU and NHANES for internal exposure data (*link via VITO, UU-IRAS, ANSES*)
- ATHLETE, EXPANSE, HEALS for exposure data (*link via ANSES*)
- EHEN for exposome data (*link via UU-IRAS*)
- COST Action CA18218 European Burden of Disease Network (*link via Sciensano*)
- EU health information projects (e.g., PHIRI, TEHDAS)

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

- AD6.6. Inventory of existing HIA, exposure and exposure-effect data for chemicals prioritised in PARC (M12)
- D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications (M36)

Partners List:

ANSES (FR); AUTH (EL); DTU (DK); ENSP (PT); FMUL (PT); IISPV (ES); INSA (PT); ISSeP (BE); IVL (SE); KI (SE); MU (CZ); NIJZ (SI); NIPH (NO); NLZOH (SI); OI (SI); SRU (NL); Sciensano (BE); STAMI (NO); USI (CH); UU-IRAS (NL); VITO (BE)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2027 (M66)

Costs:

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 42.5 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 17 950 €

P6.2.4.b_Y1_HIAMethod_UU-IRAS

Project Title	Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	HIAMethod		
Project Manager	Jelle Vlaanderen	UU-IRAS	NL
	J.J.Vlaanderen@uu.nl		
Deputy Project manager	Jurgen Buekers	VITO	BE
	jurgen.buekers@vito.be		
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	66*
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.4

Project Id P6.2.4.b_Y1_HIAMethod_UU-IRAS

* The project has been broken at M66 (that corresponds to the last landmark of the project) to assess what has been achieved and if the review is positive then then this project could go on until M81.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Data on exposure, exposure-effect relations, health outcomes, relative risk, and demographics can be used for environmental burden of disease (EBD) calculations, analytical Health Impact Assessment (HIA), cost analysis (direct, indirect and intangible) and cost-benefit analysis for chemical exposures. Several aspects of EBD and HIA methodologies can be improved to reduce uncertainties in EBD estimates and HIA calculations. The methodological improvements of EBD & HIA calculations to be realized via this project will reduce the uncertainties in health impact assessment and allow the use of a broader range of data as input for EBD and HIA calculations. This will improve the usability of EBD and HIA calculations by policy makers for evaluation and prioritization exercises. Specifically for REACH, under the restriction process, authorities should demonstrate the proportionality of the restrictive measure and should justify that the societal gain from improved environmental and human health outweighs any foreseen economic losses. Improvement of the EBD and HIA calculations may support justification of regulatory risk management of substances that are of (very) high concern to society. Similarly, e.g. improved EBD and HIA may allow for a better assessment of consequences of not taking action, which may support the Commission in deciding on regulatory action on groups of substances. This is especially useful in the context of the EU Green Deal, particularly the Zero Pollution Ambition Plan (ZPAP) in which the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability (CSS) is a cornerstone, which aims at reducing the planetary health impact from chemical exposure.

This project is part of four interrelated projects on health impact assessment. Together with results of the project on ‘Collection and generation of data for HIA of PARC priority chemicals’, the results will serve as input for the projects ‘Case studies on health impact assessment’ and ‘Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators’. The project case studies (6.2.4.c) forms the central starting point to which other projects (6.2.4.a data availability, 6.2.4.b methodologies, 6.2.4.d indicators) are linked (see Fig 11).

Main expected outputs of the project

Facilitation of EBD calculations, analytical HIA, cost analysis (direct, indirect and intangible) and cost-benefit analysis and improved confidence in results due to further development and improvement of methods to assess e.g. exposure-effect associations, dynamics in exposure and mixture risks.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Risk assessment (RA), Environmental Burden of Disease (EBD) calculations, health impact assessment (HIA), and (social) cost benefit analyses ((S)CBA) inform stakeholders and policymakers to help protect and eventually improve human health. The EU Green Deal, in particular the ZPAP in which the CSS is a cornerstone, aims at reducing the planetary health impact from chemical exposures. EBD, HIA and SCBA allow to objectify the impact of current chemical exposure on health in EU populations, prioritize preventive or mitigatory actions to be taken, and estimate the environmental burden of disease and costs avoided as a result of EU policies and regulations.

Key words: Environmental Burden of Disease (EBD), Health impact assessment (HIA), methodologies, uncertainty

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

OO3: Methodological improvements developed in this project may be incorporated in harmonized approaches for EBD and HIA calculations.

OO4: Reduction of uncertainty in EBD and HIA calculations will improve the usability of results by policy makers for evaluation and prioritization exercises.

OO5: Information exchange and collaborations with other networks and initiatives in the area of EBD and HIA will be established.

OO7: Based on methodological issues and uncertainties that are identified via this project, methodological

improvements will be developed and implemented during the course of PARC.

OO10: As the project will use data that are generated outside PARC and by other PARC projects, and will generate data that can be used by other activities in and outside of PARC, implementation of FAIR data practices is a prerequisite.

OO13: Methods developed in this project may be disseminated inside and outside of PARC via training and exchange initiatives.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- P6.2.4.c: Case studies on health impact assessment
- P6.2.4.d: Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators
- T6.2.4: Exposure through life
- T6.4.4 Risk assessment to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity
- T4.1: General population survey, Targeted surveys, Occupational surveys
- T5.3: projects identifying effect biomarkers

Links outside PARC

- HERA project: Guidelines for health impact assessment (HIA) of environmental factors
- COST Action CA18218 European Burden of Disease Network
- EPHOR: methodology for exposure dynamics (falling risk curves) and for appropriately adding effects estimates of correlated exposures
- HEALS, ICARUS, EXPANSE: ABM models for estimating the expected effect of environmental interventions

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.6. Inventory of existing HIA, exposure and exposure-effect data for chemicals prioritised in PARC (M12)

D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications (M36)

Partners List:

ANSES (FR); AUTH (EL); DTU (DK); ENSP (PT); FMUL (PT); IISPV (ES); INSA (PT); IVL (SE); KI (SE); MU (CZ); NIPH (NO); OI (SI); RIVM (NL); Sciensano (BE); UBA (DE); USI (CH); UU-IRAS (NL); VITO (BE); WR-BIOM (NL)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2027 (M66)

Costs:

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 49 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 20 287 €

P6.2.4.c_Y1_HIACaseStudies_UU-IRAS

Project Title	Case studies on health impact assessment		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	HIACaseStudies		
Project Manager	Jelle Vlaanderen J.J.Vlaanderen@uu.nl	UU-IRAS	NL
Deputy Project manager	Jurgen Buekers jurgen.buekers@vito.be	VITO	BE
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	42*
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.4

Project Id P6.2.4.c_Y1_HIACaseStudies_UU-IRAS

* The project has been broken at mid-term (M42) to assess what has been achieved at the mid-term and if the review is positive then a new project could be launched for the period M43-M81.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Environmental burden of disease (EBD) analyses are quantitative assessments of the burden of disease (including morbidity, mortality and financial costs) in a specific population that is attributable to environmental factors such as chemicals. Health impact assessment (HIA) is a tool to estimate the health impact of a policy or program on population health. EBD and HIA analyses for current chemical exposure of EU populations can be used to compare the burden of disease attributable to different environmental exposures and to prioritize preventive or mitigatory actions to be taken. Case studies will be performed for PARC priority substances.

Based on results of the T6.2.4 projects on data availability and methodological improvements, a selection of case studies will be performed to calculate the health impact and risk/benefit or cost/benefit scenarios for chemical substances, classes or mixtures, adverse health effects and exposed populations prioritized in PARC, using existing data and/or data generated in PARC. The results of the case studies will also feed into the T6.2.4 project ‘Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators’. The case studies (6.2.4.c) form the central starting point to which other projects (6.2.4.a data availability, 6.2.4.b methodologies, 6.2.4.d indicators) are linked (see Fig 11).

Main expected outputs of the project

In year 1, criteria for selection of case studies to be implemented will be defined (e.g., availability of required data, part of the population exposed above health-based guidance values, possibility for EU-wide assessment, ...) and the case studies to be initiated in year 2 will be selected and designed. In order to define the chemicals and exposure scenarios addressed in the case studies, a risk ranking exercise may be conducted based on evidence-based semi-quantitative methodologies. Prioritization of case studies will take the preferences of key stakeholders into account, across priority societal domains, quantified through multi-criteria decision analysis, and will be done in consultation with WP2 and PARC boards. The selection, design, and performance of case studies will be recurring activities during the course of PARC.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Risk assessment (RA), Environmental Burden of Disease (EBD) calculations, health impact assessment (HIA), and (social) cost benefit analyses ((S)CBA) inform stakeholders and policymakers to help protect and eventually improve human health. The EU Green Deal, in particular the Zero Pollution Ambition policy, in which the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability is a cornerstone, aims at reducing the planetary health impact from chemical exposures. EBD, HIA and SCBA allow to objectify the impact of current chemical exposure on health in EU populations, prioritize preventive or mitigatory actions to be taken, and estimate the environmental burden of disease and costs avoided as a result of EU policies and regulations.

Key words: Environmental Burden of Disease (EBD), health impact assessment (HIA), case studies

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

OO3: A prioritization framework is developed as part of this project for selection of case studies related to EBD and HIA calculations to be implemented during the course of PARC.

OO4: The project will increase the understanding of the contribution of chemicals as upstream determinants of diseases. This will support policy makers in the reduction of environmental and human health impact of exposure to hazardous chemicals and as such in the improvement of the protection of environmental and citizen’s health.

OO6: Increased understanding of the contribution of chemicals as upstream determinants of diseases will support communication to citizens and increase their awareness about risks of chemical exposures.

OO7: Prioritization and selection of case studies will be a recurring activity to develop annual working plans during the course of PARC.

OO10: As the project will use data that are generated outside PARC and by other PARC projects, and will generate data that can be used by other activities in and outside of PARC, implementation of FAIR data practices is a prerequisite.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- WP2 for prioritization
- WP3 for stakeholder consultation and communication
- Use of existing data in cooperation with WP3 and data generated in WP4, WP5 and other T6.2 activities
- Data sharing options and integrative model tools provided by WP7 and WP8
- Projects inside PARC:
 - P6.2.4.a: Collection and generation of data for HIA of PARC priority chemicals
 - P6.2.4.b: Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies
 - P6.2.4.d: Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators
 - *Projects from other WPs/Tasks to be identified*

Links outside PARC

Projects generating quantitative chemical exposures and effects data e.g. ATHLETE, EXPANSE, NHANES, HEALS, NEUROSOME

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications (M36)

AD6.6 (AWP Y1) Inventory of existing HIA, exposure and exposure-effect data for chemicals prioritised in PARC (M12)

Partners List:

ANSES (FR); AUTH (EL); BPI (EL); DTU (DK); ENSP (PT); FMUL (PT); IISPV (ES); INSA (PT); KI (SE); NIPH (NO); OI (SI); SRU (NL); Sciensano (BE); STAMI (NO); UU-IRAS (NL); VITO (BE)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2025 (M42)

Costs:

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 28 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 3 875 €

P6.2.4.d_Y1_HIAIndicators_VITO

Project Title	Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	HIAIndicators		
Project Manager	Jurgen Buekers	VITO	BE
Deputy Project manager	Jelle Vlaanderen	UU-IRAS	NL
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	42*
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.4
Project Id	P6.2.4.d_Y1_HIAIndicators_VITO		

* The project has been broken at mid-term (M42) to assess what has been achieved at the mid-term and if

the review is positive then a new project could be launched for the period M43-M81.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Indicators related to exposure, risk and health impact of chemical exposure support national and European policy makers and can complement and support monitoring frameworks for e.g., the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability (CSS), the Zero Pollution Action Plan (ZPAP), and the 8th Environment Action Programme (EAP).

The suitability of one indicator over another depends on the policy questions that need to be answered, the availability and quality of data, the uncertainties of each indicator, and on the availability of resources and expertise. Indicators applying generally to detrimental effects of chemicals range from attributable cases to DALYs/QALYs and external costs. When insufficient data for health impact analysis are available, exceedance of health-based guidance values (RCR, MOE, ..) can be used to indicate which part of the population is exposed to levels above such guidance values as a measure of potential health impact.

This project is part of four interrelated projects on health impact assessment and will interact with the three other projects: ‘Collection and generation of data for HIA of PARC priority chemicals’, ‘Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies’, and ‘Case studies on health impact assessment’. The case studies (6.2.4.c) form the central starting point to which other projects (6.2.4.a data availability, 6.2.4.b methodologies, 6.2.4.d indicators) are linked (see **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.1**).

Main expected outputs of the project

An inventory of different types of existing exposure, risk and health impact indicators for exposure to chemical (single, combined, aggregated, ..) will be made, followed by a proposal for development of (complementary) indicators based on PARC data and results (including outcomes of the T6.2 projects on data availability and methodological improvements). A selection of indicators integrating dynamic exposure and hazard data and accounting for variability in the population and for uncertainties will be developed in subsequent years, to assess the health impact of specific exposure scenarios (including between- and within-person variance estimates, and dynamics of population exposure and health risk via combining monitoring data with exposure trends as a function of specific socio-economic parameters that condition the level of population exposure per route and pathway). A link will be made with current policies to support policymakers.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Risk assessment (RA), Environmental Burden of Disease (EBD) calculations, health impact assessment (HIA), and (social) cost benefit analyses ((S)CBA) inform stakeholders and policymakers to help protect and eventually improve human health. The EU Green Deal, in particular the Zero Pollution Ambition policy, in which the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability is a cornerstone, aims at reducing the planetary health impact from chemical exposures. EBD, HIA and SCBA allow to objectify the impact of current chemical exposure on health in EU populations, prioritize preventive or mitigatory actions to be taken, and estimate the environmental burden of disease and costs avoided as a result of EU policies and regulations. Indicators related to health impact of PARC priority substances can be developed to support policymakers. Similar kind of indicators were developed for HBM4EU focusing on risk assessment

<https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/15/10/2085> ,

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1438463923000020?via%3Dihub> and

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36434900/>.

Key words: Environmental Burden of Disease (EBD), health impact assessment (HIA), indicators

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

OO3: Prioritization and selection of indicators to be developed during the course of PARC is part of this project.

OO4: Development of exposure, risk, health impact and cost indicators will increase the understanding of the contribution of chemicals as upstream determinants of diseases and support policy makers in the

reduction of environmental and human health impact of exposure to hazardous chemicals and as such in the improvement of the protection of environmental and citizen's health.

OO5: Information exchange and collaborations with other networks and initiatives in the area of EBD and HIA will be established.

OO6: Development of indicators will support communication to citizens and increase their awareness about risks of chemical exposures.

OO7: Prioritization and selection of case studies will be a recurring activity to develop annual working plans during the course of PARC.

OO9: Calculation and visualization tools for risk and health impact assessment may be developed in a later stage in this project.

OO10: As the project will use data that are generated outside PARC and by other PARC projects, and will generate data that can be used by other activities in and outside of PARC, implementation of FAIR data practices is a prerequisite.

OO13: Indicator development applied in this project may be disseminated inside and outside of PARC via training and exchange initiatives.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- Cooperation with T1.3 for the Partnership monitoring framework, WP2 for prioritization and policy uptake, and WP3 for communication
- Exchange of data and computation and visualization tools in collaboration with WP7 and Task 8.3.
- Projects inside PARC:
 - P6.2.4.a: Collection and generation of data for HIA of PARC priority chemicals
 - P6.2.4.b: Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies
 - P6.2.4.c: Case studies on health impact assessment

Links outside PARC:

Exchanges with stakeholders such as JRC and EEA are ongoing to align the PARC activities with development of an indicator framework for the EC Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, among others.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications (M36)

Partners List:

ANSES (FR); AUTH (EL); ENSP (PT); FMUL (PT); INSA (PT); IVL (SE); MU (CZ); NIJZ (SI); OI (SI); Sciensano (BE); UU-IRAS (NL); VITO (BE); WR-BIOM (NL)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2025 (M42)

Costs:

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 20 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 937 €

T6.3 Review of risk assessment methodologies - 3 PROJECTS

Review of current regulatory RA methodologies within and across relevant chemical sectors will be performed through a series of case studies. Effectiveness of the methodologies will be reviewed. The case studies will provide science-based support for method development, identify R&I needs as well as suggest improvements and harmonisation opportunities. For the first years, the case studies will focus on two areas: substance and effect specific reviews and use of tools, criteria, and methods. Thereafter the focus areas will be evaluated, and either be further analysed through additional case studies or, if relevant, replaced with new focus areas. Final conclusions and recommendations based on the case studies performed will be

generated, also considering the EU-wide relevance.

A6.3.1 Substance and effect specific reviewers – 2 PROJECTS

P6.3.1.a_Y1_SubstanceRA_SU

Project Title	Review of substance-specific risk assessment		
Project	SubstanceRA		
Acronym (15 letters max)			
Project Manager	Marlene Ågerstrand Marlene.agerstrand@aces.su.se	Stockholm University	Sweden
Deputy Project manager	Olwenn Martin olwenn.martin@ucl.ac.uk	University College London	United Kingdom
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	48
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.3.1
Project Id	P6.3.1.a_Y1_SubstanceRA_SU		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

There is a significant number of EU legislations in force that deal with chemicals directly or indirectly. These rules have been developed at different points in time and for different purposes. Attempts have been made to harmonize and streamline different parts of the regulatory system. Nevertheless, the regulatory system for risk assessment is still scattered across different laws and agencies, and between EU and national levels. This has led to a situation where there are inconsistencies between the different regulatory frameworks. Meeting the concerns about inconsistencies and inefficiency requires a move towards a more holistic approach. This is in line with the foreseen development towards a One Substance One Assessment approach. The [Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability](#) sets the objective to move towards ‘one substance, one assessment’ approach by improving efficiency, effectiveness, coherence and transparency of the delivery of safety assessments of chemicals across all relevant legislation.

Case studies will be performed to review substance-specific assessments to understand the differences and similarities based on intended use, and subsequent implications, across legislations. The case studies will evaluate opportunities for improving particular aspects of the risk assessment of chemicals. This will include aspects such as data availability and/or data sharing mechanisms, methodologies for hazard and exposure assessment, and assessment of the effectiveness of potential mitigation measures considering the impact on the environment and safety of the consumer.

The project currently contains case studies on coordination needs towards a ‘one substance one assessment’ approach looking at specific substances (case study CS12_MethodOSOA_SU), plastic additives (case study CS13_PlasticizersRA_UCL), and substances with biocidal properties (case study CS14_BiocidesRA_SU).

Main expected outputs of the project

An analysis of how to contribute to the harmonization or consolidation of requirements, guidance, and practices, and move towards a ‘one substance – one assessment’ approach in the EU.

Mapping of relevant legislation linking to functions of additives in specific polymers for various intended use, including a report describing current regulatory processes in relevant legislation, analysing commonalities and differences and justification thereof, as well as barriers and opportunities for harmonisation, and recommendations for policymakers.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The outcomes of this project may serve as a ground for adjustments of the relevant regulations. The identification of dissimilarities in testing requirements and hazard assessments of substances depending on specific uses will offer valuable information for the implementation and potential impacts of the One Substance One Assessment approach on regulations targeting specific uses of chemicals. Further, the potential barriers and opportunities, and available methods, for harmonisation in a systematic way will be presented. The analysis of the justification for risk management measures will reveal implicit or explicit value judgment that may inform the development and refinement of the essential use criteria.

Keywords: One Substance One Assessment, harmonisation, biocides, plastic, polymer, additives, essential use, circularity

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

The project will mainly contribute to the PARC operational objectives OO4, OO7, and OO9 by generating knowledge on substance-specific RAs performed across regulatory frameworks and thus informing and supporting the development and use of new risk assessment approaches and methods, regulatory processes, and policy developments (OO4, OO7). The project will be performed in close collaboration with authorities and agencies to promote and facilitate the uptake of the results in RA and regulatory contexts and will provide input to the design and implementation of projects in other Tasks and WPs related to the regulations and aspects reviewed (OO4, OO9).

The project will also contribute to the PARC operational objectives by providing input to priority-setting (OO3), cooperate with other relevant R&I initiatives (OO5), communicate and disseminate results (OO6), implement FAIR data practices to enable open science (OO10), provide input to innovative concepts for RA (OO12), and share the results and experiences through training (OO13).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

WP2: Prioritizations of chemical substances.

WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness: Various initiatives related to the issue of additives in polymers may be underway in European institutions such as the Commission, EFSA or JRC. Being alert to such developments, particularly if they are not widely advertised by responsible institutions could avoid the duplication of efforts or identification of synergies.

WP6: Potential interactions identified within WP6 that need to be explored further; Project 6.2.1.a Source-to-dose models, Activity 6.4.3 Comprehensive review and application of databases in materials.

WP7: Data management plan

WP8: Can inform case use studies for SSbD criteria (task 8.1).

Links outside PARC:

Work currently undertaken under the auspices of the Food Packaging Forum may potentially be of interest, specifically the FCCMigex database (<https://www.foodpackagingforum.org/fccmigex>) or other tools available from <https://www.plastiverse.org/tools>. The project will also take note of the Plastic additives initiative by ECHA 2016-2018 (Plastic additives initiative - ECHA (europa.eu)).

Linked to activities within the OECD WPHA project *Tools and good practices to improve the use of academic data in regulatory assessments*, led by JRC and DG Environment within the working group One Substance One Assessment.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes:

Deliverable 6.6 ‘1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M42.

Deliverable 6.17 ‘2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M81.

Milestone 13 ‘Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget’ due M42.

Partners List:

SU (SE), UCL (UK), Sciensano (BE), IRFM (IT), KI (SE)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Cost:

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 26 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 1600 €

P6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI

Project Title	Review of effect-specific risk assessment		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	EffectRA		
Project Manager	Dimitra Nikolopoulou d.nikolopoulou@bpi.gr	BPI	Greece
Deputy Project manager	Emma Westerholm Emma.Westerholm@kemi.se	KEMI	SE
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.3.1
Project Id	P.6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Chemical risk assessments are currently performed under various regulatory frameworks and at different points in time by responsible EU agencies, scientific committees, expert groups, or Commission departments. The European Green Deal and Commission Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (COM(2020) 667 final, Brussels, 14.10.2020) highlight the need for innovation in regulatory risk assessment to rapidly and effectively identify chemicals with hazardous properties for human health and the environment through a simpler “one substance one assessment” process. The project will be implemented through case studies reviewing risk assessment methodology concerning specific endpoints that are highlighted as priority in the EC Chemicals Strategy. Currently, this includes endocrine disruption (case studies CS10_ED-cosmetics_VUB, CS17_ED-in vitro_BPI CS18_ED-classes_BPI), skin sensitisation (case study CS9_SKINSENSIRISK_REGIONH), genotoxicity and carcinogenicity (case study CS11_GenotoxCarc_ISS), and developmental neurotoxicity (case study CS15_DNT_SU).

The case studies will review current regulatory practices across regulatory areas in EU. The goal is to evaluate and suggest opportunities for improving and harmonising particular aspects of risk assessment methodology, including bridging legislative inconsistencies.

Over the past few years, chemicals with endocrine disrupting (ED) properties have been identified under different regulatory frameworks, including Regulation (EC) 1107/2009 (Plant protection Products Regulation, PPPR), Regulation (EU) 528/2012 (Biocides Products Regulation, BPR), Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 (REACH) and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 (Cosmetic Products Regulation, CPR). Whilst all of these pieces of legislation endorse the WHO/IPCS (2002)⁴ definition for an endocrine disruptor, different methodology and approaches are followed for ED assessments of chemicals. The EFSA/ECHA Guidance for the identification of endocrine disruptors in the context of Regulations (EU) No 528/2012 and (EC) No 1107/2009⁵ has been endorsed⁶ to provide harmonised scientific criteria for the identification of pesticides with ED properties but not for chemicals regulated under REACH or the CPR. Moreover, the use of experimental animals for safety assessment is fully prohibited under CPR since March 2013. The new hazard classes on ED properties are expected to substantially contribute to harmonization in the identification of ED chemicals across EU.

Skin sensitization is a systemic repeat dose toxicity caused by chemicals leading to permanent changes in the immune system and potentially chronic skin disease in case exposure continues. At least 25% of the European adult population are sensitized to one or more chemicals from consumer products and/or exposures in the work environment. Skin sensitization may lead to permanent skin disease, affect quality of life, and impair work ability. The economic expenses on a European level in considerable, alone skin sensitization due to fragrance ingredients are estimated to cost 11 -16 billion Euro/year.

Genotoxicity and carcinogenicity are essential components of human health safety assessment. Although various EU and international regulations are open to the use of approaches different from standard toxicology tests on animals, such as *in vitro* short-term tests and structure-activity based methodologies, today's alternative strategies generally rely on paradigms that fail to detect the full spectrum of genotoxic and carcinogenic chemicals.

An additional case will evaluate conclusions drawn in guideline-compliant developmental neurotoxicity (DNT) studies considered under different legislative frameworks for regulation of plant protection products, biocides, food contact materials and chemicals under REACH, depending on data availability.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Development of specific criteria for evaluation of non-validated *in vitro* methods to facilitate ED assessments across regulatory frameworks ; identification of methodological differences in the assessment of substances with ED activity among legislative frameworks on cosmetics and on other chemicals; development of guidance on the added value of NAMs in classification of chemicals for endocrine disrupting properties under the new CLP criteria and for shifting away from animal testing through a WoE approach.
- Evaluation of the performance and efficacy of current legislation on skin sensitisation assessment, including practices for mixtures of skin sensitizers; identification of knowledge gaps and suggestions for improvements in risk assessment.
- Development of protocols and recommendations summarising the main directions for increasing the regulatory acceptance of QSAR-related methodologies in genotoxicity and carcinogenicity risk assessment.
- Advance the understanding of overall compliance in guideline DNT studies.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project aims to assist Member State Regulatory Authorities, EU agencies, Scientific Committees, Expert Groups, relevant Commission Departments and the Industry in adopting harmonised risk assessment methodologies on selected human health effects:

- Contribute to a harmonized way of using existing and emerging NAMs for risk assessment of compounds with potential ED concerns.
- Remove current bottlenecks regarding acceptance of non-validated *in vitro* ED test methods; provide confidence in risk assessors and consistency in the assessment of data from non-validated ED test methods for use in WoE assessment.
- Contribute to the harmonized implementation of the new CLP criteria on hazard classes for endocrine disruption taking into consideration all available methods and tools.
- Contribute to the development of harmonised risk assessment methodology on skin sensitisation.
- Identify the most relevant gaps and inconsistencies in current legislation for genotoxicity and carcinogenicity risk assessment, highlighting potential of improvement and harmonization.
- Support the integration of information from different sources (e.g., NAMs, AOPs) identifying their best placement into genotoxicity and carcinogenicity risk assessment detailing and addressing the underlying uncertainties.
- Identify areas where further development of legislation or regulatory practice is needed regarding the performance of DNT studies highlighting potential of improvement and harmonization to ensure a high level of protection for human health.

Key words: risk assessment; endocrine; *in vitro*; skin sensitization; (Q)SAR; genotoxicity, carcinogenicity, DNT, reliability, relevance, NAMs

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

The project will mainly contribute to the PARC operational objectives OO4, OO7, and OO9 by reviewing current methodology for chemical risk assessment across different regulatory frameworks with focus on specific priority endpoints, i.e., endocrine disruption, skin sensitisation, genotoxicity and carcinogenicity and skin sensitisation. The project aims to identify knowledge gaps and areas where harmonisation is mostly needed and provide recommendations for increasing regulatory acceptance of NAMs in chemicals risk assessment (OO4, OO7). This outcome is expected to provide input to related projects on the use of NAMs and IATA development towards the transition to next generation risk assessment (OO7, OO9). Identification of potential limitations in the use of NAMs is expected to inspire the design of new projects and case studies under different WPs within PARC (OO4, OO9). Collaboration with regulatory agencies and authorities is expected to promote and facilitate the uptake of results in the regulatory context (OO4, OO9).

The project will also contribute to the PARC operational objectives by providing input to priority-setting (OO3), cooperate with other relevant R&I initiatives (OO5), communicate and disseminate results (OO6), implement FAIR data practices to enable open science (OO10), provide input to innovative concepts for risk assessment (OO12), and share the results and experiences through training (OO13).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

The following links of this project to other PARC activities are identified:

- WP2: Contribute to priorities as defined in WP2 to meet the European Commission’s Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability Towards a Toxic-Free Environment; contribute to the link between research and regulatory science.
- WP3: Foster synergies and collaborations with other projects at national, EU and international level.
- WP5: Provide feedback on assessment criteria of *in vitro* studies available in the open literature that could be used to assist identification of regulatory gaps for priority compound testing; DNT activities.
- WP5/Task 5.3: Assist the development of new AOP(s) for non-genotoxic carcinogenesis.
- WP6/Task 6.1: Provide feedback for the evaluation of *in vitro* studies for use in IATAs development on EDs and assist the development of quantitative networks of AOPs and IATA for genotoxicity.
- WP6/Task 6.4/Project 6.4.1: Provide feedback on the additive or synergistic effects of mixtures of skin sensitisers.
- WP6/Task 6.4/Project 6.4.2: Developing and fostering the uptake of innovative, effective and protective regulatory approaches.
- WP7: Align with data management plan
- WP9: Scheduled training activities

Links outside PARC:

- Endocrine Disruption: Links with the EURION cluster, the work performed by the OECD Performance Based Test Guidelines (OECD PBTG), the OECD IATA Case Study Project, the ABU Project, Better use of academic data (CSS), the activities of the CARACAL Subgroup on Endocrine Disruptors (CASG ED), one-substance one-assessment.
- Skin sensitisation: Collaboration with University of Copenhagen on immune reactions to skin sensitizers, ongoing activities in France, Germany and Ireland on the potential need for regulatory action on skin sensitisers in consumer mixtures, workshop in Brussels on Application of the EU Cosmetics Regulation and relevant OSH Directives for the safe use of cosmetic products (25/10/2022), workshop in Basel on model development for quantitative risk assessment for skin sensitising pesticides (August 2022) by the State Secretariat for Economic Affairs (SECO) - Chemicals and Occupational Health, and the Swiss Centre for Applied Human Toxicology together with an international scientific organising committee.
- Genotoxicity and carcinogenicity: Links with OECD (Chemicals and Biotechnology Committee (OECD / EHS Prog.), QSAR Assessment Framework project, IATA case studies project, QSAR Toolbox

Management Group, Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics EAGMST (AOP Programme), WG on revision of Genotoxicity Test Guidelines); ECHA (Member State Committee (MSC), Committee for Risk Assessment (RAC), Risk Management and Evaluation (RiME+) platform, Competent Authorities for REACH and CLP (CARACAL)); and EFSA (Expert Panel on Food Additives and Flavouring (FAF), Working Group on Genotoxicity of the Scientific Committee, Working Group on Technological Additives of the Expert Panel on Feed Additives and Products (FEEDAP), and working groups on genotoxicity and toxicology).

- Developmental neurotoxicity: Links with EFSA, ECHA, EU Commission.

Linked to activities within the OECD WPHA project *Tools and good practices to improve the use of academic data in regulatory assessments*, led by JRC and DG Environment within the working group One Substance One Assessment.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

Findings of the project will feed into the following PARC deliverables and milestones:

- Deliverable 6.6 ‘1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M42
- Deliverable 6.17 ‘2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M81
- Milestone 13 ‘Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget’ due M42

Partners List:

REGIONH (DK), STAMI (NO), SU (SE), IRFMN (IT), UNIBAS (CH), VUB (BE), BPI (EL), KI (SE), INSERM (FR), INERIS (FR), EAA (AT), ISS (IT), NILU (NO), INSA (PT), UBA (DE), INRAE (FR)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Cost:

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 49 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 31 400 €

A6.3.2 Use of tools, criteria, and methods – 1 PROJECT

P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU

Project Title	Review of tools, criteria, and methods used in risk assessment		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	ToolsRA		
Project Manager	Jussi Reinikainen jussi.reinikainen@syke.fi	Finnish Environment Institute, SYKE	Finland
Deputy Project manager	Marlene Ågerstrand Marlene.agerstrand@aces.su.se	Stockholm University, SU	Sweden
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.3.2
Project Id	P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project:

The European Green Deal and the Initiative on the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability set as a priority for the next generation chemical safety assessments the development and implementation of the ‘one substance – one assessment’ process. This project aims at reviewing current risk assessment practices, including tools, criteria and methods currently used within and across regulatory frameworks, assessing the

level of protection to human health and the environment and making suggestions from improvements in the broader context of ‘one substance one assessment’.

This project will review the processes as well as the use of tools, criteria and methods, both within and across legislations, in order to promote more transparent and consistent evaluation of scientific information and data. The case studies will cover issues such as risk assessment methodologies, test requirements, effectiveness towards risk reduction, sources of uncertainty as well as methodological challenges in implementing uncertainty analysis and bridging of data gaps in risk assessment. Case studies related to the specific areas of environmental and occupational risk assessment have also been developed. Other specific areas in regulatory risk assessment may additionally be identified during the course of PARC.

The project currently contains case studies on comparative analysis of risk-based decision benchmarks (CS1_CARB_SYKE), identification and review of methods for evaluating the effectiveness of risk assessment for reducing risk (CS2_RiskReduction_SU), holistic overview and agreements on strategic regulatory needs for a sustainable chemical control (CS6_SusChemControl_MUI (this case study will not continue in Y2)) practical challenges in using quantitative expressions of uncertainty in assessment (CS16_UncertaintyRA_ULUND), the status of chemical data gap filling approaches (CS19_DataGapFilling_KEMI-DTU, case study starting year 2) and understanding the implementation and use of NAMs in pesticide dossiers in both the HH and the environment CS20_PESTNAM_ISS (new case study added year 3).

With regard to environmental risk assessment, two case studies are currently included on protecting the same ecosystem under different regulations (case study CS7_REGPREP_EAWAG) and secondary poisoning and protection of wildlife (case study CS4_SecPoisoning_INERIS).

With regard to occupational risk assessment, two case studies are currently included on occupational exposures to reproductive and developmental toxicants (case study CS8_OccupReproDev_KI) and workplace chemical risk assessment (case study CS3_WorkplaceRA_TTL).

Main expected outputs of the project:

- Identify inconsistencies, loopholes and gaps in the current chemical risk assessment frameworks.
- Contribute to an increased understanding of how to measure the effectiveness of risk assessment aimed at reducing risk.
- An overview of options beyond AOP, NAM and IATA development for a sustainable regulation of chemicals.
- A general introduction to uncertainty analysis for risk assessment in a PARC context.
- A systematic overview of currently used and state-of-the-art chemical data gap-filling approaches applied across EU legislations
- A review on the current PPP environmental risk assessments under different regulations.
- Practices for properly assessing the risk of secondary poisoning under different regulatory schemes.
- Comparison of coverage of known reproductive toxicants by OELs and DNELs.
- Evaluation of how regulatory information provided under different regulatory processes is utilized in workplace chemical risk assessment and risk mitigation in practice.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders:

The project will guide the future design of legislation on chemical risk assessment, focusing on sustainable management of chemical risks, as well as the implementation of the “One substance – One assessment” approach. The project will provide regulators, legislators and other stakeholders an in-depth understanding of the commonly used decision benchmarks and the significance of their appropriate foundation and application. The project will provide options for sustainable chemical control beyond NAM, AOP, and IATA development, including possible approaches for the assessment of non-chemical alternatives to chemical biocides and pesticides. The project will provide new knowledge about the practical challenges in using quantitative expressions of uncertainty in assessment, as well as pedagogical examples on how to implement quantitative expressions of uncertainty and the benefit of these in assessment and communication. The project will provide recommendations for harmonizing data gap-filling approaches in

relevant EU legislations, which will have an impact on the practices of filling data gaps during compliance reporting, monitoring and assessment by companies, scientists, and policymakers alike.

Keywords: data gaps, uncertainty, sustainable chemical control, effectiveness, comparative analysis, reference value, environmental risk assessment, OSOA, secondary poisoning, occupational exposure.

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

This project will contribute towards the WP6.3 objective to “map and evaluate current methodologies employed in regulatory risk assessment to identify gaps and needs in methodological knowledge”.

The project will contribute to PARC objective OO4 ‘Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge. Based on the priorities, PARC will deliver results relevant to support the use of new approaches and methods, fill data gaps and reduce uncertainty in risk assessment.’

The project will contribute to the PARC main objective ‘Drive innovation in regulatory RA by strengthening its scientific basis, with the implementation of NGRA as the ultimate goal’ by strengthening the implementation of uncertainty analysis in NGRA.

The project will moreover contribute to PARC objective OO9 ‘Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA’ by proposing recommendations that are harmonized across EU policies.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project has potential synergies with several other WPs, tasks, activities or projects that address holistic approaches to risk assessment. Plans for concrete cooperation will be specified during the study regarding other projects in WP6 as well as potential interactions at the task level e.g., with WP2, WP7 and WP3.

- WP2: This work will support the objective of 6.3 to contribute to priorities as defined in WP2 to meet the European Commission’s Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability Towards a Toxic-Free Environment.
- WP3: Interaction with WP3 foreseen to clarify how to best communicate on recommendations for regulatory action and for aspects related to risk communication.
- WP4/Task 4.2: “Case study on Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals (EDCs)”. One of the aims of the project are to promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity by ensuring that the environmental and multisource monitoring is designed based on complete and up-to-date information, answering the identified regulatory needs. EDCs will include a variety of different classes of chemicals, among which pesticides. Besides, it will allow for the comparison of chemical approaches, such as in prospective assessment, with effects actually found in the field using effect-based tools. Exchange will be ensured through a common research partner (INERIS, EAWAG).
- WP4: This work will be linked to WP4 for the collection of monitoring data in wildlife and their possible use in secondary poisoning assessment.
- WP5: This project could provide feedback on the need of input data for ecotoxicity studies and models to be used for SP assessment.
- WP6/Task 6.2: The project will provide feedback for the need of models for a better understanding of exposure kinetics.
- WP6/Task 6.4: uptake of the outcome of the project in Regulatory frameworks
- WP7: the project will feed into the work of WP7, specifically task 7.3 which targets the development and implementation of innovative data analytical approaches from the computational, statistical, and mathematical fields, including quantification of the uncertainties and propagation of these uncertainties when combining different sets of data. This case study is a retrospective analysis of practitioners’ experience, which make the findings valuable for the work under task 7.3 which approaches the issue of uncertainty analysis from a more normative and methodological perspective. Data related to data gap-filling methods across relevant EU legislations will be collected and generated in the present project, which will be included in the data management plan of PARC under WP7.

- WP8: The project will connect to and explore synergies with 8.1 Safe and sustainable by design (SSbD). Toolbox requirements of the PARC model network developed under WP8 will be explored to clarify how the harmonization of data gap-filling approaches across modelling, monitoring and assessment tools can consistently contribute to a strong and reliable PARC toolbox.

Links outside PARC

The project may contribute to other EU regulations and policy frameworks (i.e., those not currently or directly embedded in our project plan), such as the EU's Soil Strategy, Circular Economy and Zero Pollution Action Plans, and the EFSA-funded projects RACEMiC (RA of Combined Exposure to Multiple Chemicals) and PERA (Building a European Partnership for next generation, systems-based Environmental Risk Assessment).

The Austrian Green Chemicals Platform (<https://www.grünechemieösterreich.at/>).

The project will harvest synergies with UNEP SAICM and with Mistra SafeChem.

- Protecting the same ecosystem under different regulations: Implemented by risk assessors with a broad network regarding EU environmental risk assessment, the following list is a non-exhaustive list of their fields of collaborations and involvements: WG chemicals under the WFD. PPR panel under 1107/2009 EFSA project PERA. Premier project on improving pharmaceutical risk assessment, Norman Network (ecotoxicology database), EEA project on soil risk assessment.
- Secondary poisoning and protection of wildlife: This project will be complementary to EU and national activities regarding monitoring in biota, as a regular task under WFD, but also for the interpretation of biota level in wildlife. The project will also be linked to the Horizon project PROMISCES, in the interpretation of the risks due to the promotion of the circularity of natural resources (water, soil) during life cycle of chemicals. The project will also grounds on the EU LIFE VERMEER (Life Vermeer – Integrating VEGA, toxRead, MERLIN-Expo and ERICA in A Platform for Risk Assessment and Substitution of Risky Substance (life-vermeer.eu) for the use of the SPHERA Tools and models.
- Occupational exposures to reproductive and developmental toxicants: Partners closely connected to various OSH-stakeholders, expert group members and active researchers.

Linked to activities within the OECD WPHA project *Tools and good practices to improve the use of academic data in regulatory assessments*, led by JRC and DG Environment within the working group One Substance One Assessment.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

- Deliverable 6.6 '1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies' due M42
- Deliverable 6.17 '2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies' due M81
- Milestone 13 'Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget' due M42

Partners List:

SYKE (FI); ISSeP (BE); SU (SE); UBA (DE); STAMI (NO); UCL (UK); JSI (SI); MUI (AT); KEMI (SE); ULUND (SE); KI (SE); BPI (EL); DTU (DK); UCPH (DK); Eawag (CH); FOEN (CH); INERIS (FR); TTL (FI), LSMU (LT); RSU (LV), ISS (IT), UMIL(IT), UNIPD (IT).

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Cost:

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 55 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 25 600 €

T6.4 Transposing results to regulatory risk assessment methodologies 13 PROJECTS

This task will support regulatory processes for reducing risks to humans and the environment by undertaking scenario-based case-studies resulting in guidance documents and/or recommendations. First, in coordination with ongoing EC activities, a European framework for the regulatory assessment of

mixtures encompassing all relevant chemical classes, exposure scenarios and protection goals will be developed. It will evaluate the availability and quality of data for regulatory assessment, analyse the additional risk caused by mixtures and its implications. The second activity aims to promote and facilitate the regulatory acceptance and practical use of NAMs in RA across different chemical sectors. Focus will be put on real-life situations and application contexts encountered by risk assessors. Long-term objectives include the definition of harmonised scientific criteria for acceptance of NAMs across regulations and of an evidence-based framework to ensure systematic, transparent, and reproducible application of NAMs in RA. Next, we will develop and apply tools and databases that enable a systematic identification of priority substances in products and materials. In doing so, the activity will promote a more effective and harmonised enforcement of legislation, support informed substitution of problematic chemicals in products and materials and inform how sustainability assessments can be achieved with respect to chemicals.

T 6.4 Transposing results to risk assessment methodologies

Develop and foster the uptake of innovative, efficient and protective regulatory risk assessment and management approaches and methodologies.

Fig 12: W6.3: Risk assessment methodologies

A6.4.1 Develop regulatory relevant approaches and methods for chemical mixtures – 3 PROJECTS

P6.4.1.a_Y1_OPREMIXCS1_BRUNEL_UGot

Project Title	Optimizing regulatory risk assessment and management of chemical mixtures in Europe		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	OPREMIX		
Project Manager	Thomas Backhaus thomas.backhaus@gu.se	University of Gothenburg	Sweden
Deputy Project manager	Andreas Kortenkamp andreas.kortenkamp@brunel.ac.uk	Brunel University London	UK
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	40*
PARC (Month number)		PARC	6.4.1.
PARC Workpackage number	6	Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	
Project Id	P6.4.1.a_Y1_OPREMIXCS1_BRUNEL_UGot		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M40

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

This project has its focus on the current approaches related to the management of mixtures across regulatory areas as e.g., REACH, CLP, Pesticides and Biocides, cosmetics, food contact material, pharmaceuticals. Further regulation on food and drinking water as well as on environmental media and emission will be considered. It will also explore the use of the MAF approach for the assessment and management of mixtures across regulatory areas and uses (beyond REACH) and compare it to other mixture approaches. This project will address the question if and under which circumstances a MAF is applicable or not and how different are the conclusion drawn by different mixture approaches when challenged with real word data sets and if there are differences to what extend would the MAF approach might provide biased results. Case studies will be used from the human and ecotoxicological arenas to attempt data-driven sizings of MAFs.

This project is highly relevant for supporting the improvement of the regulatory management of mixtures across chemicals legislation and areas of use, regarding human health and the environment. It will address the overall objectives of activity 6.4.1 “*Develop regulatory and legally accepted risk assessment and management approaches and methods for chemical mixtures*”, while specifically focusing on and comparing the methods and tools currently used for the regulatory assessment and management and providing guidance for further development.

Main expected outputs of the project

A systematic comparative evaluation of current mixture tools (and those that are currently under development or might be developed within PARC). The mixture tools will be compared regarding their practicability, effectiveness and efficiency, level of protection, feasibility, applications domain and data demands. Particular focus will be on developing case studies for the comparative evaluation of the Mixture Assessment Factor (MAF). As far as feasible, the project will provide direct input and feedback to ongoing regulatory action, such as the revision of REACH or the Water Framework Directive.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project will provide the input to develop a “European cookbook” of mixture tools that describes the application domain for each tool, its data demands, protectiveness, feasibility and reliability, in the view of the different demands from regulators, industries and civil society.

Key words: mixtures, MAF, Mixture tools, European cookbook of mixtures.

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project respond to the PARC operational objectives OO4: Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge, OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives, OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA, OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake and OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC’s results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA.

Chemical mixtures were one of the highest scored topics in the first round of prioritisation within PARC, and this project will support in particular Objectives 9 and 12. The practical experiences with handling heterogeneous datasets of complex mixtures will also feed into Objective 10. The project focuses on comparing existing methods of mixture risk assessment with the Mixture Assessment Factor, which is to be implemented for industrial chemicals (REACH), as requested by the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness: a cooperation for the foreseen survey would be of value, especially in distributing it to risk assessor

WP7: Data management plan

WP9: Training, laboratory network

Other WPs: The project will primarily link to and exchange findings and input with project P6.4.1.b_Y1_CS2_UFZ (Dealing with unknown mixtures in regulatory risk assessment through the use of monitoring data and NAMs). Findings from WP 4 and WP5 regarding monitoring data and toxicity data will be considered in this Project. Further, there will probably be links to and exchange with 6.2.3 on issues related to human real-life exposure and modelling of exposure. In WP6.2 mixtures will be approached from a research science perspective with the focus on modelling, human health and dietary exposure. Relevant findings of Task 6.2 will be considered in this project for sizing one or more MAFs.

Links outside PARC

There are several currently ongoing research and policy development activities on mixtures in the EU. Under Horizon 2020, the so-called Green Deal Call includes a call dedicated to mixture toxicity, with a certain focus on aquatic environment and the occurrence of pharmaceutical residues in unintentional mixtures. There are also ongoing and planned mixture related activities related to the remits of EFSA (e.g., food safety and pesticides), e.g., regarding the further development of the Cumulative Assessment Groups (CAGs), primarily for the assessment of mixtures of pesticide residues in food. Further, the European Commission will conduct an impact assessment of the introduction of a MAF or MAFs under REACH.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.17: Optimizing regulatory risk assessment and management of chemical mixtures in Europe (M40)

D6.18: Final report on risk assessment and management methods for chemical mixtures across legislations (M81)

Partners List: UGOT (SE), BUL (UK), AGES (AT), UBA (DE), BPI (EL), UI (IS), NIVA (NO), ENSP (PT), EAWAG (CH), KEMI (SE), UK Env. Agency (UK), STAMI (NO), NIOM (PL), UAVR (PT), NLZOH (SI), UK-CEH (UK), LSMU (LT).

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/08/2025 (M40)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 63 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 18 431 €

P6.4.1.b_Y1_MONAMMIXCS2_UFZ

Project Title	Dealing with unknown mixtures in regulatory risk assessments through the use of monitoring data and NAMs		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	MONAMMIX		
Project Manager	Wibke Busch wibke.busch@ufz.de	Helmholtz Environmental Research center (UFZ)	Germany
Deputy Project manager	Enken Hassold Enken.Hassold@uba.de	German Environment Agency (UBA)	Germany
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	40*
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.1
Project Id	P6.4.1.b_Y1_MONAMMIX CS2_UFZ		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M40

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The project is highly relevant for supporting the improvement of the regulatory management of mixtures across chemicals legislation and areas of use, regarding human health and the environment by bridging data gaps. It will address the overall objectives of activity 6.4.1 “*Develop regulatory and legally accepted risk assessment and management approaches and methods for chemical mixtures*” and strives to link prospective mixture assessment methods with monitoring and AOP knowledge. In particular, it is focusing on case studies on environmental monitoring under EU directives such as WFD, (Directive 2000/60/EC), Sustainable Use of PPPs Directive 2009/128/EC) and human biomonitoring initiatives such as HBM4EU or the cohort studies within the European Exposome Network. In this project the use of new approach methods (NAMs) i.e. bioanalytical methods for untargeted exposure detection and hazard identification in conjunction with chemical screening data, to deal with unknown mixtures will be compared with mixture risk assessment methods relying on component-based standard toxicity information.

In this project we will address the following research question:

- How can data from NAMs be used to provide more comprehensive pictures of the chemical exposure that needs to be addressed in chemical risk assessment?
- How could available bioanalytical methodology and information from environmental monitoring contribute to mixture risk assessment?
- Are AOP networks a way to overcome data gaps and account for compounds mixture contributions?
- Can priority mixtures be defined with the application of non-target methods?
- Can NAMs complement component-based mixture risk assessment?

Main expected outputs of the project

The availability of empirically based support data from established monitoring efforts on human health and environmental quality, as well as adverse outcome pathway knowledge compiled under OECD efforts, will be important for developing the assessment and management of mixtures in several ways. It will for example be crucial to argue the size of a mixture assessment factor (MAF) as currently proposed under REACH, to define common assessment groups as currently under development at EFSA, or to aggregate exposures of single substances and combined exposures of mixtures in the respective regulations as well as across regulatory silos. Identified priority mixtures containing chemicals recently assessed or regulated by different regulatory authorities will be provided to provide support in these respects, while providing additional options for tiered mixture assessment strategies, e.g. in the frame of the European Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC) for environmental mixture exposures, or the European Drinking Water Directive (2020/2184) for mixtures humans are exposed to.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

To advance the regulatory assessment and management of unintentional mixtures additional approaches are needed which are practicable in a regulatory context and capable of dealing with data constraints. It can be foreseen that monitoring information based on non-target chemical and bioanalytical methods will be utilized to define unknown mixture exposures and address data gaps. Furthermore, a curated database on modes of chemical action will provide mechanistic information from *in vitro* bioanalytical NAMs and can be employed for establishing AOP networks to bridge data gaps in mixture assessment. Chemical producers, risk assessors, and respective regulators might e.g. be using NAMs and NAM-generated data in particular for chemicals with few information and to e.g., consider the expectable additional effect of product formulation compounds to the toxicity of an individually assessed active ingredient. A guidance document for the development and risk assessment of context-related reference mixtures based on monitoring and NAM data will be provided and a reference mixture developed for European wastewater treatment plant effluents.

Key words: chemical mixtures, new approach methods, environment, human health, regulatory acceptance

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

In this project, the use of data of new approach methods (NAMs) (i.e. bioanalytical methods for untargeted

exposure detection and hazard identification in conjunction with chemical screening data) to deal with mixtures will be compared with mixture risk assessment methods relying on component-based standard toxicity information. During the project data integration will be performed in collaboration with WP7 and according to the FAIR principles. Reuse of data and workflows will be enabled. Chemical mixtures are an integral part in the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability (CSS). Further, chemical mixtures were one of the highest scored topics in the first round of prioritisation within PARC. However, this project will highly support the Objectives 004 (Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge), 005 (Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives), 0010 (Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA) and 0012 (Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness: we will do a survey in cooperation with Task 6.4.2, for that we will need some support in distributing the survey to risk assessor.

WP7: Data management plan

WP9: Training, laboratory network: for now, we see no need for support from WP9, but if we identify needs, we will contact WP9

Other WPs: The project will primarily link to and exchange findings and input with project P6.4.1.a_Y1_CS1_BRUNEL_UGot (Optimising regulatory risk assessment and management of chemical mixtures in Europe) and with Task 6.4.2. Further, there will be links to and exchange with 6.2.3 on issues related to human real-life exposure and modelling of exposure. In a later stage, if available, the newly generated monitoring data from WP 4 and the outcome of WP 5 regarding toxicity testing and AOPs will be considered in our case studies.

Links outside PARC:

There are several currently ongoing research and policy development activities on mixtures in the EU. Under Horizon 2020, the so-called Green Deal Call includes a call dedicated to mixture toxicity, with a certain focus on aquatic environment and the occurrence of pharmaceutical residues in unintentional mixtures. There are also ongoing and planned mixture related activities related to the remit of EFSA (e.g. food safety and pesticides), e.g. regarding the further development of the Cumulative Assessment Groups (CAGs), primarily for the assessment of mixtures of pesticide residues in food. Further, the European Commission will conduct an impact assessment of the introduction of a MAF or MAFs under REACH, which will be supported by a consultant study.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.18: Dealing with mixtures in regulatory risk assessment through the use of monitoring data and NAMs” (M40)

D6.18: Final report on risk assessment and management methods for chemical mixtures across legislations (M81)

Partners List: UFZ (DE), UBA (DE), NIVA (NO), BPI (EL), UI (IS), AGES (AT), STAMI (NO), UKCEH (UK), EA (UK), NLZOH (SI)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/08/2025 (M40)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 25 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 5 275 €

P6.4.1.c_Y3_Skinsenmix_RegionH

Project Title	Skin sensitization – effect of mixtures, current practices and gaps
Project Acronym (15)	Skinsenmix

letters max)			
Project Manager	Jeanne Duus Johansen Jeanne.Duus.Johansen@regionh.dk	RegionH	Denmark
Deputy Project manager	Jose Hernán Alfonso jose.alfonso@stami.no	STAMI	Norway
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M25	Expected duration	48 Month
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.1
Project Id	P6.4.1.c_Y3_Skinsenmix_RegionH		

Status: Initiation

Summary of the project

A skin sensitizer is a chemical substance that will lead to an allergic response following repeated skin contact as defined by the United Nations Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals (UN GHS).

At least 25% of the European adult population are sensitized to one or more chemicals from consumer products and/or exposures in the work environment. However, no generally accepted risk assessment model exists in the EU to be used in regulations. Most consumer and occupational products contain several sensitizing chemicals which is known to influence the immune system. Furthermore, many products also contain irritants such as detergents, which may additionally impact the response, however this needs further study.

The lack of a common risk assessment model means that many skin sensitizers remain uncontrolled and that ad hoc decisions are taken when epidemics of skin sensitization occur with major consequences for those becoming sensitized. There is a paucity of knowledge concerning the impact of mixtures (allergens and irritants) on risk of skin sensitization leading to an urgent need to develop predictive models and test systems. New Approach Methods (NAMs), both in chemico and in vitro methods, have been validated and are now accepted for classification and potency grading (OECD 497) in some areas, however, they have not yet been assessed regarding their suitability for testing mixtures. In a recent questionnaire study among regulators and dermatologists/scientists in EU performed under PARC (6.3.1), most respondents found that, regulations concerning skin sensitizers could be improved, that NAMs needed further development, and that more insight into mechanisms, especially concerning effect of mixtures were required (unpublished).

To our knowledge, from a regulatory point of view, no alternative method to animal testing for skin sensitization potential assessment of mixtures exposed has yet been proposed. Therefore, this project aims to assess the performance of several NAMs in the assessment of defined mixtures and to gain more insight into effects of mixtures by using 3 D skin models, as these more closely reflect real-life, than the currently approved NAMs.

Main expected outputs of the project:

- 1) To assess the applicability and suitability of NAMs and a 3D skin model to evaluate the skin sensitization hazard of mixture exposures (several skin sensitizers together and skin sensitizers + irritant).
- 2) To integrate data from the NAMs and a 3D skin model to define a general mixture factor (MAF-SEN) that can be used in risk assessment models, which are being considered in 6.3.
- 3) To assess mixture effects on elicitation in humans to be considered in regulations of ongoing epidemics.

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

At least 25% of the European population are sensitized to one or more chemicals from consumer products and/or by occupational exposures. This project will develop new tools for risk assessment and management

of mixtures of skin sensitizers/irritants. Prevention of skin sensitization is a health priority of several national authorities. In a recent questionnaire study (PARC 6.3.1), many regulators from EU countries pointed to the need of more knowledge and data concerning NAMs and effect of mixtures. Thresholds derived from elicitation studies in humans have traditionally been used for ad hoc regulations of allergens in ongoing epidemics, however a mixture effect has not been considered. The project will therefore address considerable knowledge gap to improve regulations e.g., REACH; Cosmetics; Biocides.

Key words: skin sensitizer, mixtures, allergens, irritant, detergents, NAMS, 3D skin cell model.

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

The management of mixtures was one of the highest scoring topics in the “PARC survey”. Furthermore, mixtures are an integral part in the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability (CSS).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

WP6.3. The current regulatory practices for skin sensitization will be reviewed under 6.3 as a case story but is also of major relevance to the aims and objectives under 6.4, where it is suggested to focus especially on mixtures, both current practices and fill known gaps.

Links outside PARC:

The investigations are closely linked to projects being performed by our group in RegionH and in collaboration with University of Copenhagen already on immune reactions to skin sensitizers but will especially focus on effects of mixtures and regulatory practices. Furthermore, it is envisaged to establish an advisory group of experts, e.g., from OECD, the NTP Interagency Centre for the Evaluation of Alternative Toxicological Methods (NICEATM), EURL ECVAM and, if possible, from relevant industries.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes
 To be determined

Partners List:

National Allergy Research Centre, Denmark (REGIONH), STAMI, Norway, UCPH (DK), Dept of Immunology and Microbiology, AGES (AT), Department of Risk assessment.

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2024 (M25)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2028 (M72)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project (third year of PARC): 30 PM

Expected ODC for the first year of the project (third year of PARC): 51 000 €

A6.4.2 Facilitate the regulatory acceptance and use of new methods – 3 PROJECTS

P6.4.2.a_Y1_LandscapingSurv_UNIBAS

Project Title	Status of integration and use of New Approach Methodologies in the EU regulatory risk assessment landscape		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	P6.4.2.a_Y1_LandscapingSurv_UNIBAS		
Project Manager	Martin F. Wilks martin.wilks@unibas.ch Ellen Fritsche ellen.fritsche@unibas.ch	University of Basel (UNIBAS)	Switzerland
Deputy Project manager	Nicolas Roth nicolas.roth@unibas.ch	University of Basel (UNIBAS)	Switzerland

Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	36
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.2
Project Id	P6.4.2.a_Y1_LandscapingSurv_UNIBAS		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Innovative approaches to regulatory science and chemical risk assessment are needed to meet the goals and vision laid down by the EU Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability and the EU Green Deal. The overall aim of the project is to promote and facilitate the regulatory acceptance and practical use of New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) for use in chemical risk assessment for human health and the environment. Emphasis is put on real-life situations and application contexts encountered by risk assessors and regulators at desk level, e.g., situations with complex modes of action and/or often severe knowledge gaps. We will (i) review the status of development (incl. harmonization), integration, and use of NAMs in the different EU chemical sectors/regulatory frameworks/application contexts, through literature review and expert consultation activities (expert elicitation, survey); (ii) identify gaps, needs, barriers, opportunities, and drivers for success towards the regulatory acceptance and implementation of NAMs in the EU chemical regulatory landscape

The validation and regulatory acceptance of NAMs has been lagging behind despite significant scientific developments over the last decade. One particular challenge for risk assessment is to integrate these scientific developments into existing regulatory frameworks and best practice at desk level. While policies have long had the vision to protect human health and ecosystems with new and innovative methods, solid downstream implementation has been lagging behind, often because novel scientific methods have failed to consider regulatory needs as a driver for successful use and integration into chemical risk assessment and management practice. The project intends to follow-up on these needs, consolidating knowledge and fostering scientific cross-fertilization and harmonization in the field to develop criteria for the acceptance of NAMs and guidelines to support their integration in the daily risk assessment workflow.

The mapping activities will inform on the current status of integration and use of NAMs in regulatory risk assessment processes across chemical sectors. The outcome of the project will advance use of NAMs in regulatory science and may all together benefit all chemical sectors and risk assessment frameworks, as well as support harmonization efforts (EU Green Deal, Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability).

Outputs are planned in the form of three technical reports due M24, M26, and M36. They are aimed at knowledge consolidation, mapping gaps, needs, drivers, and areas of uncertainty for uptake of NAMs at risk assessment level. This initial phase of the work may promote and facilitate broader stakeholder engagement activities across regulatory, industry and academia, involved in similar research projects and initiatives at EU and international level.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Summary of the landscaping exercise assessing the status of integration and use of NAMs at across sectorial frameworks
- Summary of the gaps & needs analysis, barriers, opportunities, drivers for integration and use of NAMs and roadmap for use at desk level across sectorial frameworks
- Action plan for prioritization of regulatory-relevant scenario-based case studies, as an output from an international workshop
- Research “Road map” that will map the potential use of NAMs to requirements for environmental risk assessment (e.g., species section for testing and biomonitoring)
- Summary of the scenario-based case-studies

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

- Activities in years 1 and 2 will inform the development of regulatory-relevant case studies, looking

across regulatory silos and product categories.

- The selected scenario-based case studies will cover a variety of complex situations that regulators are facing when conducting hazard, exposure, and risk assessment, e.g., data-rich vs. data-poor chemicals, grouping decisions, different exposures, (occupational, environmental, consumer), identification and selection of species for testing and monitoring studies and model systems for hazard testing and assessment, classification and labelling, setting health-based guidance and environmental protection values, cumulative exposures etc.
- The output of this project will be used to orientate future coordination and harmonization efforts, foster cross-fertilization of scientific knowledge, order research needs and sharing of best research-to-policy practice in relation to the development, use and regulatory uptake of NAMs.

Key words: New Approach Methodologies; landscaping; expert elicitation; survey; regulatory acceptance; gaps & needs analysis; research road-mapping, confidence, human health risk assessment, environmental risk assessment.

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

- The project will support OO4 (Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge) through the development of regulatory-relevant case studies across regulatory silos and product categories.
- It will contribute to OO5 (Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives) by closely cooperating in particular with the ASPIS cluster of R&I initiatives.
- It addresses PARC operational objectives OO9 (Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC's results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA) by promoting and facilitating the integration and use of NAMs in chemical risk assessment practice, as well as their regulatory acceptance and uptake.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Important coordination efforts will be invested over the entire project duration within PARC to avoid overlaps and create synergies with:

- WP2, Task 2.1, Task 2.2
- WP5, Task 5.2, Task 5.3
- WP6, Task 6.1, Task 6.3

Links outside PARC

- ASPIS cluster: activities in PrecisionTox and RISK-HUNT3R are directly relevant to or even overlap with A6.4.2. ASPIS collaborators are partners in PARC 6.4.2 and/or WP6.
- PARERE at EURL ECVAM Network for Preliminary Assessment of Regulatory Relevance, which includes validation of NAMs for regulatory purposes;
- EFSA and JRC, regarding ongoing projects in the field of computer-based approaches/automation of the systematic review approach and TK/TD approaches; advisors for PARC A6.4.2;
- OECD, regarding ongoing projects in the field of harmonization and regulatory acceptance of NAMs and development of the Adverse Outcome Pathway Wiki.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.16. Status of integration and use of NAMs in the EU chemical regulatory risk assessment landscape – a mapping exercise and gaps & needs analysis (new delivery date M36)

D6.19: Report on regulatory acceptance and use of new methods (NAMs). This deliverable will give guidance for translation of the case studies results into scientific criteria to be used in regulatory actions (M81)

Partners List:

UNIBAS (Switzerland); NIPH, represented by VKM (Norway); UT (Estonia); ISS (Italy); UOB (United Kingdom); INERIS (France); UBA (Germany); BPI (Greece); EAA (Austria); UNL (Portugal); UKCEH (United Kingdom); UAVR (Portugal)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 34 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 16 875 €

P6.4.2.b_Y1_NGRApractice_VKM_NIPH

Project Title	Next generation risk assessment applied in practice		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	NGRApractice		
Project Manager	Gro Haarklou Mathisen Gro.haarklou.mathisen@vk m.no	National Institute of Public Health (NIPH), represented by the Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and Environment (VKM)	Norway
Deputy Project manager	Camilla Svendsen Camilla.svendsen@fhi.no	National Institute of Public Health (NIPH), represented by the Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and Environment (VKM)	Norway
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36*
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity	6.4.2
Project Id	P6.4.2.b_Y1_NGRApractice_VKM_NIPH		

*The project has been broken down at M36 to assess what has been achieved. If the review is positive, there will be two project phases M1-M36 and M37-M81.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Application of systematic review principles in chemical risk assessment is increasing. In 2021, a framework for the use of systematic review in chemical risk assessment was published by WHO. Evaluation of validity of studies is one important step in the systematic review process, however, tools to evaluate validity of in vitro studies (including in vitro NAMs), are currently not available. Such tools are needed to incorporate in vitro data in systematic reviews (which is a part of a chemical risk assessment), to identify data of sufficient validity to inform decision making by risk managers and to have ensure strong confidence in the conclusions. The VKM project “NGRA applied in practice” aim to create evidence-based tools and guidance’s for risk assessment based on NAMs, which will be included in an overall evidence-based NGRA framework usable for the evaluation of human health risk/safety across sectors (e.g. food and cosmetic). The framework will enable risk assessors to use other studies than human and animal studies, and also academic studies that are not OECD guideline studies, as evidence. This will contribute to fill knowledge gaps, and the outcome will be more robust risk assessments with reduced uncertainty, being a better knowledge base for the regulators/risk managers.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Generic, sector-independent tools for evidence-based hazard assessment of chemicals using NAMs addressing potential adverse human health effects.
- Generic, sector-independent guidance documents on identification of a PoD from NAMs and on the evaluation of uncertainty in NAMs.

- Generic, sector-independent checklists (reporting standards) for different NAMs, to ensure adequate design and reporting for the research outcome of NAMs to be usable as evidence in risk assessment.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

We are starting with the creation of tools for evaluation of internal and external validity of NAMs, enabling risk assessors to use NAMs in evidence-based risk assessment. The tools are needed to ensure that only evidence of sufficient quality is included based on the weight of evidence principle, that the effects addressed are relevant for human adverse health effects, and that the hazard assessment process and product is objective, robust, transparent, and reproducible. The internal validity tools will make it possible to evaluate whether a reported effect is caused by the exposure or if it may be due to systematic errors (bias) introduced by the study design, conduct, reporting or analysis. The external validity tool will make it possible to evaluate if the data generated by the study can be translated to human health effects.

Key words:

Chemical risk assessment, evidence-based, guidance, NAMs, NGRA, systematic review, tool.

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

004 (Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge), 009 (Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC’s results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA.) and 0012 (Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake): Although NAMs are developed to be used for risk assessments, risk assessors must evaluate the internal validity of the study (the risk of bias; whether the reported results may be caused by other issues than the exposure) and the external validity (the generalisability/if the results can be translated to human health effects). This validity evaluation is critical for inclusion as evidence in risk assessments, and for grading the certainty in the evidence, for transparency, and for the description of uncertainty. Using structured approaches for these evaluations makes these evaluations more transparent and objective.

005 (Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives): Knowing how to use the tools, and which information that needs to be reported to be able to apply the tools to evaluate a study, is important knowledge for researchers and to improve study reporting. In addition, our projects are highly relevant for projects focusing on readiness of in vitro studies, and vice versa, and collaborations are therefore important. We are already in contact with a RiskHunt3R project focusing of readiness evaluation, and they participate as experts in our studies to create these tools.

0013 (Build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical RA): We aim to develop training materials for the users to make them able to self-train. If possible, we will also prepare online training sessions (depends on funding).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

A scientific advisory group has been established for this project. Dimosthenis Sarigiannis (WP3) has the role as observers and will have the possibility to participate in all meetings.

It is important to ensure dissemination, communication, and awareness of the outcomes of this project. We would like to arrange a workshop and/or a symposium (year 2023/2024) to which the main stakeholders will be invited. An in-person workshop could e.g., include training people in use of the tools (presentation of the tools and the development methods, followed by hands-on training). Training could also be developed as online prerecorded material with on-demand Q&As to help users. A symposium could e.g., focus on making NAMs usable for risk managers (from science to evidence in chemical risk assessments to scientific basis for risk managers).

- WP7: This information is included in the section Data Management
- WP9: This project does not involve laboratory work. Hands-on training courses on the use of the tools, for assessors coming from different regulatory sectors including e.g., food safety, pesticides, cosmetics, consumer products, industrial chemicals, could be organised. Courses could be foreseen also for researchers and in Industries to make them aware of the tools.

- Other WPs: A scientific advisory group has been established for this project. Vera Ritz (WP2) has the role as observer and will have the possibility to participate in all meetings with the scientific advisory group.

This project is related to the two other Activity 6.4.2-projects:

- Status of integration & use of NAMs in the EU regulatory risk assessment landscape
- Landscape and readiness of advanced ML & AI approaches for Next Generation Risk Assessment

Links outside PARC

Several projects outside PARC addressing similar topics are ongoing. A scientific advisory group has been established, consisting of experts in the topic of interest with the goal to ensure a broad, multidisciplinary representation of members from academia, regulatory authorities, and scientific organizations that will give advice related to the planned work on development of tools and share information about ongoing work addressing similar question.

The purpose of the Advisory Group is to give strategic guidance and content-related support to the project group related to aspects considered important for the development of the tools, and to share information about ongoing work addressing similar questions to ensure that the outcome of the project complements the work of others, thereby creating synergies and avoiding duplication of efforts.

The members of the scientific advisory group are linked to the following institutions/projects outside PARC: CAAT (Center for Alternatives to Animal Testing), EBTC (Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration), ECHA (The European Chemicals Agency), Johns Hopkins University, JRC (Joint Research Center), Karolinska Institutet, NTP (National Toxicology program, U.S. Department of Health and Human Services), OECD, ONTOX, Radboud University, U.S. EPA (United States Environmental Protection Agency), EFSA, University of California San Francisco.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.16. Status of integration and use of NAMs in the EU chemical regulatory risk assessment landscape – a mapping exercise and gaps & needs analysis (new delivery date M36)

D6.19: Report on regulatory acceptance and use of new methods (NAMs). This deliverable will give guidance for translation of the case studies results into scientific criteria to be used in regulatory actions (M81).

Partners List:

NIPH, represented by VKM (Norway); UNIBAS (Switzerland); UT (Estonia); BPI (Greece); ISS (Italy); NIVA (Norway); UAVR (Portugal).

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Costs:

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 18 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 18 000 €

P6.4.2.c_Y1_NAMAM_UT

Project Title	Landscape and readiness of computational New Approach Methods based on advanced AI and ML approaches for chemicals' next generation risk assessment		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	NAMAM		
Project Manager	Uko Maran	University of Tartu	Estonia
	uko.maran@ut.ee		

Deputy Project manager	Sulev Sild sulev.sild@ut.ee	University of Tartu	Estonia
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	T6.4.2
Project Id	P6.4.2.c_Y1_NAMAM_UT		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Today more and more advanced machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) mathematical approaches are used to estimate effects and doses (QSAR) and to learn patterns of chemical behaviour from multiple data (in silico and in vitro). The aim of using these data-driven approaches is to make better informed decisions for the protection of human health and environment while reducing animal testing. There is a lack of transparency due to limited documentation or accessibility to underlying data and algorithms. This makes advanced computational methods (ACM) in content of NAMs difficult to understand and characterise uncertainty associated with using them. Thus, there is a clear need for better standardisation, transparent reporting, validation and illustration of AI & ML driven in silico models. This project will address the existing landscape and the potential acceptance of AI & ML driven QSAR models to important properties in chemical risk assessment with an emphasis on the regulatory use. The aim is to conduct a review and analysis of the AI and ML QSAR models and to identify best practices and further actions to ensure a transparent regulatory use, uncertainty estimation and its communication towards end-users, independent verification and understanding of the outcome of such models. To develop reporting standards and decision-making criteria for ML and AI predictive models in the context of NAMs and NGRA. The best examples will be identified and made available as FAIR data through the QsarDB.org repository.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project will provide a framework for more transparent reporting of predictions obtained using AI and ML models for regulatory purposes. This will help stakeholders (for better predictions' reporting) and regulators (for predictions' evaluation).

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The main outcomes and impacts of the project include:

- Identification of ML and AI QSAR models of PARC focused properties that could be used for filling data gaps.
- Knowledge of the transparency and potential reproducibility of ML and AI models for chemical risk assessment and decision-making workflows.
- Identification of main roadblocks related to the applications of QSAR models, including applicability domain evaluation and uncertainty estimation related to ML and AI models.
- Case studies that attempt to reuse published ML and/or AI models to identify issues that need addressing to improve acceptance for regulatory use.

Limitation of ML and/or AI models:

Limitations of these non-animal approaches are related to their data-driven nature, because if they rely on prior knowledge, this knowledge must be present before reliable models can be developed. This can be overcome by developing reliable data source(s).

Also related to the actual regulations is the transparency of ML and/or AI models, which requires the development of various metrics that contribute to confidence and help adapt best practices.

Key words:

AI model, ML model, in silico models, QSAR, QSPR, NAMs, reporting framework, applicability domain,

uncertainty.

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

In response to identified needs in Chemical RA (OO7: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA) this project will focus on advanced ML and AI models. The project will address PARC operational objectives OO9 (Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC's results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA) by facilitating the uptake of new approach methods in regulatory RA processes.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Interactions with other WPs in PARC are summarised as follows:

- Cooperation is foreseen with WP2 task 2.1 to define priorities for the research.
- Cooperation is established with WP2.2 in connection with NGRARoute.
- Potential cooperation with WP5 task 5.1 on the topic of computational NAMs for closing data gaps in human health and environmental endpoints
- Potential collaboration with WP5 task 5.3 on the evaluation of in silico methods for ADME/Tox parameters in PBK models and quantitative systems toxicology.
- Potential collaboration with WP7 task 7.1 on the PARC's FAIR Data Policy (PFDP).
- Cooperation is foreseen with WP task 7.3 in establishing FAIR predictive models.
- Cooperation with WP8 task 8.2 on the evaluation of computational NAMs for the early warning system (EWS) on chemical risks.
- Cooperation with WP8 task 8.3 on the integrating of computational NAMs.

Links outside PARC

- OECD-QAF: (OECD QSAR Assessment Framework, duration 2021-2024) develops criteria on how to assess (i) QSAR and any other computational model validity used as NAMs and (ii) how to assess validity of QSAR and any other computational prediction. Three partners (ISS, INERIS, UT) of the project are involved in OECD-QAF.
- ASPIS-cluster (<https://www.aspis-cluster.com/>): cluster acts as roof organisation for the RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX & PrecisionTOX projects. IRFM (E. Benfenati) is co-leading the WG on computational methods with other people from the lab being part of the WG; i.e., acting as liaison.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.16. Status of integration and use of NAMs in the EU chemical regulatory risk assessment landscape – a mapping exercise and gaps & needs analysis (new delivery date M36)

D6.19: Report on regulatory acceptance and use of new methods (NAMs). This deliverable will give guidance for translation of the case studies results into scientific criteria to be used in regulatory actions (M81).

Partners List:

UT (Estonia); UG-PL (Poland); IRFM (Italy); UNIBAS (Switzerland); NIPH(VKM) (Norway); ISS (Italy); INERIS (France); UKCEH (United Kingdom); NIVA (Norway), EA (UK), KEMI (SE).

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 29 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 13 125 €

A6.4.3 Developing information transfer structures and enforcement methodology for chemicals in

articles to support the transition to a circular economy – 2 PROJECTS

P6.4.3.a_Y1_SuProM_MU

Project Title	6.4.3.1 A comprehensive review and application of databases and testing methods for SUBstances in PROducts and Materials		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	SuProM		
Project Manager	Lisa Melymuk lisa.melymuk@recetox.muni.cz	MU (RECETOX)	Czechia
Deputy Project manager	Robin Vestergren robin.vestergren@kemi.se	KemI	Sweden
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.3
Project Id	P6.4.3.a_Y1_SuProM_MU		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The European Commission's Green Deal and the Chemical strategy for sustainability provides the direction for a toxic free and sustainable future where chemicals are produced and used in a way that maximises their contribution to society while minimizing risks for the environment and human health. In these strategic documents it is envisaged that products and material used in society should be designed without the use of the most harmful chemicals and that the use of other harmful chemicals should be minimized.

Enforcement of EU chemicals safety and environmental legislation has a central role in implementing the European Green Deal agenda and the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability. No matter how ambitious the legislation is on paper, it will never fulfil the level of protection of consumers and workers if not properly enforced. The methods developed in this activity will facilitate a systematic risk-based identification of priority substances, products, and materials, as well as support and direct the development of efficient analytical methods for enforcement actions. This will support national enforcement authorities of chemicals legislation, including product specific legislations (for example, the RoHS Directive, EC Toys directive, regulations on food contact materials, etc.) and restrictions of chemicals in various products. Enforcement is essential, and without enforcement any law will be ineffective.

The newly proposed Sustainable Products Initiative (SPI) aims to reduce the environmental footprint of products throughout their lifecycle. The legislative proposal will extend the scope of the Ecodesign framework beyond energy-related products, while also considering additional sustainability principles to regulate the environmental impact of goods, including chemicals in products. A consistent and complete methodology for assessing the environmental, climate and health impacts of products (and services) over their life cycle are needed. The Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) has been suggested as a basis for such a consistent and complete methodology. However, there is still a need to further develop the PEF methodology to more adequately address toxicity impacts of chemicals. The proposed project will evaluate how such sustainability assessments of products and materials are implemented with respect to chemicals, and provide a basis for future work providing recommendations on the application of this framework.

Main expected outputs of the project

This project will evaluate the currently available information on substances in products and materials, and how this information can be integrated in enforcement activities and life cycle assessments, based on a comprehensive review of chemical databases and gap and needs analysis of analytical testing methodologies. Based on this analysis, future projects on the development of new databases tools, and analytical testing methods will be designed. This will support the aim of Activity 6.4.3, in applying tools

and databases that enable a systematic identification of priority substances in products and materials to support the transition to the circular economy.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The primary stakeholders for this project are national and EU agencies responsible for enforcement of chemical and product legislations. It is envisaged that the results from this project and follow-up projects will contribute to a more systematic and effective enforcement of chemicals.

Key words

substances in products; chemical databases; materials; consumer products; enforcement; product composition.

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

In response to identified needs in Chemical RA (OO7: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA) this project will synthesize existing information from regulatory databases, other research and industry activities (OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives) to assemble a comprehensive overview of the state of information on substances in products and materials in Europe, which will be of use by risk assessors, policy makers, other research activities within and outside of PARC (OO4: Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge, OO5), and in the longer term, through further development of the activity 6.4.3, can serve as an information source to the general public to increase knowledge and awareness on chemical exposures and risks (OO6: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen's understanding/awareness of chemical RA). The project will include assessment of the FAIR and open aspects of existing databases, and recommendations for improved data structures that meet FAIR and open data criteria and are useable tools for further risk assessment related to substances in products and materials (OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA, OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- WP3: Support in administering questionnaires to national chemical agencies as an information gathering exercises on the topics of chemical databases and enforcement of chemical regulations in products and materials.
 - WP7: Data management plan
 - WP9: Evaluation of chemical laboratories/methods involved in enforcement activities related to substances in products and materials; capacity-building related to enforcement activities
 - Other WPs: WP4 (Task 4.2 Prioritization of substances for screening/monitoring; Task 4.3 Analytical method development), WP6 (Task 6.2 Exposure via consumer articles); WP8 (Task 8.1 Safe and sustainable by design; Task 8.2 Early warning systems)

Links outside PARC

The research on developing databases and improving chemical information transfer is linked to several initiatives such as the SCiP database (ECHA), development of product passports and the use of product environmental footprints.

The research on new testing methods for products and materials will be carried out in close collaboration with national agencies responsible for enforcing chemical and product legislations.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.14: Report on current screening and enforcement structures – Leader: TUKES (new delivery date M28)

AD6.15: Report on existing database structures with recommended structures - Leader: MU (M36)

D6.20 Framework & case studies for articles & recycled materials for systematic identification of priority substances, materials, & articles from market data (M81)

Partners List:

MU (Czechia); KemI (Sweden); Rise (Sweden); TUKES (Finland); VUA (Netherlands), Vito (Belgium) (WP7); TNO (Netherlands) (WP7)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 36 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 11 500 €

P6.4.3.b_Y3_ENFORCE_KemI

Project Title	New methods to support the ENFORCEment of chemicals in consumer articles		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	ENFORCE		
Project Manager	Robin Vestergren	Swedish chemicals agency	Sweden
Deputy Project manager	Robin.vestergren@kemi.se	(KemI)	
	Lisa Melymuk	MU (RECETOX)	Czechia
	lisa.melymuk@recetox.muni.cz		
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	25	Expected duration (months)	48
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.3b
Project Id	P6.4.3.b_Y3_ENFORCE_KemI		

Status: Initiation

Summary of the project

Enforcement of EU chemicals safety legislation has a central role in implementing the European Green Deal agenda and the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability. Effective enforcement will ensure that EU citizens are not exposed to regulated substances and ensure a level playing field for producers and importers of consumer articles.

The recent development in analytical techniques and use of chemical information systems have opened opportunities for characterizing the universe of chemicals in different matrices facilitating the identification of chemicals of emerging concerns. Yet, the full potential of these novel methods is not exploited for regulatory purposes.

The project will evaluate the applicability of methods of chemical identification for use in the enforcement of chemical safety legislation, to fulfil crucial needs raised in project 6.4.3a. For effective enforcement rapid screening methods that cover a wide range of restricted/SVHC substances that can be applied to a variety of sample matrices are typically needed. The methods developed and tested in this project will facilitate a systematic identification of priority substances, products, and materials and provide efficient analytical methods for enforcement actions. This will support national enforcement authorities of chemicals legislation (REACH and CLP) as well as product-specific legislations (for example, the RoHS Directive, EC Toys directive, POPs-regulation, regulations on food contact materials, etc.).

Main expected outputs of the project:

The project will evaluate methods of chemical screening and quantification according for their applicability to enforcement of chemical safety legislation. In evaluating methods, this project will further test to what

extent databases reviewed in P6.4.3a capture the chemical composition of articles. By developing and applying rapid analytical techniques for screening and validation the project will provide a proof-of-concept methodology that could be used in enforcement of chemicals legislation. The project will focus on (i) additives in high volume plastics and (ii) per- and polyfluoralkyl substances in articles identified as major use categories. Although the project will specifically focus on restricted substances and SVHCs a broader range of chemicals will be included in the methodology testing. The methods developed in this project will be presented at several stages to ECHA enforcement forum to assess the possibilities and needs for further standardisation.

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

The primary stakeholders for this project are national and EU agencies responsible for the enforcement of chemical and product legislation. It is envisaged that the results from this project will provide strategies and tools that could be implemented by enforcement agencies, that need better opportunities to prioritise enforcement and today lack fast, reliable and harmonised screening methods for analysing organic substances. The project will also foster a collaboration between scientists and regulators at national agencies and national inspectors through ECHA forum that could serve as a model for addressing future regulatory needs. Thus, the project will contribute to more systematic and effective enforcement of chemicals also beyond the completion of PARC.

Key words: Enforcement, consumer articles, PFAS, plastics, data bases.

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives: OO4: Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge, OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives, OO6: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen’s understanding/awareness of chemical RA, OO7: Develop/implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA, OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA, OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake and OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC’s results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA.

In response to identified needs in Chemical RA (OO7) this project will build on existing methodologies and ongoing research projects (OO5) to develop testing methods that can be used in enforcement of chemicals legislation (OO4, OO5), and in increase knowledge and awareness on chemical exposures and risks (OO6). The project will include assessment of the FAIR and open aspects of existing databases, and recommendations for improved data structures that meet FAIR and open data criteria and are useable tools for further risk assessment related to substances in articles and materials (OO10, OO12)

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness: Support the communication with national agencies and ECHA forum regarding their need for methods.

WP4: Considering the focus on new analytical methods the work carried out in 6.4.3a will be closely linked to Task 4.3 (Analytical method development). Two of the partners in 6.4.3 (VUA and ÖRU) have ongoing/planned projects with PMs under task 4.3. which will contribute to the objectives of this project.

WP9: Training, laboratory network: Evaluation of chemical laboratories/methods involved in enforcement activities related to substances in products and materials; capacity-building related to enforcement activities.

Other WPs: WP6 (Task 6.2 Exposure via consumer articles); WP8 (Task 8.1 Safe and sustainable by design).

Links outside PARC:

The work under 6.4.3a has identified numerous research initiatives on PFAS in consumer articles and additives in plastics which may be relevant to communicate and collaborate with. The research on new testing methods for products and materials will be carried out in close collaboration with national agencies

responsible for enforcing chemical and product legislations and ECHA forum. In particular, the competent authorities responsible for the proposal of a broad PFAS restriction (Norway, Sweden, Denmark, Germany and the Netherlands) will be consulted during the development of methods to support the upcoming restriction.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes
 D6.20 Framework & case studies for articles & recycled materials for systematic identification of priority substances, materials, & articles from market data (M81).

AD6.x. New methods to support a systematic and effective enforcement of chemicals M72 (MU/KemI).

Partners List: MU (Czechia), KemI (Sweden), Rise (Sweden), TUKES (Finland), VUA (Netherlands), Stockholm University (Sweden), Örebro University (Sweden)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2024 (M25)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2028 (M72)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project (third year of PARC): 27 PM

Expected ODC for the first year of the project (third year of PARC): 26 000 €

A6.4.4 Risk assessment to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity – 5 PROJECTS

P6.4.4.a_Y1_CRNCS1_KEMI

Project Title	Clarify regulatory needs – Transform EU strategies into regulatory useable research projects		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	CRNCS1		
Project Manager	Johan Axelman Johan.axelman@kemi.se	Swedish Chemicals Agency	Sweden
Deputy Project manager	Sabine Duquesne Sabine.Duquesne@uba.de	Umweltsbundesamt (UBA)	Germany
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	42*
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.4
Project Id	P6.4.4.a_Y1_CRNCS1_KEMI		

* The project has been broken at mid-term (M42) to assess what has been achieved at the mid-term and if the review is positive then a new project could be launched for the period M43-M81.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The activity is tailored toward supporting strategic transition initiatives such as the roadmap to systems-based ERA (by EFSA - European partnership for next generation, system-based ERA [PERA]) and European co-funded partnership on biodiversity (Biodiversa+). The project is directly applicable to the environmental risk assessment for the authorisation of PPP and aims to better link the goal of the EU environmental and agricultural strategies to the EU regulation 1107/2009.

The activity aims at better assessing effects on overall biodiversity and the possibility to simplify (i.e. less resource demanding) the methods used for the environmental risk assessment (ERA) of plant protection products (PPP) without compromising the level of protection to be ensured by the assessment. That will be

achieved by benchmarking existing and new methods (such as NAMs) against each other and against independent environmental monitoring data. Approaches, research questions and methodologies for these benchmarking activities are described in project plans for 6.4.4.b_Y1_PPPEXPCS2_SLU, 6.4.4.c_PPPEFF_CS3_UFZ and 6.4.4.d_PPPBENCHCS4_UKOLD. Furthermore, we will explore new holistic approaches to environmental risk assessment to overcome the shortcomings of the current substance-by-substance paradigm and consider the environmental context more realistically. Approaches, research questions and methodologies for these benchmarking activities are described in project plans for 6.4.4.d_PPPBENCHCS4_UKOLD and P6.4.4.e_Y1_PPPOSCS5_ISCIII. Both existing and new models for prospective risk assessment will be reviewed and amended using monitoring data. The activity will also help to explore new frameworks for risk characterisation that support system-based approaches to risk assessment by expanding the current approach.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project will ensure that the outcome of the other projects within 6.4.4 address the common goal of an improved ERA-scheme better aligning with EU strategies and assessing biodiversity. Considering regulatory needs and ensuring regulatory acceptance are key components of this project. It will be identified how the input from other stakeholders (risk managers, farmers, etc) can be integrated in the ERA development.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The current ERA scheme is well established, but has fallen out of step with environmental reality and technological possibilities. The project will provide a more realistic and resource-efficient ERA-scheme. However, the development needs to be supported by EFSA to be taken up by the risk assessors in the MS. The close collaboration with EFSA in this project, ensures a targeted and operational development of a new ERA-scheme and facilitates the application by end-users and stakeholders, e.g., risk assessors and applicants.

Key words:

Environmental risk assessment, Systems-based approach, Regulatory needs, Stakeholder engagement

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The PARC objective is the regulatory applicability of the research, and this project will assure regulatory applicability of the activity 6.4.4 through the direct involvement of regulatory risk assessors and EFSA.

OO3 (Define common R&I strategies with transparent criteria and a prioritisation strategy)– This project’s key objective is to translate regulatory and policy needs into ERA research issues for the projects involved in 6.4.4 as well as other collaboration projects (see OO5 below). The translation process will be guided by an iterative and knowledge building dialogue with regulators, policymakers and other stakeholders. The dialogue involves mutual knowledge exchange between researchers in all projects of 6.4.4.

OO4 (Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge)– See comment for OO3 (iterative knowledge-building dialogue).

OO5 (Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives)– As a representative of all projects in Activity 6.4.4 this project is approached by and actively seeks out to establish collaboration with relevant other projects (Horizon Europe and other). A knowledge exchange platform with monthly meetings for all partners in 6.4.4 has been established.

OO8 (Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes)

OO9 (Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC’s results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA)

OO12 (Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake) – This project is designed to support a step-wise transition towards systems-based assessments, a process that includes a wide range of stakeholders. A scientific reframing of (E)RA driven by integration of knowledge from many different science disciplines requires an iterative knowledge building processes involves regulatory stakeholders.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

All five projects in Activity 6.4.4 are tightly linked and addresses different aspects of a step-wise transition to next generation systems-based environmental risk assessments. The role of this project (P6.4.4.a_Y1_CRNCS1) *Clarifying regulatory needs* is to coordinate the research questions and deliverables of the other four projects in 6.4.4. The role of this project is also to organise stakeholder interactions and engagement in order to ensure regulatory relevance of all projects in 6.4.4. Other planned linked are:

- WP2 and 3 to ensure a coordinated dialogue with regulators and policy makers.
- T6.3 Project within *Review of risk assessment methodologies*: Specificities and similarities of prospective and retrospective risk assessment for pesticides.
- Activity 6.4.1 Environmental risk assessment of chemical mixtures to ensure alignment and avoid overlaps in system approaches.
- Activity 6.4.2 Project on NAMs in environmental risk assessments
- T4.2 Environmental monitoring.
- WP7 Data policy (management, harmonisation, interoperability, exchange). A standardised and comparable methodology would facilitate sharing and downstream use of the ERA-data.

Links outside PARC

Strategic partnerships at the EU-level, such as EFSA initiative Partnership and Roadmap to systems-based environmental risk assessment (PERA) and Biodiversa+, as well as projects such as SPRINT.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.7: Technical report outlining the regulatory needs for ERA development areas (new delivery date M36)

D6.21 Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents (M81)

Partners List:

KEMI (SE); UBA(DE); FOEN (CH); ANSES (FR); EFSA (EU); ULUND (SE); NIVA (NO); UOS (DE)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2025 (M42)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 30 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 10 475 €

P6.4.4.b_Y1_PPPEXPCS2_UFZ

Project Title	Reduce complexity of models for predicted environmental concentrations of plant protection products while ensuring their predictive capacity		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	PPPEXPCS2		
Project Manager	Mikaela Gönczi Mikaela.Gonczi@slu.se	SLU (M1-M24)	Se
	Matthias Liess Matthias.liess@ufz.de	UFZ (M25-M36)	DE
Deputy Project manager	Gusatf Boström Gusatf.bostrom@slu.se	SLU (M1-M24)	SE
	Ayesha Siddique ayasha.siddique@ufz.de	UFZ (M25-M36)	DE
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	36*

PARC (Month number)

PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.4
Project Id	P6.4.4.b_Y1_PPPEXPCS2_SLU (M1-M24) P6.4.4.b_Y1_PPPEXPCS2_UFZ (M25-M36)		

* The project has been initially broken at M24 (that corresponds to the end of phase 3 of the project) to assess what has been achieved but will be extended until M36.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

This project aims at investigating if the predictions in the exposure part of the ERA carried out in the context of authorization of PPPs under the Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 can be simplified, improved in predictive potential and validated by maintaining the level of protection required. In 2019 the SLU Centre for Pesticides in the Environment (CKB) at the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences developed a new method for calculating predicted concentrations in surface water (called PEC CKB) (Boström et al., 2019). This approach successfully extends the type of methods which predict environmental concentrations of PPPs in water bodies with fewer input parameters, but on the basis of established knowledge of environmental processes (e.g. Kattwinkel et al. 2011). The proposed calculation method is very simple and requires minimal input data. Further work would aim at achieving even closer conformity between predicted (PEC) and measured (MEC) concentrations by focusing improvements on the most important factors of the calculations. This proposed project aims at exploring further ways of simplifying the PEC calculations within the ERA. This can be pursued through testing and further development of the PEC CKB or similar concepts like the German models Exposit and GERDA, and through comparing the predictability of these simpler models to MEC from different EU member states (MS). The new models will be validated against currently existing models and monitoring data additional to those used to derive the models.

Main expected outputs of the project

The comparison of several models for exposure, including different parameters, with the same dataset will give us information on differences and similarities of the models' predictive capacity and protection level. By various analyses we will be able to evaluate which factor are most important to explain the concentrations in the environment and how the predictive capacity can be improved. We will also assess the transferability of the models between data from different MS and identify factors that play an important role such as geography, climate or soil properties.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The end-users of the research are mainly risk assessors in the context of authorization of plant protection products at MS and EU level. In addition, the project aims to contribute to a transition to a systems-based ERA by facilitating reusability of data generated within the ERA. In order to efficiently allocate resources, we need to examine if the ERA used for plant protection products can be simplified.

Key words:

Environmental risk assessment, exposure assessment, systems-based approach, plant protection products, monitoring

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project aims to contribute to the development of existing and new models for estimating the risks of exposure to chemicals.

The project mainly responds to the operational objective 009 - developing models and innovative concepts for RA, and to deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake, initially focusing on models for predicting surface water concentrations of pesticides.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- PARC WPs interlinking within Activity 6.4.4.
- WP2 and 3 to ensure a coordinated dialogue with regulators and policy makers.
- T6.3 Project within *Review of risk assessment methodologies*: Specificities and similarities of prospective and retrospective risk assessment for pesticides.
- Activity 6.4.1 Environmental risk assessment of chemical mixtures to ensure alignment and avoid overlaps in system approaches.
- Activity 6.4.2 Project on NAMs in environmental risk assessments
- Task 4.2 Environmental monitoring.
- WP7 Data policy (management, harmonisation, interoperability, exchange). A standardised and comparable methodology would facilitate sharing and downstream use of the ERA-data.

Links outside PARC

A member of the former FOCUS (FORum for the Co-ordination of pesticide fate models and their USE) surface water workgroup is participating in the project. Since their work is the basis of the exposure component of the existing ERA this will improve the possibility that the results of the project will be implemented in a regulatory context. Other groups working with exposure models, such as GERDA will also be contacted.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.20. Technical report on factors and processes needed to be included in robust aquatic exposure predictions for regulatory use, including an assessment of geographic representativeness (M36)
 D6.21 Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents (M81)

Partners List:

SLU (SE), UFZ (DE), Fraunhofer IME (DE), University of Osnabrück UOS (DE), EAWAG (CH), NIVA (NO), ULUND (SE), IEP-NRI (PL), UoB (UK). Regulatory core group: KEMI (SE), UBA (DE), FOEN (CH), ANSES (FR), EFSA (EU).

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)
 Expected ending date: 30/04/2024 (M24)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 22.5 PM
 Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 12 740 €

P6.4.4.c_Y1_PPPEFFCS3_UFZ

Project Title	Reduce complexity of models for predictions of environmental effects of plant protection products while ensuring their predictive capacity		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	PPPEFF CS3		
Project Manager	Matthias Liess	UFZ	DE
	matthias.liess@ufz.de		
Deputy Project manager	Paulo Sousa	UC	PT
	jps@zoo.uc.pt		
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36*
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.4
Project Id	P6.4.4.c_Y1_PPPEFF CS3_UFZ		

* The project has been broken at M36 (that corresponds to the end of phase 2 of the project) to assess

what has been achieved and if the review is positive then new projects could be launched for the period M37-M81.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The risk assessment process of PPPs has developed into a highly sophisticated, time consuming and complex process. Despite this elaborated procedure, the occurrence of PPP has been linked to adverse ecological effects on non-target organisms in several field investigations. This does not comply with the Regulation (EU) 546/2011 that “Member States shall ensure that use of plant protection products does not have any long-term repercussions for the abundance and diversity of non-target species” (EU Commission, 2011). The aim of this project is moving towards a protective ERA with reduced complexity and resources required while keeping it as information-rich as necessary. This will be achieved by including only the information and processes that have been proven by ecosystem monitoring and effect modelling to be relevant. This improves the extrapolation of effect information from lower tier laboratory investigations to field effects. The ecosystem effects will be modelled with the stress addition model (Liess et al. 2016) and compared with the effects monitored at the ecosystem level. This approach enables to identify the most parsimonious description of ecosystem processes related to the effects of PPP. A differentiation related to the mode of actions (MOA) of PPPs and in relation to the respective groups of species will be performed. This project will contribute to the development of a more resource-efficient and realistic ERA as described in 6.4.4.1. The framework will be made accessible by a software package to enable a practicable and reproducible ERA.

Main expected outputs of the project

Field monitoring data related to exposure and effects of PPP in a great variety of member states will be collated. Currently high-quality data have been identified for Germany, Sweden, Switzerland. Data from a variety of member states in different regions of the EU need to be included to reflect the European diversity. A feedback loop between existing risk assessment thresholds and retrospective ecosystem monitoring results will be formalized to constantly improve the level of realism and validation of ERA. By this the project will enable regulators to identify ecological process to be included into the risk assessment.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The end-users will be provided with the identification of the relevant factors needed to link laboratory lower-tier tests and effects at the ecosystem level to make better use of lower-tier test information. Additionally, effect information obtained from the ecosystem level will enable to better use higher-tier test information within the risk assessment framework

The implementation of the most relevant environmental factors into the risk assessment process so that the sensitive field populations can be identified and protected and that ERA at the same time strives an improved balance between reduced complexity and increased ecological realism.

Increase regulatory usability by documenting a transparent and easy to follow framework on how effect models can be replicated and adapted to ensure transferability between member states.

Key words:

Environmental risk assessment, effect assessment, systems-based approach, plant protection products, monitoring

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

OO7: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA

OO8: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes

OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA

OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake

OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC’s results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA.

Under this project, we aim to collate monitoring data from different member countries to improve current risk assessment of chemicals. This involves validation of models such as SAM covering all relevant chemical and non-chemical stressors occurring in the field. using field monitoring data and hence contribute to risk assessment.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- All the projects within 6.4.4 are closely linked, aiming at risk assessment to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity. The project 6.4.4.a will ensure and translate the regulatory needs into research projects on ERA. The exposure data from 6.4.4.b project will be used with available effect data to better link exposure and effects (6.4.4.c) in the field. Based on field effects, the additional environmental factors relevant for ERA (6.4.4.d) will be identified and approaches will be benchmarked (6.4.4.e) with exposure and effects datasets.
- Interlink within Activity 6.4.4.
- WP2 and 3 to ensure a coordinated dialogue with regulators and policy makers.
- T 6.3 Project within *Review of risk assessment methodologies*: Specificities and similarities of prospective and retrospective risk assessment for pesticides.
- Activity 6.4.1 Environmental risk assessment of chemical mixtures to ensure alignment and avoid overlaps in system approaches.
- Activity 6.4.2 Project on NAMs in environmental risk assessments
- T4.2 Environmental monitoring.
- WP 7 Data policy (management, harmonisation, interoperability, exchange). A standardised and comparable methodology would facilitate sharing and downstream use of the ERA-data.

Links outside PARC

Strategic partnerships at the EU-level, such as EFSA initiative Partnership and Roadmap to systems-based environmental risk assessment (PERA) and Biodiversa+, as well as projects such as SPRINT.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.19 Technical report informing on factors and processes needed to be included in the ERA to obtain an improved balance between reduced complexity and increased ecological realism (M36)

D6.21 Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents (M81)

Partners List:

UFZ (DE), UC (PT), EAWAG (CH), SLU (SE); UKOLD (DE); ULUND (SE), NIVA (NO), UCLM (ES), UOS (DE), ISCIII (ES)

Regulatory core team: KEMI (SE), UBA (DE), FOEN (CH), EFSA (EU), ANSES (FR), UKCEH (UK)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Costs:

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 40 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 22 687 €

P6.4.4.d_Y1_PPPBENCHCS4_UKOLD

Project Title	Benchmark ERA to support the transition towards a holistic paradigm		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	PPPBENCH		
Project	Ralf Schäfer	UKOLD	DE

Manager	schaeferralf@uni-landau.de		
Deputy	NA		
Project manager			
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	42*
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.4
Project Id	P6.4.4.d_Y1_PPPBENCHCS4_UKOLD		

* The project has been broken at mid-term (M42) to assess what has been achieved at the mid-term and if the review is positive then a new project could be launched for the period M43-M81.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

This project aims to ensure that results of any independently performed ERA of a PPP can be used as a benchmark for ERAs of other PPPs, i.e., comparing and ranking risk profiles of PPPs among substances and in different areas (e.g., for selected organism groups) of the ERA when assessed on the basis of similar level of refinement. This project aims to develop concepts and methodologies to improve the ERA so that results from the individual risk assessments become inter-comparable in terms of risk profiles considering each area of the ERA. This helps in delivering consistent ERA results and once compared to monitoring results, it will eventually improve its reliability regarding the estimation of environmental risks. The overall aim of the project is to contribute to a more holistic ERA that manages the overall risk in an efficient manner.

Based on available data sets and case studies on rejected products, the internal and external risk benchmarking will be conducted. Depending on the results, gaps will be identified in current ERA paradigm and short-term remedies proposed. Over the project period, a compatibility methodology will be suggested based on the future ERA paradigm that the partners develop in PARC. The project will thus have a direct impact on the development of an improved ERA under EU regulation 1107/2009.

Main expected outputs of the project

Expected output is an ERA concept and defined methodology to be used as a basis to develop a new guidance for ERA within the authorisation process. The resulting ERA should have an improved performance in terms of capturing the relative risk of different PPPs in a relevant spatial and temporal scale when assessed on the basis of similar data/ level of refinement. The improved ERA should also support systems-based risk assessments and facilitate use down the line, such as improved advisory services and systems-based risk management.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

One fundamental property of the ERA to improve would be the comparability of the methodology used to assess the environmental risks (not to be confused with comparative assessment performed as part of substitution process in the current assessment). If used in connection with specific decision rules, this methodology in turn could ensure that newly authorised PPPs have a lower, or if other reasons apply (e.g. resistance management) similar, risk level than those previously authorised.

The outcome of this project will aid the aims defined under 6.4.4.1 to align EU regulations and improve the ERA-scheme by identifying how a risk assessment methodology should be designed to allow for benchmarking of PPPs against each other capturing their relative risk. Furthermore, the complexity of the current ERA will be reduced by identifying key descriptors of PPP-substances (physico-chemical properties, toxicological profiles) and use (exposure related parameters) that have the most weight in the

description of the risk. Finally, the consistency of the risk assessments from different tiers regarding individual substances will be evaluated.

Key words:

Environmental risk assessment, effect assessment, systems-based approach, plant protection products, monitoring, benchmarking, comparative risk assessment

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project responds to the following PARC operational objectives OO4 (Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge), OO5 (Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives), OO10 (Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA), OO12 (Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake), OO9 (Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC’s results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA), and OO13 (Build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical RA). The expected output will promote the use of developed concepts with the possibility of their use in the approval process and also foster the uptake of PARC knowledge to increase stakeholders' awareness. It will also provide some collaboration with other partners thus enabling.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- PARC WPs interlinking within Activity 6.4.4
- WP2 and 3 to ensure a coordinated dialogue with regulators and policy makers.
- Task 6.3 Project within *Review of risk assessment methodologies*: Specificities and similarities of prospective and retrospective risk assessment for pesticides.
- Activity 6.4.1 Environmental risk assessment of chemical mixtures to ensure alignment and avoid overlaps in system approaches.
- Activity 6.4.2 Project on NAMs in environmental risk assessments
- Task 4.2 Environmental monitoring.
- WP7 Data policy (management, harmonisation, interoperability, exchange). A standardised and comparable methodology would facilitate sharing and downstream use of the ERA-data.

Links outside PARC

Strategic partnerships at the EU-level, such as EFSA initiative Partnership and Roadmap to systems-based environmental risk assessment (PERA) and Biodiversa+, as well as projects such as SPRINT.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.21 Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents (M81)

Partners List:

UKOLD (DE), UFZ (DE), ISCIII (ES); EAWAG (CH), NIVA (NO), ULUND (SE).

Regulatory core team: KEMI (SE), UBA (DE), FOEN (CH), ANSES (FR), EFSA (EU)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2025 (M42)

Costs:

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 23 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 15 409 €

P6.4.4.e_Y1_PPPOSCS5_ISCIII

Project Title	Quantify effects of PPP and other stressors through landscape risk assessment informing on environmental impacts
Project Acronym (15)	PPPOS

letters max)			
Project Manager	José Tarazona Jose.TARAZONA@efsa.europa.eu	ISCI3	ES
Deputy Project manager	Matthias Liess matthias.liess@ufz.de	UFZ	DE
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	42*
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.4
Project Id	P6.4.4.e_Y1_PPPOSCS5_ISCI3		

* The project has been broken at mid-term (M42) to assess what has been achieved at the mid-term and if the review is positive then a new project could be launched for the period M43-M81.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Despite elaborate regulation of agricultural pesticides, their occurrence has been linked to adverse ecological effects on non-target organisms in several field investigations. This situation does not comply with the Regulation (EU) 546/2011 that states “Member States shall ensure that use of plant protection products does not have any long-term repercussions for the abundance and diversity of non-target species.” (EU Commission, 2011). This project investigates how multiple PPP and additional stressors can be integrated in ERA on a landscape level considering agricultural intensification and vulnerability of populations. The aim is moving the ERA paradigm from single chemical-crop combination to landscape-based ERA integrating landscape structures and aggregated (several crops) and combined (several pesticides) exposures into the current risk assessment methods. Due to the complexity of environmental landscape-scale assessments, the identification of the key “drivers” for exposure and effects and the benchmarking proposed in the other three projects constitute a prerequisite. This project will build landscape models considering the results from the three previous projects, which will be used for the identification of the key modelling blocks under different landscape conditions. In addition, the EFSA proposals for setting protection goals based on ecosystem services and biodiversity in ERA will be implemented to develop risk characterisation tools that could be used as information source for environmental impact assessments; this will help to overcome the currently too fragmented ERA approaches.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project has direct connections and will benefit from the outcomes of the projects aiming to compare predictions with monitoring data, using the agricultural landscape characteristics for strengthening the feedback loop from environmental monitoring and vigilance and ensure focus on factors that trigger the risk and overall impact on biodiversity in terrestrial agro-biosystems and aquatic ecosystems. In addition to supporting regulatory decisions, including the design and implementation of National Plans under the Sustainable Use Directive (SUD), a complementary long-term goal is to deliver management tools to advise and support practitioners to make informed decision (e.g. considering in selection of a PPP versus another PPP the local and regional levels/ ecotype) in the design and implementation of Integrated Pest Management and optimizing use and effects of ecosystem restorations with multiple purposes (i.e. improving biodiversity, reducing PPP pollution etc. through e.g. Nature Based Solutions).

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project aims to deliver methodologies and tools to promote a transition to a system-based ERA. End-users will be actors responsible for a systems-based risk assessment, such as authorisation, enforcement and agricultural advisors. Comprehensible data on environmental impact and tools will enable these actors

to take informed decisions.

The project will provide direct support to the implementation of measures under the SUD and reduction of pesticide impacts under the EU Green Deal and specifically the Farm to Fork Strategy.

The integration of farm management with agricultural landscape characteristics will provide support to decisions on sustainability at local, regional and national level, supporting the integration of sustainability concepts in food production and the CAP.

These new approach for ERA would support other policies, including WFD and the Habitats Directive. Optimizing the overlap of concepts and terminologies between central compartments in environmental management is essential for a (cost)efficient collaboration between different public management bodies. The outcomes will successfully pinpointing key stressors at regional level that impair biodiversity, ecological quality, and ecosystem services.

Key words:

Environmental risk assessment, systems-based approach, plant protection products, landscape assessment, multiple stressors, holistic risk assessment

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project will develop new conceptual approaches, methodologies and tools for improving the environmental risk assessment of pesticides (007: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA). The project outputs will provide additional value to regulatory risk assessments, facilitating the interpretation of the risk characterisation outcome as environmental impacts, supporting not only the regulatory process for PPPs, but also associated regulatory needs connected to biodiversity protection and sustainable agriculture (0012: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake, 009: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC’s results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA). Direct links with EU projects, and EU Agencies activities have been already identified (004: Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge, 005: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives). A key element for the project is to address the combined effects of pesticides on the environment, offering realistic alternatives to the current substance-by-substance regulatory approach (007: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- PARC WPs interlinking within Activity 6.4.4
- WP2 and 3 to ensure a coordinated dialogue with regulators and policy makers.
- Task 6.2 and 6.3. The landscape approach for ERA will be used as the basis for case studies on aggregated human pesticide exposure from the environment, including the integrative prospective assessments (case study under 6.2) and a retrospective assessment (case study under 6.3) using human biomonitoring data.
- Task 6.3 Project within *Review of risk assessment methodologies*: Specificities and similarities of prospective and retrospective risk assessment for pesticides.
- Activity 6.4.1 Environmental risk assessment of chemical mixtures to ensure alignment and avoid overlaps in system approaches.
- Activity 6.4.2 Project on NAMs in environmental risk assessments
- Task 4.2 Environmental monitoring.
- WP7 Data policy (management, harmonisation, interoperability, exchange). A standardised and comparable methodology would facilitate sharing and downstream use of the ERA-data.

Links outside PARC

Strategic partnerships at the EU-level, such as EFSA initiative Partnership and Roadmap to systems-based environmental risk assessment (PERA) and BiodivERsA.

The proposed work will be interlinked with several national and international projects including the Norwegian Agriculture monitoring program for pesticides and supporting cumulative risk assessments

(<https://www.nibio.no/en/subjects/environment/the-norwegian-agricultural-environmental-monitoring-programme-jova>), the project « Cumulative hazard and risk assessment of complex mixtures and multiple stressors (MixRisk) » (www.niva.no/mixrisk), and several activities of NIVAs Computational Toxicology Program, NCTP (www.niva.no/nctp).

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.21 Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents (M81)

Partners List:

ISCHII (ES), UFZ (DE), UKOLD (DE), UC (PT), NIVA (NO), IEP-NRI (PL), OFB (FR), INERIS (FR), UCLM (ES), ULUND (SE), Uni Osnabrück (DE), UAVR (PT), SLU (SE), UoB (UK), UKCEH (UK), EAWAG (CH)

Regulatory core team: KEMI (SE), UBA (DE), FOEN (CH), ANSES (FR), EFSA (EU)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2025 (M42)

Costs:

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 73 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 45 544 €

WP7 FAIR data – 3 PROJECTS

In the context of the EU's Open Science Policy (https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en), PARC will promote harmonisation of data and exchange between different actors (scientific community, health agencies, regulators, policy-makers etc.) and disciplines (exposure science, toxicology...) to promote transparency, support RA, and allow for reuse. It will ensure data and associated information is FAIR, i.e. Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable, and addresses the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR; Regulation (EU) 2016/679) related challenges for data exchange.

T7.1 PARC FAIR Data Policy (PFDP) and DMP - No project submitted at present

Data “FAIRification” will be a key activity of PARC to facilitate data reuse. Implementing FAIR data practices is among the main operational objectives of PARC and will be measured by the proportion of datasets developed in PARC that will be FAIR, and the number of deliverables reusing existing data. A common Data Management Plan (DMP) will be established and shared.

The PARC FAIR data policy (PFDP) will define the principles and conditions that govern provision, management, access, use and re-use of data, in line with the FAIR principles, while taking into account legal aspects (i.e. GDPR), security, transparency, sustainability and quality of the data. WP7 will provide the framework (guiding principles, data policy, framework DMP), set up specific methods and tools and guidance to FAIRify data and facilitate data reuse in the R&I WPs and in regulatory agencies. Through training, FAIR implementation will be broadly embedded in PARC. PARC will establish collaboration with specialised FAIR initiatives and projects (e.g. EOSC-Life, ENVRIFAIR, WorldFAIR), and collaborate with experts from the Go FAIR Foundation to kick start the FAIRification process in the first two years.

T7.2 Data libraries – 2 PROJECTS

Data will be made FAIR at the source whenever possible, described by FAIR metadata, and associated with a persistent identifier. PARC will use established FAIRification approaches such as the Three Point FAIRification framework (3PFF), elaboration of FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) defining concrete implementation choices for each of the 15 FAIR principles (Schultes et al.¹, 2020; Wilkinson et al.², 2016), and established software solutions to manage FAIR data sources. Specific use cases will enable the multi-faceted FAIRification process to be developed gradually and pragmatically. Compatibility assessment, efforts for harmonisation and maximum interoperability will start from these FIPs. Standardised templates will be created, as necessary, based on domain specific standards, formats and vocabularies whenever available. PARC will perform landscape exercises and FAIRness assessments to identify potential partners to functionally integrate and exchange different types of data from different domains, and different national and transnational levels. It will build further upon DG ENV's Common Data Platform for Chemicals (CDPC), which will be the default option for data that are within scope for the DG ENV domain of interest (read: data relevant to regulatory RA). Because the CDPC is, at the current moment, still under development, a joint exercise will be set up to align PARC activities with the DG ENV roadmap. For data that is out of scope for the CDPC (read: not commonly used in regulatory RA), the content and accessibility of specialised data centres (e.g. ESFRI (European Strategic Forum for Research Infrastructure) research infrastructures (i.e., EIRENE -for human exposome data-, ELIXIR -life sciences collaboration-), MS Open Data initiatives -lab analysis results processing-, domain-specific repositories, institutional repositories, and open generic repositories such as Zenodo) will be explored, integrating efforts and achievements from recently ended projects such as EuroMix (<https://www.euromixproject.eu/> -chemical mixtures-), NORMAN (<https://www.norman-network.net/> -data on emerging environmental substances-) and HBM4EU (<https://www.hbm4eu.eu/> -human biomonitoring data-), ongoing project clusters such as the European Human Exposome Network (EHEN) cluster or the European Cluster to Improve Identification

of Endocrine Disruptors (EURION), and community databases such as the aforementioned NORMAN. Integration with IPCHEM – the EC’s Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring - and the OECD eChemPortal will be implemented also, through semantic mapping of the underpinning data schema. A dedicated FAIR data hub hosting core functionalities (such as querying of data, use of searchable catalogues and metadata services) complementary to existing platforms, will be implemented. Establishment of new FAIR Data Points (FDPs) (Thompson et al.³, 2020) or dedicated repositories will be considered in cases where existing solutions do not satisfy the needs of the PFDP.

A7.2.1 Mapping the PARC Data Landscape

No project submitted at present.

A7.2.2 PARC FAIR data hub – 2 PROJECTS

P7.2.2.a_Y1_chemicals-in-environment_MU_VITO

Project Title	Chemicals in the Environment data reuse		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	ENV DATA (RE)USE		
Project Manager	Richard Hůlek richard.hulek@recetox.muni.cz Katarína Řiháčková katarina.rihakova@recetox.muni.cz	Masaryk University (MU, RECETOX)	CZ
Deputy Project manager	Jana Klánová jana.klanova@recetox.muni.cz	Masaryk University (MU, RECETOX)	CZ
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	7	PARC Task/Activity/S ub-activity:	7.2.2
Project Id	P7.2.2.a_Y1_chemicals-in-environment_MU_VITO		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The project’s main goal is to support the reuse of existing data in relation to environmental exposure and the management of newly generated data in accordance with FAIR principles and in view of the concepts of Open Data and One substance, one assessment.

The monitoring component of PARC (WP4, WP6, WP9), including human biomonitoring, environmental monitoring, and innovative methods, explores the presence of (priority) chemicals in a multicompartiment environment and the resulting exposure of humans. These chemical substances originate from multiple sources and move along different pathways. Aggregated, combined, and cumulative exposures will be assessed through surveys of the co-occurrence of chemical substances, their metabolites, and degradation products in different matrices, including humans. These monitoring initiatives from source to humans foster a “one health” chemical risk assessment strategy.

Members in R&I work packages in PARC (e.g. WP4, WP6, WP8) ask for solutions to access/connect to existing data resources in monitoring programs, databases, and libraries to help them with mapping and accessing the information available in the various data resources. This includes a need to extract and combine information on (priority) chemicals in the environment that will then guide further work on improvements of human and environmental/ecological risk assessment. The structures that facilitate the review and extraction of existing information should reflect the requirements of regulatory processes and strategies to which the work of R&I work packages is linked (e.g. EU WFD, Soil strategy, ECHA PFAS

restriction proposal, REACH).

Over the years various tools and database platforms were created to provide for storage, analysis, and visualization of occurrence data and trends in chemical exposure in the environment at global, EU, and national levels (for example, EMEP³, EBAS⁴, GENASIS⁵, GMP data warehouse⁶, NORMAN⁷, IPChem⁸). Nevertheless, each of the tools or knowledge hubs was developed for different communities and comprises different services and scopes. Available datasets are often organized by environmental matrix, contain different scopes and contents, and are at various stages of development (harmonization principles, ontology, tools).

The project aims for an effective exchange of reliable, relevant, curated, and FAIR data on chemicals (specifically environmental exposure data) between different stakeholders and policy domains (in line with the European Strategy for Data). Via mapping the existing data landscape and developing tailored solutions for data re(use) and the implementation of FAIR principles, the chemical RA community in PARC and beyond will increasingly reuse both scientific and regulatory data for application and innovation in risk assessment, thus empowering the European Green Deal Data Space.

Additionally, the R&I work packages in PARC (e.g. WP4, WP6, WP9) generate new datasets, and there is a need to create solutions and provide tools to manage newly generated data in line with the FAIR principles and to provide structures for newly generated data that would further be used by risk assessors on European and national levels.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project is structured around three main activities: i) mapping the existing data resources relevant to environmental exposure to chemicals and assessing the current landscape (mainly on European and national levels), and assessment of FAIRness level of the priority resources; ii) developing solutions for accessing and re(using) existing/newly developed data resources, iii) cooperate and support other PARC WPs (WP4, WP6, WP8) in producing and managing environmental data in line with FAIR principles and in accordance with the Open Data approach, which should ultimately support the concept of “One substance, once assessment”.

The main project outputs are:

- Inventory of the priority and most relevant resources for assessing environmental exposure to chemicals with the information on the level of their FAIRness
- Online metadata catalogues of existing (priority) data resources on (priority) chemicals for reuse in risk assessment in PARC (and in particular in research and monitoring activities in WPs 4, 6, 8), but also for national users, regulatory agencies, and the research community
- PARC-generated data are in line with the FAIR principles and stored in a FAIR online platform

³ « The co-operative programme for monitoring and evaluation of the long-range transmission of air pollutants in Europe (informally 'European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme' = EMEP) is a scientifically based and policy driven programme under the Convention on Long-range Transboundary Air Pollution (CLRTAP) for international co-operation to solve transboundary air pollution problems. » <https://www.emep.int/>

⁴ « EBAS is a database with atmospheric measurement data. EBAS objective is to handle, store and disseminate atmospheric composition data generated by international and national frameworks like long-term monitoring programmes and research projects. » <https://ebas.nilu.no/>

⁵ « GENASIS (Global ENvironmental ASsessment Information System) provides a comprehensive information on contamination of the environment by chemicals, namely persistent organic pollutants (POPs). » <https://www.genasis.cz/index-en.php>

⁶ « Global Monitoring Plan (GMP) for Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) under the Stockholm Convention Data Warehouse (GMP DWH) is an online tool developed for handling persistent organic pollutants (POPs) monitoring data generated in the frame of the Global Monitoring Plan (GMP) under the Stockholm Convention on POPs. » <http://visualization.pops-gmp.org/2014/>

⁷ NORMAN organises the development and maintenance of various web-based databases for the collection & evaluation of data / information on emerging substances in the environment

⁸ « IPCHEM - the Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring is the European Commission's reference access point for searching, accessing and retrieving chemical occurrence data collected and managed in Europe. » <https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project contributes to REACH - supports human and environmental/ecological risk assessment, and allows for the reuse of data and knowledge - regulatory agencies to have direct access to environmental data, and indirectly that data will be available for reuse in models and toolboxes or for addressing research questions. The project has an important function within PARC as many other projects include a step of reviewing existing data, in order to build on them and avoid duplication. By facilitating this review and providing structures for easy access to existing data, this project will support many other activities in PARC in their address of specific regulatory needs.

Key words: (meta)data, data resources, libraries, FAIR, harmonization, (open) access, open data, environmental exposure

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

OO5 “Promote cooperation with other R&R initiatives”: The project aims to connect to existing databases.

OO7 “Develop/implement annual R&I work programs to respond to identified needs in chemical RA”: The project responds to the needs of PARC projects and WPs regarding the access and reuse of existing data relevant to chemical risk assessment.

OO8 “Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multiscore data for regulatory purposes”: The project will support the provision of environmental and multiscore data for regulatory purposes.

OO10 “Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for risk assessment”: The project aims to assess the FAIRness of existing priority data resources, and provides solutions towards FAIR management of newly generated (environmental) data in PARC.

OO9 “Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC’s results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardization and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA”: The project will support in two ways: i) supporting R&I PARC WPs directly linked to regulatory processes and strategies in reusing existing data and creating solutions for newly generated data in line with FAIR principles; and ii) creating systems and solutions for newly generated data in PARC to be further used by risk assessors.

OO13 “Build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical RA”: Through training on FAIR principles.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness: The project in 7.2 would need to establish synergies with existing projects and monitoring networks such as ERA Planet (H2020), e-shape (H2020 project EuroGEOSS Showcases: Showcasing and promoting users’ uptake of GEOSS), Solutions, IPCHEM, NORMAN, European - EMEP, global - Stockholm Convention and Minamata Convention monitoring plans and also shared infrastructures (i.e., Elixir, CESNET, EOSC, EnvriFAIR-ESFRI) to foster the environmental data management and solutions in line with FAIR principles.

WP7: Data management plan: The DMP of the project is elaborated in close collaboration with the WP7 in line with the WP7 recommendations. Data management issues observed during the project that might be relevant to the whole PARC project will be communicated to the WP7.

WP9: Training, laboratory network: The inventory of existing resources relevant for the assessment of environmental exposure is carried out in close collaboration with WP9. WP9 carried out the inventory of monitoring networks and laboratories. This project will focus on other relevant resources potentially not included in the WP9 scope, and assess the priority and FAIRness of those resources (mapped by both WP9 and WP7). The project will cooperate with tasks 9.1 and 9.2 in the development of the best-fit architecture for WP9 catalogues on laboratory and exposure monitoring networks.

Other WPs:

For this particular project, close collaboration is expected with task 4.2 Environmental monitoring and multisource exposure. The current project in T4.2 (“ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey”) includes an activity on “Review of existing knowledge”, which is also foreseen for future projects in T4.2. It is therefore expected that data from various data resources would need to be brought together, assessed against the FAIR

principles, and combined to allow for use in T4.2. This project will cooperate and support T4.2 project partners in finding and applying the best solutions for accessing all the relevant data, their connection, re(use) and management in accordance with FAIR principles and if needed, making them available and accessible via a FAIR platform/repository.

This project also aims to screen and select specific use cases in other PARC WPs/project (WP4, WP6, WP8) that would respond to the need of those projects for support in generating new environmental data in line with the FAIR principles. Similarly, close cooperation is foreseen in regard to WP6 and WP8, whenever data generated outside or within PARC are to be used in models.

Further links with PARC projects, tasks and WPs will be regularly investigated and fostered via regular communication and (if needed) workshops with the involved PARC partners.

Links outside PARC

This project serves experts/data holders and data users in tasks 4.2, 4.3, 6.2., 6.4., and WP8 but would need to establish synergies with existing projects and infrastructures, such as ERA Planet (H2020), e-shape (H2020 project EuroGEOSS Showcases: Showcasing and promoting users' uptake of GEOSS), Solutions, IPCHEM, NORMAN, European - EMEP, global - Stockholm Convention and Minamata Convention monitoring plans, and shared infrastructures (i.e., Elixir, CESNET, EOSC, EnvriFAIR-ESFRI).

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

The project will partly contribute to the following deliverables of WP7 (task 7.1):

D7.1. Data Management Plan (DMP) (M6)

D7.2. PARC FAIR data policy (PFDP) (M18)

D7.3. 1st report on Data infrastructure, tools and services for FAIRification and reuse of chemical RA data (M36)

D7.5. 1st review of the Data Management Plan (DMP) (M42)

D7.6. 2nd review of the Data Management Plan (DMP) (M72)

MS11. Network of trained FAIR data stewards (M12)

MS12. Architecture of PARC FAIR data hub & its integration with the COPCSD (M24)

Partners List: MU (CZ), VITO (BE), UFZ (DE), BRGM (FR), UNILU (LU), ISSEP (BE), JSI (SI), ANSES (FR), NIVA (NO), UBA (DE), AUTH (GR)

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Cost:

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 98 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 17 612 €

P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO

Project Title	FAIR and sustainable storage of human biomonitoring (HBM) datasets		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	HBMdatasets		
Project Manager	Eva Govarts eva.govarts@vito.be	VITO	Belgium
Deputy Project manager	Dirk Devriendt Dirk.devriendt.ext@vito.be	VITO	Belgium
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	42
PARC Workpackage number	7	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	7.2.2
Project Id	P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

This project deals with availability and (re)use of existing Human Biomonitoring (HBM) datasets (including datasets from HBM4EU, but also datasets produced in other projects), as well as with new datasets generated in PARC (i.e., in Task 4.1). HBM dataset will be made available as FAIR datasets for potential reuse by the broad risk assessment community. HBM datasets are challenging for reuse as they contain personal, sensitive data, which poses specific challenges for storage and reuse, related to ethical and legal issues. The full strength of the data for scientific and regulatory purposes will only be attained if analyses can be carried out on the individual data, if the coherence of the dataset is maintained, and if the data can be linked to different domains (e.g., health, biomolecular, spatial-environmental data, food, consumption, occupational). Finally, HBM datasets contain analyses of chemical metabolites for which no standardized identifications exist.

HBM datasets will be made available to allow reuse by different user groups: scientific users who may want to reuse the entire datasets (for research questions on exposure determinants, geographical comparisons, time trends, exposure-effect analyses, link with environmental sources, ..., comparing modelled exposure with observed exposure, ...), regulatory users who may be interested in the core occurrence data (for assessment and follow-up, integration of HBM data in models and toolboxes), and the general public. As such this project indirectly supports multiple regulatory processes and frameworks through support for improved human risk assessment, and for reuse of data and knowledge.

The broader relevance of the project lies in the development and implementation of scalable solutions for reuse of personal sensitive data while safeguarding legal and ethical constraints, including cross-domain linking of data, semantic and technical interoperability, and development and implementation of cross-domain ontologies, vocabularies and metadata schemes.

The project will be strongly aligned with Task 4.1, and more specifically with Task 4.1.5 as part of a sustainable HBM system.

Methodologically the project will investigate the feasibility to make use new developments in federated data infrastructures and federated data analysis. These methods are still in an early phase.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Short-term operational data infrastructure for exchange of HBM data between PARC partners
- Hybrid federated data infrastructure allowing
 - Reuse of HBM datasets by *new parties* while respecting privacy and consent
 - New data collected in PARC
 - New PARC partners working with the data
 - Integration with *external HBM datasets* from other projects (e.g. EHEN projects)
 - Federated data analysis
- Metadata, schema mappings and search engines to increase *findability and interoperability* across disciplines (health, biomolecular, lifestyle, ...) for cross-domain linking
- Identification scheme for metabolites linking metabolites and parent chemicals

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Facilitated access and reuse of both (individual) HBM datasets and core HBM (occurrence) data by researchers and risks assessors

Regulatory agencies improve human risk assessment

Decision makers evaluate effectiveness of adopted regulatory measures (Chemicals policy)

Researchers make new generation risk assessment tools and models available

Key words: human biomonitoring, FAIR data, personal sensitive data, federated data analysis, metadata schemas, ontologies

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project supports the achievement and is closely aligned with operational objective 0010 (Implement

FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for risk assessment) It aims for an effective exchange of reliable, relevant, curated, and FAIR human biomonitoring data between different stakeholders and policy domains (in line with the European Strategy for Data). FAIR data solutions for sensitive data will support the development of monitoring capacity (OO8: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes). Via mapping the existing data landscape and developing tailored solutions for data re(use) and the implementation of FAIR principles, the chemical RA community in PARC and beyond will increasingly reuse human biomonitoring data for application and innovation in risk assessment (OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC's results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA). Objective OO13 (Build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical RA) will be supported through training on FAIR data principles, practices and data stewardship for participants.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project is obviously strongly related with Task 4.1 and more specifically 4.1.4 and 4.1.5, with Task 6.2 for linking predicted exposure to observed exposure, with Task 8.3 for integrating HBM data in the modelling toolbox, and with Task 2.2 (data layer of PARCopedia).

WP3: a strategy will be developed on communication and awareness on FAIR data, both in general and in specific communities. This project will benefit from organisation of synergy networks and networking events. Collaboration on these aspects will be discussed with WP3.

Internally in WP7 the project will exchange with Task 7.1 on data policies, and on training and awareness on FAIR data, and with Task 7.3 for exploration of novel approaches towards enhanced privacy preservation for personal sensitive data (e.g., federated data analysis).

WP9 will be involved for the inventory of HBM projects and datasets, and for collaboration on training and awareness on FAIR data.

Links outside PARC

The project will start from the achievements of HBM4EU. It will link with other initiatives that are working on similar data, such as the European Human Exposome Network, EOSC-Life, EIRENE RI, and on generic metadata schemas and ontologies, such as HL7, Bioschemas, RDA, OHDSI. It will align with the EC's roadmap and activities towards a Common Open Platform on Chemicals data, and i.e., with IPCHEM's activities on HBM data.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D7.2. PARC FAIR data policy (PFDP) (M18). This project contributed to the FAIR methodology as well as the privacy related aspects of the PFDP.

D7.3. 1st report on Data infrastructure, tools and services for FAIRification and reuse of chemical RA data (M36)

D7.5. 1st review of the Data Management Plan (DMP) (M42)

MS11. Network of trained FAIR data stewards (M12)

MS12. Architecture of PARC FAIR data hub & its integration with the COPCSD (M24)

Partners List:

VITO (BE); MU (CZ); UU (SW); UBA (DE); ISSEP (BE); JSI (Slovenia), WR (NL)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2025 (M42)

Cost:

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 53.5 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 5012 €

A7.2.3 Solutions for FAIR data: development and implementation

No project submitted at present.

A7.2.4 Standards and harmonisation

No project submitted at present.

T7.3 Innovative analyses – 1 PROJECT

Innovative analytical approaches to maximise use and insights from increasing amounts of open and FAIR data for RA will be introduced. Promising approaches will be applied to use cases, selected together with WPs 4-8, to evaluate and showcase their usefulness. A range of advanced approaches will be developed and documented, including pooling and meta-analysis of heterogeneous datasets, uncertainty analysis, and knowledge and text mining via on-the-fly ontological mapping, Bayesian networks, machine learning and other approaches. Analytical tools will be made available as FAIR algorithms and supplied to WPs 4-8 for use and integration into toolboxes. Good practice guidelines describing the approaches and their applications for regulatory risk assessment will be published.

A7.3.1 Innovative methods for combined analyses of FAIR (heterogeneous) data

No project submitted at present.

A7.3.2 Methods for uncertainty characterisation, propagation and quantification as a basis for harmonisation in RA

No project submitted at present.

A7.3.3 Novel computational methods for integrating and extracting knowledge from non-structured data – 1 PROJECT

P7.3.3.a_Y1_ALT-IST_IISPV

Project Title	AI, text mining and ontology-assisted hazard identification and risk assessment (OnTextTox)		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	ALT-IST		
Project Manager	Vikas Kumar Vikas.kumar@iispv.cat	IISPV	ES
Deputy Project manager	Karin Slater k.slater@bham.ac.uk	UoB	UK
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	60
PARC Workpackage number	7	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	7.3.3
Project Id	P7.3.3.a_Y1_ALT-IST_IISPV		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The ALT-IST project is a part of T7.3. It involves the development of an ontology-based text-mining and data integration scheme for the classification and storage of information about chemical hazards and risk assessment. Followed up by the development of tools using the database of risk assessment. Several regulatory agencies such as OECD, EFSA and ECHA have adopted evidence-based methodologies for risk

assessment i.e. AOP (Adverse outcome pathway). The utmost requirement for developing this mechanistic pathway is data. The well-curated, connected, structured and unambiguous database will ease the accessibility of information and also compliments AOP development by filling experimental data gaps. Ontology-based data integration will further help toward the broader application of Advance data science including network biology and machine learning to predict the chemical adverse effect on the human system. The developed tools and methodologies will be validated by real case studies selected in collaboration with other WPs (WP4, WP5, WP6). Project will explore different text mining tools (e.g. INDRA, TRIPS or other tools) during scoping study to understand its usability and set the agenda for future research needs. Aside the application in developing (quantitative) adverse outcome pathways and supporting network biology approaches to identify and describe hazards in relation to disease development (i.e. AOP), other applications of AI, network approaches, text mining and ontology assisted hazard identification are foreseen as well. These, to accommodate the need for the faster detection of potential emerging risks from imported goods/chemicals into the EU, as well as the identification of data gaps within heterogeneous hazard data sources to help the further prioritization of testing.

Main expected outputs of the project

This project will deliver an ontology-based text-mining and data integration scheme for the classification and storage of information about chemical hazards and risk assessment. Linked case studies with WP5 and WP6 will establish NAM for risk assessment using new data discovery and integration of other available data and the data developed in different work packages. This will involve ontology-based data curation and its automated maintenance using NLP (Natural language processing). In addition, developed ontology will assist the further development of QAOP in collaboration with different partners.

Current status and expectation for 3rd year

So far, we have conducted a scoping study to identify relevant tools and methodologies that can benefit information extraction specifically for AOPs. We have also reviewed previous EU projects, such as the EFSA-funded "Exploring the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) for extracting and integrating data obtained through New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) for chemical risk assessment (AI4NAM)," and evaluated available tools to understand the current state of the art and gaps in current methodologies and tools for applying text mining to the development of AOPs.

In our scoping study, we performed a benchmarking analysis to compare multiple tools relevant for Named Entity Recognition (NER) and Relation Extraction (RE) in the biomedical domain. During this process, we developed a tool called BotAnnotator, which integrates and provides a common interface for various NER tools, including dictionary-based, rule-based, classical machine learning-based, and the latest deep learning models such as Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) and transformer-based models.

Alongside BotAnnotator, we created the AOP-BOT tool, which helps extract information from literature based on sentence co-occurrence, rule-based event extraction, and offers functionality for large language model (LLM)-based information extraction. The AOP-Bot Visualizer is a web-based UI plugin that enables the analysis of extracted information in a network format.

From our initial studies and analysis, we identified several gaps in the current methodologies and tools for text mining in AOPs. Some of these gaps include a) limited flexibility in defining information extraction constraints; b) inability to parse information from entire literature databases: c) lack of real-time user interaction due to time constraints

In the third year of the project, we are focusing on developing tools to address these gaps and provide a real-time information extraction tool. This tool will allow researchers to define rules, constraints, and context to extract information effectively.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project is designed according to the perspective of a computational toxicologist, epidemiologists and risk assessor because it introduces a novel *in-silico* approach toward defining associations between human

health outcomes and exposure to chemicals through the integrated use of advanced analytical and predictive tools for hazard and risk assessment and chemical screening for regulatory purposes. It will employ natural language processing, cheminformatics and bioinformatics techniques directly to the data mining of the integrated data set which will lead to the advancement of *in-silico* methodologies for OECD's integrated approaches to testing and assessment (IATA) and support the 3R strategy of chemical testing.

Key words:

Ontology, Text mining, Artificial intelligence, Natural Language Processing, System toxicology

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project will mainly contribute to the PARC operational objectives OO9 (Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC's results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA), OO10 (Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA), and OO12 (Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake) by developing and implementing R&I work programmes for new *in silico* tools and generating results and knowledge (data discovery from text mining) to support the use of new approaches and methods (AI assisted text mining), develop models and innovative concept for RA (predictive AI models) to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC results in regulatory RA processes. The project will also contribute to the PARC operational objectives by providing input to priority-setting (OO3: Define common R&I strategies with transparent criteria and a prioritisation strategy), facilitate PARC wide collaboration with different case studies and promoting cooperation with other R&I initiatives (OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives), communicate and disseminate results (OO6: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen's understanding/awareness of chemical RA) and implement FAIR data practices to enable open science (OO10).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Task 5.3.2: AOP developed in 5.3.2 can be used as case study and data generated in this project can help in developing AOPs

Task 6.1: data generated in this project can help in the development of qAOPs and IATA.

Task 6.2: mixture effects can be quantitatively addressed through targeted data mining and network modelling

WP8: SysTox bioinformatics tools can be integrated in the toolbox

WP9: training of informatics tools for regulators

Links outside PARC

Relevant text mining AI data initiatives (ELIXIR, Bio.Tools). Furthermore, the project is closely linked to other EU project in similar domain like EU-ToxRisk, RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX and PrecisionTox, and to work ongoing at OECD in relation to AOP development (OECD AOP programme) and IATA case studies. As such, regular interactions with the OECD Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics (EAGMST) and the OECD Working Party for Hazard Assessment (WPHA) are foreseen.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

D7.4: 1st Evaluation of innovative analytical approaches and uncertainty approaches for introduction in chemical RA (M36)

Partners List:

IISPV (ES), UoB (UK), ANSES (FR), INSERM (FR), JSI (SI), AUTH (GR), MU (CH), UL-LACDR (NL), KI (SE), NIVA (NO), WR (NL)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2027 (M60)

Cost:

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 30 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 15 137 €

A7.3.4 Identify additional needs in PARC for innovative analyses and promising evolutions in the data science landscape, and translate them in use cases for evaluation

No project submitted at present.

List of Project Reports, Project Key Landmarks and Deliverables, Additional deliverables, Milestones to which the projects contribute

Only Deliverables and Additional Deliverables are official documents to be submitted to HaDEA. Project reports and key landmarks correspond to intermediate or significant stage in the development of the scientific results of the projects that will be part of the annual **Additional Deliverables** or **Deliverables**.

WP4

Project ID	Project end	D_AD_M-R_L ¹ number	Title	Partner Responsible	Expected delivery date	Achievement date
P4.1.1.2.a	81	R1_GenHBMSurvey	First interim progress report (postponed from M18 to M23)	VITO	M23	
P4.1.1.2.a	81	R2_GenHBMSurvey	Second interim progress report	VITO	M42	
P4.1.1.2.a	81	R3_GenHBMSurvey	Third interim progress report	VITO	M66	
P4.1.1.2.a	81	R4_GenHBMSurvey	Final report	VITO	M81	
P4.1.1.2.a	81	D4.3	D4.3 1st Progress report on the general survey	VITO	M36	
P4.1.1.2.a	81	D4.8	D4.8 2nd Progress report on the general survey	VITO	M48	
P4.1.1.2.a	81	D4.12	D4.12 3rd Progress report on the general survey	UBA	M60	
P4.1.1.2.a	81	D4.13	D4.13: Concluding report summarizing the outcome of all studies for a future monitoring approach	INERIS	M81	
P4.1.1.4.a	48 29	AD4.8	AD4.8 Report on the occupational exposure in general population surveys: analysis of existing data and recommendations for future general population studies (postponed from M18 to M29)	TTL	M29	
P4.1.1.4.b	48 36	R_SentinelSystem	Mapping and preparation of proof-of-concept	KULeuven	M36	
P4.1.1.4.b	48 36	D4.13	D4.13: Concluding report summarizing the outcome of all studies for a future monitoring approach	INERIS	M81	
P4.1.1.4.c	48	L1_HealthCareSurvey	Study protocol	SRU	M12	M14
P4.1.1.4.c	48	L1_HealthCareSurvey	Ethical applications	SRU	M20	Partially achieved
P4.1.1.4.c	48	D4.7	D4.7 1st Progress report on occupational surveys.	TTL	M48	
P4.1.1.4.d	48	D4.7	D4.7 1st Progress Report on occupational surveys	TTL	M48	
P4.1.3.1.a	36	R1_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Substance dossier on Cyhalothrin (pyrethroid) and proposal of HBM-GVs for the general population, coordinated at project level	UBA	M24	M16
P4.1.3.1.a	36	R2_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Substance dossier on UV filter Uvinul A plus and HBM-GVs for the general population, coordinated at project level	UBA	M24	M18

P4.1.3.1.a	36	R3_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Substance dossier on aluminium and compounds and HBM-GVs for the general population and workers, coordinated at project level	ANSES	M24	
P4.1.3.1.a	36	AD4.3	AD4.3 Derivation of HBM-GVs (postponed from M12 to M36)	UBA	M36	
P4.1.3.3.a	52	R1_RoadmapLinkingHB Mhealth	Scoping document of a list of health measurements to be included in the HBM/HES surveys including Standardized procedures and materials for collecting health, dietary and occupational data	SpF	M14	M14
P4.1.3.3.a	52	R2_RoadmapLinkingHB Mhealth	Effect biomarker implementation plan for PARC general and occupational surveys	VITO	M12	M13
P4.1.3.3.a	52	R3_RoadmapLinkingHB Mhealth	Progress report on investigation of the links between exposure and adverse health outcomes, from analyses of biobanked samples within Health examination cohorts	SpF	M22	
P4.1.3.3.a	52	R4_RoadmapLinkingHB Mhealth	Roadmap for exploration of the links between HBM data and existing health outcome	SpF & VITO	M52	
P4.1.3.3.a	52	MS10	MS10 Finalisation of study design for the HBM surveys	VITO	M12	M13
P4.1.3.3.a	52	AD4.1	AD4.1 Periodic report on available supporting materials for HBM studies (postponed from M12 to M14)	SPF	M14	M16
P4.1.3.3.a	52	AD4.2	AD4.2 Periodic report on analytical methods and measurements for exposure and effect biomarkers (postponed from M12 to M36)	ISCIII	M36	
P4.1.3.3.a	52	D4.3	D4.3 1st Progress report on the general survey	VITO	M36	
P4.1.3.3.a	52	D4.8	D4.8 2nd Progress report on the general survey	VITO	M48	
P4.1.3.3.a	52	D4.12	D4.12 3rd Progress report on the general survey	UBA	M60	
P4.1.3.3.a	52	D2.22	D2.22 2nd PARC sustainability report	INSERM	M81	
P4.1.4.2.a	36	R1_DataAnalysisHBM4 EU	Statistical analysis plan	VITO	M18	M19
P4.1.4.2.a	36	L1_DataAnalysisHBM4 EU	Access to the HBM4EU data is granted	VITO	M14	M14
P4.1.4.2.a	36	D7.1	D7.1 Data management plan	TNO	M6	M6
P4.1.4.2.a	36	MS7	MS7 Establishment of working groups	ANSES	M12	M11
P4.1.4.2.a	36	AD4.11	AD4.11. Progress report statistical analyses	VITO	M36	
P4.1.5.a	66	R1_SustainHBMSystem	1st Interim progress report	VITO	M24	
P4.1.5.a	66	R2_SustainHBMSystem	2nd interim progress report	VITO	M48	
P4.1.5.a	66	R3_SustainHBMSystem	Final report	VITO	M66	
P4.1.5.a	66	D2.22	D2.22 2nd PARC sustainability report	INSERM	M81	
P4.2.a	36	R1_ENVMonitoringPilot Survey	Final report on on-going projects	INERIS/AU	M36	

P4.2.a	36	AD4.5	AD4.5. Technical specifications of the study (project design, hypothesis and research question as well as analytical procedures including QA/QC and data flows) (postponed from M12 to M14)	INERIS, AU	M14	M17
P4.2.a	36	AD4.4	AD4.4 Procedures for agreement on transparent use of existing data, access to samples and involvement of external laboratories (M12) (postponed from M12 to M24)	INERIS, AU	M24	
P4.2.a	36	D4.4	D4.4. 1st Progress report on on-going monitoring projects (M36)	AU	M36	
P4.2.b ²	30	R1_Monitoringframe	Final project report (PR)	AU/INERIS	M30	
P4.2.b	30	D4.1	D4.1. Description of a mechanism for selection of chemicals / matrices / endpoints for projects (postponed from M20 to M22)	INERIS	M22	
P4.2.b	30	AD4.9	AD4.9. Final report on the prioritization project	AU/INERIS	M34	
P4.2.c ³	72	R1_Human exposure	Workshop report	LNS, CSBT, AU, INERIS	M30	
P4.2.c	72	R2_Human exposure	Description of the study concept	LNS, CSBT, AU, INERIS	M36	
P4.2.c	72	R3_Human exposure	Progress report	LNS, CSBT, AU, INERIS	M50	
P4.2.c	72	R4_Human exposure	Project report	LNS, CSBT, AU, INERIS	M72	
P4.2.c	72	AD4.10	AD4.10. Description of the study concept	AU/INERIS/ LNS/CSTB	M36	
P4.2.c	72	AD4.14	AD4.13. project report	AU/INERIS/ LNS/CSTB	M72	
P4.3.1.a	12	R1_T01-Concept Paper	Common definitions for NTA/EDA approaches	MU	M12	M14
P4.3.1.a	12	AD4.6	AD4.6 Concept paper regarding common definitions and short to medium term support to policy objectives of innovative (self-) sampling, suspect screening and NTA/EDA approaches - M12 (postponed from M12 to M14)	INRAE, VUA	M14	M16
P4.3.1.b	36 60	R1_T02-QAQC	Protocol/guidances for QA/QC in suspect and non-target screening methods	WR	M36	
P4.3.1.b	60	R2_T02-QAQC	Guidance on identification (levels) of substances found by SS/NTS	WR	M36	
P4.3.1.b	60	MS7	MS7 Establishment of working groups	ANSES	M12	M11
P4.3.1.b	60	AD4.5	AD4.5 Technical specifications of the study (project design, hypothesis and research question as well as analytical procedures including QA/QC and data flows) (postponed from M12 to M14)	INERIS, AU	M14	M17
P4.3.1.b	60	AD4.12	AD4.12. General guideline for QA/QC in non-target screening	WR	M60	
P4.3.1.c	60	D4.10	D4.10. 3rd Proof-of-concept assessing the usefulness of innovative (self-) sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches	VUA/SLU	M60	
P4.3.1.d	60	R1_T04-Data Processing Workflow	Report on the Establishment of necessary advanced data processing methodologies and bioinformatic tools for NTS – EHESP	EHESP	M60	
P4.3.1.d	60	D4.9	D.4.9 Workflow for data processing and annotation of HRMS based chemical profiles generated from suspect/NTS approaches (e.g. inspired from	INRAE	M54	

			W4M/Galaxy)			
P4.3.2.a	48	D.4.5	D.4.5: 2nd Proof-of-concept illustrating the usefulness of innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to early warning system and risk assessment for human monitoring	INRAE	M48	
P4.3.2.b ²	60	L1	Refined study design of case studies co-built and completed with all involved partners	tbd	M24	
P4.3.2.b	60	L2	Sample sourcing and sharing completed	tbd	M30	
P4.3.2.b	60	L3	At least 50% of planned analyses completed	tbd	M48	
P4.3.2.b	60	L4	All planned analyses completed and data processing on-track	tbd	M60	
P4.3.2.b	60	L5	Identification of emerging chemicals and contribution to the prioritisation process of chemicals of interest	tbd	M60	
P4.3.2.b	60	D4.10	D.4.10. 3rd Proof-of-concept assessing the usefulness of innovative (self-) sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches	VUA/SLU	M60	
P4.3.2.c ³	72	R1_Complementary developments	Report on the development of complementary approaches/matrices for application in HBM surveys	JSI and UAntwerpen	M49	
P4.3.2.c	72	R2_Complementary developments	Report on the application of the complementary approaches/matrices to real samples from HBM surveys as a contribution to early warning system and risk assessment for human monitoring	JSI and UAntwerpen	M70	
P4.3.2.c	72	AD4.13	AD4.13. Proof-of-concept on the application of the complementary approaches/matrices to real samples from HBM surveys	JSI and UAntwerpen	M70	
P4.3.3.a	36 48	R1_E01-Wastewater based epidemiology	Final report	UFZ	M36	
P4.3.3.a	48	D4.2	D.4.2 1st Proof-of-concept illustrating the usefulness of innovative (self-) sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to early warning system and risk assessment for environmental monitoring (postponed from M35 to M48)	VUA	M48	
P4.3.3.b ²	60	R1_E02-Sentinel animals	Report on the application of innovative methods combined with suspect/NTS/EDA approaches for animal sentinel species	ONIRIS	M60	
P4.3.3.b	60	D4.14	D.4.14. Final report on the application of new exposure assessment approaches (i.e. from sampling to data interpretation) to support regulatory needs (i.e. lessons learnt and conclusions/perspective for sustainable follow-up)	INRAE	M81	
P4.3.4.a ²	48	R1_F02-Food items exposure	Final report on the application of the developed suspect screening/NTS/EDA approaches to real samples originated from food survey designed by other PARC components	ANSES	M48	
P4.3.4.a	48	D4.10	D.4.10. 3rd Proof-of-concept assessing the usefulness of innovative (self-) sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches	VUA/SLU	M60	

WP5

Project ID	Project end	D_AD_M-R_L1 number	Title	Partner Responsible	Expected delivery date	Achievement date
P5.1.1.a	36 48	R1_Toxins_BfR	Submission of two review papers on Enniatins and Alternaria toxins addressing the relevant endpoints of the project	UNIVIE, BfR	M11 (<i>Alternaria</i>), M13 (<i>Enniatins</i>)	M20 (<i>Alternaria</i> , published), M22 (<i>Enniatins</i> , finalised)
P5.1.1.a	48	R2_Toxins_BfR	Reports available with data generated	UNIVIE, BfR	M36	
P5.1.1.a	48	L1_Toxins_BfR	First test item available to start experimental studies	BfR	M13	M13
P5.1.1.a	48	D5.1	D5.1. 1st NAMs Report (postponed from M18 to M22)	BfR	M22	
P5.1.1.a	48	D5.3	D5.3. 1st new AOPs Report	INSERM	M24	
P5.1.1.a	48	D5.4	D5.4. 1st Closing data Gaps Report	ANSES	M36	
P5.1.1.a	48	D5.11	D5.11. 2nd closing data gaps report (has been shifted from M60 to M54)	ANSES	M54	
P5.1.1.b	36 54	R1_BPA_HumTox	Closing data gaps report: Gathering the data obtained within this project with the contribution from each one of the five mentioned endpoints.	BfR	M36	
P5.1.1.b	54	AD5.1	AD5.1 Report on the workshop organised with national and EU agencies (ECHA and EFSA) and stakeholders on the of-concern bisphenol A (BPA) alternatives.	BPI, MU	M9	M10
P5.1.1.b	54	D5.1	D5.1. 1st NAMs Report (postponed from M18 to M22)	BfR	M22	
P5.1.1.b	54	D5.3	D5.3. 1st new AOPs report	INSERM	M24	
P5.1.1.b	54	D5.4	D5.4. 1st closing data gaps report	ANSES	M36	
P5.1.1.b	54	D5.11	D5.11. 2nd closing data gaps report (has been shifted from M60 to M54)	ANSES	M54	
P5.1.1.c ³	60	R1_TG+ EnnB1	Protocols	tbd	tbd	
P5.1.1.c	60	R1_TG+ EnnB1	Study report	tbd	tbd	
P5.1.1.c	60	D5.4	D5.4. 1st closing data gaps report	ANSES	M36	
P5.1.1.c	60	AD5.8	AD5.8. Study report	ANSES	M41	
P5.1.1.c	60	D5.5	D5.5. 2nd NAMs report (postponed from M36 to M48)	BfR	M48	
P5.1.1.c	60	D5.8	D5.8. 3rd New approach methodologies report	BfR	M60	
P5.1.1.c	60	D5.11	D5.11. 2nd closing data gaps report (has been shifted from M60 to M54)	ANSES	M54	

P5.1.2.a	36	R1_NaturalToxins Aqua	Ecotoxicity data for Lymnaea for single toxins	SLU	M24	
P5.1.2.a	36	R2_NaturalToxins Aqua	Ecotoxicity data for Daphnia/marine copepods for single toxins	UGent	M24	
P5.1.2.a	36	R3_NaturalToxins Aqua	Ecotoxicity data for Lymnaea for mixtures of toxins	SLU	M36	
P5.1.2.a	36	R4_NaturalToxins Aqua	Ecotoxicity data for Daphnia/marine copepods for mixtures of toxins	Ugent	M36	
P5.1.2.a	36	R5_NaturalToxins Aqua	Ecotoxicity data for Chlorella vulgaris for single toxins	UAVR	M24	
P5.1.2.a	36	R6_NaturalToxins Aqua	Ecotoxicity data for Chlorella vulgaris for mixture of toxins and toxins with other chemicals	UAVR	M36	
P5.1.2.a	36	D5.4	D5.4. 1st closing data gaps report	ANSES	M36	
P5.1.2.b	42 48	R1_BPAalternatives	Progress report - advancing NAMs for the assessment of chemical mixtures including BPA alternatives (relevant for activities iii, iv and v) (postponed from M12 to M24)	MU	M24	
P5.1.2.b	48	R2_BPAalternatives	Report on the results of toxicity assessment of BPA alternatives single compounds & mixtures (selected based on available existing data) on different organisms (relevant for activities i & ii).	BPI	M28	
P5.1.2.b	48	R3_BPAalternatives	Progress report - advancing NAMs for the assessment of chemical mixtures including BPA alternatives (relevant for activities iii, iv and v).	MU	M42	
P5.1.2.b	48	R4_BPAalternatives	Report on the results of toxicity assessment of BPA alternatives single compounds & mixtures (selected based on available existing data) on different organisms (relevant for activities i & ii).	BPI	M42	
P5.1.2.b	48	L1_BPAalternatives	Selection of the compounds and mixtures to be tested based on available existing data and discussion among partners / stakeholders	BPI	M9	M9
P5.1.2.b	48	L3	Selection of the compounds and mixtures to be tested based on PARC environmental monitoring data	BPI	M30	
P5.1.2.b	48	AD5.1	AD5.1 Report on the workshop organised with national and EU agencies (ECHA and EFSA) and stakeholders on the of-concern bisphenol A (BPA) alternatives.	BPI, MU	M9	M10
P5.1.2.b	48	AD5.3	AD5.3 List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints (postponed from M12 to M18)	DTU, VUB	M18	M18
P5.1.2.b	48	D5.1	D5.1. 1st NAMs Report (postponed from M18 to M22)	BfR	M22	
P5.1.2.b	48	D5.4	D5.4. 1st closing data gaps report	ANSES	M36	
P5.1.2.b	48	D5.5	D5.5. 2nd NAMs Report (postponed from M36 to M48)	BfR	M48	
P5.1.2.b	48	D5.11	D5.11. 2nd closing data gaps report (has been shifted from M60 to M54)	ANSES	M54	
P5.2.1.a	60	R1_NGTXCs	Evaluating NAMs for the assessment of chemicals with potential NGTx activity	INRAE, BfR	M24	
P5.2.1.a	60	R2_NGTXCs	Combining NAMS for the evaluation of various NGTx activities	INRAE, BfR	M42	
P5.2.1.a	60	R3_NGTXCs	Development of an efficient and reliable testing strategy for the identification of NGTx	INRAE, BfR	M54	
P5.2.1.a	60	AD5.2	AD5.2 Guidance on animal studies in PARC	ANSES, BfR	M12	M15
P5.2.1.a	60	AD5.3	AD5.3 List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints (postponed from M12 to M18)	DTU, VUB	M18	M18

P5.2.1.a	60	D5.1	D5.1. 1st NAMs Report (postponed from M18 to M22)	BfR	M22	
P5.2.1.a	60	D5.3	D5.3. 1st new AOPs report	INSERM	M24	
P5.2.1.a	60	D5.5	D5.5. 2nd NAMs Report (postponed from M36 to M48)	BfR	M48	
P5.2.1.a	60	D5.8	D5.8. 3rd New approach methodologies report	BfR	M60	
P5.2.1.b	36 48	R1_MD-EDC	Extended assessment of NR activities testing using transfected cell lines, and application of this testing strategy to major BPA alternatives, metabolites and other compounds	INSERM	M30	
P5.2.1.b	48	R2_MD-EDC	In vitro assays for different cell types established and tools for MTOR signaling characterization established	BfR/UIBK	M34	
P5.2.1.b	48	AD5.3	AD5.3 List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints (postponed from M12 to M18)	DTU, VUB	M18	M18
P5.2.1.b	48	D5.1	D5.1. 1st NAMs Report (postponed from M18 to M22)	BfR	M22	
P5.2.1.b	48	D5.4	D5.4. 1st closing data gaps report	ANSES	M36	
P5.2.1.b	48	D5.5	D5.5. 2nd NAMs Report (postponed from M36 to M48)	BfR	M48	
P5.2.1.c	48	R1_EDThDisruption	Expand on available THSD MIEs by delivering a test battery of MIEs related to thyroid hormone transporters across physiological barriers	VUA	M36	
P5.2.1.c	48	R2_EDThDisruption	Establish plausible links between TH system MIEs and downstream effects using transcriptomics of TH target tissues and of 2D- and 3D-liver (stem) cell-based cultures; validate MIEs of THSDs and provide a framework for interpretation of in vitro and molecular data	DTU/VUB/BfR	M48	
P5.2.1.c	48	R3_EDThDisruption	Establishment and testing of in vitro assays, in silico and zebrafish/amphibian assays to identify MIEs	ISCI	M36	
P5.2.1.c	48	R4_EDThDisruption	Investigate the use of non-mammalian NAMs for extrapolation to human health for THSD: zebrafish embryo assays to be used in a case study for cross-species extrapolation	SDU/UAntwerpen	M36	
P5.2.1.c	48	R5_EDThDisruption	Release of QSAR predictions for 650,000 substances including 80,000 REACH-preregistered / 11,000 registered substances and QMRF documentation in free Danish (Q)SAR Models website	DTU	M48	
P5.2.1.c	48	AD5.2	AD5.2 Guidance on animal studies in PARC	ANSES, BfR	M12	M15
P5.2.1.c	48	AD5.3	AD5.3 List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints (postponed from M12 to M18)	DTU, VUB	M18	M18
P5.2.1.c	48	D5.1	D5.1. 1st NAMs Report (postponed from M18 to M22)	BfR	M22	
P5.2.1.c	48	D5.3	D5.3. 1st new AOPs report	INSERM	M24	
P5.2.1.c	48	D5.5	D5.5. 2nd NAMs Report (postponed from M36 to M48)	BfR	M48	
P5.2.1.d	36 48	R1_Immunotox	Characterization of in vitro systems relevant for respiratory immunotoxicity	INSERM	M36	
P5.2.1.d	48	R2_Immunotox	Immunosuppression and response to vaccination	INSERM	M36	
P5.2.1.d	48	R3_Immunotox	In vitro systems to assay key events in the immune system function or dysfunction.	INSERM	M36	

P5.2.1.d	48	AD5.2	AD5.2 Guidance on animal studies in PARC	ANSES, BfR	M12	M15
P5.2.1.d	48	AD5.3	AD5.3 List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints (postponed from M12 to M18)	DTU, VUB	M18	M18
P5.2.1.d	48	D5.1	D5.1. 1st NAMs Report (postponed from M18 to M22)	BfR	M22	
P5.2.1.d	48	D5.5	D5.5. 2nd NAMs Report (postponed from M36 to M48)	BfR	M48	
P5.2.1.e	36 48	R1_DNT-ANT	Development of NAMs relevant for detection of ANT	IUF, UKON, INSERM, UFZ	M36	
P5.2.1.e	48	R2_DNT-ANT	Fill existing gaps in the DNT IVB	NIPH, IUF, RIVM	M36	
P5.2.1.e	48	R3_DNT-ANT	Complementary zebrafish assays for the DNT and ANT IVB	UFZ, IUF, NIPH	M36	
P5.2.1.e	48	R4_DNT-ANT	Final Report	UFZ, UIF, UU	M36	
P5.2.1.e	48	AD5.2	AD5.2 Guidance on animal studies in PARC	ANSES, BfR	M12	M15
P5.2.1.e	48	AD5.3	AD5.3 List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints (postponed from M12 to M18)	DTU, VUB	M18	M18
P5.2.1.e	48	D5.1	D5.1. 1st NAMs Report (postponed from M18 to M22)	BfR	M22	
P5.2.1.e	48	D5.5	D5.5. 2nd NAMs Report (postponed from M36 to M48)	BfR	M48	
P5.3.1.a	36 48	R1_SystemsToxicology	Report on the inventory of in vitro, in vivo and human omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts and bioinformatics approaches in public domain repositories at PARC partners for all selected adverse outcomes.	UL-LACDR/SCIE NSANO	M12	see AD5.4 (M19)
P5.3.1.a	48	R2_SystemsToxicology	Report on the applicability domain of systems toxicology bioinformatics approaches for regulatory implementation (postponed from M26 to M30 due to the delayed project)	UL-LACDR/SCIE NSANO	M30	
P5.3.1.a	48	R3_SystemsToxicology	Report on translation of systems toxicology data from in vitro NAM to human in vivo.	UL-LACDR/SCIE NSANO	M36	
P5.3.1.a	48	AD5.4	AD5.4 Inventory of omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public domain repositories for all PARC selected adverse outcomes and mapping of the available information sources and datasets related to human pathophysiology focusing on the prioritised endpoints (postponed from M12 to M19)	UL-LACDR	M19	M19
P5.3.1.a	48	AD5.7	AD5.7 Draft strategy for the development of bioinformatics tools that are needed to link omics data and other mechanistic information to human relevant disease mechanisms (postponed from M12 to M20)	UL-LACDR, SCIENSANO	M20	M22
P5.3.1.a	48	D5.3	D5.3. 1st new AOPs report	INSERM	M24	
P5.3.1.a	48	D5.4	D5.4. 1st closing data gaps report	ANSES	M36	
P5.3.1.a	48	D5.7	D5.7. 2nd new AOPs report (will change the title to englobe also systems toxicology)	INSERM	M48	
P5.3.2.a	36 48	R1_AOPDevelopment	Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritization and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC.	INSERM	M12	see AD5.5 (M17)
P5.3.2.a	48	R2_AOPDevelopment	Progress report on AOP development in priority endpoints	INSERM	M36	

P5.3.2.a	48	AD5.5	AD5.5 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (postponed from M12 to M17)	INSERM	M17	M17
P5.3.2.a	48	AD5.4	AD5.4 Inventory of omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public domain repositories for all PARC selected adverse outcomes and mapping of the available information sources and datasets related to human pathophysiology focusing on the prioritised endpoints (postponed from M12 to M19)	UL-LACDR	M19	M19
P5.3.2.a	48	D5.7	D5.7. 2nd new AOPs report (will change the title to englobe also systems toxicology)	INSERM	M48	
P5.3.4.a	36 48	R1_PBK_Kinetics	Report on <i>in vitro</i> and <i>in silico</i> ADME models available and needed for PBK case studies on model and priority compounds (postponed from M12 to M24)	ITEM-Fraunhofer	M24	
P5.3.4.a	48	R2_PBK_Kinetics	Report on conceptual data gaps in IVIVE-PBK models and the thereof started case studies	ITEM-Fraunhofer	M24	
P5.3.4.a	48	R3_PBK_Kinetics	Report on the first uncertainty analyses of case studies	ITEM-Fraunhofer	M36	
P5.3.4.a	48	L1_PBK_Kinetics	Workshop with T5.1 and 5.2 on data requirement and strategy for their implementation for the proposed case studies	ITEM-Fraunhofer	M13	M13
P5.3.4.a	48	D5.2	D5.2 1st new PBK models report (delayed from M24 to M36)	Fraunhofer-ITEM	M36	
P5.3.4.a	48	D5.6	D5.6. 2nd new PBK models report	Fraunhofer-ITEM	M48	

WP6

Project ID	Project end	D_AD_M-R_L1 number	Title	Partner Responsible	Expected delivery date	Achievement date
P6.1.1.a	36	AD5.5	AD5.5 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (postponed from M12 to M17)	INSERM	M17	M17
P6.1.1.a	36	AD6.9	AD6.9. Report on draft IATAs and associated case studies (postponed from M24 to M30)	UL-LACDR	M30	
P6.1.1.a	36	D6.5	D6.5 Reports on IATAs and associated case studies	Sciensano	M42	
P6.1.1.a	36	D6.11	D6.11. Harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs	RIVM	M72	
P6.1.1.a	36	D6.12	D6.12. 2nd Report on IATAs and associated case studies	Sciensano	M81	
P6.1.1.b	36	AD5.5	AD5.5 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (postponed from M12 to M17)	INSERM	M17	M17
P6.1.1.b	36	AD6.9	AD6.9. Report on draft IATAs and associated case studies (postponed from M24 to M30)	UL-LACDR	M30	
P6.1.1.b	36	D6.5	D6.5 Reports on IATAs and associated case studies	Sciensano	M42	
P6.1.1.b	36	D6.11	D6.11. Harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs	RIVM	M72	
P6.1.1.b	36	D6.12	D6.12. 2nd Report on IATAs and associated case studies	Sciensano	M81	
P6.1.1.c	36	AD5.5	AD5.5 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (postponed from M12 to M17)	INSERM	M17	M17
P6.1.1.c	36	AD6.9	AD6.9. Report on draft IATAs and associated case studies (postponed from M24 to M30)	UL-LACDR	M30	
P6.1.1.c	36	D6.5	D6.5 Reports on IATAs and associated case studies	Sciensano	M42	
P6.1.1.c	36	D6.11	D6.11. Harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs	RIVM	M72	
P6.1.1.c	36	D6.12	D6.12. 2nd Report on IATAs and associated case studies	Sciensano	M81	
P6.1.1.d	36	AD5.5	AD5.5 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (postponed from M12 to M17)	INSERM	M17	M17
P6.1.1.d	36	AD6.9	AD6.9. Report on draft IATAs and associated case studies (postponed from M24 to M30)	UL-LACDR	M30	
P6.1.1.d	36	D6.5	D6.5 Reports on IATAs and associated case studies	Sciensano	M42	
P6.1.1.d	36	D6.11	D6.11. Harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs	RIVM	M72	
P6.1.1.d	36	D6.12	D6.12. 2nd Report on IATAs and associated case studies	Sciensano	M81	

P6.2.1.a	36	AD6.3	AD6.3 Roadmap on aggregated exposure strategy through different living environments sources and routes	UNISANTE, ANSES	M12	M14
P6.2.1.a	36	D6.1	D6.1. 1st Report on aggregate exposure for general population and workers, and source to dose models applied to case studies	ANSES	M36	
P6.2.1.b	48	AD6.3	AD6.3 Roadmap on aggregated exposure strategy through different living environments sources and routes	UNISANTE, ANSES	M12	M14
P6.2.1.b	48	D6.1	D6.1. 1st Report on aggregate exposure for general population and workers, and source to dose models applied to case studies	ANSES	M36	
P6.2.1.b	48	AD6.21	AD6.21. Report describing the results of the aggregate strategy and its application	ANSES	M48	
P6.2.2.a	48	R1_PBPk_INERIS	Refinement of existing/development of PBPk models towards multi-route and lifelong exposure	tbd	M36	
P6.2.2.a	48	R2_PBPk_INERIS	Case studies of the application of refined/developed PBPk models in the risk assessment process	tbd	M48	
P6.2.2.a	48	AD6.4	AD6.4 Inventory of PBPk models for assessing the internal exposure through life	INERIS, AUTH	M12	M14
P6.2.2.a	48	AD6.22	AD6.22. Case studies of the application of refined/developed PBPk models in the risk assessment process	INERIS	M48	
P6.2.2.a	48	D6.2	D6.2. 1st report on innovative methods based on PBPk models	AUTH	M36	
P6.2.3.a	48	AD6.5	AD6.5 Development of the strategy for mixture risk assessment using HBM data and its application to prioritized mixtures	RIVM, ANSES	M12	M14
P6.2.3.a	48	D6.3	D6.3. 1st Report on innovative approaches for real-life mixture RA	RIVM	M36	
P6.2.4.a	66	R1_HIADDataAvailability	Data, methods and indicators linked to environmental burden of disease case studies for chemicals prioritized in PARC	VITO, UU-IRAS	M24	
P6.2.4.a	66	AD6.6	AD6.6 Inventory of existing HIA, exposure and exposure-effect data for chemicals prioritised in PARC	VITO, UU-IRAS	M12	M14
P6.2.4.a	66	D6.4	D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications	VITO	M36	
P6.2.4.b	66	R1_HIAMethod	Data, methods and indicators linked to environmental burden of disease case studies for chemicals prioritized in PARC	VITO, UU-IRAS	M24	
P6.2.4.b	66	AD6.6	AD6.6 Inventory of existing HIA, exposure and exposure-effect data for chemicals prioritised in PARC	VITO, UU-IRAS	M12	M14
P6.2.4.b	66	D6.4	D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications	VITO	M36	
P6.2.4.c	42	R1_HIACaseStudies	Framework for case study selection (criteria, weighing, documentation, ranking)	VITO, UU-IRAS	M12	see AD6.6 (M14)
P6.2.4.c	42	R2_HIACaseStudies	Reporting on design and results of case studies for health impact assessment	VITO, UU-IRAS	M24-36-48-60-72-81	
P6.2.4.c	42	AD6.6	AD6.6 Inventory of existing HIA, exposure and exposure-effect data for chemicals prioritised in PARC	VITO, UU-IRAS	M12	M14
P6.2.4.c	42	D6.4	D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications	VITO	M36	
P6.2.4.d	42	R1_HIIndicators	Inventory of existing indicator types of relevance for PARC	VITO, UU-IRAS	M12	see AD6.6 (M14)

P6.2.4.d	42	D6.4	D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications	VITO	M36	
P6.3.1.a	48	R1_SubstanceRA_SU - CS12_MethodOSOA (M1-M36M42)	CS12 interim report	SU	M36	
P6.3.1.a	48	R2_SubstanceRA_SU - CS12_MethodOSOA (M1-M36M42)	CS12 final report	SU	M42	
P6.3.1.a	48	R1_SubstanceRA_SU - CS13_Plasticizers RA (M1-M24M36)	CS13 final report	UCL	M36	
P6.3.1.a	48	R1_SubstanceRA_SU - CS14_Biocides RA (M1-M24)	CS14 final report	SU	M24	
P6.3.1.a	48	D6.6	D6.6. 1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies	KEMI	M42	
P6.3.1.a	48	MS13	MS13 Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget	ANSES	M42	
P6.3.1.a	48	D6.17	D6.17 2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies	KEMI	M81	
P6.3.1.b	48	R1_EffectRA_BPI - CS9_SKINSENSIRISK (M6-M36+18)	CS9 first phase progress report	REGIONH	M36	
P6.3.1.b	48	R1_EffectRA_BPI - CS10_ED-cosmetics (M8-M32)	CS10 final report	VUB	M32	
P6.3.1.b	48	R1_EffectRA_BPI - CS11_GenotoxCarc (M1-M48)	CS11 interim report	ISS	M36	
P6.3.1.b	48	R2_EffectRA_BPI - CS11_GenotoxCarc (M1-M48)	CS11 final report	ISS	M48	
P6.3.1.b	48	R1_EffectRA_BPI - CS15_DNT (M1-M36)	CS15 final report	SU	M36	
P6.3.1.b	48	R1_EffectRA_BPI - CS17_ED-in vitro (M1-M36M48)	CS17 interim report	BPI	M36	
P6.3.1.b	48	R2_EffectRA_BPI - CS17_ED-in vitro (M1-M36M48)	CS17 final report	BPI	M48	
P6.3.1.b	48	R1_EffectRA_BPI - CS18_ED-classes (M1-M36M48)	CS18 interim report	BPI	M36	
P6.3.1.b	48	R2_EffectRA_BPI - CS18_ED-classes (M1-M36M48)	CS18 final report	BPI	M48	
P6.3.1.b	48	D6.6	D6.6. 1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies	KEMI	M42	
P6.3.1.b	48	MS13	MS13 Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget	ANSES	M42	
P6.3.1.b	48	D6.17	D6.17 2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies	KEMI	M81	
P6.3.2.a	48	R1_ToolsRA_SU - CS1_CARB (M1-M36)	CS1 final report	SYKE	M36	
P6.3.2.a	48	R1_ToolsRA_SU - CS2_RiskReduction (M1-M24M36)	CS2 final report	SU	M36	
P6.3.2.a	48	R1_ToolsRA_SU - CS3_WorkplaceRA (M1-M36)	CS3 final report	TTL	M36	

P6.3.2.a	48	R1_ToolsRA_SU - CS4_SecPoisoning (M2-M38)	CS4 final report	INERIS	M38	
P6.3.2.a	48	R1_ToolsRA_SU - CS7_REGPREP (M1-M36+48)	CS7 first phase progress report	Eawag	M36	
P6.3.2.a	48	R1_ToolsRA_SU - CS8_OccupReproDev_KI (M1-M36)	CS8 final report	KI	M36	
P6.3.2.a	48	R1_ToolsRA_SU - CS16_UncertaintyRA (M1-M36M42)	CS16 interim report	ULUND	M36	
P6.3.2.a	48	R2_ToolsRA_SU - CS16_UncertaintyRA (M1-M36M42)	CS16 final report	ULUND	M42	
P6.3.2.a	48	R1_ToolsRA_SU - CS19_DataGapFilling (M13-M24M30)	CS19 final report	KEMI	M30	
P6.3.2.a	48	R1_ToolsRA_CS20_Y3_PESTNAM (M25-M48)	CS20 interim report	ISS	M36	
P6.3.2.a	48	R2_ToolsRA_CS20_Y3_PESTNAM (M25-M48)	CS20 final report	ISS	M48	
P6.3.2.a	48	D6.6	D6.6. 1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies	KEMI	M42	
P6.3.2.a	48	MS13	MS13 Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget	ANSES	M42	
P6.3.2.a	48	D6.17	D6.17 2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies	KEMI	M81	
P6.4.1.a	36 40	R1_OPREMIXCS1	Evaluation of the stakeholder feedback collected from a survey and expert interviews on the usefulness of current mixture assessment tools (postponed from M18 to M22)	UGoT, BUL	M22	
P6.4.1.a	40	R2_OPREMIXCS1	Comparative assessment of mixture tools with respect to application domain, feasibility, data demands, protectiveness, reliability, bias.	UGoT, BUL	M24	
P6.4.1.a	40	R3_OPREMIXCS1	Draft for a European mixture framework, accompanied by a validated toolbox of instruments for mixture risk assessment and management	UGoT, BUL	M36	
P6.4.1.a	40	AD6.17	AD6.17 Optimizing regulatory risk assessment and management of chemical mixtures in Europe (postponed from M36 to M40)	UGoT, BUL	M40	
P6.4.1.a	40	D6.18	D6.18 Final report on risk assessment and management methods for chemical mixtures across legislations	Ugot	M81	
P6.4.1.b	36 40	R1_MONAMMIXCS2	Literature review on use of NAM and monitoring data for describing mixture exposure relevant for regulation (postponed from M18 to M22)	UFZ, UBA	M22	
P6.4.1.b	40	R2_MONAMMIXCS2	Guidance document for use of NAM data for specific regulatory options	UFZ, UBA	M36	
P6.4.1.b	40	AD6.18	AD6.18 Dealing with mixtures in regulatory risk assessment through the use of monitoring data and NAMs (postponed from M36 to M40)	UFZ	M40	
P6.4.1.b	40	D6.18	D6.18 Final report on risk assessment and management methods for chemical mixtures across legislations	Ugot	M81	
P6.4.1.c ³	72	R1_Skinsenmix	An overview (scientific paper/report) of current knowledge and practices concerning mixtures	tbd	M36	
P6.4.1.c	72	R2_Skinsenmix	In-vitro (NAM) testing of skin sensitizers in mixture, preliminary results	tbd	M48	
P6.4.1.c	72	R3_Skinsenmix	In-vitro testing of mixtures of skin sensitizers and irritants. Preliminary results	tbd	M60	

P6.4.1.c	72	R3_Skinsenmix	Mixtures, results	tbd	M72	
P6.4.2.a	36	R1_LandscapingSurv	Interim technical report: Landscaping exercise assessing the status of integration and use of NAMs across sectorial frameworks	UNIBAS	M12	M13
P6.4.2.a	36	R2_LandscapingSurv	Technical report: Status of integration and use of NAMs in the EU chemical regulatory risk assessment landscape – a mapping exercise and gaps & needs analysis	UNIBAS	M24	
P6.4.2.a	36	R3_LandscapingSurv	Workshop report: Prioritization of regulatory-relevant scenario-based case studies	UNIBAS	M26	
P6.4.2.a	36	R4_LandscapingSurv	Technical report summarizing the key learnings from the case studies	UNIBAS	M36	
P6.4.2.a	36	AD6.16	AD6.16: Status of integration and use of NAMs in the EU chemical regulatory risk assessment landscape – a mapping exercise and gaps & needs analysis (postponed from M24 to M36)	UNIBAS	M36	
P6.4.2.a	36	D6.19	D6.19 Report on regulatory acceptance and use of new methods (NAMs)	UNIBAS	M81	
P6.4.2.b	36	R1_NGRApractice	Protocol for designing INVITES-IN, a tool for assessing the internal validity of in vitro studies	NIPH, represented by VKM	M11	M17
P6.4.2.b	36	R2_NGRApractice	Protocol for the user testing and validation of INVITES-IN, a tool for assessing the internal validity of in vitro studies	NIPH, represented by VKM	M17	M17
P6.4.2.b	36	R3_NGRApractice	Creation of INVITES-IN, a focus group study	NIPH, represented by VKM	M16	M17
P6.4.2.b	36	R4_NGRApractice	Protocol for harmonizing and cross-walking SR and CRA terms	NIPH, represented by VKM	M18	M20
P6.4.2.b	36	R5_NGRApractice	Creation of INVITES-IN, a Delphi survey (postponed from M20 to M22)	NIPH, represented by VKM	M22	
P6.4.2.b	36	R6_NGRApractice	Core SR and CRA terms; definitions and cross-walking two disciplines	NIPH, represented by VKM	M26	
P6.4.2.b	36	R7_NGRApractice	Protocol; creating an overview of external validity items	NIPH, represented by VKM	M23	
P6.4.2.b	36	R8_NGRApractice	Creation of INVITES-IN, user testing and validation	NIPH, represented by VKM	M23	
P6.4.2.b	36	R9_NGRApractice	INVITES-IN, a tool for evaluation of internal validity of in vitro studies	NIPH, represented by VKM	M24	
P6.4.2.b	36	R10_NGRApractice	Protocol for designing INVITES-EX, a tool for assessing the external validity of in vitro studies	NIPH, represented by VKM	M29	
P6.4.2.b	36	R11_NGRApractice	External validity items, a comprehensive overview	NIPH, represented by VKM	M35	
P6.4.2.b	36	R12_NGRApractice	Protocol for the user testing and validation of INVITES-EX, a tool for assessing the external validity of in vitro studies	NIPH, represented by VKM	M36	
P6.4.2.b	36	R13_NGRApractice	Creation of INVITES-EX, a focus group study	NIPH, represented by VKM	M39	
P6.4.2.b	36	R14_NGRApractice	Creation of INVITES-EX, a Delphi survey	NIPH, represented by VKM	M42	
P6.4.2.b	36	R15_NGRApractice	Creation of INVITES-EX, user testing and validation	NIPH, represented by VKM	M46	

P6.4.2.b	36	R16_NGRApractice	INVITES-EX, a tool for evaluation of internal validity of in vitro studies	NIPH, represented by VKM	M48	
P6.4.2.b	36	R17_NGRApractice	Checklist for reporting of in vitro studies	NIPH, represented by VKM	M49	
P6.4.2.b	36	L1_NGRApractice	Ethical approval of creation of INVITES-IN	NIPH_represented by VKM	M10	M10
P6.4.2.b	36	D6.19	D6.19 Report on regulatory acceptance and use of new methods (NAMs)	UNIBAS	M81	
P6.4.2.c	36	R1_NAMAM	Overview of exploratory analysis and identification of research priorities and requirements (postponed from M12 to M24)	UT	M24	
P6.4.2.c	36	R2_NAMAM	Framework to facilitate an adequate reporting for the AI/ML NAMs to be used for regulatory purposes	UT	M24	
P6.4.2.c	36	R3_NAMAM	Final report on the main outcomes of the project	UT	M34	
P6.4.2.c	36	D6.19	D6.19 Report on regulatory acceptance and use of new methods (NAMs)	UNIBAS	M81	
P6.4.3.a	36	R1_SuProM	Report on LCA incorporation of chemical hazards (postponed from M24 to M28)	MU	M28	
P6.4.3.a	36	AD6.14	AD6.14: Report on current screening and enforcement structures (postponed from M24 to M36)	TUKES	M28	
P6.4.3.a	36	AD6.15	AD6.15. Report on existing database structures with recommended structures	MU	M36	
P6.4.3.a	36	D6.20	D6.20. Framework & case studies for articles & recycled materials for systematic identification of priority substances, materials, & articles from market data	MU	M81	
P6.4.3.b ³	72	R1_ENFORCE	A proof-of-concept methodology for testing compliance with the proposed -PFAS restriction in selected groups of consumer articles M4	Rise	M54	
P6.4.3.b	72	R1_ENFORCE	A proof-of-concept methodology for rapid quantification of regulated substances in selected types of plastics M60(VU	VUA/MU	M67	
P6.4.3.b	72	D6.20	D6.20. Framework & case studies for articles & recycled materials for systematic identification of priority substances, materials, & articles from market data	MU	M81	
P6.4.4.a	42	R1_CRNCS1	Clarifying regulatory needs (Drivers of change, Problem description, Future state of ERA, Gap analysis, Short term-remedies and potential long-term solutions, Prioritised Areas of work and research questions)	KEMI	M22	
P6.4.4.a	42	R2_CRNCS1	Clarifying regulatory needs	KEMI	M34	
P6.4.4.a	42	R3_CRNCS1	Clarifying regulatory needs and preliminary recommendations for new ERA guidance documents	KEMI	M46	
P6.4.4.a	42	R4_CRNCS1	Clarifying regulatory needs	KEMI	M58	
P6.4.4.a	42	R5_CRNCS1	Clarifying regulatory needs	KEMI	M70	
P6.4.4.a	42	R6_CRNCS1	Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents	KEMI	M81	
P6.4.4.a	42	AD6.7	AD6.7. Technical report outlining the regulatory needs for ERA development areas (postponed from M24 to M36)	UBA/KEMI/FOEN	M36	
P6.4.4.a	42	D6.21	D6.21. Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents	UBA	M81	

P6.4.4.b	24 36	R1_PPPEXPCS2	Technical report describing comparison of different existing methods for predicting PPP concentrations in surface waters within agricultural catchments validated against monitoring data from various European geographical regions.	SLU	M24	
P6.4.4.b	36	R2_PPPEXPCS2	Technical report describing the most relevant factors for predicting PPP concentrations in surface waters within agricultural catchments.	SLU	M36	
P6.4.4.b	36	AD6.20	AD6.20. Technical report on factors and processes needed to be included in robust aquatic exposure predictions for regulatory use, including an assessment of geographic representativeness	UFZ	M36	
P6.4.4.b	36	D6.21	D6.21. Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents	UBA	M81	
P6.4.4.c	36	R1_PPPEFFCS3	Technical report on the most relevant factors describing the transfer function that enables a link between laboratory lower-tier tests and effects at ecosystem level. Ranking the relevance of the factors describing the lab to field transfer function. Identification to which extent interactions between PPPs and additional environmental factors increase the sensitivity of field populations.	UFZ	M24	
P6.4.4.c	36	R2_PPPEFFCS3	Technical report informing on factors and processes needed to be included in the ERA to obtain an improved balance between reduced complexity and increased ecological realism.	UFZ	M36	
P6.4.4.c	36	R3_PPPEFFCS3	Software package software to make the framework for an improved ERA accessible to the regulators. The usability and integration of software tools needs to be developed within a structured feedback process involving the regulators within an extended timeframe.	UFZ	M48	
P6.4.4.c	36	AD6.19	AD6.19. Technical report informing on factors and processes needed to be included in the ERA to obtain an improved balance between reduced complexity and increased ecological realism	UFZ	M36	
P6.4.4.c	36	D6.21	D6.21. Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents	UBA	M81	
P6.4.4.d	42	R1_PPPBENCHCS4	Compiled data for internal risk benchmarking (postponed from M20 to M27)	UKOLD	M27	
P6.4.4.d	42	R2_PPPBENCHCS4	Analyses for internal risk benchmarking accomplished	tbd	M35	
P6.4.4.d	42	R3_PPPBENCHCS4	Database of ERA results and complementary data	tbd	M35	
P6.4.4.d	42	R4_PPPBENCHCS4	Data compiled for external risk benchmarking	tbd	M38	
P6.4.4.d	42	R5_PPPBENCHCS4	Analyses for external risk benchmarking accomplished	tbd	M44	
P6.4.4.d	42	R6_PPPBENCHCS4	Technical report on results of benchmarking analyses with suggestions for methodology and most important factors having an impact on the result of the ERA	tbd	M53	
P6.4.4.d	42	R7_PPPBENCHCS4	Report on the implementation of the comparability methodology into the risk assessment paradigm	tbd	M81	
P6.4.4.d	42	D6.21	D6.21. Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents	UBA	M81	
P6.4.4.e	42	R1_PPPOSCS5	Conceptual models for aggregate and combined exposure to pesticides at landscape level covering the local and regional needs as well as national and EU needs. The tools will support the selection of the best IPM approach allowing an ERA-based scientifically sound assessment of sustainability regarding pesticide use as well as a comparative impact with other stressors (postponed from M12 to Q1 2024)	ISCIII	Q1 2024	
P6.4.4.e	42	R2_PPPOSCS5	Case studies report	ISCIII for the compilation, case study	M30	

				leaders for each case study report		
P6.4.4.e	42	R3_PPPOSCS5	Final conceptual approach, including problem formulation and implementation options	ISCIII	M36	
P6.4.4.e	42	D6.21	D6.21. Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents	UBA	M81	

WP7

Project ID	Project end	D_AD_M-R_L ¹ number	Title	Partner Responsible	Expected delivery date	Achievement date
P7.2.2.a	36	D7.1	D7.1 Data management plan	TNO	M6	M6
P7.2.2.a	36	MS11	MS11 Network of trained FAIR data stewards	TNO	M12	M13
P7.2.2.a	36	D7.2	D7.2 PARC FAIR Data Policy (PFDP)	TNO	M18	M18
P7.2.2.a	36	MS12	MS12. Architecture of PARC FAIR data hub & its integration with the COPCSD	VITO	M24	
P7.2.2.a	36	D7.3	D7.3. 1st report on Data infrastructure, tools and services for FAIRification and reuse of chemical RA data	VITO	M36	
P7.2.2.a	36	D7.5	D7.5. 1st review of the Data Management Plan (DMP)	TNO	M42	
P7.2.2.a	36	D7.6	D7.6. 2nd review of the Data Management Plan (DMP)	TNO	M72	
P7.2.2.a	36	R-ENVIROdata.1	The level of FAIRness of the existing major data resources on chemicals in the environment	MU	M30	
P7.2.2.a	36	R-ENVIROdata.2	FAIR solutions to manage newly generated environmental data (lessons learned from the project use cases)	MU	M36	
P7.2.2.b	42	MS11	MS11 Network of trained FAIR data stewards	TNO	M12	M13
P7.2.2.b	42	D7.2	D7.2 PARC FAIR Data Policy (PFDP)	TNO	M18	M18
P7.2.2.b	42	MS12	MS12 Architecture of PARC FAIR data hub & its integration with the COPCSD	VITO	M24	
P7.2.2.b	42	D7.3	D7.3 1st report on Data infrastructure, tools and services for FAIRification and reuse of chemical RA data	VITO	M36	
P7.2.2.b	42	D7.5	D7.5 1st review of the Data Management Plan (DMP)	TNO	M42	
P7.3.3.a	60	R1_ALT-IST	Scoping study of AI, text mining and ontology-assisted hazard identification and risk assessment (postponed from M18 to M36)	IISPV	M36	
P7.3.3.a	60	R2_ALT-IST	Report on the available tool and framework, and different methodologies (like NLP and text mining) used for human health risk assessment, including ontology development.	IISPV	M48	
P7.3.3.a	60	D7.4	D7.4 1st Evaluation of innovative analytical approaches and uncertainty approaches for introduction in chemical RA	UU-IRAS	M36	

¹D = Deliverable/AD = Additional deliverable/M = Milestone/R = Project Report/L = Project Key Landmark (in grey, D/AD/M/R/L achieved)

²Projects starting Y2

³Projects starting Y3